

Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (05)

**A.E. Bras
V.H.J. van der Velden**

Laboratory Medical Immunology (LMI), Department of Immunology, Erasmus Medical Center, Erasmus University, Rotterdam, the Netherlands
Correspondence: a.e.bras@gmail.com / a.bras@erasmusmc.nl / v.h.j.vandervelden@erasmusmc.nl

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Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Inder Taneja published two papers on Zenodo (combining results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
18-01-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ²⁸
03-02-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20000 to 30000 ²⁹

Authors published five papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵
28-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (03) ²⁵
06-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (04) ³⁰

Note

Previously, authors used ‘CSR’ to refer to crazy sequential representations that evaluate to natural numbers (as originally introduced by Inder Taneja) and ‘NCSR’ to refer to crazy sequential representations that evaluate to negative integers (as introduced by ourselves). Authors always avoided ‘PCSR’ as this might introduce ambiguity (pseudo vs. positive CSR).

From this point forward, authors will use the following:

- CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any integer value
- +CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any positive integer
- CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any negative integer

Historic Overview Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases ¹⁶

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 11 through 16):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (completing the base 11 up to 16 series):

Date	Title
09-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX) ²³

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (extending the base 16 series):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFF) ²⁴

Authors published two papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 17 through 62):

Date	Title
23-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to #####) ²⁶
02-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 62 (0000 up to #####) ²⁷

Examples - Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 10 crazy sequential representations (increasing and decreasing):

2671₁₀	48₁₀
$1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*89_{10}$	$9_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$

Examples - Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 11 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

5491₁₀	4142₁₁	378₁₀	314₁₁
$-1_{11}/2_{11}*(3_{11}-4_{11}+5_{11})^6+7_{11}*89_A$		$A9_{11}^{(8_{11}-7_{11})}*6_{11}/(-5_{11}+4_{11}+3_{11})+21_{11}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1077_{10}$		$119_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 12 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

6853₁₀	3B71₁₂	419₁₀	2AB₁₂
$-1_{12}/2_{12}*(3_{12}-4_{12}+5_{12})^6+7_{12}*89A_{12}+B_{12}$		$B_{12}+A9_{12}^{(8_{12}-7_{12})}*6_{12}/(-5_{12}+4_{12}+3_{12})+21_{12}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1270_{10}+11_{10}$		$11_{10}+129_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 13 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

8460₁₀	3B0A₁₃	605₁₀	377₁₃
$-1_{13}/2_{13}*(3_{13}-4_{13}+5_{13})^6+7_{13}*89A_{13}+BC_{13}$		$CB_{13}+A9_{13}^{(8_{13}-7_{13})}*6_{13}/(-5_{13}+4_{13}+3_{13})+21_{13}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1479_{10}+155_{10}$		$167_{10}+139_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 14 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

12217₁₀	4649₁₄	302₁₀	178₁₄
$-1_{14}/2_{14}*(3_{14}-4_{14}+5_{14})^6+7_{14}*89A_{14}+BCD_{14}$		$D_{14}-CB_{14}+A9_{14}^{(8_{14}-7_{14})}*6_{14}/(-5_{14}+4_{14}+3_{14})+21_{14}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1704_{10}+2337_{10}$		$13_{10}-179_{10}+149_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 15 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

14221₁₀	4331₁₅	530₁₀	255₁₅
$-1_{15}/2_{15}*(3_{15}-4_{15}+5_{15})^6+7_{15}*89A_{15}+BCD_{15}-E_{15}$		$ED_{15}-CB_{15}+A9_{15}^{(8_{15}-7_{15})}*6_{15}/(-5_{15}+4_{15}+3_{15})+21_{15}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1945_{10}+2668_{10}-14_{10}$		$223_{10}-191_{10}+159_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 16 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

16148₁₀	3F14₁₆	4402₁₀	1132₁₆
$-1_{16}/2_{16}*(3_{16}-4_{16}+5_{16})^6+7_{16}*89A_{16}+BCD_{16}-EF_{16}$		$FED_{16}-CB_{16}+A9_{16}^{(8_{16}-7_{16})}*6_{16}/(-5_{16}+4_{16}+3_{16})+21_{16}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*2202_{10}+3021_{10}-239_{10}$		$4077_{10}-203_{10}+169_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Definition - Base 10 Crazy Sequential Representation

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
 Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
 Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 + - * / ^ ()

Digits 1 up to 9 occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$(1+2-3)*(45^*(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^*(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45/-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7/-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45^-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(-(1+2)+3)*(45^(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^(6^5)+4)*(-(3-2)+1)$
$-(1-2+234*(6-(7+8-9)))$	$-((9-(8+7-6))*543-2+1)$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Aim

Attempt to ‘fill the gaps’ in our previous work ^{6,7,8,12,13,14,15,25,30} by identifying...

- increasing genuine CSR for integers without any increasing genuine CSR.
- decreasing genuine CSR for integers without any decreasing genuine CSR.

Results

Authors identified 16488 previously unknown genuine CSR, see supplements.

	Increasing +CSR	Decreasing +CSR	Increasing -CSR	Decreasing -CSR
Genuine	2390	5425	2306	6367

Overview

Currently, within the -2147483647 up to 2147483647 range, increasing CSR are available for 1752072 integers, and decreasing CSR are available for 2441622 integers:

	Increasing +CSR	Decreasing +CSR	Increasing -CSR	Decreasing -CSR
Genuine	873978	1220568	870593	1197268
Pseudo	2103	420	5398	23366
Total	876081	1220988	875991	1220634

Note

Authors consider CSR to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial.

Authors do not guaranty:

- Published CSR are the shortest in existence.
- Published CSR are in their simplest form.
- Unavailable CSR do not exists.

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A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 06 Feb 2019

Supplement 1

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
11948	$12^* - 3^*(4 - 5^*67 - 8/9)$	60784	$(1 - (-2 - 3)^*((-4 - 5^{\wedge}6)^* - 7 + 8))/9$
22026	$((-1/2 + 3) + 4)^*5^*678 - 9$	60973	$1^*23^*(-4 - 5^*(-67 + 8)^*9)$
23819	$(1/2 - 3^{\wedge}4)^*(5 - 6^*7)^*8 - 9$	61060	$((-1 + (2^*3)^{\wedge}4) - 5)^*6^*(7 + 8/9)$
24371	$-1 - 2^* - 3/4^*(5^{\wedge}6 + 7^*89)$	61504	$((1 + 2)^*3^{\wedge}4 + 5)^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$
24763	$(1/ - 2 + 3^*(4^{\wedge}5 + 6) + 7)^*8 - 9$	61613	$-1 + (2^*3 - 456^*(- 7 - 8))^*9$
24869	$(1/2 + 3)^*(-4^{\wedge}5 + 6)^* - 7 - 8^*9$	61895	$((-1 - ((2^*3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^* - 6) - 7)^*8 - 9$
24942	$((1/2 + 3)^*(4^{\wedge}5 - 6)^*7 - 8) + 9$	61903	$((1 + 2 + 3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^*6 - 7)^*8 - 9$
25158	$12^* - 3^*(4 - 5/6 - 78^*9)$	61911	$(1 + ((2^*3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^*6 - 7)^*8 - 9$
25589	$(-1/2 + 3^*(4^{\wedge}5 + 6^*7))^*8 + 9$	61922	$1 - (((2^*3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^* - 6 + 7)^*8 + 9$
26269	$(1 + 2^{\wedge}(3 + 4 + 5))^*(6 + 7/(8 + 9))$	61978	$1^*2^*((-3 - 4^{\wedge}5 + 6^{\wedge}7) - 8)/9$
26284	$-1 + (2 + 3)^*(4^{\wedge}5^*(6 - 7/8) + 9)$	62014	$(-1 - (((2^*3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^* - 6 - 7)^*8) - 9$
26290	$(1 - (23 - 4)^{\wedge}5 + 6^{\wedge}7^*8)/ - 9$	62041	$((1 + ((2^*3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^*6) + 7)^*8 + 9$
27554	$((1 - 2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)/6^*(78 - 9)$	62701	$(1/2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6) + 7)^*8 + 9$
28354	$-1/2^*(3^{\wedge}4 - 56789)$	63252	$((1 + 2)^{\wedge}3^*4^*5^*(6 + 7) + 8)^*9$
29075	$12^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5^*6 - 7) + 8 - 9$	64246	$-12 - ((3/(4 - 5))^{\wedge}6 - 7)^* - 89$
29077	$12^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5^*6 - 7) - (8 - 9)$	64472	$1 + ((2 + 3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^*(6 + 7)^*8 - 9$
29083	$(1/2^*(3 + 4^{\wedge}5) + 6)^*7^*8 - 9$	65233	$1 + ((-2 - 3^{\wedge}4)^*(5 + 6) + 7)^* - 8^*9$
29101	$(1/2^*(3 + 4^{\wedge}5) + 6)^*7^*8 + 9$	66144	$((12 + 3^{\wedge}4 - 5) + 5)/(6^{\wedge} - 7^*8^*9)$
29227	$12^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5^*6 + 7) - (8 + 9)$	66563	$123 - ((4 + 5)^{\wedge}6 + 7)/ - 8 + 9$
29245	$12^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5^*6 + 7) - (8 - 9)$	67115	$((1/2^*(3 + 4)^{\wedge}5 - 6) - 7)^*8 - 9$
29264	$((1 - 23)^{\wedge}4 - 5 - 67)/8 - 9$	67825	$1 + (2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(5 + 6^*(7 + 8/9))$
29301	$(1 + 2^*(3 + 4))^*(5^*6 + 7)/8 - 9$	69243	$1 + (-2 - 3^*4^*5^*(- 6 - 7))^*89$
29361	$(12 + 3)^*(4 + (5^{\wedge}6 + 7)/8) - 9$	69326	$((1^*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 - 5 - 6 - 7)^*(8 + 9)$
29607	$(12 + 3^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(6 - 7 + 8^*9)$	69455	$-1 - ((2 + 3)^*(- 4 - 5^{\wedge}6) + 7)^*8/9$
32506	$-1^*2^*(3 - 4^{\wedge}5^*(6 + 7/8) + 9)$	69651	$((((-1 + (2^*3)^{\wedge}4) - 5)^*6 + 7) - 8)^*9$
32914	$1 - 23^*(4^*5^*(6 - 78) + 9)$	69669	$((((-1 + (2^*3)^{\wedge}4) - 5)^*6 - 7) + 8)^*9$
34067	$(1 + 2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^*6^*7 + 8) - 9$	69746	$((1 - 2) + 3)^*((-4^{\wedge}5 + 6^{\wedge}7)/8 + 9)$
34630	$1 + (2^*((3 - 4^{\wedge}5) + 6) - 7)^*(- 8 - 9)$	69926	$((-1 + 2) - 3)^*(4^*5 - (6^{\wedge}7/8 - 9))$
36323	$((1 + 2^{\wedge}(3^*4) + 5)^*(6/7 + 8) - 9)$	70258	$((1 - 2) + 3)^*((4^{\wedge}5 + 6^{\wedge}7)/8 + 9)$
36898	$((-1/2 + 3) + 4)^*5678 - 9$	72539	$-1 + ((2 + 3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)/6^*78^*9$
37303	$((1 + 2^{\wedge}(3^*4) + 567)^*8 - 9)$	72541	$1 + ((2 + 3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)/6^*78^*9$
37321	$((1 + 2^{\wedge}(3^*4) + 567)^*8 + 9)$	72625	$(-1 - (2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^* - 56 - 7^*(- 8 + 9)$
38446	$((-1 + 2^{\wedge}(3^*4) - 5)^*(6/(7 + 8) + 9))$	72923	$-1 - 2/ - 3^*((4 + 5^{\wedge}6)^*7 - 8) - 9$
38535	$(-12 - 3)^*(4^{\wedge}5/6^*(- 7 - 8) - 9)$	72925	$1 - 2/ - 3^*((4 + 5^{\wedge}6)^*7 - 8) - 9$
38864	$(((-1 + (2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*5)^*6 + 7) - 8 - 9)$	73250	$((-1 - 2^{\wedge}(3^*4) - 5)^*(- 6/7 - (8 + 9)))$
39116	$1^*2^*(3^{\wedge}(4 + 5) - 6 - 7^*(8 + 9))$	73471	$-1 + (2/3 + 4)^*(5^{\wedge}6 - 7^*(- 8 - 9))$
39534	$1^*2^*((3^{\wedge}(4 + 5) + 67 + 8) + 9)$	74133	$12^*((-3 - 4^{\wedge}5)^* - 6 + 7 + 8) + 9$
40135	$1^*23^*((4^*56 - 7)^*8 + 9)$	74928	$12^*((-3 - 4^{\wedge}5)^* - 6 - 7 + 89)$
40390	$((1 - 2^{\wedge}(3^*4) + 56)^*(7 - (8 + 9)))$	76206	$(1 - 2^{\wedge} - 3 + 4)^*(5^{\wedge}6 + 7)^{\wedge}(-8 + 9)$
40909	$-1 + (2^{\wedge}(3^*4) - 5)^*((6 - 7)^{\wedge}8 + 9)$	77459	$-1 + ((2^*3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^* - 6^*(7 - 8 - 9)$
41011	$1 + (2^{\wedge}(3^*4) + 5)^*((6 - 7)^{\wedge}8 + 9)$	77461	$1 + ((2^*3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^* - 6^*(7 - 8 - 9)$
41224	$(-1 - 23^*4^*56)^*((-7 + 8) - 9)$	77533	$1^*23^*(-4 - 5^*(- 67 - 8)^*9)$
43229	$-1 - 2^*(3^*((4^{\wedge}5 + 6)^* - 7 + 8) - 9)$	78773	$(1/2^*(3^{\wedge}(4 + 5) - 6) + 7)^*8 + 9$
43938	$((-1 + (2^*34 + 5)^*67) - 8)^*9$	79885	$(1 + 2^*3^*4^*5)^*(6 + 7)^{\wedge}(-8 + 9)$
44094	$(1 + 2)^*((-3^*4 + 5)^{\wedge}6 + 7)/8 - 9$	80903	$(12^{\wedge}3/4/(5 + 6) + 7)^*(8 + 9)$
44967	$1^*2^*(- 3^{\wedge}(4 + 5) + 6)/ - 7^*8 - 9$	83269	$1 + (2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(5 + 6^*(7/8 + 9))$
45076	$(1 + 2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*(5 + 6)^{\wedge}(-7 + 8) + 9$	83392	$1^*2^*3^*((4 + 5^{\wedge}6) + 7)^*8/9$
47300	$((-1 + (2^*3)^{\wedge}4) - 5)^*6^*(7 - 8/9)$	83594	$1 + (2/34)^{\wedge}(-5 - 6 + 7) + 8^*9$
47306	$((1 + 23)^{\wedge}4 - 5 - 6)/7 - 89$	85228	$((12 - 3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^*(- 6 - 7)/(8 - 9)$
48248	$((1 - 2) + 3)^*(4 - 5^*67^*8^*9)$	85825	$1 + ((2 + 3)^{\wedge}4 + 567)^*8^*9$
49906	$((12 + 3)^{\wedge}4 - 5 + 6^* - 7^*(8 + 9))$	87234	$(-1 - ((2^*3)^{\wedge}4 + 5))^* - 67^{\wedge}(-8 + 9)$
51443	$1 - ((2 + 3)^{\wedge}4 - 5 - 6^*7)^* - 89$	87417	$1/2^*((-3^{\wedge}4 - 5^*(- 6^{\wedge}7/8 + 9))$
51965	$-1 + (-2 - ((3/(4 - 5))^{\wedge}6 - 7)^* - 8)^*9$	88947	$(1/2^*(3^{\wedge}(4 + 5) + 67) + 8)^*9$
52877	$1^*23^*(4 + 5^*(6^*78 - 9))$	92521	$((1 - 2 - 3)^{\wedge}(4 + 5)^* - 6 - 7)/(8 + 9)$
52942	$1^*2/3^*((-4^{\wedge}5 + 6)^* - 78 + 9)$	92859	$(-1 - (((2^*3)^{\wedge}4 + 5/6) - 7)^* - 8)^*9$
53153	$((1 - 2^{\wedge}(3^*4) + 5)^*(- 6 - 7) - (8 + 9))$	94066	$((1 + 2)^{\wedge}(3 + 4) - 5^{\wedge}6)^* - 7^{\wedge}(-8 + 9)$
53166	$((1^*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^*(6 + 7) - 8 - 9$	94260	$1^*2^*(3^*((4 + 5^{\wedge}6) + 78) + 9)$
53169	$((1 - 2^{\wedge}(3^*4) + 5)^*(- 6 - 7) + 8 - 9)$	95574	$1^*2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4 + 5) + 6)/ - 7^*(8 + 9))$
53182	$((1^*2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^*(6 + 7) + 8 - 9$	95652	$12^*3^*((-4 + 5^*67)^*8 + 9)$
53327	$((1 + 2^{\wedge}(3^*4) + 5)^*(6 + 7) - (8 - 9))$	96709	$-1 + (-2^*3 + 4^{\wedge}5)^*(6 + 7)^*8 - 9$
53837	$(12^*345^*(6 + 7) + 8) + 9$	98180	$1^*2^*((3 - (4^{\wedge}5^* - 6 + 7)^*8) - 9)$
53868	$12^*((3 + 4 - 567)^* - 8 + 9)$	98204	$1^*2^*((-3 + (4^{\wedge}5^*6 - 7)^*8) + 9)$
53883	$(-1 - 23^*4^*5^*(- 6 - 7) + 8)^*9$	98428	$-1^*2^*((3 - (4^{\wedge}5^*6 + 7)^*8) - 9)$
54195	$(12 + 3)^{\wedge}4 - 5^*6^*7^*(- 8 - 9)$	99660	$1/2^*3^*((4 + 5)^{\wedge}6 + 7)/8 + 9$
57102	$1^* - 2^*(34^*56^*(- 7 - 8) + 9)$	99785	$(-1 + (2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(5 + 6))^*7^{\wedge}(-8 + 9)$
57554	$-1 + (2^{\wedge}(3 + 4) - 5)^*6^*78 - 9$	100651	$(12 - (3 + 4)^{\wedge}5)^* - 6 - 7^*(8 + 9)$
57556	$1 - (2^{\wedge}(3 + 4) - 5)^*6^* - 78 - 9$	101499	$123 + 4^{\wedge}5^*(6^*(7 + 8) + 9)$
57572	$-1 + (2^{\wedge}(3 + 4) - 5)^*6^*78 + 9$	101569	$((1/ - 2 + 3) + 4)^*(5^{\wedge}6 - (7 - 8)^{\wedge}9)$
57574	$1 - (2^{\wedge}(3 + 4) - 5)^*6^* - 78 + 9$	103967	$-1 - 2^*((3^*(4 - 5))^{\wedge}6 - 7)^* - 8^*9$
58733	$(1 - 2 - 34^*(- 5^{\wedge}6 + 78))/9$	103969	$1 - 2^*((3/(4 - 5))^{\wedge}6 - 7)^* - 8^*9$
60168	$-12^*((3/(4 - 5))^{\wedge}6^* - 7 + 89)$	106087	$-1 - ((2 + 3)^{\wedge}4 + 567)^* - 89$
60628	$1^*23^*(4 + 56^*(7^*8 - 9))$	106088	$1^*((2 + 3)^{\wedge}4 + 567)^*89$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
107730	$(-1-234+5^6)^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	169768	$(-1+23^*(4+5)^6+7)/8)/9$
107879	$-1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}4-56)^*(78+9)$	172284	$(-1-(2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5))^*-6^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
107881	$1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}4-56)^*(78+9)$	172575	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*((-5+6/7)^*-8+9)$
108007	$-1^*((2^*3)^{\wedge}4-5^6*7+8^*9)$	174231	$(12+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^*7^*-8)^*9$
108062	$-1^*((2^*3)^{\wedge}4-5^6*7+8+9)$	174826	$1+(((2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5)-6)^*(7+8)^*9$
108080	$-1^*((2^*3)^{\wedge}4-5^6*7+8-9)$	177507	$((1-(2^{\wedge}(3^*4)-5^6)-7)+8)^*9$
109022	$1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*-5+67)^*(-8-9)$	177633	$((1-(2^{\wedge}(3^*4)-5^6))+7+8)^*9$
111006	$(-1+234+5^6)^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	180279	$(12+3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^*7^*8)^*9$
111417	$-1+(2^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)/-6+7)^*(-8-9)$	180564	$123^*4^*((-5-6^*7)^*-8-9)$
111657	$1+(2^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)/6+7)^*(8+9)$	182359	$1/23^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*8+9)$
111776	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)/6+7)^*(-8-9)$	183012	$1^*2^*(3+((-4+5)+6)^{\wedge}7+8)/9$
112225	$((1-2^*34)^*5)^{\wedge}(-6-((-7+8)-9))$	184050	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5))^*(-6-(7-8))^*9$
113757	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^6)^*7/(-8+9)$	184497	$1^*(2^*(3+4^5)+6)^*7^*89$
114071	$((-1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(-5-6)-7)^*8-9$	184590	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5))^*(6+7-8)^*9$
114089	$((-1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(-5-6)-7)^*8+9$	185903	$-1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^*((7+8)+9)$
114436	$(12^{\wedge}3-4^*5)^*67^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	188864	$-1-(((2/34)^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)+8)/9$
114475	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*-5^*(6+7/(-8-9))$	188866	$1-(((2/34)^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)+8)/9$
115709	$((-12^{\wedge}3-4)+5)^*67^*(8-9)$	189825	$((12+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*(-6^*7/8+9)$
116511	$(1^*23+4^{\wedge}(5-(-6-7+8)))/9$	192771	$(-1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*(-6^*7+8))^*9$
116805	$((1+2^*3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*-6^*(7/8-9)$	193600	$((-1+23)^*4^*5)^{\wedge}(-6+7-8+9)$
122416	$((-1-2+3^{\wedge}(4+5))-6)^*7^*8/9$	193688	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4)-5))^*-6^*(-7-8/9)$
122494	$1/2^*((3+4)^*(5+6^{\wedge}7/8)+9)$	196851	$1-(-2-3^{\wedge}(4+5))^*((6-7)^{\wedge}8+9)$
122528	$((1-(-2-3^{\wedge}(4+5)))+6)^*7^*8/9$	198441	$(-1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*((-5-(6+7))^*8-9)$
124742	$(-1+((2^*3^*-4+5^6)-7)^*8)-9$	199254	$-12+3^*((4+5)^6+7)/8-9$
126588	$-12^*(34^*-5^*(6+7^*8)-9)$	200255	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^*(4-5)+6))^*(7-8/9)$
126656	$-1-(((2/34)^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)+8)/9$	205773	$(1-2)^*-3^*((4^{\wedge}5+6^*7-8)-9)$
126658	$1-(((2/34)^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)+8)/9$	207025	$((1-23^*4)^*5)^{\wedge}(-6-((-7+8)-9))$
127935	$1/2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)/6^*78-9)$	208241	$((1+2+34)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)+8)/9$
130127	$1/2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^{\wedge}7-8)+9)$	209811	$12^*(3+4)^5+678-9$
131044	$1^*2^*(3+4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6-7)))-(-8+9))$	209829	$12^*(3+4)^5+678+9$
132174	$1^*2^*((3^*4)^5+6^{\wedge}7)/8-9$	212688	$((1+(2+3^{\wedge}4)^*5)+6)^*7^*8^*9$
133164	$1/2^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^{\wedge}7)^*-8/9$	214970	$(-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*((-5-6)^*-7+89)$
134181	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)-56)^*7-8^*9$	215135	$-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*((-5-6)^*-7+89)$
135968	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(-3+45)^*6^*7^*8^*9$	215137	$1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*((-5-6)^*-7+89)$
137003	$(-1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*(-6-7))^*(8+9)$	215302	$(-1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*((-5-6)^*7-89)$
137038	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5+6^*7-89)$	217010	$((1-(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^*7)-8)/-9$
139708	$1-((2^*3^*4-5^6)+78)^*9$	217623	$(-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5^6))^*7/(8-9)$
140066	$1/2^*(34^*5+6^{\wedge}7+8)+9$	217881	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4))^*(5^*6^*7^*8+9)$
141329	$1^*2-((-3+4)^*-5^6-78)^*9$	219026	$1^*2^*((-3-(4+5^6))^*-7+89)$
141756	$12^*(3/4^*(5^6+7)+89)$	220851	$((((-1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5))^*6+7)-8)^*9$
143437	$((-1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*-5+6)^*7/(-8+9)$	221499	$((((-1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5))^*6+7)-8)^*9$
145476	$12^*-3^*(45^*6^*(7-8)+9)$	221517	$((((-1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5))^*6-7)+8)^*9$
146194	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5)^*67/(8-9)$	222775	$1^*2345^*((-6-7)^*-8-9)$
146432	$1^*2^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5-6^*7^*(-8-9))$	222948	$((-1/2+3^*(4^5+6))+7)^*8^*9$
147597	$(-1+2)^*-3^*((4^5+6+7)^*-8+9)$	223767	$(-1-((2-3^{\wedge}4)+5)^*6^*7^*8)^*9$
149801	$1/2^*((3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^{\wedge}7)-8-9)$	223775	$-1-((2-3^{\wedge}4)+5)^*6^*7^*8^*9$
149809	$1/2^*((3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^{\wedge}7+8)-9)$	223777	$1-((2-3^{\wedge}4)+5)^*6^*7^*8^*9$
149818	$1/2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^{\wedge}7+8+9)$	229425	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*56+7/(8-9)$
150040	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4)-5))^*-6^*(-7+8/9)$	229677	$((12-3)^{\wedge}4^*5+6)^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
151002	$((-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)-5)^*(6+7+8)^*9$	234480	$(1+2+3^*4)^*(5+6+7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
152136	$((-1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*(6+7))-8)^*9$	235120	$1^*2^*((3+4)^{\wedge}(5-(6-7)))-89)$
153104	$((1/2^{\wedge}(-3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^*7^*8/9$	235748	$12^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*7^*8/9)$
155276	$(-1-(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)^*6^{\wedge}7-8)/9$	235890	$12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*(7-8)^*9$
155464	$((-1-23^{\wedge}4)^*-5-6^*7+8)/9$	236502	$12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^*(7-8)^*9$
155465	$((1+23^{\wedge}4)-5)^*(6+7-8)/9$	236808	$(12-(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)/6-7)^*8)^*9$
155762	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)^*6^{\wedge}7-8)/9$	239873	$((12^*3)^{\wedge}4+5)-6/7-8^*9$
155764	$(1+(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6^{\wedge}7+8)/9$	240017	$((12^*3)^{\wedge}4+5)-6/7+8^*9$
156176	$((1-23)^{\wedge}4-5)^*6+78)/9$	240202	$1/(2^*3^*4)^*((56+7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
157360	$12^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*-6+78)/-9$	242073	$(-123^*4)^{\wedge}(-5^*6/(-7-8))+9$
157568	$12^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6+78)/9$	243738	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5^*6^*7-8)^*9$
160370	$1^*2^*((3-4^5)+6)^*(-7-8^*9)$	245400	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5))^*6^*(7-(8+9))$
163214	$1^*2^*((-3-4^5)-6)^*(-7-8^*9)$	246120	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5))^*6^*(7-(8+9))$
163582	$(123^*((4+5)+6)-7)^*89$	251135	$-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6^*7+8)^*9$
164913	$((-1-23^*4^5)-6)^*7/(8-9)$	251137	$1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6^*7+8)^*9$
165884	$-1-(((2+(-3^*4)^5)^*6+7)+8)/9$	254268	$(1/2^*(3-4^5)+6)^*7^*-8^*9$
165892	$1+(((2+3^*4)^5)^*6+7)+8)/9$	255250	$1^*2^*((-3+4^5)^*6-7^*(-8-9))$
166720	$12^*((3^*4+5^6)-7)^*8/9$	255294	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5)/6^*-78^*9$
166737	$((1^{\wedge}2+34)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)+8)/9$	255918	$(1+2+3^{\wedge}(4+5))^*(6+7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
167956	$((12^*3)^{\wedge}4-56)/(-7-(-8-9))$	256035	$(12+3^{\wedge}(4+5))^*(6+7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
168052	$1^*-2^*((3+4)^5)^*((-6-7)+8)+9$	256750	$1^*-2^*((-3-4^5)^*6-7^*(-8-9))$
168088	$1^*2^*((3+4)^5)^*(6+7-8)+9$	258511	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^*(4-5)+6))^*(7+8/9)$
168610	$(-1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(-5-6+7^*(-8-9))$	261748	$1/(2^*-3)^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8+9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
261751	$1/(2^3)^*((-4^{(5+6)}+7^8)+9)$	392682	$((1+2)+3)^*(4^{(56/7)}-89)$
261828	$(1/2^*(3+4^5)+6)^7*8^9$	393072	$1^2*(3/4^{(5-6-7)}-8^9)$
263700	$((1+2^{(3^4)}+5)^*(6/-7+8))^9$	393300	$12^*345^*((-6-7)^*-8-9)$
266113	$1-((2+3^4)+5)^6*7^*-8^9$	400256	$1^*-2^{(3+4)^*}(-56^*7^*8+9)$
267030	$((-1-2^{(3+4)})^*-5^*6^*(78-9))$	412690	$(1-(23-4)^5)/-6-7^*(8-9)$
271584	$((1-((2+3)^4+5)^6)+7)^*-8^9$	413217	$(1+2)^*(3^{(4+5)}-6)^7^{(8+9)}$
272736	$((1-((2+3)^4+5)^*-6)+7)^*8^9$	418455	$((1+(2+3)^{(4+5)})/(6^*7)-8)^9$
275300	$1^*-2^*((-3^{(4+5)}+6)^7+89)$	418599	$((1+(2+3)^{(4+5)})/(6^*7)+8)^9$
275358	$12^*(3^{(4+5)}/6^*7-(8+9))$	419472	$12^*((-3^*(4+5)+6^{7/8})-9)$
275766	$12^*(3^{(4+5)}/6^*7+8+9)$	419706	$-12^*((3^*4^*5-6^{7/8})/8+9)$
279117	$(1-2^{(3^4)})/5-6^{7^*(8-9)}$	420102	$12^*((3^*4^*5+6^{7/8})/8+9)$
279646	$(-1+23^4-5)-((6+7)+8)^9$	434025	$(-1-2^*(3^4-5^{(6+7)+8}))/9$
280741	$(-1-2^*-3^4)^5+6^{7/8}-(8+9)$	439200	$((-1-(2^*3-4^5)^6)-7)^*8^9$
281610	$((1-2^*(-3^4-5^6)+7)+8)^9$	441180	$12^*((3-4^{(5-6-7)})+8)^*-9$
283518	$(1-(2+3)^{(4+5)})/((-6-7^*8)/9)$	442352	$(-1+2^*((3^*-4)^5+6)+7)^*-8/9$
286785	$(1+((2+3)^4-56)^7*8)^9$	442384	$(-1+2^*((3^*4)^5+6)+7)^*8/9$
287334	$(1+(2+3)^4)^*(5^*6^*(7+8)+9)$	443556	$12^*((3+4^{(5-6-7)}))+8)^9$
289089	$(1+2^*(3+4)^5)^*(6/(-7-8)+9)$	445907	$(1-(2^*3^*-4)^5)/(6/7+8)+9$
292670	$(-1+(2^*3)^4)^*(5+(-6-7)^*(-8-9))$	447525	$(-1+2^{(3^4)})^*(5-6/7+8)^9$
293122	$(-1-(2^*3)^4)^*(-5+(6+7)^*(-8-9))$	447890	$1^2^*(-3-4/-5^*((6^7+8)-9))$
298860	$((-1-2^{(3^4)})-5)^*(-6/7-8^9)$	447902	$1^2^*(3+4/5^*((6^7+8)-9))$
300168	$((1+2^{(3^4)})+5+67)^*8^9$	460530	$(-1-2^{(3+4)})^*5^*6^*-7^*(8+9)$
300421	$(1+2^{(3^4)})^*5-6^{7^*(8-9)}$	466492	$1^*-2^*(34-5^*6^{(7+8)}-9)$
303729	$((12+3)^4-5)^*-6/(7-8)+9$	466628	$1^2^*(34-5^*-6^{(7+8)}-9)$
303780	$((12+3)^4+5)^*-6/(7-8)+9$	472328	$((1+2)^{(3^4)}-5)-67)^*8/9$
313838	$1^*-2^*((-3^{(4+5)}+67)^*8+9)$	472388	$((1/2-3-(4+5)^6)+7)^*-8/9$
313874	$1^2^*((3^{(4+5)}-67)^*8+9)$	472396	$((-1/2+3-(4+5)^6)-7)^*-8/9$
315582	$1^*-2^*((-3^{(4+5)}-6^*7)^*8+9)$	476757	$(1+2)^{(3+4)^*}*(5^*6^*7+8)-9$
315982	$1^2^*((3^{(4+5)}+67)^*8-9)$	476775	$(1+2)^{(3+4)^*}*(5^*6^*7+8)+9$
316018	$1^2^*((3^{(4+5)}+67)^*8+9)$	481914	$123/4^*(5^{6+7^*8}-9)$
316305	$(1-2^*(-3^4+5)+6^{7/8})^9$	482291	$(123^*4^*(5+6)+7)^*89$
316976	$((1-2)+3)^4+5-6^{7/8}-8^9$	502038	$1^*-2^*(-3^{(4+5)}-6^{7^*8})/9$
318028	$1/2^*(3^4+5)^{(6^{(7+8)}+9)}$	510705	$(-1+2^{(3^4)})^*(5+6/7+8)^9$
325386	$(1+(2+3)^{(4+5)})/6+(-7-8)^9$	520362	$1^*-2^*(3^{(4+5)}-6^{(7-8^9)})$
325474	$(1+(2+3)^{(4+5)})/6-(7^*8-9)$	522450	$(-1-2^{(3+4)})^*5^*6^*(-7-8)^9$
325568	$(1+(2+3)^{(4+5)})/6+7^*8-9$	525825	$123^*45^*((-6-7)^*-8-9)$
327606	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-5^6)^7+89)$	528356	$(1+2)^{(3^4)}+5^*(6-7^*89)$
328034	$(-1+2+3^*(4-5^6))^7/(8-9)$	531022	$(-1-2)^{(3^4)}-5+6^*(-78+9)$
328048	$(-1+2-3^*(4-5^6))^7/(-8+9)$	531595	$(1+2)^{(3^4)}-5^*(-6-7)+89$
328242	$(-1+2)^*3^*((-4-5^6)^*-7+8)+9$	531615	$(1+2)^{(3^4)}+(-5-6)^*(-7-8)+9$
336690	$(-1-2^{(3+4)})^*-5^*6^*(78+9)$	531616	$(1+2)^{(3^4)}+56-7^*(-8-9)$
341888	$1^*-2^{(3+4)^*}(-5^*6^*7^*8+9)$	531618	$-1^2^*(3+((4+5^6)+7)^*(-8-9))$
342028	$(1+23^4*(5+6)^{(-7+8)})/9$	531667	$(1+2)^{(3^4)}+5+(-6-7)^*(-8-9)$
343669	$(1-23)^*(4-5^6)-7^*(8-9)$	536445	$(-1+2^{(3+4+5)})^*(6^*7+89)$
344192	$1^2^{(3+4)^*}*(5^*6^*7^*8+9)$	536707	$(1+2^{(3+4+5)})^*(6^*7+89)$
346881	$(1+2^{(3+4)})^*(5^*6^*7^*8+9)$	546630	$(-1+2+34)^*(5^{6-7^{(8+9)}})$
351293	$(-1+2^*((-3-4-5)^6+7))/8+9$	557752	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4^5-6^{7^*8})-8^9$
352308	$(-12+(3^4)^{(5+6-7)})^*(8+9)$	557896	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4^5-6^{7^*8})+8^9$
352680	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^{(5-6)+7})-89$	560367	$(-1-((2^*3)^{(4-5)+6})+7)^*-8)^9$
352716	$(-12-(3^4)^{(5+6-7)})^*(-8-9)$	561992	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5+6^{7^*8})+9$
353700	$-1^*(2^*((-3^{(4+5)}-6)+78)^*9)$	562363	$12^*-3^*(4-5^6)-7^*(8-9)$
354888	$(1^*-2^*((-3^{(4+5)}+6)+78)^*9)$	566406	$-1234^*(5^*6^*(-7-8)-9)$
359493	$-1-2+(3^4+5^*(6+7)+8)^9$	578384	$(1+2+34)^*(5^{6+7})^{(8+9)}$
359495	$-1+2+(3^4+5^*(6+7)+8)^9$	580248	$(-1-((2+3)^4-5)^*(-6-7))^*8^9$
359497	$1+2+(3^4+5^*(6+7)+8)^9$	580311	$(-1+((2+3)^4-5)^*(6+7))^*8^9$
361562	$((1+2^{(3^4)}+5)^*(-6/7+89))$	580329	$(-1-((2+3)^4-5)^*(6+7))^*8^9$
364392	$((-1-2)^{(3+4+5)}-6)^7*8^9$	580392	$(1-((2+3)^4-5)^*(-6-7))^*8^9$
368091	$((1-2^{(3^4)}+5)^*-6^*(7+8)-9)$	580409	$-1-((2-3-4)^*(5^{6+7})-8)^9$
368109	$((1-2^{(3^4)}+5)^*-6^*(7+8)+9)$	580411	$1-((2-3-4)^*(5^{6+7})-8)^9$
369189	$((1+2^{(3^4)}+5)^*6^*(7+8)+9)$	580574	$1^2^*((3^4)^5/6^*7-8)-9$
374622	$1^2^*(3^4^*((5^6-7)-8)-9)$	580642	$1^2^*((3^4)^5/6^*7+8)+9$
374658	$1^2^*(3^4^*((5^6-7)-8)+9)$	586150	$1234^*5^*((-6-7)^*-8-9)$
374777	$((-1-2)^*(3^4-5^6)+7)^*8+9$	590994	$((1+2)^{(3+4)}^*5^*6^*7^*8)^9$
374787	$(-1-2)^*((3/4-5^6+7)^*8+9)$	592807	$((12^*3)^4+5)^6-7/(8+9)$
375213	$(-1-2)^*((3/4+5^6+7)^*-8-9)$	594405	$(-1+(2^*3)^4)^*(5^*6^*(7+8)+9)$
375342	$1^2^*(3^4^*((5^6+7)+8)-9)$	595323	$(-1-(2^*3)^4)^*(-5^*6^*(7+8)-9)$
375378	$1^2^*(3^4^*((5^6+7)+8)+9)$	596772	$(-123-((4+5)^6+7)/-8)^9$
376625	$1^23^*(4^{(5-6)^7+8}-9)$	598509	$((-1-2)^{(3^4)}+567)/8^9$
377039	$1^23^*(4^{(5-6)^7+8}+9)$	598986	$(123+((4+5)^6+7)/8)^9$
379683	$1/2^*((3/45)^{(6-7+8)}-9)$	599382	$1^2^*(3^{(4+5)}+6^{7+8^*9})$
379692	$1/2^*((3/45)^{(6-7+8)}+9)$	610164	$1/2^*3^{(4+5)^*}*(6+7^*8)-9$
388574	$(-1-2/-3^{(4-5-6)}-7)^*89$	610182	$1/2^*3^{(4+5)^*}*(6+7^*8)+9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
625970	$(1-2^{\wedge}((3+4*5)-6)+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	844415	$-1+(2*3*((4+5^{\wedge}6)+7)+8)*9$
626644	$(1-2*(3-4/-5^{\wedge}6)+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	844417	$1+(2*3*((4+5^{\wedge}6)+7)+8)*9$
627808	$((-1+2)-3)*(4^{\wedge}5+6^{\wedge}7/-8*9)$	852992	$1*2^{\wedge}(3+4)*56*7*(8+9)$
631904	$((1-2)+3)*(4^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7/-8*9)$	853631	$((-1-(2*3*-4)^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)-8)/9$
632809	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8(-8+9))$	853633	$((1+(2*3*4)^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)+8)/9$
634176	$12^{\wedge}3*((4*5-67)*-8-9)$	854298	$(((-1-2-3*4)^{\wedge}5+6)-7)/8*-9$
636800	$(1+2*((-3-4)^{\wedge}5+6)+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	859656	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))*56*7*(-8-9)$
637064	$(1-2*(-3*4+5^{\wedge}6)+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	873695	$-1*((2*3)^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8+9)$
638783	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	886830	$123*(4^{\wedge}5+6)*7*(-8+9)$
639618	$(1-2*3*(4^{\wedge}5+6)+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	915839	$((-1-(2*3*-4)^{\wedge}5+6^{\wedge}7)-8)/9$
639968	$(1+(-2-3)*(4^{\wedge}5-6)+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	915841	$((1+(2*3*4)^{\wedge}5+6^{\wedge}7)+8)/9$
640120	$(-1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5)*-6+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	922369	$1/((2+3)/(-4/5*(6-7^{\wedge}8)+9))$
640342	$((-12^{\wedge}3+4)-5-(-6-7^{\wedge}8))/9$	925470	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3*4))*5+(-6-7)*(-8-9))$
640726	$((12^{\wedge}3+4)-5-(-6-7^{\wedge}8))/9$	925922	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3*4))*5+(-6-7)*(-8-9))$
644267	$1*(-2*((-3-4)^{\wedge}5+6)+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	975888	$((1^{\wedge}2+3)^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7/(8*9)$
648025	$((1-2/3^{\wedge}4)*5)^{\wedge}(-6+7-8+9)$	979750	$1/2*((-3-4)*5-6^{\wedge}7)-8-9)$
649213	$-1+((2+3)^{\wedge}(-4-(-5-6))+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	979802	$1/2*((3+4)*5+6^{\wedge}7)+8+9)$
649215	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(-4-(-5-6))+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	994009	$((1+2)^{\wedge}3-4*5)^{\wedge}(-6-(-7+8)+9)$
656101	$1+(2/3^{\wedge}4*5)^{\wedge}((-6-(-7+8))+9)$	1007763	$((12*3)^{\wedge}4-5-6)/(7+8)*9$
658060	$((12+3)^{\wedge}4-5)*(-6-7)/(8-9)$	1023490	$(1/2-3^{\wedge}(4+5))*-6*78/9$
659372	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))*67-8-9)$	1023542	$(1/2+3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6*78/9$
659380	$1/-2*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))*-67-8+9)$	1026720	$((-1-(2*3)^{\wedge}4)*5+6+7)*-8*9$
659381	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))*67-8+9)$	1037640	$-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)*5/6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$
659389	$1/-2*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))*-67-8-9)$	1037642	$1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)*5/6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$
661550	$(1-((-2-3)^{\wedge}(4+5))*6+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	1046998	$((-1-2)-3)*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8)/9$
664225	$((1+2/3^{\wedge}4)*5)^{\wedge}(-6+7-8+9)$	1059510	$-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)*5/6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$
666562	$((1-23)^{\wedge}4-5-(-6-7^{\wedge}8))/9$	1059512	$1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)*5/6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$
668158	$(-1-(2/34)^{\wedge}((-5-6)+7)*-8)-9$	1062075	$(1-2)*3-4*(-5^{\wedge}6+7)*(-8-9)$
668176	$(-1-(2/34)^{\wedge}((-5-6)+7)*-8)+9$	1071224	$-1+(23*45)^{\wedge}(-6-(-7+8-9))$
668178	$1+(2/34)^{\wedge}((-5-6)+7)*8+9$	1071226	$1+(23*45)^{\wedge}(-6-(-7+8-9))$
670761	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(3*4))/5)^{\wedge}(-6+7-(-8-9))$	1074194	$(1*2+3/4)*((5*(6-7))^{\wedge}8-9)$
679396	$(1-((-2-34)^{\wedge}5-67))/89$	1078488	$(-1-2)*3*4*5*(6+7)+8)*-9$
684336	$((-1+23)*4*5+6^{\wedge}7)-8)/9$	1082621	$(1/2+3-4*(-5-6)^{\wedge}7/8)/9$
688110	$((1-2)+3)*(4^{\wedge}5*6*7*8-9)$	1101240	$1*(-2+3^{\wedge}((-4+5)+6))*7*8*9$
688146	$((1-2)+3)*(4^{\wedge}5*6*7*8+9)$	1102221	$(-1-2+3^{\wedge}((-4+5)+6))*7*8*9$
689339	$((1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))*6+7)/(8+9)$	1102275	$(1+2+3^{\wedge}((-4+5)+6))*7*8*9$
693351	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}-3+4)*5/(6^{\wedge}7*8)-9$	1103256	$1*(-2-3^{\wedge}((-4+5)+6))*7*8*9$
693369	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}-3+4)*5/(6^{\wedge}7*8)+9$	1104601	$((1+2)^{\wedge}3+4*5)^{\wedge}(-6-(-7+8)+9)$
699037	$1/(2*3)*((4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)-89)$	1107414	$(-1+((2+3)+4)*5^{\wedge}6)*7/8*9$
699060	$1/2*-3*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7*8)/9$	1117468	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6^{\wedge}7-89$
699069	$1/(2*3)*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7*8)+9$	1117646	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6^{\wedge}7+89$
703826	$-1+((-2-3-4)*-5^{\wedge}6+78)*9$	1118472	$(1-2^{\wedge}((-3+4-5)*-6))/(-7-8)-9$
703828	$1+((-2-3-4)*-5^{\wedge}6+78)*9$	1118490	$(1-2^{\wedge}((-3+4-5)*-6))/(-7-8)+9$
715151	$(1+23^{\wedge}((4-5)+6)+7+8)/9$	1121842	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6^{\wedge}7-89$
715369	$1*23*((4-5+6^{\wedge}7)-8)/9$	1122020	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6^{\wedge}7+89$
715415	$1*23*((-4+5+6^{\wedge}7)+8)/9$	1195740	$((-1+2*(3+(4+5)^{\wedge}6))-7)/8*9$
718999	$(1+23*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7))/(8+9)$	1208367	$(-1+((2*3)^{\wedge}4-5)*(6+7)*8)*9$
734655	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))*5*6*7*(-8-9)$	1208385	$(1+((2*3)^{\wedge}4-5)*(6+7)*8)*9$
736234	$((-1+23)^{\wedge}5+6)*7^{\wedge}8-9)$	1225449	$(123*(4+5))^{\wedge}(-6-(-7+8-9))$
749352	$-12*(3-4*((5^{\wedge}6-7)-8)-9)$	1234872	$((1-2)+3)*4*5*6*7*8*9$
750648	$12*(3+4*((5^{\wedge}6+7)+8)-9)$	1249440	$(1-2+3^{\wedge}4)*5^{\wedge}6+7/(8-9))$
751626	$(-1-(2/34)^{\wedge}(-5-6+7)+8)*-9$	1250550	$-1-(2-3*4)*5^{\wedge}6+7*8-9$
751752	$(-1+(2/34)^{\wedge}(-5-6+7)+8)*9$	1250552	$1-(2-3*4)*5^{\wedge}6+7*8-9$
751770	$((-1-(2/34)^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))-8)*-9$	1250568	$-1-(2-3*4)*5^{\wedge}6+7*8+9$
757568	$(-1+2-3*-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8)/9$	1250570	$1-(2-3*4)*5^{\wedge}6+7*8+9$
759354	$-12+(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)-9$	1259370	$(1/2*(3*4*-5+6^{\wedge}7)-8)*9$
759396	$12+(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)+9$	1259512	$((1/2-3^{\wedge}(-4-5))/6^{\wedge}7-8)*9$
767999	$-1-2*-3*4*5*(6-7*(-8-9))$	1259912	$((1/2+3^{\wedge}(-4-5))/6^{\wedge}7+8)*9$
768001	$1-2*-3*4*5*(6-7*(-8-9))$	1260054	$(1/2*(3*4*5+6^{\wedge}7)+8)*9$
790551	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))/(6*7)*8+9)$	1262097	$1+(((2/34)^{\wedge}5-6)+7)*8/9$
791316	$(-12^{\wedge}3+4)*5*6*(-7-8)-9)$	1302081	$((1-(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))*-6-7)-8)/9$
794988	$(12^{\wedge}3+4)*5*6*(7+8)+9)$	1313508	$12*(3*4+5*6)*7^{\wedge}8(-8+9)$
808569	$((12^{\wedge}3*(-4+56)-7)-8)*9$	1364370	$(1+2+3^{\wedge}((-4+5)+6))*7*8*9$
813626	$((1+2)*3-4*5)^{\wedge}6+7)/89$	1368899	$-1+(234*5)^{\wedge}(-6-(-7+8-9))$
827190	$(12+3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6*7^{\wedge}8(-8+9)$	1368901	$1+(234*5)^{\wedge}(-6-(-7+8-9))$
838880	$1/(2+3)*((4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)+89)$	1372495	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3*4))*-5*6*7^{\wedge}8(-8+9)$
843083	$-1-(2*3*((4-5^{\wedge}6)+7)+8)*9$	1375007	$(-1+23)*4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8(-8+9)$
843085	$1-(2*3*((4-5^{\wedge}6)+7)+8)*9$	1375154	$(-1+23)*4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8(-8+9)$
843659	$-1+(2*-3*(-4-5^{\wedge}6+7)+8)*9$	1379537	$((1-23)^{\wedge}4+5)*6(-7+8)/9$
843661	$1+(2*-3*(-4-5^{\wedge}6+7)+8)*9$	1388745	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))*5/6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9(-8+9)$
843839	$-1-(2*-3*(-4+5^{\wedge}6+7)+8)*9$	1398083	$(-1-2-3*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7*8))/-9$
843841	$1-(2*-3*(-4+5^{\wedge}6+7)+8)*9$	1405515	$((1-23)^{\wedge}4-5)*-6/(7-8)+9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1405566	$((-1-23)^{4+5})^*6/(-7+8)^9$	2050311	$-1/2^*(3-45^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9)))$
1407456	$(1/(2+34)+5)^*6^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	2050314	$1/2^*(3+45^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9)))$
1416192	$12^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6+7-89)$	2096900	$(1/2+3)^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)/7-8^*9)$
1418160	$12^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6-(7-89))$	2097058	$1/2^*((-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))-7)-89$
1431595	$((-1-23)^{4+5})^*(6+(-7+8)/9)$	2097111	$-1/2^*(3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7+8^*9)$
1439668	$(-1+((2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)-6)/7)+8-9$	2097114	$1/2^*((3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))-7-8^*9)$
1441162	$-12^*3-4^{\wedge}(5-6)^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$	2097190	$1/2^*((-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))+7+8^*9)$
1441234	$12^*3-4^{\wedge}(5-6)^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$	2097193	$1/2^*(3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7+8^*9)$
1457427	$(-1-2+(3^*4)^{\wedge}5)^*(6-7^{\wedge}(8-9))$	2097246	$1/2^*((3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))+7)+89$
1461398	$((-1-23^{\wedge}4)^*(5-6^*7)+8)/9$	2097404	$(1/2+3)^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)/7+8^*9)$
1472023	$(-1+(2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+7))/89$	2099486	$1^*2^*((3/4^*5/6^{\wedge}7-8)-9)$
1493856	$(-12-(3^*4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*8^*-9$	2099554	$1^*2^*((3/4^*5^*6^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$
1503908	$1/23^*(4^{\wedge}5+6^*(7^{\wedge}8+9))$	2120940	$(12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*7^*8)^*9$
1518731	$-1+2^*((3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)-9)$	2121552	$(12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*7^*8)^*9$
1518732	$1^*-2^*((-3/45)^{\wedge}((-6-7)+8)+9)$	2125485	$(1-2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6-7-8))^*-9$
1518733	$1+2^*((3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)-9)$	2125503	$(-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6-7-8))^*-9$
1518767	$-1+2^*((3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)+9)$	2126025	$(-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6-7-8))^*9$
1518768	$1^*2^*((3/45)^{\wedge}((-6-7)+8)+9)$	2126043	$(1-2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6-7-8))^*9$
1518769	$1+2^*((3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)+9)$	2126460	$((12+3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^*7^*(-8+9)$
1519097	$(-1^*2+(3+4)/5^{\wedge}(6-7-8))/9$	2129976	$(12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^*7^*8)^*9$
1528521	$(-1-2+(3^*4)^{\wedge}5)^*(6+7^{\wedge}(8-9))$	2130588	$(12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^*7^*8)^*9$
1534680	$(-1-2)^*((3-4^{\wedge}5)+6)^*7^*8^*9$	2134980	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5)^*6^*(78+9))$
1561896	$(-1-2)^*((3+4^{\wedge}5)+6)^*7^*-8^*9$	2141244	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5)^*6^*(78+9))$
1562112	$12^{\wedge}3^*4^*(5+(-6-7)^*(-8-9))$	2178576	$(-123^*-4)^{\wedge}(-5^*6/(-7-8))^*9$
1606024	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*-56^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	2187410	$-1+(2+3)^*4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7-89$
1640184	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4+56))^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	2187412	$1+(2+3)^*4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7-89$
1653338	$1^*2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6^*7-(-8+9))$	2187571	$-1+(2+3)^*4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7+8^*9$
1653406	$1^*2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6^*7+8+9)$	2187573	$1+(2+3)^*4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7+8^*9$
1664100	$(1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5)^{\wedge}((-6+7-8)+9)$	2187588	$-1+(2+3)^*4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7+89$
1669264	$(1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4-5)^{\wedge}((-6+7-8)+9)$	2187590	$1+(2+3)^*4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7+89$
1674091	$((1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^*6/7-8)-9$	2203806	$1^*-2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7^*8+9)$
1674109	$((1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^*6/7-8)+9$	2203815	$1^*2^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*-7^*8-9$
1674125	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^*6/7+8+9$	2203833	$1^*2^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*-7^*8+9$
1677340	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6^{\wedge}7-89$	2203842	$1^*2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*-7^*8+9)$
1677518	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6^{\wedge}7+89$	2205150	$1^*-2^*((3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*-7^*8+9)$
1679380	$1^*2^*((3^*(45+6^{\wedge}7)+8)+9)$	2205159	$1^*2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7^*8-9$
1681714	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6^{\wedge}7-89$	2205177	$1^*2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7^*8+9$
1681892	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6^{\wedge}7+89$	2205186	$1^*2^*((3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7^*8+9)$
1690000	$(1-((2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5))^{\wedge}((-6+7-8)+9)$	2237440	$1^*23^*4^{\wedge}5^*((-6-7)^*-8-9)$
1693260	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5)^*6^*(78-9))$	2242944	$((1+2+3^{\wedge}4-5)+6)/7/(-8+9)$
1695204	$(1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5)^{\wedge}((-6+7-8)+9)$	2252071	$(-1+2^*(3+4)^{\wedge}5)^*6^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
1695241	$(12^*3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6^*(-7+8)^{\wedge}9$	2278098	$(1+2)^*((3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)-9)$
1698228	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5)^*6^*(78-9))$	2278152	$(1+2)^*((3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)+9)$
1793529	$(-12+3^*((4+5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8)^*9$	2359092	$12^*(3^*4^{\wedge}(-5+6+7)-8-9)$
1793583	$(-1-(-2-3^*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7))/8)^*9$	2359500	$12^*(3^*4^{\wedge}(-5+6+7)+8+9)$
1793591	$-1+(-2-3^*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7))/-8^*9$	2370371	$(1+2)^{\wedge}-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)+8/9$
1793593	$1+(-2-3^*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7))/-8^*9$	2374952	$-1-((23-4)^*-5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9$
1793745	$(-12-3^*((4+5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8)^*-9$	2374954	$1-((23-4)^*-5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9$
1796001	$((-1-23)^{\wedge}4+5)^*(6+(7+8)/9)$	2379373	$-1/2^*(3^{\wedge}4+(-5+6^{\wedge}7)^*(-8-9))$
1834966	$((-1^{\wedge}2-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7/(-8-9)$	2379539	$1/2^*(3^{\wedge}4+(-5-6^{\wedge}7)^*(-8-9))$
1844436	$(-12+(3^*4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*89$	2388582	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)^*5)^*6^*7^*89$
1846572	$(-12-(3^*4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*89$	2396058	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)^*5)^*6^*7^*89$
1855426	$(-1+23/4)^*((5^*(6-7))^{\wedge}8-9)$	2428704	$12^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)/7^*-8^*9$
1860033	$1/2^*(-3+(-4-5)^{\wedge}6)/7^{\wedge}(8-9)$	2467725	$((12+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^*(7/8+9)$
1866187	$(1+2+3^*-4^*5^*(-6^{\wedge}7+8))/9$	2472679	$((1/(2^*3)-4)-5)^*-6^{\wedge}7-89$
1866293	$(-1-2-3^*-4^*5^*(6^{\wedge}7+8))/9$	2472857	$((1/(2^*3)-4)-5)^*-6^{\wedge}7+89$
1922358	$123^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}(-7+8))-9$	2479158	$1^*-2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7+8)^*9$
1922376	$123^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}(-7+8))+9$	2479194	$12^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)/6^*7-8)^*9$
1958901	$((1+23^{\wedge}4-5)+6)^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	2479446	$1^*2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*-7+8)^*9$
1984626	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))/((6/7+8)^*-9)$	2480670	$1^*-2^*((3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*-7+8)^*9$
1990686	$((1+23)^{\wedge}4+5)^*6/(-7+8)^{\wedge}9$	2480958	$1^*2^*((3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7+8)^*9$
1992885	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^*4)-5)^*(-6^*7/8+9)$	2499710	$-1+(2+3)^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9$
2000103	$1^*2^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6+7/8)-9$	2499934	$-1-((2+3)^*-4^*5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9$
2000121	$1^*2^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6+7/8)+9$	2499936	$1-((2+3)^*-4^*5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9$
2013106	$((-1-23)^*(4-(5+6)^{\wedge}7+8)/9)$	2499952	$-1-((2+3)^*-4^*5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9$
2014722	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4))^*(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}(-8+9))$	2499954	$1-((2+3)^*-4^*5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9$
2046408	$12^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6)^*78/9$	2500270	$-1-(-2-3)^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9$
2046971	$(1/2-3^{\wedge}(4+5))^*(-6-7)^*8-9$	2500272	$1-(-2-3)^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9$
2046989	$(1/2-3^{\wedge}(4+5))^*(-6-7)^*8+9$	2509056	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}-3+4+5)/6^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
2047075	$(1/2+3^{\wedge}(4+5))^*(6+7)^*8-9$	2514988	$(-1+23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6))^*7/(-8-9)$
2047093	$(1/2+3^{\wedge}(4+5))^*(6+7)^*8+9$	2516262	$(-1+23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6))^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
2047656	$12^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6)^*78/-9$	2517021	$((-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)/-5+6^{\wedge}7-8)^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
2520395	$-1 + ((2+3)^4 * 5 + 6^{\wedge}7) + 8)^*9$	3483444	$12 * (((3^4)^{\wedge}5 / 6 * 7 - 8) - 9)$
2521827	$((-1 + (2^3)^{\wedge}4) / 5 + 6^{\wedge}7) + 8)^*9$	3483697	$(-1 - 2^*(3^4)^{\wedge}5 - 6)^* - 7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
2562149	$1 - (-2^{\wedge}3 + 4^*(-5^*6 - 7^{\wedge}8)) / 9$	3483852	$12 * (((3^4)^{\wedge}5 / 6 * 7 + 8) + 9)$
2567999	$(-1 - (2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5)) / -6^*(7+8/9)$	3495255	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge}(3^*(4+5) - 6))^*(- 7 - 8) / 9$
2637488	$1 * 2^*((3^{\wedge}(4+5) * 6^7 - 8) - 9)$	3511807	$-1 + (-2^*(-3^{\wedge}4 + 5))^{\wedge}(6 / (7 - 8) + 9)$
2637556	$1 * 2^*((3^{\wedge}(4+5) * 6^7 + 8) + 9)$	3511808	$1 * (-2^*(-3^{\wedge}4 + 5))^{\wedge}(6 / (7 - 8) + 9)$
2691468	$(-1 + 2^{\wedge}(3+4)^5) * 6^*78^*9$	3511809	$1 + (-2^*(-3^{\wedge}4 + 5))^{\wedge}(6 / (7 - 8) + 9)$
2699892	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge}(3+4)^5) * 6^* - 78^*9$	3520000	$(-1 + 23)^*(4^*5)^{\wedge}((-6 - 7 + 8) + 9)$
2782520	$1 / 23^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6 + 7) - 89$	3542922	$1 * - 2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5) * 6^*(- 7 - 8) + 9)$
2782698	$1 / 23^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6 + 7) + 89$	3542958	$1 * 2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5) * 6^*(7+8) + 9)$
2796109	$1 * 2 / - 3^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6) + 7) - 89$	3581577	$(1 - 2^*(-3^{\wedge}4 + 5))^{\wedge}(6 / (7 - 8) + 9)$
2796181	$-1 * (2 / 3^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6) + 7) + 8 + 9)$	3595506	$(-1 + (2+3)^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6 + 7)) / 89$
2796208	$1 * 2 / 3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6) + 7 - (8 - 9))$	3610712	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^4) - 5^{\wedge}6) * 7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
2796282	$1 * 2 / - 3^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7^*(8+9))$	3612168	$(-1 + 2^{\wedge}(3+4)^5) * 6^*7^*8^*9$
2796287	$1 * 2 / - 3^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6) + 7) + 89$	3613176	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge}(3+4)^5) * 6^*7^* - 8^*9$
2796618	$1 * 2 / 3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7^* - 89)$	3637855	$(1 - 23^{\wedge}4 + 5)^*(- 6 - 7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
2809799	$-1 + (2+3)^4 * (5^{\wedge}6 - (7+8))^*9$	3680000	$1 * 23^*(4^*5)^{\wedge}((-6 - 7 + 8) + 9)$
2809801	$1 + (2+3)^4 * (5^{\wedge}6 - (7+8))^*9$	3718757	$(-1 + 2 - 34^* - 5^{\wedge}6) * 7 / (-8+9)$
2813831	$-1 - ((2+3)^* - 4^*(5^{\wedge}6 + 7) - 8)^*9$	3720479	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^4) + 56) * 7 / (-8+9)$
2813833	$1 - ((2+3)^* - 4^*(5^{\wedge}6 + 7) - 8)^*9$	3795174	$(-1 - 2) / 3^{\wedge} - 4^*(- 5^{\wedge}6 + 7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
2826539	$-1 + (2+3)^4 * (5^{\wedge}6 + 78)^*9$	3796854	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4 * 5^{\wedge}6 - 7^{\wedge}(-8+9))$
2826541	$1 + (2+3)^4 * (5^{\wedge}6 + 78)^*9$	3829462	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^4) + 5^{\wedge}6) * 7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
2831319	$(-1 + (2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6^*7)^*8)^*9$	3840000	$(1+23)^*(4^*5)^{\wedge}((-6 - 7 + 8) + 9)$
2831337	$(1 - (-2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6^*7)^*8)^*9$	3886625	$((-1 - 23^{\wedge}4) + 5)^*(- 6 - 7 - 8) / 9$
2832480	$1 * 2^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6 + 7)^* - 8^*9$	3975966	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6^* - 7+8)^* - 9$
2836224	$1 * 2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6 + 7)^*8^*9$	3979576	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4) - 5^{\wedge}6 - 7) + 8) / 9$
2837367	$(-1 + (2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6^*7)^*8)^*9$	4084107	$(1 + (-2 - 3)^* - 4)^{\wedge}5 + 6 / (-7 + 8)^{\wedge}9$
2837385	$(1 - (-2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6^*7)^*8)^*9$	4100622	$(1 - 2)^*3 + 45^{\wedge}(-6 - 7 - (-8 - 9))$
2917264	$(12^{\wedge}3 - 4^*5)^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$	4100628	$(-1 + 2)^*3 + 45^{\wedge}(-6 - 7 - (-8 - 9))$
2954961	$(12^{\wedge}3 - 4 - 5)^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$	4133358	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)^*5^*6^*7 - 8)^*9$
2982529	$(12^{\wedge}3 + 4 - 5)^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$	4133502	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)^*5^*6^*7 + 8)^*9$
2985956	$12^*((3^4)^{\wedge}5 - ((6+7)+8) / 9)$	4161600	$(12 * 34^*5)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-7 - 8 - 9))$
2986012	$12^*((3^4)^{\wedge}5 + ((6+7)+8) / 9)$	4165681	$(1+2^*(3 - 4^{\wedge}5))^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$
2989441	$(12^{\wedge}3 - 4 + 5)^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$	4169763	$-1 + (2^*(3 - 4^{\wedge}5))^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$
2999235	$((12+3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^*6^*(7/8+9)$	4169765	$1 + (2^*(3 - 4^{\wedge}5))^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$
3017169	$(12^{\wedge}3 + 4 + 5)^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$	4173849	$(1 - 2^*(3 - 4^{\wedge}5))^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$
3045263	$((1 - 23)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^*(- 6 - 7) / (8 - 9)$	4214809	$(1 - 2^*(3 + 4^{\wedge}5))^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$
3055504	$(12^{\wedge}3 + 4^*5)^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$	4218915	$-1 + (2^*(3 + 4^{\wedge}5))^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$
3069594	$1 * - 2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6)^*78 + 9)$	4218917	$1 + (2^*(3 + 4^{\wedge}5))^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$
3069630	$1 * 2^*((3^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6)^*78 + 9)$	4223025	$(1+2^*(3+4^{\wedge}5))^{\wedge}(-6+7-8+9)$
3071466	$1 * 2^*((3^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6)^*78 - 9)$	4290894	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6^*7+8)^*9$
3071502	$1 * 2^*((3^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6)^*78 + 9)$	4313023	$((1+23)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^*(- 6 - 7) / (8 - 9)$
3078269	$(-1 - 23^{\wedge}4)^*(- 5 - 6) - 7^*(8 - 9)$	4327786	$(-1 - ((2 - 3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(5 + 6 - 7) - 8)) / - 9$
3079211	$(12^*3)^{\wedge}4 + 5^*(6^{\wedge}7 - (8 + 9))$	4394430	$(12 - 3 / 4)^*((5 / (6 - 7))^{\wedge}8 - 9)$
3079291	$(12^*3)^{\wedge}4 + 5^*(6^{\wedge}7 + 8 - 9)$	4476834	$1 * 2^*((3^*45 - 6^{\wedge}7)^* - 8 + 9)$
3079301	$(12^*3)^{\wedge}4 + 5^*(6^{\wedge}7 - (8 - 9))$	4478647	$((-1 + 2) - 3)^*(4^*5 - 6^{\wedge}7)^*8 - 9$
3079381	$(12^*3)^{\wedge}4 + 5^*(6^{\wedge}7 + 8 + 9)$	4478665	$((-1 + 2) - 3)^*(4^*5 - 6^{\wedge}7)^*8 + 9$
3079656	$(12^*3)^{\wedge}4 + 5^*(6^{\wedge}7 + 8^*9)$	4479287	$((1 - 2) + 3)^*(4^*5 + 6^{\wedge}7)^*8 - 9$
3082536	$(-1 + 2^{\wedge}(3+4)^5) * 6^*78^*9$	4479305	$((1 - 2) + 3)^*(4^*5 + 6^{\wedge}7)^*8 + 9$
3083670	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)^5 * 6^*(7^*8 - 9)$	4481118	$1 * 2^*((3^*45 + 6^{\wedge}7)^*8 - 9)$
3092184	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge}(3+4)^5) * 6^*7^* - 8^*9$	4499954	$1 - ((2+34)^* - 5^{\wedge}6 + 7)^*8 + 9$
3094253	$-1 - ((2+3/4)^* - 5^{\wedge}6 - 7)^*8^*9$	4605678	$1 * - 2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(- 6 - 7) + 8)^*9$
3094255	$1 - ((2+3/4)^* - 5^{\wedge}6 - 7)^*8^*9$	4605966	$1 * 2^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(- 6 - 7) + 8)^*9$
3143529	$(12^{\wedge}3 + 45)^{\wedge}(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$	4641128	$-1 - ((2^{\wedge} - 3 + 4)^* - 5^{\wedge}6 - 7)^*8^*9$
3171577	$(-1 - 23^{\wedge}4 + 5^*(6 + 7^{\wedge}8)) / 9$	4641130	$1 - ((2^{\wedge} - 3 + 4)^* - 5^{\wedge}6 - 7)^*8^*9$
3188497	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^4) - 5)^*6 - 7^*(8+9)$	4683126	$1 * 2^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6)^* - 7^*(8+9)$
3188534	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^4) - 5)^*6 + 7 - 89$	4685982	$1 * 2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6)^*7^*(8+9)$
3188758	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^4) + 5)^*6 - 7 + 89$	4740741	$(-1 + 2 / 3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6 - 7) + 8) / 9$
3188795	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^4) + 5)^*6 - 7^*(- 8 - 9)$	4761124	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4) - 5)^{\wedge}(-6+7-8+9)$
3195936	$12^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6^{\wedge}7)^* - 8 / 9$	4804864	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4) + 5)^{\wedge}(-6+7-8+9)$
3202635	$-12^*3 - (-4 + 5^*(- 6 - 7^{\wedge}8)) / 9$	4980354	$(12 + 3 / 4)^*((5 / (6 - 7))^{\wedge}8 - 9)$
3202638	$(1 - 234 - 5^*(6 - 7^{\wedge}8)) / 9$	5020344	$((1 - 2) + 3)^*(- 4^{\wedge}5 + 6^{\wedge}7) - 8)^*9$
3202690	$(1 + 234 - 5^*(6 - 7^{\wedge}8)) / 9$	5020488	$((1 - 2) + 3)^*(- 4^{\wedge}5 + 6^{\wedge}7) + 8)^*9$
3202707	$12^*3 - (-4 + 5^*(- 6 - 7^{\wedge}8)) / 9$	5037687	$((-1 - 2^*(3^4 * 5 - 6^{\wedge}7)) - 8)^*9$
3228504	$-1 * (2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6)^*(7 - 89)$	5037705	$(1 - 2^*(3^4 * 5 - 6^{\wedge}7) - 8)^*9$
3283200	$12^{\wedge}3 * 4 * 5^*((-6 - 7)^* - 8 - 9)$	5038336	$(1 / 2 - 3^{\wedge}(-4 - 5))^*(6 / (-7 + 8))^{\wedge}9$
3296475	$(1 - 2^{\wedge}(3^4))^*(5 - 6^*(7 + 8)^*9)$	5038416	$(((-1 + 2) - 3)^*(4^*5 - 6^{\wedge}7) - 8)^*9$
3298085	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge}(3^4))^*(5 - 6^*(7 + 8)^*9)$	5038648	$(1^*(2 - 3^{\wedge}(-4 - 5))^*6^{\wedge}7 - 8)^*9$
3374811	$(-1 - 2^*(3^4 * - 5^{\wedge}6 + 7) - 8)^*9$	5038814	$((1 - 2) + 3)^*((4 + 5) / 6^{\wedge}7 - 8 - 9)$
3375189	$(-1 + 2^*(3^4 * 5^{\wedge}6 + 7) + 8)^*9$	5038882	$((1 - 2) + 3)^*((- 4 - 5)^* - 6^{\wedge}7 + 8 + 9)$
3389137	$((-1 - 23^{\wedge}4) + 5)^*(- 6 - 7 + 8 / 9)$	5039280	$((1 - 2) + 3)^*(4^*5 + 6^{\wedge}7) + 8)^*9$
3435828	$((1 - 23)^{\wedge}4 + 5)^*(6 - 78 / - 9)$	5039360	$(1 / 2 + 3^{\wedge}(-4 - 5))^*(6 / (-7 + 8))^{\wedge}9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
5039991	$(-1+2*(3^4*5+6^7)+8)^9$	6834402	$(1+2+(3/45)^{(-6-7+8)})^9$
5040009	$((1+2*(3^4*5+6^7))+8)^9$	6834483	$(12+(3/45)^{(-6-7+8)})^9$
5044210	$(((-1+2^3)^{(4+5)-6}+7)/8+9)$	6908798	$((1+2)^{(3^4+5)}*(6+7)^{(-8+9)})$
5057208	$((((1-2)+3)^{(4^5+6^7)-8})^9)$	6918223	$((-1-(2-3^{(4^5)}))-6)/(7^8*9)$
5057352	$((((1-2)+3)^{(4^5+6^7)+8})^9)$	7111096	$(-12-3-(((4^5)^{6+7}-8)-9)/-9)$
5062634	$-1-((2+34)^*-5^6-(7+8))^9$	7111126	$12+3-(((4^5)^{6+7}-8)/-9)$
5062636	$1-((2+34)^*-5^6-(7+8))^9$	7171993	$-1-((23+4)^*-5^6-7)^*(8+9)$
5124217	$(-1-2*(3+4*(56-7^8)))/9$	7171995	$1-((23+4)^*-5^6-7)^*(8+9)$
5227322	$1-((23-4)^{(5-(6-7))+8})/-9$	7340014	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^{(5+6)}*7/8-9)$
5249495	$-1-((2/3+4)^*-5^6+7)^8*9$	7340050	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^{(5+6)}*7/8+9)$
5249497	$1-((2/3+4)^*-5^6+7)^8*9$	7433280	$(-1+(2/34)^{((-5-6)+7)})^8*9$
5273146	$(-1-(((2+3^4)^{(5+6-7)-8}))/-9)$	7433458	$(-1-(2/34)^{((-5-6)+7)})^8*9$
5311904	$-1+(2+3)^*(4^5*6^7)^*(8+9)$	7456528	$((-1-2*(3-4^{(5+6)}))-7)^8*9/9$
5311906	$1+(2+3)^*(4^5*6^7)^*(8+9)$	7572963	$((1+2)^{(3^4-5)}*(6^7+8)^9)$
5312618	$-1-((2+3)^*-4^5*6^7)^*(8+9)$	7619441	$((1-23^4)^{(5+6-7)+8})/9$
5314879	$-1+(2+3)^4*(5^6+7)^*(8+9)$	7874944	$(-1/((2+3)+4)+5^6)^7*8*9$
5314881	$1+(2+3)^4*(5^6+7)^*(8+9)$	7875056	$(-1/((2+3)+4)-5^6)^7*8*9$
5315583	$(-1-(2-3^4)^{5+6})^7*8-9$	7959921	$(-1-(23^4)^{(5+6-7)+8})/-9$
5363887	$(1+2*((3-4^5)^{6-78}))/9$	8045865	$((1+2)^*(3-4^5)^{6+78})/9$
5365348	$1^*-23*(4-5^6*((7+8)-9))$	8172120	$123*((4+5)^{6+7})/8+9$
5365532	$1^*23*(4-5^6-6^{((7+8)-9)})$	8199002	$((1-23)^{4^5+6})^7^{(-8+9)}$
5508216	$((1+2)^{(3+4)}*-5+6)^7*8*9$	8201243	$-1-2*(3-45^{(-6-7-(-8-9))})$
5514264	$((1+2)^{(3+4)}*5+6)^7*8*9$	8201244	$-1^*2*(3-45^{(-6-((7-8)-9))})$
5622479	$-1-(-2+3+4)^*(-5^6+7)^8*9$	8201245	$1-2*(3-45^{(-6-7-(-8-9))})$
5622481	$1-(-2+3+4)^*(-5^6+7)^8*9$	8201255	$-1+2*(3+45^{(-6-7-(-8-9))})$
5740816	$((1+2^3)^{4-5})^{(-6+7-8+9)}$	8201256	$1^*2*(3+45^{(-6-((7-8)-9))})$
5788836	$((1-2^3)^{4+5})^{(-6+7-8+9)}$	8201257	$1+2*(3+45^{(-6-7-(-8-9))})$
5835554	$-1/23*((4-(5+6))-7-8^9)$	8387198	$1^*-2*(3-(4^{(5+6)}-78^9))$
5845844	$(1+2)^{(3^4)}*(5+6)-7^{(-8+9)}$	8387210	$1^*2*(3+4^{(5+6)}-78^9)$
5971759	$((1+2)*((3^4)^{5-6}-7)^8-9)$	8387356	$1^*-2*(3-(4^{(5+6)}-7^8*9))$
5971942	$(-1+2*((3^4)^{(5-(6-7))-8})-9)$	8387368	$1^*2*(3+4^{(5+6)}-7^8*9)$
5971950	$(-1+2*(3^4)^{(5-6+7)-8})-9$	8387594	$1^*-2*(3-4^{(5+6)}-7^8*9)$
5971994	$1+2*((3^4)^{(5-(6-7))+8})+9$	8387606	$1^*2*(3+4^{(5+6)}-7^8*9)$
5972177	$((-1-2)*((3^4-4)^{5-6+7})^8+9)$	8389610	$1^*-2*(3-4^{(5+6)}-7^8*9)$
6013440	$(-1+(2/34)^{(-5-6+7)})^8*9$	8389622	$1^*2*(3-(-4^{(5+6)}-7^8*9))$
6013503	$(-1+(2/34)^{(-5-6+7)})^8*9$	8389848	$1^*-2*(3-(4^{(5+6)}+7^8*9))$
6013511	$-1-(2/34)^{(-5-6+7)}*-8*9$	8389860	$1^*2*(3+4^{(5+6)}+7^8*9)$
6013513	$1-(2/34)^{(-5-6+7)}*-8*9$	8390006	$1^*-2*(3-(4^{(5+6)}+78^9))$
6013521	$(1-(2/34)^{(-5-6+7)}*-8)^9$	8390018	$1^*2*(3+4^{(5+6)}+78^9)$
6013584	$(-1-(2/34)^{(-5-6+7)})^*-8*9$	8483616	$((-1-2)^{(3+4)+5})^6*7/((-8^9))$
6015436	$1/23^4*(5+6*(7^8-9))$	8502588	$(1/-2-3^{(4+5)}*6+7)^8*9$
6051600	$(123^4*5)^{(-6-(-7+8)-9)}$	8503524	$(1/-2-3^{(4+5)}*(6+7))^8*9$
6095239	$((1-2^*-3*(4^5)^6)/7+8)/9$	8522496	$((1+2)^{(3+4)+5})^6*7/(8^9)$
6291419	$1/2*(3^4*5+6)^7*8-9$	8607663	$123/4*((5+6^7-8)-9)$
6291493	$1/2*(3^4*5+6)^7*8+9$	8607909	$123/4*((-5+6^7)-8+9)$
6399982	$((1-2)+3)*((4^5)^{(6+7-8)-9})$	8608155	$123/4*((5+6^7)+8-9)$
6400018	$((1-2)+3)*((4^5)^{(6+7-8)+9})$	8608401	$123/4*((-5+6^7+8)+9)$
6469645	$(1+2*(3^4)^5)*(6+7)^{(-8+9)}$	8640632	$(1+(-2+3^4)^*5^6)^7*(-8+9)$
6480000	$1/2*(3^4*5)^{(-6-7-(-8-9))}$	8999998	$-1^*2+3^4-4*(5^6)^{(7+8-9)}$
6495752	$(1-2)/3*((4-(5+6)^7)-89)$	9000002	$1^*2+3^4-4*(5^6)^{(7+8-9)}$
6705342	$(-1-2^{(-3-4)+5})^6*(7-(8-9))$	9097452	$((1/-2+3)+4)^*(5^6*7-8^9)$
6716583	$((-1-2)*((3^4-4)^{5+6+7}-8))^9$	9098388	$((1/-2+3)+4)^*(5^6*7+8^9)$
6717744	$12^3*3^4*(5-6^{(7+8-9)})$	9112392	$-12*((3/-45)^{(-6-7)+8+9})$
6717948	$(1+2)*((-3-(4^5-6^7)^8)-9)$	9112608	$12*((3/45)^{(-6-7)+8+9})$
6718020	$(-1-2)*((-3+(4^5-6^7)^8)-9)$	9241074	$(((-1-(23+4))^{5-6})^*-7-8)/9$
6718908	$(1+2)*((-3+(4^5+6^7)^8)-9)$	9381969	$((1+2)^*(3-4^5))^{(-6+7-8+9)}$
6718980	$(-1-2)*((-3-(4^5+6^7)^8)-9)$	9436608	$((1-2)^{(3+4^5-6)}+7)^8*9$
6719184	$12^3*3^4*(5+6^{(7+8-9)})$	9437760	$((1+2)^{(3+4^5-6)}+7)^8*9$
6720345	$((1+2)*((3^4)^{5+6+7}+8))^9$	9492561	$((1+2)^*(3+4^5))^{(-6+7-8+9)}$
6811776	$(-1-2)*((3^4)^5*((6-7)/8-9))$	9512500	$((1+2/3)^{(-4-5)}*(-6-7+8))^9$
6834267	$(-12+(3/45)^{(-6-7)+8})^9$	9517144	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5-6^7)^*(-8-9)$
6834348	$(-1-2+(3/45)^{(-6-7+8)})^9$	9517492	$1^*-2*(3^4+(-5+6^7)^*(-8-9))$
6834356	$-1-(2-(3/45)^{(-6-7+8)})^9$	9518156	$1^*2*(3^4+(-5-6^7)^*(-8-9))$
6834357	$1*(2-(3/45)^{(-6-7+8)})^*-9$	9518504	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5+6^7)^*(8+9)$
6834363	$-12+(3/45)^{(-6-7)+8})^9$	9535320	$((1/2-3)^{4-5})^6*7/((-8+9))$
6834372	$(-1-2)+(3/45)^{(-6-7+8)}*9$	9562618	$-1-((2+34)^*-5^6-7)^*(8+9)$
6834373	$-1^*2-(3/-45)^{(-6-7+8)}*9$	9562620	$1-((2+34)^*-5^6-7)^*(8+9)$
6834377	$1^*2+(3/45)^{(-6-7+8)}*9$	9565819	$1^*2/3^{(-4^5+6)}-7^*(8+9)$
6834378	$1+2+(3/45)^{(-6-7+8)}*9$	9565820	$1+2/3^{(-4^5+6)}-7^*(8+9)$
6834387	$12+(3/45)^{(-6-7+8)}*9$	9566056	$-1-2/-3^{(-4^5+6)}-7^*(-8-9)$
6834393	$1*(2+(3/45)^{(-6-7+8)})^9$	9566057	$-1*(-2/3^{(-4^5+6)}-7^*(8+9))$
6834394	$1+(2+(3/45)^{(-6-7+8)})^9$	9745632	$(1-(2+3)^4)^*(-5^6-7/((-8-9))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
9801885	$(1/2 - 3^{(4+5)}) * (6 - 7 * 8^9)$	15067035	$((-1 + (2+3)^{(4+5)} * 6) / 7 + 8) * 9$
9802383	$(-1/2 - 3^{(4+5)}) * (6 - 7 * 8^9)$	15093225	$(1 - (2 * 3)^4)^{(-5+6-7+8)} * 9$
9838962	$((1 - 23)^4 + 5) * 6 * 7 * (-8+9)$	15117750	$((12 * 3)^4 + 56 + 78) * 9$
9919368	$12 * (3^{(4+5)} * 6 * 7 - 8^9)$	15139881	$(1 + (-2 * 3)^4)^{(5 * 6 / (7+8))} * 9$
9921096	$12 * (3^{(4+5)} * 6 * 7 + 8^9)$	15156689	$(-12 + (3+4) * (-5-6)^{7+8}) / -9$
9939048	$(1 + (2/34)^{-5+6}) * 7^{(-8+9)}$	15187416	$12 * (3^4 / 5^4 - 6 - 7)^{(-8+9)}$
10018750	$((1 + 2/3)^{-4+5}) * (6 + 7 - 8)^9$	15194304	$12 * 3^4 * (5^6 + 7)^{(-8+9)}$
10038075	$(-1/2 + 3^{(4+5)}) * (6 - 7 * 8^9)$	15380820	$((1 + (2+3)^{(4+5)}) - 6) * 7 / 8^9$
10038585	$(1/2 + 3^{(4+5)}) * (6 - 7 * 8^9)$	15487255	$((1 - 23)^4 + 5) * (67 + 8 / -9)$
10064574	$(1 - 2^{(-3-4)} + 5) * 6^{(7 - (8-9))}$	15597449	$(-1 + 2^{(3+4 * 5 - 6)}) * 7 * (8+9)$
10077501	$(-1 - 2) * (3 * -4 * (-5 + 6^7) + 8) + 9$	15597687	$(-1 - 2^{(3+4 * 5 - 6)}) * -7 * (8+9)$
10077891	$(1+2) * (3 * 4 * (5 + 6^7) + 8) - 9$	15615180	$12 * 3^{(4+5)} * (67 + 8 / -9)$
10090818	$(1+2^{(-3-4)} + 5) * 6^{(7 - (8-9))}$	15670471	$((1 * 23^4 - 5) - 6) * 7 * 8 - 9$
10157091	$((-1 - 2) \wedge (3 * 4 + 5) * 6) * 7 / -89$	15670489	$((1 * 23^4 - 5) - 6) * 7 * 8 + 9$
10251561	$1 / -2 * (3 - 45^{(6+7-8)} / 9)$	15671703	$((1 * 23^4 + 5) + 6) * 7 * 8 - 9$
10251564	$1 / 2 * (3 + 45^{(6+7-8)} / 9)$	15671721	$((1 * 23^4 + 5) + 6) * 7 * 8 + 9$
10253892	$(-1 + (2+3)^{(4+5)}) * 6 * 7 / 8 - 9$	15695487	$((1 - 23)^4 + 5) * 67^{(-8+9)}$
10253910	$(-1 + (2+3)^{(4+5)}) * 6 * 7 / 8 + 9$	15824928	$12 * (3^4 (4+5) * 67 - 8 - 9)$
10321920	$(1 - 2^{(-3-4-5)}) / (6+7) * 8^9$	15825120	$12 * (3^4 (4+5) * 67 + 8 - 9)$
10471356	$(-1 - 2^{(-3-4)} * 5) * (6 / (7-8)) \wedge 9$	15825144	$12 * (3^4 (4+5) * 67 - (8-9))$
10690675	$(-1/2 + 34^{(5+6-7)}) * 8 - 9$	15825336	$12 * (3^4 (4+5) * 67 + 8 + 9)$
10690683	$(1/2 + 34^{(5+6-7)}) * 8 - 9$	15903719	$((1 - 23)^4 + 5) * (67 - 8 / -9)$
10690693	$(-1/2 + 34^{(5+6-7)}) * 8 + 9$	16035084	$12 * 3^{(4+5)} * (67 - 8 / -9)$
10690701	$(1/2 + 34^{(5+6-7)}) * 8 + 9$	16124312	$(1 - (2 * 3)^{(4+5)}) / (67 / 8 - 9)$
10982835	$(1/2 - 3^{(4+5)}) * (-6 - 7 * 8) * 9$	16225353	$(1 + 2 * (3 + (4 * 5)^6)) / (7 + 8 / 9)$
10983393	$(1/2 + 3^{(4+5)}) * (-6 - 7 * 8) * -9$	16252927	$-1 + (2^{\wedge} - 3 - 4^{\wedge} (-5 - 6 + 7)) * 8^9$
11160254	$(1 - 2 + 3 * (4+5)^6) * 7^{(-8+9)}$	16252929	$1 + (2^{\wedge} - 3 - 4^{\wedge} (-5 - 6 + 7)) * 8^9$
11184829	$(-1 - 2 * 3 * (-4^{(5+6-7)} * 8) / 9)$	16384000	$1 * 2^{(-3+4 * 5)} * (6 - 7 * (-8 - 9))$
11184832	$(-1 - 2 + 3 * (-4^{(5+6-7)} * 8) / -9)$	16397639	$(-1 + 2^{(3+4)} / -5 * (6 - 7^8)) / 9$
11184840	$(-12 - 3 * (4^{(5+6+7)}) * 8 / -9)$	16754688	$12 * (-3^{\wedge} - 4 + 5) / 6^{\wedge} - 7 * (-8 + 9)$
11691548	$(-1 + 23) * ((4+5)^6 + 7 / (8-9))$	16776993	$1 + (2^{\wedge} - 3 - 4^{\wedge} (-5 - 6) * 7) / 8^{\wedge} - 9$
11712599	$-12 + ((3 - (-4 * 5 + 6)^7) - 8) / 9$	16777028	$12 / 3 * (4^{\wedge} (5+6) - 7 * 8 + 9)$
11712623	$12 + ((3 - (-4 * 5 + 6)^7) - 8) / 9$	16777404	$12 / 3 * (4^{\wedge} (5+6) - (-7 * 8 + 9))$
11753490	$(-1 + 23^4 + 5) * 6 * 7 * (-8 + 9)$	16777439	$-1 + (2^{\wedge} - 3 + 4^{\wedge} (-5 - 6) * 7) / 8^{\wedge} - 9$
11756920	$((12 * 3)^4 - 56) * -7 / (8 - 9)$	16837632	$12 * (3^{\wedge} - 4 + 5) / 6^{\wedge} - 7 * (-8 + 9)$
12011442	$123 / 4 * ((5 * (6 - 7))^8 - 9)$	16948224	$12 * (3^{\wedge} (4+5) - 67) * 8^9$
12301866	$(-1 - 2) * (3 - 45^{(-6 - ((7 - 8) - 9))})$	17064000	$12 * (-3^{\wedge} (4+5) - 67) * 8^9 - 9$
12301884	$(1+2) * (3 + 45^{(-6 - 7 + 8 + 9)})$	17173512	$((1+2) * (3^{\wedge} 4 + 5))^{\wedge} (-6 + (-7 + 8) * 9)$
12401589	$(1 - 2 * (3 - (4 * -5 + 6)^7)) / (-8 - 9)$	17301503	$-1 + (-2^{\wedge} - 3 - 4^{\wedge} (-5 - 6 + 7)) * -8^9$
12803125	$(-1 - 2^{(3 * 4)}) * -5^{\wedge} (6 - (-7 + 8) \wedge 9)$	17301505	$1 + (-2^{\wedge} - 3 - 4^{\wedge} (-5 - 6 + 7)) * -8^9$
12842064	$(1 - 2^{\wedge} - 3 + 45) * 6^{\wedge} 7^{(-8+9)}$	17499990	$-1 + (2+3) * 4 * 5^6 * 7 * 8 - 9$
12959988	$-12 + (3 * 4 * 5)^{\wedge} (-6 - 7 - (-8 - 9))$	17499992	$1 + (2+3) * 4 * 5^6 * 7 * 8 - 9$
12959997	$(-1 - 2) + (3 * 4 * 5)^{\wedge} (-6 - 7 - (-8 - 9))$	17926389	$1 / (-2 - 3) * (-4^{\wedge} (5+6) - 7^{\wedge} 8) * 9$
12959998	$-1 * 2 + (3 * 4 * 5)^{\wedge} (-6 - 7 - (-8 - 9))$	18285715	$(-1 + 2 * (3 + (4 * 5)^6)) * 7^{\wedge} (8 - 9)$
12960002	$1 * 2 + (3 * 4 * 5)^{\wedge} (-6 - 7 - (-8 - 9))$	18423252	$(1/2 - 3^{\wedge} (4+5) * (6+7)) * -8^9$
12960003	$1 + 2 + (3 * 4 * 5)^{\wedge} (-6 - 7 - (-8 - 9))$	18423324	$(1/2 - 3^{\wedge} (4+5) * (6-7)) * 8^9$
12960012	$12 + (3 * 4 * 5)^{\wedge} (-6 - (7 - 8 - 9))$	18600393	$((1+2)^{\wedge} (3 * 4) * -5 + 6) * -7^{\wedge} (-8 + 9)$
12991418	$1 * 2 * -3 * (4 + ((-5 - 6)^7 + 8) / 9)$	18874116	$(1/2 + 3) * (4^{\wedge} (5+6) / -7 + 8) * -9$
12991456	$-1 * 2 * 3 * ((4 - (5+6)^7) - 8 - 9)$	18874620	$(1/2 + 3) * (4^{\wedge} (5+6) / 7 + 8) * 9$
13227018	$((-1 + 23 - 4)^{5+6}) / 7^{\wedge} (8 - 9)$	19173856	$(1 - 23 * 4^{\wedge} (-5 - 6)) / 7 * 8^9$
13392847	$(-1 + (2+3)^{(4+5)} * 6) / 7 * 8 - 9$	19478257	$1 / 23 * ((4 * 5)^6 * 7 - 89)$
13392865	$(-1 + (2+3)^{(4+5)} * 6) / 7 * 8 + 9$	19595486	$1 * 2 * (((-3 - 4) * -5 * 6^{\wedge} 7 - 8) - 9)$
13671840	$((1 + (2+3)^{(4+5)}) - 6) * -7 / (8 - 9)$	19595554	$1 * 2 * (((3 + 4) * 5 * 6^{\wedge} 7 + 8) + 9)$
13671924	$(1 + (2+3)^{(4+5)} + 6) * 7 / (-8 + 9)$	19834416	$1 * 2 * (3^{\wedge} (4+5) - 6) * 7 * 8^9$
13751208	$(-1 + 23 * ((4+5)^6 + 7) / 8) * 9$	19846512	$1 * 2 * (-3^{\wedge} (4+5) - 6) * 7 * 8^9 - 9$
13751226	$(-1 - 23 * ((4+5)^6 + 7) / 8) * -9$	20038500	$((1+2)^{\wedge} (-3 - 4) + 5^{\wedge} - 6) * (7+8) \wedge 9$
13835472	$(-1 - 2) * (3 - (-4/5 * (6 - 7^8) - 9))$	20256546	$(-1 - (2 * 3)^4) * (-5^{\wedge} 6 - 7 / (8 - 9))$
13934802	$((1+23)^4 + 5) * 6 * 7 * (-8 + 9)$	20312499	$-1 - (2+3) * 4 * 5^6 * (7 - 8 * 9)$
14045094	$(-12 + 3^{\wedge} (4+5)) * 6 * 7 * (8+9)$	20312501	$1 - (2+3) * 4 * 5^6 * (7 - 8 * 9)$
14053662	$(-1+2) * 3^{\wedge} (4+5) * 6 * 7 * (8+9)$	20692800	$(-1 + 2 + 3 * (4 * 5)^6 - 7^8) / 9$
14062230	$(-12 - 3^{\wedge} (4+5)) * 6 * 7 * (-8 - 9)$	20903346	$1 * 2 * -3^{\wedge} (4+5) * (-67 + 8) * 9$
14198569	$-1 + (2/34)^{-5} * ((6-7)^8 + 8 + 9)$	20984255	$-1 + ((2 - 3^4) * -5^{\wedge} 6 - 7) * (8 + 9)$
14198571	$1 + (2/34)^{-5} * ((6-7)^8 + 8 + 9)$	20984257	$1 + ((2 - 3^4) * -5^{\wedge} 6 - 7) * (8 + 9)$
14222213	$(1 - 2 * (3 - (4 * 5)^6) - 78) / 9$	21017706	$(12 * 3^{\wedge} (4+5) - 6 * 7) * 89$
14222239	$(1 - 2 * ((3 - (4 * 5)^6) - 78)) / 9$	21025182	$(12 * 3^{\wedge} (4+5) + 6 * 7) * 89$
14403561	$-1 / 23 * (4 + (5+6)^7) * (-8 - 9)$	21333242	$(1 - 2) / -3 * ((4 * 5)^6 - 7) - 89$
14680045	$1 / 2 * ((-3 + 4^{\wedge} (5+6)) * 7 - 8 - 9)$	21333259	$(1 - 2) / -3 * ((4 * 5)^6 - 7) - 8 * 9$
14680053	$-1 / 2 * ((-3 + 4^{\wedge} (5+6)) * -7 - (8 - 9))$	21333314	$((-1 + 2) / 3 * ((4 * 5)^6 - 7) - 8) - 9$
14680075	$1 / 2 * ((-3 - 4^{\wedge} (5+6)) * -7 - (8 - 9))$	21333326	$((12 + 3 * (4 * 5)^6) - 78) / 9$
14680083	$1 / 2 * ((3 + 4^{\wedge} (5+6)) * 7 + 8 + 9)$	21333348	$(1 - 2) / -3 * ((4 * 5)^6 - 7) + 8 + 9$
14913088	$((1 + 2^{\wedge} ((3 - 4 + 5) * 6) + 7) * 8 / 9)$	21333358	$(-12 + 3 * ((4 * 5)^6 + 78)) / 9$
15066891	$((-1 + (2+3)^{(4+5)} * 6) / 7 - 8) * 9$	21333373	$(-1 + 2) / 3 * ((4 * 5)^6 - 7 * (-8 - 9))$

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21333403	$(1-2)/-3*((4*5)^6-7)+8*9$	28760944	$1/2*(-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6))/-7*8^{\wedge}9$
21333420	$(1-2)/-3*((4*5)^6-7)+89$	28904961	$((123+4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)+8)/9$
21375503	$-1-((23-4)^{-5\wedge 6-7})^*8*9$	29177758	$1/23*(4+5*(-6*7+8^{\wedge}9))$
21375505	$1-((23-4)^{-5\wedge 6-7})^*8*9$	29177767	$1/23*(-4-5*(6-7-8^{\wedge}9))$
21381360	$1+(2*34)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)-(8+9)$	29360243	$1+(2*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7-8*-9$
21455612	$12+(3-4*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8/9$	29360380	$(12*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
21463459	$123*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	30941676	$12*3^{\wedge}(4+5)*(6*7+89)$
21523360	$(1/2*((3*(4+5))^{\wedge}6+7)-8)/9$	31179469	$1/(2+3)*((4-(5+6)^{\wedge}7)*-8+9)$
21523361	$(1/2*((3*(4+5))^{\wedge}6-7)+8)/9$	31457253	$1/2*((3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*(-7-8)-9)$
22020042	$1*2*-3*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)*7/8+9)$	31457262	$1/2*((-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*(7+8)+9)$
22020150	$1*2*3*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)*7/8+9)$	31457298	$1/2*((3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*(7+8)-9)$
22106570	$((1*-23^{\wedge}4+5)+6)*(-7-8*9)$	31457307	$1/2*((-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*(-7-8)+9)$
22320312	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3*4)-5)^*-6*7/(8-9)$	31487583	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3*4)-5)^*6*(7/8+9)$
22394628	$1*2*(-3^{\wedge}4-5*(-6^{\wedge}7*8+9))$	31489652	$-1/23*(4-(5*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9))$
22394722	$1*2*(-34-5*(-6^{\wedge}7*8+9))$	31999995	$1/2*(-3+(4*5)^{\wedge}6-7*(-8+9))$
22395038	$1*2*(34+5*(6^{\wedge}7*8+9))$	32285025	$1*2*(-3^{\wedge}((4+5)+6)+7)/-8*9$
22395132	$1*2*(3^{\wedge}4+5*(6^{\wedge}7*8+9))$	32400000	$(-1-2^{\wedge}-3)^*(4*-5)^{\wedge}(6+7-8)*9$
22500503	$-1+((-2-3)^*-4/5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8*9$	32896842	$(1+2*((3+4*5)^{\wedge}6-78))/9$
22500505	$1+((-2-3)^*-4/5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8*9$	33045740	$1/2*((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7)-8)/9$
23425222	$1*2*((3-(4*-5+6)^{\wedge}7)-8)/9$	33299770	$((1*23^{\wedge}4-5)-6)^*-7*(-8-9)$
23436780	$-12*(3*4*5+((-6-7)+8)^{\wedge}9)$	33480762	$(1+(-2/3-(4+5)^{\wedge}6)*-7-8)*9$
23438220	$12*(3*4*5-((-6-7)+8)^{\wedge}9)$	34588600	$1*2*(-3^{\wedge}4+5)+6*(7^{\wedge}8-9)$
23887859	$(1/2-(3*4)^{\wedge}(5-6+7))^*-8-9$	34589012	$1*-2*(-3^{\wedge}4+5)-6*(-7^{\wedge}8-9)$
23887885	$(1/2+(3*4)^{\wedge}(5-6+7))^*8+9$	35013274	$1/23*(-4^{\wedge}5-6*(7-8^{\wedge}9))$
23914764	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3*4)*5+6)-7-8)^*9$	35156178	$((1-2)+3)*(-4+5^{\wedge}(-6+7+8))^*9$
23914926	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3*4)*5-6)+7+8)^*9$	35156322	$((1-2)+3)*(-4-5^{\wedge}(-6+7+8))^*-9$
24299990	$(-1-(-2/3*45)^{\wedge}(6+7-8)-9)$	35555564	$(1+(2+3)*((4*5)^{\wedge}6+7)+8))/9$
24299992	$1-((2/-3*45)^{\wedge}(6+7-8)+9)$	35555599	$(1+(2+3)*((4*5)^{\wedge}6+78))/9$
24300008	$-1+(2/3*45)^{\wedge}(6+7-8)+9$	35606882	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3*4)+5)*67/(-8+9)$
24300010	$1+(2/3*45)^{\wedge}(6+7-8)+9$	35826264	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)+(-5-6)*7*8*9$
24375008	$-1+(2+3)*4*5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9$	35828238	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)-5*6*7*(8+9)$
24375010	$1+(2+3)*4*5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9$	35829846	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)-(5*6*7+8)*9$
25110351	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3*4)-5)^*6*7/8*9$	35829990	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)+(5*6*-7+8)*9$
25165338	$1*2*(-3*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+78)-9)$	35830368	$((-1+2*((3*4)^{\wedge}5-6))-7)^*8*9$
25165374	$1*-2*(3*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+78)-9)$	35833248	$((1+2*((3*4)^{\wedge}5+6))+7)^*8*9$
25165604	$1*2*(-3*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)-89)$	35833626	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)-(5*6*-7+8)*9$
25165757	$1*2*(-3*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)-8)-9$	35833770	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)+(5*6*7+8)*9$
25165772	$1*2*3*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-78/9)$	35835378	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)-5*6*7*(-8-9)$
25165876	$1*2*3*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+78/9)$	35837352	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)-(-5-6)*7*8*9$
25165891	$1*-2*(-3*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)-8)+9$	36665567	$1/23*((-4*5+6)^{\wedge}7*-8+9)$
25166044	$1*-2*(-3*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)-89)$	36962022	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3+4*5))^*6*(7*8-9)$
25166274	$1*2*(3*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+78)-9)$	36962586	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3+4*5))^*6*(-7*8+9)$
25166310	$1*-2*(-3*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+78)-9)$	38347936	$(1*2-3/-4^{\wedge}(5+6))/7*8^{\wedge}9$
25194160	$((-1+23)-4)*5*(6^{\wedge}7-8/9)$	38706521	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}((-4+5)+6)*(7*8-9)$
25194320	$((-1+23)-4)*5*(6^{\wedge}7+8/9)$	38880000	$(1+2)*(3*4*5)^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9))$
25200000	$((1+2^{\wedge}-3)^*(4*-5)^{\wedge}(6+7-8)*9)$	40292352	$((1-2)+3)*(-4^{\wedge}5+6^{\wedge}7*8)*9$
25411681	$(1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5))^{\wedge}((-6-7)+8+9)$	40308588	$12*3*(4*(-5+6^{\wedge}7)-8)-9)$
25445504	$1/(2/(-3-4)-5)*(-6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$	40309688	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}(-4-5))/6^{\wedge}-7)^*8*9$
25508760	$(-1+2/3*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7))^*8*9$	40309751	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}(-4-5))/6^{\wedge}-7*8)*9$
25508832	$1*2/3*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8*9$	40309769	$(1-(-2+3^{\wedge}(-4-5))/6^{\wedge}-7*8)*9$
25508904	$(1+2/3*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7))^*8*9$	40309832	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}(-4-5))/6^{\wedge}-7)^*8*9$
25593743	$(-1-234*-5^{\wedge}6)^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	40310523	$((-1-2)*((3*4)^{\wedge}5*-6+7)-8)*9$
25907505	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3*4)-5)^*6*(-7/8+9)$	40311045	$((1+2)*((3*4)^{\wedge}5*6+7)+8)*9$
25982897	$(-1-2-3*(4*(-5-6)^{\wedge}7-8))/9$	40311736	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}(-4-5))/6^{\wedge}-7)*-8*9$
26034048	$((-1+23)*4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7/(-8+9)$	40311799	$(-1+(2+3^{\wedge}(-4-5))/6^{\wedge}-7*8)*9$
26097889	$-1*(23-4^{\wedge}(5+6)*7*8)/9$	40311817	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}(-4-5))/6^{\wedge}-7*8)*9$
26097929	$(1-(-2*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7*8)/9$	40311880	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}(-4-5))/6^{\wedge}-7)^*8*9$
26584420	$(1*23^{\wedge}4-5)*((6+7)*8-9)$	40312980	$12*3*(4*((5+6^{\wedge}7)+8)+9)$
26585370	$(1*23^{\wedge}4+5)*((-6-7)*-8-9)$	40329216	$((1-2)+3)*(-4^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7*8)*-9$
26873409	$(1+2+3*-4*(5-6^{\wedge}7))^*8+9$	40500503	$-1-((2+34)^*-5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8*9$
26874303	$(-1-2-3*-4*(5+6^{\wedge}7))^*8-9$	40500505	$1-((2+34)^*-5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8*9$
26937507	$(12^{\wedge}3-4)/5^{\wedge}6-7/(-8+9)$	40608216	$((1/2+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7/(-8+9)$
26993095	$-12^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6)+7^{\wedge}8(-8+9)$	40773833	$-1-((2-3^{\wedge}4)^*-5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)*9$
27062500	$(12^{\wedge}3+4)*5^{\wedge}6/(-7+8)^{\wedge}9$	40773835	$1-((2-3^{\wedge}4)^*-5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)*9$
27427936	$(1/2-(3/4)^{\wedge}(5+6)*7)^*8^{\wedge}9$	41925625	$((-1+(2*3)^{\wedge}4)*5)^{\wedge}(-6+7-8+9)$
28133568	$(12*3)^{\wedge}4*((-5+6)^{\wedge}7)/8+9$	42055225	$((-1-(2*3)^{\wedge}4)*5)^{\wedge}(-6+7-8+9)$
28268892	$1*2*(-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8)*9$	42666572	$-1+2/3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7)-89$
28269000	$1*-2*(-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8)*9$	42666573	$1*2/3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7)-89$
28444440	$1/2*((-3+(4*5)^{\wedge}6)-7)^*8/9$	42666574	$1+2/3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7)-89$
28444452	$(-1/2*(-3-(4*5)^{\wedge}6)+7)^*8/9$	42666589	$-1-2/-3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7)-8*9$
28697576	$1*2*(3^{\wedge}((4+5)+6)+7*(-8-9))$	42666590	$1*2/3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7)-8*9$
28698052	$1*2*(3^{\wedge}((4+5)+6)-7*(-8-9))$	42666591	$1-(-2/3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7)+8*9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
42666644	$-1 - (-2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8) - 9$	56888992	$((-123 - (4^5)^6) + 7) * -8/9$
42666645	$1 * (2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) - 8) - 9$	57395509	$(12/3 * (-4^5 + 6) + 7 * (-8 - 9))$
42666646	$1 + 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) - (8 + 9)$	57395621	$(12/3 * (-4^5 + 6) + 7 * (-8 - 9))$
42666675	$1 * 2/3 * (((4^5)^6 + 7) - 8) + 9$	57395635	$12/3 * (-4^5 + 6) - 7 * (-8 - 9)$
42666678	$-1 + 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8 + 9$	57395747	$12/3 * (-4^5 + 6) - 7 * (-8 - 9)$
42666680	$1 + 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8 + 9$	57521876	$-12 + (-3 - 4 * (-5 - 6)) / -7 * 8^9$
42666733	$-1 - 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8 * 9$	57521890	$1 * 2 + (-3 - 4 * (-5 - 6)) / -7 * 8^9$
42666734	$1 * 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8 * 9$	57521900	$12 + (-3 - 4 * (-5 - 6)) / -7 * 8^9$
42666735	$1 - (-2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) - 8 * 9)$	57671680	$(1/2 + 3 * (4 + 5)) * -6^{\wedge} - 7) * 8^9$
42666745	$-1 - 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7 * (-8 - 9))$	58720207	$(-1 + 2 * (3 + 4 * 5) - 6) * 7^{\wedge} (-8 + 9)$
42666746	$1 * 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7 * (-8 - 9))$	58724351	$-1 + (2 * 3 * -4) * 5 * ((6 + 7) / 8 - 9)$
42666747	$1 - 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7 * (-8 - 9))$	58724353	$1 + (2 * 3 * -4) * 5 * ((6 + 7) / 8 - 9)$
42666750	$-1 + 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 89$	58786602	$((12 * 3) * 4 * 5 + 6) * 7^{\wedge} (-8 + 9)$
42666751	$1 * 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 89$	62208000	$1 * 2 * (3 * 4) * 5 * (6 - 7 * (-8 - 9))$
42666752	$1 + 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 89$	63037440	$12^{\wedge} (3 + 4) * (5/6 + 7 + 8) / 9$
42981136	$((12 - 3) * 4 - 5) * (-6 + 7 - (8 - 9))$	63986946	$(1 + 2 * (3 * 4)) * 5 * 6 + 7 / (8 - 9)$
43112356	$((12 - 3) * 4 + 5) * (-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$	64001728	$12^{\wedge} 3 + (4 * 5) * 6 / (-7 + 8) * 9$
43141428	$(12 * 3 - 4 * (5 + 6)) / 7 * 8 * -9$	64044304	$(1 + 2 * (3 * 4)) * 5 * (6 + 7) * 8^{\wedge} (-8 + 9)$
44040084	$1/2 * -3 * (-4 * (5 + 6) * 7 + 8 * 9)$	64366832	$(1 + 2) * ((3 - 4 * 5) * 6 - 7) * 8 / 9$
44040300	$1/2 * -3 * (-4 * (5 + 6) * 7 - 8 * 9)$	65628948	$(12 - 3 * 4 * 5 * (-6 - 7) + 8) / 9$
45068891	$(-1 - 2 * 3 * 4) * (5 - 6 * 7) * 8^{\wedge} (-8 + 9)$	67092480	$(-1/2 + (3 + 4 - 5) * (-6 - 7)) / -8^{\wedge} - 9$
46229303	$((-1 + 2 + 3 * 4) * 5 * 6 - 7) - 8) / 9$	67108740	$1 * 2 * ((3 - (-4 * (5 + 6) + 7) * 8) - 9)$
46469376	$(-1 - 2 * -3 * 4 + 5) * 6 * 7 * 8^{\wedge} (-8 + 9)$	67108764	$1 * 2 * ((-3 + (4 * (5 + 6) - 7) * 8) + 9)$
47535366	$1 * 2/3 * (-4 * (5 + 6) + 7) * (8 + 9)$	67108964	$1 * 2 * ((3 + (4 * (5 + 6) + 7) * 8) - 9)$
47706649	$(12^{\wedge} 3 * 4 - 5) * (-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$	67108988	$-1 * 2 * ((3 - (4 * (5 + 6) + 7) * 8) - 9)$
47844889	$(12^{\wedge} 3 * 4 + 5) * (-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$	67125248	$(1/2 + (3 + 4 - 5) * (-6 - 7)) / 8^{\wedge} - 9$
49207464	$-12 * (3 - 4 * 5 * (-6 - 7) + 8 + 9)$	68023233	$(-1 - 2) * 3 * 4 * (5 - 6 * 7) * 8^{\wedge} (-8 + 9)$
49207536	$12 * (3 + 4 * 5 * (-6 - 7) + 8 + 9)$	68025663	$(1 + 2) * 3 * 4 * (5 + 6 * 7) * 8^{\wedge} (-8 + 9)$
49345305	$((1 + 2) * (3 + 4 * 5) * 6 + 7 + 8) / 9$	68359333	$((1 + 2 * 3 * 4) * 5 - 6) * 7^{\wedge} (-8 + 9)$
49777767	$-12 + ((3 - (4 * 5) * 6 * -7) + 8) / 9$	68681728	$(1/2 - 3 * -4 * (-5 - 6 + 7)) * 8^{\wedge} 9$
49777791	$12 + ((3 - (4 * 5) * 6 * -7) + 8) / 9$	70275610	$1 * 2/3 * ((4 * 5 - 6) * 7 - 8 - 9)$
49825048	$((1 - 2) + 3) * (4 * 5 - 6 * 7) * -89$	70312428	$(-1 * 2 * 3 + 4 * 5 * (-6 + 7) + 8) * 9$
49828568	$((1 - 2) + 3) * (-4 * 5 - 6 * 7 - 89)$	70312572	$(1 * 2 * 3 - 4 * -5 * (-6 + 7) + 8) * 9$
49828648	$((1 - 2) + 3) * (4 * 5 - 6 * 7 - 89)$	70544082	$((12 * 3) * 4 * 5) * 6 * 7 * (-8 + 9)$
49832168	$((1 - 2) + 3) * (4 * 5 + 6 * 7) * 89$	71614620	$(1 + (2 + 3) * (4 + 5)) * 6 * (7 - 8) / 9$
49994820	$(-1 + 2 * (-3 - 4)) * 5 * (6 / (7 - 8)) * 9$	71663589	$(1 + 2) * (3 * (-4 - 5) * 6 * (7 + 8) - 9)$
50782140	$(-1 - 2 * (-3 - 4)) * 5 * (6 / (7 - 8)) * 9$	71663643	$(1 + 2) * (3 * (-4 - 5) * 6 * (7 + 8) - 9)$
51414458	$-1 - ((2/3 - 4) * -5 * 6 - 7 * 8) * 9$	72279217	$(-1 + (2 * 3) * 4 / 5) * ((6 * 7 + 8) - 9)$
51414460	$1 - ((2/3 - 4) * -5 * 6 - 7 * 8) * 9$	72839087	$(-1 - (2 * 3) * 4 / 5) * ((-6 * 7 - 8) + 9)$
51824159	$-1 + (2 * 3 * (4 + 5) / -6 + 7 * 8) * 9$	73138167	$(-1 + 2 * (-3 + 4 * 5) * (6 + 7 * 8)) * 9$
51824161	$1 + (2 * 3 * (4 + 5) / -6 + 7 * 8) * 9$	73138185	$(1 + 2 * (-3 + 4 * 5) * (6 + 7 * 8)) * 9$
51848379	$((-1 - 2 * (3 + 4)) * 5 * 6 + 7 * 8) * 9$	73539117	$123 * ((4 + 5) * 6 + 7) / 8 * 9$
51853684	$-1/2 - (3 * (4 + 5) / 6 - 7 * 8) * 9$	73600000	$1 * 23 / (4 * 5) * 6 * (7 - 8 * 9)$
51853685	$1/2 - (3 * (4 + 5) / 6 - 7 * 8) * 9$	73618201	$(1 + 2 + 3 * (5 + 6) * 7 - 8) / 9$
51876594	$((1 + 2) * (-3 - (-4 - 5)) + 6 - 7 * 8) * -9$	74304400	$((12^{\wedge} 3 - 4) * 5) * (-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$
51876702	$((1 + 2) * (-3 - (-4 - 5)) - 6 - 7 * 8) * -9$	74352895	$(-12 + ((34 - 5) * 6 + 7) / 8) - 9$
51889716	$((1 + 2) * (-3 - (-4 - 5)) - 6 + 7 * 8) * 9$	74352913	$(-12 + ((34 - 5) * 6 + 7) / 8) + 9$
51889824	$((1 + 2) * (-3 - (-4 - 5)) + 6 + 7 * 8) * 9$	74352919	$12 - ((34 - 5) * 6 + 7) / -8 - 9$
51912733	$-1/2 + (3 * (4 + 5) / 6 + 7 * 8) * 9$	74352937	$12 - ((34 - 5) * 6 + 7) / -8 + 9$
51912734	$1/2 + (3 * (4 + 5) / 6 + 7 * 8) * 9$	74655361	$((1 - 2/3 * 4) * 5) * (-6 + 7) + 8) / 9$
51918039	$((1 + 2 * (3 + 4)) * 5 * 6 + 7 * 8) * 9$	74995600	$((12^{\wedge} 3 + 4) * 5) * (-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$
51942257	$-1 - (2 * 3 * (4 + 5) / -6 - 7 * 8) * 9$	75497196	$1 * -2 * (3 + (-4 * (5 + 6) + 7 + 8) * 9)$
51942259	$1 - (2 * 3 * (4 + 5) / -6 - 7 * 8) * 9$	75497208	$1 * 2 * (3 - (-4 * (5 + 6) + 7 + 8) * 9)$
51965759	$1 * 2/3 - 3 * 4 * ((-5 - 6) * 7 + 8) - 9$	75497448	$1 * 2 * (3 - (-4 * (5 + 6) - (7 - 8)) * 9)$
51965767	$-1 - 2 * 3 * 4 * ((-5 - 6) * 7 + 8) / 9$	75497496	$1 * -2 * (-3 + (-4 * (5 + 6) + 7 - 8) * 9)$
51965769	$1 - 2 * 3 * 4 * ((-5 - 6) * 7 + 8) / 9$	75497736	$1 * -2 * (3 + (-4 * (5 + 6) - (7 + 8)) * 9)$
52199316	$12 * 3 * (4 + 5) * (-6 - 7) * (-8 - 9)$	75497748	$1 * 2 * (3 - (-4 * (5 + 6) - (7 + 8)) * 9)$
52539458	$-1 - ((2/3 + 4) * -5 * 6 - 7 * 8) * 9$	75520512	$((-1 - 2) * 3 + 4 * 5) * 6 * (7 - 8 + 9)$
52539460	$1 - ((2/3 + 4) * -5 * 6 - 7 * 8) * 9$	75582686	$1 * 2 * ((3 * 4 * 5 * 6 * 7 - 8) - 9)$
52612524	$((1 + 2) * (3 * 4) * (5 + 6) - 7) - 8) * 9$	75582754	$1 * 2 * ((3 * 4 * 5 / 6 * 7 + 8) + 9)$
52612794	$((1 + 2) * (3 * 4) * (5 + 6) + 7) + 8) * 9$	77236092	$12 * -3 * (4 + 5) * (-6 * 7 * 8 + 9)$
53477376	$(1 - 2 * (-3 - 4)) * (5 + 6) * 7) * 8^{\wedge} 9$	78074896	$(1 - (23 - 4) * 5) * (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9)$
53687103	$(1 + 2) * (3 + 4 / (5 * 6) * (7 + 8 * 9))$	78434641	$((1 - 2/3 * 4) * 5) * (-6 + 7) + 8) / 9$
56401920	$-12 * (3 + 4) * (5/6 - (7 + 8)) / 9$	79560704	$((1/2 * 3) * 4 * (5) / -6 + 7) / 8^{\wedge} - 9$
56622051	$1/2 * 3 * (4 * (5 + 6) - 7 * 8) * 9$	80464104	$(-1 - 2 * (-3 - 4) + 5) * 6 * 7 * 8 * 9$
56622852	$1/2 * (3 * 4 * (5 + 6) - 7 * 8) * 9$	80707078	$1 * 2 * ((-3 - 4) * (5 + 6 - 7 * 8) + 9)$
56623050	$12 * (-3 - 4 * (5 + 6) + 7) / 8 * -9$	80707350	$1 * 2 * ((3 + 4) * (5 + 6 + 7 * 8) - 9)$
56623158	$12 * (-3 + 4 * (5 + 6) + 7) / 8 * 9$	81380210	$(-1 - ((-2 + 3) + 4) * (5 + 6)) * (-7 - 8) / 9$
56623356	$1/2 * (3 * 4 * (5 + 6) + 7 * 8) * 9$	81487620	$12 * 3 * (4 + 5) * (6 * 7 * 8 + 9)$
56624157	$1/2 * 3 * (-4 * (5 + 6) - 7 * 8) * -9$	84934008	$(1 - 2 * (-3 + 4 * 5)) * (6 - 7 * 8) * 9$
56824467	$(-1 + 2 * 3) * (-4 + 5 + 6) * (7 * 8 - 9)$	84935304	$(-1 - 2 * (-3 + 4 * 5)) * (6 - 7 * 8) * 9$
56888871	$-12 - (-3 + ((4^5)^6 - 7) * -8) / 9$	85333315	$1 / (2 * 3) * ((4^5)^6 - 7) * 8 - 9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
85333324	$1/2^3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7)^8 / 9$	103771278	$((1-2)+3) * (45^6 + 7^8)^9$
85333328	$12 * ((-3 + (4^5)^6 + 7) - 8) / 9$	103877010	$((1-2)+3) * (4^5 * 6 + 7^8)^9$
85333333	$1 / (2^3) * ((4^5)^6 - 7)^8 + 9$	104060401	$((1+23)^4 + 5)^{(-6-7-(-8-9))}$
86092731	$(-1 + 2/3^{\wedge}(-4^5 + 6) - 78)^9$	106789792	$(1/2 + (3/4)^{\wedge}(5+6)^7)^8 \wedge 9$
86092749	$(1 + 2/3^{\wedge}(-4^5 + 6) - 78)^9$	108000000	$12^3 * 4/5^{\wedge} - 6^*(- 7 + 8)^9$
86094135	$(-1 - 2/ - 3^{\wedge}(-4^5 + 6) + 78)^9$	109051882	$(-1 + 2^{\wedge}(3 + 4^5)) / 6^* 78 - 9$
86094153	$((1 + 2/3^{\wedge}(-4^5 + 6)) + 78)^9$	109051926	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge}(3 + 4^5)) / 6^* - 78 + 9$
86609648	$((12^3 + 4)^*(5+6)^{\wedge}7 - 8) / 9$	112533937	$((12^3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^* - 67 / (8-9)$
88219206	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3^4)^*((-5-6)^* - 7+89)$	112665492	$12^3 \wedge (4+5)^*(6^* 78+9)$
88874495	$-1 + ((-2-3^4)^* - 5^{\wedge}6 - 7)^8 * 9$	112884397	$(1-2) / 3^*((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8 \wedge 9$
88874497	$1 + ((-2-3^4)^* - 5^{\wedge}6 - 7)^8 * 9$	113777765	$-1 - 2^*(- 3 - ((4^5)^6 - 7)^8) / 9$
89163990	$(1 - 2^*(3 / - 4)^{\wedge}5) / 6^{\wedge}(7 - 8 - 9)$	113777766	$1^2 * (3 - ((4^5)^6 - 7)^8) / 9$
89478656	$1^2 / 3^*(4^{\wedge}((5+6) - 7) + 8^{\wedge}9)$	113777767	$1 + 2^*(3 + ((4^5)^6 - 7)^8) / 9$
89481216	$1^2 / 3^*(4^{\wedge}((5-6) + 7) + 8^{\wedge}9)$	113777784	$((1-2+3)^*(4^5)^6 + 7)^8 / 9$
90558030	$(1 + (2 - 3^4)^*(- 5 - 6)^{\wedge}7) / (8+9)$	114294784	$1^*(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^* - 5+6) / 7^8 \wedge 9$
90633012	$(1 + 2^*(- 3 - 4)^{\wedge}5 + (6+7)^{\wedge}8) / 9$	115043776	$1^2 * (- 3 - 4^{\wedge}(-5-6)) / - 7^* 8 \wedge 9$
90698319	$(-1 + (2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) + (-6-7)^8)^9$	115955712	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^6 - 7/8) / 9$
90698337	$(1 - (2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) - (6+7)^8)^9$	116319504	$(-1 - (2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^* - 67^* 8 / 9$
90699182	$-1 + ((2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6 - (7+8))^9$	117407744	$(1 - 2^{\wedge} - 3 - 4^{\wedge}(-5 - (-6+7)))^8 \wedge 9$
90699184	$1 - ((2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6 - 7 - 8)^9$	117473280	$(-1 + 2^{\wedge} - 3 - 4^{\wedge}(-5 - (-6+7)))^* - 8 \wedge 9$
90699200	$(-1 - ((-2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6 - 7 + 8)^9)$	119619434	$((-1 + (-2 - 3/4)^5) - 6)^*(- 7^{\wedge}8 + 9)$
90699202	$1 + ((2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6 + 7 - 8)^9$	120774888	$((1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^5 + 5)^6 \wedge 7^* 8^9$
90699326	$-1 + ((2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6 - (7-8))^9$	120931839	$(-1 - ((2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) / - 6 + 7)^8)^9$
90699328	$1 - ((2^3 - 3)^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6 + 7 - 8)^9$	120932109	$1^*(2 - (3^4)^{\wedge} - 5) / 6^{\wedge}(7 - 8 - 9)$
90699344	$-1 - ((2^3 - 3)^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6 - (7+8))^9$	120932448	$1^2 * (3 + 45 + 6^{\wedge}(-7 + 8 + 9))$
90699346	$1 + ((2^3 - 3)^{\wedge}(4+5) + 6 - 7 - 8)^9$	120932865	$(1 - ((-2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) / 6 - 7)^8)^9$
90700191	$(-1 + (2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) - (-6-7)^8)^9$	121089816	$((1 + 2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^5)^6 \wedge 7^* 8^9$
90700209	$(1 - (2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5) + (6+7)^8)^9$	121550625	$((-1-2)^*(- 3 - 4)^5)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8+9)$
91124990	$((-1 + (2/3^4)^{\wedge}6) - 7) / 8 - 9$	122070309	$-1/2^*(3 + 4 - 5^{\wedge}(6 - ((-7-8)+9)))$
91125010	$((-1 - (2/3^4)^{\wedge}6) - 7) / - 8 + 9$	122070312	$1/2^*(3 - (4 - 5^{\wedge}(6 - ((-7-8)+9))))$
91186370	$1^2 * ((3 - (4^* - 5 + 6))^{\wedge}7 - 8) / 9$	122070313	$-1/2^*(3 - (4 + 5^{\wedge}(6 - ((-7-8)+9))))$
91551065	$-1 + 2/ - 3^*((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8^{\wedge}9$	122070316	$1/2^*(3 + 4 + 5^{\wedge}(6 - ((-7-8)+9)))$
91551066	$-1^2 * 3^*((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8^{\wedge}9$	122923008	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^6 + 7/8) / 9$
91551067	$1 + 2/ - 3^*((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8^{\wedge}9$	123598305	$(1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^5 * 5/6^{\wedge} - 7^* 89$
92447964	$(1 + (2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^6 * (7+8/9)$	124475292	$12^* - 3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(- 67^* 8 + 9)$
93375503	$-1 + ((-2-3^4)^* - 5^{\wedge}6 + 7)^8 * 9$	125544735	$(1 + 2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^5 / 6^{\wedge} - 7^* 89$
93375505	$1 + ((-2-3^4)^* - 5^{\wedge}6 + 7)^8 * 9$	126128041	$(12^3 \wedge (4+5))^* - 6 + 7^* - 89$
95420416	$(1 + 2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^*(5-6)^7)^8 \wedge 9$	126129287	$(12^3 \wedge (4+5)^* 6 + 7)^8 \wedge 9$
95659370	$(1 - 2/3^{\wedge}(-4^5 + 6))^*(7-8-9)$	127998992	$((1-2)+3)^*((4^5)^6 - 7^* 8^9)$
95659390	$(-1 - 2/3^{\wedge}(-4^5 + 6))^*(7-8-9)$	127999762	$((1-2)+3)^*((4^5)^6 - 7^*(8+9))$
95869792	$(1 + (-2 - 3^4)^{\wedge}(-5-6)) / 7^8 \wedge 9$	127999953	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5)^6 - 7^* 8 + 9$
96059601	$(1 - (2+3)^4 * 4^5)^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9))$	128000047	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5)^6 + 7^* 8 - 9$
96457400	$1^2 * 3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7^* 8^9)$	128000238	$((1-2)+3)^*((4^5)^6 - 7^*(- 8 - 9))$
96467911	$1^2 * 3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7^* 8^9)$	128001008	$((1-2)+3)^*((4^5)^6 - 7^* - 8^9)$
96470073	$1^2 * 3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6) - (-7^* 8 + 9))$	128446560	$(1 - 23^4)^*(5^6 * (-7-8) - 9)$
96480584	$1^* - 23^*(- 4^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7^* 8^9)$	128447019	$1^* - 23^4 * (5^6 * (-7-8) - 9)$
98684252	$((-1 + 2^{\wedge} - 3/4)^{\wedge}5 + 6) / 7^8 \wedge 9$	128447478	$(-1 - 23^4)^*(5^6 * (-7-8) - 9)$
99089676	$(-1 + 2^{\wedge}(-3 + 4^5))^*(6 + 78)^9$	128705847	$(-1 + 2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^5)^*(6^{\wedge}7 - 8^{\wedge}9)$
99091188	$(1 + 2^{\wedge}(-3 + 4^5))^*(6 + 78)^9$	128726820	$12^3 \wedge (4+5)^*(67^* 8 + 9)$
99137219	$12^*((34-5)^6 - 7) / (8^9)$	128974847	$-1 + (2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^5 + 6 - 7) / - 8^{\wedge} - 9$
99462573	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3-4) + 5)^6 \wedge 7^* 89$	128974849	$1 + (2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^5 + 6 - 7) / - 8^{\wedge} - 9$
99555554	$(1^2 * (-3 + (4^5)^6 * 7) - 8) / 9$	129140112	$(1 + 2)^*((3^{\wedge}(4^*(5+6-7)) - 8) - 9)$
99851859	$(-1 + 2^{\wedge}(-3-4) + 5)^6 \wedge 7^* 89$	129140214	$(1 + 2)^*((3^{\wedge}(4^*(5+6-7)) + 8) + 9)$
99989640	$(-1 + 2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^5 / 6^{\wedge} - 7^* - 8^9$	129243849	$(1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^5 * (6^{\wedge}7 + 8^{\wedge}9)$
100442300	$(1 - (23+4)^{\wedge}5 + 6)^* - 7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	131009958	$-1 - ((2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^*(- 6 - 7) + 89)$
100442314	$(1 + (23+4)^{\wedge}5 - 6)^7 \wedge (-8+9)$	131009960	$1 - ((2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^*(- 6 - 7) + 89)$
100442384	$(1 - ((23+4)^{\wedge}5 + 6))^* - 7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	131010026	$(1 - (2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5)) / - 6^* 78 - 9$
100619424	$(-1 - (2^{\wedge}(-3-4) - 5))^6 \wedge 7^* 8^9$	131010070	$(1 + (2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5)) / 6^* 78 + 9$
100619568	$(1 + (-2^{\wedge}(-3-4) + 5))^6 \wedge 7^* 8^9$	131010136	$-1 + (2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+7)+89$
100770840	$1^2 * 2^3 * 45^*((6^{\wedge}7 - 8) - 9)$	131010138	$1 + (2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+7)+89$
100783080	$1^2 * 2^3 * 45^*((6^{\wedge}7 + 8) + 9)$	131079601	$((1+2)^3 * 34 + 5)^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9))$
100934352	$(-1 + (2^{\wedge}(-3-4) + 5))^6 \wedge 7^* 8^9$	131421530	$1^2 / - 3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7) + 8^{\wedge}9$
100934496	$(1 + (2^{\wedge}(-3-4) + 5))^6 \wedge 7^* 8^9$	131587452	$(12 + ((3+4)^5)^6 - 7)^8 / 9$
101564280	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^5 / 6^{\wedge} - 7^* - 8^9$	131780407	$(-1 + 2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(5/6^{\wedge} - 7 - 8^{\wedge}9)$
103655826	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5)^6 - 7^{\wedge}8)^9$	132030227	$-1 - (2+3)^4 * 5^{\wedge}6 + 7^* 8^{\wedge}9$
103761558	$(1 - 2)^3 * (45^6 - 7^{\wedge}8)^9$	132030229	$1 - (2+3)^4 * 5^{\wedge}6 + 7^* 8^{\wedge}9$
103762386	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5)^6 - 7^{\wedge}8)^9$	132182969	$(1 + 2^*(- 34 + 5)^6 + 78) / 9$
103765870	$((-1+2) - 3)^*(4 + (5^6 - 7^{\wedge}8)^9)$	132543621	$(1 + (-2-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^6) / 7 + 8^{\wedge}9$
103765886	$((1-2)+3)^*(4 - (5^6 - 7^{\wedge}8)^9)$	133534445	$(-12 - 3^{\wedge}(4^5 - 6)) / 7 + 8^{\wedge}9$
103766950	$((-1+2) - 3)^*(4 - (5^6 + 7^{\wedge}8)^9)$	133855689	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(5/6^{\wedge} - 7 - 8^{\wedge}9)$
103766966	$((1-2)+3)^*(4 + (5^6 + 7^{\wedge}8)^9)$	134177737	$(-1 - (2^3)^{\wedge}(-4 - (-5-6))) / 7 + 8^{\wedge}9$
103770450	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5 + 7^{\wedge}8)^9$	134212667	$((1+2)^{\wedge}((-3+4)+5) - 6)^* - 7 + 8^{\wedge}9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
134214212	$((1+2^{(3^4)})+5)^{-6/7+8^9}$	161243001	$((12^{(3^4)^5*6-7}-8)^9)^9$
134221244	$((1+2^{(3^4)})+5)^{6/7+8^9}$	161243271	$((12^{(3^4)^5*6+7}+8)^9)^9$
134222789	$((1+2)^{((-3+4)+5)-6})^{7+8^9}$	161244756	$12^{(((3^4)^5*6+7)+8)^9}$
134257719	$(1+(2^3)^{(-4-(-5-6))})/7+8^9$	162072566	$-1+(2^3)^{4^4*(5^6+7)^8-9}$
134557897	$(1-2^{(-3-4)})^{(5/6^{\wedge}-7+8^9)}$	162072568	$1+(2^3)^{4^4*(5^6+7)^8-9}$
134901011	$(12+3^{(4^5-6)})/7+8^9$	163555547	$((1+23^{(4^5)^6})^{-78})/9$
135633653	$((1^{\wedge}2+3)^{4-5^{\wedge}(6+7)}-8)/-9$	163555755	$(1+23^{((4^5)^6+78)})/9$
135633749	$(1-((2+3)^{4+5^{\wedge}(6+7)-8}))/-9$	163577730	$1/2^{*(-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))}^{*78-9}$
135633751	$(-1-(((2+3)^{4+5^{\wedge}(6+7)}+8)))/-9$	163577748	$1/2^{*(-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))}^{*78+9}$
135891835	$(-1+(2+3)^{4+5^{\wedge}6})/7+8^9$	163577964	$1/2^{*(-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))}^{*-78-9}$
136048879	$((1+2)^{3^4})^{\wedge}(5+6-7)-8-9$	163577982	$1/2^{*(-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))}^{*-78+9}$
136048913	$((1+2)^{3^4})^{\wedge}(5+6-7)-(-8-9)$	164392416	$12^{*-3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+78^*-9)}$
136405227	$-1+(2+3)^{4*5^{\wedge}6*7+8^9}$	165759048	$12^{*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6)^{*78^*9}}$
136405229	$1+(2+3)^{4*5^{\wedge}6*7+8^9}$	165805380	$(12^{*3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6})^{*78^*9}$
136676919	$(1+2^{(-3-4)})^{(5/6^{\wedge}-7+8^9)}$	165813804	$(-12^{*3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6})^{*78^*-9}$
137013926	$1^{*2/3^{(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)+8^9}}$	165860136	$12^{*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6)^{*78^*-9}}$
138575432	$(-1-2^{*(3+4^{*(-5-6)^{\wedge}7})})^{*8/9}$	167226768	$12^{*3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6-78^*-9)}$
139169737	$(-1-2^{(-3-4)^{*5}})^*(6^{\wedge}7+8^9)$	168643944	$12^{*3^{\wedge}(4+5)^{*6}7^{*(8+9)}}$
139460607	$-1+(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^{*5}-(6-7))/8^{\wedge}-9$	169810798	$-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^{*(5^6)^{\wedge}7-8^9}$
139460609	$1+(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^{*5}-(6-7))/8^{\wedge}-9$	169810800	$1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^{*(5^6)^{\wedge}7-8^9}$
139751479	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^{*5})^{*(6^{\wedge}7+8^9)}$	170666636	$-12-3^{((4^5)^6-7)^*-8/9}$
142222216	$((1/2-3)/(4^5)^{\wedge}6-7)^{*8/9}$	170666639	$(1-2)/-3^{((4^5)^6-7)^*8-9}$
142426116	$(12^{*3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*-6+7+8^9})^{*-9}$	170666646	$-1^{*2+3^{((4^5)^6-7)^*8/9}}$
142426260	$(12^{*3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6+7+8^9})^{*9}$	170666648	$(1+2)^{\wedge}-3^{((4^5)^6-7)^*8^*9}$
142767330	$(12^{*3})^{4^4*-5^{((6^{\wedge}-7-8)-9)}}$	170666650	$1^{*2+3^{((4^5)^6-7)^*8/9}}$
142767390	$(12^{*3})^{4^4*5^{((6^{\wedge}-7+8)+9)}}$	170666657	$(1-2)/-3^{((4^5)^6-7)^*8+9}$
145071161	$((1-2^{*34})/(-5-6)^{\wedge}-7-8)/9$	170666671	$(-1+(-2+3^{(4^5)^6+7})^8)/9$
145282608	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(3^4+5+6+7)/8^*-9$	171050991	$(-1+(2^{*34})^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^{*8-9}$
145732932	$12^{*-3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+7^*-89)}$	171051007	$(-1-(2^{*34})^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^{*-8-9}$
147105252	$12^{*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6)^{*7*89}}$	171051009	$(-1+(2^{*34})^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^{*8+9}$
147146370	$(12^{*3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6})^{*7*89}$	171051025	$(-1-(2^{*34})^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^{*-8+9}$
147153846	$(-12^{*3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6})^{*7*-89}$	171907950	$-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^{*(5^6)^{\wedge}7+8^9}$
147177728	$((-12-3)^4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)+8^9$	171907952	$1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^{*(5^6)^{\wedge}7+8^9}$
147194964	$12^{*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6)^{*7*-89}}$	172565664	$(1-(-2-3^{4^{\wedge}(-5-6)})/7)^{*8^9}$
147386295	$(-1-(2^3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(-6-7)/8)^{*9}$	173015040	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^{*(5-6^7)})^{*8^9}$
147386313	$(1+(2^{*-3})^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(-6-7)/8)^{*9}$	174334090	$((1^{*23^{\wedge}4-5}-6)^{*7*89})^{*8^9}$
148567284	$12^{*3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6-7^*-89)}$	174347796	$((1^{*23^{\wedge}4+5}+6)^{*7*89})^{*8^9}$
148995612	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^{*6/7*89})^{*8^9}$	176884389	$-1-2/-3^{((4^5)^6-7)+8^9}$
149291181	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)^{*6^{\wedge}7*89}$	176884390	$1^{*2/3^{((4^5)^6-7)+8^9}}$
149333331	$(1-(2-3^{(4^5)^6})^{*7-8})/9$	176884391	$1-(-2/3^{((4^5)^6-7)-8^9})^{*8^9}$
149333363	$(-1+2)/-3^{((4^5)^6+7-89)}$	177332766	$1/23^{(4-(-5^{(6+7)^8-9}))}$
149680467	$(1+2^{(-3-4)+5})^{*6^{\wedge}7*89}$	179158272	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)^{*(5-6^{\wedge}(-7-8+9))}$
150111504	$(12^{*(3-4^5)})^{\wedge}(-6+7-8+9)$	179159808	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)^{*(5+6^{\wedge}(-7-8+9))}$
150962176	$(-1-(2^{\wedge}-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6+7))))^{*-8^9}$	179263836	$1^{*2^{*(-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^8)^*9}}$
150976800	$12^{*3^{(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*8^*9)}}$	179263944	$1^{*-2^{*(-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^8)^*9}}$
150994296	$12^{*(3^{*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)-8}-9)}}$	180844908	$1/(2^{*-3})^{*(4-5^{\wedge}(6+7))}^{*8/9}$
150994548	$(1/2^{*(-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)})^{*-8^*9}$	181273498	$((1-2)+3)^{*(4^5+(-6-7)^8)/9}$
150994720	$12^{*3^{(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*8/9)}}$	186646083	$1/2^{*(-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^*89}$
150995168	$12^{*3^{(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*-8/9)}}$	186646215	$1/2^{*(-3+(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^*89)}$
150995340	$(1/2^{*(3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)})^{*8^*9}$	186646218	$-1/2^{*(-3-(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^*89)}$
150995592	$12^{*(3^{*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)+8})+9)}$	186646838	$1/2^{*(-3-(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^*89)}$
151013088	$12^{*-3^{*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*8^*9)}}$	186646841	$1/2^{*(3+(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*89)}$
151027712	$(1+2^{\wedge}-3+4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6+7)))^{*8^9}$	186646973	$1/2^{*(-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^*89}$
151519232	$(1+2^{\wedge}-3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))^{*8^9}$	187388721	$((1+2)^{*(34+5)})^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9))$
151649147	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3+4^5))^{*(6+7)^*89}$	189896760	$(1-2^{*3^{\wedge}(4+5)})^{*67^*-8^*9}$
151651461	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3+4^5))^{*(6+7)^*89}$	189906408	$(-1-2^{*3^{\wedge}(4+5)})^{*67^*-8^*9}$
151880976	$(12^{*(3+4^5)})^{\wedge}(-6+7-8+9)$	193155748	$-1^{*23^{(4-5^6)^{\wedge}((-7-8)+9)}}$
153051120	$(1-2^{*3^{\wedge}(4+5)})^{*6^{\wedge}7/(-8^*9)}$	193155932	$1^{*23^{(4-5^6)^{\wedge}((-7-8)+9)}}$
153058896	$(-1-2^{*3^{\wedge}(4+5)})^{*6^{\wedge}7/(-8^*9)}$	193710150	$12^{*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5+6)+7)/-8^*9}$
155551059	$(1-2)/-3^{((4^5)^6-7)+8^9}$	193710339	$12^{*(3^{\wedge}(4+5+6)+7)/8^*9}$
155897316	$1^{*2^{*((-3-4^{((-5-6)^{\wedge}7+8)+9)})}}$	194187264	$((-1+23)^4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)+8^9$
155897420	$1^{*2^{*((3+4^{((5+6)^{\wedge}7+8)+9)})}}$	195485764	$(1/2^{*((34+5)^6+7)-8})/9$
156204287	$-1+(2+3/4+5)^{*6^{\wedge}7*8^*9}$	195485765	$(1/2^{*((34+5)^6+7)+8})/9$
156204289	$1+(2+3/4+5)^{*6^{\wedge}7*8^*9}$	196440660	$((1^{*23^{\wedge}4-5}-6)^{*78^*9})^{*8^9}$
156587344	$1/(2^3)^{*(-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)/8^{\wedge}-9}$	196456104	$((1^{*23^{\wedge}4+5}+6)^{*78^*9})^{*8^9}$
158334976	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^{*(5^6-7)})/8^{\wedge}-9$	200278016	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^{*(56+7)})^{*8^9}$
159253120	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)^{*5^{(6^{\wedge}-7-8)/-9}}$	200802304	$(1/2^{*-3+4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6-7))})^{*-8^9}$
159563045	$((12^3)^{4-5})^{*(6+7)^*8-9}$	201293824	$(1/2^{*-3+4^{\wedge}(-5+6-7)})/8^{\wedge}-9$
159563511	$(12^3)^{4^4*(5-6^{(-7-8)})-9}$	201326184	$(-1-2/3^{(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)})^{*8^*9}$
159563529	$(12^3)^{4^4*(5-6^{(-7-8)})+9}$	201326328	$(1-2/3^{(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)})^{*8^*9}$
159563995	$((12^3)^{4+5})^{*((-6-7)^*-8-9)}$	201326480	$1/2^{*(-3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6)^7)/-8^{\wedge}-9}$
161241516	$12^{*((3^4)^5*6-7)-8)^9}$	201326704	$1/2^{*(-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)^7)/-8^{\wedge}-9}$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
201359360	$(1/2^* - 3 - 4^{\wedge}(-5+6-7))/-8^{\wedge}-9$	268995368	$((-1+2)-3)^*(-4^*5-(6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9))$
201850880	$(1/2^* - 3 - 4^{\wedge}(-5-(6-7)))^*-8^{\wedge}9$	271072978	$1^*-2^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*67-8^{\wedge}9)$
202375168	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5^*(6+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	278235754	$((-1-2+3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5+6)/7-8^{\wedge}9$
203450535	$1/(2^*3)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}(6+7)+89)$	279632896	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^*5/6^{\wedge}-7+8^{\wedge}9)$
204067503	$(1+2)^{\wedge}((-3+4)+5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-8)-9$	286331153	$(1+2^{\wedge}34-5)/6/((-7+8)+9)$
204067521	$(1+2)^{\wedge}((-3+4)+5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-8)+9$	294617088	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)/5^*(6^*7-8/9)$
204079167	$(1+2)^{\wedge}((-3+4)+5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8)-9$	295157813	$1/(2+3)^*(4-(5+6+7))^{\wedge}8+9)$
204079185	$(1+2)^{\wedge}((-3+4)+5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8)+9$	296358912	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5/6^*-7/8+9)$
208973710	$(12^*3+4^{\wedge}(5-6))^*(7^{\wedge}8-9)$	296515042	$1^*2^*((3+4)^{\wedge}(5+6)/7-8^{\wedge}9)$
210937257	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3^*(4^*5^{\wedge}((-6+7)+8)-9)$	298666726	$1^*2/-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6^*-7-89)$
210937743	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3^*(4^*5^{\wedge}(-6+7+8)+9)$	301989327	$(-1-(2/3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*8)^*9$
211631606	$-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+7+8)-9$	301989372	$(1/(2^*-3)-(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7))^*8^*9$
211631608	$1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+7+8)-9$	301989396	$(1/(2^*-3)-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*-8^*9$
214958080	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(5+6)^*7^*8^{\wedge}9$	301989441	$(1-(2/-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*8)^*9$
214990695	$(-1+(-2+(3^*4)^{\wedge}(5-6+7))^*8)^*9$	301990335	$(-1-(2/3-(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7))^*8)^*9$
214990835	$1/2^*((3^*4)^{\wedge}(56/7)-8)-9$	301990380	$(1/(2^*-3)+(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7))^*8^*9$
214990861	$1/2^*((3^*4)^{\wedge}(56/7)+8)+9$	301990404	$(1/(2^*-3)-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*-8^*9$
214991001	$(1+(-2-(3^*4)^{\wedge}(5-6+7))^*-8)^*9$	301990449	$(1-(2/3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^*8)^*9$
216855351	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5/6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	303749375	$-1^*(2+3)^{\wedge}4+(5^*6)^{\wedge}7/(8^*9)$
220320000	$((-12-3)^*4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)^*(8+9)$	305175763	$1^*-2^*((-3-(-4+5^{\wedge}(6+7)))^{\wedge}8+9)$
226491408	$1^*2^*(3^*4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*8)^*9$	305175765	$1^*-2^*((-3-4-5^{\wedge}(6+7))^{\wedge}8+9)$
226493424	$1^*2^*(3^*4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^*8)^*9$	305175799	$1^*2^*((3-4+5^{\wedge}(6+7))^{\wedge}8+9)$
229582488	$(-1-2/-3^{\wedge}(-4^*5+6))^*(7-(-8-9))$	305175801	$1^*2^*((3+4+5^{\wedge}(6+7))^{\wedge}8+9)$
229582536	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}(-4^*5+6))^*(7-(-8-9))$	306377603	$12^*((-3-4)^*5)^{\wedge}6-7/(8^*9)$
234880671	$(-1-(2^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7)^*8-9$	311794694	$1^*2^*((-3^*4+(5+6)^{\wedge}7)^*8)-9$
234880687	$(1+(-2^*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7)^*8-9$	311794706	$1^*2^*((-3/4+(5+6)^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$
234880689	$(-1-(2^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7)^*8+9$	311794766	$1^*2^*((-3/4-(5+6)^{\wedge}7)^*-8+9)$
234880705	$(1+(-2^*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7)^*8+9$	311794778	$1^*2^*((3^*4-(-5-6)^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$
234880986	$(1+(-2^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*-7)^*8+9$	313174688	$(1-2)/3^*(4^{\wedge}(-5-6)-7)^*8^{\wedge}9$
234881343	$(-1+(-2^*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7)^*8-9$	320078125	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))/-5^{\wedge}(-6-(-7+8)^{\wedge}9)$
234881359	$(1-(2^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7)^*8-9$	320621769	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5/6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
234881361	$(-1+(-2^*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7)^*8+9$	321236272	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5/6)^{\wedge}7/8+9)$
234881377	$(1-(2^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7)^*8+9$	323736272	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5/6)^{\wedge}7/8+9)$
235560960	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*5/6^*(7+8/9)$	327477281	$((1-234)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)+8)/9$
238609287	$-1+(2^{\wedge}(-3-(-4-5^*6))-7^*8)/9$	329554456	$12^*((-3-4)^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)/(-8^*9)$
238609289	$1+(2^{\wedge}(-3-(-4-5^*6))-7^*8)/9$	331080890	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^*4)-5-6)^*7^*89$
238878655	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5/6-7)^*8-9$	332150637	$12+(3^*45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8+9)$
238878673	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5/6-7)^*8+9$	334588122	$1/2^*((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8^*9$
238878767	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5/6+7)^*8-9$	336662748	$(1/(-2-34))^{\wedge}-5^*((6/7)^{\wedge}-8-9)$
238878785	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5/6+7)^*8+9$	338866737	$((1+234)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)+8)/9$
240884383	$(1+2/3)^*(4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7+8^{\wedge}9$	339737112	$(-1-2)^*(3^*4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*8)^*-9$
241864669	$-12-3-4^*(5-6^{\wedge}((-7+8)+9))$	339740136	$(-1-2)^*(3^*4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^*8)^*-9$
241864699	$(12+3)-4^*(5-6^{\wedge}((-7+8)+9))$	341333279	$(-1+2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7))^*8-9$
241864709	$-12-3+4^*(5+6^{\wedge}((-7+8)+9))$	341333286	$(-1-2/-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7))^*8-9$
241864739	$12+3+4^*(5+6^{\wedge}((-7+8)+9))$	341333287	$1^*2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9$
242460944	$((-1-2)^*34)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)+8^{\wedge}9$	341333288	$1-(2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7))^*8+9)$
246857067	$((1+2-3^*(4^*5)^{\wedge}6)/-7-8)^*9$	341333295	$-1+2^*3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8/9$
246857211	$((-1-2+3^*(4^*5)^{\wedge}6)/7+8)^*9$	341333296	$1^*2^*3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8/9$
249261504	$(1+2^*(3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6))/7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	341333297	$1+2^*3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8/9$
250823048	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4)+56)^*7/(-8+9)$	341333304	$-1+2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9$
251658016	$(1+(2^{\wedge}-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	341333305	$1^*2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9$
251658236	$(1-2^{\wedge}-3^*(4^{\wedge}(-5-6)-7))^*8^{\wedge}9$	341333306	$1+2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9$
251658244	$(1+2^{\wedge}-3^*(4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7))^*8^{\wedge}9$	341333313	$(1+2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7))^*8+9$
251658464	$(1+(2^{\wedge}-3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	341333327	$(-1-(2^*-3^*(4^*5)^{\wedge}6+7)^*8)/9$
252434475	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3^*4)^*5^*((-6-7)^*-8-9)$	345888040	$1^*2^*((3-4-5^*-6/7^{\wedge}-8)-9)$
257238016	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^*-5/6^{\wedge}-7+8^{\wedge}9)$	345888080	$1^*2^*((-3+4+5^*6/7^{\wedge}-8)+9)$
264238812	$((-12^*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7-8)^*9$	348613632	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5/6^*7+8+9)$
264238956	$((12^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*-7+8)^*9$	352321284	$12^*((-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9))$
264243348	$((12^*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7-8)^*9$	354418688	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5^*6^*7/8^{\wedge}-9$
264243492	$((12^*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7+8)^*9$	359999991	$(-1+(2+3)/(4^*5)^{\wedge}-6-7)/8^*9$
265797934	$1^*2^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5))^*67+8^{\wedge}9)$	360000009	$((1+(2+3)^*(4^*5)^{\wedge}6)+7)/8^*9$
267875544	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^*5-6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$	362324664	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6^{\wedge}(7-8-9)$
267875624	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^*5-6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$	362666627	$(1-2)/-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*(8+9)$
268349440	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4^*5^*6^*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	362796786	$1^*2^*-3^*(45-6^{\wedge}((-7+8)+9))$
268429834	$1^*2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)/7+8^{\wedge}9)$	362797326	$1^*2^*3^*(45+6^{\wedge}((-7+8)+9))$
268435044	$((1-2)+3)^*(4-5^*6^*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	363083477	$(1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5+6^{\wedge}7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
268435868	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4-5^*6^*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	363269448	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6^{\wedge}(7-8-9)$
268441078	$1^*-2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)/7-8^{\wedge}9)$	364249088	$(-1+2+3^*(4^{\wedge}-5+6))/7^*8^{\wedge}9$
268521472	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^*5^*6^*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	364463530	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4-56)/7^{\wedge}8-9)/9$
268738425	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5/6-7-8)^*9$	364499983	$-1/2^*(34-(5^*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9))$
268738695	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5/6-(-7-8))^*9$	364500017	$1/2^*(34+(5^*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9))$
268995288	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^*5+6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$	367001600	$(1/2+3)^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7+8^{\wedge}9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
373063860	$((1+2)^{(3*4)-5}-6)^{*78*9}$	499117892	$(12*3-4^{(5+6)})^{*7*(-8-9)}$
378313937	$(1+23^{(-4+5+6)-7-8})/9$	499121445	$(1+(2*3-4^{(5+6)}))^{*7*(-8-9)}$
378954471	$-1+(23^{(-4-(-5-6))+7^8})/9$	499121479	$(-1-(2*3-4^{(5+6)}))^{*7*(-8-9)}$
378954472	$(1/23^{(4-5-6)+7^8})/9$	499122149	$(-1-2)^{\wedge 3-4^{(5+6)}}^{*7*(8+9)}$
378954473	$1+(23^{(-4-(-5-6))+7^8})/9$	499122203	$(1+2)^{\wedge 3-4^{(5+6)}}^{*7*(8+9)}$
383999895	$(1-2/-3^{((4*5)^{\wedge 6-7})-8})^9$	499122873	$(1-(2*3+4^{(5+6)}))^{*7*(-8-9)}$
384000072	$1*2*(3^{((4*5)^{\wedge 6+7})+8}-9)$	499122907	$(-1+(2*3+4^{(5+6)}))^{*7*(-8-9)}$
384000108	$1*2*(3^{((4*5)^{\wedge 6+7})+8}+9)$	499126460	$(12*3+4^{(5+6)})^{*7*(-8-9)}$
393287535	$(1+((2+3)^{\wedge 4-5-6})^{*7^8})/9$	500113359	$-123^4+(5*6)^{\wedge(7+8-9)}$
394762352	$(1+2)^{*((3+4*5)^{\wedge 6-7})^8/9}$	512842740	$(1+(2-3^4)^{\wedge 5})/(-6-7*(8-9))$
396361404	$12^{*(-3+4^{(5+6)})^{*7/8}}^9$	515898531	$123^{*(4^{(5+6)-7})^{\wedge(-8+9)}}$
396362052	$12^{*(3-4^{(5+6)})^{*7/-8}}^9$	519885601	$(1+2^{*(-3^4+5)})^{\wedge(-6-7-(-8-9))}$
397131149	$(1+((2+3)^{\wedge 4-5})^{*(6+7^8)})/9$	525336576	$((1-2^{\wedge(-3-4)})^{*(5+6)-7})^{*8^9}$
397770855	$(-1-((2+3)^{\wedge 4-5}))^{*(6-7^8)/9}$	528731836	$(12+((34-5)^{\wedge 6-7}))^{*8}/9$
397771683	$(-1-((2+3)^{\wedge 4-5}))^{*(-6-7^8)/9}$	533794816	$(1*2^{*(-3^4+5)})^{\wedge(-6-7-(-8-9))}$
401255192	$123^{*(4^{(5+6)})^{*7+8}}/9$	536510464	$((-1+2^{\wedge(3*-4)})^{*(5+6)+7})^{*8^9}$
402128894	$-1*2^{*(3-4^{(-5-6+7)})/8^{\wedge-9}}$	537231360	$((-1-2^{\wedge(3*-4)})^{*(5+6)+7})^{*8^9}$
402128898	$1*2^{*(3-4^{(-5-6+7)})/8^{\wedge-9}}$	546671210	$((-1-2+3^4)^{\wedge 5+6})/7+8^9$
403177470	$-1*2^{*(-3-4^{(-5-6+7)})/-8^{\wedge-9}}$	547981281	$(1-2^{*(-3^4+5)})^{\wedge(-6-7-(-8-9))}$
403177474	$1*2^{*(-3-4^{(-5-6+7)})/-8^{\wedge-9}}$	548405248	$((1+2^{\wedge(-3-4)})^{*(5+6)-7})^{*8^9}$
406901035	$(-1-2)^{*(3*4-5^{\wedge(6+7)+8})/9}$	548801406	$(1+2)^{\wedge(3*4)^{*(5^6/(7+8)-9)}}$
408503455	$(1+2)^{*((-3-4)^5)^{\wedge 6-78}}/9$	564950354	$1*2^{*((3+4)^{\wedge(5+6)})/7-8^9}$
412453393	$((-1-2+3^4)^{\wedge 5+6})/7-8^9$	564950642	$1*2^{*((3+4)^{\wedge(5+6)})/7+8^9}$
412453571	$((-1-2+3^4)^{\wedge 5+6})/7+8^9$	566226180	$(12*3-4^{(5+6)})^{*(-7-8)^9}$
419225625	$((-1+2^{\wedge(3*4)})^5)^{\wedge(-6+7-8+9)}$	566230221	$(-1+(2*3-4^{(5+6)}))^{*(-7-8)^9}$
419298270	$((1+2)^{\wedge(3*4)-5})^{*6}789$	566230239	$(1+(2*3-4^{(5+6)}))^{*(-7-8)^9}$
419635225	$((-1-2^{\wedge(3*4)})^5)^{\wedge(-6+7-8+9)}$	566230716	$(-12*3+4^{(5+6)})^{*(7+8)^9}$
423263183	$(1-(2+34)^{\wedge 5+6})^{*7^{\wedge(-8+9)}}$	566230797	$((-1-2)^{\wedge 3+4^{(5+6)}})^{*(7+8)^9}$
423263197	$(1-((-2-34)^{\wedge 5+6}))^{*7^{\wedge(-8+9)}}$	566230941	$(-1+(2/3-4^{(5+6)}))^{*(-7-8)^9}$
423263267	$(1-((2+34)^{\wedge 5+6}))^{*7^{\wedge(-8+9)}}$	566231093	$-1+(2*3-4^{(5+6)})^{*(-7-8)^9}$
423263320	$-1+(2*3)^{\wedge(4+5)^{*6}7+8^9}$	566231095	$1+(2*3-4^{(5+6)})^{*(-7-8)^9}$
423263322	$1+(2*3)^{\wedge(4+5)^{*6}7+8^9}$	566231283	$((1+2)^{\wedge 3-4^{(5+6)}})^{*(-7-8)^9}$
427729536	$((-1+23+4)^{\wedge 5*6})^{*(7+8-9)}$	566231364	$(12*3-4^{(5+6)})^{*(-7-8)^9}$
439842950	$(-12+((34+5)^{\wedge 6+7})/8)^9$	566231841	$(-1+(2*3+4^{(5+6)}))^{*(7+8)^9}$
439842968	$(-12+((34+5)^{\wedge 6+7})/8)+9$	566231859	$(1+(2*3+4^{(5+6)}))^{*(7+8)^9}$
439842974	$12-((34+5)^{\wedge 6+7})/8-9$	566235900	$(12*3+4^{(5+6)})^{*(7+8)^9}$
439842992	$12-((34+5)^{\wedge 6+7})/8+9$	566999999	$((-1+(2/3*45)^{\wedge 6*7})-8)/9$
452978460	$12^{*(-3+4^{(5+6)+7*-8})^9}$	567000001	$(1-(2/3*45)^{\wedge 6*7+8})/9$
452979108	$12^{*(-3-4^{(5+6)+7*8})^9}$	572522496	$(1/2+3)^{*(4^{(5+6)})^{*7+8^9}}$
452984580	$1/2^{*(3*4^{(5+6)+7})^8*9}$	573114351	$(-1+(23*4)^{\wedge(5+6-7)})^{*8-9}$
452985084	$1/2^{*(3*4^{(5+6)+7})^8*9}$	573114385	$(-1-(23*4)^{\wedge(5+6-7)})^{*8+9}$
452990556	$12^{*(-3+4^{(5+6)-7*-8})^9}$	581130689	$1/2^{*(3^{\wedge(4*5-(-6+7))}-8)}$
452991204	$12^{*(-3-4^{(5+6)-7*8})^9}$	581130778	$1/2^{*(3^{\wedge(4*5-(-6+7))+89})}$
453183708	$(1-234+5^{*(6+7)^8})/9$	593494016	$(1+(-2^{\wedge(-3-4)+5})^6)/7^8^{\wedge 9}$
453183760	$(1+234+5^{*(6+7)^8})/9$	599233245	$123/4^{*((5+6)^{\wedge 7+89})}$
458576472	$123^{*(4^{(5+6)-7})^8/9}$	604661692	$-1*2^{*(34-5/6^{\wedge(7-8-9)})}$
459276288	$(-1-2^{\wedge(-3-4)+5})^{*6/7*8^9}$	604661828	$1*2^{*(34-5/-6^{\wedge(7-8-9)})}$
460324864	$(-1+2^{\wedge(-3-4)^*567})/8^{\wedge-9}$	605303159	$-1+((2+3)^{\wedge 4+5})/6^{*(7^8-9)}$
461320304	$(1/2^{*(3+45^{\wedge 6})-78})/9$	605303161	$1+((2+3)^{\wedge 4+5})/6^{*(7^8-9)}$
461320321	$(1/2^{*(-3+45^{\wedge 6})+78})/9$	607968504	$(1+2)^{\wedge(3*4)^{*5-67*(-8-9)}}$
467664896	$(1/2+3)^{*(-4^{(5+6)})/7+8^9}$	610351486	$-1/2^{*(3^{\wedge 4-5^{\wedge(6+7)+8^9})}$
469761376	$(1/2-3*4^{(-5-6)})^{*7/8^{\wedge-9}}$	610351639	$1/2^{*(3^{\wedge 4+5^{\wedge(6+7)+8^9})}$
469762000	$1/2^{*(-3*4^{(-5-6)+7})^8^9}$	612755217	$((1+2)^{*((-3-4)^5)^{\wedge 6+78}}/9$
469762096	$1/2^{*(3*4^{(-5-6)+7})^8^9}$	622579985	$-1+(2-(3+4)^{\wedge-5})^{*6*7^8^9}$
469762720	$(1/2-3*-4^{(-5-6)})^{*7/8^{\wedge-9}}$	622579987	$1+(2-(3+4)^{\wedge-5})^{*6*7^8^9}$
473776128	$12^{\wedge(3+4)^5*(67-8/9)}$	626349376	$1*2/3^{*(-4^{(-5-6)+7})^8^9}$
476171127	$(-1+(2*3)^{\wedge(4+5)^{*6}7/8})^9$	626349377	$1-2/3^{*(4^{(-5-6)-7})/8^{\wedge-9}}$
476171145	$(1+(2*3)^{\wedge(4+5)^{*6}7/8})^9$	632480990	$1*2^{*((3^{*(4*5-6)^{\wedge 7-8}})-9)}$
483449472	$(12^{\wedge 3+4-5})^{*6^{\wedge 7}/(-8+9)}$	632481058	$1*2^{*(3/(4*5-6)^{\wedge-7+8+9})}$
485407657	$((-1-2-34)^{\wedge 5+6})^{*7*(8-9)}$	634894397	$-1-(((2*-3)^{\wedge(4+5)+6})^{*7+8})^9$
487862600	$1*2^{*(-3^{\wedge(4+5)+6})+7)^{*8-9)}$	634894399	$1-(((2*-3)^{\wedge(4+5)+6})^{*7+8})^9$
487862838	$(1+2)^{\wedge(3^{\wedge 4+5})^{*(6*7-8)/9}}$	634895297	$-1+(((2*3)^{\wedge(4+5)+6})^{*7+8})^9$
487863076	$1*2^{*(3^{\wedge(4+5)+6})+7)^{*8+9)}$	634895299	$1+(((2*3)^{\wedge(4+5)+6})^{*7+8})^9$
488281088	$1*-2^{*(3^{\wedge 4-5^{\wedge(6-((-7-8)+9))}})}$	643292928	$(12*3)^{\wedge 4^{*(5-6+7)^8-9}}$
488281182	$1*-2^{*(34-5^{\wedge(6-((-7-8)+9))}})}$	647495680	$(-1-(2^{\wedge(-3-4)-5})/6^{*7})^8^9$
488281318	$1*2^{*(34+5^{\wedge(6-((-7-8)+9))}})}$	652582856	$-12^{\wedge 3+4/5^{*(6+7)^8+9}}$
488281412	$1*2^{*(3^{\wedge 4+5^{\wedge(6-((-7-8)+9))}})}$	652584548	$-12*3+4/5^{*(6+7)^8+9}$
489438437	$-1+((2-3+4)/5^{*((6+7)^8+9)})$	652584571	$1/(((2+3)/(-4^{(5-6+7)^8}-9))$
489438439	$1+((2-3+4)/5^{*((6+7)^8+9)})$	652584620	$12*3+4/5^{*(6+7)^8+9}$
492131648	$(-1-2/3^{*(4^{(-5-6)-7})/8^{\wedge-9}}}$	652586312	$12^{\wedge 3+4/5^{*(6+7)^8+9}}$
494331666	$1*-2^{*((-3-4)^{\wedge(5+6)+7})/8+9)}$	655905562	$(1-23-4^{\wedge 5}*(6-7^8))/9$
494331702	$1*2^{*((3+4)^{\wedge(5+6)-7})/8+9)}$	664301250	$1*2^{*(3*45)^{\wedge(-6-7+8)+9}}$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
669176136	$(-12 - ((34-5)^{6+7}) / -8) * 9$	805240831	$-1+2*(3-4^{(-5-(-6+7))}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
669176352	$(12+((34-5)^{6+7}) / 8) * 9$	805240833	$1+2*(3-4^{(-5-(-6+7))}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
670564351	$-1+(2+3-4^{(-5-6+7)}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$	805273599	$-1+(2*3-4^{(-5-(-6+7))}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
670564353	$1+(2+3-4^{(-5-6+7)}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$	805273601	$1+(2*3-4^{(-5-(-6+7))}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
671612927	$-1+(-2-3-4^{(-5-6+7)}) / -8^{\wedge}-9$	805305632	$(-1-23*4^{(-5-6+7)}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
671612929	$1+(-2-3-4^{(-5-6+7)}) / -8^{\wedge}-9$	805305919	$-1+2*(3-4^{(-5-6+7)}) * 8^{\wedge}9$
674167936	$(12*3)^{\wedge}4+5*(6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$	805305920	$1*2*(-3+4^{(-5-6+7)}) / -8^{\wedge}-9$
682666556	$12*(-3+((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7) * 8 / 9)$	805306208	$(-1-(2+3)*4^{(-5-6+7)}) * 8^{\wedge}9$
682666588	$-12*(3-((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7) * 8) / 9$	805306528	$(-1+(2+3)*4^{(-5-6+7)}) * 8^{\wedge}9$
682666596	$12*(3+((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7) * 8) / 9$	805306816	$1*2*(-3-4^{(-5-6+7)}) / -8^{\wedge}-9$
682666628	$12*(3+((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7) * 8 / 9)$	805306817	$1+2*(3+4^{(-5-6+7)}) * 8^{\wedge}9$
693633024	$(-1+(2^{(-3-4-5)} / 6+7) * 8^{\wedge}9)$	805307104	$(-1+23*4^{(-5-6+7)}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
697356879	$1*-2*(-3^{(4*5+6)} / ((-7+8)+9))$	805339135	$-1+(2*3+4^{(-5-(-6+7))}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
701537016	$-12*(3*((4-(5+6)^{\wedge}7)+8)+9)$	805339137	$1+(2*3+4^{(-5-(-6+7))}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
701538696	$12*(3*((4+(5+6)^{\wedge}7)+8)+9)$	805371903	$-1-2*(-3-4^{(-5-(-6+7))}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
704643035	$(1/2-3*4^{(5+6)}) * -7*8-9$	805371905	$1-2*(-3-4^{(-5-(-6+7))}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
704643053	$(1/2-3*4^{(5+6)}) * -7*8+9$	805830655	$-1+(2*3+4^{(-5-6+7)}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
704643059	$(1/2-3*4^{(5+6)}) * 7*-8-9$	805830657	$1+(2*3+4^{(-5-6+7)}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
704643067	$(1/2-3*-4^{(5+6)}) * 7*8-9$	816840704	$(-1+2^{(-3-4)} * (5+6)+7) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
704643077	$(-1/2+3*4^{(5+6)}) * 7*8+9$	822083360	$(1-2^{\wedge}-3-4^{(-5-6)}) * 7 / 8^{\wedge}-9$
704643085	$(1/2-3*4^{(5+6)}) * -7*8+9$	822083575	$(1/2+3)*4^{(5+6)} * 7*8-9$
704643091	$(1/2-3*-4^{(5+6)}) * 7*8-9$	822083593	$(1/2+3)*4^{(5+6)} * 7*8+9$
704643109	$(1/2-3*-4^{(5+6)}) * 7*8+9$	822083808	$(1-2^{\wedge}-3+4^{(-5-6)}) * 7 / 8^{\wedge}-9$
725333237	$(-1+2/3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7)) * (8+9)$	826802176	$((-1-2^{(-3-4)}) * 5 / 6+7) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
725333253	$-1+2/3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7) * (8+9)$	827850751	$-1+((2^{(-3-4-5)} / 6+7) / 8^{\wedge}-9)$
725333254	$1*2/3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7) * (8+9)$	827850752	$(1*(2^{(-3-4-5)} / 6+7) / 8^{\wedge}-9)$
725333255	$1+2/3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7) * (8+9)$	827850753	$1+((2^{(-3-4-5)} / 6+7) / 8^{\wedge}-9)$
725333271	$(1+2/3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7)) * (8+9)$	833385954	$1*2*((3+4)^{\wedge}(5+6) / 7+8^{\wedge}9)$
725589216	$(1-(2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+67) * 8*-9$	836763648	$(-1+2^{(-3-4)} * 5*6+7) * 8^{\wedge}9$
725589360	$(-1-(2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+67) * 8*-9$	846526472	$-1+(2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5) * (6+78)+9$
725594043	$-12*(3/4+5-6^{(-7+8+9)})$	846526474	$1+(2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5) * (6+78)+9$
725594061	$-12*(3/4+5-6^{(-7+8+9)})$	849870848	$((1-2^{(-3-4-5)} / 6+7) / 8^{\wedge}-9)$
725594102	$-1-((2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5) * (6-78)+9)$	851367770	$(-1+2/3^{(-4*5+6-7)}) * 8^{\wedge}9$
725594104	$1-((2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5) * (6-78)+9)$	851367948	$(1+2/3^{(-4*5+6-7)}) * 8^{\wedge}9$
725594120	$-1+(2*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5) * (6-78)+9$	851369016	$(-1-2/-3^{(-4*5+6+7)}) * 8^{\wedge}9$
725594122	$1+(2*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5) * (6-78)+9$	851369194	$((1+2/3^{(-4*5+6+7)}) * 7) * 8^{\wedge}9$
725594163	$12*(-3/4+5+6^{(-7+8+9)})$	858783744	$(1-2^{(-3-4)} * (5+6)) * 7*8^{\wedge}9$
725594181	$12*(3/4+5+6^{(-7+8+9)})$	860162240	$(1-2*(3/4)^{\wedge}(5+6)) * 7*8^{\wedge}9$
725598864	$(-1+(2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+67) * 8*9$	867926016	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4) * (5*6*-7-8) / 9$
725599008	$(1-(2*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+67) * 8*9$	871696092	$((1+2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5+6)) - 7) / 8-9)$
728760320	$(1+2^{(-3-4)} * 567) / 8^{\wedge}-9$	871696110	$((1+2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5+6)) - 7) / 8+9)$
728999940	$(-12*3)^{\wedge}4+(5*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9)$	871696116	$1*2*((3*(4+5)^{\wedge}6+7) / 8^{\wedge}9)$
729000060	$(12+3)^{\wedge}4+(5*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9)$	872415136	$(1/-2-3*4^{(-5-6+7)}) * 8^{\wedge}9$
738197425	$1/2*(-3^{\wedge}4+(-5-6) * (7-8^{\wedge}9))$	872415328	$((-1/2+3/4^{(5+6)}) * 7) * 8^{\wedge}9$
738197488	$(1/2*(-3-4^{(-5-6)}) + 7) / 8^{\wedge}-9$	873997203	$1/(2/3+4) * (5*(6+7)^{\wedge}8+9)$
738197520	$(1/2*(-3-4^{(-5-6)}) + 7) / 8^{\wedge}-9$	892392588	$(1+2^{(-3+4)}) / 5 * (6*(7^{\wedge}8+9))$
738197583	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4+(5+6) * (7+8^{\wedge}9))$	902823936	$((-1-2^{(-3-4)}) * 5+6) * 7*8^{\wedge}9$
746423544	$((1+2^{(-3+4-5)})^{\wedge}6-7) / -8^{\wedge}-9$	903981099	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(3*4+5+6) * 7 / (8-9))$
755827192	$1-((2*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5) * (67+8)+9)$	905967999	$(-1-(2-3*(4^{(5+6)}-7))) * 8^{\wedge}9$
755827208	$-1+(2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5) * (67+8)+9$	905968017	$(1+(2-3*(4^{(5+6)}-7))) * 8^{\wedge}9$
756449185	$(-1-(2*3*-4)^{\wedge}5) * ((-6-7) * -8-9)$	905968125	$(-1-2+3*(4^{(5+6)}-7)) * 8^{\wedge}9$
756449375	$(1+(2*3*4)^{\wedge}5) * ((-6-7) * -8-9)$	905968179	$(-1-2-3*(4^{(5+6)}-7)) * 8^{\wedge}9$
759496704	$((1+2^{(-3)})^{\wedge}4+5) * 6/7*8^{\wedge}9$	905968287	$(1+(-2-3*(4^{(5+6)}-7))) * 8^{\wedge}9$
760567104	$(1+2/3*(-4^{(-5-6+7)}) / 8^{\wedge}-9)$	905968305	$(1-(-2-3*(4^{(5+6)}-7))) * 8^{\wedge}9$
771750441	$1*-23*((-4^{(5+6)+7}) * 8+9)$	905971023	$(1-(-2-3*(-4^{(5+6)}-7))) * 8^{\wedge}9$
771750855	$1*23*((4^{(5+6)}-7) * 8+9)$	905971041	$(1+(-2-3*(-4^{(5+6)}-7))) * 8^{\wedge}9$
771753017	$1*23*((4^{(5+6)+7}) * 8-9)$	905971149	$(-1-2-3*(-4^{(5+6)}-7)) * 8^{\wedge}9$
771753431	$1*23*((4^{(5+6)+7}) * 8+9)$	905971203	$(-1-2+3*(-4^{(5+6)}-7)) * 8^{\wedge}9$
774821294	$-1-(2-3^{(-4-5)}) * (6-(7+8))^{\wedge}9$	905971311	$(-1+(2-3*(-4^{(5+6)}-7))) * 8^{\wedge}9$
774821295	$-1*(2-3^{(-4-5)}) * (6-7-8)^{\wedge}9$	905971329	$(1-(2-3*(-4^{(5+6)}-7))) * 8^{\wedge}9$
774821296	$1-(2-3^{(-4-5)}) * (6-(7+8))^{\wedge}9$	911662101	$123 / (((-4+5)+6) * 7^{\wedge}8-9) * 9$
774860660	$-1-(2+3^{(-4-5)}) * (6-(7+8))^{\wedge}9$	915931136	$(1+(-2^{(-3-4)}+5) / 6*7) * 8^{\wedge}9$
774860661	$-1*(2+3^{(-4-5)}) * (6-7-8)^{\wedge}9$	918028288	$((-1+2^{(-3-4)} * 5) / 6+7) * 8^{\wedge}9$
774860662	$1-(2+3^{(-4-5)}) * (6-(7+8))^{\wedge}9$	919132809	$1/2*(((-3-4)^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}(-8+9))$
775084161	$((1/2*34)^{\wedge}(56/7+8) / 9)$	939523360	$1*(-23*4^{(-5-6+7)}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
789053440	$(1-2^{(-3-4)}) * 5/6*-7/8^{\wedge}-9$	939523392	$((1-23) * 4^{(-5-6+7)}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
792723240	$(-1+2)*3*(4^{(5+6)} * -7+8) * -9$	939524800	$((-1+23) * 4^{(-5-6+7)}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
792723672	$(-1+2)*3*(4^{(5+6)} * 7+8) * 9$	939524832	$(1*23/4^{(5+6)+7}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
793097760	$12*((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7-8) / 9$	951058432	$(1*2^{(-3-4)} * (5+6)+7) / 8^{\wedge}-9$
804225024	$12*(3+4) * (5*6*7-8) / 9$	957886641	$123^{\wedge}4+(5*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9)$
804782079	$-1+(2*3-4^{(-5-6+7)}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$	960000105	$(12+3) * ((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7*(8-9))$
804782081	$1+(2*3-4^{(-5-6+7)}) / 8^{\wedge}-9$	961019904	$((1-2^{(-3-4)} * 5) / 6+7) * 8^{\wedge}9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
976096825	$(1 - (2+34)^5)^* ((6/7-8) - 9)$	1291315547	$123+4^{\wedge}(-5-6)^*(7*8)^{\wedge}9$
976224256	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5+6)^*7*8^{\wedge}9$	1301132106	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5-6*7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
988663304	$1/2*((3+4)^{\wedge}(5+6)+(-7-8)^*9)$	1305169162	$-1*2*(3-4/5*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9))$
988663439	$1/2*((3+4)^{\wedge}(5+6)-(-7-8)^*9)$	1305169174	$1*2*(3+4/5*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9))$
992187500	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(5+6+7-8)^{\wedge}9$	1313832960	$12^{\wedge}(3*4-5)^*6*(7-8/9)$
996224113	$(-1+2*(-3^{\wedge}(4*5+6)))/7/(8-9)$	1338352479	$(-1+2*(34-5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8*9$
1006632864	$(1/2-3*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)^*8^{\wedge}9$	1338352497	$(-1-2*((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8)^*-9$
1006633056	$(1/2-3*-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)^*8^{\wedge}9$	1342176852	$((1-2)+3)^*(-4-5*(6*7-8^{\wedge}9))$
1007812500	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(5+6+7-8)^{\wedge}9$	1342176868	$((1-2)+3)^*(4-5*(6*7-8^{\wedge}9))$
1018885952	$(1-2*(-3/4)^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7*8^{\wedge}9$	1342177692	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4-5*(6*7+8^{\wedge}9))$
1020264448	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(-5-6))^*7*8^{\wedge}9$	1342177708	$((1-2)+3)^*(4+5*(6*7+8^{\wedge}9))$
1029177344	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	1344000007	$(-1+2+3*(4*5)^{\wedge}6)^*-7*(8-9)$
1040476679	$-1+(2+3)^*4*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	1357129728	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5*6+7/8*9)$
1040476681	$1+(2+3)^*4*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	1358952156	$(12*3*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)-8)^*9$
1042284544	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5*6+7)^*8^{\wedge}9$	1358952300	$(12*-3*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)+8)^*9$
1050097311	$((-1+2*34)^{\wedge}5+6)^*7+8)/9$	1358956692	$(12*3*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)-8)^*9$
1051197439	$-1+((-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	1358956836	$(12*3*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)+8)^*9$
1051197440	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	1359551191	$-12+3*(4+5*(6+7)^{\wedge}8)/9$
1051197441	$1+((-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	1359551199	$(-12-3*(4-5*(6+7)^{\wedge}8))/9$
1056964384	$(1+2^{\wedge}-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7/8^{\wedge}-9$	1359551215	$12+3*(4+5*(6+7)^{\wedge}8)/9$
1056964832	$(1+2^{\wedge}-3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7/8^{\wedge}-9$	1360488141	$(-1+((2*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*(-7-8))^*9$
1062207488	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(5+6+7)^*8^{\wedge}9$	1360488159	$(1+((2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)-6)^*(7+8))^*9$
1079753125	$(1-(2+34)^5)^*((-6/7-8) - 9)$	1360489761	$(-1+((2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*(7+8))^*9$
1085069372	$(1/2+3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}(6+7))^*-8/9$	1360489779	$(1+((2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*(7+8))^*9$
1085069374	$-1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}(6+7)^*8)/-9$	1365333184	$(1+23)^*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8/9$
1085069376	$1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}(6+7)^*8)/-9$	1394530536	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^*-6*7*(8+9)$
1085069516	$(1/2-3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}(6+7))^*-8/9$	1394531964	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^*6*7*(8+9)$
1085277672	$((1-23)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}(6+7))^*8/9$	1409285920	$(1/2*-3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*-7*8^{\wedge}9$
1088391162	$-1*2*(3+(-4-5)/6^{\wedge}(7-8-9))$	1409286032	$1/2*(-3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*-7*8^{\wedge}9$
1088391174	$1*2*(3+(-4-5)/-6^{\wedge}(7-8-9))$	1409286096	$1/2*3*(-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)^*8^{\wedge}9$
1098907517	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4*5))^*(6*7+89)$	1409286192	$1/2*3*(4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)^*8^{\wedge}9$
1098907779	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4*5))^*(6*7+89)$	1409286256	$1/2*(-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*-7*8^{\wedge}9$
1105199104	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5*6+7)^*8^{\wedge}9$	1409286368	$(1/2*-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*-7*8^{\wedge}9$
1112246289	$1/2*((-3-4)^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	1427528745	$-1+(-2-3/-4*5)^*((6+7)^{\wedge}8-9)$
1119214694	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(3*4+5)+6)^*78/-9$	1427528747	$1+(-2-3/-4*5)^*((6+7)^{\wedge}8-9)$
1119214798	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3*4+5)+6)^*78/9$	1433271975	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5-6*7)^*8-9$
1119877121	$(-1*2+3*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7))^*89$	1433271993	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5-6*7)^*8+9$
1119881215	$(1*2*(3+(-4-5)+6)-7))^*89$	1433272647	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5+6*7)^*8-9$
1132624648	$((1+2^{\wedge}(-3+4-5))^{\wedge}6+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	1433272665	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5+6*7)^*8+9$
1138779647	$-1+(2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*((-6-7)^*-8+9)$	1438892995	$(1+2*((3+45)^{\wedge}6-7))/ (8+9)$
1138779649	$1+(2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*((-6-7)^*-8+9)$	1441740790	$((-12-34)^{\wedge}5+6)^*7/(8-9)$
1140850672	$(1/2*(3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6))+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	1457999976	$1*2*(-3*4+(5*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9))$
1140850704	$(1/2*(3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6))+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	1457999992	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4-(5*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9))$
1146317445	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3*4))^*(-5+6^{\wedge}7)/(-8+9)$	1458000008	$((1-2)+3)^*(4-(5*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9))$
1147737600	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3*4)+5)^*6^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	1458000024	$1*-2*(-3*4-(5*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9))$
1148297472	$(-1-(2^{\wedge}(3*4)+5))^*-6^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	1467553625	$-1-(2/(3+4)-5)^*6*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
1162241784	$(-1-2+3^{\wedge}(-4-5))^*(6-(7+8))^{\wedge}9$	1467553627	$1-(2/(3+4)-5)^*6*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
1162281150	$(-1-2-3^{\wedge}(-4-5))/(6-(7+8))^{\wedge}-9$	1468315313	$-1+(2-(-3+4)/5)^*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9)$
1179010630	$((1+2^{\wedge}34)-5)/(6/7*(8+9))$	1468315315	$1+(2-(-3+4)/5)^*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9)$
1179090423	$(-1-(2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5))/-6*78)^*9$	1509946911	$(1+(-2-3)^*(4*(5+6)-7)^*8)^*9$
1179090441	$(1+(2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5))/6*78)^*9$	1509946929	$(1-(-2-3)^*(4*(5+6)-7)^*8)^*9$
1185415168	$(1-(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)/6+7)^*8^{\wedge}9$	1509951951	$(1-(-2-3)^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^*8)^*-9$
1193046471	$((1+2^{\wedge}34)^*-5+6)+7)/(8*-9)$	1509951969	$(1+(-2-3)^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^*8)^*9$
1194666648	$(-1-2+3*(4*5)^{\wedge}6)^*7*8/9$	1536953616	$((1-23)^*(4+5))^{\wedge}(-6-7-(8-9))$
1199245093	$(-1-((2*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7)^*(8+9)$	1539459000	$(-1+(2*34)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*8*9$
1199245127	$(-1+((2*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7)^*(-8-9)$	1539459063	$(-1+(2*34)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)^*8)^*9$
1199246521	$(-1+((2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7)^*(8+9)$	1539459081	$(1-(2*34)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)^*-8)^*9$
1199246537	$-1+((2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7*(8+9)$	1539459144	$(-1-(2*34)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*8*-9$
1199246539	$1+((2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7*(8+9)$	1542717440	$((1/2-(-3+4^{\wedge}-5)^*6)-7)^*8^{\wedge}9$
1199246555	$(-1-((2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7)^*(-8-9)$	1544290304	$((1/2-(-3-4^{\wedge}-5)^*6)-7)^*8^{\wedge}9$
1207435264	$(12-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/8^{\wedge}-9$	1553090848	$(12-(3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6))/7)/8^{\wedge}-9$
1207958886	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3*(4+5)))-67-8)^*9$	1556495109	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)-5*6*-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
1207959012	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3*(4+5)))+67)-8)^*-9$	1556497431	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5*6*7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
1207960092	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3*(4+5)))+67)-8)^*9$	1579049408	$12*((3+4*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8/9$
1207960218	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3*(4+5)))-67-8)^*-9$	1586195504	$(1+2)^*((34-5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8/9$
1208483840	$(-12+3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/-8^{\wedge}-9$	1600692504	$-12*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))^*6*7-8^{\wedge}9$
1217868015	$(-1+(23*4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*(8+9)$	1620532968	$12*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))^*6*7+8^{\wedge}9$
1217868049	$(-1-(23*4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*(-8-9)$	1627604181	$1/(2*-3)^*(-4-5^{\wedge}(6+7))^*8+9$
1273939389	$((-1-2)^*-34)^{\wedge}5+6)/78)^*9$	1632580191	$(1+2)^{\wedge}((-3+4)+5)^*(6^{\wedge}7*8-9)$
1291315301	$-123+4^{\wedge}(-5-6)^*(7*8)^{\wedge}9$	1632593313	$(1+2)^{\wedge}((-3+4)+5)^*(6^{\wedge}7*8+9)$
1291315401	$-1*23+4^{\wedge}(-5-6)^*(7*8)^{\wedge}9$	1634013884	$(12+((-3-4)^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8)/9$
1291315447	$1*23+4^{\wedge}(-5-6)^*(7*8)^{\wedge}9$	1668134624	$(12+(3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6))/7)/8^{\wedge}-9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1670420000	$1*2*(34*5)^{\wedge}((-6-7+8)+9)$	2046820340	$-12+(3/4*(5+6)+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$
1670420001	$1+2*(34*5)^{\wedge}((-6-7+8)+9)$	2046820350	$1*-2+(3/4*(5+6)+7)*8^{\wedge}9$
1672151040	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)*-5*(-6-78)/9$	2046820354	$1*2+(3/4*(5+6)+7)*8^{\wedge}9$
1676673024	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)*5)^*(6+7)*8^{\wedge}9$	2046820364	$12+(3/4*(5+6)+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$
1713373184	$((1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)*5)^*6+7)*8^{\wedge}9$	2056087478	$1*2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-(-6+7)))-8^{\wedge}9$
1727999712	$((-1-2+3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7))-8)*9$	2092070652	$(1+((-2+3^{\wedge}(4*5))+6)/(7+8))*9$
1727999748	$((-1+2+3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7))-8)*9$	2095875000	$(-1-2^{\wedge}-3+4)/(5*6)^{\wedge}((-7-8)+9)$
1728000252	$((1-2+3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6+7))+8)*9$	2113926768	$(-1-(-2-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)))^*7*8^*-9$
1728000288	$((1+2+3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6+7))+8)*9$	2113927704	$(-1+2)*(-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7*8*9$
1730160891	$(1-2-(-3-4)^{\wedge}(5+6)*7)/8-9$	2113929543	$(-1-(2/3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)))^*-7*8*9$
1730160909	$(1-2-(-3-4)^{\wedge}(5+6)*7)/8+9$	2113929561	$(1+(2/3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)))^*7*8*9$
1744829792	$(-1+(2-3*4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	2113930728	$(-1+2)*(-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7*8*9$
1744829844	$-1*((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5+(-6-7)*8^{\wedge}9)$	2113931664	$(-1-(-2-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)))^*7*8*9$
1744831136	$(-1+(2+3*4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	2147483617	$1+(23-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)-7)*8^{\wedge}9$
1751048192	$((-1+2)-3)*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7*8^{\wedge}9)$		
1757623778	$(1*2+((3+4)^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)*8)/9$		
1776287744	$((1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)*5)^*6+7)*8^{\wedge}9$		
1797062656	$((1+2^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*-6-7*8^{\wedge}9$		
1799487488	$((1/2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)/6+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$		
1800814096	$(1-23*(4+5))^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9))$		
1811938320	$1*2*(-3*4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)*8*9$		
1811940336	$1*2*(3*4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)*8*9$		
1812734938	$(-1+23-4*-5*(6+7)^{\wedge}8)/9$		
1812987904	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)*5)^*(6+7)*8^{\wedge}9$		
1822499990	$(-1/2+3)*(-4+(5*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9))$		
1822500010	$(1/2-3)*(-4-(5*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9))$		
1822943232	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)*5*67/8+9$		
1831093088	$(-123^{\wedge}4+5)*((6-7)^{\wedge}8-9)$		
1831093168	$(-123^{\wedge}4-5)*((6-7)^{\wedge}8-9)$		
1846233834	$(-1+((2-3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5-6)/(-7-8))*9$		
1846233852	$(1+((-2+3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5+6)/(7+8))*9$		
1871773696	$(1+23*(4+5))^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9))$		
1879047519	$-1+(2-3*4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7*8^{\wedge}9$		
1879047520	$(1*2-3/4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7/8^{\wedge}-9$		
1879047521	$1+(2-3*4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7/8^{\wedge}-9$		
1879047968	$(1-2+3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7/8^{\wedge}-9$		
1879048000	$1*2*(-3*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)*8^{\wedge}9$		
1879048128	$((-1+2)-3)*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)-7*8^{\wedge}9$		
1879048256	$(1-2+3)*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7*8^{\wedge}9$		
1879048384	$1*2*(3*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)*8^{\wedge}9$		
1879048416	$(1-2+3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7/8^{\wedge}-9$		
1879048863	$-1+(2+3*4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7*8^{\wedge}9$		
1879048864	$1*(-2-3/4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7/-8^{\wedge}-9$		
1879048865	$1+(2+3*4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7/8^{\wedge}-9$		
1898666459	$(1-2)/-3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7)*89$		
1902942375	$(-1+(2*34)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*89$		
1902942463	$-1+(2*34)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)*89$		
1902942465	$1-(2*34)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)*89$		
1902942553	$(-1-(2*34)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*89$		
1904214016	$1*-2*(-3*4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7*8^{\wedge}9)$		
1908287682	$(-1-2+34^{\wedge}5)*6*7*(-8+9)$		
1908287801	$(1-2+34^{\wedge}5*6)*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$		
1908287850	$(-1+2+34^{\wedge}5)*6*7/(-8+9)$		
1908874335	$(1+2^{\wedge}34-5*(6*7-8))/9$		
1921480704	$(12*3)^{\wedge}4*(5-67*(-8-9))$		
1923730614	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4)*5-6*-7^{\wedge}8)*9$		
1936925298	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)*(6-(7+8))^{\wedge}9$		
1937279592	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)*(6-(7+8))^{\wedge}9$		
1957753740	$-12+3*4/5*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9)$		
1957753764	$12+3*4/5*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9)$		
1980149166	$1*2*3^{\wedge}(4+5+6)*78-9$		
2007048192	$((1-2)+3)*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7*-8^{\wedge}9)$		
2012741632	$(12+3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/8^{\wedge}-9$		
2013233152	$(12+3-4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6+7)))/8^{\wedge}-9$		
2013265248	$(1-(2-3*4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*-7)/8^{\wedge}-9$		
2013265696	$(12+3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)*7)/8^{\wedge}-9$		
2013266144	$(12+3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6)*7)/8^{\wedge}-9$		
2013266592	$(1-(-2-3*4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7)/8^{\wedge}-9$		
2013298688	$(-12-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6+7)))/-8^{\wedge}-9$		
2013790208	$(-12-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/-8^{\wedge}-9$		
2039326763	$1/2*(-34+5*((6+7)^{\wedge}8-9))$		
2039326842	$1/2*(34+5*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9))$		

Supplement 2

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
14317	$9+(8-(7-(-6+5)))^4)^*(-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	65272	$((-9-8)-7)^*(6+5)+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
16571	$9*(8-7*6+5^{\wedge}4*3)+2*1$	65387	$(-9-8)*7-6*5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
18596	$(9*(87*6-5)-4)^*(3+2-1)$	65698	$9*(-8-7)*6/-5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
19931	$(-9/8-7+6+5^{\wedge}4)*32-1$	65746	$(-9+8)*7*-6*5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
20218	$(9*(87+6^{\wedge}5)-4)/(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	65849	$(98*7*(-6+54)-3)^*2-1$
21082	$(-9-8*7*-6+5)*4^{\wedge}3-2^{\wedge}-1$	66133	$((-9-8)*(-7-6^{\wedge}5)-43)/2-1$
21434	$(9+(8-7*6-5+4)^{\wedge}3)/-2+1$	66290	$(98+7)^*(6+5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
21500	$-9*((8*7*6+5)*(-4-3)-2)-1$	66867	$((9+8)+76)^*(5/(4*3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$
23948	$(9-8+76)^*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1$	67368	$9*8*7*((-65-4/3)^*-2+1)$
24155	$9*-8*(-7+(-654-3)/2)-1$	68160	$((9*8-7)+6)*5*4^{\wedge}3*(2+1)$
24925	$((9*8+7)^*(6+5^{\wedge}4)+3)/2-1$	68259	$9+(8+7+6)*((54+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
25180	$(-9/8+7*6)^*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$	68656	$(98+7*-6)*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
25261	$(-9-8)*(-7*6-(5-43)^{\wedge}2)-1$	71417	$(-9-8)*(7*6*5*4*(-3-2)-1)$
25300	$9*((8+7-6)*5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1$	72272	$9*8*((76*5/(4*3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
25573	$(9*8+7+6/(5+4))*321$	74200	$(98+7*6)*((5*4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
26662	$(-9+8/7*((6^{\wedge}5+4)*3-2)-1)$	74407	$-9+8*(7+65*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
28722	$-9*((8-7-6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3)+21$	74425	$9+8*(7+65*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
28851	$(9-8*7*6)^*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	74667	$-9+8*7/6*((5*4)^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
28922	$(9-(-8-76))*5^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1$	74685	$9+8*7/6*((5*4)^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
28924	$(9-(-8-76))*5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1$	74700	$(9*8*-7+6)*(-5-((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
28966	$(9*8*7+6^{\wedge}5-4)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	75171	$(9/8*7*6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)+2+1$
29860	$((9-8)+7)*(-6*(-5^{\wedge}4+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	75340	$-9*(8+7*65)+43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
33136	$(9-8)*76*((5+432)-1)$	75391	$-9+8*(-7-6)*-5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
34149	$-9-(-8-7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4-3))/(2+1)$	75409	$9+8*(-7-6)*-5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
37978	$(-9-8)/7*(6^{\wedge}5+43)^*-2^{\wedge}1$	75484	$9*(8-7*65)+43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
40280	$(9-8)*76*((5*4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	75500	$(98*7*(6+5)+4)^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
41756	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4-3)/2-1$	76362	$(9*8*7+6*5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
42217	$(9*87-6)^*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	76705	$(9-8*(-7-6)*5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
42234	$9*(87*6*(5+4)-3)-21$	76932	$9*((8+(-7-6)*(-5^{\wedge}4-32))-1)$
42448	$98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+432+1)$	76957	$(9*8*7+6)*-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
43118	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5*(4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	77205	$9-(8*7+6*(-5^{\wedge}4+3))*21$
43150	$(98+765)*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	77253	$98*(7-6*5)+43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
43340	$(9-8-7*(6-5^{\wedge}4))*3^{\wedge}2+1$	79341	$(9+8/7-6*(-5^{\wedge}4-3))*21$
45124	$9*8+7+(6+5)*4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1$	79365	$((98+7)+6)*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
45383	$((9+8)+7)*((6+5^{\wedge}4)*3-2)-1$	79732	$9*(-8+7+6)*5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
45451	$-9*((8*7*6*5+4)*-3+2)+1$	79737	$(9+8*7-6*(-5^{\wedge}4+3))*21$
45481	$((9+8)+7)*((6+5^{\wedge}4)*3+2)+1$	79822	$9*((8-7)+6)*5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
46343	$9*((-8*7+6^{\wedge}5)+4)/3*2-1$	79973	$9*(8/7*(6^{\wedge}5+4-3)-2)-1$
46934	$9*((87*(6+54)-3)-2)-1$	79975	$9*(8/7*(6^{\wedge}5+4-3)-2)+1$
46936	$9*((87*(6+54)-3)-2)+1$	80032	$9*8/7*((6^{\wedge}5+4-3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
47638	$9*((8*(7+654)+3)+2)+1$	80295	$-9+(8*7+6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))*21$
48474	$-9*((-8*7-(6*5+43)^{\wedge}2)-1)$	80313	$9+(8*7+6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))*21$
48480	$((9*8*7+6)-5)*4*(3+21)$	80383	$(9/8*(7+6)+5)*4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1$
48754	$-9+(8*7*6+5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	80384	$(9/8*(7+6)+5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2+1)$
49324	$(-9+8)*-76*((5^{\wedge}4+3)+21)$	80452	$9*(-8-7-6)*-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
50266	$(-9+8-7*-6)*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	80509	$(-9*(8*-7-6)+5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
50993	$9*((8*7-6^{\wedge}5/4)*-3+2)-1$	80560	$9*(87+6*5)+43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
51223	$(-9-8+7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1))$	80584	$-9*8+((-76+5)*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
51443	$(9-8)*7*(6*(5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	80668	$(9*(8+7)-6)*5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
51590	$98+7*6*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	80694	$9*(((-8-7)-6)*5*(5-432)-1)$
51799	$(9+8)*((76*5*4+3)*2+1)$	80728	$9*8+((-76+5)*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
51847	$(9-8)*7-6*5*(-4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	80738	$(-9*8-7)*(6-5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
52152	$9*8*(7/6*(5^{\wedge}4-(3+2))+1)$	80787	$(9*8+7+6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))*21$
52715	$9*8*((7/6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3)+2)-1$	80982	$9*(87/6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-21)$
52784	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3*2)/-1$	81007	$(9-8)*7+(6*5)^{\wedge}4/(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
53008	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7)*6*(5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	81206	$(-9-8)*7*6-5/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
53022	$((-9+8)+7)*((6*5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	81878	$(-9+8*7*6*5)^*(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
53112	$-9*8-((7+6)*5-4^{\wedge}(3*2))-1$	81962	$(-9+8)*-7*6-5/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
53384	$9*8+(7+6)*(5+4^{\wedge}(3*2))-1$	82040	$(98/7+6)*((5+4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1)$
53918	$9-((8+7)*6-(5*4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	82057	$(9*8*7+6)*5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
55172	$9*8+76*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	82410	$(9*8-7*-6/5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
55543	$9*8+7+6*(5/43^{\wedge}-2-1)$	82650	$(9*8+7*6)*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
55913	$(9+8)*(-7+6*5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	83378	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4*(3)^{\wedge}2+1$
56658	$((9+87*6)*5+43)*21$	83666	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4*(3)^{\wedge}2+1$
57018	$(-9+87)*6*(5+4*(4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	83977	$9+(8^{\wedge}(-7+6)+5)*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
57303	$-9*(-8*(76+5*(4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$	84012	$-9+((8+7)+6)*((5*4)^{\wedge}3/2+1)$
57442	$-98*(-7^{\wedge}(-6+5)*4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	84130	$(-9/8+7)*((-6-5)^{\wedge}4-321)$
58553	$9+8+(7-(6+5)^{\wedge}4)*(-3-2+1)$	84627	$9*((87*6*(5+4)+3)*2+1)$
59602	$(9+8)*((-76-5^{\wedge}4)*(-3-2)+1)$	84952	$-9+8*7*6^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
62829	$9*((-8+(-76-5)*43)*-2-1)$	85148	$98+7*6^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
64557	$9*((8*(-7-6)*(-5-4^{\wedge}3)-2)-1)$	86989	$(-9-8)*-7*(6+5*(4*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
65190	$(9*8+7*-6/5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$	87046	$(9+8*7+6)*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
87170	$((-9-8)+7)^6-5^4)/3-(2+1)$	123670	$-9*8-((-7-6)^5+4)/3-21$
88078	$(9*(8+7)+6)*(5^4-3^4(-2+1))$	123814	$(9*8+((7+6)^5-4)/3)-21$
88825	$(-9-8)*(7+654*(-3^2+1))$	123856	$(9*8+((7+6)^5-4)/3)+21$
89421	$9*((-87-(6+5)^4/3)^*-2+1)$	124933	$(-9-8)*(7-6*((5*(4+3))^2+1))$
89872	$((9+8)+7)*6*(5^4+3^4-2-1)$	124944	$((-9+8)-7)*(6-5^4(4^3/2)+1)$
90128	$((9+8)+7)*6*(5^4-(3^4-2-1))$	124960	$((9-8)+7)*((-6+5^4(4^3/2))+1)$
90516	$(-9-87*65^4)*((-3-2)+1)$	125171	$(9+8)*(7+6*((5*(4+3))^2+1))$
90669	$-9-(8*7+6*(-5-4)^3)*21$	125409	$(-9-8)*(7*(-6*5-4^4(3+2))+1)$
90678	$(-9+8)*-7*6*(5^432-1)$	126150	$(98+76)*5*(4^3)^2+1$
90831	$(9+(87*6)^4(-5+4)+3)/(2+1)$	126469	$98*(7*6*(5/4-32)-1)$
91106	$9*((8+7)^4(-6-(-5-4))^3-2)-1$	126657	$9*(87*6*(5+4)^3-21)$
91143	$9*((8+7)^4(-6-(-5-4))^3+2)^4-1$	126889	$(-9+8)*-7^6+5*(43^2-1)$
91833	$((-9+8)^4-6*(-5-4)^3)*21$	128316	$(9-876)*(-5-((4^3)^2-1))$
92008	$((9+8)+7)*6*(5^4-(3^4-2-1)+1)$	129401	$9+8*(7*6*5+4^4(3^2+1))$
92099	$98-(-7+6/(-5-4)^-3)*21$	129924	$9/8*((7^6-5^432)-1)$
93187	$9*((8+(7-6^5)^4)/-3-2)+1$	130948	$(-9+8)*76*(5+(-4^3)^2+1)$
93804	$((9+8)+7)*((6^5+43)/2-1)$	131243	$(-9+8)*7*(-6/5^4(4-3^2)+1)$
94203	$9*(87*6*5^4+3^4(2+1))$	131726	$98*(7^4(-6+5)+4^43^21)$
94801	$9+8/7*((6*(-5-43))^2-1)$	132196	$98*(7/(-65^4+3))^2-2+1$
95348	$((-9-8^7)/(-6-5)+43)/2+1$	132392	$9/8*(7^6-5)+43-2^4-1$
95562	$-9*(-8-((76-(-5-4))^3)^2+1))$	132393	$9/8*(7^6-5)+43+2^4-1$
95645	$-9*(8/7)*(6+(5^4+3)^2+1))$	132394	$9/8*(7^6-5*(-4-3))-2^4-1$
96513	$(-9^4(-8+7)+6)*(5+4^4(3^2+1))$	132404	$-9/8*(-7^6-((5^4/3)^2-1))$
97780	$98*((7/(-6-5^43))^2+1)$	132575	$(-9+8)*(76-(54-3)^2+1)$
99048	$((9+8)+7)*((6*5+4^4(3^2))+1)$	132761	$9-8*(7*6*5-4^4(3^2+1))$
99477	$((9+8)+7)*(6+54-3)*21$	132796	$((9*(8-7))^6-5)/4-3*21$
100240	$-98*(7^4(-6+5)-4^4(3+2)+1)$	132826	$((9*(8-7))^6-5)/4-32-1$
100268	$98*(7^4(-6+5)+4^4(3+2)-1)$	132827	$((9*(8-7))^6-5)/4-32*1$
100470	$(9*8*7+6)*(5-4^43*(-2-1))$	132828	$((9*(8-7))^6-5)/4-32+1$
101594	$(9*8+7)*(6-5^4-4^4(3+2-1))$	132832	$((9*(8-7))^6-5)/4-3^4(2+1)$
102166	$(-9+8)*-7*(6+5)^4-321$	132835	$((9*(8-7))^6-5)/4-3-21$
103424	$(9/8*7/6+5)/4^4(-3^2-1)$	132866	$((9/(8-7))^6-5)/4+3^2+1$
104160	$9*(8+7/6-5)^4*3^2+1$	132868	$((9*(8-7))^6-5)/4+3^2+1$
104553	$(9/(8*7^6-5^43))^4(-2+1)$	132869	$((9*(8-7))^6-5)/4+3^2+1$
104820	$9*8*((-7/6+(5+4)^3)^2-1)$	132877	$((9*(8-7))^6-5)/4-3+21$
105576	$(9*8*7-6)*((5^43-2)-1)$	132883	$((9/(8-7))^6-5)/4+3+21$
105896	$(-9+8)*-7*(6*5^4+3)^2-1$	132890	$((9/(8-7))^6-5)/4+32-1$
108153	$9*(-8+(7*6-5)*(4+321))$	132892	$((9/(8-7))^6-5)/4+32+1$
109381	$(-9+8)+7*((6-(5-4))^4(3^2)+1)$	133038	$9/8*((7^6+5^4+3)-21)$
109589	$(9*-8*(-765+4)+3)^2-1$	133287	$((9/8+76)-5)^4(43^2-1)$
109591	$(9*-8*(-765+4)+3)^2+1$	133301	$(9-8)*7*((6*(5^4+3))^2-1)$
110345	$(-9*(-8-76)+5)*((4^3)^2+1)$	133663	$-9+8/7*((6*(-54-3))^2-1)$
110884	$(-9+8)*76*((5+4)^3-2-1)$	133681	$9+8/7*((6*(-54-3))^2-1)$
111215	$(9/8+7)*((-6*5^4+3)^2-1)$	133821	$9*(8*7*(6-543/2)+1)$
111688	$(9/(8*(7^6+5^4)^3))^4(-2+1)$	134298	$9/8*((7^6+5^4)^32)-1$
112689	$9+8/7*((6-5^4)^3)^2-1$	134563	$(9*8*(7+6)+5)*((4^3)^2-1)$
113733	$9/8*(7+6^5*(4+3^2)+1)$	134827	$(-9-8)*(7+6^5/((4+3)^2-1))$
114233	$(-9+8)*7*(65-4^4(3^2+1))$	135564	$(-9+87*(6+5))*((4^3)^2-1)$
115271	$9/8*(7*((6+5)^4-3)-2)-1$	136445	$(9*8*(7+6)+5)*((4^3)^2+1)$
115294	$9/8*(7*(6+5)^4-3)-2^4-1$	136759	$98*(7*6*(-5/4-32)-1)$
115295	$9/8*(7*(6+5)^4-3)+2^4-1$	136875	$(9+8^4(-7+6))/(5^4-4/(3+21))$
116836	$(-98+7^6-5*((4^3)^2-1))$	136895	$(9+8/-7)*((-6-5)^4(3^2)-1)$
116862	$-9*8+7^6-5*((4^3)^2-1)$	137124	$(-9+87)*(6*5-(-4^3)^2+1)$
118049	$((-9+8)*7)^6+(5^4)^4(3-2+1)$	138138	$(9+87*(6+5))*((4^3)^2-1)$
118462	$98+7^6+5*((4^3)^2-1)$	138436	$98*((7/(65^4+3))^2-2+1)$
118524	$(98-7/6)*((5*(4+3))^2-1)$	138582	$-9*(87*6*(-5+4^3)/2+1)$
118621	$(9-(87+6-54)^3)^*-2+1$	139260	$9/8*((7+6)^5+4)/3+21$
118769	$987*(6*5^4+3^4(-2+1))$	140641	$9+8+(7*6*(-5-4)+3)^2-1$
119445	$((9-8)*7^6-54^3)*(-2-1)$	140712	$(9+(8+7)*65)*((4^3)^2-1)$
120123	$-9*(8-7*6*(-5^4+3+2)+1)$	140828	$(9-8)*76*((5+43)^2-1)$
120455	$9*8*-7*(6-5*(4+3)^2)-1$	141291	$9*(87+6*((54-3)^2+1))$
120457	$9*8*-7*(6-5*(4+3)^2)+1$	141530	$(9/(87*(6+5)^4+3))^4(-2+1)$
121797	$9*(8-7*6*(5^4+3+2)+1)$	142293	$((-9*8+76/5^4-4)+3)^2(2+1)$
121889	$-9*8+7*((-6-5)^4(3^2)-1)$	142440	$((9+8+76/-5^4-4)+3)^2(-2-1)$
122325	$(9*8*(76+5)-4-3)*21$	142941	$(987-6/5)*((4^3)^2+1)$
122694	$(9-87)*(-6-5)*((4^3)^2-1)$	143143	$(-98+7)*(-6-5)*((4^3)^2-1)$
122843	$(9-8-7)*(6-5^4(3^2))-1$	143283	$(-9+8)*7*(6+5*(-4^4(3^2)+1))$
122877	$(-9/(8-7)+6*(5^4(3^2)+1))$	143437	$(-9+8)*-7*(6+5*(4^4(3^2)+1))$
122901	$(-9/(8-7)+6*5*(4^4(3^2)+1))$	144007	$(9-8)*7-6/(5^4)^-3*(-2-1)$
122964	$(-9+87)-6*(-5^4(3^2)-1)$	145408	$(9/8*7-(6-5))^*-4^4(3^2+1)$
123469	$(9+8/7)*(6+(5^4+3)^2+1)$	145999	$(-9-8^4(-7+6))/(5^4-4)^-3^2-1$
123500	$(-9+8)*-76*5*(4+321)$	146291	$(-9-8)*7+(6+5)^4(3^2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
148511	$(9+8/7)*((6+5)^4+3)-21$	188532	$9*(8*7+6*((5-4^3)^2+1))$
148553	$(9+8/7)*((6+5)^4+3)+21$	192021	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7)*(6*5^4)^3+21$
148816	$(9+8/7)*((6+5)^4+32-1)$	192590	$9*((-8-7)-6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$
150579	$9*(87+6*5)*((4*3)^2-1)$	192592	$9*((-8-7)-6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1$
151000	$(-9*8+7*6^5)*((4/3)^2+1)$	193671	$-9*(87-6*((5*4^3)^2+1))$
151658	$(-9+87)*(6^5/4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	194225	$(9-8)*(-7+6^5)*(4*3^2+1)$
152381	$((98/7+6)^5+4-3)/21$	194393	$(-9+8)*7+6^5*(4*3^2+1)$
152383	$((98/7+6)^5+43)/21$	194407	$(9-8)*7+6^5*(4*3^2+1)$
153603	$(9*8+7)*6^5/4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	194705	$9+8*(((-7-6)^*(5+4+3))^2+1)$
153709	$((-9+8)/7+6)*((54*3)^2-1)$	194949	$9*((8+7)*(6*(5+4/3))^2+1)$
154549	$(-9^{\wedge}(-8+7)+6)/(54*3)^{\wedge}-2+1$	195268	$((9*(8-7)^6*5)^4+3)/21$
156042	$-9*((87-((-6-5)*4*3)^2)-1)$	195889	$9+8/7*((6*(5+4^3))^2-1)$
157824	$-9*(876*5+4)*((-3-2)+1)$	197600	$(9-8)*76*((54-3)^2-1)$
158134	$(9+8)*(7+65*((4*3)^2-1))$	199440	$9*8*((7+6)*5*(5^4+3)+1)$
158644	$(9+8)*(7/6*((5*4)^3-2)+1)$	200158	$(9+8)*7*(((-6-5)*4+3)^2+1)$
159124	$(-9*((8-(7+6)^5)-4)+3)/21$	200411	$(-9^{\wedge}(-8+7)*6+5^4)*321$
159369	$(98*7*(6+5)+43)*21$	200610	$(-9^{\wedge}(8-7)-6+5^4)*321$
159570	$9*(-8-7)*-6*(5-4^{\wedge}3*(-2-1))$	200745	$9*(-8*(7-65^4+3)+2-1)$
159757	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	200763	$-9*((8*(7-65^4+3)-2)-1)$
159859	$(-9*(8+7)-6)+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	200839	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)*6+5^4)*321$
159871	$-9*(8+7)+6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	200977	$-9+8*((7/(-6+54)*3)^2+1)$
160013	$(9-8)*7+6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	200995	$9+8*((7/(-6+54)*3)^2+1)$
160106	$(-9-8)*(7-65*((4*3)^2+1))$	201294	$9/8*((76*5+43)^2-1)$
160129	$(9*(8+7)-6)+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	201613	$-9*(8-7^6/(5+4^{\wedge}(-3+2)))+1$
160141	$9*(8+7)+6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	201755	$9*(8-7^6/((-5-4^{\wedge}(-3+2)))-1$
160243	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	201757	$9*(8-7^6/((-5-4^{\wedge}(-3+2)))+1$
160379	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)+6)/(54*3)^{\wedge}-2-1$	202479	$(9*(8+7*6))^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))-21$
160381	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)+6)/(54*3)^{\wedge}-2+1$	202507	$(9-8)*7+(6*5)^4/(3+2-1)$
161207	$((-9+8)/-7+6)*((54*3)^2-1)$	202518	$9*(8+(7/(-6+54^3))^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
161792	$(9+(8/7)^{\wedge}(-6+5))*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$	202521	$(9*(8+7*6))^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))+21$
162386	$98*((-765-4^{\wedge}3)^*-2-1)$	203371	$(-9-8)*7*(6+5/(-4-3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
163660	$-98*(-7+65-(4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	203850	$(98*7*(6+5)+4)/3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
164285	$-9*(8*-7*(6-5/-4^{\wedge}-3)+2)-1$	204155	$(98+7)*(6^5/4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
164540	$(-9+8)*-7*6*5*(432+1)$	204443	$9*8*(-7-6)/(-5-4^3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
165995	$9*-87*(6*5*(-4-3)-2)-1$	205275	$(9/8+7*6)*((5+4^3)^2-1)$
165997	$9*-87*(6*5*(-4-3)-2)+1$	206315	$9*8*(7+6)-(-5-4^3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
166420	$((9+8)-7)*((65+4^3)^2+1)$	206673	$9/8*(7/6*(54^3+2)-1)$
167757	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5*4)^3*21$	207553	$(-9-8)*(-7*6-(5*4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
168076	$(9-8)*76+(5*4)^3*21$	207797	$(9/((8^{\wedge}7-(65-4)^3)+2))^{\wedge}-1$
168243	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5*4)^3*21$	207909	$-9*((8*76*(5-43)+2)+1)$
169330	$-98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-(4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	208503	$9*(-8*(7*-6*(5+4^3)+2)-1)$
170316	$9*((8+7)*(-6-5^4)+3)*-2/1$	208827	$9/8*((7+6)^5-43)/2-1$
171640	$(98-7*-6)*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$	213000	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))/(5*4)^{\wedge}-3*(-2-1)$
172601	$(-9-8)*(-76+5)*((4*3)^2-1)$	213324	$(98+76)*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$
173217	$(9/(8+7)+6)*((54*3)^2+1)$	214708	$(-9-8)*76-(5*4*-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
174737	$((9+8^{\wedge}7)-65)/(4*3)-21$	214902	$9*8-7*-6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
174779	$((9+8^{\wedge}7)-65)/(4*3)+21$	214963	$98*(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4))*321$
175941	$-9*(-8*7-6*(-54-3)^2+1)$	215178	$-9*8-7*6*5*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
176127	$((9-8)+7)*-6+5*-4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1$	215322	$9*8-7*6*5*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
176719	$(9-8/-7)*(((6-5)*4*3)^2-1)$	215483	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3)^2*-1$
177042	$(9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)-5*(4+3))*2+1$	215567	$((9*8-7^6)-5)*(-4/3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
177252	$(9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)+5*(4+3))*2+1$	215779	$(-9-8)*76+(5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
179965	$9*(-8^{\wedge}(-7+6)+5^4)*32+1$	215826	$(-98-76)+(5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
180035	$-9*(-8^{\wedge}(-7+6)-5^4)*32-1$	215947	$9-(8*7+6)+(5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
180037	$-9*(-8^{\wedge}(-7+6)-5^4)*32+1$	216028	$9-8-7*-6^5*(4-32^{\wedge}-1)$
180210	$-98/7+((-6-5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$	216033	$((9-8)+7)*6+5^4)*321$
180238	$98/7+((-6-5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$	216053	$-9-8*-7+6+(5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
180370	$(9+8)*((76-(5-4)*3)^2+1)$	216174	$98+76+(5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
181090	$-98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-43^2+1)$	216221	$(-9-8)*(-7-6)+(5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
181118	$98*((7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+43^2)-1)$	217087	$((9-8)+7)*6+5*4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1$
181286	$98*((-7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+43^2)+1)$	217089	$((9-8)+7)*6+5*4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1$
182286	$98/(7*6)*5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2-1$	217292	$(9+8)*76-(5*4*-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
182291	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7)*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)*21)$	219000	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))/(5*4)^{\wedge}-3*(-2-1)$
183013	$-9+(8+7^6)*5/(4+3+2)+1$	219121	$-9+8*((7/6+54)*3)^2+1$
183031	$9+(8+7^6)*5/(4+3+2)+1$	219123	$9+8*((7/6+54)*3)^2-1$
183036	$(9+8+7^6)*5/(4+3+2)+1$	219139	$9+8*((7/6+54)*3)^2+1$
184806	$9*((8+7)*(-6*5-4-3)^2-1)$	219384	$9*8*((76*5*4+3)*2+1)$
185465	$98*((7/6-5^4)*-3+21)$	221013	$-9*8*((7-65)/4)^3-21$
187441	$-9+(8/7+6)*((54*3)^2-1)$	222190	$9/8*((-7^{\wedge}6+54^3*2)+1)$
187459	$9+(8/7+6)*((54*3)^2-1)$	222216	$((9+8)*(-7^{\wedge}6+5)+4)/(-3*(2+1))$
187872	$9*8*(((-7+6^5)-4)/3+21)$	224361	$-9*(8*-76*(5+4+32)-1)$
188211	$(9*(-8-7)+6)*((5+4)^3*-2-1)$	225303	$(9*8*7*6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))*(-2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
226413	$-9*(8+7*((6-(5*4*3)^2)-1))$	272529	$(9-8*-7*((6+5)+4))*321$
226793	$(9-8)*7*((-6-54)*3)^2-1$	272574	$(9/-87+6)*((5*43)^2+1)$
227187	$9*(8+7*((6+(5*4*3)^2)-1))$	273524	$(9-8)*76*((5*4*3)^2-1)$
227328	$(9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6)+5)*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$	273978	$-9*(8-7*6*5*((4*3)^2+1))$
228102	$(-9+8)*-7*6*(5432-1)$	274241	$9*(-87+6^{\wedge}5)*(4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
228830	$98*((7*(-6-5)+4)*-32-1)$	275275	$(9-8)*7*((6*5+4)^3+21)$
228956	$98/7*(-6*5+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$	275589	$-9*((8*765+4)*(-3-2)-1)$
229764	$(9/(8^{\wedge}7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4-3)*-2))^{\wedge}-1$	277317	$-9*(-87-6*(5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1))$
229796	$98/7*(6*5+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$	277677	$9*((8*7-6^{\wedge}5)*-4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
229851	$9*(8*((7/6+5*-4)*3)^2+1)$	277811	$-9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(-43+2)/1$
233038	$(9/(8^{\wedge}7+6-5))^{\wedge}(-4+3)+21$	277829	$9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(-43+2)/1$
233191	$-98+(7*(-65-4))^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$	277860	$9*8*7+6*((5*43)^2+1)$
233888	$(9/(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	278088	$9*8*((7+6^{\wedge}5)/(4^{\wedge}-3+2)+1)$
234293	$9-((8+7)*6-5^{\wedge}(4*3/2))^{\wedge}+1$	278163	$9*((8*7-6^{\wedge}5)*-4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
234475	$9+(8+7)*(6+5^{\wedge}(4*3/2))^{\wedge}+1$	281853	$9*((8*7*6*5*4*3-2)-1)$
234501	$((-9+8)*7*6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	282138	$(9/87+6)*((5*43)^2+1)$
234644	$(9/(8^{\wedge}7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	282900	$9*8*(7/6-5)*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
235085	$(-9*8+7^{\wedge}6+5*(-4-3))^{\wedge}+21$	283473	$-9/((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(-54^{\wedge}3-21)$
236243	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)-6*5^{\wedge}4)*-3*21$	284715	$9/(8*7)*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4*3/2)-1)$
236257	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)+6*5^{\wedge}4)*3*21$	287705	$(-9+8)*7+6^{\wedge}5*(4+3+2)+1$
237393	$9*(8*7*((-6-5)*-43-2)+1)$	288777	$(-9/((8-(7+6)^{\wedge}5)*(4+3)+2))^{\wedge}-1$
237626	$((-9+8*7+6)+5)*4^{\wedge}(3^2)+1$	289380	$(98-7)*6*((5*4+3)^2+1)$
239992	$(9/(8*((-7+(6*5)^{\wedge}4/3)-2))^{\wedge}-1)$	290083	$(9*87*(6^{\wedge}5+4)+3)/21$
239994	$(9/(-8*(7-(6*5)^{\wedge}4/3)+2))^{\wedge}-1$	290331	$9*(8*((7/6-5*-4)*3)^2+1)$
240462	$9*876*((-5+4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$	292001	$((9*8+7)-6)*5*(5*4)^3/2+1$
240984	$-9*8*((7-(6+5+4)^3)+21)$	292581	$9-(8/7*-6^{\wedge}5/43)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
241187	$(9-8)*7+(6^{\wedge}5+4)*32-1$	294420	$9*8*((-7/6*5+4^{\wedge}(3*2))-1)$
243447	$(9*8*7*6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	295404	$9*8*((7/6*5+4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1)$
243591	$-9+8*7*6*5*((4*3)^2+1)$	297676	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*5*(4+3)^2+1$
243609	$9+8*7*6*5*((4*3)^2+1)$	297918	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*5*(4+3)^2+1$
244112	$(9/(8+(76+54)^3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	298113	$((98-7)*6)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))-2+1$
245337	$((-9+8)^{\wedge}7-6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$	298119	$((98-7)*6)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))+2+1$
245392	$98*(-7+6-5^{\wedge}4)*(-3-2)+1$	298570	$((-9*8-7)+6)*5(-4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
248390	$(9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)*(5+4/3))/2+1$	299300	$(9*8+7)-6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
249165	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6)/(5/4+3)+2)-1$	299446	$((9*8+7)-6)*5(-4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
250502	$(9/8+76)*((54+3)^2-1)$	299736	$9*8*((7+6)*5*4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
251220	$(9*8+7)*6*((5*4+3)^2+1)$	302472	$9*-8*(7*6*5*4*(-3-2)-1)$
251732	$(-9/8+7)*((6-5-4)*3)^2-1$	306450	$(9+8*765)*((4+3)^2+1)$
251766	$-9*((8+7*(6-(5*4)^3))/2+1)$	307517	$(9+8)*7-((6+5)^{\wedge}4-3)*-21$
252162	$9*((-8+7*(6+(5*4)^3))/2+1)$	308693	$(9-8)*7*((6*5*(4+3))^2-1)$
252432	$9*8*((-76-5^{\wedge}4)*(-3-2)+1)$	308707	$(-9+8)*-7*(6*5*(4+3))^2+1$
252782	$(-9-((8*(7-(6-5))^{\wedge}4-3)))/-21$	309248	$(9/8*7+6+5)/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
254736	$9*8*(-7+65)*(4^{\wedge}3-2)-1$	309270	$(9-87)*-65*((4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$
254915	$9+8*((7*6*(5/4+3))^2+1)$	311343	$(9*(8*7+6))^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3-21$
257257	$(9-8)*7+6*(5*(4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	311362	$(9*(8*7+6))^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))-2/1$
257652	$9*(8*7+6*((5+4^{\wedge}3)^2+1))$	311367	$(9*(8*7+6))^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))+2+1$
257724	$9*((-8+7)-6)*5(-4^{\wedge}(3*2))-1$	312315	$-9-8*((7*6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$
257742	$-9*((8-7)+6)*5(-4^{\wedge}(3*2))-1$	312331	$-9-8*((7*6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2-1)$
258372	$9*((8-7)+6)*5(4+3)^2+1$	312349	$9-8*((7*6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2-1)$
258990	$(9/(8+7))*((654+3)^2+1)$	312667	$-9+8*((7*6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$
259639	$((98/7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(-4+3+2+1)$	312685	$9+8*((7*6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$
261289	$-9*((-8-7)*-6+5)+4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$	313455	$((98-7^{\wedge}6)+5)*4/-3*2-1$
261867	$(9-8*7)*6+5+4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$	313456	$((98-7^{\wedge}6)+5)*4/3*-2*1$
261880	$((9+8)+7)*(-6-5)+4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$	313457	$((98-7^{\wedge}6)+5)*4/-3*2+1$
261896	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-5+4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1)))$	315065	$9+8*7*((6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^2+1)$
261906	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+5+4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$	317118	$(-9-8)*7*(6*5*(43-2)+1)$
262382	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-5(-4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1)))$	320247	$9*(8/7*(6^{\wedge}5*4+32)-1)$
262421	$(9-8*7)*-6-5+4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$	321135	$(9*-8-7)*((6*5-4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1)$
262913	$(9/(-87+6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^2))^{\wedge}-1$	321536	$(9/8*(7+6)+5)*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
262999	$9*((-8-7)*-6+5)+4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$	324007	$(9-8)*7+(6*5)^{\wedge}4/(3/2+1)$
263448	$-9*(8+7-((6+5)^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$	326033	$(9*8+7)*((6*5+4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1)$
263940	$(9*8*7-6)*((5*4+3)^2+1)$	327573	$9*8*(-7-6)+5(4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
264632	$(9-8)*76*((5-4^{\wedge}3)^2+1)$	327638	$(-9+8)*7*6-5*-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
264897	$9*((8+7)*654*3+2)+1$	327667	$(-9+8)*7(6+5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
264933	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3)+21$	327693	$(-9+87)/6-5*-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
265932	$9*(8*76-5)*(4+3)^2+1$	327722	$(9-8)*7*6+5*4^{\wedge}(3/2-1)$
266182	$(9-8)*7+65*(4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	327987	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}-4+3)*-2-1$
266296	$(-9/(8-7)+65*(4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1))$	330032	$(9/(8*((7+6)^{\wedge}5-4-3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
270300	$(9*8*7+6)*((5*4+3)^2+1)$	330035	$(9/(8*((7+6)^{\wedge}5-4+3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
270742	$(9+8)*((7+6)*5*(4+3))^2+1$	331614	$(9-8)/7*6*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^2-1)$
271890	$(-9+8*7*6)*((5*4+3)^2+1)$	333577	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6+(5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
272293	$(-9+8)*7*((-6^{\wedge}5-4)*(3+2)+1)$	333721	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6+(5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
333900	$(98+7)*6*((5*4+3)^2+1)$	388695	$-98-(7-6^5*((4+3)^2+1))$
338817	$9-8*(7^6-(5*4)^{(3+2-1)})$	388704	$-9-(87-6^5*((4+3)^2+1))$
341836	$((9-8)*-7+6^5)^{(43+2-1)}$	388722	$9-(87-6^5*((4+3)^2+1))$
341894	$(9-8)*7*((6-5*-43)^2+1)$	388740	$(-9+8)*-76*5*(4^4(3+2)-1)$
342057	$9-8*7*6*(5-4^4(3+2)+1)$	388753	$9-(8*7-6^5*((4+3)^2+1))$
342137	$(-9+8)*7+6^5*(43+2-1)$	388847	$-9-8*-7+6^5*((4+3)^2+1)$
342954	$9*8*7*(6+5*(3^2-1))$	388896	$9+8+6^5*((4+3)^2+1)$
344322	$9*(8+765*((4+3)^2+1))$	388905	$98+7+6^5*((4+3)^2+1)$
345417	$9-8*-7*6*(5-(-4^4(3+2)+1))$	391758	$9*(8^7-6^5)/((4+3)^2-1)$
346071	$-9-8*7*-6*(5+4^4(3+2)+1)$	392771	$-9+((8+7)^6-5)/(-4+32+1)$
346089	$9-8*-7*6*(5+4^4(3+2)+1)$	392789	$9+((8+7)^6-5)/(-4+32+1)$
347142	$-9*((-8+7-(6*5)^4)+3)/21$	393051	$-9*(8+7)-6*(5-4^4(3^2-1))$
347148	$-9*((-8-7-(6*5)^4)+3)/21$	393177	$(-9/(8-7))-6*(5-4^4(3^2-1)))$
347383	$-9*(8+7/-6*((5*4^4-3)^2-1))$	393179	$(-9+8)*7-6*(5-4^4(3^2-1))$
348126	$(-9-8)*((7-6-5*4^4(3^2))+1)$	393239	$(-9+8)*7+6*(5+4^4(3^2-1))$
348140	$(9/8+7)*(((65-4)*3)^2-1)$	393253	$(9-8)*7+6*(5+4^4(3^2-1))$
348398	$(9+8)*((7+6-5*-4^4(3^2))+1)$	393293	$(-9+8*7+6*(5+4^4(3^2-1)))$
348525	$-9*((8+7)+6)*5(43^2-1)$	393381	$9*(8+7)+6*(5+4^4(3^2-1))$
348564	$9*(8*7+6)*5(4^4-3^4(-2+1))$	394674	$9*(8^7+6^5)/((4+3)^2-1)$
348936	$9*(8*7+6)*5(4^4+3^4(-2+1))$	397089	$9/8*(7^6/((5-4)/3)+21)$
349227	$-9*((8*7-(6^5-4)*3+2)+1)$	398556	$((9*(8-7))^6-5)/4*3-21$
350289	$9*((8+7)*6^5+4)/3+21$	398568	$((9*(8-7))^6-5)/4-3*(2+1)$
350649	$9*((8+7)/6)*5(43^2-1)$	398586	$((9/(8-7))^6-5)/4+3*(2+1)$
350664	$-9*8*((7-(6+5)^4/3+2)+1)$	398598	$((9*(8-7))^6-5)/4*3+21$
352104	$9*8*((7+(6+5)^4/3+2)+1)$	399520	$98*(7^4(-6+5)-4^4)^2-1$
354172	$98*((7+6+(5*4^3)^2)+1)$	399716	$98*(7^4(-6+5)-4^4)^2+1$
354571	$(-9+8)*-7*(6*5+4+3)^{(2+1)}$	399742	$-98*((7+6)+5-4^4(3^2))-1$
356238	$9*((87*65*(4+3)-2)-1)$	399806	$(9+8)*((-7^6+54)/(-3-2))-1$
356292	$9*((87*65*(4+3)+2)+1)$	400725	$(98-7^4(-6+5))*4^4(3^2)-1$
356405	$(-9/8+76)*5(4^4+3)^2-1$	401296	$-98*(7^4(-6+5)-4^4(3^2)+1)$
356736	$9/8*7*(((-6+5^4)*3)^2-1)$	401324	$98*(7^4(-6+5)+4^4(3^2))-1$
357014	$-98*((-7*6-(5*4^3)^2)-1)$	401393	$-98*(7^4(-6+5)-4^4(3^2))-1$
357689	$(-9+8)*7+6^5*((43+2)+1)$	401395	$-98*(7^4(-6+5)-4^4(3^2))+1$
358900	$9*((8+7)+6)+5*(43^2+1)$	401421	$98*(7^4(-6+5)+4^4(3^2))-1$
362144	$9+(8-7)^6)^5+4^4(3*(2+1))$	401423	$98*(7^4(-6+5)+4^4(3^2))+1$
363240	$9*-8*(76-5*4^4(3+2)-1)$	401492	$98*((-7^4(-6+5)+4^4(3^2))+1)$
363653	$(9+8/-7+6)*5(4^4+3)^2-1$	401520	$98*(7^4(-6+5)+4^4(3^2)+1)$
363881	$(-9+8)*-7*((6*(5-43))^2-1)$	401715	$-9*(8/7*(6-5^4(4+3)/2)+1)$
363895	$(9-8)*7*((6*(5-43))^2+1)$	401733	$9*(8/7*(-6+5^4(4+3)/2)+1)$
367115	$(9/8+76)*5(4^4+3)^2-1$	403300	$98*(7^4(-6+5)+4^4)^2+1$
368055	$9*(8-7*(6^5/4+3)*(-2-1))$	404320	$(-9+8)*7*(6^5-4^4(3^2-1))$
369549	$9/8*(((-7-6)*-5+4)^3-21)$	406017	$9*((8*7+(6+5)*4^4(3^2))+1)$
370832	$98*(7-6*-5^4+3^4(2+1))$	406511	$(9*8*(7+6)+5)*432-1$
373734	$9*(8+7^6)/((5-4/3)/2+1)$	406513	$(9*8*(7+6)+5)*432+1$
374040	$9*8*(76-5*-4^4(3+2)-1)$	415683	$9*(8*76^4((-5+4)+3)-21)$
374125	$(9*8+7-6)*5*(4^4(3+2)+1)$	415737	$9*(8*(76^4(-5+4+3)-2)+1)$
374184	$9*8*(76-(-5*4^4(3+2)-1))$	415899	$9*((8/76^4(5-4-3)+2)+1)$
374517	$(9-8*7*-6^5)*((4^4)^2-1)$	419179	$((9+8^4)-6)/5+4*-3^2*21$
374523	$9*(8-76)^4((-5+4)+3)-21$	423108	$9*876*(54-3^4(-2+1))$
374542	$((9*(8-76))^4((-5+4)+3)-2)/1$	423637	$(9-8/-7+6)*5(4^4+3)^2-1$
374546	$(9*(8-76))^4((-5+4)+3)+2/1$	425444	$9*876*(54-3^4(-2-1))$
374565	$(9*(8-76))^4((-5+4)+3)+21$	426028	$9*876*(54+3^4(-2-1))$
374880	$((9+8)+7)*((-6+5^4(4^3/2))+1)$	426540	$(9+8^4-6)/(-5-(4^3)^4(-2+1))$
375120	$((9+8)+7)*((6+5^4(4^3/2))-1)$	427386	$(9*8/7+6)*5(4^4+3)^2-1$
375154	$(9-(((8-7)+6)^5)^4)/(-3-2+1)$	427950	$(9*8+6^5)*((4+3)^2+1)$
375156	$9*(-8+7*6)*5(4^4+3)^2+1$	428364	$9*876*(54+3^4(-2+1))$
375168	$((9+8)+7)*6(5^4(4^3/2)+1)$	428741	$-9+(((8-7)+6)^5)^4/(3+2^4-1)$
375329	$(9*8+7)*((-6-5)*-432-1)$	428759	$9+(((8-7)+6)^5)^4/(3+2^4-1)$
375822	$9/8*(((-7+6^5)^4*43-2)-1)$	429300	$9*(8+7)*6*(5^4+3)^2+1$
376479	$9/8*(((-7-6^5)^4*43-21)$	430176	$-9+((8+7)+6)*-5*(-4^4(3^2)-1)$
380184	$((9-8)+7)*((654/3)^2-1)$	430194	$9+((8+7)+6)*-5*(-4^4(3^2)-1)$
380200	$((9-8)+7)*((654/3)^2+1)$	431134	$((-9*8+7^6)+5)*4(3^2+1)$
384146	$(-9+8)*-7*(6-(5-43)^{(2+1)})$	431586	$-9*((8-((7*(-6-5)+4)^3)^2)-1)$
384639	$-9+8*(7*6+5)*4^4(3+2)-1$	431712	$9*((8+((7*(-6-5)+4)^3)^2)-1)$
384657	$9+8*(7*6+5)*4^4(3+2)-1$	436829	$((-9+8)/6)^5+4^4(3^2-1)$
385002	$9/8*((7*6+543)^2-1)$	438031	$-9+8*(((-7-6)^5*54/3)^2-1)$
385391	$-9-8*(7*6+5)*(-4^4(3+2)-1)$	439008	$(9+8^4(-6-(-5-4)))/3*2*1$
385409	$9-8*(7*6+5)*(-4^4(3+2)-1)$	439009	$(9+8^4(-6-(-5-4)))/3*2+1$
385533	$9*((8*765*(4+3)-2)-1)$	439272	$9*8*(-7-6*(5-4^4(3+2)+1))$
385587	$9*((8*765*(4+3)+2)+1)$	440055	$9*((-8-76*5^4)*-32-1)$
388332	$(-9+8)*-7*6*(5/43^4-2+1)$	440791	$-9+8*76*5*(4^4)^2+1$
388450	$((9-8)*-7+6^5)*((4+3)^2+1)$	440809	$9+8*76*5*(4^4)^2+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
442143	$-9+8/7*((6-5^4-3)^2-1)$	541544	$(9-8)/7*((6^5/4+3)^2-1)$
445464	$9*8*(7+6*(5+4^(3+2)+1))$	542188	$(9/(8+(7*6+5)^4+3))^{(-2+1)}$
448092	$-9^((8+7)/6)/(5-43^2)^{-1}$	542437	$(-9-((8+7)^6+543))/-21$
449433	$9+8/7*6*(5+4^(3^2-1))$	546012	$9*87*((6+5)^4+3)/21$
451976	$98*(7*((654+3)+2)-1)$	546534	$9/8*((7+(-6-5)*4^3)^2-1)$
452790	$9*(8+7)*((6-(-5-4))^3-21)$	546770	$(9-8)*7*((6+5^4(4+3))-21)$
455520	$(9-8)/7*6*((5+4)^(3*2)-1)$	551700	$9*(8*7-6)*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$
457555	$(9/((-8-7^6)*5*(4+3)))^{(-2+1)}$	552600	$9*8*(7+6^5-4*3^(2+1))$
457920	$(-9-8*-7+6)*5*(4*3)^(2+1)$	553113	$-9*((8+7)*(-6/5-4^4(3*2))+1)$
458297	$(-9+8)*7*(65-4^4(3^2-1))$	554040	$(9-8*(7+6))*54/(-3)^(2+1)$
458542	$(-9+8)*-7*(-6*5+4^4(3^2-1))$	555631	$-9+((8+7)^6-5)/(43/2-1)$
458675	$(-9+8)*7*(6+5-4^4(3^2-1))$	555649	$9+((8+7)^6-5)/(43/2-1)$
458717	$((-9+8)^7-6)*5-4^4(3^2-1)$	556556	$(-9+8)*-7*(6-5+43^2(2+1))$
458759	$(-9+8)*-7*(6-5+4^4(3^2-1))$	556626	$(-9+8)*7*((6-5-43^2(2+1))$
458787	$((9-8)^7+6)*5+4^4(3^2-1)$	562569	$(98+7^6)*5+4/(3-21)$
458829	$(-9+8)*-7*(6+5+4^4(3^2-1))$	565704	$((98-7)+6)*54/3)^(2+1)$
458962	$(-9+8)*7*(-6*5-4^4(3^2-1))$	567144	$9*-8*(7-6^5-4*3^2(2+1))$
459207	$(-9+8)*-7*(65+4^4(3^2-1))$	568601	$9*(8*7+6)*(-5+4^4(3+2))-1$
460306	$98*7*(6+5)*((4^3-2)-1)$	568603	$9*(8*7+6)*(-5+4^4(3+2))+1$
460331	$(-9+8)*7^6*5+4^4(3^2+1)$	568710	$9/8*((7+(-6-5)*-4^3)^2-1)$
462350	$(9-8)*7*((-65*4+3)^2+1)$	568751	$-9-8/-7*((6^5*4^3+2)-1)$
462851	$-9+8/7*((6^5)^4+3)/2+1$	568769	$9-8/-7*((6^5*4^3+2)-1)$
462869	$9+8/7*((6^5)^4+3)/2+1$	570262	$-98*(7+6-(54/3)^(2+1))$
463185	$9*(8+7*(6*(5*(4+3))^2+1))$	571032	$-9*8*(7+6^5/(4+3)^2-1)$
463356	$9*(-8+7*6*((5*(4+3))^2+1))$	571861	$(-9+8)*7^6*5-4^4(3^2+1)$
465057	$9/8*(7*(6+(5+4)^(3+2))-1)$	573480	$9*(-8-7)*6*((-5-4)^3+21)$
465066	$9/8*7*(6+(5+4)^(3+2)+1)$	573768	$(-9+87)*6*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$
466033	$(9/(8^7+6-5))^{(-4+3)*2-1}$	576408	$-987*(65*((-4-3)-2)+1)$
466035	$(9/(8^7+6-5))^{(-4+3)*2+1}$	577385	$(9-8/(7*6))*5+4^4(3^2-1)$
467758	$-98+(76*(-5-4))^{(-3-2)+1}$	578574	$(9+(8+7)*((6^5)^4+3))/21$
469809	$-9*(87*6*5*4*(-3-2)-1)$	581124	$(9*8+7)*6*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$
472997	$(-9+8)*7^6*(-5-((4+3)^{-2-1}))$	583110	$(9*8+7*6)*-5*(-4^4(3+2)+1)$
473013	$9*((876*5*4*3-2)-1)$	583566	$(9*8+7*6)*5*(4^4(3+2)-1)$
473200	$(-9+8)*-7*(65^4)^(3-2)+1$	584250	$(9*8+7*6)*5*(4^4(3+2)+1)$
474329	$(-9+8)*7+6^5*(4^3-(2+1))$	585328	$(9-87^4(-6+5+4))^3(3^2-1)$
475250	$(9+8-7)*((654/3)^2+1)$	585344	$(-9-87^4(-6+5+4))^3(3^2-1)$
476933	$(-9*8-7+6*(-5+43^2(2+1)))$	585501	$98*7/6*(5*4^4(3+2)+1)$
477091	$9*8+7+6*(-5+43^2(2+1))$	586517	$(-9+8)*7^6*5-4*(3)^(2+1)$
477151	$9*8+7-6*(-5-43^2(2+1))$	587298	$-9*(8-7^6-5^4(4+3))/(2+1)$
478764	$-9*(8-76^5)*((4*3)^2-1)$	589785	$9*(8*-7/6+5+4^4(3^2-1))$
482832	$9*8*7*(-65+4^4(3+2)-1)$	589863	$-9*(8*-7/6+5-4^4(3^2-1))$
483264	$9*-8*(7*(65-4^4(3+2))+1)$	589973	$(-9+8)*7^6*5-4*(3)^(2+1)$
483345	$9*(8*7*(-65+4^4(3+2))+1)$	591336	$9*8*((76*-54-3)*-2-1)$
483408	$9*8*(-7*(65-4^4(3+2))+1)$	597920	$(9*8+7)*6^5-4^4(3^2+1)$
483446	$((9+8*(7+6))+5)*4^4(3^2+1)$	602353	$(9-8/(-7*6))*5+4^4(3^2-1)$
484190	$(9-8)*7*((65^4+3)^2+1)$	604629	$(-9+8)*7^6*5-4^4(3^2+1)$
491513	$((-9+8)*7+6*5*4^4(3^2+1))$	606241	$(9/8*(7-65)^4+3)/21$
493303	$-9+8/7*((654+3)^2-1)$	607772	$(9-8)*7^6*((5*4)^3-2)-1$
493321	$9+8/7*((654+3)^2-1)$	608228	$(-9+8)*-76*((5*4)^3+2)+1$
495828	$-9*(8+76*5*((4*3)^2+1))$	610713	$9*((87*65*4*3-2)-1)$
495972	$9*(8+76*5*((4*3)^2+1))$	610767	$9*((87*65*4*3+2)+1)$
496774	$(9/((-8-7^6)*5-43))^{(-2+1)}$	613440	$((9*8-7)+6)*5/(4*3)^{(-2-1)}$
505656	$9*((8+7)*6/5^4-4-3)-21$	614397	$(-9/(8-7)+6*((5*4^3)^2+1))$
510714	$9/8*(7-((65-4)^3*-2+1))$	615204	$9/8*(7*((-6+5^4(4+3))+2)+1)$
512928	$-9*(8+76*((-5-4)^3-21))$	615267	$9/8*(7*((6+5^4(4+3))-2)+1)$
513072	$9*(8-76*((-5-4)^3-21))$	620194	$(9+8)*((7*6+5)*4+3)^2+1$
513184	$(-9+8)*-7*(6^5+4^4(3^2-1))$	622152	$9*8*(7-6-5*(-4*3)^2(2+1))$
518424	$((9+8)+7)*6*(5*4*3)^2+1$	623907	$9*((8*7*(-6+5^4)-3)*2+1)$
524051	$(9-8^4(-7+6))*((5+4)^(3+2)-1)$	623997	$-9*((8*7*(-6+5^4)+3)*-2+1)$
525393	$9*8*7*(6+5)*((4^3-2)-1)$	627217	$9+8*((7*6*5*4/3)^2+1)$
526827	$9/((8*7)^4(6-5-4)^3)-21$	627425	$((9+8*(-7^6+5))+4)/-3*2-1$
526869	$9/((8*7)^4(6-5-4)^3)+21$	627427	$(9+8*(-7^6+5))+4/-3*2+1$
527355	$9/8*(7-6*5^4(4+3)+2+1)$	628938	$(-9-87*-6)*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$
530730	$-9/((-8+7)+6)*(-543^2-1)$	630688	$(9*8+7)*6^5+4^4(3^2+1)$
531599	$(9+(8+7)/6)*((5*43)^2+1)$	633864	$98*7*((6-5)+43)*21$
531683	$9^4((8+7)/6)+(5+4)^(3*2)-1$	636003	$9*((8*7*(-6-5^4)+3)*-2+1)$
532610	$((9+8*7)+65)*4^4(3^2+1)$	636093	$-9*((8*7*(-6-5^4)-3)*2+1)$
535500	$(-9-8)*7*6*((-5-4)^3-21)$	637812	$(9*(8+7)^4(-6-(-5-4))-3)*21$
536311	$(-9/(8-(7+6)^(5+4-3+2)))^{-1}$	637938	$(9*(8+7)^4(-6-(-5-4))+3)*21$
538813	$(9+8^4(-7+6))*((5+4)^(3+2)-1)$	639963	$-9+87*6*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$
539181	$-9*((8+7)*6-(5*4)^3/2)+1$	639981	$9+87*6*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$
540819	$9*((8+7)*6+(5*4)^3/2)+1$	646816	$(9+8)*7^6*5-4^4(3^2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
647352	$((9+8+7)+6) * (54/3)^{(2+1)}$	748510	$(9-8) * 7 * ((6 * 54+3)^{2+1})$
647654	$9 * 8 * 7 * ((6 / (5 * 43))^{2+1})$	754974	$((9+8^7)-6-5) / ((4/3)^{2+1})$
651006	$(9-8 * 7 * -6) * ((5 * (4+3))^{2+1})$	761049	$9 * ((87 * 6 * 54 * 3 - 2) - 1)$
651264	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)-6) * (-5-43)^{(2+1)}$	762183	$9 * (8-7 * (-6^{\wedge}5-4321))$
651695	$(9-8/7) * ((6 * (5+43))^{\wedge}2-1)$	762552	$9 * 8 * ((-7-6 * 54) * -32-1)$
655348	$(9+8-7) * (-6/5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	763776	$9 * 8 * ((76 - (-5-4) * 3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
655372	$(-9-8+7) * (-6/5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	764686	$((9-8) * 7^{\wedge}6-5) * (4+3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
655445	$(-9+8) * -7 * ((6 * (54-3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	765378	$-9 * (8+7 * -6^{\wedge}5 * ((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1))$
655459	$(9-8) * 7 * ((6 * (54-3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	771111	$9 * (8 * -765 * (-4 * 3 - 2) - 1)$
655707	$(9+8) / 7 * ((6 * 5)^{\wedge}4 / 3 - 2 - 1)$	772380	$(98+7) * 6 * ((5 * (4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
656084	$9 / 8 * ((765-4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	773145	$9 / 8 * ((765+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
656097	$((9 * (-8-7) * 6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3) - 2) - 1$	773190	$9 * (((-8-7)-6) * (5-4^{\wedge}(3 * 2)) - 1)$
656098	$((9 * (-8-7) * 6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3) - 2) * 1$	773208	$-9 * (((8+7)+6) * (5-4^{\wedge}(3 * 2)) - 1)$
656102	$(9 * (-8-7) * 6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3) + 2 * 1$	774291	$(-9+8) * 7 * ((6-54)^{\wedge}3 - 21)$
656103	$(9 * (-8-7) * 6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3) + 2 + 1$	774675	$(9-8/7) * ((6-5/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
658377	$9 / 8 * ((765 * (4-3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	775080	$9 * (((8+7)+6) * (5+4^{\wedge}(3 * 2)) - 1)$
659151	$-9 + (-8-7) * ((6+5)^{\wedge}4 * -3-21)$	775098	$9 * (((8+7)+6) * (5+4^{\wedge}(3 * 2)) + 1)$
660933	$9 * ((8 * 765 * 4 * 3 - 2) - 1)$	777238	$-98 * (7+6^{\wedge}5 / ((4+3)^{\wedge}-2-1))$
660987	$9 * ((8 * 765 * 4 * 3 + 2) + 1)$	779085	$9 * -87 * (6 * 5 - 4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
661134	$(-9+8) * (7-65^{\wedge}4) * 3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	782595	$(-9+8) * 765 * (-4^{\wedge}(3+2) + 1)$
663318	$-9 * (8 + ((7+6)+5) * (-4^{\wedge}(3 * 2) + 1))$	783314	$-98 * (7 + ((-6-54)/3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
663462	$9 * (8 + ((7+6)+5) * (4^{\wedge}(3 * 2) - 1))$	787440	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)+6) / (54 - (-3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$
663642	$9 * (-8 + ((7+6)+5) * (4^{\wedge}(3 * 2) + 1))$	788139	$9 / 8 * ((7 * 6 * 5 * 4 - 3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
663786	$9 * (8 + ((7+6)+5) * (4^{\wedge}(3 * 2) + 1))$	794623	$(9 * ((8+7)+6) + 5) * 4^{\wedge}(3 * 2) - 1$
664418	$(9+8/7) * (-6 * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	794625	$(9 * ((8+7)+6) + 5) * 4^{\wedge}(3 * 2) + 1$
666635	$((9+8) * (-7^{\wedge}6+5+43) / (-2-1))$	796322	$98 * (7 / (6+5^{\wedge}4))^{\wedge}(-3+2-1)$
667870	$98 * (7 * 6 + 5) * ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	799479	$9 / 8 * ((7 * 6 * 5 * 4 + 3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
669396	$(98-7) * 6 * ((5 * (4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	803214	$-9 * (-8 - ((7+6 * 5)^{\wedge}4 - 3)) / 21$
673776	$9 * 8 / 7 * (-6 * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	807126	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)+6) / (54 + (-3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$
674926	$98 * (7 * -6 * (-54 * 3 - 2) - 1)$	810852	$98 * 7 * 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3 * (-2-1))$
678096	$-9 * 8 * (7-65 * ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2+1))$	817377	$(9+8) * (7 * 6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
679104	$9 * 8 * (7+65 * ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2+1))$	818741	$(-9+8) * -7 * ((6 * (54+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
680544	$9 * 8 * ((7+6) * ((5+4)^{\wedge}3 - 2) + 1)$	818755	$(9-8) * 7 * ((6 * (54+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
683784	$9 * -8 * (7-6^{\wedge}5 + (-4 * 3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	819291	$(9/8 * 7 + 6) * ((5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
684144	$9 * 8 * ((7+6) * ((5+4)^{\wedge}3 + 2) - 1)$	825125	$(9 * (8+7) * 6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}(3+2) + 1)$
684441	$-9/8 * ((7 - (65 * 4 * 3)^{\wedge}2) + 1)$	833745	$(9 * (8+7) * -6 - 5) * (-4^{\wedge}(3+2) + 1)$
684792	$9 * 8 * (7+6^{\wedge}5 - (-4 * 3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	833985	$9 / 8 * ((7 * (6 * 5 * 4 + 3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
700443	$-9 * (8 * 7 * 6 * 5 - 43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	835375	$(9 * (-8-7) * -6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}(3+2) + 1)$
700548	$(9 * (87+6))^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3) - 21$	836115	$((-9+8) * 7)^{\wedge}6 - 54^{\wedge}3 * -21$
700590	$(9 * (87+6))^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3) + 21$	842544	$9 * (8 / -7 * (6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}(3 * 2 + 1)))$
702240	$(-9+8) * -76 * 5 * (43^{\wedge}2-1)$	843876	$9 * ((8+7+6 * 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3 / 2)) - 1)$
702852	$9 * ((-8 * 7 / 6 + 5^{\wedge}(4+3)) - 21)$	863577	$9 / 8 * (7+6) * ((5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
703014	$-9 * (8 * 7 / 6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3) + 2 + 1)$	869184	$((9 * 8 * 7 - 6) + 5) * (4 * 3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
703236	$9 * (8 * 7 / 6 + 5^{\wedge}(4+3) + 2 + 1)$	872640	$((9 * 8 * 7 + 6) - 5) / (4 * 3)^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
703398	$9 * ((8 * 7 / 6 + 5^{\wedge}(4+3)) + 21)$	876094	$(9 * 8 * (7+6))^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3) - 2^{\wedge}1$
703731	$98 * ((-6+5 / (4 * 3)^{\wedge}2-1))$	876098	$(9 * 8 * (7+6))^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3) + 2^{\wedge}1$
705678	$9 * 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 / (5+4+3) - 2) - 1)$	877219	$(-9+8) * -7 * ((6 * (5-4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
706110	$9 * 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 / (5+4+3) + 2) + 1)$	878034	$(-9 + (8 * 7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)) * (3+2) - 1$
707004	$9 * ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	878035	$(-9 + (8 * 7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)) * (3+2^{\wedge}1)$
710883	$9 * (8 * (-7-6) * 5 + 43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	878036	$(-9 + (8 * 7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)) * (3+2) + 1$
711916	$(9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4) / (3+2-1)$	878124	$(9 + (8 * 7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)) * (3+2) - 1$
712800	$9 * (8+7/6) * 5 * (4 * 3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	878125	$((-9 - (8 * 7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)) * (3+2)) * -1$
716835	$(9-8) * -7 * ((-6 - (5 * 4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2) + 1)$	878126	$(9 + (8 * 7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)) * (3+2) + 1$
720243	$-9 * (8 * (-7-6) * 5 - 43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	882330	$((9-8) * 7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
721294	$(9-8) * 7 * ((-6 * 54+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	883872	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7) * 6^{\wedge}5 * (4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
721800	$9 / 8 * (((7+65 * 4) * 3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	886437	$9 * ((8 * 76 * 54 * 3 - 2) - 1)$
725547	$(9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6)) * (5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	886491	$9 * ((8 * 76 * 54 * 3 + 2) + 1)$
726852	$(-9-8) * 7 * 6 * (5 - (4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1))$	888489	$9 * (87 * 6 * (5+4) + 3) * 21$
727040	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6)) * -5/4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1)$	889920	$(9 * 8 * -7 - 6 - 5) * (-4 * 3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
727488	$9 * 8 * (7 - ((6+5)+4)^{\wedge}3) * (-2-1)$	900007	$(9-8) * 7 + (6 * 5)^{\wedge}4 * (3^{\wedge}-2+1)$
727549	$(-9-8) * (7 * 6 * (5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)) + 1)$	902037	$(9 / ((8+7^{\wedge}6) * (5+4^{\wedge}3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
730440	$9 * 8 * ((-7+6 * 54) * 32+1)$	903550	$-9 - ((8 - (7-65))^{\wedge}4 + 3) / -21$
730512	$9 * 8 * (7 + ((6+5)+4)^{\wedge}3) * (2+1)$	903568	$9 - ((8 - (7-65))^{\wedge}4 + 3) / -21$
730683	$9 * (8 * 7 * 6 * 5 + 43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	905184	$9 / 8 * (((-7-6) * (5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
731660	$(9-87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)) * (-3^{\wedge}-2-1)$	907193	$(9-8) * 7 * ((6 * 5 * 4 * 3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
731680	$(9-87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)) * (-3^{\wedge}-2-1)$	908211	$(9-8/7+6) * (5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
733992	$(-9-8) * -7 * 6 * (5+4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$	908598	$(-9 - (-8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4 * 3))) / 2 - 1$
734256	$-9 * (8 * 7 * 6 - 5 / 4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1))$	908599	$-9 + (8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4 * 3)) / 2 * 1$
735420	$(9+8) * 7 * 6 * (5 - (-4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1))$	908600	$(-9 - (-8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4 * 3))) / 2 + 1$
738216	$9 * (8 * (7+6) + 5 * 4^{\wedge}(3 * 2 + 1))$	908616	$9 + (8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4 * 3)) / 2 - 1$
739152	$9 / 8 * (7 - ((65+4)^{\wedge}3 * -2+1))$	908617	$9 + (8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4 * 3)) / 2 * 1$
743832	$9 * 8 * (-7-6 * (5 + (-4 * 3)^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	908618	$9 + (8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4 * 3)) / 2 + 1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
909312	$(9 - (8^{\wedge}(-7+6) - 5)) * 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	1060263	$-9 * (-8 - 7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1))$
911040	$9 * 8^{\wedge}(7 * 6) * ((5 + 4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 - 1))$	1062942	$(-9 + 876) * ((5 * (4 + 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
911596	$98 * (7 + 65 * ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1))$	1064084	$(98 + 7^{\wedge}6) * (5 + 4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$
912111	$9 * ((8^{\wedge}7 + 6^{\wedge}5 * 4) + 3) / 21$	1064862	$-98 + (-7 - 6) * -5 / 4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1)$
918731	$(9 + 8)^{\wedge}(-7 - (-6 - 5)) * (4 + 3 * 2 + 1)$	1064946	$-98 / 7 - 65 / -4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1)$
924692	$(-9 + 8) * -76 / (5 * 4 + 3)^{\wedge}(-2 - 1)$	1064974	$98 / 7 - 65 / -4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1)$
925506	$9 * 87 * 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3 * (-2 - 1))$	1065058	$98 + (-7 - 6) * -5 / 4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1)$
930013	$((9 * (8 - 7))^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1067382	$(9 * 8 / 7 + 6) * (5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 - 1))$
930257	$(-9 - 8) * (76 * -5 / (4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	1071360	$9 * (-87 - 6) * 5 * -4^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
930835	$(9 + 8) * ((-7 - 6) * 54 / 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$	1076403	$(9 - 8 * 76)^{\wedge}(-5 + 4 + 3) * (2 + 1)$
932039	$9 / ((8^{\wedge}7 - 65) * 4 + 3)^{\wedge}(-2 + 1)$	1079387	$(-9 - ((8 - 7 * (6 + 5))^{\wedge}4 - 3)) / -21$
937983	$-9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - (5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2 + 1))$	1079992	$((9 - 8) + 7) * ((6 * 5)^{\wedge}4 / (3 * 2) - 1)$
938001	$9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - (5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2 + 1))$	1080008	$((9 - 8) + 7) * ((6 * 5)^{\wedge}4 / (3 * 2) + 1)$
938873	$(9 * 8 * 7 - 6 * -5^{\wedge}(4 + 3)) * 2 + 1$	1084026	$(9 / 8 * 7 + 6) * (5^{\wedge}(4 + 3) + 2 + 1)$
939067	$(9 * 87 - 6 * -5^{\wedge}(4 + 3)) * 2 + 1$	1084372	$9 / (-8 + ((7 * 6 + 5)^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 2)^{\wedge} - 1$
942225	$(-9 - 8) * (76 * (-5 - 4)^{\wedge}3 - 21)$	1085010	$(9 + 876) * ((5 * (4 + 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
944383	$-9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + (5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2 + 1))$	1087881	$(-9 - 8) * (7 + (6 * 5 * -4 / 3)^{\wedge}(2 + 1))$
944401	$9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + (5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2 + 1))$	1088119	$(9 + 8) * (7 - (6 * 5 * -4 / 3)^{\wedge}(2 + 1))$
949097	$((-9 + 87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) - 3) * 2 - 1$	1088633	$(-9 + 8) * 7 * (6^{\wedge}5 * 4 * (-3 - 2) + 1)$
949098	$((-9 + 87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) - 3) * 2 * 1$	1090152	$9 * (-8 + 76^{\wedge}(-5 + 4 + 3)) * 21$
949099	$((-9 + 87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) - 3) * 2 + 1$	1093645	$-98 / 7 * (6 - 5^{\wedge}(4 + 3)) - 21$
949109	$((-9 + 87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) + 3) * 2 - 1$	1093678	$-9 * 8 + 7 * 6 / (5^{\wedge}(-4 - 3) * (2 + 1))$
949110	$((-9 + 87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) + 3) * 2 * 1$	1093822	$9 * 8 + 7 * 6 / (5^{\wedge}(-4 - 3) * (2 + 1))$
949111	$((-9 + 87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) + 3) * 2 + 1$	1093855	$98 / 7 * (6 + 5^{\wedge}(4 + 3)) + 21$
950000	$(9 - (-8 + 7))^{\wedge}6 * ((-5 * 4)^{\wedge}(-3 + 2) + 1)$	1097577	$-9 * (8 - 7 * ((-6 - 5) * 4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
954734	$(-9 * (8 - (7 + 6)^{\wedge}5) + 4) / (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	1097721	$9 * (8 + 7 * ((-6 - 5) * 4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
959850	$(9 * 8 + 7) * 6^{\wedge}5 * ((4 / 3)^{\wedge} - 2 + 1)$	1100385	$9 / 8 * (((7 - 6 * 5) * 43)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
960007	$((9 - 8) * 7 + 6 * (5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1))$	1101528	$9 * -8 * (765 * 4 * (-3 - 2) + 1)$
972864	$9 * (8 * 7 + 6) + 5 * (4 * 3)^{\wedge}(2 + 1)$	1108710	$-9 / 8 * (7 + (65 + 4)^{\wedge}3 * (-2 - 1))$
986071	$((9 * 8 + 7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) - 3) * 2 - 1$	1108992	$9 / (8 * 76)^{\wedge}(5 - 4 - 3) / (2 + 1)$
986073	$((9 * 8 + 7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) - 3) * 2 + 1$	1110967	$(9 - 8) * (-7 + 6^{\wedge}5) * ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
986083	$((9 * 8 + 7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) + 3) * 2 - 1$	1111959	$9 / (-8 + 7) + 6^{\wedge}5 * ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
986085	$((9 * 8 + 7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) + 3) * 2 + 1$	1111975	$(9 - 8) * 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 * ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
988821	$9 * ((8 * 7 * 654 * 3 - 2) - 1)$	1116225	$-9 * (8 * 7 + 65) * (-4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) - 1)$
988875	$9 * ((8 * 7 * 654 * 3 + 2) + 1)$	1117200	$-98 * 76 * (-5 - ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1))$
990074	$(-9 + 8 * ((7 + 6)^{\wedge}5 - 4) / 3) - 21$	1117557	$((9 * 8 + 7) - 6) * (5 + 4)^{\wedge}3 * 21$
991476	$9 * ((8 - (7 * 6 + 5))^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 21$	1126505	$((9 - 8) * -7 + 6^{\wedge}5) * ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
993060	$9 * (8 + 7) * 6 * ((5 * (4 + 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1127513	$(-9 + 8) * 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 * ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
993393	$9 * ((8^{\wedge}7 + 6) + 5) / (-4 * (-3 - 2) - 1)$	1127527	$(9 - 8) * 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 * ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
995760	$9 * 8 * (7 + 6^{\wedge}5 * (4 / 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	1129310	$((9 / 8 + 7) - 6) * (5 + 4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2) - 1$
996450	$(9 / 8 * 7 - 6) * ((5 + 4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2) - 1)$	1129440	$(9 - 8 + 7^{\wedge}6) / 5 * ((4 + 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
996543	$9^{\wedge}((8 + 7) / 6) * (5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}1$	1133993	$(-9 + 8) * 7 * ((6 * 5)^{\wedge}4 / (-3 - 2) + 1)$
997137	$9 * ((8 - 76 * (5 + 4)^{\wedge}3) * -2 + 1)$	1136640	$(9 / 8 * 7 + 6) * 5 * 4^{\wedge}(3 * 2 + 1)$
1008007	$(9 - 8) * 7 - 6 * (5 * -4)^{\wedge}3 * 21$	1140600	$((9 + 8) + 7) * ((654 / 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
1017450	$9 / 8 * (((7 - 6 * 54) * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	1140626	$((9 * 8 + 7) - 6) * 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3 / 2) + 1$
1028659	$(9 * 8 + 7) / 6 * (5^{\wedge}(4 + 3) + 2 - 1)$	1142067	$(9 + 8 * 76)^{\wedge}(-5 + 4 + 3) * (2 + 1)$
1038230	$(9 - 8 * 7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) * (-3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	1142421	$(-9 + 8) * (7 * (6^{\wedge}5 - 4) - 3) * -21$
1039293	$(9 + 8 / 7 * 6) * (5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 - 1))$	1142550	$9 / 8 * ((-7 - 6) * (-5^{\wedge}(4 + 3) + 2) + 1)$
1040800	$(-9 + 8)^{\wedge}7 * 6^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1142820	$(9 * 8 + 7 * (6^{\wedge}5 - 4 * 3)) * 21$
1042470	$9 * (-8 - 7) * 6^{\wedge}5 * ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	1143044	$(-9 + 8) * (7 * 6^{\wedge}5 - 4 / 3) * -21$
1042521	$9 / 8 * (6^{\wedge}(5 + 4) + 3 * 2 + 1)$	1143100	$((9 - 8) * 7 * 6^{\wedge}5 + 4 / 3) * 21$
1043970	$-98 * (7 * 6 + 5) + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1143324	$(-9 * 8 + 7 * (6^{\wedge}5 + 4 * 3)) * 21$
1044391	$9 * (-87 - 6) * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1143975	$((9 - 8) * 7 * 6^{\wedge}5 + 43) * 21$
1044931	$9 * (-87 + 6) * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1146796	$-98 / 7 * (6 - 5 / 4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1))$
1045116	$(-98 * 7 - 6) * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1146964	$98 / 7 * (6 - 5 / -4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1))$
1045176	$(98 * -7 + 6) * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1165074	$9 / ((8^{\wedge}7 - 6) * 5 - 4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(-2 + 1)$
1047811	$(-9 + 8) * 765 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1165083	$9 / ((8^{\wedge}7 + 6) * 5 - 43)^{\wedge}(-2 + 1)$
1048047	$(-9 + 8 * (-7 - 6) * 5) + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1165087	$9 / ((8^{\wedge}7 + 6) * 5 - 4 - 3)^{\wedge}(-2 + 1)$
1048065	$9 + 8 * (-7 - 6) * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1166634	$987 * 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3 * (-2 - 1))$
1048338	$-9^{\wedge}((8 + 7) / 6) + 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1176882	$(-9 + 8) * -7 * (6 + (5 * 4)^{\wedge}3) * 21$
1048376	$(-9 * (8 + 7) - 65) + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1178340	$9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / (43 * 2 + 1)$
1048776	$9 * (8 + 7) + 65 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1178496	$9 * (8^{\wedge}(-7 + 6 + 5) - 4) * 32^{\wedge}1$
1049087	$(-9 - 8 * (-7 - 6) * 5) + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1179228	$-9 * 8 * (7 / 6 * 5 - 4^{\wedge}(3 * 2 + 1))$
1049105	$9 - 8 * (-7 - 6) * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1180068	$9 * 8 * (7 / 6 * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3 * 2 + 1))$
1050849	$9 * ((8 + 7) * (6^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}(3 / 2)) + 1)$	1183032	$9 * -8 * (-7 * 6 - (5 + 4^{\wedge}(3 * 2 + 1)))$
1051467	$(9 + 8) * (7 * (6 * 5 + 4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	1184918	$-98 * (76 - (5 * 4 + 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
1051976	$(98 * 7 - 6) * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1186339	$(9 + 8 / 7) * ((6 * (54 + 3))^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
1052036	$(98 * 7 + 6) * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1188534	$(-9 - (-8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5 + 4 * 3))) / 2 - 1$
1052221	$-9 * (-87 + 6) * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1188535	$-9 + (8^{\wedge}7 + 6^{\wedge}(-5 + 4 * 3)) / 2 * 1$
1052761	$-9 * (-87 - 6) * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1188536	$(-9 - (-8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5 + 4 * 3))) / 2 + 1$
1053182	$98 * (7 * 6 + 5) + 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1188552	$9 + (8^{\wedge}7 + 6^{\wedge}(-5 + 4 * 3)) / 2 - 1$
1057419	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1))$	1188553	$9 + (8^{\wedge}7 + 6^{\wedge}(-5 + 4 * 3)) / 2 * 1$

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1188554	$9+(8^7+6^{(-5+4*3)})/2+1$	1350048	$98*7*((6^5/4+3)+21)$
1195730	$((9*(8-7))^6-5)/4*3^2-1$	1378944	$9*8*76*((5+4)+3)*21$
1198351	$-9-8/7*(6+5-4^3(3^2+1))$	1381725	$((-9-8)/7+6)*((-5^4+3)^2-1)$
1199765	$(9-8)*7*((6*(5+4^3))^2-1)$	1384128	$9*(-8-76-5)*(-4*3)^2(2+1)$
1199779	$(9-8)*7*((6*(5+4^3))^2+1)$	1387200	$(98*7-6)^{(-5-(-4-3))}*(2+1)$
1199814	$98*(76+(5*4+3)^2(2+1))$	1387464	$9/(8-((7-65)^4)^3)^{(-2+1)}$
1203741	$(-9^8(8-7)+6*5^4*321)$	1392419	$(-9-8)*(7+6-5/4^4(-3*2-1))$
1203872	$(9+8)*(7*6^5+4^4(3*2+1))$	1392623	$(-9-8)*(7-6-5/4^4(-3*2-1))$
1208160	$9*8*(7^8(6-5+4)-3^2(2+1))$	1392657	$(9+8)*(7-6-5/-4^4(-3*2-1))$
1209575	$(-9+8*7*6^5)*((4/3)^2+1)$	1392861	$(9+8)*(7+6-5/-4^4(-3*2-1))$
1209617	$9-8*(7*6*(5*4^3)^2-1)$	1395297	$9*((8*76-5^4(4+3))*-2-1)$
1209625	$(9+8*7*6^5)*((4/3)^2+1)$	1397751	$-9+8^7/6*(5-(4^4(-3-2)+1))$
1209735	$9*(8*((7^8(6-5+4)-3)-2)-1)$	1397769	$9+8^7/6*(5-(4^4(-3-2)+1))$
1209753	$9*(8*((7^8(6-5+4)-3)-2)+1)$	1398007	$-9+8^7/6*((5-4^4(3*2))-1)$
1210081	$(-9-8-((76-5)^4+3))/-21$	1398025	$9+8^7/6*((5-4^4(3*2))-1)$
1210455	$9*(8*((7^8(6-5+4)+3)+2)-1)$	1398041	$9/(8^7*6-543)^{(-2+1)}$
1210473	$-9*(-8*((7^8(6-5+4)+3)+2)-1)$	1398045	$(-9+8^7/6-5)^4-3^2(-2+1)$
1212048	$9*8*(7^8(6-5+4)+3^2(2+1))$	1398127	$(9+8^7/6+5)^4-3^2(-2+1)$
1212732	$9*8*(7/6-5^4)^*-3^2(2+1)$	1398157	$(9+8^7/6+5)^4-3^2(-2+1)$
1215648	$(-9+8)*-7*6^5*4/3+21$	1403649	$9/8*((7/(-6^5-43))^{(-2-1)})$
1233741	$(9+8)*((7*6^5*4/3)-2)-1$	1406156	$-9*(8+(7/6-5^4(4+3)))^2-1$
1233843	$(9+8)*((7*6^5*4/3+2)+1)$	1406158	$-9*(8+(7/6-5^4(4+3)))^2+1$
1243136	$(9/8-7*(6+5))*-4^4(3*2+1)$	1406243	$(-9+8)*7-6/5^4(-4-3)*(-2-1)$
1244804	$(-9+8)*76*(5-4^4(3*2+1))$	1411128	$9*8*((7*(-6-54)/3)^2-1)$
1248129	$9/((8+7)^6-54^3)^{(-2+1)}$	1411443	$9*(((-8+7^6)-5)^4/3-21)$
1254825	$9*(8+7)*65*((4*3)^2-1)$	1411572	$9*8*((7^6/5+4-3)-2)-1$
1254916	$9/((-8*7^6+5)/(-4*3))^{(-2+1)}$	1412004	$9*8*((7^6/5+4-3)+2)+1$
1254976	$9/(8*(7^6+5))/(4*3)^{(-2+1)}$	1412133	$9*((8+7^6)+5)^4/3+21$
1257389	$9/(8+(7-65)^4-3)^{(-2+1)}$	1421684	$((9/(8-7))^6-5^4(4+3+2))*-1$
1265304	$9*(8+7)^6-5^4(-5+4)-321$	1423823	$9-((8+7)^6-5)/4*(3/2+1)$
1265554	$-9*(8-(7*6*(-5-4)+3)^2)+1$	1423832	$9+((8+7)^6-5)/4*(3/2-1)$
1265696	$9*(8+(7*6*(-5-4)+3)^2)-1$	1436592	$(98*7+6)^{(-5-(-4-3))}*(2+1)$
1265946	$9*(8+7)^6-5^4(-5+4)+321$	1436976	$9*(8*7*-6+(5*4)^3+2-1)$
1272991	$9*8*((7+6)^5-4)/3+21$	1442430	$(9-8*7)*6*5*(-4^4(3+2)+1)$
1273152	$9*-8*((-7-6)^5-43)/21$	1443024	$-9*(8*7*-6-(5*4)^3+2-1)$
1277181	$9*((876*54*3-2)-1)$	1443793	$(-9+8*7)*(6*5*4^4(3+2)-1)$
1277235	$9*((876*54*3+2)+1)$	1443887	$(9-8*7)*(6*5*-4^4(3+2)-1)$
1283121	$9/((8+7)^6+54^3)^{(-2+1)}$	1445250	$(-9+8*7)*6*5*(4^4(3+2)+1)$
1296007	$(9-8)*7-6*(5*-4*3)^2(2+1)$	1449168	$(-9+8)*-7*((65*(4+3))^2-1)$
1305663	$-9+8*((7*(6^5-4)^3-2)-1)$	1449182	$(9-8)*7*((65*(4+3))^2+1)$
1305681	$9+8*((7*(6^5-4)^3-2)-1)$	1450000	$((-9-8)+7)^6*(5/4*(-3-2)^{-1})$
1305711	$-9+8*((7*(6^5-4)^3+2)+1)$	1457964	$9*((8+7-(6*5)^4)/(-3-2)-1)$
1305729	$9+8*((7*(6^5-4)^3+2)+1)$	1458036	$-9*((8+7+(6*5)^4)/(-3-2)-1)$
1307007	$-9+8*((7*(6^5+4)^3-2)-1)$	1464320	$(9/8+7)*(-6-5)^*-4^4(3*2+1)$
1307025	$9+8*((7*(6^5+4)^3-2)-1)$	1479108	$((9*8+7)^{(-6-(-5-4))}-3)^2(2+1)$
1307055	$-9-8*((7*(6^5+4)^3-3)-2)-1$	1479126	$(9*8+7)^{(-6-(-5-4))}+3)^2(2+1)$
1307073	$9-8*((7*(6^5+4)^3-3)-2)-1$	1484366	$-9-(8/(76*-5^4(4+3)^2))^{(-1)}$
1310477	$(-9^8((8+7)/6)+5*4^4(3^2(2+1)))$	1484384	$9-(8/(76*-5^4(4+3)^2))^{(-1)}$
1310963	$9^8((8+7)/6)-5*-4^4(3^2(2+1))$	1486422	$987*-6*(5-4^4(3+2-1))$
1313811	$(9+8)*((7*6-5^4)^3)^2-1$	1491000	$(-9+8^8(-7+6))^*(5*-4)^3*21$
1314402	$(-9/8+7)*(((6-5)^4)^3)^2-1$	1494675	$((9*8+7)-6)^*5*(4^4(3*2)-1)$
1316981	$(-9-(-87^8(-6-(-5-4))+3))^2-1$	1495405	$((9*8+7)-6)^*5*(4^4(3*2)+1)$
1316982	$(-9+87^8((-6+5)+4)-3)^2+1$	1495908	$(-9+87*6)/54^4(-3+2-1)$
1316983	$(-9+87^8(-6-(-5-4))-3)^2+1$	1495917	$9+(8/76*54^4-3)^{(-2+1)}$
1316993	$(-9+87^8(-6-(-5-4))+3)^2-1$	1500644	$9+(((8-7)+6)^5)^4(-3^2-1)$
1316994	$(-9+87^8(-6+5+4)+3)^2+1$	1506696	$9/((8+7)+6)*((5^4*3)^2-1)$
1316995	$(-9+87^8(-6-(-5-4))+3)^2+1$	1511853	$(9-8)*7*((6+54)^3-21)$
1317017	$9+87^8(-6-(-5-4))-3)^2-1$	1512702	$9*(8+7^6/5^4(5^4+3)+2^2(-1))$
1317018	$(9+87^8(-6-(-5-4))-3)^2/1$	1522094	$(-9/87/(6-54^3))^{(-2+1)}$
1317019	$(9+87^8(-6-(-5-4))-3)^2+1$	1522210	$(9/87/(6+54^3))^{(-2+1)}$
1317029	$(9+87^8(-6-(-5-4))+3)^2-1$	1533000	$(-9-8^8(-7+6))^*(5*-4)^3*21$
1317030	$9+87^8((-6+5)+4)+3)^2+1$	1534734	$(-9+876^8((-5+4)+3))/2^2-1$
1317031	$(9+87^8(-6-(-5-4))+3)^2+1$	1534770	$(-9-876^8((-5+4)+3))/-2^2-1$
1320150	$9/(8*((7+6)^5*4-3)-2)^{(-1)}$	1540944	$9*87*((6^5/4+3)+21)$
1333296	$((-9-8)*(-7^6+5)-4)/(3/2*1)$	1554768	$9*8*((-7+6)/(5*4^3)^2-1)$
1333606	$((9+8(-7+6)^5)-4)/32-1$	1556100	$(-9+8)*-76*5*(4^4(3*2)-1)$
1342176	$((9+8^7(-6)-5)/((4/3)^2-2+1))$	1565190	$9*(8-7*6)^*5*(4^4(3+2)+1)$
1344551	$-9+8/7^8-6/(5^4(-4+3)+2^2(-1))$	1566096	$(9-8)*7*(((-6-5)^4)^3)^2-1$
1344569	$9+8/7^8-6/(5^4(-4+3)+2^2(-1))$	1568250	$9*(8-7*6)^*-5*(4^4(3+2)+1)$
1346675	$(9-8/7)*((6*(5+4^3))^2-1)$	1577655	$9*((8*7)^{(-6+5)+4}-321)$
1349995	$9/((8+7)*((6*5)^4-3))^{(-2+1)}$	1580223	$9*(8*7)^{(-6+5)+4}-321$
1350005	$9/((8+7)*((6*5)^4+3))^{(-2+1)}$	1580498	$9*((8*7)^{(-6+5+4)-3}-2)-1$

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1580500	$9^*((((8^7)^{-6+5+4})^{-3})^{-2})+1$	1860874	$(9-8)^*7+(6^5*4+3)^{\wedge(2+1)}$
1580588	$9^*((((8^7)^{-6+5+4})+3)+2)-1$	1864132	$(9/((8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)+4)-32))^{\wedge-1}$
1580590	$9^*((((8^7)^{-6+5+4})+3)+2)+1$	1867563	$(9^*87+6)^{\wedge(-5-(-4-3))}*(2+1)$
1580865	$9^*(8^7)^{\wedge((-6+5)+4)+321}$	1869210	$9/8^*((7-6^{\wedge}(5-(4-3)))^{\wedge 2-1})$
1583433	$9^*((8^7)^{\wedge((-6+5)+4)+321})$	1869448	$98^*-76^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$
1583992	$(9+8)^*76^*((5^*(4+3))^{\wedge 2+1})$	1874496	$9^*-8^*(7-(6^5^{\wedge}(-4-3)/2))^{\wedge-1}$
1586899	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))^*(4^*(3+2)-1)$	1874688	$9^*8^*(7+6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/(-2-1)$
1588888	$(-9+8)^*-7/(65-4)^{-3+21}$	1874972	$9^*8^*(-7/6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/(2+1)$
1607970	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)^*((5+4/3)^*2+1)$	1874976	$9^*8^*(7-(6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)))/(-2-1)$
1607988	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)^*((5+4/3)^*2+1)$	1875024	$9^*8^*(7-(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)))/(2+1)$
1609209	$(98+7^{\wedge}6)^*((5+4/3)^*2+1)$	1875312	$9^*8^*(7+6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/(2+1)$
1613400	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6/(5+4^{\wedge}(-3+2)))-1$	1875504	$9^*8^*(7+(6^5^{\wedge}(-4-3)/2))^{\wedge-1}$
1613544	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6/(5+4^{\wedge}(-3+2))+1)$	1875852	$(9^*(8^7-6^{\wedge}5)+4)^*-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
1622400	$((9+8)+7)^*(65^4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$	1876068	$(-9^*(8^7-6^{\wedge}5)+4)^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
1623055	$(98^*(7+6))^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)-21$	1889853	$(9-8)^*7^*(6^5)^{\wedge}4/3-21$
1623073	$(98^*(7+6))^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)-2-1$	1890090	$9^*((8^7*6^5*4+3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
1623074	$((98^*(7+6))^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)-2)/1$	1898000	$((-9-8)/7+6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
1623078	$(98^*(7+6))^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+2/1$	1903068	$(-9^*(8^7+6^{\wedge}5)+4)^*-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
1623079	$(98^*(7+6))^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)+2+1$	1903284	$(9^*(8^7+6^{\wedge}5)+4)^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
1623097	$(98^*(7+6))^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+21$	1906469	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3+2))^*-1$
1627224	$(-9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-54)^*-3)/21$	1910034	$9/8^*((7+6^{\wedge}(5-(4-3)))^{\wedge 2-1})$
1628907	$(-9-90^*(8^7+6)+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$	1917000	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^*(5^*-4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
1630314	$9/8^*7^*((65^*(4+3))^{\wedge 2-1})$	1925120	$(-9-87/6)^*-5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
1634116	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)^*5^*((4/3)^{\wedge 2+1})$	1941408	$(9-8)^*7^*6^*((5^*43)^{\wedge 2-1})$
1634134	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)^*5^*((4/3)^{\wedge 2+1})$	1941492	$(-9+8)^*-7^*6^*((5^*43)^{\wedge 2+1})$
1636821	$((-9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}6^5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	1942416	$987^*((6^5/4+3)+21)$
1641507	$((9-8)^*7^*6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$	1943442	$-9^*(8^7+6-(5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
1646235	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*(3/2+1)$	1944558	$9^*(8^7+6+(5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
1646280	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*(3/2+1)$	1946126	$(-9-8)^*7^*(6^5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$
1652343	$(9^*(8^7+6)+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$	1959531	$((-9+8)^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5*4^*3)^*21$
1660134	$987^*((6-5^*(-4-3))^{\wedge 2+1})$	1965200	$(9+8)^*(-7^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3)^{\wedge 2/1}$
1665918	$(9/(8^*((7+6^5)^{\wedge}4-3)-2))^{\wedge-1}$	1965945	$-9^*(8+7)-6^*-5^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1673955	$(-9-((8+(7^*(6+5))^{\wedge}4)-3))^{\wedge-21}$	1966215	$9^*(8+7)-6^*-5^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1685096	$((9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3^*21$	1975461	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*3-21$
1685132	$((9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	1975480	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*3-2^*1$
1685135	$((9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)-3-21$	1975481	$(-9+87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4))^*3-(2-1)$
1685141	$((9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3-21$	1975483	$(-9+87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4))^*3+2-1$
1685177	$((9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)-(3-21)$	1975533	$(9+87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4))^*3-(2+1)$
1685183	$((9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3+21$	1975534	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*3-2^*1$
1685186	$((9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	1975535	$(9+87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4))^*3-(2-1)$
1687268	$((9-8)^*7^*6^{\wedge}5-4)^*(32-1)$	1975537	$(9+87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4))^*3+2-1$
1687516	$(9-8)^*(7^*6^{\wedge}5+4)^*(32-1)$	1975538	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*3+2^*1$
1690981	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3+2))/-1$	1975545	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3)^*(2+1)$
1692000	$(-9+8^7)/6^*(5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	1975557	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*3+21$
1694162	$(-9/8+7)^*((-6+543)^{\wedge 2-1})$	1978884	$9^*-876^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$
1697190	$(9-8/7)^*(6+(5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	1981556	$(-9-(8/7)^{\wedge}6)/-5^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1713600	$(-9-8)^*-7^*(6^5*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$	1994620	$(9-8)^*76^*((54^*3)^{\wedge 2+1})$
1714176	$9^*8^7/(6+5)^*(-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$	1994850	$(-9-8^7)^*6^*5^*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
1725687	$-9-8^*-7^*6^{\wedge}5*(4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	2000262	$((-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)-(4^*3)^{\wedge 2})^*-1$
1725705	$9-8^*-7^*6^{\wedge}5*(4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	2018576	$(9-8)^*7^*((6-543)^{\wedge 2-1})$
1728028	$(9-8)^*7+(6^5*4)^{\wedge}3+21$	2024631	$-9+8/7^*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4^*3/2)-1)$
1730430	$9^*87^*(((-6-5)^*-4+3)^{\wedge 2+1})$	2024649	$9+8/7^*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4^*3/2)-1)$
1738435	$(9+8/7)^*((6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge 2-1})$	2025007	$(9-8)^*7+(6^5)^{\wedge}4*(3-2^{\wedge}1)$
1739264	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))/(-3^*21)$	2035172	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3)^{\wedge 2/1}$
1747618	$-9+8^{\wedge}7/6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2-1))$	2035703	$-9+8^{\wedge}7^*(6^5*4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
1747636	$9+8^{\wedge}7/6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2-1))$	2035721	$9+8^{\wedge}7^*(6^5*4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
1747657	$9+8^{\wedge}7/6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1))$	2038093	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7+(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1$
1757600	$((9+8-7)^*(65^*4)^{\wedge}(-3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	2038095	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7+(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1$
1757745	$9^*(-8-7)/-6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2-1)$	2038111	$9+8^{\wedge}7-(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1$
1757880	$9^*(-8-7)/6^*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2-1)$	2038113	$9+8^{\wedge}7-(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1$
1757943	$-9-8^*-7^*6^{\wedge}5*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	2049746	$-98-((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$
1757961	$9-8^*-7^*6^{\wedge}5*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	2049772	$-9^*8-((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$
1770725	$(-9/8+7)^*((-6-543)^{\wedge 2-1})$	2049782	$((9^{\wedge}8-(7-(6-5))^{\wedge}4)-3)/21$
1796124	$((9-8)^*7^*6^{\wedge}5-4)^*(32+1)$	2049827	$(-9-8)-((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$
1796388	$(9-8)^*(7^*6^{\wedge}5+4)^*(32+1)$	2049845	$9-8-((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$
1799365	$(9/(8-(7-65^*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	2049861	$9+8-((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$
1805400	$9^*-8^*(7^*6^{\wedge}5-43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	2049916	$9^*8-((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$
1811187	$(9^*87-6)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))^*(2+1)$	2049942	$98-((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$
1812857	$((-9+8^7)^*(6^5)^{\wedge}4-3)/21$	2059434	$9/8^*((7^*-65+4)^*3)^{\wedge 2-1}$
1817790	$(9/8+7)^*(((-6-5)^*43)^{\wedge 2-1})$	2063978	$(9-8)^*7^*((6+543)^{\wedge 2-1})$
1846080	$9/8^*((7^*(-65+4)^*3)^{\wedge 2-1})$	2086903	$-9+8^{\wedge}7^*(6-5^*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$
1848327	$-9^*(8^7/6+(5-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	2086921	$9+8^{\wedge}7^*(6-5^*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
2088985	$9+8*((7*(6*5+43))^2+1)$	2452335	$9*(87*6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)-21$
2089787	$-9+8^{\wedge}7-6*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$	2452377	$9*(87*6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+21$
2089805	$9+8^{\wedge}7-6*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$	2452545	$9*((87*6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+21)$
2091294	$-9*(-8-((7*6+5)^4-3))/21$	2460054	$(9*(8+7))^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)-321$
2093809	$(9-8*7*(6*5-4))^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$	2460343	$(9*(8+7))^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)-32/1$
2101707	$(9*(87+6))^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))*(2+1)$	2460402	$(9*(8+7))^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3^{\wedge}2+1$
2103614	$(-9-8)*(((7-6)^5+4)/3+21)$	2460407	$(9*(8+7))^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+32/1$
2104008	$((9+8)*(7+6)^5+43)/(2+1)$	2471637	$((9-8)*7^{\wedge}6+5+43)*21$
2104328	$(9+8)*(((7+6)^5-4)/3+21)$	2471700	$((9-8)*7^{\wedge}6+54-3)*21$
2104499	$-9+8^{\wedge}7+6*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$	2471826	$((9-8)*7^{\wedge}6+54)+3)*21$
2104517	$9+8^{\wedge}7+6*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$	2480016	$(-9+8)*7*6*((-5-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
2107383	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1))$	2482032	$((9-8)*7^{\wedge}6+543)*21$
2107401	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1))$	2489825	$(-9/8+7)*((-654+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
2108457	$9*(8-7*6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))*(2+1)$	2491231	$(98/(7+6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
2109291	$-9*(8*7/6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))*(2+1)$	2494819	$(9-8)*7+(6^{\wedge}5-4)*321$
2109459	$9*(8*7/6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))*(-2-1)$	2500371	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(43-2)-1$
2109800	$(9-8)*7*((6+543)^{\wedge}2-1)$	2500389	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(43-2)+1$
2110293	$9*(8-7*6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))*(-2-1)$	2514778	$(-9/((-8-((7-65)^{\wedge}4-3))^2))^{\wedge}(-1)$
2121405	$(9-8/7)*((6*5)^4/3-2-1)$	2515625	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)*-1$
2126241	$-9+(8/7*(6*5)^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	2519031	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*-6/5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
2126259	$9+(8/7*(6*5)^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	2519049	$9-8^{\wedge}7*-6/5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
2133144	$9/8*((7*65+4)*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	2523136	$98/7*(-6-5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
2133334	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7)*6*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	2534976	$(9-(8+7))^{\wedge}6*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
2137576	$98*76*((-5-4)*-32-1)$	2535932	$(-9/8+7)*((-654-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
2151786	$(9-8)*7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4-3)*21$	2537712	$(9-8^{\wedge}7+6)/((5/(4*3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
2156191	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7-(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1$	2545144	$(-9/(8-((76-5)^4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
2156193	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7-(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1$	2546515	$(-9-8)/7*(6+5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
2156209	$9+8^{\wedge}7+(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1$	2555859	$-9*(-8^{\wedge}7/6+5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
2156211	$9+8^{\wedge}7+(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1$	2555949	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/6+5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
2177294	$98/7*(6^{\wedge}5*4*(3+2)+1)$	2563185	$(9/(8^{\wedge}7*(6+5)-4-3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
2180220	$((-9+8*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)-3)*21$	2569854	$98*(7*6*5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2180346	$((9-8*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)-3)*-21$	2574936	$9*-8*7*(6-5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
2181270	$987*((-6-5)*4-3)^{\wedge}2+1$	2575146	$98*(7*6*5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2190918	$(9+8/7)*(6+(5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	2577447	$9*(8*-7*(6-5*4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1)$
2204461	$-98-((7+6+5)^{\wedge}4+3)*-21$	2577465	$-9*(8*7*(6-5*4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1)$
2210112	$(98*(-7-6)-5)*(-4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	2579976	$9*8*7*(-6-5*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
2216420	$(9/(8^{\wedge}7+65^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	2580984	$9*8*-7*(-6-5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
2244608	$(9*-8-(-7-6)*5)*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$	2586024	$9*8*7*(6-5*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
2253420	$(9/8+7)*6*((5*43)^{\wedge}2-1)$	2633976	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*(3+2-1)$
2262708	$9*876*((-5-4)*-32-1)$	2634048	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*(-3-2+1)$
2263662	$9/(8*7)*((6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	2656185	$(-9+8)*-7*((6-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
2265625	$(9/(87*6)*5^{\wedge}4(-4-3))^2)^{\wedge}(-1)$	2668559	$(9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))*-1$
2266029	$((-9+8)/7+6)*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	2670592	$(-98+(-7-6)*5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
2270898	$9/8*7*((6-543)^{\wedge}2-1)$	2682127	$(9-8)*7*(-6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3-(2-1))$
2270907	$9/8*(7*(6-543)^{\wedge}2+1)$	2687386	$((9*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4)/(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2274048	$987/(6-54)^{\wedge}(-3+2-1)$	2696340	$9*((8^{\wedge}7-6)+5)/(4+3)+2+1$
2277376	$((-9-(8+7))*6+5)*-4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$	2708223	$(-9+8)*-7*(6+(-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
2278647	$(-9+8)*-7/6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3+2)+1)$	2719990	$98*7*65*((4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$
2293718	$(-9+8)*7*(6-5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	2722717	$(-9-8)+7*6^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
2293802	$(-9+8)*-7*(6-5*-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	2722751	$9+8+(7*6)^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
2299416	$(9-8)*7*((65+4)^{\wedge}3-21)$	2723119	$(-9+8)*-7/(6*5+43)^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
2299961	$(-9+8)*7-((6+5)*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	2733125	$(9-8)/7*((6/(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
2304729	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	2738541	$(9+8/7)*((6*5)^{\wedge}4/3-2-1)$
2304792	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	2744820	$9/8*((7*6+5)^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1$
2309667	$9/(8+7)*((654*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	2752230	$-9*8-7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
2342990	$(9/8+7)*((6-543)^{\wedge}2-1)$	2752302	$(-9+8)*7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
2349675	$(9+876)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)*(2+1)$	2752374	$9*8-7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
2366301	$9/(-8+7)+6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	2752650	$-9*8-7*-6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
2370240	$9876*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	2752722	$(9-8)*7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
2373525	$9/8*7*((6+543)^{\wedge}2-1)$	2752794	$9*8-7*-6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
2373534	$9/8*(7/(6+543))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	2763459	$9+(8/7+6)*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
2376567	$(9-8)/7+6*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	2777088	$(987/6+5)*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
2420104	$(9*8*(-7^{\wedge}6+5)+4)/(-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	2782703	$(-9+8)*7*(6-5*43^{\wedge}(2+1))$
2420312	$(9*-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)-4)/(-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	2787127	$(-9+8)*-7/(6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(-3+2-1)$
2424510	$(9*8+7)*6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	2789976	$((9*(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3)*21$
2429250	$(9*8+7)*6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	2790102	$((9*(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3)*21$
2429550	$9*((-87+(6*5)^{\wedge}4)/3-21)$	2809692	$9*-8*((76-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$
2430450	$9*((-87-(6*5)^{\wedge}4)/-3+21)$	2809836	$9*8*((-76+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$
2433015	$9*((8-7)+65)*4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	2810695	$(9/(8+7^{\wedge}6)/(5*43))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
2433033	$9*((8-7)+65)/4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$	2811708	$9*-8*(7-(-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$
2448875	$(9/8+7)*((6+543)^{\wedge}2-1)$	2811852	$9*-8*(7-((-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1))$
2452167	$9*((87*6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)-21)$	2812104	$9*8*((-7-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
2812140	$9^* - 8^*(7 + (-6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / 2 + 1)$	3125020	$(98/7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)*2+1)$
2812284	$-9^*8^*(7 - ((6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / 2 + 1))$	3130368	$9^*8^{\wedge}7/6^*(- 5^*4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
2812449	$-9^*(8^*(7/6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / 2 + 1)$	3136158	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(54+3^{\wedge}2-1)$
2812467	$9^*(- 8^*(7/6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / 2 + 1)$	3139587	$9^*(8^*7^*6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
2812533	$-9^*(- 8^*(7/6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / 2 + 1)$	3149760	$((-9^{\wedge}8+7)-6) / ((-5-4/3)^*2-1)$
2812551	$9^*(8^*(7/6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / 2 + 1)$	3153344	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))^* - 1$
2812716	$9^*8^*(7 - ((6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / 2 + 1))$	3155544	$9^*87654^*(3+2-1)$
2812860	$9^*8^*(7 + (-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / 2 + 1)$	3161081	$(9 / (8^*7)^{\wedge}(6-5-4) - 3)^*2 - 1$
2812896	$9^*8^*((7+6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / 2 - 1)$	3161082	$(9 / (8^*-7)^{\wedge}(6-5-4)+3)^* - 2 / 1$
2813040	$9^*8^*((7+6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / 2 + 1)$	3161083	$(9 / (8^*7)^{\wedge}(6-5-4) - 3)^*2 + 1$
2813148	$9^*8^*(7 - ((-6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / 2 + 1))$	3161093	$(9 / (8^*7)^{\wedge}(6-5-4)+3)^*2 - 1$
2813292	$9^*8^*(7 - (-6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / 2 + 1)$	3161094	$(9 / (8^*7)^{\wedge}(6-5-4)+3) / 2^{\wedge} - 1$
2813699	$(9-8)^*7^*((6+5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	3161095	$(9 / (8^*7)^{\wedge}(6-5-4)+3)^*2 + 1$
2815164	$9^* - 8^*((-76-5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / 2 + 1)$	3173816	$(-9/8+7)^*((6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
2815308	$9^*8^*((76+5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / 2 + 1)$	3175587	$(9/87^*(65+4)^{\wedge} - 3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
2844216	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3) - 21)$	3182085	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(54-3^{\wedge}2-2^{\wedge}1)$
2847240	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - (5^{\wedge}(4+3) - 21))$	3188630	$(-9-8)+7+6^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
2847583	$-9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 - 3^*21$	3188634	$(9-8) - 7+6^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
2847601	$9 + ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 - 3^*21$	3188658	$(-9+8)+7+6^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
2847613	$-9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 - 32 - 1$	3188662	$(9+8-7)+6^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
2847614	$-9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 + 32^{\wedge}1$	3195207	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(54+3^{\wedge}2-2^{\wedge}1)$
2847615	$-9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 - 32 - 1$	3199870	$9^*(- 8 - 7) + 6 - ((5^*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
2847622	$-9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 - 3 - 21$	3200130	$(9^*(8+7) - 6) + (5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2) + 1$
2847628	$(-9 + ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 + 3) - 21$	3203541	$-9^*(8^*7^* - 6^{\wedge}5 + 43^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
2847631	$9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 - 32 - 1$	3203611	$(9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) + 4) / 32 - 1$
2847632	$9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 - 32 / 1$	3218513	$(9-8^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5+4)^*(-32+1))$
2847671	$9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 - (3^*2+1)$	3236868	$(9^*87 - (6^*5)^{\wedge}4)^*((-3-2)+1)$
2847677	$(-9 + ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 + 32) - 1$	3237256	$(98^*7 - (6^*5)^{\wedge}4)^*((-3-2)+1)$
2847678	$-9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 + 32 / 1$	3239874	$-98 + (-7 + (6^*5)^{\wedge}4)^*(3+2-1)$
2847679	$(-9 + ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 + 32) + 1$	3239930	$-98 + (-7 - (6^*5)^{\wedge}4)^*((-3-2)+1)$
2847682	$9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 - 3 + 21$	3240126	$98 + (-7 - (6^*5)^{\wedge}4)^*((-3-2)+1)$
2847688	$9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 - 3 + 21$	3241134	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(54 - (3^{\wedge}2 - 2 - 1))$
2847690	$9/8^*((7^*-6+5)^*43)^{\wedge}2 - 1$	3242744	$(98^*7 + (6^*5)^{\wedge}4)^*((3+2)-1)$
2847695	$9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 - 32 - 1$	3243132	$(9^*87 + (6^*5)^{\wedge}4)^*((3+2)-1)$
2847696	$9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 + 32 / 1$	3253481	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6 - (5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
2847697	$9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 - 32 + 1$	3264560	$((9-8)/7+6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
2847709	$-9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 + 3^*21$	3274050	$(9 / (8^*7)+6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
2847727	$9 + ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 + 3^*21$	3279591	$(-9+8)^*7^*((6+5)^{\wedge}4)^*(32-1)$
2869501	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7 - 6^*5) / ((4^*3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	3280368	$(-9+8)^* - 7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3) - 21)$
2908160	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^* - 5^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	3281124	$(9-8)^*7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3) - (2+1))$
2952936	$9^*((8+7)+6)^*(5^{\wedge}(4^*3/2) - 1)$	3281208	$(9-8)^*7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3) - (2-1))$
2953314	$-9^*((8+7)+6)^*(-5^{\wedge}(4^*3/2) - 1)$	3281243	$-98 - 7^*(6^*(- 5^{\wedge}(4+3) - 2) - 1)$
2956497	$-9^*(8^*7/6 - (5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	3281292	$(-9+8)^* - 7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2-1)$
2956665	$9^*(8^*7/6 + (5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	3281376	$(-9+8)^* - 7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2+1)$
2963241	$9^*((-87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3) / -2 - 1)$	3292469	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4)))^*(3+2) - 1$
2963259	$-9^*((-87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3) / 2 - 1)$	3292471	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4)))^*(3+2)+1$
2963268	$9^*((87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3) / 2 - 1)$	3292505	$-9+87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))^*(3+2) - 1$
2963286	$9^*((87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3) / 2 + 1)$	3292507	$-9+87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))^*(3+2)+1$
2966600	$(9-8)^*7^*((654-3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	3292523	$9+87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))^*(3+2) - 1$
2972167	$9^*((-8^*(7+65)+4/3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	3292525	$9+87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))^*(3+2)+1$
2981879	$-9+8^{\wedge}7^*(6-5+(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	3292559	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4)))^*(3+2) - 1$
2981897	$9+8^{\wedge}7^*(6-5+(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	3292561	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4)))^*(3+2)+1$
2984184	$((9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6 - (5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$	3307626	$((9-8)^*7^*6+5^{\wedge}43)^*21$
2990080	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^* - 5^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	3308877	$9/8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*(4-3))^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
2997000	$(9/8^*-7-6)^*(5^*-4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	3312383	$(-9-8)+(7^*65^*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$
3013392	$(9-8)/7^*6^*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	3312417	$9+8+(7^*65^*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$
3021536	$(9-8)^*7^*((654+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	3320352	$(-9+8)^* - 7^*6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3 - (2+1))$
3039795	$(9-8/7)^*((-6+5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	3326787	$9^*((8^*76)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3) - 21)$
3043096	$98^*(((-7+6^{\wedge}5)^*4-3) - 21)$	3326955	$9^*(8^*76)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3) - 21$
3043684	$98^*((7-6^{\wedge}5)^* - 4+3 - 21)$	3326997	$9^*(8^*76)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+21$
3047517	$-9^*(8^*7^*-6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$	3327165	$9^*((8^*76)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+21)$
3052700	$98^*((-7-6^{\wedge}5)^* - 4 - 3+21)$	3337434	$9/8^*(7/(654-3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
3053288	$98^*((7+6^{\wedge}5)^*4+3)+21$	3339504	$(-9+8)^* - 7^*6^*(5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$
3053475	$9^*(8^*7^*-6+5)^*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$	3356568	$9^*-8^*((-7 - (-6^{\wedge}5+4)^*3)^* - 2 - 1)$
3071027	$(-9/8+7)^*((6 - (5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	3357216	$9^*8^*((-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4-3)) - 21)$
3080192	$(-9+8^*7)^{\wedge}(6-5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	3358440	$9^*8^*((-7 - (-6^{\wedge}5+4)^*3)^* - 2 - 1)$
3089790	$(-9+8/7)^* - 6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 - 1))$	3358950	$(-9^*87+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3 - 21$
3103230	$(9 / (-8^*7)+6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2) - 1)$	3358992	$(-9^*87+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3+21$
3104595	$9^*87^*65^*((4^{\wedge}3 - 2) - 1)$	3359085	$(9^*8^*-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3+21$
3112720	$((-9+8)/7+6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2) - 1)$	3359379	$(9^*8^*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3 - 21$
3122257	$(-9/8+7)^*((6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2))+1)$	3359472	$(9^*87+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3 - 21$
3124980	$(98/7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)^*2 - 1)$	3359514	$(9^*87+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3+21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
3360024	$9^*8*((-7+(6^{\wedge}5+4)^*3)^*2+1)$	3748017	$-9^*8-7+((-6-5)^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
3361248	$9^*8*((7+6^{\wedge}(5+4-3))^+21)$	3748175	$(9^*8+7)+((-6-5)^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
3361896	$9^*8*((-7-(6^{\wedge}5+4)^*3)^*-2-1)$	3786525	$9/((8^{\wedge}7*65/4+3)+2)^{\wedge}-1$
3370311	$((9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)^*-3)^*2-1$	3798900	$(9^*(8+7)^{\wedge}-6/(5^{\wedge}-4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
3370312	$((-9-8)^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5+4)+3)^*-2/1$	3924099	$(9+8/7)^*((-6+5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
3370313	$((9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)^*-3)^*2+1$	3939912	$9^*8*(76^*5*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
3370323	$((9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3)^*2-1$	3950963	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*3^*2-1$
3370324	$((-9-8)^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5+4)+3)^*2/1$	3950965	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*3^*2+1$
3370325	$((9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3)^*2+1$	3950999	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*3^*2-1$
3382056	$(9^*8+7/6)^*(5^*43)^{\wedge}2-1)$	3951000	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)^*3)^*2^*1$
3399228	$9/8^*7*((654+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	3951001	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*3^*2+1$
3399237	$9/8^*(7/(654+3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	3951035	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*3^*2-1$
3410284	$(-9+(-8+7^{\wedge}6)/5)^*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	3951036	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)^*3)^*2^*1$
3411966	$((-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-(32+1))$	3951037	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*3^*2+1$
3412894	$(9-(8-7^{\wedge}6)/5)^*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	3951071	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*3^*2-1$
3413358	$(9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)/5)^*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	3951073	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*3^*2+1$
3422208	$(9/-8+7^*6^*5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$	3967488	$9^*8^*7^*(6^{\wedge}5+4^*(3+21))$
3426159	$(-9+8^*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)^*(32+1)$	3986517	$(-9-8)^*(7^*6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*(-2-1)$
3441375	$9/8^*((7^*6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	3988638	$(-9-8/7)^*-6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
3443375	$(9/8+7)^*((654-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	3988872	$9^*8^*((76^*(5+4)^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$
3459072	$(9/8+7^*6^*5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$	3989304	$9^*8^*((76^*(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$
3468600	$9^*8^*(7^*6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	4003479	$9^*-87^*(6-5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
3468969	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2)^*-1$	4003670	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)^*((-6-5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)+2)-1$
3469305	$(9-8)^*7^*((-6-5)/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	4003672	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)^*((-6-5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)+2)+1$
3490729	$(-9-8)^*(7^*6+(5-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	4005045	$9^*-87^*(6-5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
3492157	$(9+8)^*(7^*6-(5-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	4008177	$9^*87^*(6-5^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
3495978	$-9^*(8+(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4+3)^{\wedge}2+1))$	4009743	$9^*87^*(6+5^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
3496122	$9^*(8+(-7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4+3)^{\wedge}2+1))$	4012875	$9^*87^*(6-5^*-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
3500158	$(9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$	4014441	$9^*87^*(6-(-5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
3500370	$-9^*(87-(6^*5+43)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	4017573	$9^*87^*(6-5^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
3501936	$9^*(87+(6^*5+43)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	4035744	$(98^*7+6)^*(54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
3502278	$9^*(-8+(7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4+3)^{\wedge}2+1))$	4116483	$9/8^*7^*((6+(-5-4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
3502422	$9^*(8+(7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4+3)^{\wedge}2+1))$	4116492	$9/8^*(7^*(6+(-5-4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
3504774	$98^*-7^*(6-5^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$	4117540	$((9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+32-1)$
3507140	$(9/8+7)^*((654+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	4117694	$(-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(-4-3)-21$
3507504	$(9/(8+7)+6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$	4117736	$(-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(-4-3)+21$
3507518	$98^*-7^*(6-(5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$	4118629	$((9^*(8-7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4^*(32-1)$
3507933	$(9-8/76)^*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	4133781	$(-98-7^{\wedge}6)+(54^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
3508890	$98^*-7^*(6-5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	4133977	$98-7^{\wedge}6+(54^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
3510864	$(-9+8)^*-7^*6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	4134375	$9^*((-8+7)+6)^{\wedge}5^*(4+3)^*21$
3511634	$98^*7^*(6-5^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$	4190088	$98^*7^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
3513006	$98^*7^*(6+5^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$	4193518	$98^*-7^*(6^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
3513176	$(9-8)^*76^*((5^*43)^{\wedge}2+1)$	4195684	$9^*((-8+7^{\wedge}6)-5)^*(4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
3515381	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	4198320	$98^*-7^*6^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
3515383	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1$	4234678	$98^*-7^*(6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
3517122	$98^*7^*(6-(-5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$	4236050	$98^*7^*(6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
3519866	$98^*7^*(6-5^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$	4239480	$98^*7^*-6^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
3538872	$-9^*(8+(-7+6-5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	4243456	$(-9+(-8-7^*6)^*5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
3539016	$9^*(8+(-7+6-5)^*-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	4247165	$(9/8+7)^*((6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
3553200	$987/(6+54)^{\wedge}(-3+2-1)$	4251372	$-9^*8^*((7/6-(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
3587193	$((9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5)/-4^*-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	4251452	$(-9+8)^*76-(-54^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
3590961	$(9+8/76)^*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	4251684	$9^*8^*((7/6-(-5-4)^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
3595129	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6)/(5+4^{\wedge}(-3+2))+1$	4254264	$9/8^*7^*((6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
3598754	$(9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$	4254273	$9/8^*(7^*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
3610899	$-9+8^*7/6^*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	4258793	$(9-8)^*7^*((65^*4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
3610917	$9+8^*7/6^*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	4271468	$(-9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4)^*3/2-1$
3629664	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}((6-5)+4)^*-3)^*(2+1)$	4271470	$(-9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4)^*3/2+1$
3630960	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}((6-5)+4)^*-3)^*(-2-1)$	4271477	$(-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4^*3)/2-1$
3632850	$-9^*(8+7)^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}-4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	4271479	$(-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4^*3)/2+1$
3634414	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2/1$	4271486	$(9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4^*3)/2-1$
3634423	$-9+(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2/1$	4271488	$(9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4^*3)/2+1$
3634441	$9+(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2/1$	4274108	$9^*((-8+7^{\wedge}6)-5)^*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
3634450	$(9+8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2^*1$	4300758	$(-9+8)^*-7^*6^*((5^*4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
3644151	$-9+8/7^*6^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$	4300842	$(9-8)^*7^*6^*((5^*4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
3644169	$9+8/7^*6^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$	4302360	$(9+8)/7^*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4^*3/2)-1)$
3651930	$9^*(((-8+7)-6+5^{\wedge}4)+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	4318015	$(9/8+7)^*((6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2))+1)$
3659096	$(9-8)^*7^*((6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	4332343	$-9-8/-7^*((6^{\wedge}5/4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
3705714	$-9^*(8+(-7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3)/2^{\wedge}1)$	4332361	$9+8/7^*((6^{\wedge}5/4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
3706173	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3)/2^{\wedge}1)$	4341760	$(-9+8^*7+6)^*5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
3707424	$9^*8^*7^*6^*((5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	4352828	$(9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+32+1)$
3735507	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6+5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	4369079	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6)+(54^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
3735597	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6+5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	4369275	$98+7^{\wedge}6+(54^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
4384347	$((9*(8-7))^6-5)/(4/(32+1))$	5125770	$9*((8+7)^6-5)/(4*(3+2))-1$
4384972	$(9+8^7)*((6+5)^{-4+3+2})-1$	5125788	$9*((8+7)^6-5)/4/(3+2)+1$
4384974	$(9+8^7)*((6+5)^{-4+3+2})+1$	5143807	$(-9-8)+(7*6*54)^{(3-2)+1}$
4389320	$(9/8+7)*((6+(5+4)^3)^2-1)$	5143841	$9+8+(7*6*54)^{(3-2)+1}$
4439074	$(9+8)*((7*(6*5+43))^2+1)$	5184007	$(9-8)*7+(6*5*4)^3*(2+1)$
4439808	$9*8/7*((654+3)^2-1)$	5225256	$9*8*((7*6^5*4/3-2)-1)$
4455920	$(9+8/(-7-6))*((5+4)^{(3*2)-1})$	5225688	$9*8*((7*6^5*4/3+2)+1)$
4479280	$((9+8)/7+6)*((5+4)^{(3*2)-1})$	5241944	$(-9*8*(7+6)+5*4^4(3^2+1))$
4504500	$9/8*((7*6+5^4)^3)^2-1$	5243816	$9*8*(7+6)-5*-4^4(3^2+1)$
4520088	$9/(8-7+6)*((5^4*3)^2-1)$	5248485	$-9/8*(7^6-(5+4)^4(3^2+1))$
4531464	$(9*-87+6)*(54/-3)^{(2+1)}$	5267952	$(-9+87^6(-6+5+4))^*(3^2-1)$
4538368	$((-9+8*7)^*-6+5)/-4^4(-3*2-1)$	5268096	$(9+87^6(-6+5+4))^*(3^2-1)$
4562500	$((-9-8)+7)^6*(5+(4/3)^{-2}-1)$	5361093	$(9+8/-7+6)*((-5^4+3)^2-1)$
4572225	$((9-8)*7*6^5*4-3)*21$	5364254	$98/7*((-6+5^4)^4(3-2)+1)$
4574267	$(-9-((-8*(7+6)+5)^4-3))/-21$	5392410	$9*((8^7*6-5^4)^3)/21$
4594995	$9/8*((7*6+5)^4)^2-1$	5392800	$9*((8^7-6)+5^4)/(3+2^4-1)$
4601448	$(9*87+6)*(54/3)^{(2+1)}$	5423104	$(-9+(-8+76)*5)/4^4(-3*2-1)$
4613740	$(9+8^7-6)*(5^4(-4+3)+2)-1$	5451639	$-9+(8^7-6^4(-5+4*3))^*(2+1)$
4613742	$(9+8^7-6)*(5^4(-4+3)+2)+1$	5451657	$9+(8^7-6^4(-5+4*3))^*(2+1)$
4634667	$-9*(8*7*6^5-43^4(2+1))$	5487525	$(-9*87^6-6*(-5^4-4))^4(-3/2+1)$
4640625	$(9*(8+7)^6-6/(5-4/3))^4(-2+1)$	5489280	$9/8*((7*6+5)^4-321)$
4685815	$-9+8^7((7-6)*5)^*(4^3)^2-1$	5570496	$9*8*76*(-5+4^4(3+2)-1)$
4711938	$98*(7*6+5)*(4^4(3+2)-1)$	5574254	$98/7*(6+5^4)^4(3-2)+1$
4716530	$(9-8^7(-7+6))*((-5-4)^4(3^2-1))$	5575896	$9*-8*(76*(5-4^4(3+2))+1)$
4718172	$-9*8*(7/6*5-4^4(3^2-1))$	5575959	$-9*(8*76*(5-4^4(3+2))+1)$
4719012	$9*8*(7/6*5+4^4(3^2-1))$	5575977	$9*(8*76*(-5+4^4(3+2))+1)$
4721150	$-98*(7*6+5)*(-4^4(3+2)-1)$	5576040	$9*8*(-76*(5-4^4(3+2))+1)$
4741551	$-9*((8*7)^4((-6+5)+4)+3)^*(2+1)$	5581440	$9*-8*76*(5-4^4(3+2)-1)$
4741713	$9*((8*7)^4((-6+5)+4)+3)^*(2+1)$	5583939	$(-9-8)*(7*6-(5+4^4)^4(2+1))$
4754158	$(-9+8^7+6^4(-5+4*3))^2/1$	5585367	$(9+8)*(7*6+(5+4^4)^4(2+1))$
4754167	$-9+(8^7+6^4(-5+4*3))^2/1$	5624880	$9*-8*(7/6-5^4(4+3)+2^4-1)$
4754185	$9+(8^7+6^4(-5+4*3))^2/1$	5624952	$9*-8*(7/6-5^4(4+3)-2^4-1)$
4754194	$(9+8^7+6^4(-5+4*3))^2*1$	5625048	$9*8*(7/6+5^4(4+3)-2^4-1)$
4782564	$9*8*6*(-5+4^4(3+2)-1)$	5625120	$9*8*(7/6+5^4(4+3)+2^4-1)$
4786479	$9*-8*7*(6*(5-4^4(3+2))+1)$	5630679	$-9*(8*76*(-5-4^4(3+2))+1)$
4787136	$9*-8*(7-65*(4^4(3+2)-1))$	5630697	$9*(8*-76*(-5-4^4(3+2))+1)$
4787253	$-9*(87*6*(5-4^4(3+2))+1)$	5630760	$9*8*(76*(5+4^4(3+2))+1)$
4787271	$9*(87*6*(-5+4^4(3+2))+1)$	5636160	$9*8*-76*(-5-4^4(3+2)-1)$
4788045	$9*8*7*(-6*(5-4^4(3+2))+1)$	5637438	$(9+8)/7*(6*((-5^4+3)^2-1))$
4788144	$9*8*(7+65*(4^4(3+2)-1))$	5669769	$(9-8)*7*((6*5)^4-32)-1$
4791744	$9*-8*(7-(65*4^4(3+2)-1))$	5672247	$(9-8)*7*((6*5)^4+321)$
4791888	$9*-8*(7-65*4^4(3+2)-1)$	5718016	$(-9-(-8+76)*5)/-4^4(-3*2-1)$
4792752	$9*8*(7-65*-4^4(3+2)-1)$	5718672	$9*-8*(76-(-5+43^4(2+1)))$
4792896	$9*8*(7-(-65*4^4(3+2)-1))$	5719320	$9*-8*(7-(-65+43^4(2+1)))$
4796496	$9*8*(-7-65*(-4^4(3+2)-1))$	5719392	$9*-8*(76-5-43^4(2+1))$
4797504	$9*8*(7-65*(-4^4(3+2)-1))$	5719529	$(9+8^7)*6/(5^4(-4+3)+2)-1$
4810752	$(9/8*7*6^4-5*4^4-3)^4(-2+1)$	5719531	$(9+8^7)*6/(5^4(-4+3)+2)+1$
4821543	$-9*(8/7*6*(5^4(4+3)+2)+1)$	5720328	$9*8*(7-65+43^4(2+1))$
4821561	$9*(8/7*6*(5^4(4+3)+2)+1)$	5728680	$9*-8*(7-65-43^4(2+1))$
4829544	$9*8*7*6*(-5-(4^4(3+2)-1))$	5729616	$9*8*(76-5+43^4(2+1))$
4833459	$9*-8*7*(-6*(5+4^4(3+2))+1)$	5729688	$9*8*(7-(-65-43^4(2+1)))$
4834233	$-9*(87*6*(-5-4^4(3+2))+1)$	5730336	$9*8*(76-(-5-43^4(2+1)))$
4834251	$9*(87*6*(-5-4^4(3+2))+1)$	5767062	$((9+8*7)^4(-6+5+4)-3)^*21$
4835025	$9*8*7*(6*(5+4^4(3+2))+1)$	5767188	$((9+8*7)^4(-6+5+4)+3)^*21$
4838940	$9*8*7*6*(-5-4^4(3+2)-1)$	5790999	$((9+8+7)^6-5-4)/(32+1)$
4849390	$(9+8^7(-7+6))*((-5-4)^4(3^2-1))$	5816320	$(-9-(8*7+6))^*-5/4^4(-3*2-1)$
4928399	$((98*7-6*(-5-4))^3)^2-1$	5825400	$((-9+8^7+6)-5)*((4/3)^2+1)$
4928401	$((98*7-6*(-5-4))^3)^2+1$	5882200	$(9-8)*7^6*5*((4+3)^2+1)$
4975434	$9/8*(((-76-5^4)^3)^2-1)$	5882700	$(9-8)*(7^6+5)*((4+3)^2+1)$
4980356	$(-9+8)*76*(5-4^4(3^2-1))$	5906376	$(9/(8+(76*5-4)^3))^4(-2+1)$
4981116	$(-9+8)*76*(5+4^4(3^2-1))$	5923638	$9*(87^6(-6-(-5-4))-321)$
5038080	$9*(-8+7/6)*5*-4^4(3^2+1)$	5925960	$9*(87^6(-6+5+4)-3*21)$
5039237	$(9*87-(-6^4(5+4)+3))/2-1$	5926230	$9*(87^6(-6-(-5-4))-(-32+1))$
5039239	$(9*87-(-6^4(5+4)+3))/2+1$	5926248	$9*(87^6(-6-(-5-4))-32+1)$
5039240	$(9*87+6^4(5+4)+3)/2-1$	5926284	$9*(87^6(-6-(-5-4))-3^4(2+1))$
5039242	$(9*87+6^4(5+4)+3)/2+1$	5926311	$9*(87^6(-6-(-5-4))-(-3+21))$
5055456	$((9+8)*7)^4(-6+5+4)^3-21$	5926365	$9*(87^6(-6-(-5-4))+3-21)$
5055498	$((9+8)*7)^4(-6+5+4)^3+21$	5926437	$9*((87^6(-6-(-5-4))-3^4(2)-1)$
5059101	$(9-8)*7^6+5^4*43-21$	5926472	$9*(87^6((-6+5)+4)-3*2)-1$
5059143	$((9-8)*7^6+5^4*43+21)$	5926474	$9*(87^6((-6+5)+4)-3*2)+1$
5110000	$(9+8/(7+6))*((5+4)^4(3^2-1))$	5926479	$9*(87^6(-6-(-5-4))-3)-21$
5118840	$9*8/7*((6^5/4^4-3+2)-1)$	5926491	$9*(87^6(-6-(-5-4))-3-2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
5926553	$9^*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3)-2+1$	6693981	$9/8^*(((-7-6)^5)^4/3-2-1)$
5926555	$9^*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3)+2-1$	6693996	$9-(8/((-7-65^{\wedge}4)^*3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
5926557	$(9^*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3)+2)+1$	6733824	$(-9-(-8-76)^5)/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
5926563	$9^*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3+2-1)$	6736833	$-9+8/76^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
5926575	$9^*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3)+21$	6736851	$9+8/76^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
5926580	$9^*(87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3^*2)-1$	6758400	$9^*(-8-7/6)^*5^*-4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$
5926582	$9^*(87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3^*2)+1$	6890593	$((9-8^{\wedge}7)+6)^*(-5-4^{\wedge}3)/21$
5926617	$9^*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	6941586	$((-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-3^*21)$
5926689	$9^*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3+21)$	6990508	$(9/(8^{\wedge}7*6*5+4^*3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
5926743	$9^*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3+21)$	6991872	$(9^*8^{\wedge}-7/(6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2))))^{\wedge}-1$
5926806	$9^*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+32-1)$	7028736	$(-9+(-8-76)^5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
5926824	$9^*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+32+1)$	7075224	$9^*8^*(-7-6^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)))$
5927094	$9^*(87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3^*21)$	7079544	$-9^*8^*(7-6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)))$
5935904	$(-9+8)^*76^*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+21)$	7080552	$9^*8^*(7+6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)))$
5963767	$-9+8^{\wedge}7/6^*((5/4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	7098639	$(9/((8+7^{\wedge}6)^*543))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
5963785	$9+8^{\wedge}7/6^*((5/4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	7119115	$(-9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4)^*(3/2+1)$
5980077	$9/8^*(7^*(6+5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	7119160	$(9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4)^*(3/2+1)$
5980086	$9/8^*7^*((6+5)+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$	7131255	$-9+(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*(2+1)$
5980160	$((9^*8+7)-6)^*5^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$	7131273	$9+(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*(2+1)$
6023680	$(-9+8-7^{\wedge}6)/-5^*4^{\wedge}((3+2)-1)$	7143415	$-9+(-8^*(-7-6)+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
6036114	$98^*7^*(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	7143433	$9+(-8^*(-7-6)+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
6037486	$98^*7^*(6^{\wedge}5-(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$	7192576	$(9^*8^*-7+65)/-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
6046632	$9/(8+7)^*((6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3)+21)$	7260372	$987^*6^*((5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
6064289	$98^*(((-7-6)^{\wedge}5+4)/(-3^*2)-1)$	7295161	$(-98/7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)^*(2+1)$
6064386	$98^*(((-7-6)^{\wedge}5+4)/(-3^*2)-1)$	7364240	$(9-(8/7-6))^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
6064388	$98^*(((-7-6)^{\wedge}5+4)/(-3^*2)+1)$	7373730	$(9/8^*7+6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
6064485	$-98^*(((-7-6)^{\wedge}5+4)/(3^*2)-1)$	7398391	$-9+(8^*(-7^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3))^{\wedge}2/1$
6077872	$(9/((8^*7+6^*5)^{\wedge}4+32))^{\wedge}-1$	7398409	$9+(8^*(-7^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3))^{\wedge}2/1$
6086752	$9^*87^*(6^{\wedge}5+(-4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	7436288	$(9/8-7^*65)/-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
6090464	$9^*87^*(6^{\wedge}5-(-4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	7447616	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6-5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
6128480	$(-9+8)^*(7-((65-4)^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	7470701	$((9/8+7)-6)^*((5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
6133760	$(9/-8+76)^*5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$	7473152	$(9/8+7^*65)/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
6207488	$(9/8-76^*5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$	7506590	$(9/8+7+6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
6244352	$(9/8+76^*5)/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$	7509749	$9/8^*((7-(-6^{\wedge}5+4)/-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
6245397	$(9-8/-7+6)^*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	7552440	$9/8^*(((-7+6^{\wedge}5+4)/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
6256640	$(9/-8+7)^*65/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$	7564104	$9/8^*(((-7-6^{\wedge}5+4)/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
6300666	$(9^*8/7+6)^*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	7579670	$9/8^*(((-7-6^{\wedge}5+4)/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
6310850	$(-9/8+7+6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$	7585792	$((-9+87)^*6-5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$
6318080	$(9/8+76)^*5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$	7611456	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6-5/-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
6352806	$(9/8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*((-4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	7618551	$-9+(-87-6)^*-5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
6353286	$(9/8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*((-4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	7618569	$9+(-87-6)^*-5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
6406144	$(-9-8)^*((-7+6^*5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1))$	7628256	$(9+8+7-6)^{\wedge}5^*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
6454272	$9^*8^{\wedge}7/6^*((5/4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	7650270	$9^*((8+((-7-6)^5)^{\wedge}4)-3)/21$
6471206	$(-9^*8-7)^*(6-5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1))$	7661815	$-9+(8^*(7^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3))^{\wedge}2/1$
6472154	$(9^*8+7)^*(6-5/-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1))$	7661833	$9+(8^*(7^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3))^{\wedge}2/1$
6479719	$-9-8^*(7-((-6^*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	7687717	$(9+8)/((7^*6)^{\wedge}5-43))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
6479737	$9-8^*(7-((-6^*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	7733448	$9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1))$
6479831	$-9+8^*(7+(-6^*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	7763911	$(-98/7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)^*(-2-1)$
6479849	$9+8^*(7+(-6^*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	7782324	$(9-8)^*76^*((5^*4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
6480151	$-9-8^*(7-((-6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	7798056	$((-9+87)/6)^{\wedge}5+43)^*21$
6480169	$9-8^*(7-((-6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	7829971	$(9/87/((6^*5)^{\wedge}4-3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
6480263	$-9+8^*(7+(-6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	7882148	$((9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3^*21)$
6480281	$9+8^*(7+(-6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	7892640	$(-9+8)^*-7^*6^{\wedge}5^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
6482116	$((9^*8^*7+6)^*-5+4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$	7893653	$9^{\wedge}8-((-7^*(6+5))^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
6482134	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)^*((6+5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)+2+1)$	7893707	$9^{\wedge}8-((-7^*(6+5))^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
6495684	$((9+8)^*-7-(-6-5)^{\wedge}(4+3))/(2+1)$	7901720	$((9^*8^*(7+6)+5)-4)^*3^{\wedge}2-1$
6508927	$9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)^*-4)^*3/21$	7901722	$((9^*8^*(7+6)+5)-4)^*3^{\wedge}2+1$
6538644	$(9^*(-8^*7-6))^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))^*21$	7970391	$9/(-8+7)+6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
6581445	$(9/8+7)^*((6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3)+21$	8044400	$(-9-8)^*-7^*(65^*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$
6584940	$(9-87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	8045834	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(7-(-6-5))-4)/3-21$
6585030	$9^*-87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	8045876	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(7-(-6-5))-4)/3+21$
6585120	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	8050824	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6+(-54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
6591795	$(9/8^*7-6)^*((5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	8052550	$(98-76)^{\wedge}5^*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
6612606	$(-9+8)^*-7^*6^*(54^{\wedge}3-21)$	8077312	$(9^*8^*-7+6+5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
6613362	$(-9+8)^*-7^*6^*(54^{\wedge}3-(2+1))$	8132031	$9^*((-8+7-65)^{\wedge}4+3)/21$
6613446	$(-9+8)^*-7^*6^*(54^{\wedge}3-(2-1))$	8156742	$(9^*8^*7-6)^*((-5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$
6613530	$(-9+8)^*-7^*6^*(54^{\wedge}3+2-1)$	8161722	$(9^*8^*-7+6)^*(-5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$
6613614	$(-9+8)^*-7^*6^*(54^{\wedge}3+2+1)$	8169488	$9^{\wedge}8-(7/(6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
6635511	$-9+(-87+6)^*-5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$	8177463	$9^*((8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
6635529	$9+(-87+6)^*-5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$	8177481	$9^*((8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
6655000	$((98-76)^*5^{\wedge}(4/3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	8241152	$(9^*8^*-7+6-5)^*-4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$
6693978	$-9+(8/((7+65^{\wedge}4)^*3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	8263071	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)+(654/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
8263089	$9 \cdot 8^{7+(654/3)^{(2+1)}}$	9719992	$((-8)+7) \cdot ((6^5)^{4 \cdot 3/2-1})$
8272656	$9^* 8^* - 7^* (-6^5 - 4^{(3^*2+1)})$	9720008	$((-8)+7) \cdot ((6^5)^{4 \cdot 3/2+1})$
8273920	$(9^* 8^* 7+6-5)^* 4^{(3^*2+1)}$	9786713	$(9/((8^7 \cdot 6+5)^*(4+3)-2))^{-1}$
8331432	$9^*(8/7^*((-6^5)^{4+3}(-2+1)))$	9820628	$(-98-7^6)+(5^*43)^{(2+1)}$
8334071	$-9+8^{7/6^*((5-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)}$	9820824	$98-7^6+(5^*43)^{(2+1)}$
8334089	$9+8^{7/6^*((-5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)}$	9843456	$(-98/7+6^5 \cdot 4^3)^* 21$
8353290	$(9^* 8^* 7+6)^* (-5+4^{(3^*2+1)})$	9844044	$(98/7-6^* - 5^{\wedge}(4+3))^* 21$
8355721	$(-9-8)^*(7-6^5/4^{(-3^*2-1)})$	9882159	$((-9-8)^* 7^6 - 5)^* 4^3 \cdot 21$
8355840	$((9+87)+6)^* 5/4^{(-3^*2-1)}$	9904396	$(9-8)^* 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 4^{(-3-2+1)}$
8355959	$(9+8)^*(7-6^* - 5/4^{(-3^*2-1)})$	9917013	$(-9/(8+((-7-6)^{-5})^{4^*}(-3-2)))^{-1}$
8358390	$(9^* 8^* 7+6)^*(5+4^{(3^*2+1)})$	9938132	$-9^{\wedge}((-8-7)/-6)+(5^*43)^{(2+1)}$
8372224	$(-9-8^*(-7-6)^* 5)/4^{(-3^*2-1)}$	9938299	$(-9+8)^* 7^6 - (-5^*43)^{(2+1)}$
8404272	$9^* - 8^*(7^6 - 5^{(4+3)^*(2+1)})$	9938368	$(-9+8)^{\wedge} 7 - 6+(5^*43)^{(2+1)}$
8427120	$(9-8/-7^* 6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$	9938370	$(9-8)^{\wedge} 7 - 6+(5^*43)^{(2+1)}$
8427564	$9/8^*((7+(6-5^*4)^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 2-1)$	9938380	$((-9+8)^{\wedge} 7+6)+(5^*43)^{(2+1)}$
8427853	$9^* 8^* 7^6 + (-5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	9938382	$((9-8)^{\wedge} 7+6)+(5^*43)^{(2+1)}$
8437760	$((9^* 8^* 7+6)+5)^* 4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$	9938618	$9^{\wedge}((-8-7)/-6)+(5^*43)^{(2+1)}$
8489160	$9^* - 8^*(7+(6^* 5+4)^{\wedge} 3^*(-2-1))$	9965529	$((-9+87)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3)^* 21$
8513375	$(9+8^* 7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)^*(32-1)$	9965655	$((-9+87)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3)^* 21$
8513603	$9^* 8^* 7^6 + (5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	9966761	$(-9-((8+7)^6 - 5)/-4)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
8515625	$(9-8^* 7^* 6)/(-5^{(-4-3)^*(2+1)})$	9966824	$(9+((8+7)^6 - 5)/4)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
8542776	$9^*((8+7)^6 - 5)/(4^* 3 - 21)$	10055926	$(-98+7^6)+(5^*43)^{(2+1)}$
8542929	$(-9-(((8+7)^6 - 5)/-4+3))^*(2+1)$	10056122	$98+7^6+(5^*43)^{(2+1)}$
8542944	$9^*((8+7)^6 - 5)/(4^* 3 - 21)$	10110954	$((9+8)^* 7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)^* 3^* 2^{\wedge} 1$
8542971	$(9+((8+7)^6 - 5)/4)^* 3 - 21$	10233601	$((-9-8)^*(7^6+5)^* - 4+3)^{\wedge} 2^* 1$
8542975	$9+((8+7)^6 - 5)/4^* 3+2-1$	10237661	$(9+8^*((7+65)^{\wedge} 4+3))/21$
8542986	$9^*((8+7)^6 - 5)/(4^* 3)+21$	10252743	$(9/((8^7 \cdot 6+5)^* 4 - 3+2))^{-1}$
8543001	$(9-((8+7)^6 - 5)/-4+3)^*(2+1)$	10353756	$((-9^* 8-7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3)^* - 21$
8543013	$(9+((8+7)^6 - 5)/4)^* 3+21$	10353882	$((9^* 8+7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3)^* 21$
8543154	$9^*((8+7)^6 - 5)/(4^* 3+21)$	10356604	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))^* 4^*(32-1)$
8548721	$((9+8)^{\wedge} 7 - 65)/(4+3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1$	10360097	$-9^*(8+7)+(654/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
8549046	$9^*((8^7+65^{\wedge} 4)-3)/21$	10360153	$9^* - 8 - 7 - (654/-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
8578960	$(9-(-8/7-6))^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$	10360311	$9^* 8+7+(654/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
8611385	$(9-8)/7^*((6^{\wedge} 5-4^* 3)^{\wedge} 2-1)$	10360367	$9^*(8+7)+(654/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
8622480	$(9-8)/7^*((-6^{\wedge} 5+4+3)^{\wedge} 2-1)$	10407915	$(-9/8+7)^*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4^* 3/2)-1)$
8636196	$9^*((8^* 7+6+5)^{\wedge} 4+3)/21$	10475511	$-9+8^{\wedge} 7^* (6-5^* 4^{(-3-2+1)})$
8653584	$(9-8)/7^*((6^{\wedge} 5+4+3)^{\wedge} 2-1)$	10475529	$9+8^{\wedge} 7^* (6-5^* 4^{(-3-2+1)})$
8654880	$(9^* 8/7+6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$	10495991	$-9+8^{\wedge} 7^* (6+5^* 4^{(-3-2)-1})$
8749991	$-9+8^* 7^* 6/(5^{(-4-3)^*(2+1)})$	10496009	$9+8^{\wedge} 7^* (6+5^* 4^{(-3-2)-1})$
8750009	$9+8^* 7^* 6/(5^{(-4-3)^*(2+1)})$	10513404	$9/8^*((-765^* 4+3)^{\wedge} 2-1)$
8772813	$9/8^*((-7-6)^{\wedge} 5 - 43)^* - 21$	10530405	$(9/(8-7))^{\wedge} 6^5 \cdot 4^*(4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
8781192	$9^* 8^* 7^*((-6-5)^* 4^* 3)^{\wedge} 2-1$	10554714	$9/8^*(765^* 4+3)^{\wedge} 2-1$
8874702	$(-9^* 8-7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))^*(3-21)$	10567680	$(9^*(-8-7)+6)^* - 5^* 4^{\wedge}(3^* 2+1)$
8890632	$9^* 8^*(7^6 - (-54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	10607167	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*(4^3 \cdot 3^* 2-1)$
8931965	$98^*(7/6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2)-1)$	10662948	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - (7-6)^* 5)/(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
8932161	$-98^*(7/6^*((-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2)-1))$	10696887	$9^*((8^7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^* 3))/2-1)$
8957256	$(9^* 87-6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3^{\wedge} 2-1)$	10696895	$9^*(8^7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^* 3))/2-1$
8958648	$(9^* 87+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(-3^{\wedge} 2+1)$	10696897	$9^*(8^7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^* 3))/2+1$
8984375	$(9-8^* 7^* - 6)^* 5^{\wedge}(4+3)/(2+1)$	10696905	$9^*((8^7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^* 3))/2+1)$
9062500	$(9/(87^* 6^* 5^{\wedge}(4+3)^* 2))^{-1}$	10727235	$(9/(8-7))^{\wedge} 6^5 \cdot 4^*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
9062625	$(9+8^* 7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)^*(32+1)$	10749544	$((9^* 8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4)/(3/2+1)$
9063228	$(-9^* 8-7^* 6)^*(5-43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	10774209	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))^* 4^*(32+1)$
9064368	$(9^* 8+7^* 6)^*(5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	10937493	$(9-8)^* 7^*((6^5 \cdot 4/3)^{\wedge} 2-1)$
9100144	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge} 6+5+43)/21$	11024772	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))^* 4^*(32+1)$
9106027	$((9/8)^{\wedge} 7^* - 6+5)^* - 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge} 2+1)$	11035601	$(9^* 8^* 7^6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)/2-1$
9109504	$((-9-(8+7))^* 6+5)^* - 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge} 2-1)$	11035603	$(9^* 8^* 7^6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)/2+1$
9206248	$(9+8)/7^*((6^{\wedge} 5/4+3)^{\wedge} 2-1)$	11042163	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(-5-4^{\wedge} 3^*(-2-1))$
9208008	$-9^*(-8^* 7^6 - 5/4^{(-3^*2-1)})$	11068929	$(9+8^*(7^*(6-5+3)))^{\wedge} 2^* 1$
9260953	$9+8^* - 7+(6^* 5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	11074210	$(9-(8+7)^6)^*(5+4-3)^{\wedge} 2-1$
9261047	$-9+8^* 7+(6^* - 5^*(-4-3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	11165202	$((-9+8)+7)^*(6^* 5^* 4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
9322496	$(9^* 8^* 7+65)/4^{(-3^*2-1)}$	11184808	$(9/(-8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)+4)/(-3^*2))^{-1}$
9344256	$(9^*(8^*((7+6)^* 5+4))^{\wedge} - 3^* 2)^{-1}$	11196570	$(-9^* 87+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3^{\wedge} 2+1)$
9355264	$((-9-87)^* 6+5)/-4^{(-3^*2-1)}$	11197447	$(9-8)^* 7-6^{\wedge}(5+4)^*(-3^{\wedge} 2-1)$
9513450	$9^* 87^* 6^{\wedge} 5^*((4/3)^{\wedge} 2+1)$	11198310	$(9^* 87+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3^{\wedge} 2+1)$
9519104	$((-9-87)^* - 6+5)/4^{(-3^*2-1)}$	11248056	$9^* 8^*((-7-(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))))^* 2-1$
9525033	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}((6-5)+4))^* 3^* - 21$	11248200	$9^* 8^*((-7-(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))))^* 2+1$
9529377	$9/8^*((76-5)^{\wedge} 4/3-2-1)$	11248560	$9^* - 8^*(7-(-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)))^* 2+1$
9529404	$9/8^*((76-5)^{\wedge} 4/3+21)$	11248704	$9^* 8^*((-7-(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)))^* 2+1)$
9534105	$9^*(-8-7^{\wedge}((6-5)+4))^* 3^* - 21$	11248992	$9^* - 8^*(7-(-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^* 2+1)$
9643608	$9^* 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	11249136	$9^* 8^*((-7-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^* 2+1)$
9655026	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(7-6+5)-4)/(3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	11249784	$9^* 8^*((-7+6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^* 2-1)$
9687654	$(-9^{\wedge} 8+(7^* 6^*(5+4)-3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	11250216	$9^* 8^*((7-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^* 2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
11250864	$9^* - 8^* (-7 - 6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2+1)$	12342881	$(9^*8+7)^* ((-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2+1)$
11251008	$9^*8^*(7 - (-6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2)+1)$	12343197	$(9^*8+7)^* ((-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2) - 1)$
11251296	$9^*8^*((7 - (-6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2) - 1)$	12343355	$(9^*8+7)^* (-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2+1)$
11251440	$9^*8^*(7 - (-6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2+1)$	12344145	$(9^*8+7)^* (6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2 - 1)$
11251800	$9^* - 8^*((-7 - (6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)))^*2+1)$	12344303	$(9^*8+7)^* ((6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2)+1)$
11251944	$9^*8^*((7 - (-6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3)))^*2+1)$	12344619	$(9^*8+7)^* ((6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2) - 1)$
11287273	$(-9 - 8^*((-7 - 6)^{\wedge}5))^*(4+(-3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge} - 1)$	12344777	$(9^*8+7)^* ((6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2+1)$
11294244	$9^*(- 8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)/ (4^{\wedge}(-3+2) - 1)$	12351801	$((9 - 8)^*7^{\wedge}6*5 - 4^{\wedge}3)^*21$
11294364	$9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)/ (-4^{\wedge}(-3+2)+1)$	12353124	$((9 - 8)^*7^{\wedge}6*5 - 4+3)^*21$
11324718	$((-9 - 8^{\wedge}7)^*6 - 54)/ (-3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	12354489	$((9 - 8)^*7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3)^*21$
11344700	$(-9 - (-8 - 7 - 6)^{\wedge}5)^*((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	12383616	$(-9+8)^* - 7^*6^*(543^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
11344750	$(9+(8+7+6)^{\wedge}5)^*((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	12400934	$(9 - 8)^*7^*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4^*3/2)+1)$
11370374	$-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) - 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$	12422921	$9+8^{\wedge}7*6 - (5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2 - 1)$
11370376	$-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) - 3)^{\wedge}2+1$	12457375	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7 - (-654/3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
11370393	$9+((8+7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4) - 3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$	12457393	$9+8^{\wedge}7+(654/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
11371136	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6^*((5/(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	12475407	$(-9 - 8^*((-7 - 6)^{\wedge}5))^*(4+(3+2)^{\wedge} - 1)$
11390394	$9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*((4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	12521463	$-9 - 8^{\wedge}7*6^*(5^*4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2) - 1)$
11390874	$9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^*((4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	12521481	$9 - 8^{\wedge}7*6^*(5^*4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2) - 1)$
11410874	$-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4))+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$	12541943	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6 - 5^*4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2+1))$
11410876	$-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4))+3)^{\wedge}2+1$	12541961	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6 - 5^*4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2+1))$
11410894	$9+((8+7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4))+3)^{\wedge}2+1$	12550135	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6 - (5 - (4 - 3))^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$
11416412	$98^*7^*((65+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	12550153	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6 - (5 - (4 - 3))^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$
11424400	$(9^*8^*(7^*6+5) - 4)^{\wedge}(3 - (2 - 1))$	12555800	$((-9 - 8)/7+6)^*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
11506082	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*((4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1))$	12577026	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7)^*6 - (54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
11516976	$9^*8^*((-7^*6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2 - 1))$	12577134	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)^*6 - (54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
11523024	$9^* - 8^*((-7^*6 - (5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2 - 1))$	12581125	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7)^*6 - 5 - (4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
11528482	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)/ ((4/3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	12581135	$((-9+8^{\wedge}7)^*6+5) - (4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
11529362	$98^*7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*((4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	12581243	$((9+8^{\wedge}7)^*6+5) - (4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
11529842	$(98^*7^{\wedge}6+5^*((4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1))$	12582453	$9^*((8^{\wedge}7/-6+5)^* - 4 - 32+1)$
11530722	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/ ((4/3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	12582710	$((9 - 8^{\wedge}7)^* - 6 - 5) - (4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
11553122	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^*((4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1))$	12583371	$-9^*((8^{\wedge}7/6+5)^* - 4 - 32+1)$
11632640	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^* - 5/4^{\wedge}(3^*(-2 - 1))$	12584581	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7)^*6 - 5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
11632653	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(5 - 4^{\wedge}3^*(-2 - 1))$	12584689	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)^*6 - 5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
11635804	$9 - ((-8 - 7)^* - 6+5)^{\wedge}4^* - 3)/21$	12584699	$((9+8^{\wedge}7)^*6+5)+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
11647251	$((-9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}6^*(5^*4^*(3+2) - 1)$	12588690	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7)^*6+(54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
11648693	$(9 - 8)^*7^*((6^*5^*43)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	12588798	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)^*6+(54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
11649024	$-9^*(-8 - (76 - 5))/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2 - 1)$	12615671	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6+(5 - (4 - 3))^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$
11694606	$(-9 - 8)^*7^*6^*(5 - 4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$	12615689	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6+(5 - (4 - 3))^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$
11701746	$(9+8)^*7^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$	12623863	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6 - 5^* - 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2+1))$
11707619	$98^*7/6^*((5/4^{\wedge} - 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	12623881	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6 - 5^* - 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2+1))$
11740002	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*6 - 5)/ (4 - 3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	12745728	$9^*8^{\wedge}7/-6^*((-5/4)^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
11750760	$9^*8^*7^*((6^{\wedge}5 - 4)^*3 - 2)+1)$	12814425	$9^*((((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4 - 3)/2 - 1)$
11751237	$-9^*((8^*7^*(6^{\wedge}5 - 4))^* - 3+2)+1)$	12814433	$9^*((((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4 - 3)/2 - 1)$
11751291	$9^*((8^*7^*(6^{\wedge}5 - 4))^*3+2)+1)$	12814435	$9^*((((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4 - 3)/2+1)$
11763333	$9^*((8^*7^*(6^{\wedge}5+4))^*3 - 2) - 1)$	12814445	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4 - 3)/2 - 1)$
11763387	$9^*((8^*7^*(6^{\wedge}5+4))^*3+2)+1)$	12814446	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4 - 3)/2^*1$
11763864	$9^*8^*7^*((6^{\wedge}5+4))^*3+2) - 1)$	12814447	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4 - 3)/2+1$
11790164	$(-9 - (8/7)^{\wedge} - 6^*5)^* - 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	12814448	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4+3)/2 - 1)$
11796113	$((9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4))/3^*21$	12814449	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4+3)^*2^{\wedge} - 1)$
11852892	$(9 - 8^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)))^*(3 - 21)$	12814470	$-9^*((((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)/ - 4 - 3)/2 - 1)$
11852991	$9^*((87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) - 3)^*2 - 1)$	13017854	$(9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)^* - 4)/ (3+2^{\wedge} - 1)$
11852999	$9^*(87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) - 3)^*2 - 1)$	13030686	$9^*87^*((65+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
11853001	$9^*(- 87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4))+3)^* - 2+1)$	13123584	$-9^*(-8 - (76+5))/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2 - 1)$
11853009	$9^*((87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) - 3)^*2+1)$	13189120	$(9^*(-8 - 7)^*6+5)^* - 4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$
11853099	$9^*((87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) + 3)^*2 - 1)$	13245180	$(-9 - 8^{\wedge}7*6)/ ((5^*4)^{\wedge}(-3+2) - 1)$
11853117	$9^*((87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) + 3)^*2+1)$	13311675	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (7^*6)^{\wedge}(5 - 4+3))/ (2+1)$
11853216	$(-9 - 87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)))^*(3 - 21)$	13352960	$(9^*(-8 - 7)^* - 6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$
11874924	$(-9+8)^*7^*6^*((-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2+1)$	13436896	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5) - 4^{\wedge}3)^*2^{\wedge} - 1)$
11875143	$(9^*8 - 76^* - 5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2 - 1)$	13436960	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4^{\wedge}3)^*2^{\wedge} - 1)$
11875145	$(9^*8 - 76^* - 5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2+1)$	13593741	$-9+87^*6/ (5^{\wedge}(-4 - 3))^* (2+1))$
11960320	$(-9 - 8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^* - 5/4^{\wedge}(3^*(-2 - 1))$	13593759	$9+87^*6/ (5^{\wedge}(-4 - 3))^* (2+1))$
11970815	$9^*(- 8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/ (3^*2) - 1)$	13828491	$-9 - (87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4) - 3)^* - 21$
11970817	$9^*(- 8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/ (3^*2)+1)$	13828509	$9 - (87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4) - 3)^* - 21$
11992050	$987^*6^{\wedge}5^*((4/3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	13828617	$-9+(87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3)^*21$
12124160	$(9^*8+76)^*5^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$	13828635	$9+(87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3)^*21$
12127500	$98^*((-7 - 6)^{\wedge}5+43)/ (-2 - 1)$	13835519	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2 - 1)$
12176451	$-9^*((87/6^{\wedge} - 5 - 43))^* - 2 - 1)$	13835521	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2+1)$
12177981	$9^*((87/6^{\wedge} - 5 - 43))^* - 2 - 1)$	13883816	$(-9/(8+7^*(- 65^{\wedge}4+3)+2))^{\wedge} - 1)$
12187500	$(-9+87)^*6/ (5^{\wedge}(-4 - 3))^*(2+1))$	13883820	$(9/(8+7^*65^{\wedge}4 - 3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
12277587	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)^*(4+3)^*21$	13919400	$(9 - 8/7)^*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4^*3/2) - 1)$
12333060	$9/8^*((7^*(-6 - 5)^*43)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	13994613	$(9^*(8 - 7))^{\wedge}6^*(5 - 4^{\wedge}3/(-2 - 1))$
12342723	$(9^*8+7)^*((-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2 - 1)$	14062507	$(9 - 8)^*7+(6^*5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3 - (2 - 1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
14094216	$9*8*(7^6+5^4(4+3)-21)$	16270287	$(9*8+7)^{(-6-(-5-4))}*(32+1)$
14097240	$9*8*(7^6-(-5^4(4+3)-21))$	16335883	$(-9+(8/((7*6)^5-4^4(3*2))))^{(-1)}$
14212800	$987/(6*5^4)^{(-3+2)-1}$	16335901	$9-(8/((-7*6)^5+4^4(3*2)))^{(-1)}$
14218750	$(98-7)*6/(5^{(-4-3)}*(2+1))$	16354755	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}-21)$
14238229	$(-9-((8+7)^6-5)/-4)^*(3+2)-1$	16354917	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}-2-1)$
14238230	$(-9-((8+7)^6-5)/-4)^*(3+2)^1$	16354923	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}-21)$
14238231	$(-9-((8+7)^6-5)/-4)^*(3+2)+1$	16354925	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}-2)-1$
14238268	$((9-(8+7)^6)*-5/4-3)+2-1$	16354926	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}-2)^1$
14238319	$(9+((8+7)^6-5)/4)^*(3+2)-1$	16354927	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}-2)+1$
14238320	$(9-((8+7)^6-5)/-4)^*(3+2)^1$	16354941	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}-2-1)$
14238321	$(9+((8+7)^6-5)/4)^*(3+2)+1$	16354942	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}-2)^1$
14294070	$9/8*((76-5)^4-3)/2+1$	16354946	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}+2)^1$
14344810	$9^{((8+7)/6+5)}-4^{(3*2)}-1$	16354947	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}+2)+1$
14344812	$9^{(8+7)/6+5}-4^{(3*2)}+1$	16354961	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}-2)-1$
14348319	$(9^8-7*6)^{(-5+4+3)}/(2+1)$	16354962	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}-2)^1$
14348957	$9^{((8+7)/6+5)}+(-4-3)^2+1$	16354963	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}-2)+1$
14349495	$(9^8+7*6)^{(-5+4+3)}/(2+1)$	16354965	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}+2)$
14353002	$9^{(8+7)/6+5}+4^{(3*2)}-1$	16354971	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}-2-1)$
14353004	$9^{((8+7)/6+5)}+4^{(3*2)}+1$	16355133	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)}+2)$
14361212	$(9+8)^{(-7+6)}*5^{(4*3)}-21$	16425654	$987*((65+4^3)^2+1)$
14393925	$(9/8+7)^*(6+5)^{(4*3/2)}-1$	16426799	$-9+(8^{(-7-(-6-5))}-43)^2-1$
14401536	$9*8^7/6*(5+(-4/3)^{(-2-1)})$	16426800	$-9+(-8^{(-7+6+5)}+43)^2+1$
14407956	$9^{((-8+7)+6)}*(5*(4+3)^2-1)$	16426801	$-9+(8^{(-7-(-6-5))}-43)^2+1$
14669815	$-9+8^7*(6-5*4^{(-3-2)}+1)$	16426818	$9+(-8^{(-7+6+5)}+43)^2+1$
14669833	$9+8^7*(6-5*4^{(-3-2)}+1)$	16426819	$9+(-8^{(-7-(-6-5))}+43)^2+1$
14690295	$-9+8^7*(6+5*4^{(-3-2)}+1)$	16564086	$(9-8)*7*6*((5^4+3)^2-1)$
14690313	$9+8^7*(6+5*4^{(-3-2)}+1)$	16564135	$(9-8)*7*(6*(5^4+3)^2+1)$
14711112	$(-9+87)^{(-6+5+4)}*(32-1)$	16614729	$9/8*((7*(6+543))^2-1)$
14711949	$(9*(87+6))^{(-5+4)+3}*21$	16661520	$(9+8^{(7+6-5)})/((4*3)^{-2+1})$
14753907	$9*(8*-7-6+5^4(4+3))*21$	16662528	$(-987-6*5)/-4^{(-3*2-1)}$
14754600	$9*8*7*((6+5)^4-3)^2-1$	16681123	$(9*8+76^{(5-4)+3})/2-1$
14760648	$9*8*-7*((6+5)^4+3)^*-2+1$	16681125	$(9*8+76^{(5-4)+3})/2+1$
14763861	$9*(8*7/-6+5^4(4+3))*21$	16736265	$(9-8^{(-7+6+5)})*(-4^{(3*2)}+1)$
14767389	$9*(8*7/-6-5^4(4+3))*-21$	16776544	$(-9+8^7/6-5)*((4+3)^2-1)$
14777343	$9*(8*-7-6-5^4(4+3))*-21$	16777888	$(9+8^7/6+5)*((4+3)^2-1)$
15046632	$9*((((8-7)^6+5)^4-3)^2-1)$	16796155	$(9/((8+7)*(6^4(5+4)-3)))^{(-2+1)}$
15058423	$-9-(8/(-7^6+5)^4)^{(-3-2)}-1$	16796165	$(9/((8+7)*(6^4(5+4)+3)))^{(-2+1)}$
15058441	$9-(8/(-7^6+5)^4)^{(-3-2)}-1$	16809991	$-9+(8^{((-7+6)+5)+4})^{(3-2+1)}$
15059703	$-9+(8/(7^6+5)^4)^{(-3-2)}-1$	16810009	$9+(8^{((-7+6)+5)+4})^{(3-2+1)}$
15059721	$9+(8/(7^6+5)^4)^{(-3-2)}-1$	16823807	$(9-8)*7^6*((5+4+3)^2-1)$
15116904	$9*8*((7-(-6-5))^4+3)^2-1$	16851590	$((9+8)*7)^{(-6-(-5-4))}*(3^2+1)$
15146093	$(9/(8^7*65-43))^{(-2+1)}$	16872192	$9*-8*(-7-6-5^4(4+3))*(-2-1)$
15146097	$(9/(8^7*65-4-3))^{(-2+1)}$	16874784	$9*8*(-7+6+5^4(4+3))*2+1$
15284209	$(9*8+7)^{(-6-(-5-4))}*(32-1)$	16875216	$9*-8*(-7+6-5^4(4+3))*2+1$
15311814	$-98*(7-6/(5^{(-4-3)}*(2+1)))$	16877808	$9*8*(-7-(6+5^4(4+3)))*(-2-1)$
15313186	$98*(7+6/5^{(-4-3)}*(2+1))$	16930314	$9*(8^7-6+5^4*3)^{(2+1)}$
15375168	$9*(8^7-6^5*(4+3)^2+1)$	16930422	$9*(8^7+6-5^4*3)^{(2+1)}$
15377283	$(9-(8+7)^6/5)/4*-3^{(2+1)}$	16987320	$9*((8^7-6)+54)/(3^{(-2+1)})$
15386139	$(9^8+7*6)^{(5-4+3)}/(2+1)$	17006583	$-9+8^7*(6+5*(4/3)^{(-2-1)})$
15496821	$(9^8-7-(-6-5))/((4/3)^2+1)$	17006601	$9+8^7*(6+5*(4/3)^{(-2-1)})$
15659942	$(9/(87*((6*5)^4-3)^2))^{(-1)}$	17009790	$((9-8)*(-7+(6*5)^4)-3)^2+1$
15713280	$9*-8^7/6*5*(4^{(-3-2)}-1)$	17009853	$(9+8-7-((6*5)^4+3))*-21$
15725559	$9*(8^7/6*(5-4^{(-3-2)}-1)$	17055744	$9*8^7/6*(5-(-4/3)^{(-2-1)})$
15725577	$9*(8^7/6*(5-4^{(-3-2)}+1)$	17124210	$9^{((-8+7)+6)*((5+4*3)^2+1)}$
15731703	$9*(8^7/6*(5+4^{(-3-2)}-1)$	17131311	$-9+(8^{(-7-(-6-5))}+43)^2-1$
15731721	$9*(8^7/6*(5+4^{(-3-2)}+1)$	17131312	$-9+(8^{(-7+6+5)}+43)^2+1$
15744000	$9*-8^7/6*5*(-4^{(-3-2)}-1)$	17131313	$-9+(8^{(-7-(-6-5))}+43)^2+1$
15803856	$(-9+87^{(-6-(-5-4))}*(3+21)$	17131329	$9+(8^{(-7-(-6-5))}+43)^2-1$
15804288	$(9+87^{(-6-(-5-4))}*(3+21)$	17131330	$9+(8^{(-7+6+5)}+43)^2+1$
15825054	$((98-7)^{(-6-(-5-4))}+3)^2+1$	17131331	$9+(8^{(-7-(-6-5))}+43)^2+1$
15896340	$9/8*((7*(6-543))^2-1)$	17158590	$(9+8^7)*6*5/(4-3^{(-2+1)})$
15917503	$-9+8-7*((6*(-5^4+3))^2-1)$	17294187	$(9*8-7^4((6-5)+4+3))*(-2-1)$
15917521	$9+8/7*((6*(-5^4+3))^2-1)$	17294214	$(9-(8-(7-6)^5)^{(4+3))}*-21$
15936064	$((-987-(6+5))^4)^{(3-2)+1}$	17294340	$((-9+8)*-7^4(6+5-4)-3)^2+1$
15974391	$-9+(-8-7)*-65/4^{(-3*2-1)}$	17294466	$((9-8)*7^4(6+5-4)+3)^2+1$
15974409	$9+(-8-7)*-65/4^{(-3*2-1)}$	17294592	$(9+(8-(7-6)^5)^{(4+3))}*(2+1)$
16016130	$(9+8-7)*(6*5^4-3)^{(2+1)}$	17294619	$(9*8+7^4((6-5)+4+3))*2+1$
16097143	$-9+8/7*((6*5^4+3)^2-1)$	17321936	$(9/8/(7+(6+5)^{(4+3))))^{(-2+1)}$
16097161	$9+8/7*((6*5^4+3)^2-1)$	17405584	$(9*8*(7-65)+4)^{(3-2)+1}$
16142517	$9/8*((76+5)^4/3-2-1)$	17472400	$(9*8*(7-65)-4)^{(3-2)+1}$
16142544	$9/8*((76+5)^4/3+2)$	17473956	$((9-8)*7*6^5+4)*321$
16249135	$(9-8)*7*(6*(-5^4+3)^2+1)$	17480761	$(9*(-87-6)*5+4)^{(3-2+1)}$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
17554287	$9^*((8+7+65)^4+3)/21$	19034362	$9^*8^7-(6-(5^*4)^(3+2-1))$
17593337	$(9^*8^7-(6^(5+4)+3))^*2-1$	19034374	$9^*8^7+6+(5^*4)^(3+2-1)$
17593339	$(9^*8^7-(6^(5+4)+3))^*2+1$	19136147	$((-9^*8-7)+6)^*(5-4^(3*(2+1)))$
17614647	$9^*(8^7-6^(-5+4^3))/2-1$	19136877	$((9^*8+7)-6)^*(5+4^(3*(2+1)))$
17614665	$9^*(8^7-(6^(-5+4^3))/2-1))$	19196142	$-9^*(8^7-6^5)/((4+3)^(2-1))$
17676288	$9^*-8^7*(65^4^(-3-2)-1)$	19199984	$-9-(8-7-6*((5^*4)^(3+2)-1))$
17730946	$(-98+76^5)/((4^*3)^(2-1))$	19199988	$9-(8+7-6*((5^*4)^(3+2)-1))$
17779338	$(-9+87^(-6+5+4))^*3^(2+1)$	19199996	$-9-(8-(7-6*((5^*4)^(3+2)-1)))$
17779392	$9^*(87^(-6+5+4))^*3-21$	19200004	$9+8-(7-6*((5^*4)^(3+2)-1))$
17779500	$9^*(87^(-6-(-5-4))-3)^*(2+1)$	19200012	$-9+8+7-6*((5^*4)^(3+2)-1)$
17779554	$9^*(87^(-6-(-5-4)))^*3-2-1$	19200016	$9+8-7-6*((5^*4)^(3+2)-1)$
17779562	$9^*(87^(-6-(-5-4)))^*3-2-1$	19200018	$9+8+7+6*((5^*4)^(3+2)-1)$
17779564	$9^*(87^(-6-(-5-4)))^*3-2+1$	19263168	$9^*8^7+6^5*((4+3)^(2+1))$
17779598	$9^*(87^(-6-(-5-4)))^*3+2-1$	19267554	$9^*8^7-6^*(5-4^(3^2-1))$
17779600	$9^*(87^(-6-(-5-4)))^*3+2+1$	19267614	$9^*8^7+6^*(5+4^(3^2-1))$
17779608	$9^*(87^(-6-(-5-4)))^*3+2+1$	19339026	$-9^*(8^7+6^5)/((4+3)^(2-1))$
17779662	$9^*(87^(-6-(-5-4)))^*3)^*(2+1)$	19403334	$9/8^*(7-65^4)^3^(2-1)$
17779770	$9^*(87^(-6+5+4))^*3+21$	19405800	$9^*(8^7-(6/54)^(3-2)-1)$
17779824	$(9+87^(-6+5+4))^*3^(2+1)$	19405818	$-9^*(-8^7-(6/54)^(3-2)-1)$
17968680	$(9+8/7)^*((6+5)^(4^3/2)-1)$	19440007	$(9-8)^*7+(6^5)^4*(3+21)$
17999496	$((9+8)^*(-7^6+5)+4)/-3^2-2^*1$	19440303	$-9^*(8^*((-7-(6^5)^4)/3-2)+1)$
18003041	$98^*7/6*((54^3-2)-1)$	19472343	$9^*((-8+7^6)^5+43)/21$
18003727	$98^*7/6*((54^3+2)+1)$	19487199	$(9-8)^*7+(6+5)^(4+3)+21$
18104320	$(-9-8)^*(-7-6)^*5/4^(-3^2-1)$	19526777	$(9^*((8+7)^6-5)^4-3)/21$
18238770	$(9+8/-7)^*6*((-5^4+3)^(2-1))$	19529728	$9^*8^7*(6+5*((4^3)^(2-1)))$
18240000	$(9^*8+7^6)^*(5^4)^(3+2-1)$	19534374	$9/8^*((-7-65^4)^3)^(2-1)$
18262271	$9^*(-8^7-6^5(5+4))/(-3^2)-1$	19591787	$((9/8)^7*6+5)^4*(3^2+1)$
18262273	$9^*(-8^7-6^5(5+4))/(-3^2)+1$	19834020	$((9-8)^*-7+65^4)^*(3^2-2+1)$
18305189	$9^*(-8+7+6)^*5*(4^3-2)-1$	19933396	$(-9+((8+7)^6-5)/(4^3))^*21$
18305191	$9^*(8+7+6)^*5*(4^3-2)+1$	19933522	$(-9-((8+7)^6-5)/-4)/3^*21$
18310545	$(9/8^*7-6)^*(5^4(4+3^2)-1)$	19933594	$9-((8+7)^6-5)/(-4^3)^*21$
18321408	$9^*8^7*(6^5-4^(-3-2)+1)$	19933648	$(9+((8+7)^6-5)/4)/3^*21$
18342918	$9^*(8^7+(-6/54)^(3-2)-1)$	19933774	$(9+((8+7)^6-5)/(4^3))^*21$
18342936	$-9^*(8^7+(6/54)^(3-2)-1)$	20072448	$9^*-8^7*(-65^4)^(3-2)-1$
18448524	$9^*(-8+((76+5)^4+3)/21)$	20089215	$-9^*(8/7^*(6-5^4(4+3+2))+1)$
18448668	$9^*(8-((76+5)^4+3)/-21)$	20089233	$9^*(-8/7^*(6-5^4(4+3+2))+1)$
18481122	$9^*8^7-6^*(5+4^(3^2-1))$	20102652	$(-9+8^7)/654^(-3+2-1)$
18481182	$9^*8^7+6^*(5-4^(3^2-1))$	20132688	$(9+8^7-6)/5^*(4+3)^(2-1)$
18485568	$9^*8^7-6^5*((-4-3)^(2+1))$	20134071	$9^*(8^7+6^(-5+4^3))/2-1$
18521314	$98^*7*((6^5)^(4-3)+2)-1$	20134089	$9^*(8^7-(6^(-5+4^3))/2-1))$
18522686	$98^*7*((6^5)^(4-3)+2)+1$	20259632	$(-9/8+7)^*((-6+5^4)^3)^(2-1)$
18541386	$98^*((-8+7)+6)^*(5^4+3)/2^*1$	20413314	$(-9+87^(-6-(-5-4)))^*(32-1)$
18579393	$((9+87)^(6-(-5-4))-3)^*21$	20413584	$-9+87^(-6-(-5-4))^*(32-1)$
18579519	$((9+87)^(6-(-5-4))+3)^*21$	20413602	$9+87^(-6-(-5-4))^*(32-1)$
18608670	$(9+8-7)^*(6^5*4+3)^(2+1)$	20413872	$(9+87^(-6-(-5-4)))^*(32-1)$
18714362	$(9^*(8^7-7-6)-(5^4)^(3+2-1))$	20475319	$(9^*-8-7-65)^(4+3)/21$
18714374	$9^*8^7+6-(5^4)^(3+2-1)$	20528733	$(9/(8^*-7)+6)^*((5^4*3)^(2-1))$
18718118	$9^*8^7+6/(-5^(-4-3))^*(2+1))$	20571768	$(-9-8)^*(7^6)^5/-4^3^(2-1)$
18733260	$(-9/8+7)^*6*((5+4)^(3^2)-1)$	20578304	$(9/8^*(7+6)+5)^4*(3^2+1)$
18782208	$9^*8^7*(6-5*(4^(-3-2)+1))$	20591512	$((-9+8)/7+6)^*((5^4*3)^(2-1))$
18802926	$9^*(8^7+6^5)/((4+3)^(2-1))$	20703124	$(-9^(-8+7)+6)^*(5^4*3)^(2-1)$
18808164	$9^*(8^7-6^*((5^*(4+3))^2+1))$	20703126	$(-9^(-8+7)+6)^*(5^4*3)^(2+1)$
18815318	$9^*8^7-(6/54)^(3-2)-1$	20719152	$(9^*876)^(5+4+3)/2+1$
18815320	$9^*8^7-(6/54)^(3-2)+1$	20818314	$9^*(8^7-6-(5^*4^*-3)^(2+1))$
18835218	$9^*(8^7+6^*-5*((4^3)^(2+1)))$	20818422	$9^*(8^7+6+(5^*4^3)^(2+1))$
18845748	$9^*(8^7-6^*((5^*4+3)^(2+1)))$	21052757	$(-9/8+7)^*((-6-5^4)^3)^(2-1)$
18862368	$9^*(8^7-6^*(5^4)^(3-2)^(2+1))$	21053340	$98^*-7^*6^*5^*(4^(-3+2)+1)$
18867012	$9^*8^7-6^*((5^*(4+3))^2+1)$	21080493	$9^*((-8+7)+6)^*(5+4^3)^*21$
18871914	$9^*(8^7-6^*((5^*4/3)^(2+1)))$	21086208	$((-9-8)^*76+5)/-4^(-3^2-1)$
18873440	$-9^*(-8^7+65)-(4+3)^(2+1)$	21093753	$9/(8-7)+6*((5^4*3)^(2-1))$
18875296	$9^*(8^7+65)+(4+3)^(2+1)$	21094500	$98^*7^*6^*5^*(4^3+2)+1$
18876822	$9^*(8^7+6^*((5^*4/3)^(2+1)))$	21094721	$9^*8-7^*(6^5*4/3)^(2+1)$
18881724	$9^*8^7+6^*((5^*(4+3))^2+1)$	21127554	$9/(8^*(7+6))^*((5^4(4^3)-2)+1)$
18886368	$9^*(8^7+6^*(5^4)^(3-2)^(2+1))$	21139776	$98^*7^*6^5*(4-3)^(2-1)$
18902988	$9^*(8^7+6^*((5^*4+3)^(2+1)))$	21140217	$9^*87^*((6^5)^(4-3)+2)-1$
18913518	$9^*(8^7+6^*5^*((4^3)^(2+1)))$	21141783	$9^*87^*((6^5)^(4-3)+2)+1$
18920475	$9/8^*((-76^5+3)^(2-1))$	21233178	$9^*((8^7+6)-54)/(-3^2-2+1)$
18933416	$9^*8^7+(6/54)^(3-2)-1$	21234150	$9^*((8^7-6)+54)/(-3^2-2+1)$
18933418	$9^*8^7+(6/54)^(3-2)+1$	21250048	$((-9-8)^*-76+5)/4^(-3^2-1)$
18940572	$9^*(8^7+6^*((5^*(4+3))^2+1))$	21393603	$9^*(8^7+6^(-5+4^3)-21)$
18945810	$9^*(8^7-6^5)/((4+3)^(2-1))$	21393765	$9^*(8^7+6^(-5+4^3)-2-1)$
19030618	$9^*8^7+6/(5^(-4-3))^*(2+1))$	21393771	$9^*(8^7+6^(-5+4^3)-2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
21393773	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2)-1$	23626512	$9/(87+6)^*((5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)+1)$
21393774	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2)^{\wedge}1$	23794650	$9/8^*((7^*(654+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
21393775	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2)+1$	23817657	$(9/((8^*7+65)^{\wedge}4+32))^{\wedge}-1$
21393789	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))-2-1$	23876208	$9^*8/7^*(6^*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
21393790	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))-2^{\wedge}1$	23876280	$9^*8/7^*(6/(-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
21393794	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))+2^{\wedge}1$	23913215	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)^*2)-1$
21393795	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))+2+1$	23913217	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)^*2)+1$
21393809	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2))-1$	23953399	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6+5+(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
21393810	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)+2^{\wedge}1)$	23953417	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6+5+(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
21393811	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2))+1$	24030270	$9^*-87*6^*5*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
21393813	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))+21$	24071190	$(-9+8-7^{\wedge}6)/5^*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
21393819	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2-1))$	24077250	$9^*87*6^*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
21393981	$-9^*(-8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-21)$	24107127	$-9+8/7^*6^*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
21534912	$98^*7^*6^{\wedge}5*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	24107145	$9+8/7^*6^*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
21595976	$((-9+8)/-7+6)^*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	24128928	$9^*87*6^{\wedge}5*(4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
21658755	$(9/(8^*7)+6)^*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	24139150	$(9-8)^*7^*(((-6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
21730302	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*(32+1)$	24186474	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4)/(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$
21730590	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*(32+1)$	24213780	$9/8^*((76+5)^{\wedge}4*3)/2+1)$
21730608	$9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))^*(32+1)$	24257450	$98^*(((-7-6)^{\wedge}5+4)/-3^*2-1)$
21730896	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*(32+1)$	24257646	$-98^*(((-7-6)^{\wedge}5+4)/3^*2-1)$
21772791	$-9+8^*7^*6^{\wedge}5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	24310062	$((98+7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3)^*21$
21772809	$9+8^*7^*6^{\wedge}5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	24310188	$((98+7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3)^*21$
21864991	$-9+8/7^*((6/(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	24504534	$9^*(-8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
21865009	$9+8/7^*((6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	24504678	$9^*(8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
21869986	$-98/7+(6^*5)^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	24579936	$9^*87*6^{\wedge}5*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
21870014	$98/7+(6^*5)^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	24609410	$(9-8)^*-7^*(-6-((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
21939856	$(9^*8*(7+6)^*5+4)^{\wedge}(3-(-2-1))$	24990868	$(-9+8)^*7^*(65^{\wedge}4/(-3-2)+1)$
22071183	$(9^*87^*6)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))-21$	25053600	$(9-8/7)^*6^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
22071201	$(9^*87^*6)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))-2-1$	25084136	$(9-8)^*7^*(((-6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
22071202	$(9^*87^*6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)-2^{\wedge}1$	25084150	$(9-8)^*7^*(((-6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
22071206	$(9^*87^*6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)+2^{\wedge}1$	25109783	$((-9+8)^*-7-(6^*5)^{\wedge}4)^*(-32+1)$
22071207	$((9^*87^*6)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))+2)+1$	25110007	$(9-8)^*7+(6^*5)^{\wedge}4*(32-1)$
22071225	$(9^*87^*6)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))+21$	25110540	$9/8^*7^*6^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
22114942	$(9^*8+7)/6^{\wedge}(5-4^*3)-2^{\wedge}1$	25165582	$((-9+8^{\wedge}7)-6-5)^*4^*3-2^*1$
22114946	$(9^*8+7)/6^{\wedge}(5-4^*3)+2^{\wedge}1$	25165586	$((-9+8^{\wedge}7)-6-5)^*4^*3+2^{\wedge}1$
22133945	$(-9/8+7)^*((6^{\wedge}5/4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	25166062	$((9+8^{\wedge}7)+6+5)^*4^*3-2^*1$
22155840	$9^*((((87^*6+5)-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	25166066	$((9+8^{\wedge}7)+6+5)^*4^*3+2^{\wedge}1$
22155858	$9^*((((87^*6+5)-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	25192525	$(98^*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3/-2-1)$
22183927	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6+5-(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	25195955	$(98^*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3/2+1)$
22183945	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6+5-(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	25345728	$9^*8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*(-2-1)$
22207779	$9/8^*((7/(-6^{\wedge}5*4+3))^{\wedge}-2-1)$	25508232	$9^*-8*(7-6*(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
22270997	$(-9/8+7)^*((6^{\wedge}5/4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	25510104	$9^*8*(7-6*((-5-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
22320529	$(9-8)^*7*(6*(5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$	25628328	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3^*21)$
22320564	$(9-8)^*7*(6*(5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$	25628598	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-32-1)$
22373568	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1))$	25628616	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-32+1)$
22587648	$((98/7)^{\wedge}6-5/4^{\wedge}-3)^*(2+1)$	25628652	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
22588158	$(9/(8*((76-5)^{\wedge}4-3)-2))^{\wedge}-1$	25628679	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3-21)$
22589568	$((98/7)^{\wedge}6-5/-4^{\wedge}-3)^*(2+1)$	25628733	$-9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4-(3-21))$
22667085	$-9+(8-7*(6+5))^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	25628805	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
22667157	$9+(8-7*(6+5))^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	25628823	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
22671360	$9^*-8^{\wedge}7*6/5*(-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$	25628832	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3^*21)$
22857141	$-9+(8/7+6)^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	25628840	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3^*2)-1$
22857159	$9+(8/7+6)^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	25628841	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3-2-1)$
22918350	$(9/8+7^*6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$	25628847	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3)-21$
23046135	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$	25628859	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3-2+1)$
23046153	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$	25628868	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
23058423	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6-5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1))$	25628877	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3-21$
23058441	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6-5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1))$	25628888	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3^*2-1$
23063158	$((9+8)/((7^*6)^{\wedge}5-4)^*3+2))^{\wedge}-1$	25628892	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3^*(2-1)$
23078903	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$	25628948	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3^*2)-1$
23078921	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$	25628950	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3^*2)+1$
23091191	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$	25628958	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3^*21$
23091209	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$	25628967	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$
23246208	$9^*8^{\wedge}7*(6+(-5/4)^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$	25628985	$-9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4-(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
23255841	$(9-(-8-7)^{\wedge}6)/((5/(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	25629057	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3+21)$
23362029	$9/8^*((7*(654-3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	25629111	$-9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4-(3+21))$
23436996	$-9^*8*(7+(-6/5^{\wedge}(4-(-3-2))))^{\wedge}-1)$	25629138	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
23438004	$9^*8*(7-(-6/5^{\wedge}(4-(-3-2))))^{\wedge}-1)$	25629174	$-9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4-(32-1))$
23460192	$(-9+8)^*-7^*6^{\wedge}5*(432-1)$	25629192	$-9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4-(32+1))$
23544594	$(9-8^{\wedge}7)^*6*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	25629462	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3^*21)$
23546952	$9/8^*((-7^*654+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	25701231	$9^*((87+6-5)^{\wedge}4+3)/21$
23608755	$9/8^*((7^*654+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	25716159	$(9^*8+7)/6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3+2)+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
25728635	$(9/((-8^7*6+5^4(4^3))+2))^{\wedge-1}$	28237671	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
25804807	$(9-8)^{*7}*((6*5^4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	28237689	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
25825280	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	28239840	$(9-(-8-7^{\wedge}6))^*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
25907700	$(9/8+7)^*6*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$	28253040	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6)*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
26091664	$(9*8*(76-5)-4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$	28349993	$(-9+8)^*7*((6*5)^{\wedge}4*(-3-2)+1)$
26157924	$9/(8+76)*((5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)+1)$	28520667	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*5*(4+3)^*21$
26327161	$((9*8+7)^*-65+4)^{\wedge}(3-(2-1))$	28678131	$(9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6*(54-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
26372360	$(9-8)^*7*((-6^{\wedge}5/4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	28717497	$(9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
26476157	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*(-4+321)$	28799055	$-9*(8*(7+6)+(5*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
26535656	$(9-8)^*7*((6^{\wedge}5/4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	28799073	$9*(-8*(7+6)+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
26578062	$((-9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3)^*-21$	28799907	$9*(8*-7/6-(5*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
26578188	$((9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3)^*21$	28799925	$-9*(8*7/6-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
26585979	$(9/(8^{\wedge}7-(6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	28800075	$9*(8*7/6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
26611712	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$	28800093	$-9*(8*-7/6-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
26729769	$((-9+8)^*-7-(6*5)^{\wedge}4)^*(-32-1)$	28800927	$-9*(-8*(7+6)-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
26730007	$(9-8)^*7+(6*5)^{\wedge}4*(32+1)$	28800945	$9*(8*(7+6)-(5*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
26794131	$98*7*((-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2-1)$	28815435	$9/8*((7*(6+(-5-4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
26794349	26794349	28854896	$(-9/(8-(7+6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
26795503	$98*7*((-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$	28874961	$(9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
26798247	$98*7*((6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2-1)$	29020055	$((9*8+7)-6)^*5*43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
26799619	$98*7*((6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$	29115515	$(9/8+7)*(((-6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
26808320	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	29179069	$(-9+8*(7*6*5))^*43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
26808957	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-4)^*321$	29196288	$(9+87)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)^*(32+1)$
26811525	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+4)^*321$	29347353	$(9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^*54^{\wedge}-3*21$
26869759	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1$	29403108	$(9-8)^*76*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
26869761	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1$	29600550	$9*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5)*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
26872007	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-43^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$	29622847	$-9-8/7*((6*5)^{\wedge}4*-32+1)$
26872128	$(9*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+(-4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	29622865	$9-8/7*((6*5)^{\wedge}4*-32+1)$
26872831	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$	29631688	$((-9-8)/(-7+6))*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
26872833	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$	29632626	$9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))*((3+2)-1))$
26873513	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$	29632644	$9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))*((3+2)+1))$
26873604	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4*-3*21$	29751042	$(9/((-8-7)^*-65^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
26873709	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+(-4-3)^*21$	29757168	$9*-8*7*(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
26873819	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4*3^{\wedge}2-1$	29758176	$-9*8*7*((6-(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2))-1)$
26874003	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-(-4-3)^*21$	29760654	$(-9+8)^*7*(6+(-54*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
26874108	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4*3*21$	29763216	$9*8*7*((6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2))-1)$
26874199	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+(4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	29764224	$9*8*7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
26874879	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$	29779902	$9/8*((7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
26874881	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$	29942782	$(9*8*76)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)-2/1$
26875584	$(9*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-(-4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	29942786	$(9*8*76)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+2/1$
26875705	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+43^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$	29973108	$(9-8)^*76*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
26939392	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	30051684	$-9*(8-7*6*((-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))))$
26946115	$(9-8)^*7*((654*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	30051828	$9*(8+7*6*((-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))))$
26953363	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+43^{\wedge}(2+1)$	30055464	$9*(8-7*6*((-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1))))$
27043713	$9^{\wedge}8-(7*6^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	30055608	$9*(8-7*6*((-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1))))$
27126734	$(9/(-8-7-((6-5^{\wedge}4(4^3))-2)))^{\wedge-1}$	30093335	$(-9/(8+(7-654)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
27126743	$(-9/(-8*7-(6+5^{\wedge}4(4^3))))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	30174039	$(9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))/54^{\wedge}-3*21$
27136000	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$	30232941	$-9*(8*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3+21$
27144325	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*4+321$	30233235	$9*(8*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3-21$
27156528	$-9/8*-7*(((-6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	30387654	$(9-((8+7)+6)*5^{\wedge}4)/(-3-2+1)$
27231313	$(9/(8*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4^3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	30610775	$(9/8+7)*((6^{\wedge}5/4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
27257152	$(-9/(8-(7-(6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	30800315	$(9/8+7)*((6^{\wedge}5/4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
27261689	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7/(6+5))^*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	30965688	$-9*(8-7*6*5/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$
27264263	$(9+8^{\wedge}7/(6+5))^*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	30965832	$9*(8-7*6*5/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$
27426816	$(9+87)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)^*(32-1)$	31078727	$(9*876)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))/2-1$
27428571	$9/(8+7+6)*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	31078729	$(9*876)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))/2+1$
27549904	$(9^{\wedge}8-7-(-6-5))/((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	31201163	$(9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
27922432	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	31829593	$(9-8)^*7*(7+6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
27966848	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6*(5/(4+3)+2+1)$	31842713	$(-9+8)^*7+6^{\wedge}5*(4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
27989280	$9*-8*76*5*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	31842727	$(9-8)^*7+6^{\wedge}5*(4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
28018640	$(9/8+7)*(((-6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	31858279	$(-9+8)^*-7+6^{\wedge}5*(4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$
28044000	$9*8*76*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	31871385	$(9-8)^*7*(7+6+5)*(-4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$
28119528	$9*-8*(76-5^{\wedge}4(-(-3-2)+1))$	32080069	$(9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
28130472	$9*8*(76+5^{\wedge}4(-(-3-2)+1))$	32089421	$(9/(8+(7+654)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
28148527	$(9/(8^{\wedge}7+(6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	32260527	$9/8*((765*(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
28218480	$(-9*8+7^{\wedge}6)*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	32341920	$(9+8/7)*6*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
28219653	$9/8*7*(((-6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	32355828	$((-9+8^{\wedge}7)-6)*54/(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
28231680	$(-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6))^*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	32762528	$9*8*-76+(5/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
28233831	$-9+(-8+7^{\wedge}6)*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	32763302	$9*8*7*-6+(5/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
28233849	$9+(-8+7^{\wedge}6)*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	32763884	$98*7*-6+(5/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
28235520	$(-9+8+7^{\wedge}6)*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	32767757	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5*4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
28236000	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6)*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	32768243	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5*4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
32772116	$98*7*6+(5/4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	36721296	$9*8/-7*(65^{\wedge}4/(-3-2)-1)$
32772698	$9*8*7*6+(5/4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	36728476	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(-5^{\wedge}4+3)-2/1$
32773472	$9*8*7*6+(5/4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	36728480	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(-5^{\wedge}4+3)+2/1$
32804990	$(-9-((-8-7)*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)/-2)-1$	36787527	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3+2-1)$
32804992	$(-9-((-8-7)*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)/-2)+1$	36853137	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$
32805008	$9+((-8-7)*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)/2-1$	36866259	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+(-3/2)^{\wedge}2-1)$
32914215	$-9*(8/7*(6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$	36899064	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}1$
32914233	$9*(8/7*(-6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$	36912186	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}1$
33185538	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3*21)$	36944991	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4-(-3/2)^{\wedge}2-1)$
33190857	$9*((-8-7)*6)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)-3)*21$	36951552	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7)/6^{\wedge}(-5-4)*(32+1)$
33191361	$(9/(8*7)^{\wedge}(6-5-4)-3)*21$	36964674	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3-2)^{\wedge}1$
33191487	$(9/(8*7)^{\wedge}(6-5-4)+3)*21$	36971235	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$
33191991	$9*((8*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3)*21$	37023723	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3-(-2-1))$
33480825	$(9-8)*7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$	37082770	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3-2/1)$
33513480	$9*-8*7*65*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	37082774	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2/1$
33579000	$9*8*7*65*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	37141821	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2-1)$
33716241	$-9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6*((5/(-4-3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	37167918	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))*21$
33716259	$9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6*((5/(-4-3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	37168212	$9^{\wedge}8+(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))*21$
33732729	$9*(-8-7+((-6-5)*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$	37188863	$(9*8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))*2-1$
33732855	$-9*(8-7-((-6-5)*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$	37188865	$(9*8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))*2+1$
33732873	$9*(8-7+((-6-5)*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$	37293148	$((-9+8)*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-321)$
33732999	$-9*(8-7-((-6-5)*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$	37355520	$(9*8+7*6)*5*4*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
33740424	$9*-8*(7-6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$	37376532	$9^{\wedge}8-7*((-6*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
33741432	$9*8*(7+6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$	37376910	$9^{\wedge}8-7*((-6*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
33747984	$9*-8*(7-(6*5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$	37496115	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$
33751008	$9*-8*(7-6*5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21)$	37507050	$9*(8+7+6)^{\wedge}5*((-4-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
33752016	$9*8*(7-(-6*5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$	37625728	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6*(5-(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
33758568	$9*8*(7-6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$	37669632	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6*(5+(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
33759576	$9*8*(7-6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$	37747224	$((-9+8^{\wedge}7/6)-5)*4*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
33824713	$(9+8)/7*((6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	37750248	$((9+8^{\wedge}7/6)+5)*4*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
34007850	$-9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	37768218	$((9-8)*7^{\wedge}6+5)+4)*321$
34176978	$9^{\wedge}8+(((7-6)*5-4)*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	37782663	$((9-8)*7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*321$
34335900	$9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	37850409	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5*4*-32-1)$
34344360	$9*-8*(7-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	37968507	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3+21)$
34345368	$9*8*(7+6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	37988685	$9/8*(((-7+6^{\wedge}5/4)*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
34348680	$9*8*(7-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	38122980	$-98*(7-(6*5+43)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
34349688	$9*8*(7-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	38124352	$98*(7+(6*5+43)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
34471157	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6*(5+(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	38161527	$-9+(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))*21$
34552071	$-9*(8/7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3+2)+1)$	38161545	$9+(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))*21$
34552089	$9*(8/7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3-2)+1)$	38237550	$((9-8)*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+321)$
34602117	$(9-8^{\wedge}7/6)*(5*4*(-3-2)+1)$	38274677	$((-9/(8-(76+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
34603899	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7/6)*(5*4*(-3-2)+1)$	38308607	$(9*8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))*2-1$
34712064	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)/6^{\wedge}(-5-4)*(32-1))$	38308609	$(9*8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))*2+1$
34722223	$(9/((8+7*6)^{\wedge}5+4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	38322801	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3+21)$
34722227	$(9/((8+7*6)^{\wedge}5+4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	38403904	$-9^{\wedge}8+(76*5/4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
34728741	$-9+(((8+7)+6)*5)^{\wedge}4/(3+2^{\wedge}2-1)$	38539809	$9/8*(((-7-6^{\wedge}5/4)*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
34728759	$9+(((8+7)+6)*5)^{\wedge}4/(3+2^{\wedge}2-1)$	39127610	$9^{\wedge}8-7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)*2+1)$
34877135	$-98+(7/(6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	39127624	$9^{\wedge}8-7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)*2-1)$
34877161	$-9*8+(7/(6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	39162563	$(98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2-1$
34877305	$9*8+(7/(6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	39162564	$(98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2*1$
34877331	$98+(7/(6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	39162565	$(98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2+1$
34907412	$9*((8+7)*6+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/21$	39361392	$9*8*7*(6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21)$
34996224	$(9*8*-7-6*5)*-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	39367440	$9*8*-7*(-6-(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$
35016057	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)/(5^{\wedge}4-32)^{\wedge}2-1$	39371787	$-9*(8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))+21)$
35156260	$(9+(8-7)^{\wedge}6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2+1$	39372165	$9*(8*7*(6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))+21)$
35269535	$(98*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(-3-2^{\wedge}2-1)$	39377835	$-9*(8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))+21)$
35274337	$(98*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(-3+2^{\wedge}2-1)$	39378213	$9*(8*-7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))+21)$
35309405	$9/8*((7^{\wedge}(-6-(5+4)*3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	39382560	$9*-8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21)$
35388936	$-9*8*(7-6*5*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$	39388608	$9*8*-7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21)$
35389944	$9*8*(7-6*5*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$	39513795	$(98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2-1$
35488449	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3-21)$	39513796	$(98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2*1$
35842743	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3-21)$	39513797	$(98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2+1$
35997551	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*(432-1)$	39529992	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}(6+5-4)/3*2-1)$
36152424	$9*8*-7*(6^{\wedge}5-43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	39530136	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}(6+5-4)/3*2+1)$
36164593	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*(432+1)$	39546810	$9/8*((7*(6+5))^{\wedge}4-321)$
36288007	$(9-8)*7-(6*5*-4)^{\wedge}3*21$	39743823	$((9-8)/7+6)/(5^{\wedge}(4*3)+2))^{\wedge}2-1$
36302857	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5/-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	39791570	$((-9/8+76)*(-5-4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
36492282	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3*2-1)$	40323987	$9^{\wedge}8-(7*6)^{\wedge}5/(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
36529936	$(9/(8-7*(6^{\wedge}5-4)))^{\wedge}(-3-(-2+1))$	40389440	$(9-8)*7*6*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
36572032	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6*(5-(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	40389592	$(9-8)*7*6*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$
36610380	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3-2)^{\wedge}1$	40444785	$((-9+8^{\wedge}7)-6)*5*(4-3/21)$
36626704	$(9/(8+7*(6^{\wedge}5+4)))^{\wedge}(-3-(-2+1))$	40497143	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5/4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$

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40497161	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5/4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	43048846	$9^{\wedge}8+765*((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
40690104	$(9-8)^{\wedge}7/6*((5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)+1)$	43049896	$9^{\wedge}8+7+6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
40768596	$-9^{\wedge}8*((7-(6/5+4))^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1$	43051164	$9^{\wedge}8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5*4-3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
40798630	$9^{\wedge}8+(7-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	43052174	$9^{\wedge}8+7*((65^{\wedge}4*3-2)+1)$
40801426	$(-9+8*((-7-6)*5)^{\wedge}4)/(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	43052188	$9^{\wedge}8+7*((65^{\wedge}4*3+2)-1)$
40824203	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6*(5-(-4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	43052540	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)-6)+(54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
40987310	$(9/8+76)*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	43052594	$9^{\wedge}8-7*(6*5*(4-32)+1)$
40996877	$9^{\wedge}8+((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$	43055744	$9^{\wedge}8+7*((6*5^{\wedge}43-2)+1)$
41087154	$9^{\wedge}8-(7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)+2)+1)$	43055758	$9^{\wedge}8+7*((6*5^{\wedge}43+2)-1)$
41087156	$(-9+8*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)+2)+1)$	43058864	$9^{\wedge}8-7+6^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
41087182	$9^{\wedge}8-(7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2)+1)$	43058878	$(9^{\wedge}8+7)+6^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
41087184	$9^{\wedge}8-7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2)+1$	43077171	$9^{\wedge}8+7*6*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
41143536	$9*8*7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	43101821	$9^{\wedge}8+76*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
41149080	$(-9*8+7/6^{\wedge}(5-4*3))^{\wedge}21$	43105762	$9^{\wedge}8-(7-(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1$
41152104	$(9*8-7/-6^{\wedge}(5-4*3))^{\wedge}21$	43105764	$9^{\wedge}8-7+(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1$
41360976	$9/8*((7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1)$	43105776	$9^{\wedge}8+7+(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1$
41485122	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^{\wedge}3*21$	43105778	$9^{\wedge}8+7+(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1$
41485500	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^{\wedge}3*21$	43131771	$9^{\wedge}8+7*6^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
41485689	$9*87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)*(3*2+1)$	43163215	$9^{\wedge}8+7*((65+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
41485878	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^{\wedge}3*21$	43168682	$9^{\wedge}8+7*((-6-5)^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
41486256	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^{\wedge}3*21$	43187345	$9^{\wedge}8+(7*6*(5-4)+3)^{\wedge}2+1$
41696712	$9*8/(765-4)^{\wedge}((-3+2)-1)$	43187347	$9^{\wedge}8+(7*6*(5+4))^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
41748035	$(9/-8+7+6)*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	43223121	$9^{\wedge}8-7*6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
42206892	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	43261551	$9^{\wedge}8-7*6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
42206934	$9^{\wedge}8+(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	43261971	$9^{\wedge}8-7*6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
42328944	$9*8*7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	43298721	$9^{\wedge}8-7/6*(5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
42378336	$9*8*7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	43388568	$((9*8*(7+6)+5)*(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1$
42456231	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(-5/(4*3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	43388569	$((9*8*(7+6)+5)*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1$
42473239	$9^{\wedge}8-7*(6-5/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$	43388570	$((9*8*(7+6)+5)*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1$
42473323	$9^{\wedge}8+7*(6-5/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$	43460057	$9^{\wedge}8+7*((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$
42486834	$9^{\wedge}8-((7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	43460071	$9^{\wedge}8+7*((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
42486835	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}2*1$	43582032	$9*(8*7+6)*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21)$
42486836	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}2*1$	43605468	$-9*(8*7+6)*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21)$
42486862	$9^{\wedge}8+(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}2-1$	43606578	$9^{\wedge}8-((7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
42486863	$9^{\wedge}8+(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}2+1$	43606579	$9^{\wedge}8-(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}2*1$
42486864	$9^{\wedge}8+(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}2+1$	43606580	$9^{\wedge}8-(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}2+1$
42577992	$9*8/(765+4)^{\wedge}((-3+2)-1)$	43606606	$9^{\wedge}8+(7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}2-1$
42633371	$9^{\wedge}8-7*((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$	43606607	$9^{\wedge}8+(7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}2+1$
42633385	$9^{\wedge}8-7*((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$	43606608	$9^{\wedge}8+(7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}2+1$
42666666	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)*6*(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	43620119	$9^{\wedge}8-7*(6-5/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$
42794721	$9^{\wedge}8-7/6*(5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	43620203	$9^{\wedge}8+7*(6-5/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$
42818258	$98/(7+654)^{\wedge}(-3+2-1)$	43620824	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7+6)*5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21$
42831471	$9^{\wedge}8-7*6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	43849730	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)*((6+5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-21)$
42831891	$9^{\wedge}8-7*6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	43886508	$9^{\wedge}8-(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
42870321	$9^{\wedge}8-(7*(6+54))^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$	43886550	$9^{\wedge}8+(7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
42906095	$9^{\wedge}8-(7*6*(5-4)+3)^{\wedge}2-1$	43925210	$(9^{\wedge}8-76/5)*((4+3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
42906097	$9^{\wedge}8-(7*6*(5-4)+3)^{\wedge}2+1$	43990632	$9*8*7*(6^{\wedge}5+43)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
42924760	$9^{\wedge}8-7*((-6-5)^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	44062218	$(9-8*7)*6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1$
42930227	$9^{\wedge}8-7*((65+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	44062782	$(9-8*7)*6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1$
42961671	$9^{\wedge}8+7*-6^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	44130825	$(9-8)/7*(6*(6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
42987664	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1$	44229887	$(9*8+7)/6^{\wedge}(5-4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
42987666	$9^{\wedge}8-7-(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1$	44229889	$(9*8+7)/6^{\wedge}(5-4*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
42987678	$9^{\wedge}8+7-(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1$	44231032	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)*((6+5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)+21)$
42987680	$9^{\wedge}8+7-(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1$	44342871	$((9-8/7)+6)*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
42991621	$9^{\wedge}8+76*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	44459686	$(9+8^{\wedge}7-6)*5^{\wedge}(-4+3)+21$
43016271	$9^{\wedge}8-7*6*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	44832940	$(-9+(8/7)^{\wedge}-6)*5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
43034564	$9^{\wedge}8-7-6^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	45006258	$9^{\wedge}8-(7*(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)+2)+1)$
43034578	$(9^{\wedge}8+7-6^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1))$	45006260	$9^{\wedge}8+7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2)+1$
43037684	$9^{\wedge}8-7*((6*5*43+2)-1)$	45006286	$9^{\wedge}8+7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)+2)-1$
43037698	$9^{\wedge}8-7*((6*5*43-2)+1)$	45006288	$9^{\wedge}8+7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)+2)+1$
43040848	$9^{\wedge}8-7*(6*5*(4-32)-1)$	45096565	$9^{\wedge}8-((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$
43040902	$(9^{\wedge}8+7)+6-(54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	45120000	$(-9+8*7)*6*(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
43041254	$9^{\wedge}8-7*((65*4*3+2)-1)$	45199056	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)+6)*5/(4-(3+2)^{\wedge}-1)$
43041268	$9^{\wedge}8-7*((65*4*3-2)+1)$	45294812	$9^{\wedge}8-(7-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
43042278	$9^{\wedge}8-(7/(6^{\wedge}5*4-3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	45438120	$9/8*76*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
43043546	$(9^{\wedge}8-7)-6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	45769455	$9^{\wedge}8+(7*6)^{\wedge}5/(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
43044596	$9^{\wedge}8-765*((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	45855612	$9*87*(-6-5)^{\wedge}4*(3+2-1)$
43044629	$9^{\wedge}8-(7/((6+5)^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	46373600	$98*7/(65*4)^{\wedge}((-3+2)-1)$
43045141	$(9^{\wedge}8-7+(-6-5))*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	46453434	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+6)/(-5-4-(3*2)^{\wedge}-1)$
43045494	$(9^{\wedge}8-7)+6-(5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1$	46463125	$(9+8)/7*(6/(6/(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
43048301	$9^{\wedge}8+7+(6+5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	46530560	$(9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^{\wedge}5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
43048813	$9^{\wedge}8+(7/((6+5)^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	46621044	$((-9+8+7)*654^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$

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46656007	$(9-8)^*7-(6^*5^*-4^*3)^(2+1)$	54401275	$(-9-8)^*(-76+(5^*-4)^(3+2)+1)$
46965818	$9^{\wedge}8+7^*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3)^*2-1)$	54401309	$(9+8)^*(76+(5^*4)^(3+2)+1)$
46965832	$9^{\wedge}8+7^*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3)^*2+1)$	54534256	$98^*-7^*(6-(-5+43^(2+1)))$
47764080	$(9/8+7)/6^{\wedge}(5-4^*3)^*21$	54541116	$98^*-7^*(6-5-43^(2+1))$
47829683	$9^{\wedge}8-7+(6/54)^(3^*2-1)$	54542488	$98^*7^*(6-5+43^(2+1))$
47829697	$9^{\wedge}8+7+(6/54)^(3^*2-1)$	54549348	$98^*7^*(6-(-5-43^(2+1)))$
47841280	$(9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^*5^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	54587519	$(9/-8-7)^*6^{\wedge}(5+4)/-3^*2-1$
48093750	$(-9/((8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5-43)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	54587521	$(9/-8-7)^*6^{\wedge}(5+4)/-3^*2+1$
48716532	$9^{\wedge}8+7^*((-6^*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2+1)$	54684182	$(9-8)^*7^*((65^*43)^{\wedge}2+1)$
48716910	$9^{\wedge}8+7^*((-6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	54857142	$(9-8)/7^*6^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3^*2-1)$
48779283	$(9/8^*7+6)^*((5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	55200000	$(9+8^*7^*6)^*(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
48828049	$((-9+8)^*76+5^{\wedge}(4+3^*2+1))$	55472683	$(98^*76)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))-21$
48925230	$9^{\wedge}8-(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*21$	55472725	$(98^*76)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))+21$
48925524	$9^{\wedge}8-(-7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*21$	55683936	$(-9+8)^*-7^*6^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
49064832	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*(2+1)$	56003862	$(9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6)^*(-5-(-4^*3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
49071033	$9/87^*((6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3^*-2+1)$	56010523	$(-9^*(8-(7^*6)^{\wedge}5+4)+3)/21$
49538900	$(-9-(8/7)^{\wedge}6)^*-5^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	56010533	$(9^*(8-(7^*6)^{\wedge}5+4)-3)/21$
49658189	$9^{\wedge}8+7+6)^*((5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	56388711	$(9^*8^{\wedge}7-(6^{\wedge}5(4+3)))^*(2+1)$
49918839	$-9-(-8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*21$	56388747	$(9^*8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*(2+1)$
49918857	$9+(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*21$	56752216	$(9-(-8/7-6))^*((5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
50073552	$(-9^{\wedge}(-8+7)+6)^*54^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	56753858	$98/(765-4)^{\wedge}(-3+2-1)$
50319351	$-9+8^{\wedge}7^*6^*(5-(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$	56857461	$(9^*8^{\wedge}7-(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)))^*(2+1)$
50319369	$9+8^{\wedge}7^*6^*(5-(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$	56857497	$(9^*8^{\wedge}7+6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*(2+1)$
50331354	$(98-((-7+6)+5)^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*(-2-1)$	56888888	$(9/8)^{\wedge}(-7+6)^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
50331942	$(98+((-7+6)+5)^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*(2+1)$	57606135	$-9+8^{\wedge}7^*6^*(5-(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
50343927	$-9+8^{\wedge}7^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$	57606153	$9+8^{\wedge}7^*6^*(5-(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
50343945	$9+8^{\wedge}7^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$	57614396	$98^*7^*6^*(5-(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
50353772	$(9-8)^*-7^*6^*(5-432-1)$	57681624	$98^*7^*6^*(5+(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
50528513	$(9/(8+(765+4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	57902298	$(9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6)^*(-5+(-4^*3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
50708874	$((9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(432-1)$	57904121	$(9^*8^{\wedge}7-(-6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3))^*2-1$
50898204	$(9+8)^*7/654^{\wedge}(-3+2-1)$	57904123	$(9^*8^{\wedge}7-(-6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3))^*2+1$
50944182	$((9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(432+1)$	57953378	$98/(765+4)^{\wedge}(-3+2-1)$
51029730	$9^*((-8+7^*(6^*5)^{\wedge}4-3)-2)+1$	58319640	$-9^*8^*(7-(((6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3)-2)-1)$
51029853	$(-9+8)^*7^*((-7+(6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3)^*-21)$	58320648	$-9^*8^*(7-(((6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3)-2)-1)$
51030270	$9^*((8+7^*(6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3)+2)-1$	58368609	$9/8^*((7/(6-5))^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
51294964	$(9-8)^*7^*6^*(5+432-1)$	58460001	$(9^*8^*-7+(6+5)^{\wedge}(4+3))^*(2+1)$
51380221	$((-9+8^{\wedge}7)^*6+5)^*-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	58463025	$(9^*8^*7-(-6-5)^{\wedge}(4+3))^*(2+1)$
51380227	$((-9-8^{\wedge}7)^*6+5)^*-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	58690921	$((-9-8)^*7+6^{\wedge}5+4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
51416001	$9/8^*(7+6)^*((5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	58720229	$9^*((8^{\wedge}7^*(6/54+3)-2)-1)$
51499476	$9^*(87^*6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)^*21$	58720283	$9^*((8^{\wedge}7^*(6/54+3)+2)+1)$
51657159	$((9+8/7)+6)^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	59049729	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^*6^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
51828156	$9^*(8/7^*((6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3)/2-1))$	59265270	$9^*-87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)^*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
51916464	$9^{\wedge}8+(((7+6)^*5+4)^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	59630203	$9+8^*-7-6^*(5^*-43)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
51963120	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)+6)^*54^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	59630297	$-9+8^*7-6^*(5^*-43)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
52234400	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}5)^*((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	59768643	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7^*(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4)-3)-21)$
52320000	$(-9-8^*-7^*6)^*(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	59768811	$9^*-8^{\wedge}7^*(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4)-3)-21$
52623200	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5)^*((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	59768829	$9/8^{\wedge}-7^*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3)-(-2+1)$
52728007	$(9-8)^*7+(65^*4)^{\wedge}3^*(2+1)$	59768830	$9^*8^{\wedge}7^*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3)-2^*1$
52926615	$9/8^*((7-6^*5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$	59768834	$9^*8^{\wedge}7^*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3)+2^1$
52930800	$9^*87/(65^*4)^{\wedge}((-3+2)-1)$	59768835	$9^*8^{\wedge}7^*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3)+2+1$
53037647	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4^*3)+2)^*-1$	59768853	$9^*-8^{\wedge}7^*(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4)-3)+21$
53037651	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4^*3)-2)^*-1$	59769021	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7^*(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4)-3)-21)$
53187848	$9^*(-8-7)^*6^*(5-4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$	59800503	$(-9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4+3))^*21$
53187849	$9^*(-8-7)^*6^*(5-4+3)^{\wedge}2^*1$	59800629	$(-9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4+3))^*21$
53187850	$9^*(-8-7)^*6^*(5-4+3)^{\wedge}2+1$	59800683	$-9+(((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3)^*21$
53551749	$-9^*(8+7+(65^{\wedge}4+3)/(-2-1))$	59800701	$9+(((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3)^*21$
53552001	$9^*(8+7+(-65^{\wedge}4+3)/(-2-1))$	59800733	$(9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6)^*(-5-4^{\wedge}(-3+2))-1$
53616492	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(5+43^*21)$	59800735	$(9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3+2))+1$
53747584	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4^{\wedge}3)^*2^{\wedge}1$	59800809	$-9-(((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4-3)^*21$
53747626	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-43)/2^{\wedge}-1$	59800827	$9-(((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4-3)^*21$
53747798	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+43)/2^{\wedge}-1$	59800881	$(9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3)^*21$
53747840	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4^{\wedge}3)^*2^{\wedge}1$	59801007	$(9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4+3)^*21$
53837485	$((-9+8)^*-7+6)^{\wedge}5^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	59861168	$(9-8^*-7^*6^*(5^*4+3))^{\wedge}2-1$
53926704	$9^*(8/-7^*(6-5^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)))$	59861169	$(9-8^*-7^*6^*(5^*4+3))^{\wedge}2+1$
54225971	$((-9+8^{\wedge}7)-6)^*543/21$	59861170	$(9-8^*-7^*6^*(5^*4+3))^{\wedge}2+1$
54253471	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7))^*((-6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*-2-1)$	59978633	$(9+8^{\wedge}7-6)/5^*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
54398691	$(-9-8)^*(76-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	60170931	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)/1)$
54398725	$(9+8)^*(76-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	60204032	$((-9-(-8-7))^*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1))$
54399269	$(-9-8)^*(7^*6+(5^*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	60402012	$(9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)-5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
54399303	$(9+8)^*(7^*6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	60412242	$(9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
54400697	$(-9-8)^*(7^*6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	60445629	$9^*((8/(7-6^*5))^{\wedge}4^*3-2)-1)$
54400731	$(9+8)^*(7^*6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	60445683	$9^*((8^*(7+6^*-5))^{\wedge}4^*3+2)+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
60466087	$9^*(-8-(7-6^{\wedge}(5+4)))/3^*2+1$	67030830	$9/8*((7+6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
60466265	$9^*(-8-(7+6^{\wedge}(5+4)))/-3^*2-1$	67106176	$((-9+8^{\wedge}7/6)-5)^*4^{\wedge}3*(2+1)$
60466649	$(9^*8+7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*3^*2-1$	67111552	$((9+8^{\wedge}7/6)+5)^*4^{\wedge}3*(2+1)$
60466651	$(9^*8+7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*3^*2+1$	67354624	$(98^*7^*-6+5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
60496356	$9^*((8^*(7+6)+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/21$	67518464	$(98^*7^*6+5)/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
60520100	$(9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)-5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	67692429	$9/8*((-7+6^{\wedge}5-4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
60530350	$(9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	67878725	$9/8*((7-(6^{\wedge}5-4/3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
60682689	$9^{\wedge}8+7/(6^{\wedge}(-5-4))^*(3+2-1)$	67925339	$9/8*((7-(6^{\wedge}5+4/3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
60728320	$((-9-(-8-7))^*6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1))$	67936995	$9/8*((7+6^{\wedge}5-4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
60805111	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)))-1$	68111955	$9/8*((-7+6^{\wedge}5+4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
60805129	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)))-1$	68170325	$9/8*((7+6^{\wedge}5+4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
60829687	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2)))-1$	68222967	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
60829705	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2)))-1$	68222985	$9+8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
61519689	$9/8^*7*((65^*43)^{\wedge}2-1)$	68357277	$9/8*((7+6^{\wedge}5+4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
61533447	$(9^*8^{\wedge}(-6-(-5+4))^*3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$	68389767	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+65)/(4^*-3)^*2-1$
61865981	$((-9+8^{\wedge}-7)^*-6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	68389769	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+65)/(4^*-3)^*2+1$
61865987	$((-9-8^{\wedge}-7)^*-6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	68868024	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7/6+5)/(4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
62029815	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*5-(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	68891071	$-9+8/7*((6^{\wedge}5+4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
62029833	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*5-(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	68891089	$9+8/7*((6^{\wedge}5-4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
62128128	$(-9-8^*7*(-6-5))^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	68904192	$(98-7^*6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*-21$
62157435	$(9^*876)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))-21$	68904738	$(-9^*8+7^*6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$
62157477	$(9^*876)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))+21$	68907762	$(9^*8-7^*-6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$
62245368	$9^*-8^*7*(6-(-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	68908308	$(98-7^*6^*-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$
62253198	$9^*-8^*7*(6-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	68979831	$-9+8/7*((-6^{\wedge}5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
62254764	$9^*8^*7*(6-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	68979849	$9+8/7*((-6^{\wedge}5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
62262594	$9^*8^*7*(6-(-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	69025374	$9/8*((7-(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
62417744	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)+6)^*(5/4+(3+2)^{\wedge}-1)$	69228663	$-9+8/7*((6^{\wedge}5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
62783479	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-(-2+1)))$	69228681	$9+8/7*((6^{\wedge}5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
62783497	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-(-2+1)))$	69272334	$9/8*((7+6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
62853111	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*6*5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$	69500673	$9^{\wedge}8+7/(6^{\wedge}-5^*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
62853129	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6*5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$	69568583	$(-9+8)^*7*(6+(-5^*43)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
62865399	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$	69866496	$9^*(8^*76)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)^*21$
62865417	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$	70431261	$9/((8+76^{\wedge}5)/4+3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
62906359	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$	70541625	$(-9+8)^*7*((-6^{\wedge}5+4)+321)$
62906377	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$	70543675	$(-9-(8/7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3)^*21$
62913783	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1))$	70543691	$(-9+(8/7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3)^*21$
62913801	$9+8^{\wedge}7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1))$	70544053	$(9+(-8/7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3)^*21$
62915319	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1))$	70544069	$(9-(-8/7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3)^*21$
62915337	$9+8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1))$	70992841	$-9+(-8-7^*-6)^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
62922743	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(-6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$	70992859	$9+(-8-7^*-6)^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
62922761	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(-6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$	71766189	$9/8*((7+6+(-5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
62932489	$(9*(876+5)+4)^{\wedge}(3-2)+1$	71982000	$9/8*((7-6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
62963703	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$	72018000	$9/8*((7-6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
62963721	$9+8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$	72029902	$-98+(7^*6^*5)^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
62975991	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*6*5*(-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$	72230098	$98+(7^*6^*5)^{\wedge}4/3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
62976009	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6*5*(-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$	72234189	$9/8*((7+6-(-5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
63045623	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(-6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-(-2+1)))$	72521552	$-9^*8-7*(654/-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
63045641	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(-6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-(-2+1)))$	72521696	$9^*8-7*(654/-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
63307776	$(-9-(-8-7)^*65)^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	72801099	$9^*((8^{\wedge}7-6)+5)^*(4-3/21)$
63737856	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2))^*-1$	73161711	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3^*21$
63799287	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*5+(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	73234324	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}(6+5)+4)^*3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
63799305	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*5+(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	74114881	$(9^*8^*7*(-6-5)+4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$
63999756	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1$	74301955	$(9-8)^*7*((6^*543)^{\wedge}2+1)$
63999757	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2+1)$	74399871	$(9+8)^*((7/((6+5)^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}-2-1)$
63999758	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1$	74399905	$(9+8)^*((7/((6+5)^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}-2+1)$
64000243	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2+1)$	74430343	$-9-8^{\wedge}7+(6^*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1$
64000244	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1$	74430361	$9-8^{\wedge}7+(6^*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1$
64181376	$9*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*(2+1)$	75110328	$(-9-(-8+7)/6)/-54^{\wedge}((-3-2)+1)$
64998721	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^*6^*5^*4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	75413793	$9/8^*7*((6^*5)^{\wedge}(4^*3/2)-1)$
64999415	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)))+1$	75466341	$(9^*8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}5)^*4-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
64999433	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)))+1$	75466395	$(9^*8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}5)^*4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
65023991	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2)))+1$	75485175	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
65024009	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2)))+1$	75485193	$9+8^{\wedge}7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
65343558	$(-98+(7^*6)^{\wedge}((5-4)+3))^*21$	75497325	$(9^*8^{\wedge}7-6^*5)^*4-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
65345259	$(-9-8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3))^*21$	75497379	$(9^*8^{\wedge}7-6^*5)^*4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
65345973	$(-9-8-(7^*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3))^*-21$	75497565	$(9^*8^{\wedge}7+6^*5)^*4-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
65347674	$(-98-(7^*6)^{\wedge}((5-4)+3))^*-21$	75497619	$(9^*8^{\wedge}7+6^*5)^*4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
65812491	$-9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6*((5+(4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$	75509751	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
66355200	$9^*(-8-7)^*6*-5^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$	75509769	$9+8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
66787902	$9/8*((7-(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	75523671	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)/6)/(-5-4^*321)$
66961557	$-9-(8/7^*-6^*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1$	75528549	$(9^*8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5)^*4-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
66961575	$9-(8/7^*-6^*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1$	75528603	$(9^*8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5)^*4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)$

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76114161	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5+4*321)$	88783860	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)+6)*((5/4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
76527457	$9-8*7+(6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1$	88941255	$9/8*(7+(6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3/(-2-1))$
76527490	$-98/7+(6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1$	89111319	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3*2)+1)$
76527518	$98/7+(6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1$	89139492	$-9*(8-76^{\wedge}5*4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$
76527551	$(-9+8*7)+(6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1$	89139636	$9*(8-76^{\wedge}5*-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$
76886496	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4*3-21$	89497760	$(9-8/7)*((6-(-5-4))^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
76886604	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3*(2+1)$	89571328	$(9*8*-76+5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
76886685	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4*3^{\wedge}(2-1)$	89701164	$9/8*7*((6+5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
76886766	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3*(2+1)$	89735168	$(9*8*76+5)/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
76886874	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4*3+21$	89870400	$(9*8+7)*6*5*4^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
76890112	$(9*87*-6+5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$	90344970	$9^{\wedge}((8-7)+6)*((5*4-3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
77053952	$(9*87*6+5)/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$	90367245	$-9^{\wedge}8-(7*6)^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
77590386	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))/-54^{\wedge}(-3-(2-1))$	91353237	$-9^{\wedge}8-7*-6*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
77662265	$(9-8)/7*((6^{\wedge}5-4)*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	91353321	$-9^{\wedge}8-7*-6*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
77923954	$9^{\wedge}8+(7/(6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	91552740	$9/8*(7+(6-5^{\wedge}(4*3))/(-2-1))$
77944680	$(-9+(-8+7)/6)/-54^{\wedge}((-3-2)+1)$	91675764	$9*(8^{\wedge}7+6)*(5-(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
78051708	$(9*8*(7*6)^{\wedge}5/43)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	91974672	$98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$
78159735	$((9+8^{\wedge}7-65)^{\wedge}4+3)/21$	92236669	$98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4+3*21$
78193773	$9*((8^{\wedge}7-6)+5)*(4+3/21)$	92236684	$98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4*(32+1)$
78624647	$-9+8^{\wedge}7+(6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1$	92236692	$98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4*(32-1)$
78624665	$9+8^{\wedge}7+(6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1$	92236708	$98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4/3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
79066611	$9^{\wedge}8*((-8+7)+6)*(-5+4^{\wedge}3*21)$	92236720	$98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4*(3+21)$
79114432	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(6-5+4))/3*(2-1)$	92236912	$98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4*(3+21)$
79355136	$(9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)-5)*4^{\wedge}3*21$	92236924	$98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4/3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
79368576	$(9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)+5)*4^{\wedge}3*21$	92236940	$98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4*(32-1)$
79378628	$-98*((7-(6*5)^{\wedge}4+3*2)+1)$	92236948	$98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4*(32+1)$
79381372	$98*((7+(6*5)^{\wedge}4+3*2)+1)$	92236960	$98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+(4*3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
79657101	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*5+4^{\wedge}3*21$	92236963	$98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4+3*21$
80615304	$(9*87-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(-3^{\wedge}2+1)$	92498960	$98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$
80616080	$(9*87-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(-3^{\wedge}2+1)$	93177117	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6)*(5*4*(-3-2)+1)$
80621120	$-9*(8*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(-3^{\wedge}2+1)$	93178899	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6)*(5*4*(-3-2)+1)$
80622016	$9*(8*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(-3^{\wedge}2+1)$	93908348	$(9/(8+(76^{\wedge}5-4)/3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
80627056	$(98*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3^{\wedge}2-1$	93933000	$(9+8/7)*(6*5*(4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
80627832	$(9*87+6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3^{\wedge}2-1$	93972624	$9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4/(32+1)$
81380204	$((-9+87)/6-5^{\wedge}(4*3))/(-2-1)$	93972912	$(9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4)*(32+1)$
81380250	$((-9-8)*-7+6+5^{\wedge}(4*3))/(2+1)$	94058482	$98/7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3*2-1)$
82031208	$(-9+8)*-7*6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3+2)-1)$	94058510	$98/7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3*2+1)$
82031257	$(-9+8)*7*(-6*5^{\wedge}(4-(3-2))-1)$	94279680	$9*8^{\wedge}7*(6+5/-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
82285713	$9/(8-7+6)*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	94464000	$9*-8^{\wedge}7*(-6-5/4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
82485047	$(-9/8+7)*((-6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	94702619	$(9^{\wedge}8-76)/5^{\wedge}(-4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
82749422	$(-9/8+7)*((6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	95482233	$9^{\wedge}8(8-(7-6))*5*4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
83348919	$-9*(8-(7*6*5)^{\wedge}(4-3)+2)+1$	95682560	$((9*8+7)-6)*5*4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$
83348937	$-9*(8-((7*6*5)^{\wedge}(4-3)+2)+1)$	95781096	$9^{\wedge}8-(7*6*(-5-4)+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
83349063	$9*(8-((7*6*5)^{\wedge}(4-3)+2)+1)$	96017950	$98*(7/(6^{\wedge}(5-4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$
83349081	$9*(8+(7*6*5)^{\wedge}(4-3)+2)+1$	96018146	$-98*(7/(-6^{\wedge}(5-4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$
83883920	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7/6)*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	96300000	$(9+8+7+6)^{\wedge}5*(4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
83885648	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7/-6*5)*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	97068456	$9*(8^{\wedge}7+6)*(5-(-4-3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
83886512	$(9-8^{\wedge}7/-6*5)*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	97290156	$((9-(8*7)^{\wedge}6)-5)/(4-321)$
83888240	$(9+8^{\wedge}7/6)*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	97494761	$(9-8)*7*((6*(-5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
84131840	$(9*8+7)*65*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$	97494775	$(9-8)*7*((6*(-5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
84917781	$(9*8^{\wedge}7/-6+5^{\wedge}4)*-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	97535374	$(9876^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)-2)^{\wedge}1$
84951531	$(9*8^{\wedge}7/-6-5^{\wedge}4)*-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	97535378	$9876^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+2^{\wedge}1$
85164629	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+6)/(-5+(4+3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$	97785144	$(-9+(-8-7)/6)/-54^{\wedge}((-3-2)+1)$
85207707	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*((5-43)^{\wedge}2-1)$	98100000	$(9+8+7+6)^{\wedge}5*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
85333332	$((9-8)+7)/6*(5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1$	98280070	$(9-8)*7*((-6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
85343301	$9^{\wedge}8*((7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-4)^{\wedge}3+2/1)$	98595056	$(-9+8)*-7*((6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
85441983	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))*4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1$	98595070	$(9-8)*7*((6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
85562000	$-9+8*((76+5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-2)-1$	99384761	$(9-8)*7*((6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
85562002	$-9+8*((76+5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-2)+1$	99384775	$(9-8)*7*((6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
85609025	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$	100528491	$((9+8)/(7*((-6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3)+2))^{\wedge}-1$
85764447	$9/8*((76-5)^{\wedge}4+3+21)$	100699200	$(-9+8)*-7*6^{\wedge}5*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$
86624882	$9^{\wedge}8*((76+5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)+2)-1$	100769130	$(-9*87+6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
86624884	$9^{\wedge}8*((76+5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)+2)+1$	100770100	$(-98*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
86669913	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3*2)+1)$	100776400	$-9*(8*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
86843583	$9^{\wedge}8*((-7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+4)^{\wedge}3+2)^{\wedge}1$	100777520	$9*(8*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
87328125	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4*(32-1)$	100783820	$(98*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
87628127	$(-9^{\wedge}8+(7*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$	100784790	$(9*87+6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
87660895	$(-9^{\wedge}8+(7*6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$	101040219	$9/8*((7+6)*5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
88277026	$(-9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4)*(32-1)$	101695500	$9/(8+7)^{\wedge}6*-5^{\wedge}(-4-(-3+2))+1$
88277296	$-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4*(32-1)$	101792992	$(9/((8*7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3*2)))^{\wedge}-1$
88277314	$9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4*(32-1)$	101808576	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
88277584	$(9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4)*(32-1)$	101977623	$9^{\wedge}8((-8+7)+6)*54*32-1$

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102036651	$(9*8)^{-7}6^{6}((-5-4)^{-3})-21$	118589688	$9*8*((7^{6}(6+5-4)-3)^{2}-1)$
102036679	$(9-8)^{7}+(6*54)^{3}(2+1)$	118589832	$9*8*((7^{6}(6+5-4)-3)^{2}+1)$
102095721	$9^{8}((-8+7)+6)^{5}(54*32+1)$	118590552	$9*8*((7^{6}(6+5-4)+3)^{2}-1)$
102514833	$-9*((87-(6+5+4)^{3})^{2}+1)$	118784000	$9*87*(6/5*4^{4}-3)^{2}-1$
102516417	$9*((87+(6+5+4)^{3})^{2}+1)$	119069937	$(-9+8)^{7}(7*(6*5)^{4}-3)^{2}-21$
102584642	$((-9-8)^{7}+65)/(-4-3)^{2}-1$	119186337	$((-9+87)/6)^{5}+4)^{3}321$
103016448	$(9*8)^{7}((-7+6)+5)^{4}(4+(-3)^{2})^{-1}$	119574218	$(9^{8}-7)-(-6*54^{4}(-3-2))^{-1}$
103312128	$((9^{8}-7)+6)/(5/(4*3)^{2}-1)$	119574232	$9^{8}+7+(6*54^{4}(-3-2))^{-1}$
103335750	$9/(8+7)^{4}-6*(5^{4}(-4-(-3+2))^{2}+1)$	119766682	$(-9+8)^{7}7^{6}*(5-(4^{4}(3+2)-1))$
103656231	$-9*(8/7*(6^{4}(5+4)+3)^{2}+1)$	119812608	$(9*8)^{7}(7-(6-5)^{4})^{3}321$
103656249	$9*(8/7*(6^{4}(5+4)-3)^{2}+1)$	120585100	$((9-8)^{7}7^{6}-5)^{4}(4^{4}(3+2)+1)$
103656300	$9*(8/7*(6^{4}(5+4)+(-3)^{2})^{-1})$	120932028	$9*8*((-7+6^{4}(5+4)/3)/2-1)$
103656321	$9*(8/7*(6^{4}(5+4)+3-2)+1)$	120932172	$9*8*((-7+6^{4}(5+4)/3)/2+1)$
104857531	$-9-(8/7*(6^{4}(5+4)+3)^{2}+1)$	120932532	$9*8*((7+6^{4}(5+4)/3)/2-1)$
104857549	$9-(-8^{7}+6/5)*((4+3)^{2}+1)$	120932676	$9*8*((7+6^{4}(5+4)/3)/2+1)$
105823810	$(-9+8)^{7}((-6+5)^{4}3)^{2}+1$	121134908	$(9*8+7^{6})*((5+4^{4}(3+2))^{-1})$
106165017	$((9+8)^{7})^{4}(-6-(-5-4))^{3}21$	121134910	$(9*8+7^{6})*((5+4^{4}(3+2))^{2}+1)$
106655616	$(9*8)^{7}((-7+6)+5)^{4}(4-3)^{2}-1$	121139193	$(9-8)^{7}*(65^{4}4)^{2}-1$
106666665	$(9+8-7)/6*(5^{4})^{3}-1$	121550644	$9+((8+7)+6)^{5}4^{-1}(-3)^{2}-1$
106677486	$-9/87^{4}(6-5-4)^{3}(3-21)$	122343750	$9*87^{6}/(5^{4}(-4-3)^{2}+1)$
107187500	$98^{7}6/5^{4}(-4-3)^{2}+1$	122851903	$-9-8/7*((6^{4}5^{4}/3)^{2}-1)$
107495103	$(9*8)^{7}((-7+6)+5)^{4}-321$	122851921	$9-8/7*((6^{4}5^{4}/3)^{2}-1)$
107495391	$(9*8)^{7}((-7+6)+5)^{4}-32-1$	123633664	$98^{7}*(-6-5)/(-4)^{4}(-3)^{2}-1$
107495392	$(9*8)^{7}((-7+6)+5)^{4}-32*1$	123925746	$(-9/8+7)^{6}*(5^{4}4)^{2}-1$
107495393	$(9*8)^{7}((-7+6)+5)^{4}-32+1$	124452864	$9*-8^{7}*(6^{4}5^{4}4(-3-2)+1)$
107495406	$((9*8)^{7}((-7+6)+5)^{4}+3-21)$	124497346	$9^{8}+(76^{5}/4)^{4}(3+2-1)$
107495442	$(9*8)^{7}((-7+6)+5)^{4}-3+21$	124687500	$(-9+8)^{7}76^{5}4^{4}(4+3)^{2}-21$
107495455	$((9*8)^{7}((-7+6)+5)^{4}+32-1)$	124954144	$(9-8)^{7}*(65^{4}4-32)^{-1}$
107495457	$((9*8)^{7}((-7+6)+5)^{4}+32+1)$	124954606	$(-9+8)^{7}*(65^{4}+32)^{2}+1$
107495745	$(9*8)^{7}((-7+6)+5)^{4}+321$	127172608	$(98/7-6^{4}5)^{4}*(3^{2}+1)$
108335232	$(9*8)^{7}((-7+6)+5)^{4}(4+3)^{2}-1$	127250595	$9^{8}((-8+7)+6)^{5}*(432-1)$
108827307	$9^{8}((-8+7)+6)^{5}(-5+4)^{3}-1$	127340129	$(-9+8)^{7}*(-7/(65^{4}+3))^{2}-1$
109172356	$9^{8}((-8+7)+6)^{5}4^{3}2^{2}+1$	127631360	$(98/7+6^{4}5)^{4}*(3^{2}+1)$
109190846	$9^{8}((-8+7)+6)^{5}4^{3}2^{2}+1$	127841085	$9^{8}((-8+7)+6)^{5}*(432+1)$
109349406	$9*((8+7)^{6}*(6^{4}5^{4}-3)-21)$	128024001	$(9*8^{7})^{4}((-6+5)+4)^{-3}21$
109350594	$-9*((8+7)^{6}*(6^{4}5^{4}+3)-21)$	128024032	$(9*8^{7})^{4}((-6+5)+4)^{-3}21$
109417797	$9^{8}((-8+7)+6)^{5}(5+4)^{3}-1$	128024057	$(9*8^{7})^{4}((-6+5)+4)^{-3}21$
109432895	$(9-8/7)^{6}*(6^{4}(-5+4+3))^{2}-1$	128024071	$(9*8^{7})^{4}((-6+5)+4)^{3}2+1$
109714284	$9*8/(7*6)^{4}((5^{4})^{3}-1)$	128024096	$(9*8^{7})^{4}((-6+5)+4)+32/1$
110565063	$9/8^{7}*(6^{4}5^{4}+3)^{2}-1$	128024127	$(9*8^{7})^{4}((-6+5)+4)+3^{2}21$
110565072	$9/8^{7}*(6^{4}5^{4}+3)^{2}+1$	128144466	$9*((8+7)^{6}-5)/4^{4}(3+2)-1$
110667920	$(9-8/7)^{6}*(6^{4}5^{4}+3)^{2}-1$	128144475	$9*((8+7)^{6}-5)/4^{4}(3+2)^{2}+1$
110919438	$9/8^{7}*(6^{4}5^{4}+3)^{2}-1$	128144484	$9*((8+7)^{6}-5)/4^{4}(3+2)+1$
110919447	$9/8^{7}*(6^{4}5^{4}+3)^{2}+1$	128390022	$9^{8}*((7^{6}(-6+5)-4)^{-3}+2+1)$
111070574	$(9/(8^{7}*(6^{4}5^{4}+3)^{-2}))^{-1}$	128562627	$9/(8+7)^{6}*((6+5)^{4}-3)^{2}+1$
111806208	$-9*(8^{7}6+(5+4)^{3}-21)$	128581632	$-9*(-8-7*6^{5})^{4}4^{3}2+1$
112860333	$9*(8^{7}6+(-5*(4+3))^{2}+1)$	128608722	$-9^{8}*((76+5)^{4}(-4+3)-2+1)$
112877568	$9*8^{7}*(6-5*4^{4}(-3-2+1))$	128668041	$9/(8+7)^{6}*((6+5)^{4}+3)^{2}-1$
112951296	$9*8^{7}*(6+(-5+4-3)^{2}-1)$	128798199	$-9-8^{7}*(6-5)^{4}3^{2}+1$
112997661	$(9+8/7)^{6}(((6-5)+4)^{3}+21)$	128798217	$9-8^{7}*(6-5)^{4}3^{2}+1$
113197056	$-9*8^{7}6^{4}((5+4)^{3}-1)$	128894484	$((9-(8-76))^{4}5+4+3)/21$
113541120	$9*8^{7}*(6+(5-(4-3))^{2}-1)$	129783654	$((9-8)^{7}*(7^{6}5^{4}*(4^{3})^{-2}-1)$
113614848	$9*8^{7}*(6-5^{4}-4^{4}(-3-2+1))$	130625696	$(-9+8)^{7}*((-7^{6})^{4}5+4^{4}(3^{2}-1))$
113632083	$9*(8^{7}6+(5*(4+3))^{2}+1)$	130674750	$(-98-(-7^{6})^{4}5)^{4}4^{3}2+1$
114075065	$(9/8+7)^{6}*((-6/5^{4}-4+3)^{2}-1)$	130674946	$98-(-7^{6})^{4}5-4^{4}(3^{2}+1)$
114440690	$(9/8+7)^{6}*((6/5^{4}-4+3)^{2}-1)$	130707518	$(-98-(-7^{6})^{4}5)+4^{4}(3^{2}+1)$
114686208	$-9*(-8^{7}6-(5^{4})^{3}-2+1)$	130707714	$98-(-7^{6})^{4}5+4^{4}(3^{2}+1)$
114819063	$-9-8^{7}*(6-54/(-3^{2}-2+1))$	130756768	$(-9+8)^{7}*(-7^{6})^{4}5+4^{4}(3^{2}-1)$
114819081	$9-8^{7}*(6-54/(-3^{2}-2+1))$	132028416	$9*8^{7}*(6-5/4^{4}(3+2)+1)$
115330023	$(9*((8+7)^{6}-5)-4)/(-3^{2}-2+1)$	132212736	$9*8^{7}*(6+5/4^{4}(3+2)+1)$
115330032	$(9*((8+7)^{6}-5)+4)/(-3^{2}-2+1)$	133413949	$(-9-8)-7^{6}5^{4}/((4+3)^{2}-1)$
115533472	$(9+8/7)^{6}*((6-(-5-4))^{3}-1)$	133413965	$-9+8-7^{6}5^{4}/((4+3)^{2}-1)$
116859348	$(9^{8}-7^{6})^{4}5/(4^{4}(-3+2)-1)$	133413967	$9-8-7^{6}5^{4}/((4+3)^{2}-1)$
117160704	$9*(8/7*((6+5)+4)^{3}-1)$	133413983	$9+8-7^{6}5^{4}/((4+3)^{2}-1)$
117186996	$-9*8^{7}*(7+(-6/5^{4}(4+3)^{2})^{-1})$	133414029	$((9-8)^{7}7^{6}5^{4}3)^{2}+1$
117188004	$9*8^{7}*(7-(-6/5^{4}(4+3)^{2})^{-1})$	133923125	$(9-8)^{7}*(6*(5+4)^{3})^{2}-1$
117239434	$((-9-8)^{7}+654)/(-3-2)^{2}-1$	134217702	$(-9+8)^{7}*((-7+6)+5)^{4}(4^{3}-2)^{-1}$
117239638	$((9+8)^{7}+654)/(3+2)^{2}-1$	134369260	$((9*8)^{7}((-7+6)+5)^{-4}*(3+2)^{2}+1$
118061496	$9*-8*(7^{6}-5^{4}(4+3))^{2}+1$	134369300	$((9*8)^{7}((-7+6)+5)^{4}*(3+2)^{2}+1$
118121976	$9*-8*(7^{6}-5^{4}(4+3))^{2}+1$	135419768	$(9*((8-7)^{6}+5)^{4}-3)^{2}-1$
118128024	$9*8*(7^{6}+5^{4}(4+3))^{2}+1$	135419769	$(9*((8-7)^{6}+5)^{4}-3)^{2}+1$
118188504	$9*8*(7^{6}+5^{4}(4+3))^{2}+1$	135419770	$(9*((8-7)^{6}+5)^{4}-3)^{2}+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
135430135	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(65-(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	150958081	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)-4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1$
135430153	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(65-(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	150958089	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)-4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$
135498033	$(9/8*7+6)*(5^{\wedge}(4+3*2)-1)$	150995019	$9*(8+((7-6)-5)^{\wedge}(4*3))-(-2-1)$
135989847	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5+43)^{\wedge}2-1)$	151031799	$9*((8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)+4^{\wedge}(3*2))-1)$
136181751	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*65*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$	151031807	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)+4^{\wedge}(3*2))-1$
136181769	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*65*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$	151031809	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)+4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1$
136447991	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*65*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$	151031817	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)+4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$
136448009	$9+8^{\wedge}7*65*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$	151068672	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
137199607	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(65+(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	151068690	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
137199625	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(65+(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	151290000	$9/(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+4)^{\wedge}(-3+2-1)$
137329110	$9/8*((7+6+5^{\wedge}(4*3))/2+1)$	151511472	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
137363456	$9/8*-7*-6*(-5/4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	151511490	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
138235064	$(9-8)/7*((6^{\wedge}5*4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	151611285	$(9/8+7*6)*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
139460419	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3))*21$	151880967	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
139460797	$(9+8^{\wedge}7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3))*21$	151880985	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
141086232	$9*8*(7/6^{\wedge}(5-4*3)-21)$	152393045	$(9/(8^{\wedge}7*654-3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
141087366	$98/7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	152523567	$(9*(8-7))^{\wedge}6*((-5-4)^*-32-1)$
141087528	$9*8*(7/6^{\wedge}(5-4*3)-2-1)$	152900000	$9*8^{\wedge}7*(6-5*((4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1)))$
141087960	$9*-8*(7/-6^{\wedge}(5-4*3)-2-1)$	153461457	$9/8*(7*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4+3)-2)+1)$
141088122	$98/7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	153527400	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*((54-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
141089256	$9*8*(7/6^{\wedge}(5-4*3)+21)$	153645498	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*((54-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
141115392	$9*8*((-6-5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$	154181880	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+43)^{\wedge}2-1)$
141267919	$(9+8/7)*((6*(-5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	154181889	$(-9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+43)^{\wedge}2)*-1$
141557256	$9*-8*(7-6*5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	154181898	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+43)^{\wedge}2+1)$
141558264	$9*8*(7-6*5*-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	154218750	$987*6/(5^{\wedge}(-4-3)*2+1)$
141851745	$9/8*((-8^{\wedge}7+6)*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	154533888	$9*8^{\wedge}7*(6-5*((4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1)))$
142248960	$(9*8*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)*(3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	154854146	$(-9+8)*7+(6-543)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
142500000	$9*8*76/(5^{\wedge}(-4-3)*2+1)$	155351296	$((-9-(8-7-6)^{\wedge}5)*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
142822251	$9/8*(7+6)*(5^{\wedge}(4+3*2)-1)$	155514447	$9/(8*7)*((6^{\wedge}5*4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
142862224	$(9+8/7)*((6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	157151296	$((-9+(8-7-6)^{\wedge}5)*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
142914870	$9/8*(((-7-6*5^{\wedge}4)*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	157436881	$(-9-8)*7+(6*5*(-4-3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
143257608	$9*8/7*((6*(-5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	157437119	$(9+8)*7+(6*5*(4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
143701131	$(-9/8-7*-6)*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	158669847	$(-9+8)*-7*(65+4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
144932609	$9/(((-8^{\wedge}7+6)*(-5^{\wedge}4+3)-2))^{\wedge}(-1)$	158723717	$(9/8*7*6*(5+4+3)*2-1)$
145282707	$9/8*((76+5)^{\wedge}4*3+21)$	158723719	$(9/8*7*6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3)*2+1$
145489920	$((98+7)+6)*5*4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$	160102701	$9*(8-7*6)+543^{\wedge}(2+1)$
145752064	$9*8^{\wedge}7*6*(5/4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	160103313	$-9*(8-7*6)+543^{\wedge}(2+1)$
146393545	$(9+8)/7*((6^{\wedge}5-4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	160655256	$-9*((8-((-7-6)^{\wedge}5)*4)+32+1)$
146582160	$(9+8)/7*((-6^{\wedge}5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	160655994	$9*((8+((-7-6)^{\wedge}5)*4)+32+1)$
146732724	$9/8*((7*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1)))$	161548175	$(-9/((8-76)^{\wedge}5-(4+3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
147033657	$9/((8^{\wedge}7*(6+5^{\wedge}4+3)-2))^{\wedge}(-1)$	161548179	$(-9/((8-76)^{\wedge}5-43))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
147322548	$(9/((7*6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))))$	162135027	$9/8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
147588768	$9*8*((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/21$	162201600	$9*8^{\wedge}7*(6^{\wedge}5*4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
147656208	$(9-8)*7*6*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	162527400	$(9/((-8^{\wedge}7+6/5^{\wedge}(4*3)+2))^{\wedge}(-1)$
147656292	$(9-8)*7*6*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	162760407	$(-9/(87-6*5^{\wedge}(4*3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
147718144	$98*(-7+6*5)*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	162760415	$(-9/(8+7-6*5^{\wedge}(4*3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
147806207	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)*(4+3/2)-1$	162760416	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7)*6*(5^{\wedge}(4*3)-(-2-1))$
147806209	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)*(4+3/2)+1$	164916144	$-9*8-7+((-6-5)*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
147841272	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-43)^{\wedge}2-1)$	165736560	$(9-8/7)*6*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
147841281	$(-9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-43)^{\wedge}2)*-1$	166330359	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*(4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$
147841290	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-43)^{\wedge}2+1)$	166330377	$9*(8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*(4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$
150111495	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	166418112	$(98*76)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))*(2+1)$
150111503	$9*(8^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	167081778	$9*(-8+(7+6)^{\wedge}5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
150111504	$(-9*(8^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4*3)^{\wedge}2)*-1$	167081922	$9*(8+(7+6)^{\wedge}5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
150111505	$9*(8^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4*3)^{\wedge}2+1$	168194961	$(9*(8-7*(-65-4)*-3))^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
150111513	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	168291954	$((9+8^{\wedge}7)-65)/4*321$
150115680	$9*(8+7)*6^{\wedge}5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	168300942	$((-9+8^{\wedge}7)+65)/4*321$
150321875	$(9+8/7)*((6/(5+4))^{\wedge}(-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	168374732	$(9+8)*76^{\wedge}5*4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1)$
150399671	$(9-8*7)*(6-((5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$	169599947	$(-9+8*7+6)*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
150399765	$(9-8*7)*(6-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	169600053	$(9-8*7-6)*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
150400235	$(-9+8*7)*(6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	171386670	$(9/8+7)*6*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
150400329	$(-9+8*7)*(6-((5*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$	172490743	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(65/4*(3+2)+1)$
150479280	$9*((87*((6+5)*4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	172490761	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(65/4*(3+2)+1)$
150479298	$9*((87*((-6-5)*-4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	172556042	$(9/(87*65^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
150732800	$9*8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)-4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$	172641504	$(98/7)^{\wedge}((6-5)+4)*321$
150896647	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	173721569	$9^{\wedge}8-((-7*6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$
150896656	$9*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4/3)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$	173754337	$9^{\wedge}8-((-7*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$
150896665	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	174877300	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)+6)*((5/4-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
150921216	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-(-4-3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	174956976	$9*8*((-7+(6*5)^{\wedge}4)*3-21)$
150921234	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-(-4-3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	174958461	$9*((8*(-7+(6*5)^{\wedge}4)*3-2)-1)$
150958071	$9*((8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)-4^{\wedge}(3*2))-1)$	174958515	$9*((8*(-7+(6*5)^{\wedge}4)*3+2)+1)$
150958079	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)-4^{\wedge}(3*2))-1$	174961485	$9*((-8*(-7-(6*5)^{\wedge}4)*3-2)-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
174961539	$-9 * ((8 * (-7 - (6 * 5)^4) * 3 - 2) - 1)$	203885717	$(-9 + 8) * 7^6 * (-5 - (4 * 3)^{(2+1)})$
174963024	$9 * 8 * ((-7 - (6 * 5)^4) * -3 + 21)$	204119928	$-9 * (8 - 7 * (6 * 5)^4 * ((3 + 2) - 1))$
176460687	$9^8 - (7 * 6)^5 / ((4 + 3)^{-2 - 1})$	204120072	$9 * (8 + 7 * (6 * 5)^4 * ((3 + 2) - 1))$
177446679	$9^8 - 7 * -6 * ((5 * 4)^{(3+2)} - 1)$	204204952	$-98 + (7 * 6)^5 * ((4/3)^{-2+1})$
177446763	$9^8 - 7 * 6 * ((5 * 4)^{(3+2)} - 1)$	204204978	$-9 * 8 + (7 * 6)^5 * ((4/3)^{-2+1})$
178913280	$(-98 + 7) * 6 * 5 * -4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1)$	204205050	$(9 - 8) * (7 * 6)^5 * ((4/3)^{-2+1})$
179199944	$(98 - 7 * 6) * ((5 * 4)^{(3+2)} - 1)$	204205122	$9 * 8 + (7 * 6)^5 * ((4/3)^{-2+1})$
179200056	$(-98 + 7 * 6) * ((5 * 4)^{(3+2)} - 1)$	204205148	$98 + (7 * 6)^5 * ((4/3)^{-2+1})$
179306469	$9 * ((8^7 / 6 * (54 + 3) - 2) - 1)$	205312500	$9 * 876 / (5^{\wedge}(-4 - 3) * (2 + 1))$
179306523	$9 * ((8^7 / 6 * (54 + 3) + 2) + 1)$	206962688	$-9 * -8^{\wedge}7 * (6 * 5 * 4 * ((4 * 3)^{-2 - 1}))$
179401698	$(-9 - ((8 + 7)^6 - 5) / -4) * 3 * 21$	207312552	$9 * (8 / 7 * ((-6^{\wedge}(5 + 4) + 3) * -2 + 1))$
179402076	$(-9 + ((8 + 7)^6 - 5) / 4 * 3) * 21$	207359013	$-987 + (6 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
179402256	$-9 + ((8 + 7)^6 - 5) / 4 * 3 * 21$	207359217	$-9 * 87 + (6 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
179402265	$9 * ((8 + 7)^6 - 5) / (4 * 3) * 21$	207359314	$-98 * 7 + (6 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
179402274	$9 + ((8 + 7)^6 - 5) / 4 * 3 * 21$	207359904	$(-9 - 87) + (6 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
179402454	$(9 - ((8 + 7)^6 - 5) / -4 * 3) * 21$	207359909	$(-98 + 7) + (6 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
179402832	$(9 + ((8 + 7)^6 - 5) / 4) * 3 * 21$	207359922	$9 - 87 + (6 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
181439993	$(-9 + 8) * 7 * ((6 * 5)^4 * -32 + 1)$	207360078	$(-9 + 87) + (6 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
182845440	$9 * (8 * 7 + 6) * 5 * 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1)$	207360091	$98 - 7 + (6 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
183606408	$9 * 8 / 7 * ((65^{\wedge}4 - 3) + 2 - 1)$	207360096	$9 + 87 + (6 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
183606432	$9 * 8 / 7 * (65^{\wedge}4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 + 1))$	207360105	$98 + 7 + (6 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
183722337	$9 / 8^{\wedge}(6 - 5 - 4) * (32 - 1)$	207360686	$98 * 7 + (6 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
184265981	$(-9 * (8 - 7 - 6))^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}(3 * (2 + 1))$	207360783	$9 * 87 + (6 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
184277871	$9 * ((8 * (7 + 6 + 5))^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 21$	207360987	$987 + (6 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
184469076	$9^{\wedge}((-8 + 7) + 6) * (5^{\wedge}(4 + 3 - 2) - 1)$	207415296	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 + 5) * (-4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2) + 1)$
184473503	$(98^{\wedge}(-7 + 6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3) * 2 - 1$	207525888	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 + 5 * (-4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2) + 1))$
184473504	$(98^{\wedge}(-7 + 6) + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3 * 2^{\wedge}1$	207612702	$(-9 + 8^{\wedge}7 / 6) * ((5^{\wedge}4 - 32) + 1)$
184473505	$(98^{\wedge}(-7 + 6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3) * 2 + 1$	207617792	$9 / 8^{\wedge} - 7 * (6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
184473759	$(98^{\wedge}(-7 + 6 + 5) + 4^{\wedge}3) * 2 - 1$	207618304	$9 / 8^{\wedge} - 7 * (6 + 5) + 4^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1)$
184473760	$(98^{\wedge}(-7 + 6) + 5) + 4^{\wedge}3 * 2^{\wedge}1$	207623394	$(9 + 8^{\wedge}7 / 6) * ((5^{\wedge}4 - 32) + 1)$
184473761	$(98^{\wedge}(-7 + 6 + 5) + 4^{\wedge}3) * 2 + 1$	207682389	$9 / 8 * ((7 * (-6^{\wedge}5 / 4 + 3))^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
184527100	$(9 * ((-8 + 7) + 6))^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) - 1$	207704796	$9 * ((-8 + 76)^{\wedge}5 + 4) / (3 * 21)$
184527102	$(9 * ((-8 + 7) + 6))^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) + 1$	207710208	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 + 5 * (4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2) + 1))$
184529148	$(9 * ((-8 + 7) + 6))^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) - 1$	207820800	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2) + 1)$
184529150	$(9 * ((-8 + 7) + 6))^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) + 1$	208273408	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 + 5 * ((4 * 3)^{-2 + 1}))$
184544624	$(-9 + 8^{\wedge}7 / 6) * ((5 * 4 + 3)^2 - 1)$	208968345	$9 / 8 * ((7 * (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 + 3))^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
184554128	$(9 + 8^{\wedge}7 / 6) * ((5 * 4 + 3)^2 - 1)$	210366016	$(98 * (-7 - 6 * 5) * 4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2 + 1)$
184587174	$9^{\wedge}((-8 - 7) + 6) * (5^{\wedge}(4 + 3 - 2) + 1)$	211376574	$(-9 + 8^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4))) * 321$
184730049	$((9 * 8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(5 + 4)) - 3) * 21$	211382352	$(9 + 8^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4))) * 321$
184730175	$(9 * 8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(5 + 4) + 3) * 21$	211631379	$(-9 * 8 + 7 * 6^{\wedge}(5 + 4)) * 3 - 21$
184790269	$(-9 * (8 - 7 - 6))^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}(3 * (2 + 1))$	211631421	$(-9 * 8 + 7 * 6^{\wedge}(5 + 4)) * 3 + 21$
186472368	$(9 * 876)^{\wedge}(-5 - (-4 - 3)) * (2 + 1)$	211631811	$(9 * 8 - 7 * 6^{\wedge}(5 + 4)) * 3 - 21$
188116964	$((9 * 8)^{\wedge}((-7 + 6) + 5) - 4) * (3 * 2 + 1)$	211631853	$(9 * 8 - 7 * 6^{\wedge}(5 + 4)) * 3 + 21$
188117020	$((9 * 8)^{\wedge}((-7 + 6) + 5) + 4) * (3 * 2 + 1)$	211943424	$-9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 + 5) / ((4 + 3)^{-2 - 1})$
188827929	$((9 - 8) * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4) * 321$	212517351	$9^{\wedge}((-8 + 7) + 6) * ((5 * 4 * 3)^2 - 1)$
189887147	$(-9 / (8 + 7 * (6 - 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3) + 2)))^{\wedge} - 1$	212635449	$9^{\wedge}((-8 + 7) + 6) * ((5 * 4 * 3)^2 + 1)$
189887149	$(9 / (8 - 7 * (6 - 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3))))^{\wedge}(-2 + 1)$	212701440	$((9^{\wedge}8 - 7) + 6) / ((5 / 4 + 3) / 21)$
189887153	$(9 / (((8 - 7) + 6) * 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3) + 2))^{\wedge} - 1$	213081264	$((9^{\wedge}8 - 7) + 6) * (5 + (-4 * (3 + 2)))^{\wedge} - 1$
190095750	$9 / 8 * ((7 * (-6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3)^2 - 1)$	213950832	$(9 + 8 / 7) * 6 * ((5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^2 - 1)$
190102016	$(9 - (-8 - 7) / -6)^{\wedge}5 / 4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1)$	215568864	$9 * 8 * 7 / 654^{\wedge}(-3 + 2) - 1$
191791152	$9^{\wedge}((-8 + 7) + 6) * ((54 + 3)^2 - 1)$	215580672	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 + 5 - (-4 / 3)^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$
191909250	$9^{\wedge}((-8 + 7) + 6) * ((54 + 3)^2 + 1)$	216909312	$(9 / (-8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3))))^{\wedge}(-2 + 1)$
194051875	$(9 + 8 / 7) * ((6 / (5 + 4)^{-3})^2 - 1)$	217013928	$(9 / (8 * ((7 * 6 + 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3) + 2)))^{\wedge} - 1$
195231744	$-9 * (8 * 7 * (6 + 5) * 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1))$	217385936	$((9^{\wedge}8 - 7) + 6) * (5 + (4 * (3 + 2)))^{\wedge} - 1$
195575391	$9 / 8^{\wedge}(6 - 5 - 4) * (32 + 1)$	217406112	$((9 - 8) * 7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (43^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
196171875	$9 * (-87 - 6) * 5^{\wedge}(4 + 3) * (-2 - 1)$	217659900	$((-9 + 8) * 7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 * (43^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
196515072	$(9 - 87) / (-6^{\wedge}(-5 - 4) * (3 + 2 - 1))$	217887121	$((-9^{\wedge}((-8 + 7) + 6) + 5) / 4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2 + 1)$
196607993	$(-9 + 8) * 7 + 6 / (5 / 4^{\wedge} - 3)^{\wedge}(-2 - 1)$	217975695	$((-9^{\wedge}((-8 + 7) + 6) + 5) / 4 - 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
196608007	$(9 - 8) * 7 + 6 / (5 / 4^{\wedge} - 3)^{\wedge}(-2 - 1)$	217975697	$((-9^{\wedge}((-8 + 7) + 6) + 5) / 4 - 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$
197537625	$9 / 8 * ((7 * (-6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3)^2 - 1)$	219702978	$((9 * 8 + 7^{\wedge}(6 + 5)) - 4) * 3^{\wedge}2 - 1$
198165744	$-9 * 8 * 7 * 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1))$	219726540	$9 * (8 + 7) / 6 * (5^{\wedge}(4 + 3 * 2) - 1)$
198195984	$9 * 8 * 7 * 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1))$	219726585	$9 * (-8 - 7) / 6 * (-5^{\wedge}(4 + 3 * 2) - 1)$
198639616	$(-9 - 8 * -76 * 5) * 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1)$	220312918	$98 * (-7 + 6 * (5 * 4 + 3))^{\wedge}(2 + 1)$
199148534	$-9 + (8 / (7 * 6)^{\wedge}(5 - 4 - 3))^2 - 1$	220591866	$((-9 + 8) / 7^{\wedge} - 6 * 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * (-2 - 1)$
199148536	$-9 + (8 / (7 * 6)^{\wedge}(5 - 4 - 3))^2 + 1$	220591884	$(-9 + 8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * (-2 - 1)$
199148554	$9 + (8 / (7 * 6)^{\wedge}(5 - 4 - 3))^2 + 1$	220686345	$(9 - 8) / 7 * ((6 * 5 + 4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2) - 1)$
199655424	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 + 5 + (-4 / 3)^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	223007904	$(9 - 8) * 7 * 6^{\wedge}5 * (4^{\wedge}(3 * 2) + 1)$
199819264	$(-9 - 8 * 76 * 5) * -4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1)$	224040600	$9 * 8 * ((7 * 6)^{\wedge}((5 - 4) + 3) - 21)$
200439504	$9 * 8 / 7 * (((6 + 5)^{\wedge}(4 + 3) + 2) + 1)$	224043624	$9 * 8 * ((7 * 6)^{\wedge}((5 - 4) + 3) + 21)$
202709227	$(-9 + 8) * 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + (4 * -3)^{\wedge}(2 + 1))$	226419200	$98 / (76 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(-3 - 2) - 1$
203246208	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 - (-5 / 4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2 + 1))$	228571425	$((-9 - 8) / 7 + 6) * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2) - 1)$
203657135	$(-9 + 8 / 7) * ((6 * 5)^4 * -32 + 1)$	230394456	$9 * -8 * (76 - ((5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2) - 1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
230394527	$9^* - 8^*(76 - (5^*4)^{(3+2)}) - 1$	241866048	$9^*8^*((-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3+21)$
230394529	$9^* - 8^*(76 - (5^*4)^{(3+2)}) + 1$	241866384	$9^*8^*((7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3+21)$
230394600	$9^* - 8^*(76 + (-5^*4)^{(3+2)}) - 1$	241885183	$(9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2) - 1$
230396967	$9^*(8^*(-7^*6+(5^*4)^{(3+2)})) - 1$	241885185	$(9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2) + 1$
230396985	$-9^*(8^*(7^*6+(5^*4)^{(3+2)})) - 1$	242100900	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(-5 - 4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
230399907	$9^*((-8^*(7/6 - (5^*4)^{(3+2)})) - 1)$	242218998	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(-5 - (4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1))$
230399925	$-9^*(8^*(7/6 - (5^*4)^{(3+2)})) - 1$	243135625	$((9^*8+7) - 6)^*5^{\wedge}(4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
230400075	$9^*(8^*(7/6 + (5^*4)^{(3+2)})) - 1$	243140623	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}(4^*3)+2)^* - 1$
230400093	$9^*(8^*(7/6 + (5^*4)^{(3+2)})) + 1$	243140627	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}(4^*3) - 2)^* - 1$
230403015	$9^*(8^*(7^*6 - (5^*4)^{(3+2)})) - 1$	243878479	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}(4^*3)+2)^* - 1$
230403033	$-9^*(8^*(-7^*6 - (5^*4)^{(3+2)})) - 1$	243878483	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}(4^*3) - 2)^* - 1$
230405400	$9^*8^*(76 - (5^*4)^{(3+2)}) - 1$	244093967	$(9^{\wedge}(-8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}(4^*3)+2)^* - 1$
230405544	$9^*8^*(76 - ((-5^*4)^{(3+2)})) - 1$	244093971	$(9^{\wedge}(-8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}(4^*3) - 2)^* - 1$
230660046	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4^*3^{\wedge}2 - 1$	244140379	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) + 5^{\wedge}(4^*3) - 2) - 1$
230660064	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4^*3^{\wedge}2 + 1$	244140380	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) + 5^{\wedge}(4^*3) - 2^{\wedge}1$
230736100	$(98^*(7 - 6^*(5+4)^*3))^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$	244140381	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) + 5^{\wedge}(4^*3)) - 2 + 1$
231650604	$(9^{\wedge}8 + (7^*6)^{\wedge}5)/(- 4^{\wedge}(-3+2) + 1)$	244140382	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) + 5^{\wedge}(4^*3)/(2 - 1)$
233279595	$-9^*(-8^*(-8+7)+6)^*((6^*5^*4)^{\wedge}3 - 2) - 1$	244140384	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) - (5^{\wedge}(4^*3) - 2)^* - 1$
233280405	$9^*(8+7)^*((6^*5^*4)^{\wedge}3 + 2) + 1$	244140385	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) + 5^{\wedge}(4^*3) + 2) + 1$
233963520	$(-9 - 8)^*7^*6^*5^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	244140659	$(9 - 8)^*7 + 6 + 5^{\wedge}(4^*3) + 21$
234149696	$9^{\wedge}8 + ((7 - 6) + 5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2) - 1$	244140865	$((9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) + 5^{\wedge}(4^*3)) - 2) - 1$
234136951	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(5^*(5^*4)^{\wedge}3/2+1)$	244140866	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) + 5^{\wedge}(4^*3) - 2^{\wedge}1$
236186496	$9^* - 8^*7^*6^*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+21)$	244140868	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) + 5^{\wedge}(4^*3)/(2 - 1)$
236196001	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)/(5^*(4^{\wedge}3+2) + 1)$	244140869	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) + 5^{\wedge}(4^*3) + 2 - 1$
236243448	$9^*8^*7^*(-6^*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2) - 1)$	244140870	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) + 5^{\wedge}(4^*3) + 2^{\wedge}1$
236243880	$9^*8^*(7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3) - 2) - 1)$	244140871	$(9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) + 5^{\wedge}(4^*3) + 2) + 1$
236244024	$9^*8^*(7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3) - 2) + 1)$	244258253	$((-9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}(-4^*3) - 21$
236244456	$9^*8^* - 7^*(6^*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2) - 1)$	244258295	$((-9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}(-4^*3) + 21$
236249784	$9^*8^*(7^*6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3) - (2+1))$	244760472	$-9 + (8/7^*654^{\wedge} - 3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
236249847	$9^*(-8^*(7^*6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2) - 1)$	244760490	$9 + (8/7^*654^{\wedge} - 3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
236249865	$-9^*(8^*(7^*6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2) - 1)$	244881183	$-9 + 8/7^*((-6 - 5)^{\wedge}4 - 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
236249928	$9^*8^*(7^*6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3) - (2 - 1))$	244881201	$9 + 8/7^*((6 + 5)^{\wedge}4 - 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
236249964	$9^*8^*(7^*6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3) - 2^{\wedge}1 - 1)$	247165833	$-9 + (8/(7^{\wedge}(6+5) - 4 - 3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
236250036	$9^*8^*(7^*6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3) + 2^{\wedge}1 - 1)$	247165851	$9 + (8/(7^{\wedge}(6+5) - 4 - 3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
236250072	$9^*8^*(7^*6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3) + 2 - 1)$	247670128	$9^*8^*7^* - 6 + (5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
236250135	$9^*(8^*(7^*6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2) - 1)$	247673137	$(-9/(8-7) - 6) + (5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
236250153	$-9^*(-8^*(7^*6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2) - 1)$	247676176	$9^*8^*7^*6 + (5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
236250216	$9^*8^*(7^*6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2+1)$	249599454	$(9 - 87)^*(6 - (5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
236255049	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3/2+1)$	249599610	$(-9+87)^*(-6 - (5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
236255544	$9^*8^*7^*(6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2) - 1)$	249600390	$(9 - 87)^*(-6 + (5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
236255976	$9^*8^*(7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2) - 1)$	254541824	$((-9+8-7)^* - 6)^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1))$
236256120	$9^*8^*(7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2) + 1)$	254855484	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5+4321)$
236256552	$9^*8^* - 7^*(-6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2) - 1)$	255066112	$((-9+8-7)^* - 6)^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1))$
236313504	$9^*8^*7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)+21)$	255445974	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5+4321)$
236924991	$-9 - (8+7)^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}(-4+3) - 21)$	256048121	$((9^*8^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4) - 3)^*2 - 1$
236925009	$9 - (8+7)^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}(-4+3) - 21)$	256048122	$((9^*8^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4) - 3)^*2^*1$
237961216	$(-9 - 8^* - 7^*65)^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	256048123	$((9^*8^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4) - 3)^*2 + 1$
238085631	$9/8^*(-7 - (-6^{\wedge}(5+4) - 3)^*21)$	256048133	$((9^*8^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4) - 3)^*2 - 1$
239140864	$(-9 - 8^*7^*65)^* - 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	256048134	$((9^*8^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4) - 3)^*2^*1$
240110407	$(-9^{\wedge}((8-7)^*6) - (-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	256048135	$((9^*8^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4) - 3)^*2 + 1$
240638824	$9^*8^*7^* - 6 - (-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	257187500	$9876/(5^{\wedge}(-4-3)^*(2+1))$
240641806	$(-9+8)^*7^*6 + (5^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	260007753	$(-9+8)^*7 - (-7 + (6^*5)^{\wedge}4)^* - 321$
240641833	$(-9^*(8-7) - 6) + (5^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	260010007	$(9-8)^*7 + (6^*5)^{\wedge}4^*321$
240641890	$(-9+8)^*7^* - 6 + (5^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	260702208	$9^*8^{\wedge}7^*(6+5^*(4/3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
240644872	$9^*8^*7^*6 - (-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	261994188	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7)^*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4+3+2)+1)$
240759497	$((9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6 + (5^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	262902847	$(-9-8/7)^*((6^*5)^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$
241481241	$-9 + (8+7)^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}(-4+3)+21)$	263232347	$(9/-8+76)^*((5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
241481259	$9 + (8+7)^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}(-4+3)+21)$	266827932	$98^*(7^*6)^{\wedge}5/(4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
241510410	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(5 - 4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$	267187424	$(9-8)^*76^*((5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
241628508	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(-5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$	267257104	$((-9+8^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5))^*4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2 + 1)$
241844223	$(-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)+5)^* - 4^{\wedge}(3^*2) - 1$	267964634	$98^* - 7^*(6 - 5^{\wedge}(4 - ((-3 - 2) + 1)))$
241844225	$(-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)+5)^* - 4^{\wedge}(3^*2) + 1$	267972866	$98^*7^*(6 + 5^{\wedge}(4 - ((-3 - 2) + 1)))$
241863024	$9^*8^*((-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3 - 21)$	268062048	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}(4^*(3+2))^* - 1$
241863360	$9^*8^*((7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3 - 21)$	268738520	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5) - 4)^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
241863984	$9^*8^*((-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3 - 2) - 1$	268738600	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5) + 4)^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
241864173	$9^*((-8^*(7 - 6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3) - 2) - 1)$	268799928	$9^*8^*(7/6^*(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
241864227	$9^*((-8^*(7 - 6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3) + 2) + 1)$	268800072	$9^*8^*(7/6^*(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2) + 1)$
241864320	$9^*8^*((-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3 - 2 - 1)$	269616400	$((-9 - 8^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5))^*4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2 + 1)$
241865088	$9^*8^*((7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3 + 2 + 1)$	269725596	$98^*7^* - 6^*(5 - 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 - 1))$
241865181	$9^*((8^*(7+6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3) - 2) - 1)$	269766756	$98^*7^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2 - 1))$
241865235	$9^*((8^*(7+6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3) + 2) + 1)$	271142501	$(9/8+76)^*((5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
241865424	$9^*8^*((7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3 + 2) + 1$	271180945	$(9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*((5+43)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
272097207	$-9*(8*7+(-6^{(5+4)+3})^{(2+1)})$	322828535	$(98*7)^{(-6-(-5-4))}-321$
272098377	$9*(8*7+(6^{(5+4)+3})^{(2+1)})$	322828793	$(98*7)^{(-6+5+4)+3^*-21}$
272109375	$(9*(8+7)^{-6}/(5*43))^{(-2+1)}$	322828829	$(98*7)^{(-6-(-5-4))}-3^{(2+1)}$
273088512	$-9*(-8-7*65)^4(3^{(2-1)})$	322828852	$(98*7)^{(-6-(-5-4))}-3-(-2-1)$
273559071	$((-9-8)^{7+65})^4/(-3^2)-1$	322828860	$(98*7)^{(-6-(-5-4))+3+2-1}$
273559073	$((-9-8)^{7+65})^4/(-3^2)+1$	322828883	$(98*7)^{(-6-(-5-4))+3^{(2+1)}}$
273559095	$((9+8)^{7/6-5})^4-3^{(-2+1)}$	322828919	$(98*7)^{(-6+5+4)-3^*-21}$
273559135	$((9+8)^{7/6+5})^4-3^{(-2+1)}$	322829177	$(98*7)^{(-6-(-5-4))+321}$
274658292	$9/8*((76+5^{(4*3)+2})+1)$	323401340	$9+(-8*7)^{6-5^{(4*3-(-2-1))}}$
275894444	$(-9+8)*(7-(654-3)^{(2+1)})$	323414238	$-987*(6-5*4^{(3^{(2-1))})}$
276710415	$(98^{(-7+6+5)-4})^3-21$	323426082	$987*(6-5^*-4^{(3^{(2-1))})}$
276710433	$(98^{(-7+6+5)-4})^3-2-1$	324615200	$98/(7*65*4)^{(-3+2)-1}$
276710434	$(98^{(-7+6+5)-4})^3-2*1$	325129504	$98*(7^{6+5}*(5*4)^{(3+2)-1})$
276710435	$(98^{(-7+6+5)-4})^3-2+1$	325129700	$-98*(-7^{6+5}*(5^*-4)^{(3+2)-1})$
276710461	$(98^{(-7+6+5)+4})^3+2-1$	325771866	$-9+(8+7)^{6/5*((4*3)^{2-1})}$
276710462	$(98^{(-7+6+5)+4})^3+2*1$	325771884	$9+(8+7)^{6/5*((4*3)^{2-1})}$
276710463	$(98^{(-7+6+5)+4})^3+2+1$	326181513	$9/(8+7)*(((6^{5+4})^3)^{2-1})$
276710481	$(98^{(-7+6+5)+4})^3+21$	329148288	$(-9-8)*(7*6)^{5*-4*3^{(-2-1)}}$
281725048	$(-9/(8-76^{5-4^3}))^{(-2+1)}$	332074706	$(9^{(87/6-5)+4})/(3+2^{(-1)})$
282475168	$-9*((8-(7^{(-6-(-5+4))})^3)^{(-2+1)})+1$	332563959	$9/(-8+7)+6^{(5+4)}*(32+1)$
282475330	$9*((8+(7^{(-6-(-5+4))})^3)^{(-2+1)})+1$	333811169	$(9+8)^{7-6*(5^{(4-3-2)})}^{(-1)}$
284830728	$(9-8)*7/6*(5^{(4*3)}-(-2-1))$	335999475	$(98+7)*(-6-(5^*-4)^{(3+2)+1})$
285212637	$(9+8)*(((7+6)+5)^{(4*3)-2})-1$	336000525	$(-98-7)*(-6+(5^*-4)^{(3+2)+1})$
285212639	$(9+8)*(((7+6)+5)^{(4*3)-2})+1$	336000735	$(98+7)*6+(5*4)^{(3+2)+1}$
285212651	$(9+8)*((-7+6)+5)^{(4*3)-21}$	339443776	$(98*(7*6+5)^4)^{(3-2)+1}$
285212693	$(9+8)*((-7+6)+5)^{(4*3)+21}$	342018495	$(9+8)^{((-7+6)+5)*4^{(3*2)-1}}$
285383817	$9^{8*7-6/(-5*4)+3)^{(-2+1)}}$	342185537	$(9+8)^{((-7+6)+5)*4^{(3*2)+1}}$
290816000	$(9-8^{(-7+6)})*(5/4^{(-3)^{(2+1)}}$	342854532	$(9*8-7^6)/-54^{(-3+2)-1}$
291199363	$(-98+7)^*(6-(5*4)^{(3+2)+1})$	342884352	$9*8^{7*6}*(6^{(-5+4)}-(-3-21))$
291199545	$(98-7)*(-6-(5^*-4)^{(3+2)+1})$	343274436	$(9*8+7^6)/54^{(-3+2)-1}$
291200455	$(-98+7)*(-6+(5^*-4)^{(3+2)+1})$	343453824	$9*(8^7-6^{(-5+4*3)})^*21$
291200637	$(98-7)^*(6+(5*4)^{(3+2)+1})$	344196621	$9^{8*7+6-(-5+4)}^{(-3-2)+1}$
293945922	$9^{8*7-6/5*4-3)^{(-2-1)}}$	344255679	$9/8*(7^6*(54-3)^{2-1})$
298593750	$98*(-7-6)^*5^{-4}*(4+3)^*(2+1)$	344550915	$9^{8*7}*((7-(6-(5+4))^{(-3-2))}+1)$
299008000	$(9+8^{(-7+6)})*(5/4^{(-3)^{(2+1)}}$	347253480	$9/8*((7-(6*5-4)^3)^{2-1})$
299140047	$9^{8*7-6/(-5*4)+3)^{(-2-1)}}$	347807124	$9/8*((7+(6+5*4)^3)^{2-1})$
299428416	$9/(8-76^{(-5+4)+3})^{(-2+1)}$	349360128	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)/(4+3^2)^{-1}}$
302070496	$-98*(7^{6-5}*(4)^{(3+2)-1})$	349360129	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)*4^{(3+2)+1}}$
303514047	$9^{8*7+6/(-5*4)+3)^{(-2-1)}}$	353046591	$-9+8/7*((6+5*4)^{(3*2)-1})$
305854677	$9*-87*(6-5^{(4-(-3-2)+1)})$	353046609	$9+8/7*((6+5*4)^{(3*2)-1})$
305864073	$9*87*(6+5^{(4-(-3-2)+1)})$	353939706	$9^{8/((7/6+5)^*(4/3))^{(-2+1)}}$
306122698	$(9-8)*7^6*(54-3)^{(2+1)}$	354599490	$(9/-8+7)*((-6^{(5+4+3)})^{2-1})$
306500961	$9/87*((6^5*(4+3))^{2-1})$	355770567	$-9*(8*7^{(6+5-4)}-3*2+1)$
307199328	$(-9-87)^*(6-(5*4)^{(3+2)+1})$	355770585	$9*(8*7^{(6+5-4)}*3*2+1)$
307199520	$(9+87)^*(6-(5^*-4)^{(3+2)+1})$	355878642	$(9/-8+7)*((6^{(5+4+3)})^{2-1})$
307200480	$(-9-87)^*(6+(5^*-4)^{(3+2)+1})$	358585632	$9*8*-76*(5-4^{(3^{(2-1))})}$
307200672	$(9+87)^*(6+(5*4)^{(3+2)+1})$	358640352	$9*8*76*(5+4^{(3^{(2-1))})}$
307529973	$9*((((8+7)^{6-5^4})^3-2)-1)$	359437824	$9^{(-8+7)/6^{(-5-4)}*321}$
307530027	$9*((((8+7)^{6-5^4})^3+2)+1)$	362442762	$(9-(8+7))^{(6+5)*4^{(-3-2)-1}}$
307563723	$9*((((8+7)^{6+5^4})^3-2)-1)$	362796372	$9*-8*(7+(-6^{(5+4)+3})/2+1)$
307563777	$9*((((8+7)^{6+5^4})^3+2)+1)$	362796588	$9*-8*(7-(6^{(5+4)+3})/2+1)$
307864638	$9*87*-6*(5-4^{(3^{(2-1))})}$	362796840	$9*-8*((7-6^{(5+4)-3})/2+1)$
307911618	$9*87*6*(5+4^{(3^{(2-1))})}$	362797272	$9*8*((7+6^{(5+4)-3})/2+1)$
308708172	$9^{8*7-6/(-5*4+3)^{(-2-1)}}$	362797740	$9*8*(7+(6^{(5+4)+3})/2+1)$
310361544	$((9*8+7)-6)/(54*3)^{(-2-1)}$	363031000	$(-9*8+(7*6)^5)*((4/3)^{2+1})$
312408567	$9/(-8+7)+6^{(5+4)}*(32-1)$	363031102	$-98+(7*6)^5*((4/3)^{2+1})$
313895025	$-9*(8-(7/(6+5^{(4*3)}))^{(-2+1)})$	363031128	$-9*8+(7*6)^5*((4/3)^{2+1})$
313895169	$9*(8+(7/(6+5^{(4*3)}))^{(-2+1)})$	363031200	$(9-8)*(7*6)^5*((4/3)^{2+1})$
317657412	$9*(((-8-7)^*(6+5))^{4+3})/21$	363031272	$9*8+(7*6)^5*((4/3)^{2+1})$
318047944	$(-9-8)+7*((6*5+4)^{(3+2)-1})$	363031298	$98+(7*6)^5*((4/3)^{2+1})$
318047992	$9+8+7*((6*5+4)^{(3+2)+1})$	363031400	$(9*8-(-7*6)^5)*((4/3)^{2+1})$
318049639	$((98-(7-6))^{5-4})^3-2-1$	363151350	$(9-(8+7))^{(6+5)*(-4^{(-3-2)-1})}$
321550152	$98*7*6*(5^{(4+3)}-2-1)$	363893776	$(9^{((-8+7)+6)-5^{(4+3)}})^{2/1}$
321553582	$98*7*(-6*(-5^{(4+3)+2})-1)$	364903143	$(-9+8^{7*6/5})*((4*3)^{2+1})$
321554954	$98*7*(6*(5^{(4+3)}-2)+1)$	364905753	$(9+8^{7*6/5})*((4*3)^{2+1})$
321558384	$98*7*6*(5^{(4+3)}-2+1)$	367017156	$9*87*6*(5^{(4+3)}-2-1)$
321561814	$98*-7*(-6*5^{(4+3)+2}-1)$	367021071	$9*87*(-6*(-5^{(4+3)+2})-1)$
321563186	$98*7*(6*5^{(4+3)+2}-1)$	367022637	$9*87*(6*(5^{(4+3)}-2)+1)$
321566616	$98*7*-6*(-5^{(4+3)}-2+1)$	367026552	$9*87*6*(5^{(4+3)}-2+1)$
321570046	$98*7*(6*(5^{(4+3)+2})-1)$	367030467	$9*-87*(-6*5^{(4+3)+2}-1)$
321571418	$98*7*(6*(5^{(4+3)+2})+1)$	367032033	$9*87*(6*5^{(4+3)+2}-1)$
321574848	$98*7*-6*(-5^{(4+3)}-2-1)$	367035948	$9*87*-6*(-5^{(4+3)}-2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
367039863	$9*87*(6*(5^(4+3)+2)-1)$	420277054	$((9+8)^7+6)+(5*43)^(2+1)$
367041429	$9*87*(6*(5^(4+3)+2)+1)$	421142535	$(9/8+7*6)*(5^(4+3)^2-1)$
367045344	$9*87*-6*(-5^(4+3)-2-1)$	421957865	$(9-8)*7*((6^5-4*3)^2-1)$
369096007	$(9-8)*7+(65*4)^3*21$	422501520	$(-9+8)*-7*((-6^5+4+3)^2-1)$
372506624	$98*(-7+65)*4^(3^2-1)$	422827888	$(9-8)*7*(-6^5+4)^(3-(2-1))$
374857137	$((9-8)/-7+6)*((5*4)^(3*2)-1)$	423154368	$(9-8)*7*((-6^5+4-3)^2-1)$
374863116	$9*-8-(((7-6)*5)^(4+3))*-21$	423263190	$98/7*(6^(5+4)*3-2-1)$
375390208	$9*8^7*(6+5*((4/3)^(2+1)))$	423263218	$98/7*(6^(5+4)*3-2+1)$
375633389	$(-9+8+76^5*4)*3^4(-2-1)$	423263246	$98/-7*(6^(5+4)*-3-2+1)$
382359250	$(9-8)*7^6*((5+4+3)^2+1)$	423263274	$98/-7*(6^(5+4)*-3-2-1)$
383999997	$9/(-8+7)+6*((5*4)^(3*2)+1)$	423372096	$(9-8)*7*((6^5+4-3)^2-1)$
384000003	$9^4(8-7)+6*((5*4)^(3*2)-1)$	423698800	$(9-8)*7*(6^5+4)^(3-(2-1))$
385875968	$9*8^7*(6+5*(4-3^2-2-1))$	424025616	$(9-8)*7*((6^5+4+3)^2-1)$
390200888	$(-9/(8-(76*5*4)^3))^4(-2+1)$	424570601	$(9-8)*7*((6^5+4+3)^2-1)$
390483072	$(9*8^7-6^4(-5+4^3))^*21$	427483584	$9*8*76*(5^(4+3)-2-1)$
392073567	$((-9+8)*7*6)^5+43)^*(-2-1)$	427488984	$9*8*(-76*(-5^4(4+3)+2)-1)$
393142851	$((9-8)/7+6)*((5*4)^(3*2)-1)$	427489128	$9*8*(76*(5^4(4+3)-2)+1)$
396809279	$(9*8*7*6^4(5+4)*3+2)-1$	427494528	$9*8*76*(5^4(4+3)-2+1)$
396809281	$9/8*7*6^4(5+4)*3+2+1$	427505472	$9*8*-76*(-5^4(4+3)-2+1)$
398131200	$((9-8+7)*6)^5*(4/3)^(2+1)$	427510872	$9*8*(76*(5^4(4+3)+2)-1)$
399169881	$(-9/8+7*6)*(5^4(4+3)^2-1)$	427511016	$9*8*(76*(5^4(4+3)+2)+1)$
400400292	$(9+8)^7-6-(5*43)^(2+1)$	427516416	$9*8*-76*(5^4(4+3)-2-1)$
402240384	$(9*8^7+6^4(-5+4^3))^*21$	427830024	$(9+8^7/6)*(5*(4+3))^2-1$
405555704	$(9+8)^7-6/(54)^(3^2-1)$	427957320	$(9-8)*7*((6^5+43)^2-1)$
406087139	$(9+8)^7-6-(54*3)^(2+1)$	429839592	$(-9^4(8+7-6)+5^4(4*3))^*(-2-1)$
406087151	$((9+8)^7+6)-(54*3)^(2+1)$	430021800	$9/8*(7^6*(5+4+3)^2-1)$
406265625	$(9*(8+7)^6)^(5+4)*321$	430259193	$(9-8)*7*((6^5+4^3)^2-1)$
406559520	$-9*(8-7*6)^5+4^4(3*(2+1))$	439453041	$-9*(8*7/6-5^4(4+3^2+1))$
406847488	$9*8^7*(6+5*(4-(3^2-2+1)))$	439453209	$9*(8*7/6+5^4(4+3^2+1))$
408656672	$-9*(8-7*6)^4(5-4^4(3*(2+1)))$	446496768	$9*(-8+765)*4^4(3^2-1)$
408771360	$-9*((8+7*-6)^5+4^4(3^2+1))$	447328259	$(9-8)*7*((6+(-5*4)^3)^2+1)$
409066272	$-9*((8+7*-6)^5-4^4(3^2+1))$	448000035	$(9-8)*-7*((-6-((5*4)^(3*2)-1))$
409180960	$-9*(8-7*6)^5+4^4(3*(2+1))$	448672259	$(9-8)*7*((6-(-5*4)^3)^2+1)$
409220007	$(9*8^7-6+5)^(4+3)*-21$	448790528	$(9*8^7-7/6)^(5+4)*321$
409241175	$(9*8*7+(6+5)^(4+3))^*21$	449269632	$-9*(-8^7-6^4(-5+4^3))^*21$
409418520	$(9-8)*7^6*((5-4^3)^2-1)$	451215288	$-9*(8-765*4^4(3^2-1))$
410156292	$(-9+8)*-7*6*(5^4(4+3^2)+1)$	451215432	$9*(8-765*-4^4(3^2-1))$
410233697	$(9+8)^7-6*(54)^(3-2+1)$	451635488	$((98/7)^6-54^4(3+2))^*-1$
410271073	$(9+8)^7-6*(54)^(3-2+1)$	452874240	$9*8^7*6*(5-(4^4(-3-2)+1))$
410279623	$(9+8)^7-6/(54)^(3-2)-1$	453095424	$9*8^7*6*(5-(-4^4(-3-2)+1))$
410279625	$(9+8)^7-6/(54)^(3-2)+1$	455933952	$-9*(-8-765)*4^4(3^2-1)$
410331317	$(9+8)^7-6*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$	455999488	$-98*((-76+5)*4^4(3^2-1))$
410334323	$(9+8)^7+6*-5*((4*3)^2+1)$	458633583	$((9/(8-7))^6-54^4(3+2))^*-1$
410336880	$(9+8)^7-65-(4^3)^(2+1)$	458902880	$((9-8+7)^6-54^4(3+2))/-1$
410337010	$((9+8)^7+65)-(4^3)^(2+1)$	460728189	$9/8*(7^6*(5-4^3)^2-1)$
410340336	$(9+8)^7-65+(4^3)^(2+1)$	461184099	$(98^4(-7-(-6-5))+4)^*(3+2)-1$
410340466	$((9+8)^7+65)+(4^3)^(2+1)$	461184101	$(98^4(-7-(-6-5))+4)^*(3+2)+1$
410343023	$(9+8)^7+6*5*((4^3)^2+1)$	463495284	$(9*8^7*6)^(5+4+3)*21$
410346029	$(9+8)^7+6*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$	464413824	$(9*8+7)/6^4(5-4^3)^*21$
410397721	$(9+8)^7+(6/54)^(3-2)-1$	470919393	$9/8*7*((-6^5+4+3)^2-1)$
410397723	$(9+8)^7+(6/54)^(3-2)+1$	471151971	$9^4((-8+7)+6)*((5*4)^3-21)$
410406273	$(9+8)^7+(65*4)^(3-2)+1$	472391997	$9^4((-8+7)+6)/(5*4)^(3-2)-1$
410443649	$(9+8)^7+(65*4)^(3-2)+1$	472391999	$9^4((-8+7)+6)/(5*4)^(3-2)+1$
411278112	$-9*((8-7*6)^5-4^4(-3*(-2-1)))$	472392001	$9^4((-8+7)+6)/(5*4)^(3+2)-1$
411278400	$((-9+87)*65*4)^(3-2)+1$	473632029	$9^4((-8+7)+6)*((5*4)^3+21)$
412090368	$9*8^7*((6/5)^(4+3)+21)$	474360633	$-9*(8-7*((6-5*4)^(3*2)-1))$
413208144	$((-9-8)^7+6*5)/((4*3)^(2-1))$	474360903	$9*(8+7*((6-5*4)^(3*2)+1))$
414590195	$(9+8)^7-6+(54*3)^(2+1)$	474552007	$(9-8)*7+(65*4^3)^2+1$
414590207	$((9+8)^7+6)+(54*3)^(2+1)$	474609303	$-9*(8+(7*6*(-5-4)+3)^(2+1))$
415065456	$9*8*(7^4((6-5)+4)+3)-2-1$	474609447	$9*(8-(7*6*(-5-4)+3)^(2+1))$
415065645	$9*((8*7^4(6-5+4+3)-2)-1)$	475004928	$9*8^7*(6+5*(4-(3*2)^(2-1)))$
415065699	$9*(8*7^4(6-5+4+3)+2)+1$	475314210	$9/8*7*((-6^5+4+3)^2-1)$
415065888	$9*8*(7^4((6-5)+4)+3)-(-2-1)$	475314219	$9/8*(7*(-6^5+4+3)^2+1)$
415121642	$(9+8)^7+(6/54)^(3^2-1)$	475410936	$-9*(8-76^5/((4+3)^2-1))$
415409583	$-9+((-8+76)^5+4)/(3+2^2-1)$	475411080	$9*(8+76^5/((4+3)^2-1))$
415409601	$9+((-8+76)^5+4)/(3+2^2-1)$	476048664	$9/8*7*((-6^5+4-3)^2-1)$
416324601	$(9-8)*7*((6^5-4^3)^2-1)$	476048673	$9/8*(7*((6^5-4)+3)^2+1)$
417463634	$-98*(7-65*4^4(3^2-1))$	476170920	$9*8*((7*6*5^4)^3-2)-1$
417464320	$98*(-7-6)*5*-4^4(3^2-1)$	476171352	$9*8*((7*6*5^4)^3+1)$
417465006	$98*(7-65*-4^4(3^2-1))$	476293608	$9/8*7*((6^5+4-3)^2-1)$
418595016	$(9-8)*7*((6^5-43)^2-1)$	476293617	$9/8*(7*((6^5+4)-3)^2+1)$
420277042	$(9+8)^7-6+(5*43)^(2+1)$	477028818	$9/8*7*((6^5+4+3)^2-1)$

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477028827	$9/8 * (7 * (6^5 + 4 + 3)^2 + 1)$	545908005	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6) * 5/43^{\wedge}-2^{\wedge}1$
478416168	$9 * 8 * (((7 * 6 + 5)^4)^3 - 2) - 1)$	545967054	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6) * (5 * 43^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
478416600	$9 * 8 * (((7 * 6 + 5)^4)^3 + 2) + 1)$	546203250	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6) * 5 * (43^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
481451985	$9/8 * 7 * ((6^5 + 43)^2 - 1)$	546858224	$(9 * ((8 + 7 + 6^{\wedge}5) + 4) / 3)^2 - 1$
482461546	$98 / (7 + 6) * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2) + 1)$	546858226	$(9 * ((8 + 7 + 6^{\wedge}5) + 4) / 3)^2 + 1$
483728832	$9 * -8 * (7 - 6^{\wedge}(5 + 4) / 3 * 2 - 1)$	547246080	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2)) - 1)$
483728976	$9 * -8 * (7 + 6^{\wedge}(5 + 4) / -3 * 2 - 1)$	547467264	$9 * -8^{\wedge}7 * (-6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2)) + 1)$
483729840	$9 * 8 * (7 - 6^{\wedge}(5 + 4) / -3 * 2 - 1)$	549316410	$9/8 * ((7/6 + 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3))^2 + 1)$
483729984	$9 * 8 * (7 - 6^{\wedge}(5 + 4) / -3 * 2 - 1)$	549453824	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * 6 * (5 - 4 * 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$
486866177	$(9 + 8)^{\wedge}7 + (6 * 54^{\wedge}(-3 - 2))^{\wedge}-1$	550998016	$((9/8 - 7) + 6) * (5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * (2 - 1))$
490403550	$(9/8 + 7) * ((-6^{\wedge}5 + 4 + 3)^2 - 1)$	553849156	$((9 - 8 + 7^{\wedge}6) / 5 + 4)^{\wedge}((3 - 2) + 1)$
490733763	$9 * ((8^{\wedge}7 * 6 + 5) * (4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 + 1)))$	558268416	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 * 5 - (4/3)^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$
492172590	$(9/8 + 7) * ((6^{\wedge}5 + 4 + 3)^2 - 1)$	559600812	$9/8 * (7 + 6 - (5 + 4)^{\wedge}(-3 - 2 + 1))$
503312880	$(-9 + 8^{\wedge}7 - 6) * 5 * ((4 + 3)^2 - 1)$	559609560	$9/8 * (7 + 6 + ((5 + 4) * 3)^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$
503315031	$-9 - (-8^{\wedge}7 + 6) * 5 * ((4 + 3)^2 - 1)$	559613934	$9/8 * (7 + 6 + (5 + 4)^{\wedge}(-3 - 2 + 1))$
503315049	$9 - (-8^{\wedge}7 + 6) * 5 * ((4 + 3)^2 - 1)$	560003885	$(-9/8 + 7^{\wedge}6) * ((5 + 4^{\wedge}3)^2 - 1)$
503315760	$(9 - 8^{\wedge}7 - 6) * -5 * ((4 + 3)^2 - 1)$	560009240	$(9 - 8) * 7^{\wedge}6 * ((5 + 4^{\wedge}3)^2 - 1)$
503317200	$(9 + 8^{\wedge}7 - 6) * 5 * ((4 + 3)^2 - 1)$	560014595	$(9/8 + 7^{\wedge}6) * ((5 + 4^{\wedge}3)^2 - 1)$
503317911	$-9 - (-8^{\wedge}7 - 6) * 5 * ((4 + 3)^2 - 1)$	563809515	$(9 + 8 / (-7 * 6)) * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2) - 1)$
503317929	$9 - (-8^{\wedge}7 - 6) * 5 * ((4 + 3)^2 - 1)$	564349632	$((9 * 8)^{\wedge}((-7 + 6) + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3) * 21$
503320080	$(9 - (-8^{\wedge}7 - 6)) * 5 * ((4 + 3)^2 - 1)$	564350829	$((9 * 8)^{\wedge}(-7 - (-6 - 5)) - 4) - 3) * 21$
507354624	$9 * (8 * 7)^{\wedge}((-6 + 5) + 4) * 321$	564350948	$(9 * 8)^{\wedge}(-7 - (-6 - 5)) - 4) - 3) * 21$
508382934	$((9 - 8) * 7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4321$	564351004	$((9 * 8)^{\wedge}(-7 - (-6 - 5)) + 4/3) * 21$
508690432	$(98/7 - 6^{\wedge}5) * -4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1)$	564352320	$((9 * 8)^{\wedge}((-7 + 6) + 5) + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21$
509149184	$((-9 + 8) * 7 + 6^{\wedge}5) * 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1)$	565051392	$9/8^{\wedge}-7 * (6 * 5 - 4^{\wedge}(-3 - (-2 + 1)))$
509607817	$((-9 + 8) * 7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * -4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1))$	565289073	$-9/8 * ((7 - (6 + 5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3 * 2) - 1)$
509607929	$((9 - 8) * -7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * -4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1))$	565678080	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * 6 * 5 * (-4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2) + 1)$
509607943	$((9 - 8) * 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1))$	565788672	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2 + 1))$
509608055	$((9 + 8) * 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 * 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1))$	566120439	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2)) - 1)$
510066688	$((-9 + 8) * -7 + 6^{\wedge}5) * 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1)$	566120457	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2)) + 1)$
510525440	$(98/7 + 6^{\wedge}5) * 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1)$	566157312	$9/8^{\wedge}-7 * (6 * 5 - 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2 + 1))$
510603264	$(9 * 8)^{\wedge}((-7 + 6) + 5) * (4 * (3 + 2) - 1)$	566304768	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2 + 1))$
513022499	$((98 * 7 * (6 + 5) + 4) * 3)^2 - 1$	566328360	$(9 * -8 + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5) * (4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 + 1))$
513022500	$((98 * 7 * (6 + 5) + 4) * 3)^2 + 1$	566328984	$(9 * 8 - (-7 * 6)^{\wedge}5) * (4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 + 1))$
513022501	$((98 * 7 * (6 + 5) + 4) * 3)^2 + 1$	566341623	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2)) - 1)$
513736704	$-9 * (-876 + 5) * 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1)$	566341641	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2)) + 1)$
516428298	$-9/8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 54^{\wedge}(3 + 2) - 1)$	566406250	$(9 / (87 * 6)) * 5^{\wedge}(-4 - 3 * 2)^{\wedge}-1$
516693006	$9/8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 54^{\wedge}(3 + 2) - 1)$	566673408	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2 + 1))$
517924414	$-98 + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	566784000	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * 6 * 5 * (4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2) + 1)$
517924440	$9 * -8 + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	567410688	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(-3 - (-2 + 1)))$
517924495	$(-9 - 8) + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	569263149	$(9 - 8/76) * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2) - 1)$
517924511	$(-9 + 8) + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	574193664	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 * 5 + (4/3)^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$
517924512	$(-9 + 8) * (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (-4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	576239991	$-9 - 8 * (7 * 6 * 5)^{\wedge}4 * -3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1)$
517924513	$9 - 8 + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	576240009	$9 - 8 * (7 * 6 * 5)^{\wedge}4 * -3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1)$
517924529	$9 + 8 + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	577787903	$(9 * 8)^{\wedge}((-7 + 6) + 5) * 43/2 - 1$
517924584	$9 * 8 + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	577787904	$(9 * 8)^{\wedge}((-7 + 6) + 5) * 43/2 + 1$
517924610	$98 + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	577787905	$(9 * 8)^{\wedge}((-7 + 6) + 5) * 43/2 + 1$
519634944	$-9 * (-876 - 5) * 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1)$	582665076	$9/8 * (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$
520224768	$-98 * (-76 - 5) * 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1)$	582736833	$(9 + 8/76) * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2) - 1)$
526848000	$(9 * ((8 + 76) * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(-2 + 1)$	584994816	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2)) + 1)$
527605246	$-98 + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	585216000	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2)) + 1)$
527605272	$9 * -8 + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	585640000	$((-98 + 76) * 5)^{\wedge}4 * (3 + 2 - 1)$
527605327	$(-9 - 8) + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	585874591	$(9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 * 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1)$
527605343	$(-9 + 8) + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	588190467	$(9 + 8 / (7 * 6)) * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2) - 1)$
527605344	$((-9 + 8) * 7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (-4 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	591224832	$(9 * 8)^{\wedge}((-7 + 6) + 5) * (43 - 21)$
527605345	$9 - 8 + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	591847686	$-9/8 + (-7 + 6^{\wedge}5 + 4) * 3 * 21$
527605361	$9 + 8 + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	591848568	$-9/8 - (-7 - 6^{\wedge}5 + 4) * 3 * 21$
527605416	$9 * 8 + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	592399980	$9/8 + (-7 * (6 * 5 - 4 + 3))^{\wedge}(2 + 1)$
527605442	$98 + (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	593556012	$9/8 * (7 * 6)^{\wedge}5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$
533387430	$(9 * 87)^{\wedge}((-6 + 5) + 4) * (3^{\wedge}2 - 2 + 1)$	595230660	$-9/8 + (7 * (6 * 5 * 4 + 3))^{\wedge}(2 + 1)$
533647476	$-9/8 * ((7 + (6 - 5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3 * 2) - 1)$	595591168	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * (6 * 5 * (4 - (-3^{\wedge}2 - 1)))$
533655855	$-9 * (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) / -3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	597333315	$-9 + 8 * 7 / 6 * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2) - 1)$
533655873	$9 * (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) / 3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	597333333	$9 + 8 * 7 / 6 * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2) - 1)$
536615393	$(9 - 8 / (7 + 6)) * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2) + 1)$	600182784	$(9 * 8)^{\wedge}(-7 - (-6 - 5)) * (4/3 + 21)$
538206228	$9 * (((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 - 3) * 21$	600585876	$9 * (8 - 7/6) * (5^{\wedge}(4 + 3 * 2) - 1)$
538206732	$9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 - 3) * 21$	600585999	$9 * (8 - 7/6) * (5^{\wedge}(4 + 3 * 2) + 1)$
538206858	$9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 + 3) * 21$	601406355	$(9 * 8 - 7^{\wedge}6) * 5 * (-4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) + 1)$
538207362	$9 * (((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 + 3) * 21$	602142915	$(9 * 8 + 7^{\wedge}6) * -5 * (-4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) + 1)$
539428563	$((-9 - 8) / -7 + 6) * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2) - 1)$	602582125	$(9 * 8 - 7^{\wedge}6) * -5 * (4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) + 1)$
541539442	$(9 * ((8 + 7 - 6^{\wedge}5) + 4) / 3)^2 + 1)$	603320125	$(9 * 8 + 7^{\wedge}6) * 5 * (4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) + 1)$
545612760	$9^{\wedge}((-8 + 7) + 6) * 5 * (43^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	607125495	$9 * (-8^{\wedge}7 * (-6^{\wedge}(-5 + 4) - 32) - 1)$
545848956	$9^{\wedge}((-8 + 7) + 6) * (5 * 43^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	607125513	$-9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * (-6^{\wedge}(-5 + 4) - 32) - 1)$

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607993281	$((9^8 \wedge 7 + 6^{\wedge}(5+4)) - 3) * 21$	681324102	$9^{\wedge} 8 + (7 * (6 * 5^4 + 3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
607993407	$(9^8 \wedge 7 + 6^{\wedge}(5+4) + 3) * 21$	683671063	$(-9 + 8^{\wedge} 7 * 6) * (54 + 3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
611223165	$9/8 * ((7 + (-6^{\wedge} 5 + 4) * 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	683672041	$(9 + 8^{\wedge} 7 * 6) * (54 + 3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
611226728	$(9^8 * (-8/7^{\wedge}(6-5-4) - 3))^{\wedge} 2 - 1$	687234375	$(9^8 * (8+7))^{\wedge} 6 / 543)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
611226729	$(9^8 * (-8/7^{\wedge}(6-5-4) - 3))^{\wedge} 2 / 1$	688746753	$-9^8 * (87 - (6 * 54^{\wedge}(-3-2)))^{\wedge}(-1)$
611226730	$(9^8 * (-8/7^{\wedge}(6-5-4) - 3))^{\wedge} 2 + 1$	688747032	$9^8 * (8^8 - 7 + (6 * 54^{\wedge}(-3-2)))^{\wedge}(-1)$
611296392	$(9 - (8+7)^{\wedge} 6) * (-54 + 3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	688747401	$-9^8 * (8+7 - (6 * 54^{\wedge}(-3-2)))^{\wedge}(-1)$
611296866	$-9 + (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 * (54 - 3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	688747671	$9^8 * (8+7 + (6 * 54^{\wedge}(-3-2)))^{\wedge}(-1)$
611296884	$9 + (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 * (54 - 3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	688748040	$9^8 * (8^7 + (6/54^{\wedge}(3+2)))^{\wedge}(-1)$
611297358	$-9 + (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 * (54 - 3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	688748319	$9^8 * (87 - (6 * 54^{\wedge}(-3-2)))^{\wedge}(-1)$
611408335	$(9 + 8/7) * ((6^{\wedge} 5 - 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	691731700	$(9^8 * 7 / -6) * (5^{\wedge}(4+3^2) - 1)$
611590329	$-9/8 * ((7 - ((6^{\wedge} 5 - 4) * 3)^{\wedge} 2) + 1)$	691980165	$-9^8 * ((8+7)^{\wedge} 6 - 5) / 4 * 3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
611590347	$9/8 * ((7 + ((6^{\wedge} 5 - 4) * 3)^{\wedge} 2) + 1)$	699560064	$(-9 - 8) * 7 / -6^{\wedge}(5 - 4 * 3) * 21$
611957619	$9/8 * ((7 - (6^{\wedge} 5 + 4) * 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	702465363	$-9 - (8^8 * (7^8 - 6)^{\wedge} 5 / 43)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
612196080	$(9 + 8/7) * ((6^{\wedge} 5 - 4 - 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	711524352	$-987 * (-6 - 5) * 4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
612219967	$-9 - 8 * (7 - (6 * 54^{\wedge}(-3-2)))^{\wedge}(-1)$	711529984	$(9 - 8) * 7 + (6 - 54^{\wedge})^{\wedge} 3 * (-2 - 1)$
612219985	$9 - 8 * (7 - (6 * 54^{\wedge}(-3-2)))^{\wedge}(-1)$	711529998	$((-9 + 8) * 7 + (6 - 54^{\wedge})^{\wedge} 3) * (-2 - 1)$
612220079	$-9 + 8 * (7 + (6 * 54^{\wedge}(-3-2)))^{\wedge}(-1)$	714256711	$(9 - 8) * 7 + (6 * 54^{\wedge})^{\wedge} 3 * 21$
612220097	$9 + 8 * (7 + (6 * 54^{\wedge}(-3-2)))^{\wedge}(-1)$	714518156	$(9^8 - 7 / -6) * (5^{\wedge}(4+3^2) - 1)$
612482499	$9/8 * ((7 - (6^{\wedge} 5 + 4) * 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	718092564	$((-9 - 8)^{\wedge} 7 + 65) / (4 * -3) * 21$
612850041	$-9/8 * ((7 - ((6^{\wedge} 5 - 4) * 3)^{\wedge} 2) + 1)$	720896000	$(98 - 76) / (5/4^{\wedge} 5 - 3)^{\wedge}(-2 - 1)$
613217709	$9/8 * ((7 + (6^{\wedge} 5 + 4) * 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	725589072	$9^8 - 8 * (7 - (6^{\wedge} 5 + 4) - 3 * 21)$
614404464	$(9 + 8/7) * ((-6^{\wedge} 5 - 4 - 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	725590080	$9^8 * (7 + 6^{\wedge}(5+4) - 3 * 21)$
614671866	$-9 + (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 * (54 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	725593104	$9^8 - 8 * (7 - (6^{\wedge} 5 + 4) - (3 * 2 + 1))$
614671884	$9 + (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 * (54 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	725593518	$9^8 * (-8 * (7 - 6^{\wedge}(5+4)) - 3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
615384625	$(9 - 8 * (-7 - 6)) * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2) + 1)$	725593698	$9^8 * ((-8 * (7 - 6^{\wedge}(5+4)) + 3^{\wedge} 2) + 1)$
615515616	$-9 + (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 * (54 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	725594004	$((9^8 * 8)^{\wedge}((-7 + 6) + 5) - 4) * 3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
615515634	$9 + (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 * (54 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	725594220	$((9^8 * 8)^{\wedge}((-7 + 6) + 5) + 4) * 3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
618098688	$(9^8 * 8)^{\wedge}((-7 + 6) + 5) * (-4 + 3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	725594526	$9^8 * (8 * (7 + 6^{\wedge}(5+4)) - 3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
618890136	$(9 - (8+7)^{\wedge} 6) * (-54 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	725594706	$-9^8 * (-8 * (7 + 6^{\wedge}(5+4)) - 3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
618890616	$-9 + (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 * (54 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 + 1))$	725595120	$9^8 * (7 + 6^{\wedge}(5+4) + 3 * 2 + 1)$
618890634	$9 + (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 * (54 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 + 1))$	725598144	$9^8 - 8 * (7 - (6^{\wedge}(5+4) + 3 * 21))$
618891114	$(9 + (8+7)^{\wedge} 6) * (54 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 + 1))$	725599152	$9^8 * (7 + 6^{\wedge}(5+4) + 3 * 21)$
620019720	$9^8 / 7 * ((6^{\wedge} 5 - 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	731278125	$(-9^8 * (8 - (7 + 6)))^{\wedge} 5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$
620607744	$(9^8 * 7^{\wedge}((-6 + 5) + 4) + 3)^{\wedge} 2 / 1$	732244728	$(-9^{\wedge} 8 * (-8 - (-7 - 6)) + 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3))^{\wedge} 2 + 1$
621298111	$-9 + 8/7 * ((6^{\wedge} 5 - 4) * 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1$	732421647	$(-9 + 8) * (-76 + 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3))^{\wedge} 2 - 1$
621298129	$9 + 8/7 * (((6^{\wedge} 5 - 4) * 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	732421885	$(-9 - (8 + 7) + (6 + 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3)))^{\wedge} 2 + 1$
626953125	$(-9 - 8 * (7 + 6)^{\wedge} 5 + 4) * 321$	732421900	$(9 - 8) * 7 + (-6 - 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3))^{\wedge} 2 - 1$
628798464	$(9^8 * 76)^{\wedge}((-5 + 4) + 3) * 21$	732422001	$(-9 + 8) * (7 * 6 + 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3))^{\wedge} 2 - 1$
630142749	$9/8 * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge} 3))^{\wedge} 2 - 1$	732599022	$(9^{\wedge} 8 * (-8 - (-7 - 6)) + 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3))^{\wedge} 2 + 1$
634863096	$(9^8 * 8 - 7 + 6^{\wedge}(5+4))^{\wedge} 3 * 21$	734309035	$((-9 - (8 * 7)^{\wedge} 6) - 5) / (-43 - (-2 + 1))$
634926600	$(9^8 * 8 - 7 - 6^{\wedge}(5+4))^{\wedge} 3 * 21$	734484660	$((9^{\wedge} 8 - 7) + 6) * ((5/4 + 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
638934912	$(9 - 8) * (7 * 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 - (3^{\wedge} 2 - 1))$	735306250	$(-9 + 8) / 7^{\wedge} 6 - 5^{\wedge} 4 * (3^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$
641154075	$((9 + 8)^{\wedge} 7 - 65) * ((4/3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	742187424	$(-9 + 8) * 76 * (-5^{\wedge}(4 + 3^2) + 1)$
641154175	$((9 + 8)^{\wedge} 7 - 6) + 5) * ((4/3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	744946875	$(-9^8 * (8 - (7 + 6)))^{\wedge} 5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$
644972040	$9^8 * (8 + 7)^{\wedge} 6 * (5 + 4) * (-3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	746770782	$(-9^{\wedge} 8 * (8 + 7 + 6) - 5^{\wedge}(4 * 3))^{\wedge} 2 - 1$
644972096	$9^8 * (-7 + 6^{\wedge}(5+4))^{\wedge} 3 * 21$	750224025	$(9 + 8) / 7 * ((6 + 5^4)^{\wedge}(3 * 2) - 1)$
644972992	$9^8 * (7 + 6^{\wedge}(5+4))^{\wedge} 3 * 21$	751266778	$(9 / ((8 * 76^{\wedge} 5 + 4) / 3 - 2))^{\wedge} 2 - 1$
644973048	$9^8 * (7 + 6^{\wedge}(5+4))^{\wedge} 3 * 21$	752467975	$(9 - 8) * 7 * ((6^{\wedge} 5 * 4 / 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$
645657705	$((98 * 7)^{\wedge} 6 - (-6 - (-5 - 4)) - 3) * 2 - 1$	756627878	$(9 / (8 - (7 - 6) * 5) / (4 + 3) * 2))^{\wedge} 2 - 1$
645657706	$((98 * 7)^{\wedge} 6 - (-6 + 5 + 4) - 3) * 2 + 1$	772987056	$(9^8 * (87 + 6)^{\wedge} 5)^{\wedge} 5 * (-4 + 3) - 21$
645657707	$((98 * 7)^{\wedge} 6 - (-6 - (-5 - 4)) - 3) * 2 + 1$	772987074	$(9^8 * (87 + 6)^{\wedge} 5)^{\wedge} 5 * (-4 + 3) - 2 - 1$
645657717	$((98 * 7)^{\wedge} 6 - (-6 - (-5 - 4)) + 3) * 2 - 1$	772987080	$(9^8 * (87 + 6)^{\wedge} 5)^{\wedge} 5 * (-4 + 3) + 2 + 1$
645657718	$((98 * 7)^{\wedge} 6 - (-6 - (-5 - 4)) + 3) * 2 + 1$	772987098	$(9^8 * (87 + 6)^{\wedge} 5)^{\wedge} 5 * (-4 + 3) + 21$
645657719	$((98 * 7)^{\wedge} 6 - (-6 - (-5 - 4)) + 3) * 2 + 1$	773955495	$9/8 * ((7 * (-6 * 5^4 + 3))^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
649230400	$(98 * (-7 - 6) * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2 + 1)$	775009920	$((9 + 8)^{\wedge} 7 - (-6 - 5) - 4) / 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1$
656099979	$9^8 * ((8 + 7) * 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (-4 + 3) - 21$	775009921	$((9 - 8)^{\wedge} 7 - (-6 + 5) - 4) / 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1$
656099997	$9^8 * ((8 + 7) * 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (-4 + 3) - 2 - 1$	775009922	$((9 + 8)^{\wedge} 7 - (-7 - 6) - 5) - 4) / 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1$
656100003	$9^8 * ((8 + 7) * 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (-4 + 3) + 2 + 1$	776436120	$9/8 * ((7 * (6 * 5^4 + 3))^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
656100021	$9^8 * ((8 + 7) * 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (-4 + 3) + 21$	777337856	$((9 - (8 - 7)) * 6)^{\wedge} 5 - 4^{\wedge}(3 * (2 + 1))$
656908235	$(9 / (8 + 7 * (65 - 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2)))^{\wedge} 2 - 1$	777862144	$((9 - (8 - 7)) * 6)^{\wedge} 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3 * (2 + 1))$
659108868	$(-9 * 8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 + 5) - 4) / 3 - 21$	784147176	$9^8 - 8 * (((-7 * 6)^{\wedge} 5) / (4 * 3) * 2) + 1$
659108958	$(9^8 * (-7^{\wedge} 6 + 5) + 4) / 3 + 21$	784147608	$9^8 * (((7 * 6)^{\wedge} 5) / (4 * 3) * 2) + 1$
665832554	$((-9 - 8)^{\wedge} 7 + 6) / (-5 / 43 - 2^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	789780375	$(9^8 * (8 + 7))^{\wedge} 5 * (-6 + 5) + 4) * 321$
669840888	$(-9 / (8 - (7 * 65 * 4)^{\wedge} 3))^{\wedge} 2 - 1$	793151881	$(-9 - 8) * (7 - (6 * 5^4 * 3)^{\wedge}(2 + 1))$
674179200	$9^8 * (765 * 4)^{\wedge} 4 * (-3 + 2) - 1$	793152119	$(-9 - 8) * (-7 + (6 * 5^4 * 3)^{\wedge}(2 + 1))$
675282461	$(-9 + 8^{\wedge} 7 * 6) * (54 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 + 1))$	794495745	$9^8 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge} 6 - 5) / 4 * (32 - 1)$
675283427	$(9 + 8^{\wedge} 7 * 6) * (54 - 3^{\wedge}(-2 + 1))$	794812500	$(9^8 * (8 + 7))^{\wedge} 6 / (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3))^{\wedge} 2 - 1$
677941128	$9^8 * (-7 + 6^{\wedge}(5+4))^{\wedge} 3 * 21$	799621875	$(-9^8 * (8 - (7 + 6)))^{\wedge} 5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2 + 1))$
677942010	$9^8 * (-7 - 6^{\wedge}(5+4))^{\wedge} 3 * 21$	805663980	$9^8 * (8 + 7 / 6) * (5^{\wedge}(4 + 3^2) - 1)$
679366656	$9^8 * 8^{\wedge} 7 * 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2) + 1)$	805664145	$9^8 * (8 + 7 / 6) * (5^{\wedge}(4 + 3^2) + 1)$
679587840	$9^8 * 8^{\wedge} 7 * 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2) + 1)$	806215120	$9^8 * (-7 + 6^{\wedge}(5+4))^{\wedge} 3 * (-2 + 1)$

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806215176	$9^* - 8^*(7 - 6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3^{\wedge}-2+1))$	967163571	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(-5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$
806216184	$9^*8^*(7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3^{\wedge}-2+1))$	967376896	$(9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6) - 5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$
806216240	$9^*8^*(7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3^{\wedge}-2+1))$	967458690	$9^*(- 8 - ((7 - (6^{\wedge}5^*4/3)^{\wedge}2) - 1))$
813802084	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7)^*6^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	967458711	$-98 - (7 - (6^{\wedge}5^*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1))$
818458328	$(9^*8+7)^*(654/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	967458725	$-98+7+(6^{\wedge}5^*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$
820117473	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2 - 1$	967458738	$9 - (87 - (6^{\wedge}5^*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1))$
820117474	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2^{\wedge}1$	967458894	$-9+87+(6^{\wedge}5^*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$
820117475	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2+1$	967458907	$98 - (7 - (6^{\wedge}5^*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1))$
820578100	$((9^{\wedge}8 - 7)+6)^*((5/4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	967458921	$98+7+(6^{\wedge}5^*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$
821237217	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2 - 1$	967458942	$-9^*(- 8 - ((7 + (6^{\wedge}5^*4/3)^{\wedge}2) - 1))$
821237218	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2^{\wedge}1$	967540736	$(9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$
821237219	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2+1$	967754061	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(- 5 - 4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$
826871976	$9^*8^* - 7^*(6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$	968486547	$(98^*7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))^*3 - 21$
826878024	$9^*8^*7^*(6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$	968486565	$(98^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)^*3 - 2 - 1$
845753535	$9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4^*(32+1)$	968486566	$(98^*7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))^*3 - 2^{\wedge}1$
856406061	$(9 - 87^*6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3))^* - 21$	968486567	$(98^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)^*3 - 2+1$
856406439	$(9 - 87^*6^* - 5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$	968486569	$((98^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4))^*3+2 - 1$
859963264	$((9+8)^{\wedge}((- 7+6)+5) - 4)/32^{\wedge} - 1$	968486570	$(98^*7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))^*3+2/1$
859963384	$((9-8)+7)^*((6^{\wedge}5^*4/3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	968486571	$((98^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4))^*3+2+1$
859963400	$((9-8)+7)^*((6^{\wedge}5^*4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	968486589	$(98^*7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))^*3+21$
859963520	$((9+8)^{\wedge}((- 7+6)+5)+4)/32^{\wedge} - 1$	969948736	$((- 9 - (8-7) - 6^{\wedge}5)^*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
862801399	$-9+(8^*7^*((- 6+5^*4)+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	976562468	$(9-8)+7)^*((- 6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3))/2 - 1)$
862801417	$9+(8^*7^*((- 6+5^*4)+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	976562484	$((9-8)+7)^*((- 6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3))/2+1)$
871796880	$(9-8)/7^*((6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	976562516	$((9-8)+7)^*((6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3))/2 - 1)$
873813333	$9/((8^*7^*6^*5^{\wedge}4 - 3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	976562532	$((9-8)+7)^*((6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3))/2+1)$
878811889	$9/((8+7)^{\wedge}(6+5))^*4 - 3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	988663428	$(9^*8+7^{\wedge}(6+5)+43)/2 - 1$
885937507	$(9-8)^*7^*((6^*5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	988663430	$(9^*8+7^{\wedge}(6+5)+43)/2+1$
886857129	$(9-8/7+6)^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2) - 1)$	992174399	$(9^*(8 - (7-6)))^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1))$
891795456	$(9/8 - 7^*6^{\wedge}5)/ - 4^{\wedge}(-3^*2 - 1)$	992698687	$(9^*(8 - (7-6)))^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1))$
891832320	$(9/8 - 7^* - 6^{\wedge}5)/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2 - 1)$	994332672	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*(4+32+1)$
896484375	$(9+8)^*(7^*6^*(5+4) - 3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	997499811	$(9 - 8^*76^*5^{\wedge}(4+3))^* - 21$
899280143	$((- 9 - 8)/7^*6)^{\wedge}(5 - 4 - 3))^{\wedge}2 - 1$	997500189	$(9 - 8^*76^* - 5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$
899280144	$((- 9 - 8)/7^*6)^{\wedge}(5 - 4 - 3))^{\wedge}2^*1$	1011179654	$(9 - (8^*7)^{\wedge}6)/((5 - 4^{\wedge}3)/2 - 1)$
899280145	$((- 9 - 8)/7^*6)^{\wedge}(5 - 4 - 3))^{\wedge}2+1$	1012921518	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7 - 6)^*(54 - 3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
899678208	$9^* - 8^{\wedge}7^*(6 - 54 + 3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	1012927314	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7 + 6)^*(54 - 3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
900544266	$(9 + ((- 8 - 7) - 6)^{\wedge}(-5 + 4^*3))^*/2^* - 1$	1025504394	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7 - 6)^*(54 + 3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
900544274	$(9 - ((- 8 - 7) - 6)^{\wedge}(-5 + 4^*3))^*/2 - 1$	1025510262	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7 + 6)^*(54 + 3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
900544275	$(9 - ((- 8 - 7) - 6)^{\wedge}(-5 + 4^*3))^*/2^*1$	1029600149	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3^{\wedge}2))/ - 1$
900544276	$(9 - ((- 8 - 7) - 6)^{\wedge}(-5 + 4^*3))^*/2+1$	1033142841	$(9+8/7+6)^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2) - 1)$
903449700	$-9+8^*((7+5)^{\wedge}(-4+3) - 21)$	1036616265	$(9-8)/7^*((- 6 - 5)^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2) - 1$
904512582	$9^{\wedge}8^*((7+5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)+21)$	1043432695	$-9 - 8^*((- 7^*6)^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1)))$
906987600	$-9^*(8^*7 - 6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	1043342713	$9 - 8^*((- 7^*6)^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1)))$
906997680	$9^*(8^*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	1047626999	$-9 - 8^*((- 7^*6)^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}(-3^*(- 2 - 1)))$
912789135	$(- 9 - (-8 - 76^{\wedge}5))/((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	1047627017	$9 - 8^*((- 7^*6)^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}(-3^*(- 2 - 1)))$
914097246	$-9 + ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4^*321$	1063125000	$(9^*8/7^*(6^*5)^{\wedge}(-4-3))^*2^{\wedge} - 1$
914097264	$9 + ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4^*321$	1067311719	$-9 + 8^*((- 7^*6)^{\wedge}5/(4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
918330055	$(9-8)^*7+(6^*54^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	1067311737	$9 + 8^*((- 7^*6)^{\wedge}5/(4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
921001103	$(9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4) - 3))^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	1068338670	$987^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)^*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$
921001104	$(9^*((- 8 - 7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3))^{\wedge}2/1$	1071382528	$(- 9+8^{\wedge}(-7 - (-6-5)))^*4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1))$
921001105	$(9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4) - 3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	1071384921	$-9^*(8+7^*((6^*54)^{\wedge}3/2+1))$
922581576	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(- 5^{\wedge}(4^*3/2)+1)$	1071385191	$9^*(8+7^*((6^*54)^{\wedge}3/2+1))$
922699674	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(5^{\wedge}(4^*3/2)+1)$	1073442825	$(9 - 8^{\wedge}((7-6)+5))^*(- 4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
924281603	$(9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4) + 3))^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	1073516535	$(- 9 - 8^{\wedge}((7-6)+5))^*(- 4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
924281604	$(9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4) + 3))^{\wedge}2^*1)$	1073967095	$(- 9+8^{\wedge}((7-6)+5))^*(4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
924281605	$(9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4) + 3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	1074040841	$(9+8^{\wedge}((7-6)+5))^*(4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
941685268	$((- 9+8+76)^*5)^{\wedge}4+3)/21$	1076101120	$(- 9 - 8^{\wedge}(-7 - (-6-5)))^* - 4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1))$
944724951	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3^*2 - 1)$	1082673216	$(9^*(8+76^*(5+43)))^{\wedge}2/1$
944783999	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)/(5^*4)^{\wedge} - 3^*2 - 1$	1086222744	$9/8^*((- 7+6^{\wedge}5)^*4 - 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
944784001	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)/(5^*4)^{\wedge} - 3^*2+1$	1086642270	$9/8^*((- 7+6^{\wedge}5)^*4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
944843049	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*((5^* - 4)^{\wedge}3^*2 - 1)$	1088391510	$(98^*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4+3))/2 - 1$
952430013	$(- 9/(8+(7^*65)^{\wedge}4/(-3-2))^{\wedge} - 1)$	1088391512	$(98^*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4+3))/2+1$
954148916	$((98 - (7-6))^{\wedge}5 - 4)^*3^{\wedge} - 2 - 1$	1090141470	$9/8^*((- 7-6^{\wedge}5)^*4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
954148918	$((98 - (7-6))^{\wedge}5 - 4)^*3^{\wedge} - 2+1$	1095299901	$-9+8^*((- 7-6 - ((5+4/-3)^{\wedge}2 - 1))$
955511964	$(9+8+7)^{\wedge}6^*(5 - 4^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2+1))$	1105880503	$-9+8/7^*((6^{\wedge}5^*4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
955511796	$(9+8+7)^{\wedge}6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2+1))$	1105880521	$9+8/7^*((6^{\wedge}5^*4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
960097367	$((9^*87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4) - 3))^*2 - 1$	1110222400	$(98^*(7^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4) - 3))^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
960097368	$((9^* - 87)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3)/ - 2^{\wedge} - 1$	1112246298	$9/8^*((7^{\wedge}(6+5) - (-4-3))/2+1)$
960097369	$((9^*87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4) - 3))^*2+1$	1112246316	$9/8^*((7^{\wedge}(6+5)+43)/2 - 1)$
960097379	$((9^*87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4) + 3))^*2 - 1$	1116304896	$(- 9+8)^*(76^*5 - 4)^{\wedge}3^* - 21$
960097380	$((9^*87)^{\wedge}(-6+5)+4+3)/2^{\wedge} - 1$	1124589382	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)+65^{\wedge}4)^*3^*21$
960097381	$((9^*87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4) + 3))^*2+1$	1124742859	$((9+((8+7)^*6)^{\wedge}5)^*4+3)/21$
964972096	$((- 9 - (8-7)+6^{\wedge}5)^*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$	1126170624	$9^*8^{\wedge}7^*(6+54 - 3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$

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1139829650	$((9+8)^{7+6}-5)^*(4/3)^{2+1}$	1230176211	$((9+8)^{7-6}(-5+4^3))^*(2+1)$
1142258475	$9/((8^7)^{6-5^4}/3-2)^{\wedge-1}$	1231855827	$((9+8)^{7+6}(-5+4^3))^*(2+1)$
1142258498	$(-9+(8^7)^{6-(5-4)})/3^{\wedge(2+1)}$	1234796544	$9^8 7^*(65-(-4/3)^{\wedge(-2-1)})$
1145371743	$9^*(8+7^*(6^5+43))^{\wedge(2+1)}$	1236197376	$(9^8)^{\wedge((-7+6)+5)^*(43+2+1)}$
1155575787	$(9^8)^{\wedge((-7+6)+5)^*43-21}$	1249198264	$-9^8+((7^6+5)^4)^{\wedge(3+2-1)}$
1155575805	$(9^8)^{\wedge((-7+6)+5)^*43-2-1}$	1249198408	$9^8+((7^6+5)^4)^{\wedge(3+2-1)}$
1155575806	$(9^8)^{\wedge((-7+6)+5)^*43-2^*1}$	1255580316	$9^8/-7^*((6-5^{\wedge(4^3)})/2+1)$
1155575807	$(9^8)^{\wedge((-7+6)+5)^*43-2+1}$	1261125578	$-9^*(8^{\wedge 7+6})+(5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1155575809	$((9^8)^{\wedge((-7+6)+5)^*43+2-1})$	1261125686	$9^*(8^{\wedge 7+6})+(5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1155575811	$((9^8)^{\wedge((-7+6)+5)^*43+2+1})$	1271529272	$9^8*-7^6-(-5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1155575829	$(9^8)^{\wedge((-7+6)+5)^*43+21}$	1279999526	$(-9^8-7)^*6-(-5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1161141723	$-9^{\wedge(-8+7)^*(6^{\wedge(5+4)}-3^{\wedge 21})}$	1279999757	$-9^{\wedge((8+7)/6)}+(5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1161999323	$9^{\wedge(87/6-5)-4^{\wedge(3^*(2+1))}}$	1279999859	$-9^*(8+7)-6+(5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1162171467	$-9^{\wedge(-8+7)^*((6^5)^{\wedge 4}-3^{\wedge 21})}$	1279999871	$-9^*(8+7)+6-(-5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1162258011	$9^{\wedge(-8+7)^*(-6^{\wedge 5^4+3^{\wedge 21}})}$	1279999927	$-9^8-(-7-6-(-5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)})$
1162261610	$9^{\wedge(87/6-5)+(4^3)^{\wedge 2-1}}$	1279999980	$(-98/7-6)+(5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1162264923	$9^{\wedge(-8+7)^*(6^{\wedge 5^4+3^{\wedge 21}})}$	1279999987	$(-9+87)/-6+(5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1162351467	$9^{\wedge(-8+7)^*((6^5)^{\wedge 4+3^{\wedge 21}})}$	1280000020	$98/7+6+(5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1162523611	$9^{\wedge(87/6-5)+4^{\wedge(3^*(2+1))}}$	1280000073	$9^8+7-6+(5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1163381211	$9^{\wedge(-8+7)^*(6^{\wedge(5+4)}+3^{\wedge 21})}$	1280000129	$9^*(8+7)-6+(5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1164926784	$(98^*76)^{\wedge(-5-(-4-3))^*21}$	1280000243	$9^{\wedge((8+7)/6)}+(5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1166632336	$9+(-8-7^*(6+5)^{\wedge 4})/3^{\wedge 2^*1}$	1280000474	$(9^8+7)^*6-(-5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1167862276	$9-(-8-7^*(6+5)^{\wedge 4})/3^{\wedge 2^*1}$	1280240640	$(9^8*7)^{\wedge((-6+5)+4)^*(3^{\wedge 2+1})}$
1171012279	$((9+(-87+6)^5)^{\wedge 4+3})/21$	1285040811	$(-9-((8^7)^{\wedge 6-5}-4)/(-3-21))$
1173861720	$-9^*(8+(-7^6)^{\wedge 5+4^{\wedge(3^*(2+1))}})$	1288470728	$9^8*7^{\wedge 6-(-5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}}$
1173861864	$9^*(8-(-7^6)^{\wedge 5-4^{\wedge(-3^*(-2-1))}})$	1288685376	$(9^8)^{\wedge 7^6-5^*(4^{\wedge(-3-2)}+1)}$
1176073560	$-9^*(8-(-7^6)^{\wedge 5+4^{\wedge(3^*2+1))})$	1289865581	$(9^8)^{\wedge 7^6-5-43^{\wedge(2+1)}}$
1176073704	$9^*(8+(-7^6)^{\wedge 5-4^{\wedge(3^*2+1))})$	1290024595	$(9^8)^{\wedge 7^6-5+43^{\wedge(2+1)}}$
1176368472	$-9^*(8-(-7^6)^{\wedge 5-4^{\wedge(3^*2+1))})$	1291204800	$(9^8)^{\wedge 7^6-5^*(4^{\wedge(-3-2)}+1)}$
1176368616	$9^*(8+(-7^6)^{\wedge 5+4^{\wedge(3^*2+1))})$	1298715263	$9/8*7^*((6+5)^4)^{\wedge(3+2)-1}$
1178580312	$-9^*(8+(-7^6)^{\wedge 5-4^{\wedge(-3^*(-2-1))}})$	1298715265	$9/8*7^*((6+5)^4)^{\wedge(3+2)+1}$
1178580456	$9^*(8-(-7^6)^{\wedge 5+4^{\wedge(3^*(2+1))}})$	1298874314	$-9^*(8^{\wedge 7+6})+(5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1182449664	$(9^8)^{\wedge((-7+6)+5)^*(43+2-1)}$	1298874422	$9^*(8^{\wedge 7+6})+(5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}$
1185939456	$9^*-8^{\wedge 7^*(6^{\wedge(-5+4)}-3^*21)}$	1300967687	$(9+8)^*(7+6^{\wedge 5^4}(-3-2)^{\wedge-1})$
1186396041	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge(6+5)})/((4+3)^*-2-1)$	1301785704	$9^8/7^*((6^5)^{\wedge 4^3})^{\wedge 2-1}$
1199078607	$98^{\wedge(-7+6+5)^*(4+3^{\wedge 2})-1}$	1305306576	$(9^8 76)^{\wedge(-5-(-4-3))^*21}$
1199078609	$98^{\wedge(-7+6+5)^*(4+3^{\wedge 2})+1}$	1305326952	$9/8^*((7+6)^5)^{\wedge(4+3-2)-1}$
1200725622	$-9^*(8+(-7^6)^{\wedge 5}/((4+3)^{\wedge-2-1}))$	1306912280	$((9-8)^*(7^6)^{\wedge 5-4})^*(3^{\wedge 2+1})$
1200725766	$9^*(8+(-7^6)^{\wedge 5}/((4+3)^{\wedge-2-1}))$	1312713536	$(-9/(-87^*-6))^{\wedge(-5/(4-3))^*2/-1}$
1209264471	$-9^{\wedge((-8+7)+6)^*(5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}}$	1320258505	$(9+8)/7^*((6^{\wedge 5-4})^3)^{\wedge 2-1}$
1209382569	$9^{\wedge((-8+7)+6)^*(5^4)^{\wedge(3^*2+1)}}$	1325562413	$-9+(8/((7+6)^{\wedge(5+4)+3}))^{\wedge(-2+1)}$
1212682752	$9^8/(76^*54)^{\wedge((-3+2)-1)}$	1325562431	$9+(8/((7+6)^{\wedge(5+4)+3}))^{\wedge(-2+1)}$
1213173589	$((-98/-7)^{\wedge 6-5^{\wedge(4+3^{\wedge 2})}})^*-1$	1330571528	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))-43}))^{\wedge 2-1}$
1214999999	$9^{\wedge(-8+7)^*(6^5)^{\wedge(4+3)}/2-1}$	1330571529	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))-43}))^{\wedge 2^*1}$
1215000001	$9^{\wedge(-8+7)^*(6^5)^{\wedge(4+3)}/2+1}$	1330571530	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))-43}))^{\wedge 2+1}$
1216342940	$(-9+8^{\wedge 7})/6^*((5-4^{\wedge 3})^{\wedge 2-1})$	1332584841	$(9^8*7^*(6^5)^{\wedge 4-3})^{\wedge(-2+1)}$
1216348151	$-9+8^{\wedge 7}/6^*((5-4^{\wedge 3})^{\wedge 2-1})$	1343692800	$(9^8)^{\wedge((-7+6)+5)^*((4+3)^{\wedge 2+1})}$
1216348169	$9+8^{\wedge 7}/6^*((5-4^{\wedge 3})^{\wedge 2-1})$	1347401913	$((9-8^7)^{\wedge 6-5}/4-3)/2-1$
1216353380	$(9+8^{\wedge 7})/6^*((5-4^{\wedge 3})^{\wedge 2-1})$	1347401914	$((9-8^7)^{\wedge 6-5}/4-3)/2^*1$
1217341152	$9/8^*((765^*43)^{\wedge 2-1})$	1347401917	$((9-8^7)^{\wedge 6-5}/4+3)^*2^{\wedge-1}$
1218871296	$9^8 7^*(65+(-4/3)^{\wedge(-2-1)})$	1347401918	$((9-8^7)^{\wedge 6-5}/4+3)/2+1$
1219703125	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge 6-5^{\wedge(4+3^{\wedge 2})}})/-1$	1350621892	$-9^8+7/((6^{\wedge 5+43}))^{\wedge(-2-1)}$
1220656469	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge 6-5^{\wedge(4+3^{\wedge 2})}})^*-1$	1351003535	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))+4^*-3}))^{\wedge 2-1}$
1220703020	$((-9+8)^{\wedge 7+6})^*(5^{\wedge(4^3)}-21)$	1351003536	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))-4^*3}))^{\wedge 2^*1}$
1220703230	$((9-8)^{\wedge 7-6})^*(-5^{\wedge(4^3)}-21)$	1351003537	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))+4^*-3}))^{\wedge 2+1}$
1222115319	$9^*(8^{\wedge 7^*(65-4^{\wedge(-3+2)})}-1)$	1351836559	$9/((8^*(7+6)^{\wedge 5+4+3}))^{\wedge(-2+1)}$
1222115337	$9^*(8^{\wedge 7^*(65-4^{\wedge(-3+2)})}+1)$	1351836563	$9/((8^*(7+6)^{\wedge 5+4+3}))^{\wedge(-2+1)}$
1224393408	$((-9+8)+7)^{\wedge 6^*((54^*3)^{\wedge 2-1})}$	1355316471	$-9^*(8^7)^{\wedge 6^*5-4^{\wedge(3+2)+1}}$
1224486720	$((-9+8)+7)^{\wedge 6^*((54^*3)^{\wedge 2+1})}$	1355316489	$9^*(8^7)^{\wedge 6^*5/4^{\wedge(3+2)+1}}$
1224510000	$(-9-8)^*(7^6*5)^{\wedge 4^*-3^{\wedge(-2-1)}}$	1356080624	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))+4+3}))^{\wedge 2-1}$
1225261056	$9^8 7^*(65+(-4^3)^{\wedge(-2+1)})$	1356080625	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))-4-3}))^{\wedge 2/1}$
1225635840	$9^8 7^*65^*(-4^{\wedge(-3-2)}+1)$	1356080626	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))+4+3}))^{\wedge 2+1}$
1225654272	$9^8 7^*(65-4^{\wedge(-3+2-1)})$	1356522560	$(-9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))+4+3}))^{\wedge 2-1}$
1226760192	$9^8 7^*(65-4^{\wedge(-3-2)+1})$	1356522561	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))-4+3}))^{\wedge 2/1}$
1226815479	$9^*(8^{\wedge 7^*(65-4^{\wedge(-3-2)})}-1)$	1356522562	$(-9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))+4+3}))^{\wedge 2+1}$
1226815497	$9^*(8^{\wedge 7^*(65-4^{\wedge(-3-2)})}+1)$	1361388608	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))-4-3}))^{\wedge 2-1}$
1226852343	$9^*(8^{\wedge 7^*(65+4^{\wedge(-3-2)})}-1)$	1361388609	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7+6+5)+4-3}))^{\wedge 2^*1}$
1226852361	$9^*(8^{\wedge 7^*(65+4^{\wedge(-3-2)})}+1)$	1361388610	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))+4-3}))^{\wedge 2+1}$
1226907648	$9^8 7^*(65+4^{\wedge(-3-2)+1})$	1361610000	$(9^*(8^{\wedge((-7+6)+5)+4}))^{\wedge(3-(2-1))}$
1228013568	$9^8 7^*(65+4^{\wedge(-3+2-1)})$	1361831408	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))+4+3}))^{\wedge 2-1}$
1228032000	$9^8 7^*65^*(4^{\wedge(-3-2)+1})$	1361831409	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7+6+5)+4+3}))^{\wedge 2^*1}$
1228406784	$9^8 7^*(65-(-4^3)^{\wedge(-2+1)})$	1361831410	$(9^*(8^{\wedge(-7-(-6-5))+4+3}))^{\wedge 2+1}$

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1363603328	$(9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+4+3))^{\wedge}2-1$	1491970480	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)+6)*((5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)+1)$
1363603329	$(9*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4+3))^{\wedge}2*1$	1499897301	$(9-8)*7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}2-1$
1363603330	$(9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+4+3))^{\wedge}2+1$	1501127159	$(9-8)*7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2+1$
1366928783	$(9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-4*-3))^{\wedge}2-1$	1501852266	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7-6))/(5^{\wedge}4+3)^2-1$
1366928784	$(9*(8^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4*3))^{\wedge}2/1$	1504438013	$-9+((8*7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(43/2-1)$
1366928785	$(9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-4*-3))^{\wedge}2+1$	1504438031	$9+((8*7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(43/2-1)$
1367630991	$-9+((8-7*6*(5+4))*-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	1504575094	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7-6-5)*4/3*2+1$
1373291064	$9/8*((7*6+5^{\wedge}(4+3^{\wedge}2))+1)$	1504575138	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7+6)-5*(4/3*2+1)$
1380939378	$((-9+(8*7)^{\wedge}6)-5)/(4/3+21)$	1508982048	$9*8/(7*654)^{\wedge}((-3+2)-1)$
1384660625	$(9+8)*(76*5/4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	1516769481	$(9-(8*7)^{\wedge}6)/(-5*4-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
1387637000	$(9*(-8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-43))^{\wedge}2-1$	1516800474	$(9*8+7)*-6*((5*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
1387637001	$(9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+43))^{\wedge}2/1$	1520444835	$((9-8)*7+6)^{\wedge}5*(4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
1387637002	$(9*(-8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-43))^{\wedge}2+1$	1524629504	$(9*8^{\wedge}-7/6543)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
1393412995	$(9/8)*((6-5*4)^{\wedge}3-21)$	1526726647	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*((-6+5)+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1$
1393668515	$-98+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	1526726665	$9+8^{\wedge}7*((-6+5)+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1$
1393668541	$-9*8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	1530920951	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*((-6+5)+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)+1$
1393668596	$-9-(8-(7/(6^{\wedge}5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	1530920969	$9+8^{\wedge}7*((-6+5)+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)+1$
1393668612	$-9+8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	1532402009	$9/8-(7/(6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
1393668614	$9-(8-(7/(6^{\wedge}5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	1533011533	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7)*(6+5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
1393668630	$9+8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	1533018103	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
1393668685	$9*8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	1533018121	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
1393668711	$98+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	1533024691	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)*6+5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
1395089271	$-9-8/7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	1542062080	$(-9+8-7^{\wedge}6)/-5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1395089289	$9-8/7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	1544143188	$((9-8)*7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4+3)*21$
1398752712	$987/6*54^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$	1549622907	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*((54*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
1400846643	$(9-(8+7)*6*5)^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	1549741005	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*((54*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
1401046875	$9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*((-5-4/3)*-2+1)$	1552416768	$9*-8^{\wedge}7*(65/4*(-3-2)-1)$
1424153647	$(9-8)*7/6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	1552836303	$-9+((8-7*6*(-5-4))*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
1431228544	$(-9-8+7^{\wedge}6)*(5*4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	1552836321	$9+((8-7*6*(-5-4))*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
1431423216	$(-9+8+7^{\wedge}6)*(5*4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	1585557504	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)*(-4+3*21)$
1431447550	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6)*(5*4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	1597339125	$(9*8+7+6)^{\wedge}5/(4/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
1431642222	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6)*(5*4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	1612796967	$9*(8*-7*(6-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))-1)$
1436715334	$9+8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	1612796985	$-9*(8*7*(6-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))-1)$
1437717008	$(-9^{\wedge}(-8+7)+6)*((5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)+1)$	1612800000	$9/(8/-7-6)*(-5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
1437751296	$((-9+8)+7)^{\wedge}(6+5)*(4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	1612803015	$9*(8*7*(6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))-1)$
1440926979	$-9*(8*7/6-543^{\wedge}(2+1))$	1612803033	$9*(8*7*(6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
1440927147	$9*(8*7/6+543^{\wedge}(2+1))$	1614144279	$(98*7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))*3+2-1$
1443851088	$(9-8-7)*(6-5^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	1614144281	$(98*7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))*3+2+1$
1443851095	$((9-8)*7-6/(-5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	1614620385	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4*3*21$
1446308567	$-9+8-(7/(6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	1622736240	$(-9-(-8-7^{\wedge}6))/((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
1453218008	$((9+8)*7+6)^{\wedge}5+43/21$	1628860662	$(9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6)*((5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
1453218009	$((-9-8)*7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3/21$	1633640391	$-9+8*(7*6)^{\wedge}5*(4/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
1458805509	$((-9+8)^{\wedge}7+6)^{\wedge}5+4)^{\wedge}3/21$	1633640409	$9+8*(7*6)^{\wedge}5*(4/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
1464625152	$((-9+8)+7)^{\wedge}(6+5)*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	1635675308	$9*((-8+7*6)^{\wedge}5*4+3)+2-1$
1464843519	$(-98-7)-6*(-5^{\wedge}(4*3)+21)$	1635675310	$9*((-8+7*6)^{\wedge}5*4+3)+2+1$
1464843533	$(-98+7)-6*(-5^{\wedge}(4*3)+21)$	1641353652	$(9+8)^{\wedge}7+65*-4*(3+2-1)$
1464843631	$(9-8)*7+6*(5^{\wedge}(4*3)-21)$	1641355732	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7-65*-4)*(3+2-1)$
1464843637	$(-9-8)*7+6*(5^{\wedge}(4*3)+2-1)$	1641599487	$(-9+8*7*6)*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
1464843649	$(-9-8)*7+6*((5^{\wedge}(4*3)+2)+1)$	1641600513	$(9-8*7*6)*((5*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
1464843778	$((9-8)*7+6*5^{\wedge}(4*3))+21$	1644165110	$98*((7-6)-5)^{\wedge}(4*3)-21$
1464843851	$(9+8)*7+6*((5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)-1)$	1644167119	$98*((-7+6)+5)^{\wedge}(4*3)-2^{\wedge}-1$
1464843863	$(9+8)*7-6*(-5^{\wedge}(4*3)+2-1)$	1644167217	$98*((-7+6)+5)^{\wedge}(4*3)+2^{\wedge}-1$
1464843883	$(9*(8+7)+6/5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)^{\wedge}1$	1644169226	$98*((-7+6)+5)^{\wedge}(4*3)+21$
1464843967	$98-7+6*(5^{\wedge}(4*3)+21)$	1652994048	$((9+8-7)+6)/5*4^{\wedge}3*2+1$
1464843981	$98+7+6*(5^{\wedge}(4*3)+21)$	1666598968	$-9+(8/(7*6^{\wedge}(5+4-3)))^{\wedge}-2+1$
1468618039	$((-9+(8*7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)-3)/21$	1668294255	$-9+(8-7/6)*((5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)+1)$
1468618062	$-9+((8*7)^{\wedge}6-5*(-4-3))/21$	1668294273	$9+(8-7/6)*((5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)+1)$
1481419359	$(-9*8+7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3))*21$	1675524699	$9/-8*(7/(6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
1481420185	$98*((-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3/2-1)$	1693052712	$9*8*((7*6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3-2)-1$
1481420241	$(9*-8-7*(-6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3))*21$	1693052915	$-9+8*(7*6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3-2^{\wedge}-1$
1481420381	$-98*((-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3/-2-1)$	1693052923	$-9+8*(7*6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3+2^{\wedge}-1$
1481421753	$(-9+8)*7*(-6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3)*21$	1693052933	$9+8*(7*6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3-2^{\wedge}-1$
1481422243	$98*((-7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3/-2-1)$	1693052941	$9+8*(7*6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3+2^{\wedge}-1$
1481422383	$(9*8+7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3))*21$	1693053144	$9*8*((7*6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3+2)+1$
1481422439	$-98*((-7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*3/2-1)$	1699199469	$(9+8*7*6)*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
1481423265	$(9*8-7*(-6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3))*21$	1699200531	$(-9-8*7*6)*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
1489355216	$-9*8-(7/(6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	1706489856	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
1489355271	$-9-(8+(7/(6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	1713387748	$(-9-((8*7)^{\wedge}6-5)-4)/(3-21)$
1489355287	$-9+8-(7/(6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	1731601875	$((9+8+76)*5)^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
1489355289	$9-(8+(7/(6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	1733363712	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)*(4^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
1489355305	$9+8-(7/(6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	1735205101	$(98/(7^{\wedge}(6+5)*43*2))^{\wedge}-1$
1489355360	$9*8-(7/(6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	1738524060	$9/8*((7+(6*5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1752577159	$((9+8-7*65)^4+3)/21$	2066224368	$(9^8-76*5)*((4+3)^2-1)$
1757623704	$(9*8-7^4(6+5)+4)*(3^4-2-1)$	2066232528	$(9^8-7*6*5)*((4+3)^2-1)$
1757623832	$((9*8+7^4(6+5))-4)*(-3^4-2+1)$	2066239488	$(9^8+(-7-6)*5)*((4+3)^2-1)$
1759502977	$(9-8^7)*(6*5*(4-32)+1)$	2066242104	$-9*8*(7+6/(-5-4)^{-3*2-1})$
1759510519	$-9-8^7*(6*5*(4-32)+1)$	2066242328	$(9^8+7/-6*5)*((4+3)^2-1)$
1759510537	$9-8^7*(6*5*(4-32)+1)$	2066242888	$(9^8-7/-6*5)*((4+3)^2-1)$
1759518079	$(-9-8^7)*(6*5*(4-32)+1)$	2066243112	$9*8*(7+6/(5+4)^{-3*2-1})$
1765490751	$-9+8/7*((6*5+4)^{3*2}-1)$	2066245728	$(9^8-(-7-6)*5)*((4+3)^2-1)$
1765490769	$9+8/7*((6*5+4)^{3*2}-1)$	2066260848	$(9^8+76*5)*((4+3)^2-1)$
1783880728	$(9-8)*7*(6+5^4+3)^{2+1}$	2066264448	$(9^8+7*65)*((4+3)^2-1)$
1798045687	$-9+(8*76*((-5+4)+3))^{2+1}$	2066279328	$(9^8+765)*((4+3)^2-1)$
1798045705	$9+(8*76*((-5+4)+3))^{2+1}$	2066615520	$(9^8-7+6^5)*((4+3)^2-1)$
1800874944	$9*8*((-6-5)*-4*3)^{2+1}$	2066616192	$(9^8+7+6^5)*((4+3)^2-1)$
1807960095	$1807960095*((-5-4)*3)^{-2-1}$	2068048827	$9/8*((7*(6-(5-4)))^{3*2}-1)$
1807964469	$9^8*(7*6+((5+4)*3)^{-2-1})$	2069296875	$9*(8+7)^6*5^4*(4+3)^{-2-1}$
1812361351	$((9+8^7)-6)/5^4*321$	2081640625	$((9^8+7)-6)*5^4)^{3-(2-1)}$
1815328341	$(9^8-(7*6)^{5+4-3})/(-2-1)$	2082471936	$(987+6)/((-5+4)+3)^{-2-1}$
1818230784	$(9-876)/((5-4)-3)^{-2-1}$	2084484375	$9*((8+7)^6*(5^4+3^4)^{-2+1})$
1819653984	$(9/(8-7)*6)^{5*4-3^4-2-1}$	2126250000	$(9*8/7*(6*5)^{-4-3})^{2+1}$
1840444704	$98/(7+6)*((5^4(4*3)-2)+1)$	2126542743	$-9*((8+7)^6-(5^4+3)^{2+1})$
1844026155	$(9^8+7*6)^{5+4-3}/(2+1)$	2131746901	$((9-((8-7)^6+5)^4)^{3+2})*-1$
1847365632	$-9*(8^7*(6*5*4)^{3+2-1})$	2131746905	$((9-((8-7)^6+5)^4)^{3-2})*-1$
1853666208	$(9^8(8-7)*6)^{5*4+3^4-2-1}$	2135696401	$(9-8^4(-7+6))*5^4(4-3)^{2+1}$
1855979520	$(9+876)/((-5+4)+3)^{-2-1}$	2146689007	$(9-8)*7+(6*5^4)^{2+1}$
1862270967	$-9+8^7*-6*(-5-((4*3)^2-1))$	2146893824	$(-9+(8/(7-6))^5)*4^4(3^2-1)$
1862270985	$9+8^7*-6*(-5-((4*3)^2-1))$		
1865813431	$(-9+8)/-7*(6^4(5+4^4(3/2))+1)$		
1867766355	$9/8*7*((-6+5^4)^3+21)$		
1885114368	$9*(8^7+(6*5^4)^{3+2-1})$		
1894683342	$(-9^8(8+7-6)-5^4(4*3))*(-2-1)$		
1901763252	$-9^8+(-7*6*5)^4-3^4(2+1)$		
1901763306	$-9^8+(-7*6*5)^4+3^4(2+1)$		
1904673897	$(-9*(8*7-6^4(5+4))-3)*21$		
1904674023	$(-9*(8*7-6^4(5+4))+3)*21$		
1904695065	$9*(8*7+6^4(5+4))-3)*21$		
1904695191	$9*(8*7+6^4(5+4))+3)*21$		
1916799401	$(-9+8*76)*((5*4)^{3+2}-1)$		
1916800599	$(9-8*76)*((5*-4)^{3+2}-1)$		
1916928000	$9*8^7*65*((4/3)^{-2+1})$		
1927060525	$(9/8+7)*((-6+5^4)^3+21)$		
1928149461	$(-9+8)*7^6*(-5-4^4(3*2+1))$		
1936971792	$(98^4(-7+6+5)-4^4)^3*21$		
1936974480	$(98^4(-7+6+5)+4^4)^3*21$		
1953124856	$((-9-8)-7)*(6+5^4(4*3)/(-2-1))$		
1953124931	$((-9+8)-7)*(6-5^4(4*3))-21$		
1953124969	$((-9+8)-7)*(6-(5^4(4*3)+2))+1$		
1953124973	$((-9+8)-7)*(6-5^4(4*3))+21$		
1953125027	$((9-8)+7)*(6+5^4(4*3))-21$		
1953125031	$((9-8)+7)*(6-(-5^4(4*3)+2))-1$		
1953125069	$((9-8)+7)*(6+5^4(4*3))+21$		
1953125144	$((9+8)+7)*(6+5^4(4*3)/(2+1))$		
1960984088	$((-9^4((-8+7)+6)+5)/4^4)^3)^2-1$		
1960984089	$((-9^4((-8+7)+6)+5)/4^4)^3)^2*1$		
1960984090	$((-9^4((-8+7)+6)+5)/4^4)^3)^2+1$		
1974399383	$(9+8*76)*((5*4)^{3+2}-1)$		
1974400617	$(-9-8*76)*((5*-4)^{3+2}-1)$		
1975509000	$9*(87*6*5)^{-4-(-3+2))}^{-1}$		
1987681045	$-9+((87+6)^5-4)/(3+2^4-1)$		
1987681063	$9+((87+6)^5-4)/(3+2^4-1)$		
1987856694	$9^8+(-7*6*5)^4-3^4(2+1)$		
1987856748	$9^8+(-7*6*5)^4+3^4(2+1)$		
1996150987	$((9+8*-7)^6*5+4)/3^4(2+1)$		
2031328125	$9*(8+7)^6*5*(4-3^4(-2-1))$		
2046515625	$9*(8+7)^6*(5*4-3^4(-2-1))$		
2047025232	$(9-8/(7+6))*((5^4(4*3)-2)+1)$		
2054109375	$9*(8+7)^6*(5*4+3^4(-2-1))$		
2056065312	$((-9-(8*7)^6)/-5+43)/(2+1)$		
2061704836	$((9^8+7)-6)*(-5^4+3)^2*1$		
2065869024	$(9^8-7-6^5)*((4+3)^2-1)$		
2065869696	$(9^8+7-6^5)*((4+3)^2-1)$		
2066205888	$(9^8-765)*((4+3)^2-1)$		
2066220768	$(9^8-7*65)*((4+3)^2-1)$		

Supplement 3

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-20103	$((-1-2)^{(3+4)}-5/6*7^8)*9$	-67115	$((-1/2*(3+4)^{(5+6)}+7)^8+9$
-28273	$((1-2^\wedge(3^4))+56)^7^\wedge(-8+9)$	-67825	$-1+(2*3)^\wedge4*(-5-6*(7+8/9))$
-29083	$(1/2*(3+4^\wedge5)+6)^*-7*8+9$	-69243	$-1-(-2-3*4*5*(-6-7))^*89$
-29101	$(1/2*(3+4^\wedge5)+6)^*-7*8-9$	-69326	$((1*2^\wedge3)^\wedge4-5-6-7)^*(-8-9)$
-32506	$1*2*(3-4^\wedge5*((6+7/8)+9))$	-69455	$1-((2+3)*(-4-5^\wedge6)+7)^*-8/9$
-32902	$1-2^\wedge(3*((4-5)+6))+(-7-8)*9$	-69651	$((((-1+(2*3)^\wedge4)-5)^*-6-7)+8)^*9$
-32914	$-1-23*(4*-5*(6-78)-9)$	-69669	$((((-1+(2*3)^\wedge4)-5)^*-6+7)-8)^*9$
-34067	$(-1-2*3^\wedge4)*((5*6*7+8)-9)$	-69746	$((1-2)+3)*((4^\wedge5-6^\wedge7)/8-9)$
-34630	$-1+(2*(3-4^\wedge5)+6)-7)^*(8+9)$	-69926	$((1-2)+3)*(4*5-6^\wedge7/8+9)$
-36323	$((-1-2^\wedge(3*4))-5)^*(6/7+8)+9$	-70258	$((1-2)+3)*((-4^\wedge5-6^\wedge7)/8-9)$
-36898	$((1/2-3)-4)^*5678+9$	-72527	$(-1+(2*3)^\wedge4)^*-56+7/(8-9)$
-37073	$12*-3*(4^\wedge5+6)-7*(8-9)$	-72539	$1+((2+3)^\wedge4-5)/-6*78*9$
-37303	$((-1-2^\wedge(3*4))-567)^*8+9$	-72541	$-1+((2+3)^\wedge4-5)/-6*78*9$
-37321	$((-1-2^\wedge(3*4))-567)^*8-9$	-72923	$1-2/3*((4+5^\wedge6)*7-8)-9$
-38446	$((1-2^\wedge(3*4))+5)^*(6/(7+8)+9)$	-72925	$-1-2/3*((4+5^\wedge6)*7-8)-9$
-38535	$(12+3)*(4^\wedge5/6*(-7-8)-9)$	-73250	$((1+2^\wedge(3*4))+5)^*(-6/7-(8+9))$
-38864	$((1+(2*3)^\wedge4*-5)^*6-7)+8+9$	-73471	$1+(-2/3-4)*(5^\wedge6-7*(-8-9))$
-39116	$1*-2*(3^\wedge(4+5)-6-7*(8+9))$	-74133	$12*(3+4^\wedge5)^*-6-7-8-9$
-39534	$1*2*((-3^\wedge(4+5)-67-8)-9)$	-74928	$-12*((-3-4^\wedge5)^*-6-7+89)$
-40135	$1*23*((4*56-7)^*-8-9)$	-76025	$12^\wedge3*4*(-5-6)-7*(8-9)$
-40390	$((-1+2^\wedge(3*4))-56)^*(7-(8+9))$	-77459	$1-((2*3)^\wedge4-5)^*-6*(7-8-9)$
-40909	$1+(-2^\wedge(3*4)+5)*((6-7)^\wedge8+9)$	-77461	$-1-((2*3)^\wedge4-5)^*-6*(7-8-9)$
-41011	$-1+(-2^\wedge(3*4)-5)*((6-7)^\wedge8+9)$	-77533	$1*23*(4-5*(-67-8)^*-9)$
-41224	$(1-23*4*-56)*((-7+8)-9)$	-78773	$(1/2*(-3^\wedge(4+5)+6)-7)^*8-9$
-43162	$(1-23-4^\wedge5*6)^*7^\wedge(-8+9)$	-80903	$(12^\wedge3/(4/(5+6))+7)^*(-8-9)$
-43229	$1-2*(3*((4^\wedge5+6)*7-8)+9)$	-83269	$-1+(2*3)^\wedge4*(-5-6*(7/8+9))$
-43938	$((1+(-2*34-5)*67)+8)^*9$	-83392	$1*2*3*((4+5^\wedge6)+7)^*-8/9$
-44094	$(-1-2)*(((3*4+5)^\wedge6+7)/8-9)$	-83504	$-1*((2/34)^\wedge(-5-6+7)-8)+9$
-44967	$1*2*(-3^\wedge(4+5)+6)/7*8+9$	-85825	$-1+((2+3)^\wedge4+567)^*-8*9$
-45074	$(-1-2^\wedge(3*4))^*(5+6)-7^\wedge(-8+9)$	-87417	$1/2*(3^\wedge4+5*(-6^\wedge7/8+9))$
-47300	$((-1+(2*3)^\wedge4)-5)^*-6*(7-8/9)$	-88947	$(-1/2*(3^\wedge(4+5)+67)-8)^*9$
-47306	$((1+23)^\wedge4-5-6)/-7+89$	-92521	$((1^\wedge2+3)^\wedge(4+5)^*-6+7)/(8+9)$
-48248	$((-1+2)-3)*(4-5*67*8*-9)$	-92859	$(1-(((2*3)^\wedge4+5/6)-7)^*8)^*9$
-51443	$-1+((2+3)^\wedge4-5-6*7)^*-89$	-94260	$1*2*(3*((-4-5^\wedge6)-78)-9)$
-51965	$1-(-2-((3/(4-5))^\wedge6-7)^*-8)*9$	-95574	$1*2*(-3^\wedge(4+5)+6)/7*(8+9)$
-52877	$1*23*(-4-5*(6*78-9))$	-95652	$12*3*((-4+5*67)^*-8-9)$
-52942	$1*2/-3*((-4^\wedge5+6)^*-78+9)$	-96709	$1+(2*3-4^\wedge5)*((-6-7)^*-8-9)$
-53153	$(1-2^\wedge(3*4))+5)^*(6+7)+8+9$	-96999	$(-12^\wedge3-4)*56+7*(8-9)$
-53166	$((1*2^\wedge3)^\wedge4-5)*(-6-7)+8+9$	-98180	$1*2*((-3-(4^\wedge5*6-7)*8)+9)$
-53169	$((1-2^\wedge(3*4))+5)^*(6+7)-(8-9)$	-98204	$1*2*(3+(4^\wedge5*-6+7)*8)-9$
-53182	$1+(2^\wedge(3*4)-5)*(-6-7)^\wedge(-8+9)$	-98428	$1*2*((3-(4^\wedge5*6+7)*8)-9)$
-53327	$((1+2^\wedge(3*4))+5)^*(6-7)+8-9$	-99660	$1/2*3*((4+5^\wedge6)+7)/-8-9$
-53366	$(-1-2)+(3/-4^\wedge-5-67)^*(8+9)$	-99785	$(-1+(2*3)^\wedge4*(5+6))^*-7^\wedge(-8+9)$
-53837	$(-12*345*(6+7)-8)-9$	-100651	$(12-(3+4)^\wedge5)^*6+7*(8+9)$
-53868	$12*((-3-(4-567))^*-8-9)$	-101499	$-123+4^\wedge5*(6*(-7-8)-9)$
-53883	$(1+23*4*5*(-6-7)-8)^*9$	-101569	$((1/2-3)-4)^*(5^\wedge6-(7-8)^\wedge9)$
-57102	$1*2*(34*56*(-7-8)+9)$	-101688	$-1*-2*(-3^\wedge4+5)*(678-9)$
-57554	$1+(2^\wedge(3+4)-5)*6*-78+9$	-103967	$1+2*((3/(4-5))^\wedge6-7)^*-8*9$
-57556	$-1-(2^\wedge(3+4)-5)*6*78+9$	-103969	$-1+2*((3/(4-5))^\wedge6-7)^*-8*9$
-57572	$1+(2^\wedge(3+4)-5)*6*-78-9$	-106087	$1+((2+3)^\wedge4+567)^*-89$
-57574	$-1-(2^\wedge(3+4)-5)*6*78-9$	-106088	$((1-2*3)^\wedge4+567)^*-89$
-59869	$(1/(2*3)-4)*(5^\wedge6+7/(8-9))$	-107879	$1+((2*3)^\wedge4-56)*(-78-9)$
-60168	$12*((3/(4-5))^\wedge6*-7+89)$	-107881	$-1+((2*3)^\wedge4-56)*(-78-9)$
-60628	$1*23*(-4-56*(7*8-9))$	-109022	$-1+((2*3)^\wedge4*5+67)^*(8+9)$
-60784	$((-1-(2+3)*((4+5^\wedge6)*7+8))/9)$	-110743	$-1*((2*3)^\wedge4+5^\wedge6*7+8*9)$
-60973	$1*23*(4-5*(-67+8)^*-9)$	-111020	$(-1-234-5^\wedge6)^*7^\wedge(-8+9)$
-61060	$((-1+(2*3)^\wedge4)-5)^*-6*(7+8/9)$	-111417	$1+(2*3^\wedge(4+5))/-6+7)^*(8+9)$
-61613	$1-(2*3-456*(-7-8))^*9$	-111657	$-1+(2*3^\wedge(4+5)/6+7)^*(-8-9)$
-61895	$((1-((2*3)^\wedge4-5)*6)+7)^*8+9$	-114071	$((-1-(2*3)^\wedge4)*5+6)+7)^*8+9$
-61903	$((1+2+3)^\wedge4-5)^*-6+7)^*8+9$	-114089	$((-1-(2*3)^\wedge4)*5+6)+7)^*8-9$
-61911	$((-1+((2*3)^\wedge4-5)*6)+7)^*8+9$	-114475	$(-1-2^\wedge(3*4))^*5*(6+7)/(-8-9))$
-61922	$(-1-((2*3)^\wedge4-5)*6-7)^*8)-9$	-116511	$(-1*23-4^\wedge(5(-6-7+8)))/9$
-61978	$1*2*((3+4^\wedge5-6^\wedge7)+8)/9$	-116805	$((1+2*3)^\wedge4-5)^*6*(7/8-9)$
-62014	$1-(((2*3)^\wedge4-5)^*6+7)^*8+9$	-122416	$((1-(-2+3^\wedge(4+5)))+6)^*7*8/9$
-62041	$((-1+((2*3)^\wedge4-5)^*-6)-7)^*8-9$	-122494	$1/2*((-3-4)^*(5+6^\wedge7/8)-9)$
-62701	$(1/2*((-34-5^\wedge6)-7)^*8-9)$	-122528	$((-1-2-3^\wedge(4+5))-6)^*7*8/9$
-63252	$((-1-2)^\wedge3*4*5*(6+7)-8)^*9$	-124742	$1+((2*3*4-5^\wedge6)+7)^*8+9$
-64246	$12+((3/(4-5))^\wedge6-7)^*-89$	-126231	$((-1*2*3^\wedge4-5^\wedge6)+7)^*8+9$
-64472	$-1-((2+3)^\wedge4-5)^*(6+7)^*8+9$	-126588	$12*(34*-5*(6+7*8)-9)$
-65233	$-1-((-2-3^\wedge4)*5+6)+7)^*-8*9$	-126656	$1+(((2/34)^\wedge-5+6^\wedge7)+8)/9$
-66144	$((12+3^\wedge-4)+5)/(-6^\wedge-7*8*9)$	-126658	$-1+(((2/34)^\wedge-5+6^\wedge7)+8)/9$
-66563	$(-123-((4+5)^\wedge6+7)/8)-9$	-127935	$1/2*(3^\wedge(4+5))/-6*78+9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-130127	$1/2^*((3^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6^{\wedge}7+8) - 9)$	-208241	$((1+2+34)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)+8)/-9$
-131044	$-1^*2^*(3+4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6-7))-(8+9))$	-209811	$12^*((-3-4)^{\wedge}5-678)+9$
-132174	$1^*2^*((-3^*4)^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)/8+9$	-209829	$12^*((-3-4)^{\wedge}5-678)-9$
-133164	$1/2^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^{\wedge}7)^*8/9$	-212688	$((1+(2+3^{\wedge}4)^*5)+6)^*-7^*8^*9$
-134181	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+56)^*7+8)^*9$	-214970	$(-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*((-5-6)^*7-89)$
-135968	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}-3+45)^*6^*7^*-8^*9$	-215135	$1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4*((-5-6)^*7-89)$
-137003	$(1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6+7))^*(8+9)$	-215137	$-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4*((-5-6)^*7-89)$
-137038	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4^{\wedge}5*67-89)$	-215302	$(-1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*((-5-6)^*-7+89)$
-137551	$(1-2^*(3+4^{\wedge}5))^*67^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-217010	$((1-(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^*7)-8)/9$
-139328	$1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6/((-7+8)/9)$	-217881	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))^*(5^*6^*7^*8+9)$
-139708	$-1+((2^*3^*4-5^{\wedge}6)+78)^*9$	-219026	$1^*2^*((-3-(4+5^{\wedge}6))^*7-89)$
-140066	$-1/2^*(34^*5+6^{\wedge}7+8)-9$	-220851	$((((-1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))-5)^*-6-7)+8)^*9$
-141250	$-1^*((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6/((7-8)/9))$	-221499	$((((-1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))-5)^*6-7)+8)^*9$
-141329	$1^*-2+((-3+4)^*-5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9$	-221517	$((((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))+5)^*-6+7)-8)^*9$
-141756	$-12^*(3/4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)+89)$	-222775	$1^*-2345^*((6+7)^*8-9)$
-143283	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*-5+6)^*7/((-8+9)$	-222948	$((1/2-3^*(4^{\wedge}5+6))-7)^*8^*9$
-145476	$12^*3^*(45^*6^*(-7-8)+9)$	-223767	$(1-((2-3^{\wedge}4)+5)^*6^*-7^*8)^*9$
-146432	$1^*-2^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5-67^*(-8-9))$	-223775	$1-((2-3^{\wedge}4)+5)^*6^*7^*-8^*9$
-147597	$(-1+2)^*3^*((4^{\wedge}5*6+7)^*-8+9)$	-223777	$-1-((2-3^{\wedge}4)+5)^*6^*7^*-8^*9$
-149801	$1/2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^{\wedge}7)+8+9)$	-229327	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*56+7/(-8-9)$
-149809	$1/2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^{\wedge}7-8)+9)$	-235120	$-1^*2^*((3+4)^{\wedge}(5-(6-7)))-89)$
-149818	$-1/2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^{\wedge}7+8+9)$	-235748	$-12^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*7^*8/9)$
-150040	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))-5)^*6^*(-7+8/9)$	-235890	$-12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)+(6^*7-8)^*9$
-151002	$(((-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)-5)^*(-6-7)-8)^*9$	-236502	$-12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)-(6^*7-8)^*9$
-152136	$((1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*(-6-7)+8)^*9$	-236808	$((-12-(3^{\wedge}(4+5)/6+7)^*8)^*9$
-153104	$((1/2^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*-6^*7^*8/9$	-239873	$((12^*3)^{\wedge}4+5)-6/-7+8^*9$
-155276	$(1+(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)^*6^{\wedge}7+8)/9$	-240017	$((12^*3)^{\wedge}4+5)-6/-7-8^*9$
-155464	$((1+23^{\wedge}4)^*-5+6^*7)-8)/9$	-240202	$1/(2^*3^*4)^*((-56-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-155465	$((1+23^{\wedge}4)-5)^*(-6-7+8)/9$	-243738	$((-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5^*6^*7+8)^*9$
-155762	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)^*6^{\wedge}7+8)/9$	-245400	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))+5)^*-6^*(7-(8+9))$
-155764	$(1+(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6^{\wedge}7+8)/-9$	-246120	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))+5)^*6^*(7-(8+9))$
-156176	$((1-23)^{\wedge}4-5)^*-6-78)/9$	-251135	$1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6^*7+8)^*9$
-157360	$12^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*-6+78)/9$	-251137	$-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6^*7+8)^*9$
-157568	$12^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6+78)/-9$	-254268	$(1/2^*(3-4^{\wedge}5)+6)^*7^*8^*9$
-160370	$1^*2^*((-3+4^{\wedge}5)-6)^*(-7-8^*9)$	-255250	$1^*-2^*(-3+4^{\wedge}5)^*(6-7^*(-8-9))$
-163214	$1^*2^*((3+4^{\wedge}5)+6)^*(-7-8^*9)$	-255294	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5)/6^*78^*9$
-163582	$(-123^*((4+5)+6)+7)^*89$	-256750	$1^*2^*(-3-4^{\wedge}5)^*(6-7^*(-8-9))$
-164815	$(1-23^*4^{\wedge}5+6)^*7/((-8+9)$	-258511	$((-1-2^{\wedge}(3^*(4-5+6)))^*(7+8/9)$
-165884	$1+(((2-(3^*4)^{\wedge}5)^*6+7)+8)/9$	-261748	$1/(2^*3)^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-165892	$-1-(((2-(-3^*4)^{\wedge}5)^*6+7)+8)/9$	-261751	$1/(2^*3)^*((4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-166720	$12^*((-3^*4-5^{\wedge}6)+7)^*8/9$	-261828	$(1/2^*(3+4^{\wedge}5)+6)^*7^*-8^*9$
-166737	$((1^{\wedge}2+34)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)+8)/-9$	-263700	$((-1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))-5)^*(6/-7+8)^*9$
-167956	$((12^*3)^{\wedge}4-56)/(-7-(8+9))$	-266113	$-1-((2+3^{\wedge}4)+5)^*6^*7^*8^*9$
-168052	$1^*2^*((3+4)^{\wedge}5*((-6-7)+8)+9)$	-267030	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))^*5^*6^*(78-9)$
-168088	$1^*-2^*((3+4)^{\wedge}5^*(6+7-8)+9)$	-271584	$((1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*-6)+7)^*8^*9$
-168610	$(-1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5+6-7^*(-8-9))$	-272736	$((1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*6)+7)^*-8^*9$
-169768	$(-1+23^*((4+5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8)/-9$	-274030	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))+5)^*67^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-171780	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4)-5)^*6^*7^*(8-9)$	-275300	$1^*2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7+89)$
-172575	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*(5-6/7)^*8+9$	-275358	$-12^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)/6^*7-(8+9))$
-174231	$(1-2-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*7^*-8)^*9$	-275766	$-12^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*7+8+9)$
-174826	$-1+(((2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5)-6)^*(-7-8)^*9$	-279646	$1-23^{\wedge}4+5+((6+7)+8)^*9$
-177507	$((-1-(2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5^{\wedge}6)+7)-8)^*9$	-281610	$((-1+2^*(-3^*4-5^{\wedge}6)-7)-8)^*9$
-177633	$((-1-(2^{\wedge}(3^*4)+5^{\wedge}6))-7-8)^*9$	-283518	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))/((-6-7^*8)/-9)$
-179607	$(1/2-3^*4)^*(5^{\wedge}6-7^*(-8+9))$	-286785	$(-1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4-56)^*-7^*8)^*9$
-180279	$(-12-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*7^*8)^*9$	-287334	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^*6^*(-7-8)-9)$
-180564	$123^*4^*((-5-6^*7)^*8+9)$	-289089	$(-1+2^*(-3-4)^{\wedge}5)^*(6/(-7-8)+9)$
-182359	$-1/23^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*8+9)$	-292670	$(-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(-5+(6+7)^*(-8-9))$
-183012	$1^*-2^*(3+((-4+5)+6)^{\wedge}7+8)/9$	-293122	$(-1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5+(-6-7)^*(-8-9))$
-184050	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))+5)^*(6+7-8)^*9$	-298860	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))+5)^*(-6/7-8^*9)$
-184497	$-1^*(2^*((3+4^{\wedge}5)+6)+7)^*89$	-300168	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))+5+67)^*-8^*9$
-184590	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))+5)^*(-6-(7-8))^*9$	-303713	$((12+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*-6-7/(-8-9)$
-185903	$1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^*((-7-8)-9)$	-303720	$((12+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*6/(7-8)^{\wedge}9$
-188864	$1+(((2/34)^{\wedge}-5-6^{\wedge}7)+8)/9$	-303727	$((12+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*-6+7/(-8-9)$
-188866	$-1+(((2/34)^{\wedge}-5-6^{\wedge}7)+8)/9$	-303787	$((12+3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*-6+7/(-8-9)$
-189825	$((12+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6^*7/8-9)$	-313838	$1^*2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+67)^*8+9)$
-192771	$(1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*(6^*7-8))^*9$	-313874	$1^*2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+67)^*8-9)$
-193688	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))-5)^*6^*(-7-8/9)$	-315582	$1^*2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*7)^*8+9)$
-196851	$-1-(-2-3^{\wedge}(4+5))^*6^*(-7-8)/9$	-315982	$1^*2^*((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-67)^*8+9)$
-198441	$(-1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*((-5-(6+7))^*-8+9)$	-316018	$1^*-2^*((3^{\wedge}(4+5)+67)^*8+9)$
-199254	$12-3^*((4+5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8-9$	-316305	$(-1+2^*(-3^{\wedge}4+5)-6^{\wedge}7/8)^*9$
-200255	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3^*(4-5+6)))^*(7-8/9)$	-316976	$((1-2)+3)^*-4^{\wedge}5+6^{\wedge}7/-8^*9$
-205773	$(1-2)^*3^*((4^{\wedge}5*67-8)-9)$	-318028	$-1/2^*(3^{\wedge}4+5)^{\wedge}(-6^{\wedge}(-7+8)+9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-325386	$(1+(2+3)^{(4+5)})/(-6-(-7-8))^9$	-520362	$1^2*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)-(6^{\wedge}7-8^9))$
-325474	$(1+(2+3)^{(4+5)})/(-6+7^8-9)$	-522450	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))^5*6^*(7+8)^9$
-325568	$(1+(2+3)^{(4+5)})/(-6-(7^8-9))$	-525825	$123^*-45^*((6+7)^8-9)$
-327606	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-5^6)^*-7-89)$	-531618	$1^2*(3+((4+5^6)+7)^*(-8-9))$
-328242	$(-1+2)^*-3^*((-4-5^6)^*-7+8)-9$	-536445	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3+4+5))^*(6^7+89)$
-336690	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))^5*6^*(78+9)$	-536707	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4+5))^*(6^7+89)$
-341888	$1^2*2^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(-5^*6^7*8+9)$	-546630	$(1-2-34)^*(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}(-8+9))$
-342028	$(-1-23^{\wedge}4*(5+6)^{\wedge}(-7+8))/9$	-556868	$(12+3)^{\wedge}4*(-5-6)-7^*(8-9)$
-342973	$(1+(-2-3)^4*5^6)^*6^7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-557752	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)+8^9$
-344192	$1^*-2^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6^7*8+9)$	-557896	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)-8^9$
-346881	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))^*(5^*6^7*8+9)$	-560367	$(1-((2^3)^{\wedge}((4-5)+6)+7)^8)^9$
-351293	$(-1+2^*((-3-4-5)^{\wedge}6+7))/(-8-9)$	-561992	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4^{\wedge}5+6^{\wedge}7)-8^9$
-352308	$(-12+(3^4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*(-8-9)$	-562637	$12^*-3^*(4+5^6)-7^*(8-9)$
-352680	$(-1-2)^*((3+4)^{\wedge}(5-6)+7)-89)$	-566406	$1234^*(5^*6^*(7-8)-9)$
-352716	$(-12-(3^4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*(8+9)$	-580248	$(1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6+7))^8*9$
-353700	$(1^*-2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)+78)^9$	-580311	$(-1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6+7)^8)^*-9$
-354307	$(1+(2+3+4)^{\wedge}5)^*-6+7/(8-9)$	-580329	$(-1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6+7)^8)^9$
-354888	$-1^*(2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6)+78)^9$	-580392	$(-1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6+7))^8*9$
-359493	$(1+2)-(3^4*5^*(6+7)+8)^9$	-580409	$1+((-2^{\wedge}3-4)^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)-8)^9$
-359495	$1^{\wedge}2-(3^4*5^*(6+7)+8)^9$	-580411	$-1+((-2^{\wedge}3-4)^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)-8)^9$
-359497	$1-(2+(3/4^{\wedge}5-6)^*(6+7)+8)^9$	-580574	$1^2*(((-3^4)^{\wedge}5/6^7+8)+9)$
-361562	$((-1-2^{\wedge}(3^4))-5)^*(-6/7+89)$	-580642	$1^2*((3^4)^{\wedge}5/-6^7-8)-9)$
-364392	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(-3+4+5)-6)^*-7^*8^9$	-586150	$1234^*-5^*((6+7)^8-9)$
-368091	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3^4))+5)^*6^*(7+8)+9$	-590994	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(3+4)^*5*6-7^*8)^9$
-368109	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3^4))+5)^*6^*(7+8)-9$	-592807	$((12^3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*-6+7/(8+9)$
-369189	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^4))+5)^*-6^*(7+8)-9$	-594405	$(-1+(2^3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^*6^*(7+8)-9)$
-374622	$1^2*(3^4*((-5^{\wedge}6+7)+8)+9)$	-595323	$(-1-(2^3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^*6^*(7+8)+9)$
-374658	$1^2*(3^4*((-5^{\wedge}6+7)+8)-9)$	-596772	$(123-((4+5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8)^9$
-374777	$((1+2)^*(3^4-5^6)-7)^8-9$	-598509	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^4)+567)/-8^9$
-374787	$(-1-2)^*((3/4-5^{\wedge}6+7)^*-8-9)$	-598986	$(-123+((4+5)^{\wedge}6+7)/-8)^9$
-375213	$(-1-2)^*((3/4+5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$	-599382	$1^*-2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^{\wedge}7+8^9)$
-375342	$1^2*(3^4*((-5^{\wedge}6-7)-8)+9)$	-610164	$1/2^*-3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+7^8)+9$
-375378	$-1^2*(3^4*((5^{\wedge}6+7)+8)+9)$	-610182	$1/2^*-3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+7^8)-9$
-376625	$1^*23^*((-4^{\wedge}(5-6)^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$	-625970	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)^*5-6)^{-7^{\wedge}8}/9$
-377039	$-1^*23^*(4^{\wedge}(5-6)^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$	-626644	$(-1+2^*(3-4/-5^{\wedge}6)-7^{\wedge}8)/9$
-379683	$1/2^*((-3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)+9)$	-627808	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^{\wedge}5+6^{\wedge}7/-8^9)$
-379692	$-1/2^*((3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)+9)$	-631904	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7/-8^9)$
-388574	$(-1-2/-3^{\wedge}(4-5-6)-7)^*-89$	-634176	$-12^3*((4^{\wedge}5-6)^*-8-9)$
-392682	$1^2*-3^*(4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6-7))-89)$	-636800	$(-1-2^*((-3-4)^{\wedge}5+6)-7^{\wedge}8)/9$
-393072	$1^2*(3/4^{\wedge}(5-6-7)+8^9)$	-637064	$(-1+2^*(-3^4+5^{\wedge}6)-7^{\wedge}8)/9$
-393300	$12^*-345^*((6+7)^8-9)$	-638783	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)/9$
-400256	$1^2*2^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6^7*8+9)$	-639618	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3^*(4^{\wedge}5+6)-7^{\wedge}8)/9$
-406068	$(1-23-4)^*(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}(-8+9))$	-639968	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4^{\wedge}5-6)-7^{\wedge}8)/9$
-412683	$(1-(23-4)^{\wedge}5)/6^*(7+8)^{\wedge}9$	-640120	$(1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*6-7^{\wedge}8)/9$
-418455	$((1+(2+3)^{(4+5)})/(6^*-7)+8)^9$	-640342	$((12^{\wedge}3-4)+5-(6+7^{\wedge}8))/9$
-418599	$((1+(2+3)^{(4+5)})/(-6^*7)-8)^9$	-640726	$((-12^{\wedge}3-4)+5-(6+7^{\wedge}8))/9$
-419472	$12^*((3^*(4+5)-6^{\wedge}7/8)+9)$	-644267	$(1^2*((-3-4)^{\wedge}5+6)-7^{\wedge}8)/9$
-419706	$12^*((3^4*5-6^{\wedge}7)/8+9)$	-649213	$1-((2+3)^{\wedge}(-4-(-5-6))+7^{\wedge}8)/9$
-420102	$-12^*((3^4*5+6^{\wedge}7)/8+9)$	-649215	$-1-((2+3)^{\wedge}(-4-(-5-6))+7^{\wedge}8)/9$
-434025	$(1-2^*(-3^4+5^{\wedge}((-6+7)+8)))/9$	-659372	$-1/2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6^7-8-9)$
-439200	$((1-(-2^*3+4^{\wedge}5)^*6)+7)^8*9$	-659380	$1/2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*-6^7-8+9)$
-441180	$12^*((3-4^{\wedge}(5-(6-7)))+8)^9$	-659381	$-1/2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6^7-8+9)$
-442352	$(-1+2^*((3^*-4)^{\wedge}5+6)+7)^8/9$	-659389	$1/2^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*-6^7-8-9)$
-442384	$(-1+2^*((3^4)^{\wedge}5+6)+7)^*-8/9$	-661550	$(-1-((2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6-7^{\wedge}8))/9$
-443556	$12^*((3+4^{\wedge}(5-(6-7)))+8)^*-9$	-666562	$((1-23)^{\wedge}4-5-(-6-7^{\wedge}8))/-9$
-445907	$(1-(2^*3^*-4)^{\wedge}5)/((-6/7-8)-9)$	-668158	$1-(2/34)^{\wedge}((-5-6)+7)^8+9$
-447525	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3^4))^*(5-6/7+8)^9$	-668176	$1-(2/34)^{\wedge}((-5-6)+7)^8-9$
-447890	$1^2*(3+4/-5^*((6^{\wedge}7+8)-9))$	-668178	$(-1+(2/34)^{\wedge}((-5-6)+7)^*-8)-9$
-447902	$1^2*(-3-4/5^*((6^{\wedge}7+8)-9))$	-679396	$(-1-((2+34)^{\wedge}5+6^7))/89$
-460530	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))^5*6^*7^*(8+9)$	-684336	$((1-23)^*(4^{\wedge}5+6^{\wedge}7)+8)/9$
-466492	$1^2*(34-5^*6^{\wedge}((7+8)-9))$	-688110	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^{\wedge}5*6^*-7^*8+9)$
-466628	$1^*-2^*(34-5^*-6^{\wedge}((7+8)-9))$	-688146	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4^{\wedge}5*6^*7^*8+9)$
-472328	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^4)-5)-67)^*-8/9$	-689339	$((1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^*-6-7)/(8+9)$
-472388	$((-1/2+3+(4+5)^{\wedge}6)-7)^*-8/9$	-693351	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}-3+4)^*5/(-6^{\wedge}-7^*8)+9$
-472396	$((-1/2+3-(4+5)^{\wedge}6)-7)^*8/9$	-693369	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}-3+4)^*5/(-6^{\wedge}-7^*8)-9$
-476757	$(-1-2)^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6^7+8)+9$	-699037	$1/(2^3)^*(4^{\wedge}5+6)-7+89)$
-476775	$(-1-2)^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6^7+8)-9$	-699060	$1/2^*3^*((-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*8)/9)$
-481914	$123/4^*((-5^{\wedge}6-7^*8)+9)$	-699069	$1/(2^*-3)^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^*8)-9$
-482291	$(-123^4*(5+6)-7)^8*9$	-703826	$1-(2-3-4)^*-5^{\wedge}6+7^8)^9$
-484158	$(1+2-34)^*(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}(-8+9))$	-703828	$-1-((2-3-4)^*5^{\wedge}6+7^8)^9$
-502038	$1^2*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^{\wedge}7^*8)/9$	-715151	$(-1-23^{\wedge}((4-5)+6)-7-8)/9$
-510705	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3^4))^*(5+6/7+8)^9$	-715369	$1^2*3^*((-4+5-6^{\wedge}7)+8)/9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-715415	$1*23*((4-5-6^7)-8)/9$	-1171238	$(1-23)^4*-5-6*7/(8-9)$
-718999	$(-1-23*((-4-5)^6-7))/(8+9)$	-1171274	$((1-23)^4*-5-6/(7-8)^9)$
-734655	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))^5*67*(8+9)$	-1195740	$((1-2*(3+(4+5)^6))+7)/8*9$
-746295	$(1+2)*((-3*4)^5+67)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-1208367	$(1+((2*3)^4-5))*(-6-7)^8*9$
-749352	$12*(3-4*((5^6-7)-8)-9)$	-1208385	$(-1+((2*3)^4-5))*(-6-7)^8*9$
-750648	$-12*(3+4*((5^6+7)+8)-9)$	-1234872	$((1-2)+3)*4*5*-6*7*8*9$
-751626	$(-1-(2/34)^{\wedge}(-5-6+7)+8)*9$	-1250550	$1+(2-3*4)*(5^6+7)*8+9$
-751752	$(-1+(2/34)^{\wedge}(-5-6+7)+8)*-9$	-1250552	$-1+(2-3*4)*(5^6+7)*8+9$
-751770	$((-1-(2/34)^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))-8)*9$	-1250568	$1+(2-3*4)*(5^6+7)*8-9$
-757568	$(1-2+3*-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^8)/9$	-1250570	$-1+(2-3*4)*(5^6+7)*8-9$
-759354	$12-(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)+9$	-1259370	$(1/2*(3*4*5-6^7)+8)*9$
-759396	$-12-(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)-9$	-1259512	$((1/2-3^{\wedge}(-4-5))/-6^{\wedge}-7+8)*9$
-767999	$1-2*3*4*5*(6-7*(-8-9))$	-1259912	$((-1/2-3^{\wedge}(-4-5))/6^{\wedge}-7-8)*9$
-768001	$-1-2*3*4*5*(6-7*(-8-9))$	-1260054	$(1/2*(3*4*5-6^7)-8)*9$
-790551	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))/(6*7)*(-8-9)$	-1262097	$-1+(((2/34)^{\wedge}-5-6)+7)*-8/9$
-791316	$(12^{\wedge}3-4)*5*6*(-7-8)-9$	-1265058	$1^2*-3^4*(5^6+7/(8-9))$
-794988	$(12^{\wedge}3+4)*5*6*(-7-8)-9$	-1302081	$((1-(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))*6+7)+8)/9$
-808569	$((12^{\wedge}3*(4-56)+7)+8)*9$	-1311492	$12*(3*4-5^6)*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-813626	$((-1-2)*(3-4*5)^6-7)/89$	-1312437	$12*(3/4-5^6)*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-826182	$(12-3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-1364370	$(1+2+3^{\wedge}((-4+5)+6))*-7*89$
-838880	$1/(2+3)*((-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)-89)$	-1368899	$1-(234*5)^{\wedge}(-6-(-7+8-9))$
-843083	$1+2*3*((4-5^6)+7)+8*9$	-1368901	$-1-(234*5)^{\wedge}(-6-(-7+8-9))$
-843085	$-1+(2*3*(4-5^6)+7)+8*9$	-1371825	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3*4))*-5*6*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-843659	$1-(2*-3*(-4-5^6+7)+8)*9$	-1379537	$((1-23)^4+5)*(-6-(7-8)/9)$
-843661	$-1-(2*-3*(-4-5^6+7)+8)*9$	-1388745	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))*5/6^{\wedge}-7/(8-9)$
-843839	$1+2*-3*(-4+5^6+7)+8*9$	-1398083	$(-1-2-3*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7*8))/9$
-843841	$-1+(2*-3*(-4+5^6+7)+8)*9$	-1405499	$((1-23)^4-5)*-6-7/(8-9)$
-844415	$1-(2*3*((4+5^6)+7)+8)*9$	-1405506	$((1-23)^4-5)*6/(7-8)^9$
-844417	$-1-(2*3*((4+5^6)+7)+8)*9$	-1405513	$((1-23)^4-5)*-6+7/(8-9)$
-852992	$1*2^{\wedge}(3+4)*5*6*7*(-8-9)$	-1405573	$((1-23)^4+5)*-6+7/(8-9)$
-853631	$((1-(2*3*4)^5+6^7)+8)/9$	-1416192	$-12*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6+7-89$
-853633	$((-1+(2*3*-4)^5+6^7)-8)/9$	-1418160	$-12*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6-(7-89)$
-854298	$((-1-2-3*4)^5+6)-7)/8*9$	-1422512	$(1-23*4)*(5^6+7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-859656	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))*5*6*7*(8+9)$	-1431595	$((1-23)^4+5)*(-6+(7-8)/9)$
-876305	$-1*((2*3)^4+5^6+7*8+9)$	-1441162	$12*3+4^{\wedge}(5-6)*(-7^8+9)$
-915839	$((1-(2*3*4)^5-6^7)+8)/9$	-1441234	$-12*3+4^{\wedge}(5-6)*(-7^8+9)$
-915841	$((-1+(2*3*-4)^5-6^7)-8)/9$	-1457427	$(-1-2+(3*4)^5)*(-6+7^{\wedge}(8-9))$
-922369	$1/((2+3)/(4/5*(6-7^8)-9))$	-1461398	$((1+23/4)*(-5-6*7)-8)/9$
-925470	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3*4))*5+(-6-7)*(-8-9))$	-1472023	$(1+(2*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5))*6+7)/89$
-925922	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3*4))*5+(-6-7)*(-8-9))$	-1493856	$(-12-(3*4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))*8*9$
-975888	$(1^{\wedge}2+3)^4-5*-6^7/(8*9)$	-1503908	$1/23*(-4^5-6*(7^8+9))$
-979750	$1/2*(3+4)*(5-6^7)+8+9$	-1518731	$1-2*((3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)-9)$
-979802	$1/2*((-3-4)*(5+6^7)-8-9)$	-1518732	$1*2*((-3/45)^{\wedge}((-6-7)+8)+9)$
-1007763	$((12*3)^4-5-6)/(-7-8)*9$	-1518733	$-1-2*((3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)-9)$
-1023490	$(1/2-3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6*7*8/9$	-1518767	$1-2*((3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)+9)$
-1023542	$(1/2+3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6*7*8/9$	-1518768	$1*-2*((3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7)+8)+9$
-1026720	$((-1-(2*3)^4)*(5+6)+7)*8*9$	-1518769	$-1-2*((3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)+9)$
-1037640	$1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)*(5/6^{\wedge}-7-8^9)$	-1519097	$(1*2+(-3-4)/5^{\wedge}(6-7-8))/9$
-1037642	$-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)*(5/6^{\wedge}-7-8^9)$	-1528521	$(-1-2+(3*4)^5)*(-6-7^{\wedge}(8-9))$
-1046998	$1*2*-3*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^8)/9$	-1534680	$(-1-2)*((3-4+5)+6)*7*-8*9$
-1047344	$(1-2*34)*(5^6+7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-1561896	$(-1-2)*((3+4^5)+6)*7*8*9$
-1059510	$1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)*(5/6^{\wedge}-7+8^9)$	-1562112	$12^{\wedge}3*-4*(5+(-6-7)*(-8-9))$
-1059512	$-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)*(5/6^{\wedge}-7+8^9)$	-1577917	$(1-23*4^5)*6*7*(-8+9)$
-1062075	$((-1+2)*-3+4*(-5^6+7))*8+9$	-1593771	$(-1-2)*((34*5^6+7^{\wedge}(-8+9))$
-1071224	$1-(23*45)^{\wedge}(-6-(-7+8-9))$	-1605240	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3*4))*-5*6*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-1071225	$-1/(23*45)^{\wedge}(6-7-(-8+9))$	-1653338	$1*-2*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6*7*(-8+9)$
-1071226	$-1-(23*45)^{\wedge}(-6-(-7+8-9))$	-1653406	$1*-2*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6*7+8+9$
-1074194	$(-1*2-3/4)*((5/(6-7))^8-9)$	-1674091	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))*-6/7+8+9$
-1078488	$(-1-2)*(3*4*5*(6+7)+8)*9$	-1674109	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))*-6/7+8-9$
-1082621	$-1/2*((3-4+(5+6)^7)+8)/9$	-1674125	$((1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))*-6/7-8)-9$
-1101240	$1*(-2+3^{\wedge}((-4+5)+6))*7*-8*9$	-1677340	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))-5)/6^{\wedge}-7+89$
-1102221	$(1+2-3^{\wedge}((-4+5)+6))*7*8*9$	-1677518	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))-5)/6^{\wedge}-7-89$
-1102275	$(-1-2-3^{\wedge}((-4+5)+6))*7*8*9$	-1679380	$1*2*((-3*(-4+5+6^7)-8)-9)$
-1103256	$1*(-2-3^{\wedge}((-4+5)+6))*7*8*9$	-1681714	$((-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))-5)/6^{\wedge}-7+89$
-1107414	$(-1+(2+3)+4)*5^6*7/-8*9$	-1681892	$((-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))-5)/6^{\wedge}-7-89$
-1117468	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)/6^{\wedge}-7+89$	-1693260	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3*4))+5)*6*(78-9)$
-1117557	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)*6^7/(8-9)$	-1698228	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3*4))+5)*-6*(78-9)$
-1117646	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)/6^{\wedge}-7-89$	-1793529	$(-12+3*((4+5)^6+7)/8)*-9$
-1118472	$(1-2^{\wedge}((-3+4-5)*-6))/(7+8)+9$	-1793583	$(1-(2+3*((4+5)^6-7))/8)*9$
-1118490	$(1-2^{\wedge}((-3+4-5)*-6))/(7+8)-9$	-1793591	$1-(2-3*((4+5)^6-7))/-8*9$
-1121842	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)/6^{\wedge}-7+89$	-1793593	$-1-(2-3*((4+5)^6-7))/-8*9$
-1122020	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)/6^{\wedge}-7-89$	-1793745	$(-12-3*((4+5)^6+7)/8)*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1796001	$((-1-23)^{4+5}) * (-6+(-7-8)/9)$	-2379539	$-1/2 * (3^4 + (-5-6^7)) * (-8-9)$
-1844436	$(-12+(3^4)^{(5+6-7)}) * -89$	-2388582	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)^5) * 6^* - 7^* 89$
-1846572	$(-12-(3^4)^{(5+6-7)}) * 89$	-2396058	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)^5) * 6^* 7^* 89$
-1855426	$(1-23/4) * ((5/(6-7))^{\wedge} 8-9)$	-2428704	$12^* (-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) / 7^* 8^* 9$
-1860019	$(-1/2-3) * ((4+5)^{\wedge} 6-7^{\wedge} (-8+9))$	-2467725	$((12+3)^{\wedge} 4-5) * 6^* (7/8-9)$
-1866187	$(-1-2-3^* - 4^* 5^* (-6^{\wedge} 7+8)) / 9$	-2472679	$((1/(2^* 3)-4)-5) * 6^{\wedge} 7+89$
-1866293	$(1+2+3^* - 4^* 5^* (6^{\wedge} 7+8)) / 9$	-2472857	$((1/(2^* 3)-4)-5) * 6^{\wedge} 7-89$
-1958488	$(1-23^{4+56}) * 7^{\wedge} (-8+9)$	-2479158	$1^* 2^* ((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * 7+8) * 9$
-1958873	$(1-23^{4-5+6}) * 7^{\wedge} (-8+9)$	-2479194	$-12^* (3^{\wedge}(4+5) / 6^* 7-8) * 9$
-1984626	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5)) / (6/7+8) * 9$	-2479446	$1^* - 2^* ((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * - 7+8) * 9$
-1990619	$((1+23)^{\wedge} 4-5) * -6-7 / (8-9)$	-2480670	$1^* 2^* ((3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * - 7+8) * 9$
-1990626	$((1+23)^{\wedge} 4-5) * 6 / (7-8) \wedge 9$	-2480958	$1^* - 2^* ((3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * 7+8) * 9$
-1990693	$((1+23)^{\wedge} 4+5) * -6+7 / (8-9)$	-2499728	$1-(2+3) * (4^* 5^{\wedge} 6-7) * 8-9$
-1992885	$((1+2)^{\wedge} 3(3^* 4)-5) * (6^* 7^* 8-9)$	-2499730	$-1-(2+3) * (4^* 5^{\wedge} 6-7) * 8-9$
-2000103	$1^* - 2^{\wedge}(3+4) * (5^{\wedge} 6+7/8)+9$	-2499934	$1+(2+3) * -4^* 5^{\wedge} 6+7) * 8+9$
-2000121	$1^* - 2^{\wedge}(3+4) * (5^{\wedge} 6+7/8)-9$	-2499936	$-1+(2+3) * -4^* 5^{\wedge} 6+7) * 8+9$
-2013106	$((-1+23) * (4-(5+6)))^{\wedge} 7-8) / 9$	-2499952	$1+(2+3) * -4^* 5^{\wedge} 6+7) * 8-9$
-2014722	$(-1-(2+3) * (4+5)) * (5^{\wedge} 6-7^{\wedge} (-8+9))$	-2499954	$-1+(2+3) * -4^* 5^{\wedge} 6+7) * 8-9$
-2015625	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)) * 5^{\wedge} 6^* (-7+8) \wedge 9$	-2500290	$-1+(-2-3) * (4^* 5^{\wedge} 6+7) * 8-9$
-2046408	$12^* (3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6) * 78 / -9$	-2517021	$((-1+(2^* 3)^{\wedge} 4) / 5-6^{\wedge} 7+8) * 9$
-2046971	$(1/2-3^{\wedge}(4+5)) * (6+7) * 8+9$	-2520395	$1-((2+3) * 4^* 5+6^{\wedge} 7+8) * 9$
-2046989	$(1/2-3^{\wedge}(4+5)) * (6+7) * 8-9$	-2521827	$((-1+(2^* 3)^{\wedge} 4) / -5-6^{\wedge} 7-8) * 9$
-2047075	$(1/2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)) * (-6-7) * 8+9$	-2546875	$(-1-2/3^{\wedge} 4) * 5^{\wedge} 6^* (-7+8) \wedge 9$
-2047093	$(1/2+3^{\wedge}(4+5)) * (-6-7) * 8-9$	-2562149	$-1+(-2^{\wedge} 3+4^* (-5^* 6-7^{\wedge} 8)) / 9$
-2047656	$12^* (-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6) * 78 / 9$	-2567999	$(1-(-2-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)) / -6^* (7+8/9)$
-2050311	$1/2^* (3-45^{\wedge} (-6-7-(-8-9)))$	-2576809	$(1-23)^{\wedge} 4^* (-5-6)-7^* (8-9)$
-2050314	$-1/2^* (3+45^{\wedge} (-6-7-(-8-9)))$	-2624993	$(1-2^* 3^* 4^* 5^{\wedge} 6) * 7 / (-8+9)$
-2096900	$(1/2+3) * (-4^{\wedge}(5+6) / 7+8) * 9$	-2637488	$1^* 2^* ((-3^{\wedge}(4+5) * 6+7+8)+9)$
-2097058	$1/2^* ((3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))+7)+89$	-2637556	$1^* 2^* ((-3^{\wedge}(4+5) * 6+7-8)-9)$
-2097111	$1/2^* (3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7+8) * 9$	-2657163	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^* 4) * -5+6/7^{\wedge}(8-9))$
-2097114	$1/2^* ((-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))+7+8) * 9$	-2691468	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)^5) * 6^* - 7^* 8^* 9$
-2097190	$1/2^* ((3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))-7-8) * 9$	-2699892	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)^5) * 6^* 7^* 8^* 9$
-2097193	$-1/2^* (3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7+8) * 9$	-2782520	$-1/23^* ((4^* 5)^{\wedge} 6+7)+89$
-2097246	$-1/2^* ((-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))-7)-89$	-2782698	$-1/23^* ((4^* 5)^{\wedge} 6+7)-89$
-2097404	$(1/2+3) * (-4^{\wedge}(5+6) / 7-8) * 9$	-2796109	$1^* 2/3^* (-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)+89$
-2099486	$1^* 2^* ((-3/4^* 5^* 6^{\wedge} 7+8)+9)$	-2796181	$-1^* (2/3^* (4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)-8)+9$
-2099554	$1^* 2^* ((3/4^* -5^* 6^{\wedge} 7-8)-9)$	-2796208	$1^* 2 / -3^* (4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7-(8-9))$
-2120940	$(12^* 3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^* 7^* 8) * -9$	-2796282	$1^* 2/3^* (-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^* (8+9))$
-2121552	$(12^* 3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^* 7^* 8) * -9$	-2796287	$1^* 2/3^* (-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)-89$
-2125485	$(1-2^* (3^{\wedge}(4+5) * 6-7-8)) * 9$	-2796618	$1^* 2 / -3^* (4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^* -89)$
-2125503	$(-1-2^* (3^{\wedge}(4+5) * 6-7-8)) * 9$	-2809799	$1-(2+3) * 4^* (5^{\wedge} 6-(7+8)) * 9$
-2126025	$(1+2^* (3^{\wedge}(4+5) * 6-7-8)) * 9$	-2809801	$-1-(2+3) * 4^* (5^{\wedge} 6-(7+8)) * 9$
-2126043	$(1-2^* (3^{\wedge}(4+5) * 6-7-8)) * -9$	-2813831	$1+((2+3) * -4^* (5^{\wedge} 6+7)-8) * 9$
-2129976	$(12^* 3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^* 7^* 8) * -9$	-2813833	$-1+((2+3) * -4^* (5^{\wedge} 6+7)-8) * 9$
-2130588	$(12^* 3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^* 7^* 8) * -9$	-2826539	$1-(2+3) * 4^* (5^{\wedge} 6+7^* 8) * 9$
-2134980	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3^* 4))+5) * 6^* (7+8+9)$	-2826541	$-1-(2+3) * 4^* (5^{\wedge} 6+7^* 8) * 9$
-2141244	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^* 4))+5) * -6^* (7+8+9)$	-2831319	$(1+(-2^* 3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^* 7) * 8) * 9$
-2178576	$(-123^* -4)^{\wedge} (-5^* 6 / (-7-8)) * -9$	-2831337	$(-1-(2^* 3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^* 7) * 8) * 9$
-2187410	$1-(2+3) * 4^* 5^{\wedge} 6^* 7+89$	-2832480	$1^* 2^* (-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6+7) * 8^* 9$
-2187412	$-1-(2+3) * 4^* 5^{\wedge} 6^* 7+89$	-2836224	$1^* 2^* (3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6+7) * -8^* 9$
-2187427	$1-(2+3) * 4^* 5^{\wedge} 6^* 7+8^* 9$	-2837367	$(1+(-2^* 3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^* 7) * 8) * 9$
-2187429	$-1-(2+3) * 4^* 5^{\wedge} 6^* 7+8^* 9$	-2837385	$(-1-(2^* 3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6^* 7) * 8) * 9$
-2187588	$1-(2+3) * 4^* 5^{\wedge} 6^* 7-89$	-2985956	$-12^* ((3^* 4)^{\wedge} 5 - ((6+7)+8) / 9)$
-2187590	$-1-(2+3) * 4^* 5^{\wedge} 6^* 7-89$	-2986012	$-12^* ((3^* 4)^{\wedge} 5 + ((6+7)+8) / 9)$
-2203806	$1^* 2^* ((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * 7^* 8+9)$	-2986788	$12^* ((-3^* 4)^{\wedge} 5 - 67)^{\wedge} (-8+9)$
-2203815	$1^* 2^* (-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * 7^* 8+9$	-2999235	$((12+3)^{\wedge} 4-5) * -6^* (7/8+9)$
-2203833	$1^* 2^* (-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * 7^* 8-9$	-3045263	$((1-23)^{\wedge} 4-5) * (-6-7)^{\wedge} (-8+9)$
-2203842	$1^* - 2^* ((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * - 7^* 8+9)$	-3069594	$1^* 2^* ((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * 7^* 8+9)$
-2205150	$1^* 2^* ((3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * - 7^* 8+9)$	-3069630	$1^* 2^* ((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * 7^* 8-9)$
-2205159	$1^* 2^* (3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * - 7^* 8+9$	-3071466	$1^* 2^* ((-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6) * 7^* 8+9)$
-2205177	$1^* 2^* (3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * - 7^* 8-9$	-3071502	$1^* - 2^* ((3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * 7^* 8+9)$
-2205186	$1^* - 2^* ((3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6) * 7^* 8+9)$	-3082536	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)^5) * 6^* 7^* - 8^* 9$
-2237440	$1^* 23^* -4^{\wedge} 5^* ((-6-7) * -8-9)$	-3083670	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4) * -5^* 6^* (7^* 8-9)$
-2242944	$((1+2+3^{\wedge} 4)+5) / 6^{\wedge} -7 / (8-9)$	-3092184	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)^5) * 6^* 7^* 8^* 9$
-2278098	$(-1-2) * ((3/45)^{\wedge} (-6-7+8)-9)$	-3094253	$1+((2+3/4) * -5^{\wedge} 6-7) * 8^* 9$
-2278152	$(-1-2) * ((3/45)^{\wedge} (-6-7+8)+9)$	-3094255	$-1+((2+3/4) * -5^{\wedge} 6-7) * 8^* 9$
-2359092	$12^* (-3^* 4^{\wedge} (-5+6+7)+8+9)$	-3171577	$(1+23^{\wedge} 4-5) * (6+7^{\wedge} 8) / 9$
-2359500	$-12^* ((3^* 4^{\wedge} (56/7)+8)+9)$	-3188497	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^* 4)-5) * -6+7^* (8+9)$
-2370371	$(-1-2)^{\wedge} -3^* ((4^* 5)^{\wedge} 6-7)-8/9$	-3188758	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^* 4)+5) * -6+7-89$
-2374934	$1+((23-4) * -5^{\wedge} 6+7) * 8+9$	-3188795	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^* 4)+5) * -6-7^* (8+9)$
-2374936	$-1+((23-4) * -5^{\wedge} 6+7) * 8+9$	-3195936	$12^* (-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^{\wedge} 7) * 8/9$
-2379373	$1/2^* (3^{\wedge} 4+(-5+6^{\wedge} 7)) * (-8-9)$	-3202635	$12^* 3+(-4+5^* (-6-7^{\wedge} 8)) / 9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-3202638	$(-1+234+5*(6-7^{\wedge}8))/9$	-5040009	$((-1-2*(3*4*5+6^{\wedge}7))-8)*9$
-3202690	$(-1-234+5*(6-7^{\wedge}8))/9$	-5044210	$((-1-2*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)-7)/8-9$
-3202707	$-12*3+(-4+5*(-6-7^{\wedge}8))/9$	-5057208	$((1-2)+3)*(4^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)+8)*9$
-3228504	$(1*2*3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)*(7-8-9)$	-5057352	$((1-2)+3)*(4^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)-8)*9$
-3283200	$12^{\wedge}3*4*-5*((-6-7)^*-8-9)$	-5062634	$1+((2+34)^*-5^{\wedge}6-(7+8))*9$
-3296475	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3*4))*5*6*(7+8)*9$	-5062636	$-1+((2+34)^*-5^{\wedge}6-(7+8))*9$
-3298085	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3*4))*5*6*(7+8)*9$	-5124217	$(1+2*(3+4*(56-7^{\wedge}8)))/9$
-3374811	$(-1+2*(3*4*5^{\wedge}6+7)+8)*9$	-5227322	$-1+((23-4)^{\wedge}(5-(6-7))+8)/-9$
-3375189	$(1-2*(3*4*5^{\wedge}6+7)-8)*9$	-5249495	$1+((2/3+4)^*-5^{\wedge}6+7)*8*9$
-3389137	$((1+23^{\wedge}4)-5)*(-6-7+8/9)$	-5249497	$-1+((2/3+4)^*-5^{\wedge}6+7)*8*9$
-3435828	$((1-23)^{\wedge}4+5)*(-6+78/-9)$	-5249748	$12*(3-4*5^{\wedge}6)*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-3483444	$12*((-3*4)^{\wedge}5/6*7+8)+9$	-5273146	$(-1-((2+3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)-8))/9$
-3483599	$(1-2*(3*4)^{\wedge}5+6)*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-5311904	$1-(2+3)*(4*5^{\wedge}6-7)*(8+9)$
-3483852	$-12*((3*4)^{\wedge}5/6*7+8)+9$	-5311906	$-1-(2+3)*(4*5^{\wedge}6-7)*(8+9)$
-3495255	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3*(4+5)-6))*(7+8)/9$	-5312618	$1+((2+3)^*-4*5^{\wedge}6-7)*(8+9)$
-3511808	$-1*((-2*(-3^{\wedge}4+5))^{\wedge}(6/(7-8)+9))$	-5314879	$1-(2+3)*4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)*(8+9)$
-3520000	$(1-23)*(4*5)^{\wedge}((-6-7+8)+9)$	-5314881	$-1-(2+3)*4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)*(8+9)$
-3542922	$1*2*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6*(-7-8+9)$	-5359375	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*-5^{\wedge}6*7^{\wedge}(8-9)$
-3542958	$1*-2*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6*(7+8)+9$	-5363887	$(-1-2*((3-4*5)^{\wedge}6-78))/9$
-3595506	$(-1+(2+3)*(4*5)^{\wedge}6+7)/-8-9$	-5365348	$1*23*(4-5*6^{\wedge}(7+8)-9)$
-3612168	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)*56)*7*-8*9$	-5365532	$1*-23*(4-5*-6^{\wedge}(7+8)-9)$
-3613176	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)*56)*7*8*9$	-5508216	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)*5+6)*7*8*9$
-3637855	$(1-23^{\wedge}4+5)*(6+7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-5514264	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)*5+6)*7*-8*9$
-3649529	$(1+23)^{\wedge}4*(-5-6)-7*(8-9)$	-5546880	$((1+2)^{\wedge}3-4)*5/6^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-3680000	$1*-23*(4*5)^{\wedge}((-6-7+8)+9)$	-5622479	$1+(-2+3+4)*(5^{\wedge}6+7)*8*9$
-3795174	$(1+2)/3^{\wedge}4*(-5^{\wedge}6+7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-5622481	$-1+(-2+3+4)*(5^{\wedge}6+7)*8*9$
-3796848	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6*(-7+8)-9)$	-5835554	$1/23*((4-(5+6))-7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-3840000	$(-1-23)*(4*5)^{\wedge}((-6-7+8)+9)$	-5845844	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3*4)*(-5-6)-7*(8-9)$
-3886625	$((1+23^{\wedge}4)-5)*(-6-7-8/9)$	-5971759	$((-1-2)*(3*4)^{\wedge}5-6+7)*8+9$
-3975966	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)*5*6*-7+8)*9$	-5971942	$1-2*((3*4)^{\wedge}5-(6-7))-8+9$
-3979576	$((-12^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^{\wedge}6+7)-8)/9$	-5971994	$(-1-2*((3*4)^{\wedge}5-(6-7))+8)-9$
-4084034	$(-1+(-2-3)*4)^{\wedge}5-6*7*(8-9)$	-5972177	$((1+2)*((3*-4)^{\wedge}5-6)-7)*8-9$
-4100622	$(-1+2)*3-45^{\wedge}(-6-7-(8-9))$	-6013440	$(-1+(2/34)^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))*-8*9$
-4100628	$(1-2)*3-45^{\wedge}(-6-7-(8-9))$	-6013503	$(1+(2/34)^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))*-8*9$
-4133358	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)*5*6*-7+8)*9$	-6013511	$1+(2/34)^{\wedge}(-5-6+7)*-8*9$
-4133502	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(3+4)*5*6*7-8)*9$	-6013513	$-1+(2/34)^{\wedge}(-5-6+7)*-8*9$
-4169763	$1-(2*(3-4^{\wedge}5))^{\wedge}(-6+7-8+9)$	-6013521	$(-1-(2/34)^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))*8*9$
-4169765	$1-(2*(3-4^{\wedge}5))^{\wedge}(-6+7-8+9)$	-6013584	$(-1-(2/34)^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))*8*9$
-4218915	$1-(2*(3+4^{\wedge}5))^{\wedge}(-6+7-8+9)$	-6015436	$1/23*-4*(5+6*(7^{\wedge}8-9))$
-4218917	$1-(2*(3+4^{\wedge}5))^{\wedge}(-6+7-8+9)$	-6095239	$((-1+2*-3*(4*5)^{\wedge}6)/7-8)/9$
-4290894	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)*5*6*7+8)*-9$	-6291419	$1/2*(-3*4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7*8)+9$
-4313023	$((1+23)^{\wedge}4-5)*(-6+7*(8-9))$	-6291493	$1/2*(-3*4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7*8)-9$
-4327786	$(-1-((2-3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)-8))/9$	-6399982	$((1-2)+3)*((-4*5)^{\wedge}(6+7-8)+9)$
-4394430	$(-12+3/4)*((5*(6-7))^{\wedge}8-9)$	-6400018	$((-1+2)-3)*((4*5)^{\wedge}(6+7-8)+9)$
-4476834	$1*2*((3*45-6^{\wedge}7)*8-9)$	-6480000	$-1/2*(3*4*5)^{\wedge}(-6-7-(8-9))$
-4478647	$((1-2)+3)*(4*5-6^{\wedge}7)*8+9$	-6495752	$(-1+2)/3*((4-(5+6)^{\wedge}7)-8-9)$
-4478665	$((1-2)+3)*(4*5-6^{\wedge}7)*8-9$	-6705342	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)*6^{\wedge}(7-(8-9))$
-4479287	$((-1+2)-3)*(4*5+6^{\wedge}7)*8+9$	-6716583	$((1+2)*((3*-4)^{\wedge}5+6+7)+8)*9$
-4479305	$((-1+2)-3)*(4*5+6^{\wedge}7)*8-9$	-6717744	$12*3*4*(5-6^{\wedge}(7+8-9))$
-4481118	$1*2*((3*45+6^{\wedge}7)*-8+9)$	-6717948	$(-1-2)*((-3-(4*5-6^{\wedge}7)*8)-9)$
-4499934	$1+((2+34)^*-5^{\wedge}6+7)*8+9$	-6718020	$(1+2)*((-3+(4*5-6^{\wedge}7)*8)-9)$
-4499936	$-1+((2+34)^*-5^{\wedge}6+7)*8+9$	-6718908	$(-1-2)*((-3+(4*5+6^{\wedge}7)*8)-9)$
-4605678	$1*2*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))*(-6-7)+8)*9$	-6718980	$(1+2)*((-3-(4*5+6^{\wedge}7)*8)-9)$
-4605966	$1*-2*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5))*(-6-7)+8)*9$	-6719184	$12*3*-4*(5+6^{\wedge}(7+8-9))$
-4641128	$1+((2^{\wedge}-3+4)^*-5^{\wedge}6-7)*8*9$	-6720345	$((-1-2)*((3*4)^{\wedge}5+6+7)-8)*9$
-4641130	$-1+((2^{\wedge}-3+4)^*-5^{\wedge}6-7)*8*9$	-6746976	$-12^{\wedge}3/4*(5^{\wedge}6+7/(8-9))$
-4683126	$1*2*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)*7*(8+9)$	-6811776	$(-1-2)*(3*-4)^{\wedge}5*(6-7)/8-9$
-4685982	$1*2*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)*-7*(8+9)$	-6834267	$(12-(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7)+8)*9$
-4740741	$(1-2/3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7)-8)/9$	-6834348	$(1+2-(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8))*9$
-4980354	$(-12-3/4)*((5*(6-7))^{\wedge}8-9)$	-6834356	$1+(2-(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8))*9$
-5020344	$((1-2)+3)*(4^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)+8)*9$	-6834357	$(1*2+(-3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8))*9$
-5020488	$((1-2)+3)*(4^{\wedge}5-6^{\wedge}7)-8)*9$	-6834363	$12-(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7)+8)*9$
-5037687	$((1+2*(3*4*5-6^{\wedge}7))+8)*9$	-6834372	$1+2-(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)*9$
-5037705	$(-1+2*(3*4*5-6^{\wedge}7)+8)*9$	-6834373	$1*2-(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7)+8)*9$
-5038336	$(1/2-3^{\wedge}(-4-5))*6/(7-8)^{\wedge}9$	-6834377	$-1*2+(3/-45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)*9$
-5038416	$((1-2)+3)*(4*5-6^{\wedge}7)+8)*9$	-6834378	$(-1-2)-(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8)*9$
-5038648	$(1*(-2+3^{\wedge}(-4-5))*6^{\wedge}7+8)*9$	-6834387	$-12-(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7)+8)*9$
-5038814	$((1-2)+3)*((-4-5)/6^{\wedge}7+8+9)$	-6834393	$(1*-2-(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8))*9$
-5038882	$((1-2)+3)*(4+5)*-6^{\wedge}7-8-9)$	-6834394	$-1-(2+(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8))*9$
-5039280	$((-1+2)-3)*(4*5+6^{\wedge}7)-8)*9$	-6834402	$(-1-2-(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8))*9$
-5039360	$(1/2+3^{\wedge}(-4-5))*6/(7-8)^{\wedge}9$	-6834483	$(-12-(3/45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8))*9$
-5039991	$(1-2*(3*4*5+6^{\wedge}7)-8)*9$	-6918223	$((1-(-2+3^{\wedge}(4*5)))+6)/(7*8*9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-7111096	$12+3+((4*5)^6+7)-8)/-9$	-10038075	$(1/2-3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6-7*8*-9$
-7111126	$(-12-3)+((4*5)^6+7)-8)/-9$	-10038585	$(-1/2-3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6-7*8*-9$
-7171993	$1+((23+4)^*-5^{\wedge}6-7)*(8+9)$	-10064574	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))-5)*6^{\wedge}(7-(8-9))$
-7171995	$-1+((23+4)^*-5^{\wedge}6-7)*(8+9)$	-10077501	$(1+2)^*(3*4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)+8)-9$
-7340014	$((1-2)+3)*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)*7/-8+9)$	-10077891	$(-1-2)*(3*-4*(-5-6^{\wedge}7)+8)+9$
-7340050	$((-1+2)-3)*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)*7/8+9)$	-10090818	$((-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))-5)*6^{\wedge}(7-(8-9))$
-7433280	$(-1+(2/34)^{\wedge}((-5-6)+7))*-89$	-10157091	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(3*4+5)+6)*7/89$
-7433458	$(-1-(2/34)^{\wedge}((-5-6)+7))*89$	-10251561	$1/2*(3-45^{\wedge}(6+7-8)/9)$
-7456528	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3-4*-5))+6+7)*8/9$	-10251564	$1/-2*(3+45^{\wedge}(6+7-8)/9)$
-7572963	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3*4)-5)*(-6*7/8-9)$	-10253892	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))*-6*7/8+9$
-7619441	$((1-23*4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)+8)/-9$	-10253910	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))*-6*7/8-9$
-7684056	$-123*4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-10321920	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4-5))/(6+7)*8/9$
-7874944	$(-1/((2+3)+4)+5^{\wedge}6)*7*-8*9$	-10471356	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)*5)*(6/(7-8))^{\wedge}9$
-7875056	$(-1/((2+3)+4)-5^{\wedge}6)*7*8*9$	-10690675	$(1/2-34^{\wedge}(5+6-7))*8+9$
-7959921	$(-1-(23*4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)+8)/9$	-10690683	$(-1/2-34^{\wedge}(5+6-7))*8+9$
-7971510	$((-12-3)*((4+5)^6+7/(8-9)))$	-10690693	$(1/2-34^{\wedge}(5+6-7))*8-9$
-8045865	$((-1-2)*((3-4*5)^6-78)/9)$	-10690701	$(-1/2-34^{\wedge}(5+6-7))*8-9$
-8172120	$123*((4+5)^6+7)/(-8-9)$	-10982835	$(1/2-3^{\wedge}(4+5))*(-6-7*8)*-9$
-8201243	$1+2*(3-45^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9)))$	-10983393	$(1/2+3^{\wedge}(4+5))*(-6-7*8)*9$
-8201244	$1*2*(3-45^{\wedge}(-6-((7-8)-9)))$	-11160254	$(-1+2-3*(4+5)^6)*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-8201245	$-1+2*(3-45^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9)))$	-11184829	$(-1-2-3*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)*8)/-9$
-8201255	$1-2*(3+45^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9)))$	-11184832	$(-1-2+3*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7))*8/9$
-8201256	$-1*2*(3+45^{\wedge}(-6-((7-8)-9)))$	-11184840	$(-12-3*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7))*8/9$
-8201257	$-1-2*(3+45^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9)))$	-11712599	$12-((3-(-4*5+6)^7)-8)/9$
-8387198	$1*2*(3-(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-78*9))$	-11712623	$-12-((3-(-4*5+6)^7)-8)/9$
-8387210	$1*-2*(3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)-78*9)$	-11753154	$((-1-23^{\wedge}4)+5)*6*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-8387356	$1*2*(3-(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7*89))$	-11756920	$((12*3)^{\wedge}4-56)*-7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-8387368	$1*-2*(3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7*89)$	-12011442	$-123/4*((5/(6-7))^{\wedge}8-9)$
-8387594	$1*2*(3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7*-8*9)$	-12301866	$(1+2)*(3-45^{\wedge}(-6-((7-8)-9)))$
-8387606	$1*-2*(3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7*8*9)$	-12301884	$(-1-2)*(3+45^{\wedge}(-6-7+8+9))$
-8389610	$1*2*(3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7*8*9)$	-12352176	$(-1+2^{\wedge}-3+45)*-6^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-8389622	$1*-2*(3-(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7*8*9))$	-12401589	$(1-2*(3-(4*-5+6)^7))/(8+9)$
-8389848	$1*2*(3-(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7*89))$	-12803125	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3*4)*5)^{\wedge}(6-(-7+8)^{\wedge}9)$
-8389860	$1*-2*(3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7*89)$	-12959988	$12-(3*4*5)^{\wedge}(-6-7-8-9))$
-8390006	$1*2*(3-(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7*8*9))$	-12959997	$1+2-(3*4*5)^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9))$
-8390018	$1*-2*(3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7*8*9)$	-12959998	$1*2-(3*4*5)^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9))$
-8483616	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5)*6^{\wedge}7/(8*9)$	-12959999	$1^{\wedge}2-(3*4*5)^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9))$
-8502588	$(-1-2*3^{\wedge}(4+5)*6+7)*8*9$	-12960001	$1-2-(3*4*5)^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9))$
-8503524	$(1/2-(3^{\wedge}(4+5)*6+7))*8*9$	-12960002	$-1*(2+(3*4*5)^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9)))$
-8522496	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3+4)+5)*6^{\wedge}7/(-8*9)$	-12960003	$-1-(2+(3*4*5)^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9)))$
-8607663	$123/4*((-5-6^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$	-12960012	$-12-(3*4*5)^{\wedge}(-6-7-(-8-9))$
-8607909	$123/4*((5-6^{\wedge}7)+8-9)$	-12991418	$1*2*3*(4+((-5-6)^{\wedge}7+8)/9)$
-8608155	$123/4*((-5-6^{\wedge}7)-8+9)$	-12991456	$1*2/3*(4-(5+6)^{\wedge}7)-8-9$
-8608401	$123/4*((5-6^{\wedge}7-8)-9)$	-13227018	$((1-(23-4))^{\wedge}5-6)*-7/(8-9)$
-8999998	$1*2-3^{\wedge}-4*(5*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9)$	-13392847	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5)*6)/-7*8+9$
-9000002	$-1*2-3^{\wedge}-4*(5*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9)$	-13392865	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5)*6)/-7*8-9$
-9078118	$(1+(-2-3^{\wedge}4)*5^{\wedge}6)*7/(-8+9)$	-13671826	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)*-7/(8-9)$
-9097452	$((1/2-3)-4)*(5*6^{\wedge}7-8*9)$	-13751208	$(-1+23*((4+5)^6+7)/8)*-9$
-9098388	$((1/2-3)-4)*(5*6^{\wedge}7+8*9)$	-13751226	$(-1-23*((4+5)^6+7)/8)*9$
-9112392	$12*((3/45)^{\wedge}((-6-7)+8)+9)$	-13835472	$(1+2)*(3-(-4/5*(6-7^{\wedge}8)-9))$
-9112608	$-12*((3/45)^{\wedge}((-6-7)+8)+9)$	-14045094	$(-12+3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6*7*(-8-9)$
-9241074	$((1-(23+4))^{\wedge}5-6)*7+8)/9$	-14053662	$(-1+2)*3^{\wedge}(4+5)*6*-7*(8+9)$
-9436608	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3+4*5-6))+7)*8*9$	-14062230	$(-12-3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6*7*(8+9)$
-9437760	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3+4*5-6))+7)*8*-9$	-14198569	$1+(-2/34)^{\wedge}-5*((6-7)^{\wedge}8+9)$
-9512500	$((1+2/3)^{\wedge}-4-5)*((6+7)-8)^{\wedge}9$	-14198571	$-1+(-2/34)^{\wedge}-5*((6-7)^{\wedge}8+9)$
-9517144	$((1-2)+3)*(4*5-6^{\wedge}7)*(8+9)$	-14222213	$(-1+2*(3-(4*5)^6)+78)/9$
-9517492	$1*2*(3^{\wedge}4+(-5+6^{\wedge}7)*(-8-9))$	-14222239	$(-1+2*(3-(4*5)^6)-78)/9$
-9518156	$1*-2*(3^{\wedge}4+(-5-6^{\wedge}7)*(-8-9))$	-14403561	$1/23*(4+(5+6)^{\wedge}7*(-8-9))$
-9518504	$((1-2)+3)*(4*5+6^{\wedge}7)*(-8-9)$	-14680045	$1/2*((3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))*7+8+9)$
-9562618	$1+((2+34)^*-5^{\wedge}6-7)*(8+9)$	-14680053	$1/2*((-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))*-7-(8-9))$
-9562620	$-1+((2+34)^*-5^{\wedge}6-7)*(8+9)$	-14680075	$-1/2*((-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))*-7-(8-9))$
-9565819	$1*-2/3^{\wedge}(-4*5+6)-7*(-8-9)$	-14680083	$1/2*((-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))*7-8-9)$
-9565820	$-1-2/3^{\wedge}(-4*5+6)-7*(-8-9)$	-14913088	$((1+2^{\wedge}((3-4+5)*6))+7)*-8/9$
-9566056	$1-2/3^{\wedge}(-4*5+6)-7*(8+9)$	-15066891	$((-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5)*6)/-7+8)*9$
-9566057	$1*-2/3^{\wedge}(-4*5+6)-7*(8+9)$	-15067035	$((1+(-2-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)*6)/7-8)*9$
-9776868	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(-5^{\wedge}6-7/(8-9))$	-15093225	$(1-(2*3)^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(-5+6-7+8)*-9$
-9801885	$(-1/2+3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6-7*8*9$	-15117750	$((12*3)^{\wedge}4+56)+78)*-9$
-9802383	$(1/2+3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6-7*8*9$	-15139881	$(1+(-2*3)^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(5*6/(7+8))*-9$
-9919368	$-12*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6*7-8*9$	-15156689	$(-12+(3+4)*(-5-6)^{\wedge}7+8)/9$
-9921096	$-12*(3^{\wedge}(4+5))*6*7+8*9$	-15194304	$-12*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-9939048	$(-1-(2/34)^{\wedge}-5-6)*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-15380820	$((1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))-6)*-7/8*9$
-10018750	$((1+2/3)^{\wedge}-4+5)*((-6-7)+8)^{\wedge}9$	-15487255	$((1-23)^{\wedge}4+5)*(-6-7-8/-9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-15597449	$(-1+2^{23}(3+4^5-6))^{*-7*(8+9)}$	-22020042	$1*2*3*(-4^{(5+6)*7/8+9})$
-15597687	$(-1-2^{23}(3+4^5-6))^{*7*(8+9)}$	-22020150	$1*2*-3*(4^{(5+6)*7/8+9})$
-15615180	$12*-3^{(4+5)*(67+8/-9)}$	-22106570	$((1*23^{23}(4-5)-6)^*(-7-8*9))$
-15670471	$((1*23^{23}(4-5)-6)^{*7*-8+9})$	-22320312	$((1+2)^{(3*4)-5})^{*6*7/(8-9)}$
-15670489	$((1*23^{23}(4-5)-6)^{*7*-8-9})$	-22394628	$1*2*(3^{4+5}*(-6^{7*8+9}))$
-15671703	$((-1*23^{23}(4-5)-6)^{*7*8+9})$	-22394722	$1*2*(34+5*(-6^{7*8+9}))$
-15671721	$((-1*23^{23}(4-5)-6)^{*7*8-9})$	-22395038	$1*2*(-34-5*(6^{7*8+9}))$
-15824928	$-12*(3^{(4+5)*67-8-9})$	-22395132	$1*2*(-3^{4-5}*(6^{7*8+9}))$
-15825120	$-12*(3^{(4+5)*67+8-9})$	-22500503	$1-((-2-3)^{-4/5^{6+7}})^{*8*9}$
-15825144	$-12*(3^{(4+5)*67-(8-9)})$	-22500505	$-1-((-2-3)^{-4/5^{6+7}})^{*8*9}$
-15825336	$12*(3^{(4+5)*67-8-9})$	-23425222	$1*2*((-3-(4*5-6)^7)+8)/9$
-15903719	$((1-23)^{(4+5)*(-67+8/-9)})$	-23436780	$12*(3^4*5+((-6-7)+8)^9)$
-16035084	$12*-3^{(4+5)*(67-8/-9)}$	-23438220	$-12*(3^4*5-((-6-7)+8)^9)$
-16124312	$(1-(2+3)^{(4+5)})/((-67/8+9))$	-23887859	$(1/2-(3^4)^{(5-6+7)})^{*8+9}$
-16225353	$(-1-2*(3+(4*5)^6))/((7+8)/9)$	-23887885	$(1/2+(3^4)^{(5-6+7)})^{*-8-9}$
-16252927	$1-(2^{23}-3-4^{(-5-6+7)})^{*8^9}$	-23914764	$((1+2)^{(3*4)^{-5-6}})^{+7+8}^{*9}$
-16252929	$-1-(2^{23}-3-4^{(-5-6+7)})^{*8^9}$	-23914926	$((1+2)^{(3*4)^{-5+6}})^{-7-8}^{*9}$
-16384000	$-12*(3^{(4+5)*67-(8-9)})$	-24299990	$1-(2/3^{45})^{(6+7-8)+9}$
-16397639	$(1+2^{23}(3+4)/5^{(6-7^8)})/9$	-24299992	$-1-(2/3^{45})^{(6+7-8)+9}$
-16776993	$-1-(2^{23}-3-4^{(-5-6)*7})/8^{8-9}$	-24300008	$1-((2/3^{45})^{(6+7-8)+9})$
-16777028	$-12/3*(4^{(5+6)-7*8+9})$	-24300010	$-1-((2/3^{45})^{(6+7-8)+9})$
-16777404	$-12/3*(4^{(5+6)-(-7*8+9)})$	-24374990	$1-(2+3)^4*5^6*7^8+9$
-16777439	$1-(2^{23}-3+4^{(-5-6)*7})/8^{8-9}$	-24374992	$-1-(2+3)^4*5^6*7^8+9$
-16948224	$12*(3^{(4+5)-67})^{*8*-9}$	-25110351	$((1+2)^{(3*4)-5})^{*-6*7/8*9}$
-17064000	$12*(-3^{(4+5)-67})^{*8*9}$	-25165338	$1*-2*(-3*(-4^{(5+6)+78})-9)$
-17173512	$((-1-2)^*(3^{4+5}))^{(-6+(-7+8)*9)}$	-25165374	$1*2*(3*(-4^{(5+6)+78})-9)$
-17301503	$1+(-2^{23}-3-4^{(-5-6+7)})^{*8^9}$	-25165604	$1*-2*(-3*(-4^{(5+6)+78})-9)$
-17301505	$-1+(-2^{23}-3-4^{(-5-6+7)})^{*8^9}$	-25165757	$1*-2*(-3*(-4^{(5+6)+78})-9)+9$
-17332658	$(1+(23-4)^{5-6})^{*-7^{(8-9+)}}$	-25165772	$1*2*-3*(4^{(5+6)-78/9})$
-17500008	$1-(2+3)^4*5^6*7^8-9$	-25165876	$1*2*-3*(4^{(5+6)+78/9})$
-17500010	$-1-(2+3)^4*5^6*7^8-9$	-25165891	$1*2*(-3*(4^{(5+6)+78})-9)$
-17926389	$-1/(-2-3)^*(4^{(5+6)-7^8})^{*9}$	-25166044	$1*2*(-3*(4^{(5+6)+78})-9)$
-18423252	$(1/2-3^{(4+5)*6+7})^{*8*9}$	-25166274	$1*-2*(3*(4^{(5+6)+78})-9)$
-18423324	$(1/2-3^{(4+5)*6+7})^{*8*9}$	-25166310	$1*2*(3*(4^{(5+6)+78})-9)$
-18475769	$(12*3)^{4*5}*(-5-6)^{-7*(8-9)}$	-25194160	$((-1+2)-3)^{4*5}*(6^{7-8}/9)$
-18600393	$((1+2)^{(3*4)^{-5+6}})^{7^{(8-9+)}}$	-25194320	$((-1+2)-3)^{4*5}*(6^{7+8}/9)$
-18748945	$(1-23^{23}(4+5)^{67})^{(-8+9)}$	-25200000	$(-1+2^{23}-3)^{(4*5)^{(6+7-8)*9}}$
-18874116	$(1/2+3)^*(4^{(5+6)/(-7+8)})^{*9}$	-25445504	$1/(2/(-3-4)-5)^*(6^{7+8}/9)$
-18874620	$(1/2+3)^*(4^{(5+6)/7+8})^{*-9}$	-25508760	$(-1+2/3*((4+5)^6-7))^{*-8*9}$
-19173856	$(1-23^{23}(4-5-6))/7^{*-8^9}$	-25508832	$-1*2/3*((4+5)^6-7)^{*8*9}$
-19478257	$1/23*((4*5)^6-7+89)$	-25508904	$(1+2/3*((4+5)^6-7))^{*-8*9}$
-19595486	$1*2*((3+4)^{-5*6^{7+8}})^{+9}$	-25907505	$((1+2)^{(3*4)-5})^{*6*(7/8-9)}$
-19595554	$1*2*((-3-4)^{5*6^{7+8}})^{-9}$	-25974512	$((-1-2)^{34})^{(5+6-7)-8^9}$
-19834416	$1*2*(3^{(4+5)-6})^{*7*8*-9}$	-25982897	$(1+2+3^4)^{(4*(-5-6)^{7-8})}/9$
-19846512	$1*2*(-3^{(4+5)-6})^{*7*8*9}$	-26097889	$1*(23-4^{(5+6)*7*8})/9$
-20038500	$((1+2)^{(3-4)+5^6})^{(-7-8)^9}$	-26097929	$(-1-(2*3+4^{(5+6)})^{*7*8})/9$
-20225310	$(-1+(2*3)^4)^{(-5^6-7/(8-9))}$	-26584420	$(1*-23^{23}(4+5)^*(6+7)^{-8-9})$
-20312499	$1+(2+3)^4*5^6*(7-8^9)$	-26585370	$(-1*23^{23}(4-5)^*(6+7)^{-8-9})$
-20312501	$-1+(2+3)^4*5^6*(7-8^9)$	-26873409	$(-1-2-3^4)^{-5^6-7^8}/9$
-20692800	$(1-2-3^4)^{(4*5)^6+7^8}/9$	-26874303	$(1+2+3^4)^{(4*(5+6)^7)}^{*8+9}$
-20903346	$1*2*3^{(4+5)*(-67+8)*9}$	-27006905	$-12^{23}*(4+5^6)^{7^8+(-8+9)}$
-20984255	$1-((2-3^4)^{-5^6-7})^{*(8+9)}$	-27050376	$(-12^{23}-4)^{(5^6+7/(8-9))}$
-20984257	$-1-((2-3^4)^{-5^6-7})^{*(8+9)}$	-27062493	$((-12^{23}-4)^{5^6-7/(8-9)})$
-21017706	$(12*3^{(4+5)-6*7})^{*-89}$	-27074624	$(-12^{23}-4)^{(5^6-7^8)(8-9)}$
-21025182	$(12*3^{(4+5)+6*7})^{*-89}$	-27427936	$(1/2-(3/4)^{(5+6)*7})^{*-8^9}$
-21333242	$(1-2)/3*((4*5)^6-7)+89$	-28133568	$(12*3)^{4*5}*((5-6)^7/8-9)$
-21333259	$(1-2)/3*((4*5)^6-7)+8*9$	-28268892	$1*-2*(-3-4^{(5+6)+7^8})^{*9}$
-21333314	$(1-2)/3*((4*5)^6-7)+8+9$	-28269000	$1*2*(-3+4^{(5+6)-7^8})^{*9}$
-21333326	$((-12-3^4)^{(4*5)^6+78})/9$	-28444440	$-1/2*((-3+(4*5)^6)-7)^{*8/9}$
-21333348	$((-1+2)/-3*((4*5)^6-7)-8)-9$	-28444452	$(1/2*(-3-(4*5)^6)-7)^{*8/9}$
-21333358	$(12-3^4)^{(4*5)^6+78})/9$	-28697576	$1*2*(-3^{(4+5)+6})^{-7*(-8-9)}$
-21333373	$(-1+2)/-3*((4*5)^6-7^8*(-8-9))$	-28698052	$1*-2*(3^{(4+5)+6})^{-7*(-8-9)}$
-21333403	$(1-2)/3*((4*5)^6-7)-8*9$	-28760944	$1/2*(-3-4^{(-5-6)})/7^8+9$
-21333420	$(1-2)/3*((4*5)^6-7)-89$	-28904961	$((123+4)^{(5+6-7)+8})/9$
-21375503	$1+(23-4)^{-5^6-7})^{*8*9}$	-29177758	$1/23*(-4-5^6-6^{7+8})^{*9}$
-21375505	$-1+(23-4)^{-5^6-7})^{*8*9}$	-29177767	$1/23*(4+5^6-6^{7-8})^{*9}$
-21381392	$1-(2*34)^{(5+6-7)-8+9}$	-29359876	$(12*3-4^{(5+6)})^{*7/(8+9)}$
-21455612	$(-12+((3-4*5)^6-7)^{-8})/9$	-30941676	$12*-3^{(4+5)*6}*(7+89)$
-21463459	$-123*(-4^{(5+6)+7^8})/9$	-31179469	$-1/(2+3)^*(4-(5+6)^7)^{-8+9}$
-21523360	$(-1/2*((3*(4+5))^6+7)+8)/9$	-31457253	$1/2*((-3+4^{(5+6)})^{*7-8})^{*9}$
-21523361	$(-1/2*((3*(4+5))^6-7)-8)/9$	-31457262	$1/2*((3-4^{(5+6)})^{*7+8})^{*9}$
-21835398	$(1+2-3^4)^{(5+6^7)^{(-8+9)}}$	-31457298	$1/2*((-3-4^{(5+6)})^{*7+8})^{*9}$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-31457307	$1/2 * ((3+4^{(5+6)}) * (-7-8) - 9)$	-42666746	$1 * 2 / -3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7 * (-8-9))$
-31487583	$((1+2)^{(3^4)} - 5) * -6 * (7/8+9)$	-42666747	$-1 - 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7 * (-8-9))$
-31695652	$1/23 * (4 - (5^6)^{(7+8-9)})$	-42666750	$1+2/-3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) - 89$
-32000005	$-1/2 * (3 + (-4^5)^6 + 7^{(8+9)})$	-42666751	$-1 * 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) - 89$
-32285025	$1 * 2 * (-3^{(4+5)} + 6) + 7 / 8 * 9$	-42666752	$-1 - 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) - 89$
-32400000	$(-1 - 2^{-3}) * (4^5)^{(6+7-8)} * 9$	-43141428	$(1/2 * -3 - 4^{(5+6)}) / 7 * 8 * 9$
-32896847	$(-1 - 2 * ((3+4^5)^6 - 78)) / 9$	-44040084	$1/2 * 3 * (-4^{(5+6)} * 7 + 8 * 9)$
-33045740	$-1/2 * (((34-5)^6 + 7) - 8) / 9$	-44040300	$1/2 * 3 * (-4^{(5+6)} * 7 - 8 * 9)$
-33299770	$((1 * 23^{4-5} - 6) * 7 * (-8-9))$	-45054443	$((1 - 2 * 3^4)^5 - 6) * 7^{(8+9)}$
-33343421	$(1 - 2 * (3^4)^5) * 67 * (-8+9)$	-45068891	$(-1 + 2 * 3^4) * (5 - 6^{(7)})^{(8+9)}$
-34156566	$(-1 - 2)^{(3+4)} * (5^6 + 7 / (8-9))$	-45070501	$(1 - 2 * 3^4) * (5 + 6^{(7)})^{(8+9)}$
-34588600	$1 * -2 * (-3^{(4+5)} - 6 * (7^{(8-9)}))$	-46229303	$(((-1 - 2 - 34)^5 * 6 + 7) + 8) / 9$
-34589012	$1 * 2 * (-3^{(4+5)} + 6 * (-7^{(8-9)}))$	-47535366	$1 * 2/3 * (-4^{(5+6)} + 7) * (8+9)$
-35013274	$1/23 * (4^5 + 6 * (7 - 8^9))$	-49207464	$12 * (3 - 45^{(6+7)} + 8 + 9)$
-35156178	$((1 - 2) + 3) * (-4 + 5^{(6+7+8)}) * -9$	-49207536	$-12 * (3 + 45^{(6-7)} + 8 + 9)$
-35156322	$((1 - 2) + 3) * (-4 - 5^{(6+7+8)}) * 9$	-49345305	$((-1 - 2) * (3 + 4^5)^6 - 78) / 9$
-35555564	$(-1 + (-2 - 3) * ((4^5)^6 + 7 + 8)) / 9$	-49777767	$12 - ((3 - (4^5)^6 * 7) + 8) / 9$
-35555599	$(1 + 2 * 3) * ((4^5)^6 + 78) / -9$	-49777791	$-12 - ((3 - (4^5)^6 * 7) + 8) / 9$
-35826264	$-12^{(3+4)} - (-5 - 6) * 7 * 8 * 9$	-49825048	$((1 - 2) + 3) * (4^5 - 6^{(7)}) * 89$
-35828238	$-12^{(3+4)} - 5 * 6 * 7 * (-8 - 9)$	-49828568	$((1 - 2) + 3) * (4^5 - 6^{(7)} * 89)$
-35829846	$-12^{(3+4)} + (5 * 6 * 7 + 8) * 9$	-49828648	$((1 - 2) + 3) * (-4^5 - 6^{(7)} * 89)$
-35829990	$-12^{(3+4)} - (5 * 6 * 7 + 8) * 9$	-49832168	$((1 - 2) + 3) * (4^5 + 6^{(7)}) * -89$
-35830368	$((1 + 2 * ((-3^4)^5 + 6)) + 7) * 8 * 9$	-49994820	$(1 - 2^{(3-4)}) * 5 * (6 / (7 - 8))^{(9)}$
-35833248	$((1 + 2 * ((3^4)^5 + 6)) + 7) * -8 * 9$	-50389105	$-1 * ((2 + 3)^4 - 5 * (6 / (7 - 8))^{(9)})$
-35833626	$-12^{(3+4)} + (5 * 6 * 7 + 8) * 9$	-50782140	$(1 + 2^{(3-4)}) * 5 * (6 / (7 - 8))^{(9)}$
-35833770	$-12^{(3+4)} - (5 * 6 * 7 + 8) * 9$	-51414458	$1 + ((2/3 - 4) * -5^{(6-7+8)}) * 9$
-35835378	$-12^{(3+4)} - 5 * 6 * 7 * (8 + 9)$	-51414460	$-1 + ((2/3 - 4) * -5^{(6-7+8)}) * 9$
-35837352	$-12^{(3+4)} + (-5 - 6) * 7 * 8 * 9$	-51824159	$1 - (2 * 3^{(4+5)} / -6 + 7^{(8)}) * 9$
-36075382	$(12 - 34)^5 + 6 * 7^{(8-9)}$	-51824161	$-1 - (2 * 3^{(4+5)} / -6 + 7^{(8)}) * 9$
-36665567	$1/23 * ((-4^5 + 6)^7 * 8 - 9)$	-51848379	$((1 + 2^{(3+4)}) * 5 * 6 - 7^{(8)}) * 9$
-36962022	$(-1 + 2^{(3+4^5)}) * 6 * (-7 * 8 + 9)$	-51853684	$1/2 + (3^{(4+5)} / 6 - 7^{(8)}) * 9$
-36962586	$(-1 - 2^{(3+4^5)}) * 6 * (7 * 8 - 9)$	-51853685	$-1/2 + (3^{(4+5)} / 6 - 7^{(8)}) * 9$
-37498818	$(1 + 2 * 3)^4 * (-5^6 - 7 / (8 - 9))$	-51876594	$((1 + 2)^{(3-4-5)} + 6 - 7^{(8)}) * 9$
-38347936	$(1 * -2 - 3/4^{(5+6)}) / 7 * 8 * 9$	-51876702	$((1 + 2)^{(3-4-5)} - 6 - 7^{(8)}) * 9$
-38706521	$(1 - 2^{(3)})^{(4-5+6)} * (7 * 8 - 9)$	-51889716	$((1 + 2)^{(3-4-5)} - 6 + 7^{(8)}) * -9$
-38880000	$(-1 - 2) * (3^4 * 5)^{(6-7-8-9)}$	-51889824	$((1 + 2)^{(3-4-5)} + 6 + 7^{(8)}) * -9$
-40292352	$((1 - 2) + 3) * (-4^5 + 6^{(7+8)}) * -9$	-51912733	$1/2 - (3^{(4+5)} / 6 + 7^{(8)}) * 9$
-40308588	$12 * 3 * (4 * (5 - 6^{(7+8)} + 9))$	-51912734	$-1/2 - (3^{(4+5)} / 6 + 7^{(8)}) * 9$
-40309688	$(1 + (-2 + 3^{(4-5)}) / 6^{(7-8)}) * 8 * 9$	-51918039	$((-1 - 2^{(3+4)}) * 5 * 6 - 7^{(8)}) * 9$
-40309751	$(1 + (-2 + 3^{(4-5)}) / 6^{(7-8)}) * 9$	-51942257	$1 + (2 * 3^{(4+5)} / -6 - 7^{(8)}) * 9$
-40309769	$(-1 - (2 - 3^{(4-5)}) / 6^{(7-8)}) * 9$	-51942259	$-1 + (2 * 3^{(4+5)} / -6 - 7^{(8)}) * 9$
-40309832	$(-1 - (2 - 3^{(4-5)}) / 6^{(7-8)}) * 8 * 9$	-51965759	$1 * 2/3 * 4 * ((-5 - 6)^7 + 8) + 9$
-40310523	$((1 + 2) * ((3^4)^5 - 6 + 7) + 8) * 9$	-51965767	$1 - 2 * -3 * 4 * ((-5 - 6)^7 + 8) / 9$
-40311045	$((-1 - 2) * ((3^4)^5 * 6 + 7) - 8) * 9$	-51965769	$-1 - 2 * -3 * 4 * ((-5 - 6)^7 + 8) / 9$
-40311736	$(1 - (2 + 3^{(4-5)}) / 6^{(7-8)}) * 8 * 9$	-52199316	$12 * 3^{(4+5)} * (-6 - 7) * (8 + 9)$
-40311799	$(1 - (2 + 3^{(4-5)}) / 6^{(7-8)}) * 9$	-52539458	$1 + ((2/3 + 4) * -5^{(6-7+8)}) * 9$
-40311817	$(-1 - (2 + 3^{(4-5)}) / 6^{(7-8)}) * 9$	-52539460	$-1 + ((2/3 + 4) * -5^{(6-7+8)}) * 9$
-40311880	$(1 + (2 + 3^{(4-5)}) / 6^{(7-8)}) * -8 * 9$	-52612524	$((1 + 2)^{(3^4)} * (-5 - 6 + 7) + 8) * 9$
-40312980	$12 * 3 * (4 * ((-5 - 6^{(7-8)} - 9)))$	-52612794	$((1 + 2)^{(3^4)} * (-5 - 6) - 7) - 8) * 9$
-40329216	$((1 - 2) + 3) * (-4^5 - 6^{(7+8)}) * 9$	-53477376	$(-1 + 2^{(3-4)} * (5 + 6) * 7) * 8 * 9$
-40354232	$-1 * ((2 + 3)^4 + ((5 - 6)^7 + 8) + 9)$	-53687103	$(-1 - 2) * (3 - 4 / (5 * 6) * (7 + 8^9))$
-40500503	$1 + ((2 + 34) * -5^6 - 7) * 8 * 9$	-56401920	$12^{(3+4)} * (5/6 - (7+8)) / 9$
-40500505	$-1 + ((2 + 34) * -5^6 - 7) * 8 * 9$	-56622051	$1/2 * 3 * (4^{(5+6)} - 78) * -9$
-40773833	$1 + ((2 - 3^4) * -5^6 - 7^{(8)}) * 9$	-56622852	$1/2 * (3^4 * 4^{(5+6)} - 7 * 8) * -9$
-40773835	$-1 + ((2 - 3^4) * -5^6 - 7^{(8)}) * 9$	-56623050	$12 * (-3 - 4^{(5+6)} + 7) / 8 * 9$
-42270336	$(1 - 2 * (3^{(4-5)})) * 6^{(7-8)} * (-8+9)$	-56623158	$12 * (-3 + 4^{(5+6)} + 7) / 8 * -9$
-42666572	$1 + 2 / -3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 89$	-56623356	$1/2 * (3^4 * 4^{(5+6)} + 7 * 8) * -9$
-42666573	$-1 * 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 89$	-56624157	$1/2 * 3 * (-4^{(5+6)} - 78) * 9$
-42666574	$-1 - 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 89$	-56888871	$12 + (-3 + ((4^5)^6 - 7) * -8) / 9$
-42666589	$1 + 2 / -3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8 * 9$	-56888992	$((-123 - (4^5)^6 + 7) * 8 / 9)$
-42666590	$-1 * 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8 * 9$	-57395509	$-12/3^{(4-5+6)} - 7 * (-8-9)$
-42666591	$-1 + 2 / -3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8 * 9$	-57395621	$-12/3^{(4-5+6)} - 7 * (8-9)$
-42666644	$1 + 2 / -3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8 + 9$	-57395635	$-12/3^{(4-5+6)} - 7 * (-8+9)$
-42666645	$-1 * 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8 + 9$	-57395747	$-12/3^{(4-5+6)} - 7 * (8+9)$
-42666646	$-1 - 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) + 8 + 9$	-57521876	$12 + (-3 - 4^{(5-6)}) / 7 * 8^9$
-42666675	$-1 * 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 + 7) - 8) - 9$	-57521890	$-1 * 2 + (-3 - 4^{(5-6)}) / 7 * 8^9$
-42666678	$1 + 2 / -3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) - (8+9)$	-57521900	$-12 + (-3 - 4^{(5-6)}) / 7 * 8^9$
-42666680	$(-1 - 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) - 8 - 9)$	-57671680	$(1 / -2 + 3^{(4+5)} * 6^{-7}) * 8^9$
-42666733	$1 + 2 / -3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) - 8 * 9$	-58593743	$(-1 - 2 * 3^4)^5 * 6^{-7} * (8-9)$
-42666734	$-1 * 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) - 8 * 9$	-58720305	$(-1 - 2^{(3+4^5)} - 6) * 7^{(8-9)}$
-42666735	$-1 + 2 / -3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7) - 8 * 9$	-58724351	$1 + (2 * 3^4)^5 * ((6+7) / 8 - 9)$
-42666745	$1 - 2/3 * ((4^5)^6 - 7 * (-8 - 9))$	-58724353	$-1 + (2 * 3^4)^5 * ((6+7) / 8 - 9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-58786602	$((12^3)^4)^{5+6} * -7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-88874495	$1 - ((2-3^4)^* -5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8^*9$
-62208000	$1^* -2^*(3^4)^5 * (6-7^*(-8-9))$	-88874497	$-1 - ((2-3^4)^* -5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8^*9$
-63037440	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5/6+7+8)/9$	-89163990	$(-1-2^*(3/4)^5)/6^{\wedge}(7-8-9)$
-63955710	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3^4))^*(5^{\wedge}6+7/(8-9))$	-89478656	$1^*2/-3^*(4^{\wedge}((5+6)-7)+8^{\wedge}9)$
-64015625	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3^4))^*5^{\wedge}6/(-7+8)^{\wedge}9$	-89481216	$1^*2/-3^*(4^{\wedge}((5-6)+7)+8^{\wedge}9)$
-64366832	$(1+2)^*(3-4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^* -8/9$	-90558030	$(1+(2-3^4)^*(-5-6)^{\wedge}7)/(-8-9)$
-65366382	$-123^*(4+5)^{\wedge}6+7/(8-9)$	-90633012	$(1+2^*(-3-4)^5+(6+7)^{\wedge}8)/-9$
-65628948	$(12-34^5*(-6-7)+8)/-9$	-90698319	$(1+(-2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+(6+7)^*8)^*9$
-67092480	$(-1/2+(3+4-5)^{\wedge}(-6-7))/8^{\wedge}-9$	-90698337	$(-1-(-2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)-(-6-7)^*8)^*9$
-67108740	$1^*2^*((-3-(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^*8)+9)$	-90699182	$1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6-7-8)^* -9$
-67108764	$1^*2^*((3+(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*8)-9)$	-90699184	$-1-((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6-(7+8))^*9$
-67108964	$-1^*2^*((3+(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*8)-9)$	-90699200	$1-((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)-6+7-8)^*9$
-67108988	$1^*2^*((3-(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*8)-9)$	-90699202	$(-1+((-2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6-7+8)^*9)$
-67125248	$(-1/2*(3+4-5)^{\wedge}(-6-7))/8^{\wedge}-9$	-90699326	$1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)-6+7-8)^*9$
-68023233	$(1+2)^*3^4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-90699328	$-1-((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6-(7-8))^*9$
-68025663	$(-1-2)^*3^4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-90699344	$1-((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6-7-8)^* -9$
-68359382	$(-1+(2+3)^4*-5^{\wedge}6)^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-90699346	$-1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6-(7+8))^*9$
-68359417	$((1+2)^3)^4)^5+6)^* -7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-90700191	$(1+(-2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)-(-6+7)^*8)^*9$
-68681728	$(1/-2-3^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))^*8^{\wedge}9$	-90700209	$(-1-(-2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+(-6-7)^*8)^*9$
-69343951	$(-1-2-34)^5-6/(7-8)^{\wedge}9$	-91124990	$((-1+(2/3^*45)^{\wedge}6)-7)/-8+9$
-70275610	$1^*2/3^*((-4^*5+6)^{\wedge}7+89)$	-91125010	$((-1-(2/3^*45)^{\wedge}6)-7)/8-9$
-70312428	$(1^*2^{\wedge}3-4^*5^{\wedge}((-6+7)+8))^*9$	-91186370	$1^*2^*((-3-(4^*5-6)^{\wedge}7+8)/9)$
-70312572	$(1^*-2^{\wedge}3-4^*5^{\wedge}((-6+7)+8))^*9$	-91551065	$1-(-2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)+8^{\wedge}9)$
-70543662	$((12^3)^4-5)^*6^*7/(8-9)$	-91551066	$1^*2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)-8^{\wedge}9$
-71614620	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^* -6^*(7-8/9)$	-91551067	$-1-2/-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)-8^{\wedge}9$
-71663589	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}(-4-5)^*6^{\wedge}(7+8)-9)$	-92447964	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^* -6^*(7+8/9)$
-71663643	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}(-4-5)^*6^{\wedge}(7+8)+9)$	-93375503	$1-((-2-3^4)^* -5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8^*9$
-72279217	$(-1+(2^*3)^4/5)^*((-6^{\wedge}7-8)+9)$	-93375505	$-1-((-2-3^4)^* -5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8^*9$
-72412686	$(-1-2)^*((3-4^*5)^{\wedge}6+7/(8-9))$	-95420416	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^*(5-6^*7))^*8^{\wedge}9$
-72839087	$(-1-(2^*3)^4/5)^*((6^{\wedge}7+8)-9)$	-95659370	$(-1-2/-3^{\wedge}(-4^*5+6))^*(7-8-9)$
-73138167	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3+4^*5)^*(6+7^*8))^*9$	-95659390	$(-1-2/3^{\wedge}(-4^*5+6))^*(7+8+9)$
-73138185	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3+4^*5)^*(6+7^*8))^*9$	-95869792	$(-1+(2+3^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6))/7)^*8^{\wedge}9$
-73539117	$-123^*((4+5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8^*9$	-96457400	$1^*-23^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*8^*9)$
-73600000	$1^*23/(-4^*5)^{\wedge}(6+7-8^*9)$	-96467911	$1^*-23^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*8+9)$
-73618201	$(-1-2-34^*(5+6)^{\wedge}7+8)/9$	-96470073	$1^*-23^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-(-7^*8+9))$
-74248192	$((-1+23)^4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)-8^{\wedge}9$	-96480584	$1^*23^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*8^*9)$
-74352895	$12+((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7)/-8+9$	-98684252	$((1-2^{\wedge}-3/4)^5-6)/7^*8^{\wedge}9$
-74352913	$12+((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7)/-8-9$	-99089676	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3+4^*5))^*(6+78)^*9$
-74352919	$(-12-((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8)+9$	-99091188	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3+4^*5))^*(6+78)^*9$
-74352937	$(-12-((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8)-9$	-99137219	$-12^*((34-5)^{\wedge}6-7)/(8^*9)$
-74655361	$((1-2/3^{\wedge}-4)^{\wedge}(5-(-6+7))+8)/-9$	-99462573	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)^*6^{\wedge}7^*89$
-75497196	$1^*2^*(3+(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7+8)^*9)$	-99555554	$(1^*-2^*(3+(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7+8)^*9)/9)$
-75497208	$1^*-2^*(3-(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7+8)^*9)$	-99851859	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)^*6^{\wedge}7^*89$
-75497448	$1^*-2^*(3-(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-(-7-8))^*9)$	-99989640	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5/6^{\wedge}-7^*8^*9$
-75497496	$1^*2^*(-3+(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7-8)^*9)$	-100442398	$(1+(2+3+4)^5+6)^* -7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-75497736	$1^*2^*(3+(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-(-7-8))^*9)$	-100619424	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)^*6^{\wedge}7^*8^*9$
-75497748	$1^*-2^*(3-(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-(-7+8))^*9)$	-100619568	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8^*9$
-75520512	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}-3+45)^* -6^{\wedge}(7-8+9)$	-100770840	$1^*2^{\wedge}3^*45^*((-6^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$
-75582686	$1^*2^*((-3^*45/6^{\wedge}-7+8)+9)$	-100783080	$1^*2^{\wedge}3^*-45^*((6^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$
-75582754	$1^*2^*((3^*45/-6^{\wedge}-7-8)-9)$	-100934352	$(1-(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8^*9$
-77236092	$12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6^*7^*8+9)$	-100934496	$(-1-(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8^*9$
-78434641	$((1-2/-3^{\wedge}-4)^{\wedge}(5-(-6+7))+8)/-9$	-101564280	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5/6^{\wedge}-7^*8^*9$
-79560704	$((1/2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)/-6+7)/-8^{\wedge}-9$	-102399994	$(-12^*3-4)^5-6/(7-8)^{\wedge}9$
-80464104	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)^*6^{\wedge}7^*8^*9$	-102469698	$(12-3)^4*(5^{\wedge}6-7/(8-9))$
-80707078	$1^*2^*((3+4)^*(5+6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$	-103655826	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^{\wedge}5^*6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-80707350	$1^*2^*((-3-4)^*(5+6+7^{\wedge}8)+9)$	-103761558	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^{\wedge}5^*6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-81380210	$(-1-((-2+3)+4)^{\wedge}(5+6))^*(7+8)/9$	-103762386	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^*5^*6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-81487620	$12^*-3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6^*7^*8+9)$	-103765870	$((1-2)+3)^*(4+(5^*6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
-83169674	$((1-(23+4)^{\wedge}5-6)^* -7/(8-9))$	-103765886	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4-(5^*6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
-84934008	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3+4^*5))^*(6-78)^*9$	-103766950	$((1-2)+3)^*(4-(5^*6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
-84935304	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3+4^*5))^*(6-78)^*9$	-103766966	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4+(5^*6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
-85333315	$-1/(2^*3)^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9$	-103770450	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^*5^*6+7^{\wedge}8)^* -9$
-85333324	$-1/2^*3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8/9$	-103771278	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^*5^*6+7^{\wedge}8)^* -9$
-85333328	$-12^*((-3+(4^*5)^{\wedge}6+7)-8)/9$	-103877010	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^{\wedge}5^*6+7^{\wedge}8)^* -9$
-85333333	$-1/(2^*3)^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9$	-106789792	$(1/2+(3/4)^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7^* -8^{\wedge}9$
-85561994	$(1-23^*(4+5)^{\wedge}6)^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-107951616	$12^{\wedge}3^*-4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7/(8-9))$
-86092731	$(1-2/3^{\wedge}(-4^*5+6)+78)^*9$	-109051882	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4^*5))/6^*-78+9$
-86092749	$(-1-2/3^{\wedge}(-4^*5+6)+78)^*9$	-109051926	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4^*5))/6^*78-9$
-86094135	$(1+2/-3^{\wedge}(-4^*5+6)-78)^*9$	-112665492	$12^*-3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6^*78+9)$
-86094153	$((-1-2/3^{\wedge}(-4^*5+6))-78)^*9$	-112884397	$(1-2)/-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)-8^{\wedge}9$
-86609648	$((12^*3+4)^*(5-6)^{\wedge}7+8)/9$	-113777765	$1-2^*(3+((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8)/9$
-88219206	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3^4)^*((-5-6)^*7-89)$	-113777766	$1^*2^*(3-((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^* -8)/-9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-113777767	$-1 \cdot 2^*(3 - ((4^5)^{\wedge}6 - 7)^* - 8)/9$	-137013926	$1^*2/-3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7) - 8^{\wedge}9$
-113777784	$((1 - 2+3)^*(4^5)^{\wedge}6+7)^* - 8/9$	-138575432	$(-1 - 2^*(3+4^*(- 5 - 6)^{\wedge}7))^* - 8/9$
-114294784	$(1^*2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4)^* - 5+6)/-7^*8^{\wedge}9$	-139169737	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4)^*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7 - 8^{\wedge}9)$
-115043776	$1^*2^*(- 3 - 4^{\wedge}(-5 - 6))/7^*8^{\wedge}9$	-139460607	$1+(2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4)^*5 - (6 - 7))/-8^{\wedge} - 9$
-115955712	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6 - 7/8)/9$	-139460609	$-1+(2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4)^*5 - (6 - 7))/-8^{\wedge} - 9$
-116319504	$(-1 - (2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^*67^*8/9$	-139751479	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4)^*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$
-117407744	$(-1+2^{\wedge} - 3+4^{\wedge}(-5 - (-6+7)))^*8^{\wedge}9$	-142222216	$((1/2 - 3)/(4^5)^{\wedge} - 6+7)^*8/9$
-117473280	$(-1+2^{\wedge} - 3 - 4^{\wedge}(-5 - (-6+7)))^*8^{\wedge}9$	-142426116	$(12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)^* - 67+8)^*9$
-119619434	$((1+(2+3/4)^*5)+6)^*(-7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-142426260	$(12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*67+8)^* - 9$
-120774888	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4)) - 5)^*6^{\wedge}7^*8^*9$	-142767330	$(12^*3)^{\wedge}4^*5^*((6^{\wedge} - 7 - 8) - 9)$
-120931839	$(1 - ((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)/6 - 7)^*8)^*9$	-142767390	$(12^*3)^{\wedge}4^*5^*((-6^{\wedge} - 7 - 8) - 9)$
-120932109	$(1^* - 2+(3^*4)^{\wedge} - 5)/6^{\wedge}(7 - 8 - 9)$	-145071161	$((-1+2^*34)/(-5 - 6)^{\wedge} - 7+8)/9$
-120932256	$1^*2^*(3+45 - 6^{\wedge}(-7+8+9))$	-145282608	$((-1 - 2)^{\wedge}(3^*4+5)+67)/8^*9$
-120932865	$(-1 - (2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)/6+7)^*8)^*9$	-145732932	$12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+7^* - 89)$
-121089816	$((-1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4)) - 5)^*6^{\wedge}7^*8^*9$	-147105252	$12^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6)^*7^* - 89$
-121257728	$((-12 - 3)^*4)^{\wedge}(5+6 - 7) - 8^{\wedge}9$	-147146370	$(12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6)^*7^* - 89$
-122070309	$1/2^*(3+4 - 5^{\wedge}(6 - ((-7 - 8)+9)))$	-147153846	$(-12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6)^*7^*89$
-122070312	$(-1 - 2^*(3 - (4 - 5^{\wedge}(6 - ((-7 - 8)+9))))$	-147194964	$12^*(- 3^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6)^*7^*89$
-122070313	$1/2^*(3 - (4+5^{\wedge}(6 - ((-7 - 8)+9))))$	-147386295	$(1 - (2^* - 3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^*(- 6 - 7)/8)^*9$
-122070316	$-1/2^*(3+4+5^{\wedge}(6 - ((-7 - 8)+9)))$	-147386313	$(-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^*(- 6 - 7)/8)^*9$
-122923008	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6+7/8)/9$	-148567284	$12^* - 3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6 - 7^* - 89)$
-123598305	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4))^*5/6^{\wedge} - 7^*89$	-148995612	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5))^*6/ - 7^*89$
-124475292	$12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(- 67^*8+9)$	-149291181	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4)) - 5)^*6^{\wedge}7^*89$
-125544735	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4))^*5/6^{\wedge} - 7^*89$	-149333331	$(-1 - (- 2+3^*(4^5)^{\wedge}6)^*7+8)/9$
-126128041	$(12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)^* - 6+7)^*89$	-149333363	$(-1+2)/3^*((4^5)^{\wedge}6^* - 7 - 89)$
-126129287	$(12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6+7)^* - 89$	-149680467	$((-1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4)) - 5)^*6^{\wedge}7^*89$
-127998992	$((-1+2) - 3)^*((4^5)^{\wedge}6 - 7^*8^*9)$	-150962176	$(-1 - (2^{\wedge} - 3 - 4^{\wedge}(-5 - (-6+7))))^*8^{\wedge}9$
-127999762	$((-1+2) - 3)^*((4^5)^{\wedge}6 - 7^*(8+9))$	-150976800	$12^* - 3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7^*8^*9)$
-127999953	$((-1+2) - 3)^*(4^5)^{\wedge}6+7^*8 - 9$	-150994296	$12^*(3^*(- 4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)+8)+9$
-128000047	$((-1+2) - 3)^*(4^5)^{\wedge}6 - 7^*8+9$	-150994548	$(1/2^*(- 3 - 4^{\wedge}(5+6))+7)^*8^*9$
-128000238	$((-1+2) - 3)^*((4^5)^{\wedge}6 - 7^*(- 8 - 9))$	-150994720	$12^* - 3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7^*8/9)$
-128001008	$((-1+2) - 3)^*((4^5)^{\wedge}6 - 7^* - 8^*9)$	-150995168	$12^* - 3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7^* - 8/9)$
-128446560	$(-1+23^{\wedge}4)^*(5^*6^*(- 7 - 8) - 9)$	-150995340	$(1/2^*(- 3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))+7)^* - 8^*9$
-128447019	$1^*23^{\wedge}4^*(5^*6^*(- 7 - 8) - 9)$	-150995592	$-12^*(3^*((4^5)^{\wedge}6+7)+8)+9$
-128447478	$(1+23^{\wedge}4)^*(5^*6^*(- 7 - 8) - 9)$	-151013088	$12^*3^*(- 4^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7^*8^*9)$
-128705847	$(1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4))^*5^*(6^{\wedge}7 - 8^{\wedge}9)$	-151027712	$(-1 - (2^{\wedge} - 3+4^{\wedge}(-5 - (-6+7))))^*8^{\wedge}9$
-128726820	$12^* - 3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(67^*8+9)$	-151519232	$(-1 - (2^{\wedge} - 3+4^{\wedge}(-5 - 6+7)))^*8^{\wedge}9$
-128974847	$1+(2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4))^*5+6 - 7/8^{\wedge} - 9$	-151649147	$(1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3+4^5))^*(6+7)^*89$
-128974849	$-1+(2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4))^*5+6 - 7/8^{\wedge} - 9$	-151651461	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3+4^5))^*(6+7)^*89$
-129140112	$(-1 - 2)^*((3^{\wedge}(4^*(5+6 - 7)) - 8) - 9)$	-153051120	$(1 - 2^*3^{\wedge}(4+5))^*6^{\wedge}7/(8^*9)$
-129140214	$(-1 - 2)^*((3^{\wedge}(4^*(5+6 - 7))+8)+9)$	-153058896	$(-1 - 2^*3^{\wedge}(4+5))^*6^{\wedge}7/(8^*9)$
-129243849	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4))^*5^*(6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-155551059	$(1 - 2)/3^*((4^5)^{\wedge}6 - 7) - 8^{\wedge}9$
-131009958	$1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(- 6 - 7)+89$	-155897316	$1^*2^*((3+4^*(- 5 - 6)^{\wedge}7+8) - 9)$
-131009960	$-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(- 6 - 7)+89$	-155897420	$1^*2^*((-3 - 4^*(5+6)^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$
-131010026	$(1 - (2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5))/6^*78+9$	-156204287	$1 - ((2+3/4)+5)^*6^{\wedge}7^*8^*9$
-131010070	$(1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5))/-6^*78 - 9$	-156204289	$-1 - ((2+3/4)+5)^*6^{\wedge}7^*8^*9$
-131010136	$1 - ((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+7)+89)$	-156587344	$1/(2^* - 3)^*(- 4^{\wedge}(-5 - 6)+7)/8^{\wedge} - 9$
-131010138	$-1 - ((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+7)+89)$	-158334976	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4)^*(5^*6 - 7))/8^{\wedge} - 9$
-131421530	$1^*2/3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7) - 8^{\wedge}9$	-159253120	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)^* - 5^*(6^{\wedge}7 - 8/ - 9)$
-131587452	$(-12+((3+4^5)^{\wedge}6 - 7)^* - 8)/9$	-159563045	$((12^*3)^{\wedge}4 - 5)^*((-6 - 7)^*8+9)$
-131780407	$(1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4))^*(5/6^{\wedge} - 7 - 8^{\wedge}9)$	-159563511	$(12^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(- 5+6^*(- 7 - 8))+9$
-132030227	$1+(2+3)^*4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7 - 8^{\wedge}9$	-159563529	$(12^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(- 5+6^*(- 7 - 8)) - 9$
-132030229	$-1+(2+3)^*4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7 - 8^{\wedge}9$	-159563995	$((12^*3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*((-6 - 7)^*8+9)$
-132182969	$(-1 - 2^*(- 34+5)^{\wedge}6 - 78)/9$	-161241516	$12^*((-3^*4)^{\wedge}5^*6+7)+8)^*9$
-132543621	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6)/7 - 8^{\wedge}9$	-161243001	$((12^*(3^*4)^{\wedge}5^* - 6+7)+8)^*9$
-133534445	$(12+3^{\wedge}(4^5 - 6))/7 - 8^{\wedge}9$	-161243271	$((-12^*(3^*4)^{\wedge}5^*6 - 7) - 8)^*9$
-133855689	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4))^*(5/6^{\wedge} - 7 - 8^{\wedge}9)$	-161244756	$-12^*((3^*4)^{\wedge}5^*6+7)+8)^*9$
-134177737	$(1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(-4 - (-5 - 6)))/7 - 8^{\wedge}9$	-162072584	$1 - (2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8 - 9$
-134212667	$((1+2)^{\wedge}((-3+4)+5) - 6)^*7 - 8^{\wedge}9$	-162072586	$-1 - (2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8 - 9$
-134214212	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))+5)^*6/7 - 8^{\wedge}9$	-163555547	$((-1 - 23^*(4^5)^{\wedge}6)+78)/9$
-134221244	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))+5)^* - 6/7 - 8^{\wedge}9$	-163555755	$(-1 - 23^*((4^5)^{\wedge}6+78))/9$
-134222789	$((1+2)^{\wedge}((-3+4)+5) - 6)^* - 7 - 8^{\wedge}9$	-163577730	$1/2^*(- 3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^* - 78 - 9$
-134257719	$(-1 - (2^*3)^{\wedge}(-4 - (-5 - 6)))/7 - 8^{\wedge}9$	-163577748	$1/2^*(- 3 - 4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*78+9$
-134557897	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4))^*(5/6^{\wedge} - 7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-163577964	$1/2^*(- 3 - 4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*78+9$
-134901011	$(-12 - 3^{\wedge}(4^5 - 6))/7 - 8^{\wedge}9$	-163577982	$1/2^*(- 3 - 4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*78 - 9$
-135633653	$((-1 - 2+3)^{\wedge}4 - 5^{\wedge}(6+7) - 8)/9$	-164392416	$12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+78^* - 9)$
-135633749	$(1 - ((2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}(6+7) - 8))/9$	-165759048	$12^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6)^*78^* - 9$
-135633751	$(-1 - (((2+3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}(6+7))+8))/9$	-165805380	$(12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6)^*78^* - 9$
-135891835	$(1+(-2 - 3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6)/7 - 8^{\wedge}9$	-165813804	$(-12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6)^*78^*9$
-136405227	$1 - (2+3)^*4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7 - 8^{\wedge}9$	-165860136	$12^*(- 3^{\wedge}(4+5) - 6)^*78^*9$
-136405229	$-1 - (2+3)^*4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7 - 8^{\wedge}9$	-167226768	$12^* - 3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6 - 78^* - 9)$
-136676919	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge}(-3 - 4))^*(5/6^{\wedge} - 7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-168643944	$12^*3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6^*7^*(- 8 - 9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-169810798	$1-2^{-(3-4)}*((5^6)^{7-8})^9$	-214990818	$(-12^{(3+4)+5})^{*6}(-7+8)^9$
-169810800	$-1-2^{-(3-4)}*((5^6)^{7-8})^9$	-214990835	$-1/2*((3^4)^{56/7}-8)+9$
-170666636	$12+3*((4^5)^{6-7})^{*8}/9$	-214990861	$-1/2*((3^4)^{56/7}+8)-9$
-170666639	$(1-2)/3*((4^5)^{6-7})^{*8}+9$	-214990871	$(-12^{(3+4)-5})^{*6}-7/(8-9)$
-170666646	$1^*2+3*((4^5)^{6-7})^{*8}/9$	-214991001	$(-1+(-2-(3^4)^{56/7}))^{*8})^9$
-170666648	$(1-2)^*3*((4^5)^{6-7})^{*8}/9$	-216852351	$(12^{(3+4)}*5/-6+7)^8)^9$
-170666650	$-1^*2+3*((4^5)^{6-7})^{*8}/9$	-220320000	$((-12-3)^4)^{56/7}*(-8-9)$
-170666657	$(1-2)/3*((4^5)^{6-7})^{*8}-9$	-225348480	$(1-2^*3^4)^5*6^7/(-8+9)$
-170666671	$(1+(2-3^*(4^5)^{6-7})^8)/9$	-226491408	$1^*-2^*(3^4)^{56/7}+7^8)^9$
-171050991	$(-1+(2^*34)^{56/7})^{*8}+9$	-226493424	$1^*-2^*(3^4)^{56/7}+7^8)^9$
-171051007	$(-1-(2^*34)^{56/7})^{*8}+9$	-228886637	$(-123^4+5-(-6+7)^8)^9$
-171051009	$(-1+(2^*34)^{56/7})^{*8}-9$	-228886655	$(-123^4-5*(6-7)^8)^9$
-171051025	$(-1-(2^*34)^{56/7})^{*8}-9$	-229582488	$(1-2/3^{-(4^5+6)})^{*7}(-8-9)$
-171907950	$1-2^{-(3-4)}*((5^6)^{7+8})^9$	-229582536	$(-1-2/3^{-(4^5+6)})^{*7}(-8-9)$
-171907952	$-1-2^{-(3-4)}*((5^6)^{7+8})^9$	-233847024	$-12^*(3^4-(5+6)^7/(-8-9))$
-172565664	$(-1-2)^*(3+4)^{56/7}+8^9$	-234880671	$(1-(-2^*3+4^5+6)^7)^8+9$
-173015040	$(-1+2^{-(3-4)}*(5-6^7))^8+9$	-234880687	$(-1+(2^*3-4^5+6)^7)^8+9$
-174334090	$((1^*23^4-5)-6)^*7^8+9$	-234880689	$(1-(-2^*3+4^5+6)^7)^8-9$
-174347796	$((-1^*23^4-5)-6)^*7^8+9$	-234880705	$(-1+(2^*3-4^5+6)^7)^8-9$
-176884389	$1+2/-3^*((4^5)^{6-7})^{*8}/9$	-234880986	$-1+(2^*3+4^5+6)^7)^8-9$
-176884390	$-1^*2/3^*((4^5)^{6-7})^{*8}/9$	-234881343	$(1+(-2^*3-4^5+6)^7)^8+9$
-176884391	$-1+2/-3^*((4^5)^{6-7})^{*8}/9$	-234881359	$(-1-(2^*3+4^5+6)^7)^8+9$
-177332766	$1/23^*(-4-5^*(6-7)^8)^9$	-234881361	$(1+(-2^*3-4^5+6)^7)^8-9$
-178032735	$(1+2)^{(3^4)}^{*5}/67^{(8-9)}$	-234881377	$(-1-(2^*3+4^5+6)^7)^8-9$
-179158272	$-12^{(3+4)}*(5-6^{-(7-8+9)})$	-235560960	$12^{(3+4)}*5/-6^*(7+8)/9$
-179159808	$-12^{(3+4)}*(5+6^{-(7-8+9)})$	-238609287	$1-(2^{-(3-(-4-5^6))})^{*7}+8)^9$
-179263836	$1^*-2^*(-3+4^{56/7}+7^8)^9$	-238609289	$-1-(2^{-(3-(-4-5^6))})^{*7}+8)^9$
-179263944	$1^*2^*(-3-4^{56/7}+7^8)^9$	-238878655	$(12^{(3+4)}*5/-6+7)^8+9$
-180844908	$1/(2^*3)^*(4-5^{6+7})^8/9$	-238878673	$(12^{(3+4)}*5/-6+7)^8-9$
-181273498	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5-6+7)^8/9$	-238878767	$(-12^{(3+4)}*5/6-7)^8+9$
-186646083	$1/2^*(-3+4^{56/7}-7)^8-9$	-238878785	$(-12^{(3+4)}*5/6-7)^8-9$
-186646215	$-1/2^*(-3+4^{56/7}-7)^8+9$	-240884383	$(-1-2/3)^*(4^5)^{6-7}-8^9$
-186646218	$1/2^*(-3-(4^{56/7}+7)^8+9)$	-241864669	$(12+3+4^*(5-6^{-(7+8)+9}))$
-186646838	$1/2^*(3-(4^{56/7}+7)^8+9)$	-241864699	$-12-3+4^*(5-6^{-(7+8)+9})$
-186646841	$1/2^*(-3+(-4^{56/7}-7)^8+9)$	-241864709	$12+3-4^*(5+6^{-(7+8)+9})$
-186646973	$1/2^*(-3-4^{56/7}-7)^8+9$	-241864739	$-12-3-4^*(5+6^{-(7+8)+9})$
-189896760	$(1-2^*3^4(4+5))^*67^8+9$	-246857067	$((-1-2+3^*(4^5)^{6/7}-7+8)^9$
-189906408	$(-1-2^*3^4(4+5))^*67^8+9$	-246857211	$((1+2-3^*(4^5)^{6/7}-7+8)^9$
-191102964	$12-((-3+4-5)^6)^{7+8-9}$	-249261504	$(-1-2^*(3+4^{-(5-6)})/7)^8-9$
-191102973	$1+2-(((3-4)+5)^6)^{7+8-9}$	-250822579	$(-12^{(3+4)+5+6})^{*7}+8)^9$
-191102988	$-12-((-3+4-5)^6)^{7+8-9}$	-251658016	$(-1-(2^{\Delta}3-4^{-(5-6)})^7)^8-9$
-193155748	$1^*23^*(4-5^6)^{7+8+9}$	-251658236	$(-1+2^{\Delta}3-4^{-(5-6)-7})^8+9$
-193155932	$-1^*23^*(4-5^6)^{7+8+9}$	-251658244	$(-1-2^{\Delta}3-4^{-(5-6)+7})^8+9$
-193710150	$12^*(3^{\Delta}(4+5+6)+7)^8+9$	-251658464	$(-1-(2^{\Delta}3+4^{-(5-6)})^7)^8-9$
-193710339	$12^*(3^{\Delta}(4+5+6)+7)^8-9$	-252434475	$(1+2)^{\Delta}(3^4)^*5^*(6-7)^8-9$
-195485764	$(-1/2^*((34+5)^{6+7}+8)/9$	-2527238016	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5-5/6^{\Delta}7-8^{\Delta}9)$
-195485765	$(1/2^*((34+5)^{6-7}+8)/-9$	-264238812	$((12^*3-4^{\Delta}(5+6))^7+8)^9$
-196440660	$((1^*23^4-5)-6)^*78^9$	-264238956	$((12^*3-4^{\Delta}(5+6))^7-8)^9$
-196456104	$((-1^*23^4-5)-6)^*78^9$	-264243348	$((12^*3+4^{\Delta}(5+6))^7+8)^9$
-200278016	$(-1-2^{-(3-4)}*(56+7))^8+9$	-264243492	$((-12^*3-4^{\Delta}(5+6))^7-8)^9$
-200802304	$(1/2^*-3+4^{-(5-6)+7})/8^{\Delta}-9$	-265797934	$1^*-2^*(-3^{\Delta}(4+5)^6+7+8)^9$
-201293824	$(1/2^*-3+4^{-(5+6-7)})/8^{\Delta}-9$	-267875544	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4^5-6^{7+8})^9$
-201326184	$(1+2/3^*(4^{\Delta}(5+6)+7))^8+9$	-267875624	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5+6^{7+8})^9$
-201326328	$(1-2/3^*(4^{\Delta}(5+6)+7))^8-9$	-268349440	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5+6^7-8^{\Delta}9)$
-201326480	$1/2^*(-3+4^{-(5-6)+7})/8^{\Delta}-9$	-268429834	$1^*-2^*((-3^{\Delta}(4+5)+6)/7+8)^9$
-201326704	$1/2^*(-3-4^{-(5-6)+7})/8^{\Delta}-9$	-268435044	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4-5^6+7+8)^9$
-201359360	$(1/2^*-3-4^{-(5+6-7)})/8^{\Delta}-9$	-268435868	$((1-2)+3)^*(4-5^6+7-8^{\Delta}9)$
-201850880	$(1/2^*-3-4^{-(5-6)+7})/8^{\Delta}-9$	-268441078	$1^*2^*((-3^{\Delta}(4+5)+6)/7-8^{\Delta}9)$
-202375168	$(-1+2^{-(3-4)}*5^*(6-7))/8^{\Delta}-9$	-268521472	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4^5+6^7+8^{\Delta}9)$
-203450535	$1/(2^*-3)^*(4+5^{\Delta}(6+7)+8)$	-268738425	$(12^{(3+4)}*5/-6+7+8)^9$
-204067503	$(1+2)^{\Delta}((-3+4)+5)^*(6^{\Delta}7+8)+9$	-268738695	$(12^{(3+4)}*5/-6-(7+8))^9$
-204067521	$(1+2)^{\Delta}((-3+4)+5)^*(6^{\Delta}7+8)-9$	-268995288	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5-6^{\Delta}7-8^{\Delta}9)$
-204079167	$(1+2)^{\Delta}((-3+4)+5)^*(6^{\Delta}7-8)+9$	-268995368	$((1-2)+3)^*(4^5-(6^{\Delta}7+8^{\Delta}9))$
-204079185	$(1+2)^{\Delta}((-3+4)+5)^*(6^{\Delta}7-8)-9$	-271072978	$1^*2^*((-3^{\Delta}(4+5))^6+7-8^{\Delta}9)$
-208324872	$(1+2)^{\Delta}(3^4)^*56/7^{(8-9)}$	-278235754	$((1+2-3^{\Delta}4)^{5-6})/7+8^{\Delta}9$
-208973710	$(12^*3+4^{\Delta}(5-6))^*(7^{\Delta}8+9)$	-279632896	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4^5/6^{\Delta}7+8^{\Delta}9)$
-210937257	$(-1-2)^{\Delta}3^*(4^5)^{\Delta}((-6+7)+8)-9$	-286331153	$(-1-2^{\Delta}3+5)/6/((-7+8)+9)$
-210937743	$(1+2)^{\Delta}3^*(4^5)^{\Delta}(-6+7+8)-9$	-289650744	$-12^*((3-4^5)^{6+7}/(-8-9))$
-211631624	$1+(2^*-3)^{\Delta}(4+5)^*(6+7+8)-9$	-294617088	$12^{(3+4)}/5^*(6^{\Delta}7+8)^9$
-211631626	$-1+(2^*-3)^{\Delta}(4+5)^*(6+7+8)-9$	-295157813	$-1/(2+3)^*(4-(5+6+7))^{\Delta}+9$
-214958080	$(-1-2^{-(3-4)}*(5+6)^7)^8+9$	-296358912	$-12^{(3+4)}*(5/6^{\Delta}7+8)^9$
-214990695	$(1+(-2+(3^4)^{56/7}))^{*8})^9$	-296515042	$1^*-2^*((3+4)^{56/7}-8)^9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-298666726	$1^2/3^*((4^5)^{6^*}-7-89)$	-396361404	$12^*(3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*7/-8)^*9$
-301989327	$(1-(2/3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^*8)^*9$	-396362052	$12^*(-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*7/8)^*9$
-301989372	$(1/(2^*3)-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*8^*9$	-397131149	$(-1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*(-6-7^{\wedge}8))/9$
-301989396	$(1/(2^*-3)-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*8^*9$	-397770855	$(-1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5))^*(-6+7^{\wedge}8)/9$
-301989441	$(-1-(2/3-(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7))^*8)^*9$	-397771683	$(-1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5))^*(6+7^{\wedge}8)/9$
-301990335	$(1-(2/3-(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7))^*8)^*9$	-401255192	$123^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*7+8)/-9$
-301990380	$(1/(2^*-3)+(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7))^*-8^*9$	-402128894	$1^2-(3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/8^{\wedge}-9$
-301990404	$(1/(2^*-3)-(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7))^*8^*9$	-402128898	$-1^2-(3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/8^{\wedge}-9$
-301990449	$(-1-(2/3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*8)^*9$	-403177470	$1^2+(-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/8^{\wedge}-9$
-305175763	$1^2*((-3-(-4+5^{\wedge}(6+7)))/8+9)$	-403177474	$-1^2+(-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/8^{\wedge}-9$
-305175765	$1^2*((-3-4-5^{\wedge}(6+7))/8+9)$	-406901035	$(1+2)^*(3^*4-5^{\wedge}(6+7)+8)/9$
-305175799	$1^*-2*((3-4+5^{\wedge}(6+7))/8+9)$	-408503455	$(-1-2^*((-3-4)^*5)^{\wedge}6-78))/9$
-305175801	$1^2*((-3-4-5^{\wedge}(6+7))/8-9)$	-412453393	$((1+2-3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5-6)/7+89$
-306377603	$-12^*((-3-4)^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)/(8^*9)$	-412453571	$((1+2-3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5-6)/7-89$
-311794694	$1^2*((3^*4+(-5-6)^{\wedge}7^*8)+9)$	-416063735	$(-1-2-34)^{\wedge}5^*6-7/(8-9)$
-311794706	$1^2*((-3/4+(5+6)^{\wedge}7)^*-8+9)$	-419298270	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^*4)-5)-6)^*-789$
-311794766	$1^2*((-3/4-(5+6)^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$	-423263142	$1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*-6^*7+89$
-311794778	$1^2*((-3^*4-(5+6)^{\wedge}7^*8)-9)$	-423263144	$-1+(2^*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6^*7+89$
-313174688	$(-1+2)/3^*(4^{\wedge}(-5-6)-7)^*8^{\wedge}9$	-423263281	$(1+(2+34)^{\wedge}5+6)^*-7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-320078125	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))/5^{\wedge}(-6-(-7+8)^{\wedge}9)$	-439842950	$12+(34+5)^{\wedge}6+7/-8+9$
-320621769	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*5/-6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	-439842968	$12+(34+5)^{\wedge}6+7/-8-9$
-321236272	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*((5/-6)^{\wedge}7/8+9)$	-439842974	$(-12-((34+5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8)+9$
-323736272	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*((5/6)^{\wedge}7/8+9)$	-439842992	$(-12-((34+5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8)-9$
-327477281	$((1-234)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)+8)/-9$	-444107646	$(-1-2)^*((3+4^*5)^{\wedge}6+7/(8-9))$
-329554456	$12^*((-3-4)^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)/(8^*9)$	-452978460	$12^*(-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^*-8)^*-9$
-331080890	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^*4)-5)-6)^*-7^*89$	-452979108	$12^*(-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^*8)^*9$
-332150613	$12-(3^*45)^{\wedge}(-6-7+8+9)$	-452984580	$1/2^*(-3^*4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*8^*9$
-334588122	$-1/2^*((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8^*9$	-452985084	$1/2^*(3^*4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*-8^*9$
-336662748	$(1/(2+34))^{\wedge}-5^*((6/7)^{\wedge}-8-9)$	-452990556	$12^*(-3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*-8)^*-9$
-338866737	$((1+234)^{\wedge}(5+6-7)+8)/-9$	-452991204	$12^*(-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*8)^*9$
-339737112	$(-1-2)^*(3^*4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^*8)^*9$	-453183708	$(-1+234-5^*(6+7)^{\wedge}8)/9$
-339740136	$(-1-2)^*(3^*4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^*8)^*9$	-453183760	$(-1-234-5^*(6+7)^{\wedge}8)/9$
-341333279	$(1-2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7))^*8+9$	-458576472	$123^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^*8/-9$
-341333286	$1+2/-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9$	-459276288	$((1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))-5)^*6/7^*8^{\wedge}9$
-341333287	$-1^2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9$	-460324864	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^*567)/8^{\wedge}-9$
-341333288	$-1+2/-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9$	-461320304	$(1/2^*(-3-45^{\wedge}6)+78)/9$
-341333295	$1+2^*-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8/9$	-461320321	$(1/2^*(3-45^{\wedge}6)-78)/9$
-341333296	$-1^2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8/9$	-465813569	$(-12^{\wedge}(3+4)-5)^*(6-7/(8-9))$
-341333297	$-1+2^*-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8/9$	-467664896	$(1/2+3)^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)/7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-341333304	$1-(2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$	-469761376	$(1/2-3^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*-7/8^{\wedge}-9$
-341333305	$-1^2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9$	-469762000	$1/2^*(-3^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)^*-8^{\wedge}9$
-341333306	$(-1-2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$	-469762096	$1/2^*(3^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)^*-8^{\wedge}9$
-341333313	$(-1+2/-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7))^*8-9$	-469762720	$(1/-2-3^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7/8^{\wedge}-9$
-341333327	$(1-(2^*3^*(4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8)/9$	-473776128	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)/5^*(67-8/9)$
-345888040	$1^2*((-3+4+5^*-6/7^{\wedge}8)-9)$	-476171127	$(1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6^*-7/8)^*9$
-345888080	$1^2*((3-4-5^*6/7^{\wedge}8)-9)$	-476171145	$(-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*-6^*7/8)^*9$
-348613632	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5/6^*7/8+9)$	-485407657	$((-1-2-34)^{\wedge}5+6)^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-352321788	$12^*(-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$	-487862600	$1^2*((-3)^{\wedge}((4+5)+6)+7)^*(8+9)$
-354418688	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^*5^*6^*7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	-487862838	$(-1-2)^{\wedge}(3^*4+5)^*(6^*7-8)/9$
-359999991	$(-1+(2+3)/(4^*5)^{\wedge}-6-7)/8^*-9$	-487863076	$1^2*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)+7)^*(-8-9)$
-360000009	$((1+(2+3)^*(4^*5)^{\wedge}6)+7)/-8^*9$	-488281088	$1^2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}(6-((-7-8)+9)))$
-362324664	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))-5)/6^{\wedge}(7-8-9)$	-488281182	$1^2*(34-5^{\wedge}(6-((-7-8)+9)))$
-362523595	$(-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(-5-6^*7^{\wedge}(-8+9))$	-488281318	$1^*-2^*(34+5^{\wedge}(6-((-7-8)+9)))$
-362666627	$(1-2)/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*(8+9)$	-488281412	$1^*-2^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}(6-((-7-8)+9)))$
-362796786	$1^2*3^*(45-6^{\wedge}((-7+8)+9))$	-489438437	$1+((-2+3)-4)/5^*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9)$
-362797326	$1^2*3^*(45+6^{\wedge}((-7+8)+9))$	-489438439	$-1+((-2+3)-4)/5^*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9)$
-363269448	$((-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))-5)/6^{\wedge}(7-8-9)$	-492131648	$(1-2/3^*(-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7))/8^{\wedge}-9$
-364249088	$(-1+2+3^*(-4^{\wedge}-5+6))/-7^*8^{\wedge}9$	-494331666	$1^2*(((-3-4)^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)/8+9)$
-364463530	$(-1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4-56))/-7^{\wedge}8-9)/9$	-494331702	$1^2*(((-3-4)^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)/8-9)$
-364499983	$1/2^*(34-(5^*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9))$	-499117892	$(12^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*-7^*-8-9)$
-364500017	$-1/2^*(34+(5^*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9))$	-499121445	$(-1+(2^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*-7)^*(-8-9)$
-367001600	$(1/2+3)^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-499122179	$(1-(2^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7)^*(-8-9)$
-373063860	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^*4)-5)-6)^*-78^*9$	-499122149	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*7^*(8+9)$
-378313937	$(-1-23^{\wedge}(-4+5+6)+7+8)/9$	-499122203	$(-1-2)^{\wedge}3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*7^*(8+9)$
-378954471	$1-(23^{\wedge}(-4-(-5-6))+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	-499122873	$(-1-(2^*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*-7)^*(-8-9)$
-378954472	$(-1/23^{\wedge}(4-5-6)-7^{\wedge}8)/9$	-499122907	$(1+(2^*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7)^*(-8-9)$
-378954473	$-1-(23^{\wedge}(-4-(-5-6))+7^{\wedge}8)/9$	-499126460	$(12^*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7^*(-8-9)$
-383999895	$(-1+2/-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)+8)^*9$	-500113359	$123^{\wedge}4-(5^*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9)$
-384000072	$1^2*((-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6+7)+8)+9)$	-515900253	$123^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-384000108	$1^2*((-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6+7)+8)-9)$	-525336576	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(5+6)+7)^*8^{\wedge}9$
-393287535	$(-1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5-6)^*-7^{\wedge}8)/9$	-528731836	$(-12+((34-5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*-8)/9$
-394762352	$(1+2)^*((3+4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*-8/9$	-533794816	$-1/(2^*(-3^{\wedge}4+5))^{\wedge}((6+7-8)-9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-536510464	$((-1+2^{(3^*-4)})^{(5+6)+7})^{*8^{\wedge}9}$	-704643035	$(1/2-3^*4^{(5+6)})^{*7^*8+9}$
-537231360	$((-1-2^{(3^*-4)})^{(5+6)+7})^{*8^{\wedge}9}$	-704643053	$(1/2-3^*4^{(5+6)})^{*7^*8-9}$
-546671210	$((1+2-3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5-6)/7-8^{\wedge}9$	-704643059	$(1/2-3^*4^{(5+6)^*7})^{*8+9}$
-548405248	$((-1-2^{(3-4)})^{(5+6)+7})^{*8^{\wedge}9}$	-704643067	$(1/-2-3^*4^{(5+6)^*7})^{*8+9}$
-548801406	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3^*4)^*(5^{\wedge}6/(7-8)+9)$	-704643077	$(1/2-3^*4^{(5+6)^*7})^{*8-9}$
-564950354	$1^*-2^*((3+4)^{\wedge}(5+6)/7-8^*9)$	-704643085	$(1/-2-3^*4^{(5+6)^*7})^{*8-9}$
-564950642	$1^*-2^*((3+4)^{\wedge}(5+6)/7+8^*9)$	-704643091	$(1/-2-3^*4^{(5+6)})^{*7^*8+9}$
-566226180	$(12^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^{*(7+8)^*9}$	-704643109	$(1/-2-3^*4^{(5+6)})^{*7^*8-9}$
-566230221	$(1+(2^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^{*(7+8)})^*9$	-716800042	$((12^*3+4)^{\wedge}5+6)^*-7^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-566230239	$(-1+(2^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^{*(7+8)})^*9$	-717609375	$(12-3)^{\wedge}4^*-5^{\wedge}6/7^{\wedge}(8-9)$
-566230716	$(12^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*(7+8))^*9$	-725333237	$(1-2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7))^{*(8+9)}$
-566230797	$((1+2)^{\wedge}3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*(7+8))^*9$	-725333253	$1+2/-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*(8+9)$
-566230941	$(1+(2/3-4^{\wedge}(5+6))^{*(7+8)})^*9$	-725333254	$-1^*2/3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*(8+9)$
-566231093	$1-(2^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*(-7-8))^*9$	-725333255	$-1+2/-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*(8+9)$
-566231095	$-1-(2^*3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*(-7-8))^*9$	-725333271	$(-1+2/-3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7))^{*(8+9)}$
-566231283	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*(-7-8))^*9$	-725589216	$(1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+67)^*8^*9$
-566231364	$(12^*-3-4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*(7+8))^*9$	-725589360	$(-1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+67)^*8^*9$
-566231841	$(1+(2^*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^{*(7-8)})^*9$	-725594033	$12^*(3/4+5-6^{\wedge}((-7+8)+9))$
-566231859	$(-1+(2^*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^{*(7-8)})^*9$	-725594061	$12^*(-3/4+5-6^{\wedge}((-7+8)+9))$
-566235900	$(12^*3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))^{*(7-8)^*9}$	-725594102	$1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6-78)+9$
-566999999	$((1+(2/3^*45)^{\wedge}6-7)+8)/9$	-725594104	$-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6-78)+9$
-567000001	$((-1-(2/3^*45)^{\wedge}6^*7)-8)/9$	-725594120	$1-(2^*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6-78)+9$
-572522496	$(1/2+3)^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-725594122	$-1-(2^*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6-78)+9$
-573114351	$(-1+(23^*4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*-8+9$	-725594163	$12^*(3/4-5-6^{\wedge}(-7+8)+9)$
-573114385	$(-1-(23^*4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*-8+9$	-725594181	$-12^*(3/4+5+6^{\wedge}(-7+8)+9)$
-581130689	$-1/2^*(3^{\wedge}(4^*5-(-6+7))-89)$	-725598864	$(-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+67)^*8^*-9$
-581130778	$1/2^*(-3^{\wedge}(4^*5-(-6+7))-89)$	-725599008	$(1-(2^*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+67)^*8^*-9$
-593494016	$(1+(-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)^*6)/7^*-8^{\wedge}9$	-728760320	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^*567)/8^{\wedge}9$
-599233245	$123/4^*((-5-6)^{\wedge}7-89)$	-728999940	$(12+3)^*4-(5^*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9)$
-604661692	$1^*2^*(34-5/6^{\wedge}(7-8-9))$	-729000060	$(-12-3)^*4-(5^*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9)$
-604661828	$-1^*2^*(34-5/-6^{\wedge}(7-8-9))$	-729000625	$-1^*((2+3)^{\wedge}4+(5^*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9))$
-605303159	$1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4+5)/6^*(-7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-738197425	$1/2^*(3^{\wedge}4+(5+6)^*(7-8^{\wedge}9))$
-605303161	$-1+((2+3)^{\wedge}4+5)/6^*(-7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-738197488	$(1/2^*(-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7))/-8^{\wedge}9$
-607968504	$(1+2)^{\wedge}(3^*4)^*(-5+67^*(-8-9))$	-738197520	$(1/2^*(-3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7))/-8^{\wedge}9$
-610351486	$1/2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}(6+7)+8^*9)$	-738197583	$1/2^*(-3^{\wedge}4+(-5-6)^*(7+8^{\wedge}9))$
-610351639	$-1/2^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}(6+7)+8^*9)$	-746423544	$((1+2^{\wedge}(-3+4-5))^{\wedge}6-7)/8^{\wedge}9$
-612755217	$((-1-2)^*(3-4)^*5)^{\wedge}6-78)/9$	-755827192	$-1+(2^*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(67+8)+9$
-622579985	$1-(2-(3+4)^{\wedge}5)^*6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9$	-755827208	$1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(67+8)+9$
-622579987	$-1-(2-(3+4)^{\wedge}5)^*6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9$	-756449185	$(1-(2^*3^*4)^{\wedge}5)^*((-6-7)^*-8-9)$
-626349376	$1^*2/-3^*(-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)^*8^{\wedge}9$	-756449375	$(-1+(2^*3^*-4)^{\wedge}5)^*((-6-7)^*-8-9)$
-626349377	$-1-2/3^*(-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)/8^{\wedge}9$	-758550528	$(-12^*(3^{\wedge}4-5))^{\wedge}(-6^{\wedge}(-7+8)+9)$
-632480990	$1^*2^*((3^*4)^{\wedge}5-4^*5+6)^{\wedge}7+8+9)$	-759496704	$((1+2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4+5)^*-6/7^*8^{\wedge}9$
-632481058	$1^*2^*(3/(-4^*5+6)^{\wedge}7-8-9)$	-760567104	$(-1-2/3^*(-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7))/8^{\wedge}9$
-634894397	$1+(((2^*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7+8)^*9$	-771750441	$1^*23^*((-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*8+9)$
-634894399	$-1+(((2^*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7+8)^*9$	-771750855	$1^*23^*((-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*8-9)$
-634895297	$1-(((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7+8)^*9$	-771753017	$1^*23^*((-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^*8+9)$
-634895299	$-1-(((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7+8)^*9$	-771753431	$1^*-23^*((4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)^*8+9)$
-643292928	$(12^*3)^{\wedge}4^*((-5+6+7)^*8+9)$	-774821294	$1+(2-3^{\wedge}(-4-5))^*(6-7-8)^{\wedge}9$
-647495680	$(1-(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6^*7)^*8^{\wedge}9$	-774821295	$1^*(2-3^{\wedge}(-4-5))^*(6-7-8)^{\wedge}9$
-652582856	$12^*3-4/5^*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9)$	-774821296	$-1+(2-3^{\wedge}(-4-5))^*(6-7-8)^{\wedge}9$
-652584548	$12^*3-4/5^*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9)$	-774860660	$1+(2+3^{\wedge}(-4-5))^*(6-7-8)^{\wedge}9$
-652584571	$1/((2+3)/(4^*(5-(6+7)^{\wedge}8)+9))$	-774860661	$1^*(2+3^{\wedge}(-4-5))^*(6-7-8)^{\wedge}9$
-652584620	$-12^*3-4/5^*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9)$	-774860662	$-1+(2+3^{\wedge}(-4-5))^*(6-7-8)^{\wedge}9$
-652586312	$-12^{\wedge}3-4/5^*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9)$	-775084161	$((1/2^*34)^{\wedge}(56/7+8))/-9$
-655905562	$(-1+23+4^{\wedge}5^*(6-7^{\wedge}8))/9$	-789053440	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5/6^*7/8^{\wedge}9$
-656506767	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5)/-6-7^*(8-9)$	-790661250	$(12+3)^{\wedge}4^*((-5^{\wedge}6-7)/(8-9))$
-664301250	$1^*-2^*(3^*45)^{\wedge}((-6-7+8)+9)$	-792723240	$(-1+2)^*3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*-7+8)^*9$
-668009344	$(12^*3)^{\wedge}4+5^*(6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-792723672	$(-1+2)^*3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*7+8)^*-9$
-669176136	$(12-((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8)^*9$	-793097760	$-12^*((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7-8)/9$
-669176352	$(-12+((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7)/-8)^*9$	-804225024	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6^*7-8)/9$
-670564351	$1-(2+3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/8^{\wedge}9$	-804782079	$1+(2^*3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/-8^{\wedge}9$
-670564353	$-1-(2+3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/8^{\wedge}9$	-804782081	$-1+(2^*3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/-8^{\wedge}9$
-671612927	$1+(-2-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/8^{\wedge}9$	-805240831	$1-2^*(3-4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6+7)))/8^{\wedge}9$
-671612929	$-1+(-2-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/8^{\wedge}9$	-805240833	$-1-2^*(3-4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6+7)))/8^{\wedge}9$
-682666556	$12^*(3+((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*-8/9)$	-805273599	$1+(2^*3-4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6+7)))/-8^{\wedge}9$
-682666588	$12^*(3-((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8)/9$	-805273601	$-1+(2^*3-4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6+7)))/-8^{\wedge}9$
-682666596	$-12^*(3+((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8)/9$	-805305632	$(1+23^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)-7)/8^{\wedge}9$
-682666628	$-12^*(3+((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7)^*8)/9$	-805305919	$1-2^*(3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)^*7)^*8^{\wedge}9$
-693633024	$(1-(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)/6-7)^*8^{\wedge}9$	-805305920	$1^*2^*(-3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6)^*7)/8^{\wedge}9$
-697356879	$1^*2^*(-3^{\wedge}(4^*5)+6)/((-7+8)+9)$	-805306208	$(1+(2+3)^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)-7)^*8^{\wedge}9$
-701537616	$12^*(3^*(4-(5+6)^{\wedge}7)+8)+9$	-805306528	$(1-(2+3)^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)-7)^*8^{\wedge}9$
-701538696	$12^*(-3^*(4+(5+6)^{\wedge}7+8)-9)$	-805306816	$1^*2^*(-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)^*7)/8^{\wedge}9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-805306817	$-1-2^*(3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7^*8^{\wedge}9$	-1040476681	$-1-(2+3)^*4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-805307104	$(1-23^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)-7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	-1042284544	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)^*5^*6)-7)^*8^{\wedge}9$
-805339135	$1+(2^*3+4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6+7)))/-8^{\wedge}-9$	-1050097311	$((1-2^*34)^{\wedge}5-6)^*7-8)/9$
-805339137	$-1+(2^*3+4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6+7)))/-8^{\wedge}-9$	-1051197439	$1+((-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6+7)/-8^{\wedge}-9$
-805371903	$1-2^*(-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6+7)))/-8^{\wedge}-9$	-1051197440	$(1^*(-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6+7)/-8^{\wedge}-9$
-805371905	$-1-2^*(-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-(-6+7)))/-8^{\wedge}-9$	-1051197441	$-1+((-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6+7)/-8^{\wedge}-9$
-805830655	$1+(2^*3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/-8^{\wedge}-9$	-1056964384	$(-1-(2^{\wedge}(-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6))))^*7/8^{\wedge}-9$
-805830657	$-1+(2^*3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/-8^{\wedge}-9$	-1056964832	$(-1-(2^{\wedge}(-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6))))^*7/8^{\wedge}-9$
-816840704	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(5+6)-7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	-1062207488	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(5+6)-7)^*8^{\wedge}9$
-822083360	$-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7/8^{\wedge}-9$	-1079753125	$(1-(2+34)^{\wedge}5)^*(6/7+8)+9$
-822083575	$(1/2+3)^*-4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*7^*8+9$	-1085069372	$(1/2+34^{\wedge}5-6(6+7))^*8/9$
-822083593	$(1/2+3)^*-4^{\wedge}(5+6)^*7^*8-9$	-1085069374	$1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}(6+7)^*8)/-9$
-822083808	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6))^*7/8^{\wedge}-9$	-1085069376	$-1-((2+3)^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}(6+7)^*8)/-9$
-826802176	$((-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5/6+7)/-8^{\wedge}-9$	-1085069516	$(1/2-3/4^{\wedge}5(6+7))^*8/9$
-827850751	$1-((2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)/6+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	-1085277672	$((1-23)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}(6+7))^*-8/9$
-827850752	$(1^*(-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6-7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	-1088391162	$1^*2^*(3+(-4-5)/6^{\wedge}(7-8-9))$
-827850753	$-1-((2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)/6+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	-1088391174	$-1^*2^*(3+(-4-5)/-6^{\wedge}(7-8-9))$
-83385954	$1^*-2^*((3+4)^{\wedge}(5+6)/7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-1098907517	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3+4^*5))^*(6/7+8)+9$
-836763648	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5^*6-7)^*8^{\wedge}9$	-1098907779	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4^*5))^*(6^*7+89)$
-846526454	$1+(2^*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+78)+9$	-1105199104	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5^*6+7)^*-8^{\wedge}9$
-846526456	$-1+(2^*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6+78)+9$	-1112246289	$1/2^*((-3-4)^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)/8^*9$
-849870848	$((-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6-7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	-1119214694	$((-1-2)^{\wedge}(3+4^*5)+6)^*78/9$
-851367770	$(1-2/3^{\wedge}(-4^*5+6)+7)^*89$	-1119214798	$((1+2)^{\wedge}(3^*4+5)+6)^*78/-9$
-851367948	$(-1-2/3^{\wedge}(-4^*5+6)+7)^*89$	-1119877121	$(1^*2-3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7))^*89$
-851369016	$(1+2/-3^{\wedge}(-4^*5+6)-7)^*89$	-1119881215	$(-1^*2+3^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7))^*89$
-851369194	$((-1-2/3^{\wedge}(-4^*5+6))-7)^*89$	-1132624648	$((1+2^{\wedge}(-3+4-5))^{\wedge}6+7)/-8^{\wedge}-9$
-858783744	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(-5-6))^*7^*8^{\wedge}9$	-1138779647	$1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6-7^*(8+9))$
-860162240	$(1-2^*(3/4)^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7^*-8^{\wedge}9$	-1138779649	$-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)^*(6-7^*(8+9))$
-867926016	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6^*-7-8)/9$	-1140850672	$(1/2^*(3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7))/-8^{\wedge}-9$
-871696092	$((1+2^*(3^{\wedge}(4^*5+6))-7)/-8+9$	-1140850704	$1/2^*(3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)/-8^{\wedge}-9$
-871696110	$((1+2^*(3^{\wedge}(4^*5+6))-7)/-8-9$	-1146317445	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*(5-6^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}(-8+9))$
-871696116	$-1^*2^*((3^*(4+5))^{\wedge}6+7)/8^*9$	-1146877307	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*(5-6^{\wedge}7)^{\wedge}(-8+9)$
-872415136	$(1/2-(-3^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7))^*8^{\wedge}9$	-1162241784	$(1+2-3^{\wedge}(-4-5))^*(6-(7+8))^{\wedge}9$
-872415328	$(1/2-(-3^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7))^*8^{\wedge}9$	-1162241150	$(1+2+3^{\wedge}(-4-5))/(-6-(7+8))^{\wedge}-9$
-873997203	$1/(2/3+4)^*(-5^*(6+7)^{\wedge}8-9)$	-1179010630	$((-1-2^{\wedge}34)+5)/(6/7^*(8+9))$
-892392588	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))/5^*(6^*(7^{\wedge}8+9))$	-1179090423	$(1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)/6^*78)^*9$
-902823936	$((-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5+6)^*-7^*8^{\wedge}9$	-1179090441	$(-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)/-6^*78)^*9$
-905967999	$(1-(2-3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7))^*8-9)^*9$	-1185415168	$(1-(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)/6+7)^*-8^{\wedge}9$
-905968017	$(-1+(2-3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7))^*8)^*9$	-1193046471	$((1+2^{\wedge}34)^*-5+6+7)/(8^*9)$
-905968125	$(-1-2+3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^*8)^*-9$	-1194666648	$(-1-2+3^*(4^*5)^{\wedge}6)^*7^*-8/9$
-905968179	$(-1-2-3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7)^*8)^*9$	-1199245093	$(-1-((2^*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7)^*(-8-9)$
-905968287	$(1+(2-3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7))^*8)^*9$	-1199245127	$(-1+((2^*-3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7)^*(8+9)$
-905968305	$(1-(-2-3^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7))^*8)^*-9$	-1199246521	$(-1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7)^*(-8-9)$
-905971023	$(1-(-2-3^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7))^*8)^*9$	-1199246537	$1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*-7^*(8+9)$
-905971041	$(1-(-2-3^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7))^*8)^*-9$	-1199246539	$-1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*-7^*(8+9)$
-905971149	$(-1-2-3^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7))^*8^*-9$	-1199246555	$(-1-((2^*3)^{\wedge}(4+5)+6)^*7)^*(8+9)$
-905971203	$(-1-2+3^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7))^*8^*9$	-1207435264	$(-12+3+4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/8^{\wedge}-9$
-905971311	$(1+(2-3^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7))^*-8)^*9$	-1207958886	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*(4+5)))^-67-8)^*-9$
-905971329	$(-1-(-2-3^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7))^*8)^*9$	-1207959012	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3^*(4+5))+67)-8)^*9$
-911662101	$123/((4-5)-6)^*7^{\wedge}-8)^*9$	-1207960092	$((1+2^{\wedge}(3^*(4+5))+67)-8)^*-9$
-915931136	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}(-3-4)-5)/6^*7)^*8^{\wedge}9$	-1207960218	$((1-2^{\wedge}(3^*(4+5)))^-67-8)^*9$
-918028288	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5)/6+7)^*-8^{\wedge}9$	-1208483840	$(-12+3-4^{\wedge}(-5-6+7))/8^{\wedge}-9$
-939523360	$1^*(23^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)-7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	-1217868015	$(-1+(23^*4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*(-8-9)$
-939523392	$((-1+23)^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)-7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	-1217868049	$(-1-(23^*4)^{\wedge}(5+6-7))^*(8+9)$
-939524800	$((1-23)^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)-7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	-1254113322	$(12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*5+6)^*7/(8-9)$
-939524832	$-1^*(23^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	-1273939389	$((1+2)^*-34)^{\wedge}5-6)/78^*9$
-951058432	$1^*(-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(5+6)-7)/8^{\wedge}-9$	-1291315301	$123-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)^*(7^*8)^{\wedge}9$
-957886641	$-123/4^{\wedge}(-5^*6)^{\wedge}(7+8-9)$	-1291315401	$1^*23-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)^*(7^*8)^{\wedge}9$
-961019904	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5)/6-7)^*8^{\wedge}9$	-1291315447	$-1^*23-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)^*(7^*8)^{\wedge}9$
-976096825	$(1-(2+34)^{\wedge}5)^*((-6/7+8)+9)$	-1291315547	$-123-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)^*(7^*8)^{\wedge}9$
-976224256	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*5+6)^*-7^*8^{\wedge}9$	-1301132106	$(-12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*5+6^*7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-988663304	$-1/2^*((3+4)^{\wedge}(5+6)+(-7-8)^*9)$	-1305169162	$1^*2^*(3-4/5^*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9))$
-988663439	$-1/2^*((3+4)^{\wedge}(5+6)-(-7-8)^*9)$	-1305169174	$1^*2^*(3-4/5^*((6+7)^{\wedge}8+9))$
-992187500	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(5+6+7-8)^{\wedge}9$	-1313832960	$-12^{\wedge}(3^*4-5)^*6^*(7-8/9)$
-996224113	$(-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}(4^*5)+6))^*7^{\wedge}(8-9)$	-1338352479	$(-1+2^*(34-5)^{\wedge}6+7)/-8^*9$
-1006632864	$(1/2-3^*4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)^*-8^{\wedge}9$	-1338352497	$(-1-2^*(34-5)^{\wedge}6+7)/8)^*9$
-1006633056	$(1/2-3^*-4^{\wedge}(-5-6)+7)^*-8^{\wedge}9$	-1342176852	$((1-2)+3)^*(4+5^*(6^*7-8^{\wedge}9))$
-1007812500	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(5+6+7-8)^{\wedge}9$	-1342176868	$((-1+2)-3)^*(4-5^*(6^*7-8^{\wedge}9))$
-1018885952	$(-1-2^*(3/4)^{\wedge}(5+6))^*7^*8^{\wedge}9$	-1342177692	$((1-2)+3)^*(4-5^*(6^*7+8^{\wedge}9))$
-1020264448	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3-4))^*(5-6))^*7^*-8^{\wedge}9$	-1342177708	$((1-2)+3)^*(4-5^*(6^*7+8^{\wedge}9))$
-1029177344	$((-1+2^{\wedge}(-3-4)+5)/6+7)/-8^{\wedge}-9$	-1357129728	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)^*(5^*6+7/8^*9)$
-1040476679	$1-(2+3)^*4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	-1358952156	$(12^*3^*(-4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7)+8)^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1358952300	$(12^3 * (-4^{(5+6)+7}) - 8)^9$	-1744831136	$(1 + (-2 - 3^4 \wedge (-5-6))^7) / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1358956692	$(12^3 * (-3^4 \wedge (5+6)+7) + 8)^9$	-1751048192	$((1-2)+3) * ((4^5)^{\wedge 6} - 7^8 \wedge 9)$
-1358956836	$(-12^3 * (4^{\wedge (5+6)+7}) - 8)^9$	-1757623778	$(1^2 * ((3+4)^{\wedge (5+6)+7}) * 8) / -9$
-1359551191	$12 - 3^4 * (4+5^6+7)^{\wedge 8} / 9$	-1776287744	$((-1-2^{\wedge (-3-4)} * 5)^6 - 7)^8 \wedge 9$
-1359551199	$(12+3^4 * (4-5^6+7)^{\wedge 8}) / 9$	-1776430584	$-12^2 * ((3+4^5)^{\wedge 6} + 7) / (8-9)$
-1359551215	$-12 - 3^4 * (4+5^6+7)^{\wedge 8} / 9$	-1784469942	$(-1-2)^2 * ((34-5)^{\wedge 6} + 7) / (8-9)$
-1360488141	$(1 + ((2^3 - 3)^{\wedge (4+5)+6}) * (7+8))^9$	-1797062656	$((1+2^{\wedge (-3)} - 4)^5 * 6 + 7) / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1360488159	$(-1 + ((2^3 - 3)^{\wedge (4+5)+6}) * (7+8))^9$	-1799487488	$((1/2^3)^{\wedge (4+5)/6+7}) / -8^{\wedge -9}$
-1360489761	$(1 + ((-2^3)^{\wedge (4+5)-6}) * (7+8))^9$	-1811938320	$1^2 * (-3^4 \wedge (5+6)+7)^8 * 9$
-1360489779	$(-1 + ((2^3)^{\wedge (4+5)+6}) * (-7-8))^9$	-1811940336	$1^2 * (3^4 \wedge (5+6)+7)^8 * 9$
-1365333184	$(1+23)^2 * ((4^5)^{\wedge 6} - 7)^8 / 9$	-1812734938	$(-1+23 - 4^5 - 5^6 + (6+7)^{\wedge 8}) / -9$
-1394530536	$(1 - (2+3)^{\wedge (4+5)})^6 * 7^8 (8+9)$	-1812987904	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge (-3-4)} * 5)^6 * (6+7)^8 \wedge 9$
-1394531964	$(1 + (2+3)^{\wedge (4+5)})^6 * 7^8 (-8-9)$	-1822499990	$(1/2 - 3)^2 * (-4 + (5^6)^{\wedge (7+8-9)})$
-1407999846	$(1 + 23)^2 * ((4^5)^{\wedge 6} + 7) / (8-9)$	-1822500010	$(-1/2+3)^2 * (-4 - (5^6)^{\wedge (7+8-9)})$
-1407999993	$(1 - 23)^2 * (4^5)^{\wedge 6} - 7^8 (8-9)$	-1822943232	$-12^{\wedge (3+4)} * (5^6 / 7 + 8 + 9)$
-1409285920	$(1/2^2 * (-3+4^{\wedge (-5-6)}))^7 * 8^{\wedge 9}$	-1831093088	$(123^{\wedge 4} - 5)^2 * ((6-7)^{\wedge 8} - 9)$
-1409286032	$1/2^2 * (-3+4^{\wedge (-5-6)})^7 * 8^{\wedge 9}$	-1831093168	$(123^{\wedge 4} + 5)^2 * ((6-7)^{\wedge 8} - 9)$
-1409286096	$1/2^2 * (-3^4 * (-4^{\wedge (-5-6)} + 7))^8 \wedge 9$	-1840134665	$((-1-2)^3 * 34)^{\wedge 5} / 6 + 7^8 (-8+9)$
-1409286192	$1/2^2 * (-3^4 * (4^{\wedge (-5-6)} + 7))^8 \wedge 9$	-1846233834	$(1 + ((2 - 3^4)^{\wedge 5} - 6) / (7+8))^9$
-1409286256	$1/2^2 * (-3 - 4^{\wedge (-5-6)})^7 * 8^{\wedge 9}$	-1846233852	$(-1 + ((2 - 3^4)^{\wedge 5} - 6) / (7+8))^9$
-1409286368	$(1/2^2 * (-3 - 4^{\wedge (-5-6)})^7 * 8^{\wedge 9})$	-1879047519	$1 + (2 - 3^4 \wedge (-5-6))^7 / -8^{\wedge -9}$
-1427528745	$1 + (2+3 / -4^5)^2 * ((6+7)^{\wedge 8} - 9)$	-1879047520	$(1^2 - 3 / 4^{\wedge (5+6)})^2 * -7 / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1427528747	$-1 + (2+3 / -4^5)^2 * ((6+7)^{\wedge 8} - 9)$	-1879047521	$-1 + (2 - 3^4 \wedge (-5-6))^2 * -8^{\wedge 9}$
-1433271975	$(-12^{\wedge (3+4)} * 5 + 6^7)^8 * 9$	-1879047968	$(-1 + 2 - (3 - 4^{\wedge (-5-6)}))^2 * 7 / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1433271993	$(-12^{\wedge (3+4)} * 5 + 6^7)^8 * 9$	-1879048000	$1^2 * (-3^4 \wedge (-5-6) + 7)^2 * -8^{\wedge 9}$
-1433272647	$(-12^{\wedge (3+4)} * 5 - 6^7)^8 * 9$	-1879048128	$(1 - 2 + 3)^2 * (4^{\wedge (-5-6)} - 7)^8 \wedge 9$
-1433272665	$(-12^{\wedge (3+4)} * 5 - 6^7)^8 * 9$	-1879048256	$((-1+2) - 3)^2 * (4^{\wedge (-5-6)} + 7)^8 \wedge 9$
-1438892995	$(1 + 2^2 * ((3+4)^{\wedge 6} - 7)) / (-8-9)$	-1879048384	$1^2 * (3^4 \wedge (-5-6) + 7)^2 * -8^{\wedge 9}$
-1457999976	$1^2 * (-3^4 + (5^6)^{\wedge (7+8-9)})$	-1879048416	$(-1 + 2 - (3 + 4^{\wedge (-5-6)}))^2 * 7 / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1457999992	$((1 - 2 + 3)^2 * (4 - (5^6)^{\wedge (7+8-9)}))$	-1879048863	$1 + (-2 - 3^4 \wedge (-5-6))^2 * 7 / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1458000008	$((-1 + 2) - 3)^2 * (4 + (5^6)^{\wedge (7+8-9)})$	-1879048864	$1^2 * (-2 - 3 / 4^{\wedge (5+6)})^2 * 7 / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1458000024	$1^2 * (-3^4 - (5^6)^{\wedge (7+8-9)})$	-1879048865	$-1 + (-2 - 3^4 \wedge (-5-6))^2 * 7^8 \wedge 9$
-1467553625	$1 + (2 / (3+4) - 5)^2 * 6^7 \wedge 8^9$	-1898666459	$(1 - 2) / 3^2 * (4^5)^{\wedge 6} - 7^8 \wedge 9$
-1467553627	$-1 + (2 / (3+4) - 5)^2 * 6^7 \wedge 8^9$	-1902942375	$(-1 + (2^3 * 34)^{\wedge (5+6-7)})^2 * -89$
-1468315313	$1 + (-2 - (3-4) / 5)^2 * ((6+7)^{\wedge 8} + 9)$	-1902942463	$1 + (2^3 * 34)^{\wedge (5+6-7)} * -89$
-1468315315	$-1 + (-2 - (3-4) / 5)^2 * ((6+7)^{\wedge 8} + 9)$	-1902942465	$-1 - (2^3 * 34)^{\wedge (5+6-7)} * 89$
-1509946911	$(1 + (-2 - 3)^2 * (4^{\wedge (5+6)} - 7)^8)^9$	-1902942553	$(-1 - (2^3 * 34)^{\wedge (5+6-7)})^2 * 89$
-1509946929	$(1 - (-2 - 3)^2 * (4^{\wedge (5+6)} - 7)^8)^9$	-1904214016	$1^2 * (-3^4 \wedge (5+6) - 7)^8 \wedge 9$
-1509951951	$(1 - (-2 - 3)^2 * (-4^{\wedge (5+6)} - 7)^8)^9$	-1908287766	$(-1 + 2 - 34^5)^2 * 6^7 / (-8+9)$
-1509951969	$(1 + (-2 - 3)^2 * (-4^{\wedge (5+6)} - 7)^8)^9$	-1908287815	$(1 - 2 - 34^5 * 6)^2 * 7^{\wedge (-8+9)}$
-1539459000	$(-1 + (2^3 * 34)^{\wedge (5+6-7)})^8 * -9$	-1908287934	$(-1 - 2 - 34^5)^2 * 6^7 * (-8+9)$
-1539459063	$(1 + (2^3 * 34)^{\wedge (5+6-7)})^8 * -9$	-1908874335	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge 3} * 34 + 5^6)^2 * (6^7 - 8) / 9$
-1539459081	$(-1 - (2^3 * 34)^{\wedge (5+6-7)})^8 * 9$	-1921480704	$(12^3)^{\wedge 4} * (-5 + 6^7 * (-8-9))$
-1539459144	$(-1 - (2^3 * 34)^{\wedge (5+6-7)})^8 * 9$	-1923730614	$(12^{\wedge (3+4)} * -5 - 6^7 \wedge 8)^9$
-1542717440	$((-1/2 - (3 - 4^{\wedge (-5)}))^6 + 7)^8 \wedge 9$	-1936925298	$((-1-2)^{\wedge (-3-4)} + 5)^2 * (6 - (7+8))^{\wedge 9}$
-1544290304	$((-1/2 - (3 + 4^{\wedge (-5)}))^6 + 7)^8 \wedge 9$	-1937279592	$((1+2)^{\wedge (-3-4)} * 5)^2 * (6 - (7+8))^{\wedge 9}$
-1553090848	$(-12 + (3 + 4^{\wedge (-5-6)}) / 7)^8 \wedge -9$	-1957753740	$12 - 3^4 / 5^2 * ((6+7)^{\wedge 8} + 9)$
-1556495109	$(1 + 2^{\wedge (3+4)} + 5^6 * -7^8)^9$	-1957753764	$-12 + 3^4 * 5^2 * ((6+7)^{\wedge 8} + 9)$
-1556497431	$(-1 - 2^{\wedge (3+4)} - 5^6 * 7^8)^9$	-1980149166	$1^2 * -3^{\wedge (4+5+6)} * (78-9)$
-1579049408	$-12^2 * ((3+4^5)^{\wedge 6} - 7)^8 / 9$	-2007048192	$((-1+2) - 3)^2 * ((4^5)^6 - 7^8 - 8^{\wedge 9})$
-1586195504	$(1+2)^2 * ((34-5)^{\wedge 6} - 7)^8 / 9$	-2012741632	$(-12 - 3 + 4^{\wedge (-5-6+7)}) / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1600692504	$12^2 * (3^{\wedge (4+5)} * 6^7 - 8^{\wedge 9})$	-2013233152	$(-12 - 3 + 4^{\wedge (-5 - (-6+7))}) / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1620532968	$-12^2 * (3^{\wedge (4+5)} * 6^7 + 8^{\wedge 9})$	-2013265248	$(-1 - (2 - 3^4 \wedge (-5-6))^7) / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1627604181	$1 / (2^3)^2 * (-4 - 5^{\wedge (6+7)})^8 * 9$	-2013265696	$(-12 - 3 + 4^{\wedge (-5-6)} * 7) / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1632580191	$(1+2)^{\wedge ((-3+4)+5)} * (-6^{\wedge 7} * 8+9)$	-2013266144	$(-12 - 3 - 4^{\wedge (-5-6)} * 7) / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1632593313	$(1+2)^{\wedge ((-3+4)+5)} * (-6^{\wedge 7} * 8-9)$	-2013266592	$(-1 - (2 + 3^4 \wedge (-5-6))^7) / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1634013884	$(-12 + (((-3-4)^5)^{\wedge 6} - 7)^8)^9$	-2013298688	$(-12 - 3 - 4^{\wedge (-5 - (-6+7))}) / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1668134624	$(-12 - (3 + 4^{\wedge (-5-6)}) / 7)^8 \wedge -9$	-2013790208	$(-12 - 3 - 4^{\wedge (-5-6+7)}) / 8^{\wedge -9}$
-1670419999	$1 - 2^2 * (34^5)^{\wedge ((-6-7+8)+9)}$	-2039326763	$1/2^2 * (34 - 5^2 * ((6+7)^{\wedge 8} - 9))$
-1670420000	$1^2 * -2^2 * (34^5)^{\wedge ((-6-7+8)+9)}$	-2039326842	$-1/2^2 * (34 + 5^2 * ((6+7)^{\wedge 8} + 9))$
-1672151040	$12^{\wedge (3+4)} * 5^2 * (-6-78) / 9$	-2046820340	$12 + (3/4 * (5+6) + 7) / -8^{\wedge -9}$
-1676673024	$(-1 + 2^{\wedge (-3-4)} * 5)^2 * (6+7)^8 \wedge 9$	-2046820350	$1^2 * 2 + (3/4 * (5+6) + 7)^2 * -8^{\wedge 9}$
-1713373184	$((-1 + 2^{\wedge (-3-4)} * 5)^6 - 7)^8 \wedge 9$	-2046820354	$1^2 * -2 + (3/4 * (5+6) + 7)^2 * -8^{\wedge 9}$
-1727999712	$((1 + 2 - 3^2 * ((4^5)^{\wedge 6} - 7))^8)^9$	-2046820364	$-12 + (3/4 * (5+6) + 7) / -8^{\wedge -9}$
-1727999748	$((1 - 2 - 3^2 * ((4^5)^{\wedge 6} - 7))^8)^9$	-2056087478	$-1^2 * (3^{\wedge (4^5 - (-6+7))}) - 8^{\wedge 9}$
-1728000252	$((-1 + 2 - 3^2 * ((4^5)^{\wedge 6} + 7))^8)^9$	-2092070652	$(-1 + ((2 - 3^{\wedge (4^5)} - 6) / (7+8)))^9$
-1728000288	$((-1 - 2 - 3^2 * ((4^5)^{\wedge 6} + 7))^8)^9$	-2095875000	$(1 + 2^{\wedge (-3-4)} / (5^6)^{\wedge ((-7-8)+9)})$
-1730160891	$(-1 + 2 - (3+4)^{\wedge (5+6)} * 7) / 8+9$	-2113926768	$(-1 - (2 - 3 + 4^{\wedge (5+6)})^7)^8 * 9$
-1730160909	$(-1 + 2 - (3+4)^{\wedge (5+6)} * 7) / 8-9$	-2113927704	$(-1 + 2)^2 * (-3 + 4^{\wedge (5+6)})^7 * -8^9$
-1743392167	$-1/2^2 * (3^{\wedge (4^5)} + 67) / (8-9)$	-2113929543	$(1 - (2/3 + 4^{\wedge (5+6)})^7)^8 * 9$
-1744829792	$(1 + (2 - 3^4 \wedge (-5-6))^2 * -7) / 8^{\wedge -9}$	-2113929561	$(-1 + (2/3 + 4^{\wedge (5+6)})^2 * -7^8)^9$
-1744831084	$-1^2 * ((2+3)^{\wedge 4} - (5 - (6+7))^8 \wedge 9)$	-2113930728	$(-1 + 2)^2 * (-3 - 4^{\wedge (5+6)})^7 * 8^9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2113931664	$(-1 - (-2 - 3 - 4^{(5+6)}) * 7) * 8^* - 9$		
-2147483617	$-1 - (23 - 4^{(-5-6)} - 7) * 8^9$		

Supplement 4

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-18596	$(9*(87*-6+5)+4)*(3+2-1)$	-68259	$-9+(-8-7-6)*((54+3)^2+1)$
-19067	$(-9-8-7)-(6*(5^4+3))^2+1$	-68274	$(-9+8*7*(6-(5*(4+3))^2))-1$
-19069	$(-9-8-7)-(6*(5^4+3))^2-1$	-68656	$(-98-7*-6)*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$
-21500	$9*((8*7*6+5)*(-4-3)-2)+1$	-70868	$(9-8)*7-(6+5+4)^3*21$
-23924	$(9-8)*76+(5^4)^3*(-2-1)$	-71417	$(9+8)*(7*6*5*4*(-3-2)-1)$
-24155	$9*-8*(7+(-654-3)/-2)+1$	-72272	$-9*8*((76*5/(4*3))^2+1)$
-28851	$(-9-87*6)*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-72366	$(9-8)*7*6*(5+(-4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-32282	$(9+8)*7-((-6-54)^3)^2-1$	-74003	$9*-8*(-7/6+5+4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1$
-34149	$9-(8+7*((6+5)^4-3))/(2+1)$	-74200	$(-98-7*6)*((5^4+3)^2+1)$
-37716	$(-9+8)*-7*6*(5-43*21)$	-74407	$9-8*(7+65*((4*3)^2-1))$
-37718	$-9*((-8-7)*-6+5+4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1$	-74425	$-9-8*(7+65*((4*3)^2-1))$
-37978	$(9+8)*(7*(-6*54+3+2)-1)$	-74667	$9-8*7/6*((5^4)^3+2)-1$
-40280	$(-9+8)*76*((5^4+3)^2+1)$	-74685	$-9-8*7/6*((5^4)^3+2)-1$
-41756	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4-3)/-2+1$	-74700	$(9*8*7-6)*(-5-((4*3)^2+1))$
-42217	$(9*-87+6)*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-75171	$((-9/87*6^{\wedge}-5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-2)-1$
-42234	$9*(87*6*(-5-4)+3)+21$	-75340	$9*(8+7*65)-43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-42448	$-98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+432+1)$	-75391	$9+8*(-7-6)*5*((4*3)^2+1)$
-43118	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(-5*(4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-75409	$-9+8*(-7-6)*5*((4*3)^2+1)$
-43150	$(-98-765)*((4+3)^2+1)$	-75484	$-9*(8-7*65)-43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-43340	$(-9+8+7*(6-5^4))*(3^2+1)$	-75500	$(-98*7*(6+5)-4)*(3^2+1)$
-44812	$((9-(8+7))^{\wedge}6+5-43^2)*-1$	-76362	$(9*8*-7-6*5)*((4*3)^2-1)$
-45124	$((-9*8-7)+(-6-5)*(4^{\wedge}(3^2)-1))$	-76705	$(-9+8*(-7-6)*5)*((4*3)^2+1)$
-45212	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6-(5-43)^2)*-1$	-76932	$9*((-8+(7+6)*(-5^4-32))+1)$
-45451	$9*((8*7*6*5+4)*-3+2)-1$	-76957	$(9*8*7+6)*5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-45481	$((9+8)+7)*((-6-5^4)*3-2)-1$	-77205	$-9+(8*7+6*(-5^4+3))*21$
-45650	$(-9+87)*6-(5*43)^2-1$	-77253	$-98*(7-6*5)-43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-46040	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6-5^4+3^2)*-1$	-77408	$((9+8)*7*6-5^4(4+3))+2+1$
-46346	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6-5*(4^3-2))*-1$	-79341	$(-9-8/7+6*(-5^4-3))*21$
-46934	$9*((-87*(6+54)+3)+2)+1$	-79365	$((98+7)+6)*-5*((4*3)^2-1)$
-46936	$9*((-87*(6+54)+3)+2)-1$	-79732	$9*(-8+7+6)*-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-47638	$9*((-8*(7+654)-3)-2)-1$	-79737	$(-9-8*7+6*(-5^4+3))*21$
-48474	$9*((-8*7-(6*5+43)^2)-1)$	-79822	$9*((8-7)+6)*-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-48480	$((9*8*7+6)-5)*-4*(3+21)$	-79973	$9*(-8/7*(6^5+4-3)+2)+1$
-48533	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6+5^4*3+2)*-1$	-79975	$9*(-8/7*(6^5+4-3)+2)-1$
-48754	$9+(-8*7*6-5)*((4*3)^2-1)$	-80032	$9*8/7*((-6^5-4+3^{\wedge}-2)-1)$
-49324	$(-9+8)*76*((5^4+3)+21)$	-80295	$9-(8*7+6*(5^4+3))*21$
-49781	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6+5^4(4+3-2))*-1$	-80313	$-9-(8*7+6*(5^4+3))*21$
-50266	$(9-8*7+6)*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$	-80383	$(9/8*(7+6)+5)*-4^{\wedge}(3^2)+1$
-50993	$-9*((8*7-6^5/4)*-3+2)+1$	-80384	$(9/8*(7+6)+5)*-4^{\wedge}(3+2+1)$
-51223	$9+8-7*((6+5)^4-3)/2+1$	-80452	$9*(-8-7-6)*5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-51443	$(9-8)*-7*(6*(5*(4+3))^2-1)$	-80509	$(9*(8*-7-6)-5)*((4*3)^2-1)$
-51590	$9*(-8*7/6)*(5^4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-80560	$-9*(87+6*5)-43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-51799	$(-9-8)*((76*5*-4-3)*-2+1)$	-80584	$9*8-((-76+5)^4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
-52152	$9*8*(-7/6*(5^4-(3+2))-1)$	-80668	$(-9*(8+7)+6)*(5^4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-53008	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7)*-6*(5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-80694	$9*((8+7)+6)*5(432+1)$
-53022	$(9-8)-7*((6^5+4^3)^2+1)$	-80728	$-9*8-((-76+5)^4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
-53918	$-9+(8+7)*6-(5^4*3)^2+1$	-80738	$(9*8+7)*(6-5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-54076	$(-9-8)*(7+6*(5^4+3)^2)+1$	-80787	$(-9*8-7-6*(5^4+3))*21$
-55172	$-9*8+76*-5*((4*3)^2+1)$	-80982	$9*(-87/6*(5^4-3)+21)$
-55543	$(-9*8-7)-6*(5/43^{\wedge}-2-1)$	-81007	$(-9+8)*7+(6*5)^4/(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-55913	$(-9-8)*(-7+6*5)*((4*3)^2-1)$	-81206	$(-9-8)*-7*6-5/4^{\wedge}(-3^2-1)$
-57018	$(9-87)*(6+5*((4*3)^2+1))$	-81962	$(-9+8)*7*6-5/4^{\wedge}(-3^2-1)$
-57303	$9*(-8*(76+5*(4*3)^2)+1)$	-82040	$(98/-7-6)*((5+4^{\wedge}(3^2))+1)$
-57442	$98*(-7^{\wedge}(-6+5)*4^{\wedge}(3^2)-1)$	-82057	$(9*8*7+6)*-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-57463	$(-9+8)*7*((6^5+432)+1)$	-82410	$(9*-8-7*6/5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
-59602	$(-9-8)*((-76-5^4)*(-3-2)+1)$	-82650	$(-9*8-7*6)*5*((4*3)^2+1)$
-62829	$9*((8+(76+5)*43)*-2+1)$	-82976	$9+8*(-7-6^5*4/3+2)-1$
-64557	$9*((-8*(7+6)*5+4^{\wedge}3)+2)+1$	-83435	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-43^2)*-1$
-65190	$(9*-8+7*6/5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$	-83476	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-43-2)*-1$
-65272	$((9+8)+7)*(6+5)-4^{\wedge}(3^2-1)$	-83480	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-43+2)*-1$
-65387	$(9*8+7*(6+5)-4^{\wedge}(3^2-1))$	-83587	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4^{\wedge}3+2)*-1$
-65698	$9*(-8-7)*6/5-4^{\wedge}(3^2-1)$	-83649	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4*32)*-1$
-65746	$(-9+8)*(7*6*5+4^{\wedge}(3^2-1))$	-83977	$-9-(8^{\wedge}(-7+6)+5)*4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
-65849	$(98*-7*(-6+54)+3)*2+1$	-84012	$9+((-8-7)-6)*((5^4)^3/2+1)$
-66133	$((9+8)*(-7-6^5)+43)/2+1$	-84130	$(9/8-7)*((6+5)^4-321)$
-66290	$(-98-7)*(6+5^4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-84627	$9*((-87*6*(5+4)-3)*2-1)$
-66634	$9/(-8+7)-65*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-84952	$98+7*-6^5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-66867	$((9+8)+76)*(-5/(4*3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-85148	$-98+7*-6^5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-67368	$9*8*-7*((-65-4/3)*-2+1)$	-85370	$((9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+43^2)*-1$
-67481	$(9+8)*7-(65*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$	-86989	$(-9-8)*7*(6+5*((4*3)^2+1))$
-67502	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)+6/5^{\wedge}-4)*(3-21)$	-87046	$(-9-8*7-6)*((5*(4+3))^2+1)$
-68160	$((9*8-7)+6)*5*4^{\wedge}3*(-2-1)$	-87170	$((9-8)+7)^{\wedge}6-5^4/(-3+2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-88078	$(9^{*}(-8-7)-6)^{*}(5^{*}4-3^{*}(-2+1))$	-123814	$-9^{*}8+((-7-6)^{*}5+4)/3+21$
-88825	$(9+8)^{*}(7+654^{*}(-3^{*}2+1))$	-123856	$-9^{*}8+((-7-6)^{*}5+4)/3-21$
-89421	$-9^{*}((-87-(6+5)^{*}4/3)^{*}2+1)$	-124933	$(9+8)^{*}(7-6^{*}((5^{*}(4+3))^{*}2+1))$
-89872	$((-9-8)-7)^{*}6^{*}(5^{*}4+3^{*}2-1)$	-124944	$((9-8)+7)^{*}(6-5^{*}(4^{*}3/2)+1)$
-90128	$((-9-8)-7)^{*}6^{*}(5^{*}4-(3^{*}2-1))$	-124960	$((9-8)+7)^{*}((6-5^{*}(4^{*}3/2))-1)$
-90516	$(9-87^{*}65^{*}4)^{*}((-3-2)+1)$	-125171	$(-9-8)^{*}(7+6^{*}((5^{*}(4+3))^{*}2+1))$
-90669	$9+(8^{*}7+6/(-5-4)^{*}3)^{*}21$	-125409	$(9+8)^{*}(7^{*}(-6^{*}5-4^{*}(3+2))+1)$
-90713	$(-9-8)^{*}(7+(6^{*}5+43)^{*}2)-1$	-126150	$(98+76)^{*}5^{*}((4^{*}3)^{*}2+1)$
-90831	$(9+(87^{*}6)^{*}(-5+4)^{*}3)/(-2-1)$	-126469	$-98^{*}(7^{*}6^{*}(5/4-32))-1$
-91106	$9^{*}((-8-7)^{*}(-6-(-5-4))^{*}3+2)+1$	-126657	$-9^{*}(87^{*}6^{*}(5+4)^{*}3-21)$
-91143	$-9^{*}((8+7)^{*}(-6-(-5-4))^{*}3+2^{*}1)$	-128316	$(-9+876)^{*}(-5-((4^{*}3)^{*}2-1))$
-91833	$((9-8)^{*}7+6^{*}(-5-4)^{*}3)^{*}21$	-129401	$-9+8^{*}(7^{*}6^{*}5-4^{*}(3^{*}2+1))$
-92008	$(-9^{*}(-8+7)+6)^{*}(-5^{*}(4^{*}3/2)+1)$	-129630	$(-9+8)^{*}7^{*}6^{*}5^{*}4321$
-92099	$(9-87^{*}65^{*}4)^{*}(-5-4)^{*}3)^{*}21$	-129924	$9/8^{*}((-7^{*}6+5^{*}432)+1)$
-93187	$9^{*}((8+(7-6^{*}5)^{*}4)/3+2)-1$	-130289	$((9-8+7+6+5)^{*}4-32)^{*}-1$
-93804	$((-9-8)-7)^{*}((6^{*}5+43)/2-1)$	-130315	$((9-8+7+6+5)^{*}4-3^{*}2)^{*}-1$
-94203	$-9^{*}(87^{*}6^{*}5^{*}4+3^{*}2+1)$	-130327	$((9-8+7+6+5)^{*}4+3^{*}2)^{*}-1$
-94801	$-9-8/7^{*}((6^{*}(-5-43))^{*}2-1)$	-130353	$((9-8+7+6+5)^{*}4+32)^{*}-1$
-95562	$9^{*}(-8-((76-(-5-4)^{*}3)^{*}2+1))$	-130559	$9^{*}((-8-7/6)-5)/4^{*}(-3-2)+1$
-95645	$(-9-8/-7)^{*}(6+(5^{*}4+3)^{*}2+1)$	-131726	$98^{*}(-7^{*}(-6+5)-4^{*}3^{*}21)$
-96513	$(9^{*}(-8+7)-6)^{*}(5+4^{*}(3^{*}2+1))$	-132196	$-98^{*}((7/(-65^{*}4+3))^{*}2+1)$
-97174	$(-9+8)^{*}7^{*}6+5^{*}(4^{*}(3^{*}2)-1)$	-132392	$(9/8^{*}(-7^{*}6+5)-43)+2^{*}1-1$
-97780	$-98^{*}((7/(-6-5^{*}43))^{*}2+1)$	-132393	$(9/8^{*}(-7^{*}6+5)-43)-2^{*}1-1$
-99048	$((9+8)+7)^{*}((-6^{*}5-4^{*}(3^{*}2))-1)$	-132394	$-9/8^{*}(7^{*}6-5^{*}(-4-3))+2^{*}1-1$
-99477	$((9^{*}8+7)^{*}(-6-54)+3)^{*}21$	-132404	$9/8^{*}(-7^{*}6-((5^{*}4/3)^{*}2-1))$
-100240	$98^{*}(7^{*}(-6+5)-4^{*}(3+2)+1)$	-132727	$(-9+8)^{*}(76+(54-3)^{*}(2+1))$
-100268	$98^{*}((-7^{*}(-6+5)-4^{*}(3+2))+1)$	-132761	$-9-8^{*}(7^{*}6^{*}5+4^{*}(3^{*}2+1))$
-100470	$(9^{*}8^{*}7-6)^{*}(5-4^{*}3^{*}(-2-1))$	-132796	$((9^{*}(8-7))^{*}6-5)/-4+3^{*}21$
-100774	$((-9+8)^{*}7^{*}6+5^{*}4^{*}3^{*}2+1)$	-132826	$((9/(8-7))^{*}6-5)/-4+32+1$
-101594	$(-9^{*}8-7)^{*}(6-5^{*}4^{*}(3+2-1))$	-132827	$((9^{*}(8-7))^{*}6-5)/-4+32^{*}1$
-103424	$(9/8^{*}7/6+5)/-4^{*}(-3^{*}2-1)$	-132828	$((9/(8-7))^{*}6-5)/-4+32-1$
-104160	$(-9^{*}(8+7/6)+5)^{*}4^{*}3^{*}21$	-132832	$((9^{*}(8-7))^{*}6-5)/-4+3^{*}(2+1)$
-104553	$(9/(-8^{*}7^{*}6+5^{*}43))^{*}(-2+1)$	-132835	$((9/(8-7))^{*}6-5)/-4+3+21$
-104820	$9^{*}8^{*}((7/6+(-5-4)^{*}3^{*}2)+1)$	-132868	$((9^{*}(8-7))^{*}6-5)/-4-3^{*}2^{*}1$
-105576	$(9^{*}8^{*}7+6)^{*}((5^{*}43-2)-1)$	-132869	$((9^{*}(8-7))^{*}6-5)/-4-(3^{*}2+1)$
-105677	$9^{*}((-8^{*}7-6^{*}5)+4)^{*}3/2+1$	-132877	$((9/(8-7))^{*}6-5)/-4+3-21$
-105679	$9^{*}((-8^{*}7-6^{*}5)+4)^{*}3/2-1$	-132883	$((9^{*}(8-7))^{*}6-5)/-4-3-21$
-108153	$9^{*}(8+(-7^{*}6+5)^{*}4+321)$	-132890	$((9^{*}(8-7))^{*}6-5)/-4-32+1$
-108159	$(9^{*}8^{*}(7^{*}6+5)+4)^{*}32+1$	-132892	$((9^{*}(8-7))^{*}6-5)/-4-32-1$
-108161	$(9^{*}8^{*}(7^{*}6+5)+4)^{*}32-1$	-133038	$9/8^{*}((-7^{*}6-5^{*}4-3)+21)$
-109284	$98-7^{*}((6-(-5-4))^{*}3^{*}2+1)$	-133287	$((9/8+76)-5)^{*}(-43^{*}2+1)$
-109381	$9^{*}8-7^{*}((6-(-5-4))^{*}3^{*}2+1)$	-133301	$(-9+8)^{*}7^{*}((6^{*}(5^{*}4+3))^{*}2-1)$
-109496	$(9-8)^{*}7+(65+4)^{*}3/(-2-1)$	-133663	$9-8/7^{*}((6^{*}(-54-3))^{*}2-1)$
-109589	$(9^{*}8^{*}(-765+4)-3)^{*}2+1$	-133681	$-9-8/7^{*}((6^{*}(-54-3))^{*}2-1)$
-109591	$(9^{*}8^{*}(-765+4)-3)^{*}2-1$	-133821	$-9^{*}(8^{*}7^{*}(6-543/2)+1)$
-110345	$(9^{*}(-8-76)-5)^{*}((4^{*}3)^{*}2+1)$	-134298	$9/8^{*}((-7^{*}6-54^{*}32)+1)$
-111215	$(-9/8-7)^{*}((-6^{*}5^{*}4+3)^{*}2-1)$	-134563	$(-9^{*}8^{*}(7+6)-5)^{*}((4^{*}3)^{*}2-1)$
-111688	$(9/(-8^{*}(7^{*}6+5^{*}4)^{*}3))^{*}(-2+1)$	-134827	$(9+8)^{*}(7+6^{*}5/((4+3)^{*}2-1))$
-112313	$(9-8)^{*}7-65/(4^{*}3)^{*}(-2-1)$	-135564	$(9+87^{*}(-6-5))^{*}((4^{*}3)^{*}2-1)$
-112689	$-9-8/7^{*}((6-5^{*}4^{*}3)^{*}2-1)$	-136445	$(-9^{*}8^{*}(7+6)-5)^{*}((4^{*}3)^{*}2+1)$
-113733	$-9/8^{*}(7+6^{*}5^{*}(4+3^{*}2)+1)$	-136759	$-98^{*}(7^{*}6^{*}(-5/4-32))-1$
-115143	$(-9+8)^{*}7^{*}(65+4^{*}(3^{*}2+1))$	-136875	$(-9-8^{*}(-7+6))/((5^{*}4/(3+21))$
-115271	$9/8^{*}(-7^{*}((6+5)^{*}4-3)+2)+1$	-136895	$(-9+8/7)^{*}((-6-5)^{*}4^{*}3)^{*}2-1$
-115294	$9/8^{*}(-7^{*}(6+5)^{*}4+3)+2^{*}1-1$	-137057	$((9^{*}(8-7))^{*}6-5^{*}(4+3)^{*}2)^{*}-1$
-115295	$9/8^{*}(-7^{*}(6+5)^{*}4+3)-2^{*}1-1$	-137124	$(-9+87)^{*}(6^{*}5-(4^{*}3)^{*}2+1)$
-115753	$((-9+8)^{*}7^{*}6+5^{*}4^{*}3+21)$	-138138	$(9-(8+7)^{*}65)^{*}((4^{*}3)^{*}2-1)$
-116836	$98-7^{*}6+5^{*}((4^{*}3)^{*}2-1)$	-138436	$-98^{*}((7/((65^{*}4+3))^{*}2+1)$
-116862	$9^{*}8-7^{*}6+5^{*}((4^{*}3)^{*}2-1)$	-138582	$9^{*}(87^{*}6^{*}(-5+4^{*}3)/2+1)$
-118462	$(-98-7^{*}6-5^{*}((4^{*}3)^{*}2-1))$	-139260	$9/8^{*}((-7-6)^{*}5-4)/3-21$
-118524	$(-98+7/6)^{*}((5^{*}(4+3))^{*}2-1)$	-140327	$-9^{*}(8^{*}((7+6^{*}5)/4+3)+2)+1$
-118769	$-987^{*}(6^{*}5^{*}4+3^{*}2+1)$	-140329	$-9^{*}(8^{*}((7+6^{*}5)/4+3)+2)-1$
-120123	$9^{*}(8-7^{*}6^{*}(-5^{*}4^{*}3+2)+1)$	-140712	$(-9+(-8-7)^{*}65)^{*}((4^{*}3)^{*}2-1)$
-120149	$-98^{*}(7-6+(5^{*}(-4-3))^{*}2)-1$	-140828	$(9-8)^{*}76^{*}((5+43^{*}2)-1)$
-120455	$9^{*}8^{*}7^{*}(6-5^{*}(4+3)^{*}2)+1$	-141291	$-9^{*}(87+6^{*}((54-3)^{*}2+1))$
-120457	$9^{*}8^{*}7^{*}(6-5^{*}(4+3)^{*}2)-1$	-141337	$(-9+8)^{*}7^{*}((-6-5^{*}4)^{*}32-1)$
-120460	$(-9+8)^{*}76^{*}5^{*}(4-321)$	-141530	$(-9/(87^{*}(6+5)^{*}4+3))^{*}(-2+1)$
-121797	$-9^{*}(8-7^{*}6^{*}(5^{*}4^{*}3+2)+1)$	-142293	$((9^{*}8-76/5^{*}4)-3)^{*}(2+1)$
-121889	$9^{*}8-7^{*}((-6-5)^{*}4^{*}3)^{*}2-1$	-142440	$((9+8+76/-5^{*}4)+3)^{*}(2+1)$
-122694	$(-9+87)^{*}(-6-5)^{*}((4^{*}3)^{*}2-1)$	-142941	$(-987+6/5)^{*}((4^{*}3)^{*}2+1)$
-122964	$9-87+6^{*}(-5^{*}4^{*}(3^{*}2)-1)$	-143143	$(98-7)^{*}(-6-5)^{*}((4^{*}3)^{*}2-1)$
-123469	$(-9+8/-7)^{*}(6+(5^{*}4+3)^{*}2+1)$	-143283	$(-9+8)^{*}7^{*}(6+5^{*}(-4^{*}(3^{*}2)+1))$
-123670	$(9^{*}8-((7+6)^{*}5-4)/3)+21$	-143437	$(-9+8)^{*}7^{*}(6+5^{*}(4^{*}(3^{*}2)+1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-145408	$(9/8^* - 7 - (6-5))^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$	-184806	$-9^*((8+7)^*(-6^*5-4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-145999	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))/(5^*4)^{\wedge}-3^*2+1$	-185465	$-98^*((7/6-5^{\wedge}4)^*-3+21)$
-146291	$(9+8)^*7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4^*(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-187143	$((9-8)^*7^*6-5^{\wedge}4)^*321$
-147877	$(9-8)^*(-7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^*(3+2)-1)$	-187441	$9+(-8/7-6)^*((54^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-148511	$(-9-8/7)^*((6+5)^{\wedge}4+3)+21$	-187459	$-9+(8/-7-6)^*((54^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-148553	$(-9-8/7)^*((6+5)^{\wedge}4+3)-21$	-187872	$9^*8^*((7-6^{\wedge}5)+4)/3-21$
-148816	$(-9-8/7)^*((6+5)^{\wedge}4+32-1)$	-188211	$(9^*(8+7)-6)^*((-5-4)^{\wedge}3^*2-1)$
-149056	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6+(5/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}2)^*-1$	-188532	$9^*(-8^*7-6^*((5-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-150579	$-9^*(87+6^*5)^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-190519	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)/(-6-5)+4^*(32+1)$
-151000	$9^*8-7^*6^{\wedge}5)^*((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-192021	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7)^*(6^*-5^*4)^{\wedge}3-21$
-151589	$(9-8)^*(-7-6^*5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$	-192590	$9^*((8+7)+6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1$
-151658	$(9-87)^*(6^{\wedge}5/4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-192592	$9^*((8+7)+6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$
-152381	$((-98/7-6)^{\wedge}5-4+3)/21$	-193671	$9^*(87-6^*((5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-152383	$((98/-7-6)^{\wedge}5-43)/21$	-194393	$(9-8)^*7-6^{\wedge}5^*(4^*3^*2+1)$
-153603	$(9^*8+7)^*6^{\wedge}5/-4-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-194705	$-9-8^*((-7-6)^*(5+4+3))^{\wedge}2+1$
-153709	$((9-8)/7-6)^*((54^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-194949	$9^*((-8-7)^*(6^*(5+4/3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
-154549	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)-6)/(54^*3)^{\wedge}-2-1$	-195268	$((9^*(8-7)^{\wedge}6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$
-154629	$(9^*(8+7)^*6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2+1$	-195889	$-9-8/7^*((6^*(5+4/3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
-154631	$(9^*(8+7)^*6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2-1$	-197600	$(-9+8)^*76^*((54-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-156042	$9^*((87-((-6-5)^*4^*3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-199440	$9^*8^*((-7-6)^*(5^*43-2)-1)$
-157824	$9^*(876^*5+4)^*((-3-2)+1)$	-200158	$(-9-8)^*7^*((-6-5)^*4+3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-158134	$(-9-8)^*(7+65^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1))$	-200411	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)^*6-5^{\wedge}4)^*321$
-158644	$(-9-8)^*(7/6^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3-2)+1)$	-200628	$(-9^{\wedge}(-8-7)+6-5^{\wedge}4^*321)$
-159124	$(9^*((8-(7+6)^{\wedge}5)-4)-3)/21$	-200640	$(-9^{\wedge}(-8-7)-6-5^{\wedge}4^*321)$
-159369	$(-98^*7^*(6+5)-43)^*21$	-200745	$9^*(8^*(7-65^*43)-2+1)$
-159570	$9^*(-8-7)^*6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^*(-2-1))$	-200763	$9^*((8^*(7-65^*43)-2)-1)$
-159757	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	-200839	$(-9^{\wedge}(-8+7)^*6-5^{\wedge}4)^*321$
-159987	$(9-8)^*7+6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	-200977	$9-8^*((7/-6+54)^*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-160106	$(9+8)^*(7-65^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$	-200995	$-9-8^*((7/-6+54)^*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-160379	$(-9^{\wedge}(-8+7)-6)/(54^*3)^{\wedge}-2+1$	-201294	$-9/8^*((76^*5+43)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-160381	$(-9^{\wedge}(-8+7)-6)/(54^*3)^{\wedge}-2-1$	-201613	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6/(-5-4^{\wedge}(-3+2)))-1$
-161207	$((9-8)/-7-6)^*((54^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-201755	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6/(5+4^{\wedge}(-3+2)))+1$
-161792	$(-9-(8/7)^{\wedge}(-6+5))^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$	-201757	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6/(5+4^{\wedge}(-3+2)))-1$
-163660	$98^*(-7+65-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-202493	$(9-8)^*7+(6^*5)^{\wedge}4/(-3-2+1)$
-164285	$9^*(8^*-7^*(6-5/-4^{\wedge}-3)+2)+1$	-202498	$((9^*(8+7^*6))^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)-2)^*-1$
-165995	$9^*87^*(6^*5^*(-4-3)-2)+1$	-202502	$((-9+8)-7-(6^*5)^{\wedge}4)/(3+2-1)$
-165997	$9^*87^*(6^*5^*(-4-3)-2)-1$	-202518	$-9^*(8-(7/(6-54^*3))^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-166420	$((-9-8)+7)^*((65+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-202906	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)^2)/-1$
-167757	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-(5^*4)^{\wedge}3^*21$	-203095	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2))^*-1$
-167867	$(9-8)^*7-(-6-(-5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$	-203371	$(-9-8)^*-7^*(6+5/(-4-3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-167924	$(9-8)^*76-(5^*4)^{\wedge}3^*21$	-203850	$(98^*7^*(6+5)+4)/-3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-168243	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+(5^*-4)^{\wedge}3^*21$	-204155	$(-98-7)^*(6^{\wedge}5/4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-169330	$98^*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-204443	$9^*8^*(7+6)+(5-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-170316	$9^*((8+7)^*(-6-5^{\wedge}4)+3)^*2^*1$	-205275	$(-9/8-7^*6)^*((5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-171640	$(-98+7^*-6)^*((5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-206315	$9^*8^*(-7-6)+(5-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-172200	$(-9^*8-((7+6)/5^{\wedge}-4+3))^*21$	-206673	$9/8^*(7/6^*(-5^*4^*3-2)+1)$
-172601	$(9+8)^*(-76+5)^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-207553	$(9+8)^*(-7^*6-(5^*4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-173217	$(-9/(8+7)-6)^*((54^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-207797	$(-9/((8^{\wedge}7-(65-4)^{\wedge}3)+2))^{\wedge}-1$
-174737	$((-9-8^{\wedge}7)+65)/(4^*3)+21$	-207909	$9^*((8^*76^*(5-43)+2)+1)$
-174779	$((9+8^{\wedge}7)-65)/(4^*-3)-21$	-208503	$-9^*(-8^*(7^*-6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+2)-1)$
-175941	$9^*(-8^*7-6^*(-54-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-208827	$9/8^*((-7-6)^{\wedge}5+43)/2+1$
-176127	$((-9-8)+7)^*-6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1$	-213000	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))/(5^*4)^{\wedge}-3^*(2+1)$
-176719	$(-9-8/7)^*((-6-5)^*4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-213324	$(-98-76)^*((5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
-177042	$(9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)-5^*(4+3))^*(-2-1)$	-214708	$(9+8)^*76+(5^*4^*-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-177252	$(-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)-5^*(4+3))^*(2+1)$	-214902	$-9^*8-7^*6^*5^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-179965	$9^*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6)-5^{\wedge}4)^*32-1$	-214963	$98^*(-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4))^*321$
-180035	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}(-7+6)-5^{\wedge}4)^*32+1$	-214998	$(-9+8)^*-7^*6^*(-5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-180037	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}(-7+6)-5^{\wedge}4)^*32-1$	-215178	$9^*8-7^*-6^*5^*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-180210	$98/7+(-6-5)/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$	-215322	$-9^*8-7^*-6^*5^*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-180238	$-98/7+(-6-5)/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$	-215567	$((9^*8-7^{\wedge}6)-5)^*(4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-180370	$(-9-8)^*((76-(-5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-215779	$(-9-8)^*(-7-6)-(5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-181090	$98^*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-43^{\wedge}2+1)$	-215826	$98+76-(5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-181118	$98^*((-7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-43^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-215947	$-9-8^*-7+6-(5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-181272	$(-9+8)^*-7^*6^*(5-4321)$	-216033	$((-9-8)+7)^*-6-5^{\wedge}4)^*321$
-181286	$98^*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-43^{\wedge}2-1)$	-216053	$9-(8^*7+6)-(5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-182291	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7)^*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)^*21)$	-216174	$(-98-76)-(5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-183013	$9+(-8-7^{\wedge}6)^*(5/(4+3+2)+1)$	-216221	$(-9-8)^*(7+6)-(5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-183031	$-9+(-8-7^{\wedge}6)^*(5/(4+3+2)+1)$	-217087	$((-9-8)+7)^*6+5)^*-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1$
-183036	$(-9-8-7^{\wedge}6)^*(5/(4+3+2)+1)$	-217089	$((-9-8)+7)^*6+5)^*-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1$
-183412	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3/2)/-1$	-217292	$(-9-8)^*76+(5^*4^*-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-184017	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2)/-1$	-219000	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))/(5^*4)^{\wedge}-3^*(2+1)$
-184021	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2)^*-1$	-219022	$((-9+87)^*6)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3)-2)^*-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-219026	$((-9+87)*6)^{-5-(-4-3)+2}*-1$	-258990	$9/(-8-7)*((65+3)^{2+1})$
-219121	$9-8*((7/6+54)^3)^{2+1}$	-259019	$((9-8+7)^{6-5^{4+3-2}})/-1$
-219123	$-9-8*((7/6+54)^3)^{2-1}$	-259639	$((98/7)^{6-5}/(4-32-1))$
-219139	$-9-8*((7/6+54)^3)^{2+1}$	-259840	$((9-8+7)^{6-(5+43)^2})*-1$
-219384	$9*8*((76*5^4+3)^{-2-1})$	-260267	$((9-8+7)^{6-5^{4*3-2}})*-1$
-221013	$9*8*((7-65)/4)^{3-21}$	-260271	$((9-8+7)^{6-5^{4*3+2}})*-1$
-221940	$9/8*((7^6-54^3)^2-1)$	-260300	$((9-8+7)^{6+5-43^2})*-1$
-222216	$((9+8)^{-7^{6+5}+4})/(3*(2+1))$	-260416	$((9-8+7)^{6-54*32})*-1$
-224361	$9*(8*-76*(5+4+32)-1)$	-260700	$((9-8+7)^{6-(5-43)^2})/-1$
-225303	$(9*8*7*6-5^{4+3})*(2+1)$	-260919	$((9-8+7)^{6-(5*(4+3))^2})*-1$
-226413	$9*(8+7*((6-(5*4^3)^2-1)))$	-261058	$((9-8+7)^{6-543*2})*-1$
-226793	$(-9+8)*7*((-6-54)^3)^{2-1}$	-261115	$((9-8+7)^{6-5-4^{(3+2)}})*-1$
-227187	$-9*(8+7*((6+(5*4^3)^2-1)))$	-261125	$((9-8+7)^{6+5-4^{(3+2)}})*-1$
-227328	$((-9+8^{-(7+6)})-5)^{4^{(3*2+1)}}$	-261289	$9*((-8-7)*-6+5-4^{(3*(2+1))})$
-228830	$-98*((7*(-6-5)+4)^{-32-1})$	-261417	$((9-8+7)^{6-(5+4)^3+2})*-1$
-228956	$98/7*(6*5-4^{(3*2+1)})$	-261513	$((9-8+7)^{6-5^{4-3*2}})*-1$
-229764	$(9/(-8^{7+((6+5)^4-3)^2})^{-1})$	-261514	$((9-8+7)^{6-5^{4-3-2}})*-1$
-229796	$98/7*(-6*5-4^{(3*2+1)})$	-261524	$((9-8+7)^{6-5^{4+3+2}})*-1$
-229851	$9*(-8*((7/6+5*-4)^3)^{2-1})$	-261528	$((9-8+7)^{6-5^{4+3^2}})*-1$
-233038	$(-9/(8^{7+6-5}))^{-(4+3)-21}$	-261599	$((9-8+7)^{6-543-2})*-1$
-233191	$98-(7*(65+4))^{-(3-2)+1}$	-261717	$((9-8+7)^{6+5-432})*-1$
-233888	$(9/(-8^{7-6^{5-4^3}}))^{-(2+1)}$	-261820	$((9-8+7)^{6-543*2})*-1$
-234224	$((9-8+7-6*5)^{4-32})*-1$	-261834	$((9-8+7)^{6-5*(4^3-2)})*-1$
-234293	$-9+(8+7)*(6-5^{4(3/2)})+1$	-261867	$((9-8+7)*-6-5-4^{(3*(2+1))})$
-234457	$9-((8+7)*(6+5^{4(3/2)}))+1$	-261880	$((9+8)+7)*(6+5)-4^{(3*(2+1))}$
-234475	$-9-((8+7)*(6+5^{4(3/2)}))+1$	-261896	$9^{((8+7)/6)+5-4^{(3*(2+1))}}$
-234644	$(9/(-8^{7-((6+5)^4+3)}))^{-(2+1)}$	-261899	$((9-8+7)^{6-5*(4+3)^2})*-1$
-235085	$(9*8-7^{6-5*(-4-3)})^{*2-1}$	-261906	$9^{((8+7)/6)-(5+4^{(3*(2+1))})}$
-235900	$((9-8+7)^{6-(54^3)^2})*-1$	-261931	$((9-8+7)^{6-5*43+2})*-1$
-236243	$(9^{-(8+7)-6*5^4})^{*3*21}$	-262005	$((9-8+7)^{6+5-(4*3)^2})*-1$
-237393	$-9*(8*7*((-6-5)^{-43-2}))+1$	-262030	$((9-8+7)^{6-(54+3)^2})/-1$
-237626	$((9-8*7-6)-5)^{4^{(3*2+1)}}$	-262258	$((9-8+7)^{6+(54+3)^2})/-1$
-239992	$(9/(8*((7+(6*5)^4/3)+2)))^{-1}$	-262357	$((9-8+7)^{6+5*43-2})*-1$
-239994	$(9/(8*(7-(6*5)^4/3)-2))^{-1}$	-262361	$((9-8+7)^{6+5*43+2})*-1$
-240462	$9*876*((5-4^3)/2-1)$	-262382	$-9^{((8+7)/6)+5-4^{(3*(2+1))}}$
-240984	$9*8*((7+(-6-(5+4))^3)+21)$	-262389	$((9-8+7)^{6+5*(4+3)^2})*-1$
-241187	$(-9+8)*7+(-6^{5-4})^{*32-1}$	-262421	$(9-8*7)*6+5-4^{(3*(2+1))}$
-242144	$((9-8+7)^{6-5^{4*32}})*-1$	-262689	$((9-8+7)^{6+543+2})*-1$
-243447	$(9*8*7*6+5^{4+3})*(-2-1)$	-262760	$((9-8+7)^{6+5^{4-3^2}})*-1$
-243591	$9+8*7*6*5*(4^3)^{2+1}$	-262763	$((9-8+7)^{6+5^{4-3*2}})*-1$
-243609	$-9+8*7*6*5*(4^3)^{2+1}$	-262764	$((9-8+7)^{6+5^{4-3-2}})*-1$
-244112	$(-9/(8+(76+54)^3))^{-(2+1)}$	-262875	$((9-8+7)^{6+(5+4)^3+2})*-1$
-245337	$((9-8)^{7+6})^{5-4^{(3*(2+1))}}$	-262913	$(9/(87-6*(5^{4+3})^2))^{-1}$
-245392	$-98*(-7+6-5^4)*((-3-2)+1)$	-262999	$-9*((-8-7)*-6+5)-4^{(3*(2+1))}$
-246144	$((9-8+7)^{6+(5^4)^3})*-1$	-263163	$((9-8+7)^{6-5+4^{(3+2)}})*-1$
-248390	$(9+(8+7^6)*(5+4/3))/(-2-1)$	-263230	$((9-8+7)^{6+543*2})*-1$
-249165	$9*((-8-7^6)/(5/4+3)-2)+1$	-263369	$((9-8+7)^{6+(5*(4+3))^2})*-1$
-250502	$(-9/8-76)*((54+3)^2-1)$	-263440	$9*-8*(7+6+5)-4^{3^2}+1$
-251220	$(-9*8-7)*6*((5^4+3)^2+1)$	-263448	$9*(8+7-((6+5)^4+3)^2+1)$
-251732	$(9-8-7)*(((-65-4)^3)^2-1)$	-263588	$((9-8+7)^{6+(5-43)^2})*-1$
-251766	$9*((8+7*(6-(5*4)^3))/2+1)$	-263872	$((9-8+7)^{6+54*32})*-1$
-251994	$9-(8+(7+6)*(-5+43))^2+1$	-263940	$(-9*8*7+6)*((5^4+3)^2+1)$
-251996	$9-(8+(7+6)*(-5+43))^2-1$	-264021	$((9-8+7)^{6+5^{4*3+2}})*-1$
-252162	$-9*((-8+7*(6+(5*4)^3))/2+1)$	-264304	$((9-8+7)^{6+5*432})*-1$
-252432	$9*-8*((-76-5^4)*(-3-2)+1)$	-264448	$((9-8+7)^{6+(5+43)^2})*-1$
-252782	$(-9-((8*(7-(6-5)))^{4-3}))/21$	-264632	$(-9+8)*76*((5-4^3)^2+1)$
-252899	$((9-8+7)^{6-5/43^2})*-1$	-264897	$9*(((-8-7)*654^3-2)-1)$
-254146	$((9-8+7)^{6-(5^4)^3+2})*-1$	-264933	$9*(((-8-7^6+5)/4-3)-21)$
-254736	$9*8*(7-65)*((4^3-2)-1)$	-265393	$((9-8+7)^{6+(54+3)^2})*-1$
-254915	$-9-8*((7*6*(5/4+3))^2+1)$	-265894	$((9-8+7)^{6+5^{4*3*2}})*-1$
-256519	$((9-8+7)^{6-5^{4*3^2}})*-1$	-265932	$-9*((8*76-5)*(4+3)^2+1)$
-256712	$((9-8+7)^{6-5432})*-1$	-267576	$((9-8+7)^{6+5432})/-1$
-256733	$(9-8)*7+(-6^{5-4})*32+1$	-270142	$((9-8+7)^{6+(5^4)^3-2})*-1$
-256747	$(-9+8)*7+(-6^{5-4})*32+1$	-270146	$((9-8+7)^{6+(5^4)^3+2})*-1$
-257652	$9*(-8*7-6*((5+4^3)^2+1))$	-270300	$(-9*8*7-6)*((5^4+3)^2+1)$
-257724	$9*(((-8-7)+6)*5-4^{(3*2)}+1)$	-270742	$(-9-8)*((7+6)*(5*(4+3))^2+1)$
-257742	$9*(((-8-7)+6)*5-4^{(3*2)}-1)$	-271389	$((9-8+7)^{6+5*43^2})*-1$
-258144	$((9-8+7)^{6+(5^4)^3/2})*-1$	-271890	$(9-87*6)*((5^4+3)^2+1)$
-258372	$9*(((-8+7)-6)*(5+4^{(3*2)}-1))$	-272027	$(-9+8)*7*((6^{5-4})*32+1)$
-258394	$((9-8+7)^{6-5^{4*3*2}})*-1$	-272529	$(-9-8*7*((6+5+4))^3+1)$
-258544	$((-9+8-7)^{6-(5^4*3)^2})*-1$	-272574	$(9/87-6)*((5^4+3)^2+1)$
-258895	$((9-8+7)^{6-(54+3)^2})*-1$	-273524	$(9-8)*-76*((5^4*3)^2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-273978	$9*(8-7*6*5*((4*3)^2+1))$	-336126	$(9-8)*7*6*((-5*4)^3-(2+1))$
-274241	$9*(87-6^{\wedge}5)*(4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-338817	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$
-275275	$(-9+8)*7*((6*5+4)^3+21)$	-340267	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2)/-1$
-275589	$9*((8*765+4)*(-3-2)-1)$	-340271	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2)*-1$
-277317	$9*(-87-6*(5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1))$	-340876	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+54^{\wedge}3/2)*-1$
-277677	$-9*((8*7-6^{\wedge}5)*-4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-341185	$(9-87)/6*(54*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-277811	$9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(-43+2)/1$	-341505	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6+543^{\wedge}2)*-1$
-277829	$-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(-43+2)/1$	-341894	$(-9+8)*7*((6-5*-43)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-277860	$-9*8*7-6*((5*43)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-342057	$-9-8*7*-6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-278088	$9*8*((-7-6^{\wedge}5)/(4^{\wedge}-3+2)-1)$	-342954	$9*87*(-6-54*(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-278144	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3*2)*-1$	-344322	$-9*(8+765*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-281963	$((9+87*6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)+2)*-1$	-345417	$-9-8*-7*6*(-5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-282138	$(-9/87-6)*((5*43)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-346071	$9-8*7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-282900	$9*8*(7/6-5)*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-346089	$-9-8*7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-283473	$9/((-8+7)+6)*(-54^{\wedge}3-21)$	-347142	$9*((-8+7-(6*5)^{\wedge}4)+3)/21$
-284715	$-9/(8*7)*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4*3/2)-1)$	-347148	$9*((-8-7-(6*5)^{\wedge}4)+3)/21$
-288388	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+(54*3)^{\wedge}2)*-1$	-347383	$9+8^{\wedge}7/6*((5*4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-288777	$9/((8-(7+6)^{\wedge}5)*(4+3)+2)^{\wedge}-1$	-347732	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)-6)*(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$
-289380	$(-98+7)*6*((5*4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-348126	$(9+8)*((7-6-5*4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1)$
-290083	$(9*-87*(6^{\wedge}5+4)-3)/21$	-348140	$(-9/8-7)*(((6-5*4)^3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-290331	$9*(-8*((7/6-5*-4)^3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-348398	$(-9-8)*((7+6-5*-4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1)$
-292001	$((-9*8-7)+6)*(5*4)^{\wedge}3/2-1$	-348525	$9*((8+7)+6)*(5-43^{\wedge}2-1)$
-292581	$-9+(8/7*-6^{\wedge}-5/43)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-348564	$-9*(8*7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-294420	$9*8*((7/6*5-4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1)$	-348936	$-9*(8*7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-295404	$9*8*((-7/6*5-4^{\wedge}(3*2))-1)$	-349227	$9*((8*7+(6^{\wedge}5-4)*(-3-2))+1)$
-297676	$-9^{\wedge}((-8-7)/-6)*(5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1$	-350289	$-9*((8+7)*(6^{\wedge}5+4)/3+21)$
-297918	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-350649	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*((5-43)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-298570	$((9*8+7)-6)*(5-(4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1))$	-350664	$9*8*((7-(6+5)^{\wedge}4/3+2)+1)$
-299300	$((-9*8-7)+6)*(5+4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	-352104	$-9*8*((7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4/3+2)+1)$
-299446	$((-9*8-7)+6)*(5-(-4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1))$	-352461	$((-9+8)*-7^{\wedge}6-54*3)*(-2-1)$
-299736	$9*8*(((-7-6)*5*4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$	-353433	$((-9+8)*-7^{\wedge}6+54*3)*(-2-1)$
-302472	$9*8*(7*6*5*4*(-3-2)-1)$	-354172	$-98*((7+6+(5*4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-306450	$(-9-8*765)*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-356238	$-9*((87*65*(4+3)-2)-1)$
-307251	$(-9+8)*(7-(6+5)^{\wedge}4+3)*-21$	-356292	$9*((-87*65*(4+3)-2)-1)$
-307517	$(9-8)*7+((6+5)^{\wedge}4+3)*-21$	-356405	$(9/8-76)*((5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-308369	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+(5*43)^{\wedge}2)*-1$	-356736	$-9/87*(((-6+5^{\wedge}4)^3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-308693	$(-9+8)*7*((6*5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	-357014	$98*((-7*6-(5*4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-309248	$(9/8*7+6+5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$	-358900	$(9*((8+7)+6)+5)*(-43^{\wedge}2-1)$
-309270	$(9-87)*65*((4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$	-363240	$9*8*(76-5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-311362	$((9*(8*7+6))^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))-2)/-1$	-363653	$(-9-8/-7-6)*((54*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-312315	$9+8*((7*6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$	-363895	$(-9+8)*7*((6*(5-43))^{\wedge}2+1)$
-312331	$9+8*((7*6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2-1)$	-367115	$(-9/8-76)*((5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-312349	$-9+8*((7*6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2-1)$	-368055	$-9*(8-7*(6^{\wedge}5/4+3)*(-2-1))$
-312667	$9-8*((7*6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$	-369549	$9/8*((7+6)*-5-4)^{\wedge}3+21$
-312685	$-9-8*((7*6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$	-370832	$-98*(7-6*-5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-313455	$((98-7^{\wedge}6)+5)*4/3*2+1$	-373734	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6)/((-5+4/3)/2-1)$
-313456	$((98-7^{\wedge}6)+5)*4/3*2*1$	-374040	$9*-8*(76-5*-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-313457	$((98-7^{\wedge}6)+5)*4/3*2-1$	-374125	$(9*8+7-6)*-5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-315065	$-9-8*7*((6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-374184	$9*-8*(76-(-5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
-317118	$(-9-8)*(7*65*(43-2)-1)$	-374517	$(-9-87*65)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-320247	$-9*(8/7*(6^{\wedge}5*4+32)-1)$	-374542	$((9*(8-76))^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)-2)*-1$
-321135	$(9*8+7)*((6*5-4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1)$	-374546	$((9*(8-76))^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+2)/-1$
-321193	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2))*-1$	-374880	$((9+8)+7)*((6-5^{\wedge}(4*3/2))-1)$
-321536	$(9/8*(7+6)+5)*-4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$	-375120	$((9+8)+7)*((-6-5^{\wedge}(4*3/2))+1)$
-323993	$(9-8)*7+(6*5)^{\wedge}4/(-3/2-1)$	-375154	$(9-((8-7)+6)*5)^{\wedge}4/(3+2-1)$
-325926	$(-9+8)^{\wedge}7*6*54321$	-375156	$9*(8-7*6)*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
-326033	$(9*-8-7)*((6*5+4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1)$	-375168	$((-9-8)-7)*(6+5^{\wedge}(4*3/2)+1)$
-327573	$9*8*(7+6)-(-5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$	-375191	$(9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)*2*-1$
-327638	$(-9+8)*-7*6-5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-375329	$(-9*8-7)*((6+5)*432-1)$
-327667	$(-9+87)/6-5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-375822	$9/8*((7-6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}4+2)+1$
-327693	$(9-87)/6-5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-376479	$9/8*((-7-6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}4+21)$
-327722	$(-9+8)*7*6-5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-380184	$((-9+8)-7)*((654/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-327987	$-9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6*-5^{\wedge}-4+3)*-2-1$	-380200	$((-9+8)-7)*((654/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-330032	$(-9/(8*((7+6)^{\wedge}5-4-3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-384639	$9-8*(7*6+5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
-330035	$(9/(-8*((7+6)^{\wedge}5-4-3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-384657	$-9-8*(7*6+5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$
-331614	$(9-8)/-7*6*((-5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-385002	$-9/8*((7*6+5)^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}2-1$
-333577	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6+(5*-4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-385391	$9+8*(7*6+5)*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-333721	$-9*8-7^{\wedge}6+(5*-4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-385409	$-9+8*(7*6+5)*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-333900	$(-98-7)*6*((5*4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-385533	$-9*((8*765*(4+3)-2)-1)$
-335118	$(-9+8)*-7*6*((-5*4)^{\wedge}3+21)$	-385587	$9*((-8*765*(4+3)-2)-1)$
-335874	$(-9+8)*-7*6*((-5*4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$	-388248	$(-9+8)*-7*6*(-5/43^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-335958	$(-9+8)*-7*6*((-5*4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$	-388450	$(9-8)*(7-6^{\wedge}5)*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-388695	$98+7-6^{\wedge}5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-439272	$9*8*(7+6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1))$
-388704	$9+87-6^{\wedge}5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-440055	$9*((8+76*5^{\wedge}4)^{-32+1})$
-388722	$-9+87-6^{\wedge}5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-440791	$9-8*76*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-388753	$-9-8*7-6^{\wedge}5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-440809	$-9-8*76*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-388847	$9-8*7-6^{\wedge}5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-442584	$9*(-8-((-7+6)+5)^{\wedge}(4+3))*(2+1)$
-388896	$-9-87-6^{\wedge}5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-445329	$(-9+8)*7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-388905	$-98-7-6^{\wedge}5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-445464	$9*8*(-7-6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1))$
-390506	$(9+8)*7-(-6+5-4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-448092	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)/(5-43^{\wedge}2)^{-1}$
-390549	$(9-8)*76-5^{\wedge}(4+3+2-1)$	-449433	$-9-8/7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-390593	$((98/7+6+5)^{\wedge}4-32)^{-1}$	-451976	$98*(7*((-654-3)-2)+1)$
-390657	$((98/7+6+5)^{\wedge}4+32)^{-1}$	-452790	$9*(8+7)*((-6-(5+4))^{\wedge}3+21)$
-391758	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}5)/((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-453314	$((9*(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2)^{-1}$
-392771	$9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(4-32-1)$	-453318	$((9*(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2)^{-1}$
-392789	$-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(4-32-1)$	-455520	$(9-8)/-7*6*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
-393051	$9*(8+7)+6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-456944	$((98-7-65)^{\wedge}4-32)^{-1}$
-393179	$(9-8)*7+6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-457008	$((98-7-65)^{\wedge}4+32)^{-1}$
-393239	$(9-8)*7-6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-457555	$(9/((-8-7^{\wedge}6)*5*(4+3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-393253	$(-9+8)*7-6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-457920	$(-9-8*7+6)^{-1}$
-393293	$9-8*7-6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-458297	$(-9+8)*-7*(65-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-393381	$-9*(8+7)-6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-458542	$(-9+8)*7*(-6*5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-394674	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5)/((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-458675	$(-9+8)*-7*(6+5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-397089	$9/8*(7^{\wedge}6/((-5+4)/3)-21)$	-458717	$(9-8)^{\wedge}7+6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-398556	$((9*(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5)/-4*3+21$	-458745	$(-9-8)*7*((6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$
-398568	$((9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5)/-4+3*(2+1)$	-458759	$(-9+8)*7*(6-5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-398586	$((9*(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3*(-2-1)$	-458787	$((-9+8)^{\wedge}7-6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-398598	$((9*(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5)/-4*3-21$	-458829	$(-9+8)*7*(6+5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-399520	$-98*((7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-458962	$(-9+8)*-7*(-6*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-399716	$-98*((7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-459207	$(-9+8)*7*(65+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-399742	$98*((7+6)+5-4^{\wedge}(3*2))-1$	-460306	$98*7*(-6-5)*((4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$
-399806	$(-9-8)*((-7^{\wedge}6+54)/(-3-2))-1$	-460331	$((-9+8)*7)^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-400725	$(-98+7^{\wedge}(-6+5))*4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1$	-462350	$(-9+8)*7*((-65*4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-401296	$98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$	-462851	$9+8/-7*((6*5)^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1$
-401324	$98*((-7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1)$	-462869	$-9+8/-7*((6*5)^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1$
-401393	$98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1$	-463185	$-9*(8+7*(6*(5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1))$
-401395	$98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-4^{\wedge}(3*2))-1$	-463356	$9*(8-7*6*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1))$
-401421	$-98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1$	-465057	$9/8*(-7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
-401423	$-98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+4^{\wedge}(3*2))-1$	-465066	$9/8*-7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-401492	$98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-4^{\wedge}(3*2))-1$	-466033	$(-9/(8^{\wedge}7+6-5))^{\wedge}(-4+3)*2+1$
-401520	$-98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$	-466035	$(9/(-8^{\wedge}7-(6-5)))^{\wedge}(-4+3)*2-1$
-401715	$9*(8/7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)/2)+1)$	-467758	$98-(76*(5+4))^{\wedge}(3-2)+1$
-401733	$-9*(8/7*(6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)/2)+1)$	-469809	$9*(87*6*5*4*(-3-2)-1)$
-403300	$-98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$	-472266	$(-9+8)*7*(6*5-54*3)*(-2-1)$
-404320	$(-9+8)*-7*(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-473013	$9*((-876*5*4*3+2)+1)$
-406017	$-9*(8*7+(6+5)*4^{\wedge}(3*2))+1$	-473200	$(-9+8)*7*(65*4)^{\wedge}(3-2)+1$
-406511	$(-9*8*(7+6)-5)*432+1$	-475250	$(-9-8+7)*((654/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-406513	$(-9*8*(7+6)-5)*432-1$	-476933	$9*8+7-6*(-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-415683	$9*(-8*76^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+21)$	-477091	$(-9*8-7)-6*(-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-415737	$9*(-8*(76^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)-2)-1)$	-477151	$(-9*8-7+6*(-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
-415899	$9*((-8/76^{\wedge}(5-4-3)-2)-1)$	-478764	$9*(8-76*5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-419179	$((-9-8^{\wedge}7)+6)/5+4*3*21$	-482832	$9*8*-7*(-65+4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-419606	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+54^{\wedge}3-2)^{-1}$	-483264	$9*8*(7*(65-4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
-419610	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+54^{\wedge}3+2)/-1$	-483345	$-9*(8*7*(-65+4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
-423108	$9*-876*(54-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-483408	$9*-8*(-7*(65-4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
-423637	$(-9+8/-7-6)*((54*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-483446	$((-9-8*(7+6))-5)*4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1$
-425444	$9*-876*(54-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-484190	$(-9+8)*7*((65*4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-426028	$9*-876*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-485216	$((9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6-(5*43)^{\wedge}2)^{-1}$
-426540	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7+6)/(5-(4*3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-491527	$(-9+8)*7-6*5*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
-427386	$(-9*8/7-6)*((54*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-493303	$9-8/7*((654+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-427709	$(9-8)*7-654^{\wedge}(3-(2-1))$	-493321	$-9-8/7*((654+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-427950	$(-9*87-6^{\wedge}5)*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-495828	$9*(8+76*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-428364	$9*-876*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-495972	$-9*(8+76*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-428741	$9+((8-7)+6)^5/4/(-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-496774	$(9/((8+7^{\wedge}6)^*(5-43)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-428759	$9+(((8-7)+6)^5)/4/(-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-505656	$-9*((8+7)*(6/5^{\wedge}4-3)-21)$
-429300	$9*(-8-7)*6*((5*4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-508738	$(-9+8)*7^{\wedge}6*5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-430176	$9+((8+7)+6)*5*(-4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	-510714	$9/8*(-7-((65-4)^{\wedge}3*2-1))$
-430194	$-9+((8+7)+6)*5*(-4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	-511441	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}32)^{-1}$
-431134	$((9*8-7^{\wedge}6)-5)*4/3*2+1$	-512928	$9*(8+76*((-5-4)^{\wedge}3-21))$
-431586	$9*((8-((7*(-6-5)+4)*3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-513072	$-9*(8-76*((-5-4)^{\wedge}3-21))$
-431712	$-9*((8+((7*(-6-5)+4)*3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-513184	$(-9+8)*7*(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-438031	$9-8*((-7-6)*54/3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-515141	$(9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3*2)^{-1}$
-439008	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))/3*2/1$	-518424	$((-9-8)-7)*(6*(5*4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-439009	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))/3*2-1$	-522196	$((9*(8-7))^{\wedge}6-5*43^{\wedge}2)^{-1}$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-523439	$((9/(8-7))^6 - (5^4)^3 - 2)^{-1}$	-540819	$-9 * ((8+7) * (6 + (5^4)^3/2) + 1)$
-523443	$((9/(8-7))^6 - (5^4)^3 + 2)^{-1}$	-541544	$(-9+8)/7 * ((6^5/4+3)^2 - 1)$
-524051	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6)) * ((5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$	-542188	$(-9 / ((8 + (7^6 + 5)^4) + 3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-525393	$9 * 8^7 * (-6-5) * ((4^{\wedge}3 - 2) - 1)$	-542437	$(-9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 + 543)) / 21$
-526009	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 - 5432)^{-1}$	-546012	$-9 * 8^7 * ((6+5)^4 + 3) / 21$
-526827	$9 / ((8^* - 7)^{\wedge}(6 - 5 - 4)^3) + 21$	-546534	$-9 / 8^* ((7 + (-6 - 5)^4)^3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-526869	$9 / ((8^* - 7)^{\wedge}(6 - 5 - 4)^3) - 21$	-546980	$(9 - 8)^7 * ((6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3)) - 21)$
-527340	$((9/(8-7))^6 - (5+4^{\wedge}(3^2)))^{-1}$	-547441	$((9/(8-7))^6 + (5^4)^3)^2)^{-1}$
-527355	$-9/8^* (7-6^* - 5^{\wedge}(4+3) + 2 + 1)$	-551441	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 + 5^4 * 3^2)^{-1}$
-527441	$((9^*(8-7))^6 + (5^4)^3 / - 2)^{-1}$	-551700	$9^* (-8 - 7^6)^* ((5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-527691	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 - 5^4 * 3^2)^{-1}$	-551921	$((9 / (-8+7))^6 + 5^4 * 3^2)^{-1}$
-527841	$((9/(8-7))^6 - (5^4 * 3)^2)^{-1}$	-552600	$9^* - 8^* (7 + 6^5 - 4^* 3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-528840	$((9/(8-7))^6 - (54-3)^2)^{-1}$	-553113	$9^* ((8+7)^* (-6/5 - 4^{\wedge}(3^2)) + 1)$
-529568	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 - 5^4 * 3 + 2)^{-1}$	-554040	$(9 - 8^* (7+6))^* (54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-529597	$((9/(8-7))^6 + 5 - 43^2)^{-1}$	-555631	$9 + ((8+7)^6 - 5) / (-43/2+1)$
-529997	$((9/(8-7))^6 - (5-43)^2)^{-1}$	-555649	$-9 + ((8+7)^6 - 5) / (-43/2+1)$
-530216	$((9/(8-7))^6 - (5^*(4+3))^2)^{-1}$	-556472	$(-9+8)^* 7^* (-6-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-530355	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 - 543^2)^{-1}$	-556556	$(-9+8)^* 7^* (6-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-530412	$((9/(8-7))^6 - 5 - 4^{\wedge}(3+2))^{-1}$	-556993	$((9-8+7)^6 + 543^2)^{-1}$
-530422	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}(3+2))^{-1}$	-562569	$(-98 - 7^6)^* (5+4 / (3-21))$
-530730	$9 / ((-8+7)+6)^* (-543^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-565704	$((-98+7) - 6)^* (54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-530784	$((-9^*(8-7))^6 - 5^4 * 32)^{-1}$	-567144	$9^* 8^* (7 - 6^5 - 4^* 3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-530801	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 - 5^4 * 3^2)^{-1}$	-568710	$-9 / 8^* ((7 + (-6 - 5)^4)^3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-530912	$((9/(8-7))^6 - (5^4 + 3)^2)^{-1}$	-568751	$9 - 8 / 7^* ((6^5 * 4^3 + 2) - 1)$
-531011	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 - 5^4 * 3^2)^{-1}$	-568769	$-9 - 8 / 7^* ((6^5 * 4^3 + 2) - 1)$
-531123	$((9^*(8-7))^6 - 5^4 * 3 + 2)^{-1}$	-570262	$98^*(7+6 - (54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-531131	$((9/(8-7))^6 - 5^*(4^3 - 2))^{-1}$	-571032	$9^* 8^*(7+6^5 / ((4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1))$
-531171	$((9/(8-7))^6 - 54^*(3+2))^{-1}$	-571861	$(-9+8)^* 7^6 * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^2 + 1)$
-531196	$((9/(8-7))^6 - 5^*(4+3)^2)^{-1}$	-573480	$-9^*(-8 - 7)^* 6^* ((-5 - 4)^3 + 21)$
-531228	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 - 5^4 * 3 + 2)^{-1}$	-573768	$(9 - 87)^* 6^* ((5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-531236	$((9/(8-7))^6 - 5^*(43 - 2))^{-1}$	-574181	$9^*(8^* 7 + 6)^* (-5 - 4^{\wedge}(3+2)) + 1$
-531277	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 - 54^* 3 - 2)^{-1}$	-574183	$9^*(8^* 7 + 6)^* (-5 - 4^{\wedge}(3+2)) - 1$
-531281	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 - 54^* 3 + 2)^{-1}$	-576408	$98^7 * (65^* ((-4 - 3) - 2) + 1)$
-531303	$((9/(8-7))^6 - (5+4^3)^2)^{-1}$	-577385	$(-9 - 8 / (-7^6))^* (5+4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1))$
-531308	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 - 5 - 4^3)^2)^{-1}$	-577666	$((9^*(8-7))^6 + (5^4 * 3)^2)^{-1}$
-531318	$((9/(8-7))^6 + 5 - 4^3)^2)^{-1}$	-578574	$(9 + (8+7)^* ((6^5)^4 + 3)) / -21$
-531321	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 - 5^4 * 3^2)^{-1}$	-581124	$(-9^* 8 - 7)^6 * ((5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-531561	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 + 5^4 * 3^2)^{-1}$	-583110	$(9^* 8 + 7^6)^* 5^* (-4^{\wedge}(3+2) + 1)$
-531564	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 - 5 + 4^3)^2)^{-1}$	-583566	$(9^* 8 + 7^6)^* (-5^4 * 3 + 2) + 1$
-531574	$((9/(8-7))^6 + 5 + 4^3)^2)^{-1}$	-584250	$(9^* 8 + 7^6)^* - 5^* (4^{\wedge}(3+2) + 1)$
-531579	$((9/(8-7))^6 + (5+4^3)^2)^{-1}$	-585328	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^* (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-531599	$(-9 + (-8 - 7) / 6)^* ((5^4 * 3)^2 + 1)$	-585344	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^* (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-531601	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 + 54^* 3 - 2)^{-1}$	-585501	$98^7 / -6^* (5^4 * 3 + 2) + 1$
-531605	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 + 54^* 3 + 2)^{-1}$	-586517	$(-9+8)^* 7^6 * 5 + (4^* 3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-531646	$((9/(8-7))^6 + 5^*(43 - 2))^{-1}$	-586901	$((-9+8)^* 7^6 * 5 + 4^3)^2 + 1$
-531654	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 + 5^4 * 3 - 2)^{-1}$	-587298	$9^*(8 - 7^6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3)) / (2+1)$
-531686	$((9/(8-7))^6 + 5^*(4+3)^2)^{-1}$	-589785	$-9^*(8^* - 7 / 6 + 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1))$
-531711	$((9/(8-7))^6 + 54^*(3+2))^{-1}$	-589863	$9^*(8^* - 7 / 6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1))$
-531751	$((9/(8-7))^6 + 5^*(4^3 - 2))^{-1}$	-589973	$(-9+8)^* 7^6 * 5 - (4^* 3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-531759	$((9/(8-7))^6 + 5^4 * 3^2)^{-1}$	-591336	$9^* 8^* ((76^* - 54 - 3)^2 + 1)$
-531871	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 + 5^4 * 3^2)^{-1}$	-597920	$(9^* 8 + 7)^* - 6^5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^2 + 1)$
-531970	$((9/(8-7))^6 + (5^4 + 3)^2)^{-1}$	-602353	$(-9 - 8 / (7^6))^* (5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1))$
-532060	$((9/(8-7))^6 + 5^4 * 3 - 2)^{-1}$	-604629	$(-9+8)^* 7^6 * 5 - 4^{\wedge}(3^2 + 1)$
-532061	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 + 5^4 * 3 - 2)^{-1}$	-606241	$(-9 / 8^* (7 - 65)^4 - 3) / 21$
-532081	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 + 5^4 * 3^2)^{-1}$	-607772	$(9 - 8)^* - 76^* ((5^4)^3 - 2) - 1$
-532098	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 + 5^4 * 32)^{-1}$	-609564	$((9/(8-7))^6 + 5^{\wedge}(4+3) - 2)^{-1}$
-532168	$((9/(8-7))^6 + (5+4)^3 - 2)^{-1}$	-609568	$((9/(8-7))^6 + 5^{\wedge}(4+3) + 2)^{-1}$
-532172	$((9/(8-7))^6 + (5+4)^3 + 2)^{-1}$	-610713	$9^* ((-87^* 65^4 * 3 + 2) + 1)$
-532460	$((9/(8-7))^6 - 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3+2))^{-1}$	-610767	$-9^* ((87^* 65^4 * 3 + 2) + 1)$
-532610	$((-9 - 8^7) - 65)^* (4^{\wedge}(3^2) + 1)$	-613440	$((9^* 8 - 7) + 6)^* 5 / (-4^* 3)^{\wedge}(-2 - 1)$
-533285	$((9/(8-7))^6 - 5 + 43^2)^{-1}$	-614650	$((98 + 7^6) / 5)^4 - 3^2)^{-1}$
-533318	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 + 5^4 * 3 + 2)^{-1}$	-614688	$((98 + 7^6) / 5)^4 + 32)^{-1}$
-533601	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 + 5^4 * 32)^{-1}$	-615204	$9 / 8^* (7^* ((6 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3)) - 2) - 1)$
-535041	$((9/(8-7))^6 + (5^4 * 3)^2)^{-1}$	-615267	$9 / 8^* (-7^* ((6 + 5^{\wedge}(4+3)) - 2) - 1)$
-535191	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 + 5^4 * 3^2)^{-1}$	-617471	$-9^*(8^* 7 + 6 + 5)^4 * 3 + 2 + 1$
-535500	$(-9 - 8)^* - 7^6 * ((-5 - 4)^3 - 21)$	-617473	$-9^*(8^* 7 + 6 + 5)^4 * 3 + 2 - 1$
-535532	$((-9 / (8 - 7))^6 - 5 + 4^{\wedge}(-3^* - 2))^* - 1$	-620194	$(-9 - 8)^* (((7^6 + 5)^4 + 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-536311	$9 / (8 - (7 + 6)^{\wedge}(5 + 4 - 3) + 2))^{\wedge} - 1$	-622152	$9^* - 8^* (7 - 6 - 5^* (-4^* 3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-536561	$((9^*(8-7))^6 - 5^* - 4^{\wedge}(3+2))^* - 1$	-623907	$-9^* ((8^* 7^* (-6 + 5^4) - 3)^2 + 1)$
-536873	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7))^6 + 5432)^{-1}$	-623997	$9^* ((8^* 7^* (-6 + 5^4) + 3)^2 - 2 + 1)$
-539181	$9^* ((8+7)^* (6 - (5^4)^3/2) + 1)$	-624017	$(9 - 8)^* 7 - 6^5 / 4^* 321$
-539439	$((9/(8-7))^6 + (5^4)^3 - 2)^{-1}$	-627217	$-9 - 8^* ((7^6 * 5^4 / 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-627425	$((9+8*(-7^6+5))+4)/3^2+1$	-721800	$-9/8*((7+65^4)^3)^2-1$
-627427	$((9+8*(-7^6+5))+4)/3^2-1$	-725547	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^*(5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-627437	$(-9+8*(-7^6+5)+4)/3^2+1$	-726852	$(9+8)^*7^*6*(5-(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
-628938	$(9+87^*-6)*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-727040	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^*5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
-630688	$(9*8+7)^*-6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$	-727488	$9*8*(7-((6+5)+4)^3)^*(2+1)$
-633841	$((9*(8-7))^{\wedge}6+(5*4^3)^{\wedge}2)^*-1$	-727549	$(9+8)^*(7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
-633864	$98^*-7*((6-5)+43)^*21$	-730440	$9*8*((-7+6*5^4)^*-32-1)$
-636003	$-9*((8*7*(-6-5^{\wedge}4)+3)^*-2+1)$	-730512	$9*8*(7+((6+5)+4)^3)^*(-2-1)$
-636093	$9*((8*7*(-6-5^{\wedge}4)-3)^*2+1)$	-730683	$-9*(8*7*6*5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-637812	$(-9*(8+7))^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))^*21$	-731660	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-637938	$(-9*(8+7))^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3)^*21$	-731680	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-639963	$9-87*6*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-733992	$(-9-8)^*7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-639981	$-9-87*6*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-734256	$9*(8*7*6-5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1))$
-646816	$(-9-8)^*(7*6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$	-735420	$(-9-8)^*7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
-647352	$((-98-7)-6)*(54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-737851	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3)^2*-1$
-647654	$-9*8*7*((6/(5^*43))^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-738216	$9*(8*(-7-6)-5*4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$
-651006	$(-9+87*-6)*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-739152	$9/8*(7-((65+4)^3)^2-1)$
-651264	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)-6)^*(5+43)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-743832	$9*8*(7+6*(5+(-4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
-651695	$(-9+8/7)^*(6*(5+43))^{\wedge}2-1$	-748510	$(-9+8)^*7*((6*54+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-654321	$(-9+8)^{\wedge}7*654321$	-751687	$((9-876)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)-2)^*-1$
-655348	$(-9-8+7)*(-6/5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-751691	$((9-876)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)+2)^*-1$
-655372	$(9+8-7)^*(-6/5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-754974	$((-9-8/7)+6+5)/((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-655459	$(-9+8)^*7*((6*(54-3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-761049	$9*((-87*6*5^4+3)^2+1)$
-655707	$(9+8)/-7*((6*5)^{\wedge}4/3-2-1)$	-762183	$-9*(8-7*(-6^{\wedge}5-4321))$
-656084	$-9/8*((765-4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-762552	$9*8*((-7-6*5^4)^3)^2+1$
-656098	$((9*(-8-7)*6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)-2))^*-1$	-763776	$-9*8*((76-(-5-4)^3)^2-1)$
-656102	$((9*(-8-7)*6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+2))^*-1$	-764751	$((-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-656292	$(-9+8)^*-7*6*(-5^{\wedge}(4*3/2)-1)$	-765378	$9*(8+7*-6^{\wedge}5*(4/3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-658377	$-9/8*((765/(4-3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	-771111	$-9*(8*-765*(-4*3-2)-1)$
-659151	$9+(-8-7)*((6+5)^{\wedge}4+3+21)$	-772380	$(-98-7)^*6*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
-660933	$9*((-8*765*4^*3+2)+1)$	-773145	$-9/8*((765+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-660987	$-9*((8*765*4^*3+2)+1)$	-773190	$9*((8+7)+6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
-661134	$(9-8)^*(7-65^{\wedge}4)^*3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	-773208	$9*((8+7)+6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
-663318	$9*(8+((7+6)+5)*(-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1))$	-774123	$(-9+8)^*7/(6-5^{\wedge}4)^{-3+21}$
-663462	$-9*(8+((7+6)+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1))$	-774291	$(9-8)^*7*((6-5^{\wedge}4)^3-21)$
-663642	$9*(8+((-7-6)-5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1))$	-774675	$(-9+8/7)^*((6-5/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-663786	$-9*(8+((7+6)+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1))$	-775080	$-9*((8+7)+6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
-664418	$(-9-8/7)^*(-6*5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-775098	$9*(((-8-7)-6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2))-1)$
-667752	$(-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6*5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-777238	$98*(7+6^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^{\wedge}-2-1))$
-667870	$-98*(7*6+5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-779085	$9*87*(6*5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-669396	$(-98+7)^*6*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-783223	$((9+876)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)-2)^*-1$
-673776	$9*8/-7*(-6*5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-783227	$((9+876)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)+2)^*-1$
-674926	$-98*(7*-6*(-5^*3-2)-1)$	-783314	$98*(7+((-6-5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-678096	$9*8*(7-65*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$	-784125	$(-9+8)^*765*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-679104	$9*8*(-7-65*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$	-787440	$((-9^{\wedge}8+7)-6)/(54-(-3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$
-680544	$9*8*(7+6)*((-5-4)^3+2)-1$	-788139	$-9/8*((7*6*5^4-3)^2-1)$
-683784	$9*8*(7-6^{\wedge}5+(-4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-796322	$-98*(7/(6+5^{\wedge}4))^{\wedge}(-3+2-1)$
-684144	$9*8*((-7-6)*((5+4)^3+2)+1)$	-799479	$-9/8*((7*6*5^4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-684441	$9/8*((7-(65*4^3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-803214	$9*(-8-((7+6*5)^{\wedge}4-3))/21$
-684792	$9*-8*(7+6^{\wedge}5-(-4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-807126	$((-9^{\wedge}8+7)-6)/(54+(-3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$
-685072	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3)^2*-1$	-810852	$98*7*-6*(5-4^{\wedge}3*(-2-1))$
-687691	$((9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^2*-1$	-817377	$(-9-8)^*(7*6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-688903	$((9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6+54^{\wedge}3)^2*-1$	-818755	$(-9+8)^*7*((6*(54+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
-688907	$((9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6+54^{\wedge}3+2)^*-1$	-819291	$(9/8*7+6)*((-5-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-700443	$9*(8*7*6*5-43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-825125	$(9*(-8-7)^*6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-702852	$9*((8*7/6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))+21)$	-825339	$((9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^3)^*(-2-1)$
-703000	$(-9+8)^*-76*5*(-43^{\wedge}2-1)$	-830004	$((-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$
-703014	$9*(8*7/6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2+1)$	-833745	$(9*(-8-7)^*-6+5)*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-703236	$-9*(8*7/6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2+1)$	-833985	$-9/8*((7*(6*5^4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
-703398	$9*((-8*7/6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))-21)$	-835375	$(9*(8+7)^*-6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-703731	$987*((6-5/(4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-842534	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3)^2*-1$
-705151	$(9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-543^{\wedge}2/-1$	-842538	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3+2)^*-1$
-705678	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6/(5+4+3)-2)-1)$	-842544	$9*(8/7*(6-5*4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)))$
-706110	$9*8*((-7^{\wedge}6/(5+4+3)-2)-1)$	-843876	$-9*((8+7+6*5^{\wedge}4)^3)^2-1$
-707004	$-9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-860118	$(-9+8)^*-7*6*(-5*4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
-707313	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^3)^2*-1$	-863577	$9/8*(7+6)*((-5-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-710883	$-9*(8*(-7-6)^*5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-866250	$(-9+8)^*-7*6/(5^{\wedge}4/(-32-1))$
-711916	$(-9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4)/(3+2-1)$	-869184	$((9*8*7-6)+5)/(-4*3)^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-712800	$9*(8+7/6)^*5*(4*-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-872640	$((-9*8*7-6)+5)/(4*3)^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-716835	$(9-8)^*7*((-6-5*4^3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-876094	$((9*8*(7+6))^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)-2)^*-1$
-720243	$9*(8*(-7-6)^*5-43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-876098	$((9*8*(7+6))^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+2)^*-1$
-721294	$(-9+8)^*7*((-6*54+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-878034	$(9-(8*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4))^*(3+2)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-878035	$(9 - (8^7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4))^*(3+2)^{\wedge}1$	-991998	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (5^4)^{\wedge}3 - 2)^* - 1$
-878036	$(9 - (8^7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4))^*(3+2) - 1$	-992002	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (5^4)^{\wedge}3 + 2)^* - 1$
-878124	$(-9 - (8^7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4))^*(3+2)+1$	-993060	$9^*(- 8 - 7)^*6^*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
-878125	$(-9 - (8^7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4))^*(3+2^{\wedge}1)$	-993393	$9^*((-8^{\wedge}7-6)-5)/(4*(3+2)-1)$
-878126	$(-9 - (8^7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4))^*(3+2) - 1$	-994375	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
-882405	$((-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6 - 5)^*(4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-994568	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}432)^* - 1$
-883872	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7)^*6^{\wedge}5 * (-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-995760	$-9^*8^*(7+6^{\wedge}5 * (4/3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-886437	$9^*((-8^*76^*54^*3+2)+1)$	-996000	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (5^*4)^{\wedge}3/2)^* - 1$
-886491	$-9^*((8^*76^*54^*3+2)+1)$	-996400	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
-888489	$-9^*(87^*6^*(5+4)+3)^*21$	-996450	$(9/-8^*7+6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
-889920	$(9^*8^*-7-6-5)^*(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-996543	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2))^{\wedge}1$
-897600	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$	-996751	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (54+3)^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-899993	$(9-8)^*7+(6^*5)^{\wedge}4 * (-3^{\wedge}-2) - 1$	-996875	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4(4+3-2))^* - 1$
-902037	$(9/((-8-7^{\wedge}6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-(-2+1))$	-997137	$9^*((-8+76*(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^* - 2 - 1)$
-903550	$9+((8-(7-65))^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$	-997399	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (54-3)^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
-903568	$-9+((8-(7-65))^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$	-997840	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*432)^* - 1$
-905184	$-9/8^*(((-7-6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	-998123	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 - 2)^* - 1$
-907193	$(9-8)^*-7^*((6^*5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-998127	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 + 2)^* - 1$
-908211	$(-9 - (-8/7+6))^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-998156	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 43^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
-908598	$9 - (8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))/2+1$	-998272	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 54^*32)^* - 1$
-908599	$9 - (8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))/2^*1$	-998775	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
-908600	$9 - (8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))/2 - 1$	-998914	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 54^*32)^* - 1$
-908616	$(-9+(-8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))/2)+1$	-998981	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}(3+2))/-1$
-908617	$-9 - (8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))/2^*1$	-999269	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (5+4)^{\wedge}3 - 2)^* - 1$
-908618	$(-9+(-8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))/2) - 1$	-999273	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (5+4)^{\wedge}3 + 2)^* - 1$
-909312	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6)-5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-999280	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
-911040	$-9^*8/(7^*6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$	-999343	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 - 32)^* - 1$
-911596	$-98^*(7+65^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1))$	-999370	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 - 3 - 2)^* - 1$
-912111	$9^*((-8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}5^4) - 3)/21$	-999380	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 + 3 + 2)^* - 1$
-918325	$(9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6 + (5^{\wedge}4 - 3)^{\wedge}2)/-1$	-999381	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 + 3^*2)^* - 1$
-918731	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7 - (-6-5))^*(-4^*3+2-1)$	-999407	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 + 32)^* - 1$
-921268	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 54^{\wedge}3/2)^* - 1$	-999455	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 54^{\wedge}3 - 2)^* - 1$
-921873	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4(4+3) - 2)/-1$	-999459	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 54^{\wedge}3 + 2)^* - 1$
-921877	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4(4+3) + 2)^* - 1$	-999563	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 432)^* - 1$
-925506	$9^*87^*-6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^*(-2-1))$	-999570	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*43^*2)^* - 1$
-928515	$(-9+8)^*-7^*(6-(54-3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-999573	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 432)^* - 1$
-930013	$((9^*(8-7))^{\wedge}6 - 5)/(-4^*3)^*21$	-999676	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 54^*3^*2)^* - 1$
-930257	$(-9-8)^*(76^*5/(4^*3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-999690	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*(4^{\wedge}3 - 2))^* - 1$
-930835	$(-9-8)^*(((-7-6)^*54/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-999730	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 54^*(3+2))^* - 1$
-932039	$(9/((-8^{\wedge}7+65)^*4-3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-999755	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*(4+3)^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
-935933	$(9^*87-6^*5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2+1$	-999775	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*(43+2))^* - 1$
-937983	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - (5^*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1))$	-999783	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 - 2)^* - 1$
-938001	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - (5^*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1))$	-999787	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*43+2)^* - 1$
-942225	$(9+8)^*(76^*(5-4)^{\wedge}3-21)$	-999795	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*(43-2))^* - 1$
-944383	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + (5^*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1))$	-999820	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4^*3^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
-944401	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + (5^*4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1))$	-999836	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 54^*3 - 2)^* - 1$
-949097	$((9-87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))+3)^*2+1$	-999840	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 54^*3+2)^* - 1$
-949098	$((9-87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))+3)^*2^*1$	-999851	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 - (4^*3)^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
-949099	$((9-87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))+3)^*2-1$	-999856	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (5+4+3)^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
-949109	$((9-87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))-3)^*2+1$	-999861	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 - (4^*3)^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
-949110	$((9-87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))-3)^*2^*1$	-999867	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4^*32)^* - 1$
-949111	$((9-87)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))-3)^*2-1$	-999877	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4^*32)^* - 1$
-950000	$(9 - (-8+7))^{\wedge}6 * ((5^*4)^{\wedge}(-3+2) - 1)$	-999880	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4^*3^*2)^* - 1$
-954734	$(9^*(8 - (7+6)^{\wedge}5) - 4)/(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-999882	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}3)^*2)^* - 1$
-959850	$(-9^*8-7)^*6^{\wedge}5 * ((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-999886	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (54+3)^*2)^* - 1$
-959993	$(9-8)^*7-6^*(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	-999898	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (54-3)^*2)^* - 1$
-962359	$((987-6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3) - 2)^* - 1$	-999900	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4^*(3+2))^* - 1$
-962363	$((987-6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3) + 2)^* - 1$	-999904	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (5+43)^*2)^* - 1$
-964217	$(9-8)^*7-6^{\wedge}5^*4^*(32-1)$	-999914	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 54 - 32)^* - 1$
-972864	$(9^*(8^*7+6)+5)^*(-4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-999919	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 43^*2)^* - 1$
-973756	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - (54^*3)^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$	-999924	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 + (5-43)^*2)^* - 1$
-986071	$((-9^*8-7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))+3)^*2+1$	-999933	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 - (4^*3+2))^* - 1$
-986073	$((-9^*8-7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))+3)^*2-1$	-999935	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*(4+3^{\wedge}2))/-1$
-986083	$((-9^*8-7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))-3)^*2+1$	-999950	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 43 - 2)^* - 1$
-986085	$((-9^*8-7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))-3)^*2-1$	-999955	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 54 + 3^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
-987758	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)^*3)/2+1$	-999959	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4 - 32)^* - 1$
-987760	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)^*3)/2-1$	-999960	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 43 - 2)^* - 1$
-988821	$9^*((-8^*7^*654^*3+2)+1)$	-999971	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4 - 3^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
-988875	$-9^*((8^*7^*654^*3+2)+1)$	-999978	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 54 + 32)^* - 1$
-990074	$9+8^*((-7-6)^{\wedge}5+4)/3+21$	-1000022	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 + 54 - 32)^* - 1$
-990755	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4^*3^{\wedge}2)/-1$	-1000029	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4^*3^{\wedge}2)^* - 1$
-991476	$-9^*((8-(7^*6+5))^{\wedge}4+3)/21$	-1000040	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 43 + 2)^* - 1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1000041	$((9+8-7)^{6+5+4+32})^{-1}$	-1042470	$9*(8+7)^6*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1000045	$((9+8-7)^{6+54-3^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1042521	$-9/87*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3*2+1)$
-1000049	$((9+8-7)^{6+54-3-2})^{-1}$	-1043970	$98*(7*6+5)-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000050	$((9+8-7)^{6+5+43+2})^{-1}$	-1044391	$-9*(-87-6)^5*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000067	$((9+8-7)^{6+5+4^{\wedge}3-2})^{-1}$	-1044931	$-9*(-87+6)^5*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000086	$((9+8-7)^{6+54+32})^{-1}$	-1045116	$(98*7+6)^5*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000091	$((9+8-7)^{6+5+43*2})^{-1}$	-1045176	$(98*7-6)^5*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000096	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5+43)^2})^{-1}$	-1046225	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5*43)^2})/-1$
-1000100	$((9+8-7)^{6+5*4*(3+2)})^{-1}$	-1048047	$9-8*(-7-6)^5*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000102	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5+4-3)^2})^{-1}$	-1048065	$(-9-8*(-7-6)^5*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-1000114	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5+4+3)^2})^{-1}$	-1048328	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000118	$((9+8-7)^{6-(5-4^{\wedge}3)^2})^{-1}$	-1048338	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-1000120	$((9+8-7)^{6+5*4*3*2})^{-1}$	-1048376	$9*(8+7)+65-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000123	$((9+8-7)^{6-5+4^{\wedge}32})^{-1}$	-1048776	$(-9*(8+7)-65-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-1000133	$((9+8-7)^{6+5+4*32})^{-1}$	-1049087	$9+8*(-7-6)^5*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000138	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5+4^{\wedge}3)^2})^{-1}$	-1049105	$(-9+8*(-7-6)^5*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-1000139	$((9+8-7)^{6-5+(4*3)^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1050849	$-9*((8+7)*(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3/2))+1)$
-1000144	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5+4+3)^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1051467	$(-9-8)*(7*(6*5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1000149	$((9+8-7)^{6+5+(4*3)^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1051976	$(98*-7+6)^5*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000164	$((9+8-7)^{6+54*3+2})^{-1}$	-1052036	$(-98*7-6)^5*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000180	$((9+8-7)^{6+5*4*3^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1052221	$9*(-87+6)^5*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000205	$((9+8-7)^{6+5*(43-2)})^{-1}$	-1052761	$9*(-87-6)^5*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000213	$((9+8-7)^{6+5*43-2})^{-1}$	-1053182	$-98*(7*6+5)-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000217	$((9+8-7)^{6+5*43+2})^{-1}$	-1056352	$(-9+8)^{\wedge}7*6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000225	$((9+8-7)^{6+5*(43+2)})^{-1}$	-1057419	$-9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6-5-((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-1000245	$((9+8-7)^{6+5*(4+3)^{\wedge}2})/-1$	-1060263	$9*(-8-7^{\wedge}6-5-((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-1000270	$((9+8-7)^{6+54*(3+2)})^{-1}$	-1062942	$(9-876)*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000324	$((9+8-7)^{6+54*3*2})^{-1}$	-1064084	$(-98-7^{\wedge}6)*(5+4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-1000427	$((9+8-7)^{6-5+432})^{-1}$	-1064862	$98+(-7-6)^5/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-1000430	$((9+8-7)^{6+5*43*2})^{-1}$	-1064946	$98/7-65/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-1000437	$((9+8-7)^{6+5+432})^{-1}$	-1064974	$-98/7-65/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-1000486	$((9+8-7)^{6+54*3^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1065058	$-98+(-7-6)^5/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-1000541	$((9+8-7)^{6+543-2})^{-1}$	-1067382	$(-9*8/7-6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-1000545	$((9+8-7)^{6+543+2})^{-1}$	-1071360	$9*(-87-6)^5*4^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
-1000616	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1076403	$(9-8*76)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)*(-2-1)$
-1000619	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4-3*2})^{-1}$	-1078123	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3)-2})/-1$
-1000630	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4+3+2})^{-1}$	-1078127	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3)+2})^{-1}$
-1000631	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4+3*2})/-1$	-1078732	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4(3/2)})^{-1}$
-1000634	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1079387	$(-9-((8-7*(6+5))^{\wedge}4-3))/21$
-1000640	$((9+8-7)^{6+5*4*32})^{-1}$	-1080008	$((9-8)+7)*((6*5)^{\wedge}4/(-3*2)-1)$
-1000657	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4+32})^{-1}$	-1084026	$(-9/8*7-6)^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2+1)$
-1000720	$((-9-8+7)^{6+5/(4*3)^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1084372	$9/(8+((7*6+5)^{\wedge}4-3)*(-2))^{\wedge}-1$
-1000727	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3-2})^{-1}$	-1085010	$(-9-876)*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1000731	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2})^{-1}$	-1087881	$(9+8)*(7+(6*5*-4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-1001029	$((9+8-7)^{6+5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)})/-1$	-1088119	$(-9-8)*(7-(6*5*-4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-1001225	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1088633	$(-9+8)*-7*(6^{\wedge}5*4*(-3-2)+1)$
-1001444	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5-43)^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1090152	$9*(8-76^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3))^*21$
-1001728	$((9+8-7)^{6+54*32})^{-1}$	-1093645	$98/7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))+21$
-1001844	$((9+8-7)^{6-5+43^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1093678	$9*8-7*6/(5^{\wedge}(-4-3))*(2+1))$
-1001873	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4*3-2})^{-1}$	-1093822	$-9*8-7*6/(5^{\wedge}(-4-3))*(2+1))$
-1001877	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4*3+2})^{-1}$	-1093855	$-98/7*(6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))-21$
-1002160	$((9+8-7)^{6+5*432})^{-1}$	-1097577	$9*(8-7*((-6-5)^4*3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
-1002304	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5+43)^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1097721	$-9*(8+7*((-6-5)^4*3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
-1003125	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3-2)})^{-1}$	-1100385	$-9/8*((7-6*5)^4*43)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1003249	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5+4+3)^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1101528	$9*8*(765*4*(-3-2)+1)$
-1003600	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5*4*3)^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1102400	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5/4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$
-1003750	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4*3*2})^{-1}$	-1108710	$9/8*(7+(65+4)^{\wedge}3*(-2-1))$
-1004000	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3/2})^{-1}$	-1108992	$-9/(8*76)^{\wedge}(5-4-3)/(2+1)$
-1005432	$((9+8-7)^{6+5432})^{-1}$	-1112969	$(9-8)*(-7-6^{\wedge}5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1005625	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1115856	$(-9+8)*-7*6^{\wedge}5*(-43/2+1)$
-1007993	$(9-8)*7-6*(5*4)^{\wedge}3*21$	-1116225	$9*(8*7+65)*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-1007998	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3-2})^{-1}$	-1117200	$98*76*(-5-((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-1008002	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3+2})^{-1}$	-1117557	$((-9*8-7)+6)^*(5+4)^{\wedge}3*21$
-1009245	$((9+8-7)^{6+5*43^{\wedge}2})^{-1}$	-1127513	$(9-8)*7-6^{\wedge}5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1016000	$((9+8-7)^{6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3*2})^{-1}$	-1129310	$((-9/8-7)+6)*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
-1017450	$-9/8*((7-6*54)^3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1129440	$(-9+8-7^{\wedge}6)/5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1020000	$((9+8-7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4*32})^{-1}$	-1133993	$(-9+8)*-7*((6*5)^{\wedge}4/(-3-2)+1)$
-1026244	$((9+8-7)^{6+(54*3)^{\wedge}2})/-1$	-1136640	$(9/8*7+6)*-5*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
-1026425	$(9-8)*7-6^{\wedge}5*4*(32+1)$	-1140600	$((-9-8)-7)*((654/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1028659	$(9*8+7)/-6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2-1)$	-1140626	$((-9*8-7)+6)^5*5^{\wedge}(4*3/2)-1$
-1038230	$((-9-8)+7)*((6+5)^4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1142067	$(9+8*76)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)*(-2-1)$
-1039293	$(-9+8/-7*6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-1142547	$((9-8)*-7*(6^{\wedge}5-4-3))^*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1142550	$9/8 * ((7+6) * (-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2) - 1)$	-1310963	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) - 5 * 4^{\wedge}(3 * (2+1))$
-1143723	$((9-8) * 7 * (-6^{\wedge}5-4) - 3) * 21$	-1313811	$(-9-8) * ((7 * 6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-1146796	$98/7 * (6 - 5/4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1))$	-1314402	$(9/8 - 7) * (((-6-5) * 4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-1146964	$-98/7 * (6 - 5/-4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1))$	-1314928	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 + 54^{\wedge}3 * 2) * -1$
-1157462	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 + 54^{\wedge}3 - 2) * -1$	-1316981	$(9-87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))+3) * 2+1$
-1165074	$(9/((-8^{\wedge}7+6) * 5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-1316982	$(9-87^{\wedge}(-6+5)+4)+3) * 2^{\wedge}1$
-1165083	$(-9/((8^{\wedge}7+6) * 5-43))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-1316983	$(9-87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))+3) * 2-1$
-1165087	$(9/((-8^{\wedge}7-6) * 5+4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-1316993	$(9-87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4)) - 3) * 2+1$
-1166634	$987 * -6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3 * (-2 - 1))$	-1316994	$(9-87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4)) - 3) * 2/1$
-1175118	$(-9+8) * -7 * (6 - (5 * 4)^{\wedge}3) * 21$	-1316995	$(9-87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4)) - 3) * 2-1$
-1178340	$9 * ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / (-43 * 2 - 1)$	-1317017	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))+3) * 2+1$
-1178496	$9 * (8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5) - 4) * -32^{\wedge}1$	-1317018	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3) * 2^{\wedge}1$
-1179228	$9 * 8 * (7/6 * 5 - 4^{\wedge}(3 * 2+1))$	-1317019	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))+3) * 2-1$
-1180068	$-9 * 8 * (7/6 * 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3 * 2+1))$	-1317029	$(-9 - (87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))+3)) * 2+1$
-1183032	$9 * 8 * (-7 * 6 - (5+4^{\wedge}(3 * 2+1)))$	-1317030	$(-9-87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4) - 3) * 2^{\wedge}1$
-1184918	$98 * (76 - (5 * 4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-1317031	$(-9 - (87^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5-4))+3)) * 2-1$
-1185889	$((98 - (7+6) * 5)^{\wedge}4 - 32) * -1$	-1320150	$(9/(8 * ((7+6)^{\wedge}5 - 4+3)+2))^{\wedge}-1$
-1185915	$((98 - (7+6) * 5)^{\wedge}4 - 3 * 2) / -1$	-1333296	$((9+8) * (-7^{\wedge}6+5+4) / (3/2 * 1))$
-1185926	$((98 - (7+6) * 5)^{\wedge}4 + 3 + 2) * -1$	-1333606	$((9^{\wedge}8 - (7+6)^{\wedge}5) - 4) / -32 + 1$
-1185953	$((98 - (7+6) * 5)^{\wedge}4 + 32) * -1$	-1336304	$((9 - (8 - 7 - 6) * 5)^{\wedge}4 - 32) / -1$
-1186339	$(-9 - 8/7) * ((6 * (5+4+3))^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-1336341	$((9 - (8 - 7 - 6) * 5)^{\wedge}4 + 3 + 2) * -1$
-1188534	$9 - (8^{\wedge}7 + 6^{\wedge}(-5+4 * 3)) / 2 + 1$	-1336368	$((9 - (8 - 7 - 6) * 5)^{\wedge}4 + 32) * -1$
-1188535	$9 - (8^{\wedge}7 + 6^{\wedge}(-5+4 * 3)) / 2 * 1$	-1342176	$((-9 - 8^{\wedge}7 + 6) + 5) / ((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-1188536	$9 - (8^{\wedge}7 + 6^{\wedge}(-5+4 * 3)) / 2 - 1$	-1344551	$9 - 8/7^{\wedge}6 / (5^{\wedge}(-4+3) + 2^{\wedge}-1)$
-1188552	$(-9 + (-8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4 * 3)) / 2) + 1$	-1344569	$-9 - 8/7^{\wedge}6 / (5^{\wedge}(-4+3) + 2^{\wedge}-1)$
-1188553	$-9 - (8^{\wedge}7 + 6^{\wedge}(-5+4 * 3)) / 2 * 1$	-1346675	$(-9+8/7) * ((6 * (5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-1188554	$(-9 + (-8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5+4 * 3)) / 2) - 1$	-1349995	$(9/((-8-7) * ((6 * 5)^{\wedge}4 - 3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-1195730	$((9 * (8-7))^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 * 3^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-1350005	$(9/((-8-7) * ((6 * 5)^{\wedge}4 + 3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-1199765	$(-9+8) * 7 * ((6 * (5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-1350048	$98 * 7 * ((-6^{\wedge}5/4 - 3) - 21)$
-1199814	$-98 * (76 + (5 * 4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-1378944	$9 * 8 * -76 * ((5+4+3) * 21)$
-1203750	$(-9+8)^{\wedge}7 * 6 * 5^{\wedge}4 * 321$	-1381725	$((9+8) / 7 - 6) * ((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-1203759	$(-9^{\wedge}(8-7) - 6 * 5^{\wedge}4 * 321)$	-1384128	$9 * (-8 - 76 - 5) * (4 * 3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-1203872	$(-9-8) * (7 * 6^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}(3 * 2+1))$	-1387200	$(98 * 7 - 6)^{\wedge}(-5 - (-4 - 3)) * (-2 - 1)$
-1208160	$9 * -8 * (7^{\wedge}(6-5+4) - 3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-1387464	$(-9/((8 - ((7-65) * 4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-1209617	$-9 - 8 * (7 * 6 * (5 * 4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-1392419	$(9+8) * (7+6-5/4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1))$
-1209625	$(-9+8 * 7 * -6^{\wedge}5) * ((4/3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-1392623	$(9+8) * (7-6-5/4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1))$
-1209735	$-9 * (8 * ((7^{\wedge}(6-5+4) - 3) - 2) - 1)$	-1392657	$(-9-8) * (7-6-5/-4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1))$
-1209753	$9 * (8 * ((-7^{\wedge}(6-5+4) + 3) + 2) - 1)$	-1392861	$(-9-8) * (7+6-5/-4^{\wedge}(-3 * 2 - 1))$
-1210081	$(-9-8 - ((76-5)^{\wedge}4 + 3)) / 21$	-1395297	$-9 * ((8 * 76 - 5^{\wedge}(4+3)) * -2 - 1)$
-1210455	$-9 * (8 * ((7^{\wedge}(6-5+4) + 3) + 2) - 1)$	-1397751	$9 - 8^{\wedge}7 / 6 * (5 - (4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2) + 1))$
-1210473	$9 * -8 * ((7^{\wedge}(6-5+4) + 3) + 2) - 1$	-1397769	$-9 - 8^{\wedge}7 / 6 * (5 - (4^{\wedge}(-3 - 2) + 1))$
-1212048	$9 * -8 * (7^{\wedge}(6-5+4) + 3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-1398007	$9+8^{\wedge}7 / -6 * ((5-4^{\wedge}(3 * 2 - 2)) - 1)$
-1212732	$9 * 8 * (7/6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1398025	$-9+8^{\wedge}7 / -6 * ((5-4^{\wedge}(3 * 2 - 2)) - 1)$
-1233741	$(-9-8) * ((7 * 6^{\wedge}5 * 4/3 - 2) - 1)$	-1398041	$(-9/(8^{\wedge}7 * 6 - 543))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-1233843	$(-9-8) * ((7 * 6^{\wedge}5 * 4/3 + 2) + 1)$	-1398045	$(9 - 8^{\wedge}7 / 6 + 5) * 4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-1243136	$(9/8 - 7 * (6+5)) * 4^{\wedge}(3 * 2+1)$	-1398127	$((-9 - 8^{\wedge}7) / 6 - 5) * 4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-1245564	$(-9+8) * 76 * (5+4^{\wedge}(3 * 2+1))$	-1398157	$(-9 - (8^{\wedge}7 / 6 + 5)) * 4 + 3^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-1248129	$(-9/((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 54^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-1403649	$-9/8 * ((7/((-6^{\wedge}5 - 43))^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-1254825	$9 * (-8-7) * 65 * ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-1406342	$-9 * (8 + (7/6 + 5^{\wedge}(4+3)) * 2) + 1$
-1254916	$(9/(-8 * 7^{\wedge}6 + 5) / (4 * 3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-1406344	$-9 * (8 + (7/6 + 5^{\wedge}(4+3)) * 2) - 1$
-1254976	$(9/(8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5)) / (-4 * 3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-1411128	$-9 * 8 * ((7 * (-6 - 54) / 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-1257389	$(-9/((8 + (7 - 65)^{\wedge}4) - 3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-1411443	$9 * (((8 - 7^{\wedge}6) + 5) * 4/3 + 21)$
-1262139	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4^{\wedge}3 * 2) * -1$	-1411572	$9 * 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 / (-5 - 4 + 3) + 2) + 1)$
-1265304	$(-9 * (8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / (-5+4) + 321$	-1412004	$9 * 8 * ((-7^{\wedge}6 / (5+4-3) - 2) - 1)$
-1265696	$-9 * (8 + (7 * 6 * (-5 - 4) + 3)^{\wedge}2) + 1$	-1412133	$-9 * (((8 + 7^{\wedge}6) + 5) * 4/3 + 21)$
-1265946	$(-9 * (8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / (-5+4) - 321$	-1423823	$(9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4) * (3/2 - 1)$
-1272991	$(9 * 8 * ((-7 - 6)^{\wedge}5 + 4) - 3) / 21$	-1423832	$(9 + ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4) * (-3/2 + 1)$
-1273152	$9 * 8 * ((-7 - 6)^{\wedge}5 - 43) / 21$	-1423839	$(-9 + (((8+7)^{\wedge}6 - 5) / -4 - 3) / 2) - 1$
-1277181	$-9 * ((876 * 54 * 3 - 2) - 1)$	-1436592	$(98 * 7 + 6)^{\wedge}(-5 - (-4 - 3)) * (-2 - 1)$
-1277235	$9 * ((-876 * 54 * 3 - 2) - 1)$	-1436976	$-9 * (8 * 7 * -6 + (5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1))$
-1283121	$(-9/((8+7)^{\wedge}6 + 54^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-1442430	$(9 - 8 * 7) * 6 * -5 * (-4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) + 1)$
-1294849	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6 + 543^{\wedge}2) * -1$	-1443024	$9 * (8 * 7 * -6 - (5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 + 2 - 1))$
-1295993	$(9-8) * 7 - 6 * (5 * 4 * 3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1443793	$(9 - 8 * 7) * (6 * 5 * 4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) - 1)$
-1305663	$9 - 8 * ((7 * (6^{\wedge}5 - 4) * 3 - 2) - 1)$	-1443887	$(-9 + 8 * 7) * (6 * 5 * -4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) - 1)$
-1305681	$-9 - 8 * ((7 * (6^{\wedge}5 - 4) * 3 - 2) - 1)$	-1445250	$(9 - 8 * 7) * 6 * 5 * (4^{\wedge}(3 + 2) + 1)$
-1305711	$9 - 8 * ((7 * (6^{\wedge}5 - 4) * 3 + 2) + 1)$	-1449182	$(-9 + 8) * 7 * ((65 * (4 + 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-1305729	$-9 - 8 * ((7 * (6^{\wedge}5 - 4) * 3 + 2) + 1)$	-1450000	$((-9 - 8) + 7)^{\wedge}6 * (-5/4 - (3 + 2)^{\wedge}-1)$
-1307007	$9 - 8 * ((7 * (6^{\wedge}5 + 4) * 3 - 2) - 1)$	-1457964	$-9 * ((8 + 7 - (6 * 5)^{\wedge}4) / (-3 - 2) - 1)$
-1307025	$-9 - 8 * ((7 * (6^{\wedge}5 + 4) * 3 - 2) - 1)$	-1458036	$9 * ((8 + 7 + (6 * 5)^{\wedge}4) / (-3 - 2) - 1)$
-1307055	$9 + 8 * ((7 * (6^{\wedge}5 + 4) * 3 - 2) - 1)$	-1464320	$(9/8 + 7) * ((-6 - 5) * 4^{\wedge}(3 * 2 + 1))$
-1307073	$-9 + 8 * ((7 * (6^{\wedge}5 + 4) * 3 - 2) - 1)$	-1479108	$((-9 * 8 - 7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) + 3) * (2 + 1)$
-1310477	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) - 5 * 4^{\wedge}(3 * (2+1))$	-1479126	$((-9 * 8 - 7)^{\wedge}(-6 - (-5 - 4)) - 3) * (2 + 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1484366	$9+(8/(76^*-5^\wedge(4+3)*2))^\wedge-1$	-1742727	$(-9+8)*7*((-6^\wedge5-4)*-32+1)$
-1484384	$-9+(8/(76^*-5^\wedge(4+3)*2))^\wedge-1$	-1747618	$9-8^\wedge7/6*(5+4^\wedge(-3^\wedge2-1))$
-1486422	$987*6*(5-4^\wedge(3+2-1))$	-1747636	$-9-8^\wedge7/6*(5+4^\wedge(-3^\wedge2-1))$
-1491000	$(-9+8^\wedge(-7+6))*5*(5*4)^\wedge3*21$	-1747657	$-9-8^\wedge7/6*(5+4^\wedge(-3^\wedge2-1))$
-1494675	$((9*8+7)-6)*5*(-4^\wedge(3*2)+1)$	-1757600	$(((-9-8)+7)*(65*4)^\wedge-3)^\wedge(-2+1)$
-1495405	$((-9*8-7)+6)*5*(4^\wedge(3*2)+1)$	-1757745	$9*(-8-7)/6*(5^\wedge(4+3)-2-1)$
-1495917	$-9-(8/76*54^\wedge-3)^\wedge(-2+1)$	-1757880	$9*(8+7)/6*(-5^\wedge(4+3)-2-1)$
-1500593	$((9+8+7+6+5)^\wedge4-32)*-1$	-1757943	$9-8*7*6^\wedge5*(4+3^\wedge(-2-1))$
-1500657	$((9+8+7+6+5)^\wedge4+32)*-1$	-1757961	$-9-8*7*6^\wedge5*(4+3^\wedge(-2-1))$
-1506696	$-9/((8+7)+6)*((5^\wedge4*3)^\wedge2-1)$	-1770725	$(9/8-7)*((6+5^\wedge4)^\wedge2-1)$
-1511853	$(-9+8)*7*((6+5^\wedge4)^\wedge3-21)$	-1799365	$(-9/((8-(7-65*4)^\wedge3))^\wedge(-2+1)$
-1512702	$-9*(8+7^\wedge6/(5^\wedge(-4+3)+2^\wedge-1))$	-1805400	$9*8*(7*6^\wedge5-4^\wedge3(2+1))$
-1522094	$(9/87/(6-5^\wedge4)^\wedge)^\wedge(-2+1)$	-1811187	$(9*87-6)^\wedge(-5-(-4-3))*(-2-1)$
-1522210	$(-9/87/(6+5^\wedge4)^\wedge)^\wedge(-2+1)$	-1812857	$((9-8*7)*(6*5)^\wedge4+3)/21$
-1533000	$(-9-8^\wedge(-7+6))*5*(5*4)^\wedge3*21$	-1817790	$(-9/8-7)*(((-6-5)*43)^\wedge2-1)$
-1534734	$(9-876^\wedge((-5+4)+3))/2^\wedge-1$	-1846080	$-9/8*((7*(-65+4)*3)^\wedge2-1)$
-1534770	$(-9-876^\wedge((-5+4)+3))/2^\wedge-1$	-1848327	$9*(8*7/6+(5-4^\wedge3)^\wedge(2+1))$
-1540944	$9*8*((-6^\wedge5/4-3)-21)$	-1860860	$(-9+8)*(-7+(6*5*4+3)^\wedge(2+1))$
-1554768	$9*8*((7-6/(5*4*3)^\wedge-2)-1)$	-1864132	$(-9/((8^\wedge(7+6-5)+4)-32))^\wedge-1$
-1556860	$(-9+8)*-7*6*5*(-4^\wedge(3*2)-1)$	-1867563	$(9*87+6)^\wedge(-5-(-4-3))*(-2-1)$
-1565190	$9*(8-7*6)*-5*(-4^\wedge(3+2)+1)$	-1869448	$98*76*(5-4^\wedge(3+2-1))$
-1566096	$(-9+8)*7*(((-6-5)*43)^\wedge2-1)$	-1874496	$9*8*(7-(6*5^\wedge(4+3)-2)/2)^\wedge-1$
-1568250	$9*(8-7*6)*5*(4^\wedge(3+2)+1)$	-1874688	$9*8*(7+6-5^\wedge(4+3))/2+1$
-1572827	$(9-8)*7+6*(5-4^\wedge(3*(2+1)))$	-1874972	$9*8*(-7/6+5^\wedge(4+3))/(-2-1)$
-1577655	$-9*((8*7)^\wedge((-6+5)+4)-321)$	-1874976	$9*8*(7-(6+5^\wedge(4+3)))/2+1$
-1580223	$9*(-8*7)^\wedge((-6+5)+4)+321$	-1875024	$9*8*(7-(6-5^\wedge(4+3)))/(-2-1)$
-1580498	$9*(((-8*7)^\wedge(-6+5+4)+3)+2)+1$	-1875312	$9*8*(7+6+5^\wedge(4+3))/(-2-1)$
-1580500	$9*(((-8*7)^\wedge(-6+5+4)+3)+2)-1$	-1875504	$9*-8*(7+(6*5^\wedge(4-3)/2)^\wedge-1)$
-1580588	$9*(((-8*7)^\wedge(-6+5+4)-3)-2)+1$	-1875852	$(9*(8*7-6^\wedge5)+4)*3^\wedge(2+1)$
-1580590	$9*(((-8*7)^\wedge(-6+5+4)-3)-2)-1$	-1876068	$(-9*(8*7-6^\wedge5)+4)*-3^\wedge(2+1)$
-1580865	$9*(-8*7)^\wedge((-6+5)+4)-321$	-1889853	$(9-8)*-7*((6*5)^\wedge4/3-21)$
-1583433	$9*((-8*7)^\wedge((-6+5)+4)-321)$	-1890090	$-9*((8*7*6*5^\wedge4+3^\wedge2)+1)$
-1583992	$(-9-8)*76*(5*(4+3)^\wedge2+1)$	-1898000	$((9+8)/7-6)*((5+4)^\wedge(3*2)-1)$
-1586899	$(9+8)^\wedge(-7-(-6-5))*(-4*(3+2)+1)$	-1903068	$(-9*(8*7+6^\wedge5)+4)*3^\wedge(2+1)$
-1607970	$9+(-8-7^\wedge6)*((-5-4/3)*-2+1)$	-1903284	$(9*(8*7+6^\wedge5)+4)*-3^\wedge(2+1)$
-1607988	$-9+(-8-7^\wedge6)*((-5-4/3)*-2+1)$	-1910034	$-9/8*((7+6^\wedge5(-4-3))^\wedge2-1)$
-1609209	$(-98-7^\wedge6)*((-5-4/3)*-2+1)$	-1917000	$(-9+8^\wedge(-7+6))*5*(5*4*3)^\wedge(2+1)$
-1613400	$9*-8*(7^\wedge6/(5+4^\wedge(-3+2)))-1$	-1925120	$(-9-87/6)*5/4^\wedge(-3*2-1)$
-1613544	$9*8*(-7^\wedge6/(5+4^\wedge(-3+2)))-1$	-1941408	$(-9+8)*7*6*((5*43)^\wedge2-1)$
-1622400	$((-9-8)-7)*(65*4)^\wedge((3-2)+1)$	-1942416	$987*((-6^\wedge5/4-3)-21)$
-1623074	$((98*(7+6))^\wedge((-5+4)+3)-2)*-1$	-1943442	$9*(8*7+6-(5*4*3)^\wedge(2+1))$
-1623078	$((98*(7+6))^\wedge((-5+4)+3)-2)/-1$	-1944558	$-9*(8*7+6+(5*4*3)^\wedge(2+1))$
-1627224	$(9-((8+7)^\wedge6-5^\wedge4)*3)/21$	-1946126	$(-9-8)*-7*(6*5-4^\wedge(3*2+1))$
-1628907	$(9*(8*7+6)-5^\wedge(4+3))*21$	-1965200	$(-9-8)*(-7^\wedge((-6+5)+4)+3)^\wedge2/1$
-1630314	$-9/8*7*((65*(4+3))^\wedge2-1)$	-1965945	$9*(8+7)-6*5*4^\wedge(3^\wedge2-1)$
-1634116	$9+(8+7^\wedge6)*-5*((4/3)^\wedge2+1)$	-1966215	$-9*(8+7)-6*5*4^\wedge(3^\wedge2-1)$
-1634134	$-9+(8+7^\wedge6)*-5*((4/3)^\wedge2+1)$	-1975461	$(9-87^\wedge(-6-(-5-4)))^3+21$
-1636821	$(((-9+8)*7)^\wedge6*5-4^\wedge(3^\wedge2+1))$	-1975480	$(9-87^\wedge(-6+5+4))^3+2*1$
-1640631	$(-9+8)^\wedge7*6-5^\wedge(4+3)*21$	-1975481	$(9-87^\wedge((-6+5)+4))^3+2-1$
-1646235	$(9-87^\wedge(-6+5+4))*3/2+1$	-1975483	$(9-87^\wedge((-6+5)+4))^3-(-2-1)$
-1646280	$(-9-87^\wedge(-6+5+4))*3/2+1$	-1975533	$(-9-87^\wedge((-6+5)+4))^3+2+1$
-1652343	$(-9*(8*7+6)-5^\wedge(4+3))*21$	-1975534	$(-9-87^\wedge(-6-(-5-4)))^3+2^\wedge1$
-1660134	$-987*((6-5*(-4-3))^\wedge2+1)$	-1975535	$(-9-87^\wedge((-6+5)+4))^3+2-1$
-1665918	$(9/(-8*((7+6*5)^\wedge4-3)+2))^\wedge-1$	-1975537	$(-9-87^\wedge((-6+5)+4))^3-(-2-1)$
-1673955	$(-9-((8+(7*(6+5))^\wedge4)-3))/21$	-1975538	$(-9-87^\wedge(-6+5+4))^3-2*1$
-1685096	$((-9-8)*7)^\wedge(-6-(-5-4))+3*21$	-1975545	$(-9-87^\wedge(-6+5+4)-3)*(2+1)$
-1685132	$((-9-8)*7)^\wedge(-6+5+4)+3^\wedge(2+1)$	-1975557	$(-9-87^\wedge(-6-(-5-4)))^3-21$
-1685141	$((-9-8)*7)^\wedge(-6+5+4)-(3-21)$	-1978884	$9*876*(5-4^\wedge(3+2-1))$
-1685177	$((-9-8)*7)^\wedge(-6+5+4)+3-21$	-1981556	$(-9-(8/7)^\wedge-6)/5*4^\wedge(3^\wedge2+1)$
-1685183	$((-9-8)*7)^\wedge(-6+5+4)-3-21$	-1994620	$(9-8)*-76*((5^\wedge4*3)^\wedge2+1)$
-1685186	$((-9-8)*7)^\wedge(-6+5+4)-3^\wedge(2+1)$	-1994850	$(9*-8+7)*6*5*(4^\wedge(3+2)-1)$
-1692000	$(-9+8*7)/6*(5*(5*4*3)^\wedge(2+1))$	-1999804	$((-9-8)*(-7^\wedge6+5)-4*(3)^\wedge2)*-1$
-1694162	$(9/8-7)*((6-5^\wedge4)^\wedge2-1)$	-2018576	$(-9+8)*7*((6-5^\wedge4)^\wedge2-1)$
-1697190	$(-9+8/7)*6+(5*4*3)^\wedge(2+1))$	-2024631	$9-8/7*((6+5)^\wedge(4*3/2)-1)$
-1713600	$(-9-8)*7*(6*5*4)^\wedge(3-2+1)$	-2024649	$-9-8/7*((6+5)^\wedge(4*3/2)-1)$
-1714176	$9*8^\wedge7/(6+5)*4^\wedge(-3-2)-1$	-2024993	$(9-8)*7+(6*5)^\wedge4*(-3/2-1)$
-1725687	$9-8*7*6^\wedge5*(4-3^\wedge(-2-1))$	-2035172	$(-9-8)*7^\wedge((-6+5)+4)+3)^\wedge2/1$
-1725705	$-9-8*7*6^\wedge5*(4-3^\wedge(-2-1))$	-2035703	$9-8^\wedge7*(6*5*-4^\wedge(-3-2)+1)$
-1727972	$(9-8)*7-(6*5*4)^\wedge3+21$	-2035721	$-9-8^\wedge7*(6*5*-4^\wedge(-3-2)+1)$
-1730430	$9*-87*((6+5)^\wedge4+3)^\wedge2+1$	-2038093	$9-8^\wedge7+(6/5)^\wedge4^\wedge(-3-2)+1$
-1738435	$(-9-8/7)*((6*(5+4^\wedge3))^\wedge2-1)$	-2038095	$9-8^\wedge7+(6/5)^\wedge4^\wedge(-3-2)-1$
-1739264	$9*(-8^\wedge7-6^\wedge(5+4))/3^\wedge21$	-2038111	$(-9-8^\wedge7-(-6/5)^\wedge4)^\wedge(-3-2)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2038113	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7-(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1$	-2309667	$-9/(8+7)^{*}((654*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2049746	$98+((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$	-2321301	$9/(8-7)-6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2049772	$9*8+((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$	-2342990	$(-9/8-7)^{*}((6-543)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2049782	$((9^{\wedge}8-(7-(6-5)^{\wedge}4)-3)/-21)$	-2349675	$(9+876)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)^{*}(-2-1)$
-2049827	$9+8+((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$	-2370240	$-9876*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2049845	$(-9+8)+((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$	-2373525	$-9/8*7*((6+543)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2049861	$(-9-8)+((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$	-2373534	$9/8*(-7/(6+543)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2049916	$-9*8+((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$	-2385203	$(9-8)^{*}7-6*5/43^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-2049942	$-98+((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$	-2420104	$(9*8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4)/(-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-2059434	$-9/8*((7*65+4)^{*}3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-2420312	$(9*8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4)/(-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-2063908	$(9-8)^{*}7*((6-543)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2424510	$(9*8+7)^{*}-6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-2063978	$(9-8)^{*}-7*((6+543)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2429250	$(9*8+7)^{*}6*5*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-2085130	$((9-8+7+6*5)^{\wedge}4-3*2)/-1$	-2429550	$9*((-87+(6*5)^{\wedge}4)/-3+21)$
-2085131	$((9-8+7+6*5)^{\wedge}4-3-2)^{*}-1$	-2430450	$9*((-87-(6*5)^{\wedge}4)/3-21)$
-2085141	$((9-8+7+6*5)^{\wedge}4+3+2)^{*}-1$	-2433015	$-9*(((-8-7)+65)^{*}4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
-2085142	$((9-8+7+6*5)^{\wedge}4+3*2)/-1$	-2433033	$-9*(((-8-7)+65)/4^{\wedge}(3*-2)+1)$
-2086903	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6-5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$	-2448875	$(-9/8-7)^{*}((6+543)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2086921	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6-5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$	-2452167	$-9*((87*6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)-21)$
-2088985	$-9-8*((7*(6*5+43))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-2452335	$-9*(87*6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+21$
-2089787	$9-(8^{\wedge}7-6*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1))$	-2452353	$-9/(87*6)^{\wedge}((-5-4)-3)+2+1$
-2089805	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7-6*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1))$	-2452359	$-9/(87*6)^{\wedge}((-5-4)-3)-(-2+1)$
-2091294	$9*(-8-((7*6+5)^{\wedge}4-3)/21)$	-2452377	$-9*(87*6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)-21$
-2101707	$(9*(87+6))^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))^*(-2-1)$	-2452545	$-9*((87*6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+21)$
-2103614	$(9+8)*(((7-6)^{\wedge}5+4)/3+21)$	-2457441	$(((-9+8)^{*}7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4-3)^{*}-21$
-2104008	$((9+8)^{*}(7+6)^{\wedge}5+43)/(-2-1)$	-2457567	$((9-8)^{*}7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4-3))^*-21$
-2104328	$(-9-8)*(((7+6)^{\wedge}5-4)/3+21)$	-2459226	$((-9+8)^{*}7^{\wedge}6+543)^{*}21$
-2104499	$9-8^{\wedge}7-6*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-2460054	$(-9*(8+7))^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+321$
-2104517	$-9-8^{\wedge}7-6*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-2460343	$(-9*(8+7))^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+32/1$
-2107383	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1))$	-2460348	$(-9*(8+7))^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-2107401	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1))$	-2460402	$(-9*(8+7))^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-2108457	$9*(8-7*6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*(-2-1)$	-2460407	$((-9*(8+7))^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)-32)/1$
-2109291	$9*(8*7/6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*(2+1)$	-2466114	$((-9+8)^{*}7^{\wedge}6+5*43)^{*}21$
-2109459	$9*(8*-7/6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*(2+1)$	-2467227	$((-9+8)^{*}7^{\wedge}6+54*3)^{*}21$
-2109800	$(-9+8)^{*}7*((6+543)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2469432	$((-9+8)^{*}7^{\wedge}6+54+3)^{*}21$
-2110293	$9*(8-7*6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*(2+1)$	-2469558	$((-9+8)^{*}7^{\wedge}6+54-3)^{*}21$
-2121405	$(-9+8/7)*((6*5)^{\wedge}4/3-2-1)$	-2469621	$((-9+8)^{*}7^{\wedge}6+5+43)^{*}21$
-2126241	$9-(8/7*(6*5)^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-2471637	$((-9+8)^{*}7^{\wedge}6-5)-43)^{*}21$
-2126259	$-9-(8/7*(6*5)^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-2471826	$((-9+8)^{*}7^{\wedge}6-54-3)^{*}21$
-2133144	$-9/8*((7*65+4)^{*}3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-2474031	$((-9+8)^{*}7^{\wedge}6-54*3)^{*}21$
-2133334	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7)^{*}6*((-5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-2475144	$((-9+8)^{*}7^{\wedge}6-5*43)^{*}21$
-2137576	$98*-76*((5+4)^{*}32-1)$	-2483691	$((-9+8)^{*}7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{*}21$
-2151786	$(9-8)^{*}-7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4-3)^{*}21$	-2484566	$(9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3+2))^*-1$
-2156191	$9-8^{\wedge}7-(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1$	-2489825	$(9/8-7)^{*}((654-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2156193	$9-8^{\wedge}7-(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1$	-2491231	$(-98/(7+6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-2156209	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7+(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1$	-2500371	$-9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/((43-2)-1)$
-2156211	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7+(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1$	-2500389	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/((-43+2)-1)$
-2177294	$98/7*(6^{\wedge}5*4*(-3-2)-1)$	-2514778	$(9/((-8-((7-65)^{\wedge}4-3))^2))^{\wedge}-1$
-2180220	$((9-8*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3)^{*}21$	-2519031	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6/5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
-2180346	$((9-8*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)-3)^{*}21$	-2519049	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*6/5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
-2181270	$-987*(((-6-5)^{*}4-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-2523136	$98/7*((-6-5)/4)^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-2190918	$(-9-8/7)^{*}(6+(5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-2534976	$(9-(8+7))^{\wedge}6*(-54-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-2197250	$9/8*(7+6-5^{\wedge}(4-(-3-2)))$	-2535932	$(9/8-7)^{*}((654+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2197252	$9/8*(7+6-5^{\wedge}(4-(-3-2)))-1$	-2537712	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7-6)/((5/(4*3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2210112	$(98*(-7-6)-5)^{*}(4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-2546515	$(-9-8)/-7*(6+5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-2215269	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3+2))/-1$	-2555859	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7/6+5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-2216420	$(-9/(8^{\wedge}7+65^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-2555949	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7/6+5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-2221183	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-2559968	$((98+7-65)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-2244608	$(9*(87*(-7-6)*5)^{*}-4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$	-2560032	$((98+7-65)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-2253420	$(-9/8-7)^{*}6*((5*43)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2563185	$(9/(-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5)+4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-2262708	$9*-876*((5+4)^{*}32-1)$	-2569854	$-98*(7*6*5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-2263662	$-9/(8*7)^{*}((6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2574936	$9*8*7*(6-5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
-2265625	$(9/(87*(-6)^{*}5^{\wedge}(-4-3))^2)^{\wedge}-1$	-2575146	$-98*(7*6*5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-2266029	$((9-8)/7-6)^{*}((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2577447	$9*(8*7*(6-5*4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
-2270898	$-9/8*7*((6-543)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2577465	$9*(8*7*(6-5*4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1)$
-2270907	$9/8*(-7*(6-543)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2579976	$9*8*-7*(-6-5*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
-2274048	$-987/(6-54)^{\wedge}((-3+2)-1)$	-2580984	$9*-8*-7*(-6-5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
-2277376	$((-9-(8+7))^*6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$	-2586024	$9*-8*7*(6-5*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$
-2293718	$(-9+8)^*-7*(6-5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-2633976	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*(-3-2+1)$
-2293802	$(-9+8)^*7*(6-5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-2634048	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*(3+2-1)$
-2299416	$(-9+8)^*7*((65+4)^{\wedge}3-21)$	-2670592	$(-98+(-7-6)^*5)/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-2304729	$(9-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-2687386	$((9*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4)/(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2304792	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-2696340	$9*((-8^{\wedge}7+6)-5)/(4+3)-2-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2708153	$(9-8)^{*7} * (6 - (-5^4+3)^2-1)$	-2966600	$(-9+8)^{*7} * ((654-3)^2-1)$
-2708195	$((-9+8)^7-6) * ((5^4-3)^2+1)$	-2972167	$-9 * ((-8 * (7+65)+4/3)^2-1)$
-2719990	$98^{*7} * 65 * ((-4^4+3)+1)$	-2981879	$9-8^7 * (6-5+(4/3)^{-2}-1)$
-2722717	$9+8 - (7^6)^5 / ((4+3)^2-1)$	-2981897	$-9-8^7 * (6-5+(4/3)^{-2}-1)$
-2722751	$(-9-8) - (7^6)^5 / ((4+3)^2-1)$	-2990080	$(-9-8^7-7+6) * 5^4 * (3^2-1)$
-2733125	$(9-8) / -7 * ((6/(5+4)^{-3})^2-1)$	-2997000	$(9/8^* - 7 - 6) * (5^4 * 3)^2 + 1$
-2738541	$(-9-8/7) * ((6^5)^4/3-2-1)$	-3013392	$(-9+8) / 7^6 * ((5^4 * 3)^2-1)$
-2744820	$9/8 * (((7^6+5)^4-3) / -2-1)$	-3021536	$(-9+8)^{*7} * ((654+3)^2-1)$
-2752230	$9^*8-7^*-6^*(5-4^4(3^2-1))$	-3039795	$(-9+8/7) * ((-6+5^4+3)^2-1)$
-2752302	$(-9+8)^{*7} * -6^*(5-4^4(3^2-1))$	-3043096	$98 * (((7-6^5)^4+3)+21)$
-2752374	$-9^*8-7^*-6^*(5-4^4(3^2-1))$	-3043684	$98 * ((-7+6^5)^* - 4 - 3 + 21)$
-2752650	$9^*8-7^*6^*(5+4^4(3^2-1))$	-3047517	$9^*(8^*7^*-6+5)^*(4^4(3+2)-1)$
-2752722	$(-9+8)^{*7} * 6^*(5+4^4(3^2-1))$	-3052700	$-98 * ((-7-6^5)^* - 4 - 3 + 21)$
-2752794	$(9-8-7^*6^*(5+4^4(3^2-1)))$	-3053288	$-98 * (((7+6^5)^4+3)+21)$
-2760653	$(-9+8)^* - 7^*(6 - (5^4+3)^2-1)$	-3053475	$-9^*(8^*7^*-6+5)^*(-4^4(3+2)-1)$
-2763441	$9+(-8/7-6)^*((-5^4+3)^2-1)$	-3071027	$(9/8-7)^*((6-(5+4)^3)^2-1)$
-2763459	$-9+(-8/7-6)^*((-5^4+3)^2-1)$	-3089790	$(-9+8/7)^*6^*(5+4^4(3^2-1))$
-2777088	$(98/6+5)^* - 4^4(3^2+1)$	-3103230	$(9/(8^*7)-6)^*((5+4)^4(3^2)-1)$
-2782787	$(9-8)^* - 7^*(6+5^4 * 43^2(2+1))$	-3104595	$9^*87^*65^*((-4^4+3)+1)$
-2789976	$((9^*(8-7))^6-5)/-4+3)^*21$	-3112720	$((9-8)/7-6)^*((5+4)^4(3^2)-1)$
-2790102	$((9^*(8-7))^6-5)/4+3)^* - 21$	-3122257	$(9/8-7)^*((6+(5+4)^4(3^2))+1)$
-2809692	$9^*8^*(76-5^4(4+3))/2+1$	-3124980	$(98/7+6)^*((-5^4(4+3)^2+1)$
-2809836	$9^*8^*((76-5^4(4+3))/2-1)$	-3125020	$(-98/7-6)^*(5^4(4+3)^2+1)$
-2810695	$(9/(8+7^6))/(-5^4 * 43)^{-2+1}$	-3130368	$9^*8^7/7-6^*(5^4 * 4^4(-3-2)+1)$
-2811708	$9^*8^*(7 - (-6+5^4(4+3))/2+1)$	-3136158	$-9^*((-8+7)+6)^*(54+3^2-2-1)$
-2811852	$9^*8^*(7 - (-6+5^4(4+3))/2+1)$	-3139587	$-9^*(8^*7^*6+5)^*(4^4(3+2)-1)$
-2812104	$9^* - 8^*((-7-6+5^4(4+3))/2+1)$	-3149760	$((9^4-7)+6)/((-5-4/3)^2-1)$
-2812140	$9^*8^*(7+(-6-5^4(4+3))/2+1)$	-3155544	$9^*87654^*((-3-2)+1)$
-2812284	$9^*8^*(7 - ((6+5^4(4+3))/2+1))$	-3161081	$(9/(8^*-7))^4(6-5-4+3)^2+1$
-2812449	$9^*8^*(7/6-5^4(4+3))/2+1$	-3161082	$(9/(8^*-7))^4(6-5-4+3)/2^4-1$
-2812467	$-9^*((-8^*(7/6-5^4(4+3))/2+1)$	-3161083	$(9/(8^*-7))^4(6-5-4+3)^2-1$
-2812533	$9^*((-8^*(7/6+5^4(4+3))/2+1)$	-3161093	$(-9/(8^*7))^4(6-5-4-3)^2+1$
-2812551	$-9^*(8^*(7/6+5^4(4+3))/2+1)$	-3161094	$(9/(8^*7))^4(6-5-4+3)^*-2^2+1$
-2812716	$-9^*8^*(7 - ((6-5^4(4+3))/2+1))$	-3161095	$(-9/(8^*7))^4(6-5-4-3)^2-1$
-2812860	$9^* - 8^*(7+(-6+5^4(4+3))/2+1)$	-3173816	$(9/8-7)^*((6+(5+4)^3)^2-1)$
-2812896	$9^*8^*((-7-6-5^4(4+3))/2+1)$	-3175065	$((-9+8)^*7^6+54)^*3^4(2+1)$
-2813040	$9^*8^*((-7-6-5^4(4+3))/2-1)$	-3175587	$(-9/87^*(65+4)^{-3})^4(-2+1)$
-2813148	$9^* - 8^*(7 - ((-6-5^4(4+3))/2+1))$	-3182085	$-9^*((-8+7)+6)^*(54-3^4-2^4)$
-2813292	$9^* - 8^*(7 - (-6-5^4(4+3))/2+1)$	-3188630	$((9+8)-7)-6^*((5+4)^4(3^2)-1)$
-2813699	$(-9+8)^{*7} * ((6+5^4+3)^2+1)$	-3188634	$(-9+8)+7-6^*((5+4)^4(3^2)-1)$
-2815164	$9^*8^*((-76-5^4(4+3))/2+1)$	-3188658	$((9-8)-7-6^*((5+4)^4(3^2)+1))$
-2815308	$9^*8^*((-76-5^4(4+3))/2-1)$	-3188662	$(-9-8)+7-6^*((5+4)^4(3^2)+1)$
-2834345	$((-9-8-7+6)^5+4)^3/2+1$	-3195207	$-9^*((-8+7)+6)^*(54+3^4-2^4)$
-2844216	$9^* - 8^*(7^6-5^4(4+3)-21)$	-3199870	$(9^*(8+7)-6) - (5^4)^4(3+2)+1$
-2847240	$9^* - 8^*(7^6-5^4(4+3)-21))$	-3200130	$9^*((-8-7)+6) - ((5^4)^4(3+2)+1)$
-2847583	$9 - ((8+7)^6-5)/4+3^*21$	-3203541	$9^*(8^*7^*-6^5+4^4+3^2+1)$
-2847601	$-9 + ((8+7)^6-5) / -4+3^*21$	-3203611	$(-9^*((8+7)^6-5) - 4) / 32+1$
-2847614	$9 + ((8+7)^6-5) / -4+3^2+1$	-3211488	$(-9+8)^* - 7^6 * 6^5 * (4-3^*21)$
-2847628	$9 + ((8+7)^6-5) / -4-3+21$	-3218513	$(9-8^*7)^4(-6+5+4)^*(32-1)$
-2847631	$-9 - ((8+7)^6-5) / 4+3^2+1$	-3236868	$(9^*87 - (6^5)^4)^4 * ((3+2)-1)$
-2847632	$-9 + ((8+7)^6-5) / -4+3^2+1$	-3237256	$(98^*7 - (6^5)^4)^4 * ((3+2)-1)$
-2847677	$9 + ((8+7)^6-5) / -4-3^2+1$	-3239874	$98 + (-7 + (6^5)^4)^4 * ((-3-2)+1)$
-2847678	$9 + ((8+7)^6-5) / -4-3^2/1$	-3239930	$98 + (-7 - (6^5)^4)^4 * (3+2-1)$
-2847679	$9 + ((8+7)^6-5) / -4-3^2-1$	-3240070	$-98 + (-7 + (6^5)^4)^4 * ((-3-2)+1)$
-2847682	$(-9 - ((8+7)^6-5) / 4+3) - 21$	-3240126	$-98 + (-7 - (6^5)^4)^4 * (3+2-1)$
-2847688	$(-9 - (((8+7)^6-5) / 4+3)) - 21$	-3241134	$-9^*((-8+7)+6)^*(54 - (3^4-2-1))$
-2847690	$-9/8 * (((7^*-6+5)^4 * 43)^2-1)$	-3242744	$(98^*7 + (6^5)^4)^4 * ((-3-2)+1)$
-2847695	$(-9 - (((8+7)^6-5) / 4+3^2)) + 1$	-3243132	$(9^*87 + (6^5)^4)^4 * ((-3-2)+1)$
-2847696	$-9 + ((8+7)^6-5) / -4-3^2+1$	-3246656	$((9-8-7)^6 + (5^4)^4(3+2))^*-1$
-2847697	$(-9 - (((8+7)^6-5) / 4+3^2)) - 1$	-3260871	$((-9-8)/7-6)^*((-5^4+3)^2-1)$
-2847709	$9 - ((8+7)^6-5) / 4-3^*21$	-3264560	$((-9+8)/7-6)^*((5+4)^4(3^2)-1)$
-2847727	$-9 + ((8+7)^6-5) / -4-3^*21$	-3274050	$(-9/(8^*7)-6)^*((5+4)^4(3^2)-1)$
-2869501	$((-9-8)^7+6^5)/((4^3)^2-1)$	-3279591	$(-9+8)^* - 7^*(6+5)^4 * 3^2 - 1$
-2908160	$(-9+8^7(-7+6))^*5^4 * 4^4(3^2-1)$	-3281257	$-98-7^*6^*(5^4(4+3)-2)-1$
-2952936	$-9^*((8+7)+6)^*(5^4(4^3/2)-1)$	-3282132	$(-9+8)^* - 7^*6^*(5^4(4+3)-2)-1$
-2953314	$9^*((8+7)+6)^*((-5^4(4^3/2)-1)$	-3292469	$(-9-87^4(-6 - (-5-4)))^*(3+2)+1$
-2956497	$9^*(8^*7/6 - (5+4^3)^4(2+1))$	-3292471	$(9-87^4(-6 - (-5-4)))^*(3+2)-1$
-2956665	$-9^*(8^*7/6 + (5+4^3)^4(2+1))$	-3292505	$9 - (87^4(-6 - (-5-4)))^*(3+2)-1$
-2963241	$9^*((-87^4((-6+5)+4)+3)/2+1)$	-3292507	$9-87^4(-6 - (-5-4))^*(3+2)-1$
-2963259	$9^*((-87^4((-6+5)+4)+3)/2-1)$	-3292523	$-9-87^4(-6 - (-5-4))^*(3+2)+1$
-2963268	$-9^*((87^4((-6+5)+4)+3)/2-1)$	-3292525	$-9-87^4(-6 - (-5-4))^*(3+2)-1$
-2963286	$9^*((87^4((-6+5)+4)+3)/-2-1)$	-3292559	$(-9-87^4(-6 - (-5-4)))^*(3+2)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-3292561	$(-9-87^{(-6-(-5-4))})^{(3+2)}-1$	-3539016	$-9^{(8+(-7+6-5))} \cdot 4^{(3^2-1)}$
-3305862	$((9-8)^{7*6-54^3})^{*21}$	-3553200	$-987/(6+54)^{((-3+2)-1)}$
-3308877	$9/8^{(-7^6*(5*(4-3))^2+1)}$	-3562281	$((-9+8+7)^6+5^{4*3})^2 \cdot -1$
-3312328	$9^*8-(7^65^4)^{(3-2+1)}$	-3587193	$((9/(8-7))^6-5)/-4^3 \cdot 3^{(2+1)}$
-3326787	$-9^*((8^*76)^\wedge((-5+4)+3)-21)$	-3590961	$(-9-8/76)^*(5^{4+3})^2-1$
-3326955	$-9^*(8^*76)^\wedge((-5+4)+3)+21$	-3598754	$(-9-8^\wedge(-7+6))^{*(5^{4+3})^2*1}$
-3326973	$-9/(8^*76)^\wedge((5-4)-3)+2+1$	-3610899	$9+8^*-7/6^{*((-5^4+3)^2-1)}$
-3326979	$-9/(8^*76)^\wedge((5-4)-3)-(2+1)$	-3610917	$-9+8^*-7/6^{*((-5^4+3)^2-1)}$
-3326997	$-9^*(8^*76)^\wedge((-5+4)+3)-21$	-3629664	$9^*8^{(7^\wedge((6-5)+4)-3)^{*(-2-1)}}$
-3327165	$-9^*((8^*76)^\wedge((-5+4)+3)+21)$	-3630960	$9^*8^{(-7^\wedge((6-5)+4)-3)^{*(2+1)}}$
-3337434	$9/8^{(-7/(654-3))^\wedge-2-1}$	-3632850	$9^*(8+7)^6 \cdot 5^{(5^4-4-3^\wedge(-2-1))}$
-3339084	$(-9+8)^{*-7*6^{(5-43^2+1)}}$	-3634414	$(9-8^\wedge 7+6^\wedge(-5+4^3))^{*2/1}$
-3356214	$9-(8^{*(7+65)^*-4+3})^\wedge 2+1$	-3634423	$9-(8^\wedge 7-6^\wedge(-5+4^3))^{*2/1}$
-3356216	$9-(8^{*(7+65)^*-4+3})^\wedge 2-1$	-3634441	$-9-(8^\wedge 7-6^\wedge(-5+4^3))^{*2/1}$
-3356568	$9^*8^{*((-7-(-6^\wedge 5+4))^3)^*-2-1}$	-3634450	$(-9-8^\wedge 7+6^\wedge(-5+4^3))^{*2*1}$
-3357216	$9^*8^{*((-7-6^\wedge(5+4-3))^2+1)}$	-3644151	$9+8/-7^*6^{*((5+4)^\wedge(3^2)-1)}$
-3358440	$9^*8^{*((-7+(-6^\wedge 5+4))^3)^*2+1}$	-3644169	$-9+8/-7^*6^{*((5+4)^\wedge(3^2)-1)}$
-3358950	$(9^*87-6^\wedge(5+4))/3+21$	-3651930	$-9^*((8+7)-6+5^4+3)^2-1$
-3358992	$(9^*87-6^\wedge(5+4))/3-21$	-3705714	$9^*(8+(-7^\wedge 6+5)^*(4+3))/2^\wedge 1$
-3359085	$(9^*8^*7-6^\wedge(5+4))/3-21$	-3706173	$-9^*(8+(7^\wedge 6+5)^*(4+3))/2^\wedge 1$
-3359379	$(9^*8^*-7-6^\wedge(5+4))/3+21$	-3707424	$-9^*8^*7^*6^{*((5^*(4+3))^2+1)}$
-3359472	$(-9^*87-6^\wedge(5+4))/3+21$	-3720052	$((9^*(8-7))^\wedge 6-5)^*(4-3^\wedge(2-1))$
-3359514	$(-9^*87-6^\wedge(5+4))/3-21$	-3728255	$((9-8^\wedge 7-6)^\wedge 5)^*(4/3)^2+1$
-3360024	$9^*8^{*((-7+(6^\wedge 5+4))^3)^*-2-1}$	-3728257	$((9-8^\wedge 7-6)^\wedge 5)^*(4/3)^2-1$
-3361248	$9^*8^{*((-7-6^\wedge(5+4-3))^\wedge -21)}$	-3731441	$((9/(8-7))^\wedge 6+(5^*4)^\wedge(3+2))^{*-1}$
-3361896	$9^*8^{*((-7-(6^\wedge 5+4))^3)^*2+1}$	-3735507	$9^*(-8^\wedge 7/6+5-4^\wedge(3^\wedge 2-1))$
-3370311	$(((-9-8)^*7)^\wedge((-6+5)+4)+3)^*2+1$	-3735597	$-9^*(8^\wedge 7/6+5+4^\wedge(3^\wedge 2-1))$
-3370312	$(((-9-8)^*7)^\wedge(-6-(-5-4))+3)/2^\wedge -1$	-3748064	$((98/7+6^*5)^\wedge 4-32)^{*} -1$
-3370313	$(((-9-8)^*7)^\wedge((-6+5)+4)+3)^*2-1$	-3748090	$((98/7+6^*5)^\wedge 4-3^*2)/-1$
-3370323	$(((-9-8)^*7)^\wedge((-6+5)+4)-3)^*2+1$	-3748101	$((98/7+6^*5)^\wedge 4+3+2)/-1$
-3370324	$(((-9-8)^*7)^\wedge(-6+5+4)-3)^*2/1$	-3748102	$((98/7+6^*5)^\wedge 4+3^*2)/-1$
-3370325	$(((-9-8)^*7)^\wedge((-6+5)+4)-3)^*2-1$	-3748128	$((98/7+6^*5)^\wedge 4+32)^{*} -1$
-3382056	$(-9^*8-7/6)^*(5^43)^\wedge 2-1$	-3748175	$-9^*8-7-((-6-5)^4)^\wedge(3+2-1)$
-3399228	$-9/8^{7*((654+3)^\wedge 2-1)}$	-3777769	$((9-8+7)^\wedge 6+(5^\wedge 4^3)^\wedge 2)/-1$
-3399237	$9/8^{(-7/(654+3))^\wedge -2-1}$	-3786525	$9/((-8^\wedge 7*65/4-3)-2)^\wedge -1$
-3410284	$(9+(8-7^\wedge 6)/5)^*(4^*3)^\wedge 2+1$	-3798900	$(-9^*(8+7)^\wedge -6/(5^\wedge 4+3))^\wedge (-2+1)$
-3411676	$((9-8)^*7^\wedge 6-5)^*(4-(32+1))$	-3924099	$(-9-8/7)^*(6+5^\wedge 4+3)^\wedge 2-1$
-3412894	$(-9-(-8+7^\wedge 6)/5)^*(4^*3)^\wedge 2+1$	-3939912	$9^*8^{*(76^*-5^*(4^*3)^\wedge 2-1)}$
-3413358	$(-9+(-8-7^\wedge 6)/5)^*(4^*3)^\wedge 2+1$	-3948544	$(-9-(-8-7^*6)^*5)/-4^\wedge(-3^*2-1)$
-3418795	$((9-8+7)^*6-5)^\wedge 4-3^*2)^{*} -1$	-3950963	$(9-87^\wedge(-6-(-5-4)))^{*3*2+1}$
-3418796	$((9-8+7)^*6-5)^\wedge 4-(3+2)^{*} -1$	-3950965	$(9-87^\wedge(-6-(-5-4)))^{*3*2-1}$
-3418806	$((9-8+7)^*6-5)^\wedge 4+3+2)/-1$	-3950999	$(9-87^\wedge(-6-(-5-4)))^{*3} *2+1$
-3418807	$((9-8+7)^*6-5)^\wedge 4+3^*2)^{*} -1$	-3951000	$(9-87^\wedge(-6+5+4))^3 *2^*1$
-3422208	$(9/8+7^*-6^*5)^*4^\wedge(3^*2+1)$	-3951001	$(9-87^\wedge(-6-(-5-4)))^{*3} *2-1$
-3426159	$(9-8^*7)^\wedge(-6+5+4)^*(32+1)$	-3951035	$(-9-87^\wedge(-6-(-5-4)))^{*3} *2+1$
-3430980	$(9^*8+7^*6^\wedge 5+4)^3)^*-21$	-3951036	$(-9-87^\wedge(-6+5+4))^3 *2^*1$
-3441375	$-9/8^{*((7^*6-5^\wedge 4)^3)^\wedge 2-1}$	-3951037	$(-9-87^\wedge(-6-(-5-4)))^{*3} *2-1$
-3443375	$(-9/8-7)^*((654-3)^\wedge 2-1)$	-3951071	$(-9-87^\wedge(-6-(-5-4)))^{*3*2+1}$
-3459072	$(9/8+7^*6^*5)^*-4^\wedge(3^*2+1)$	-3951073	$(-9-87^\wedge(-6-(-5-4)))^{*3*2-1}$
-3468600	$9^*8^{*(7^*-6-5)^*(4^\wedge(3+2)+1)}$	-3967488	$9^*8^*-7^*(6^\wedge 5+4^*(3+2))$
-3469305	$(-9+8)^*7^{*((-6-5)/4^\wedge(-3)^\wedge 2-1)}$	-3982233	$(-9-8)^*(7^*6-5^\wedge(4+3))^{*(-2-1)}$
-3490729	$(9+8)^*(7^*6+(5-4^\wedge 3)^\wedge(2+1))$	-3986517	$(-9-8)^*(7^*6+5^\wedge(4+3))^{*(2+1)}$
-3492157	$(-9-8)^*(7^*6-(5-4^\wedge 3)^\wedge(2+1))$	-3988638	$(-9-8/7)^*6^{*(5+4^\wedge(3^\wedge 2-1))}$
-3495978	$9^*(8+(7-6^\wedge 5)^*((4+3)^\wedge 2+1))$	-3988872	$9^*8^{*((-76^*(5+4)^\wedge 3+2)+1)}$
-3496122	$9^*(-8+(7-6^\wedge 5)^*((4+3)^\wedge 2+1))$	-3989304	$9^*8^{*((76^*(-5-4)^\wedge 3-2)-1)}$
-3500158	$(-9+8^\wedge(-7+6))^{*(5^\wedge 4+3)^\wedge 2*1}$	-4003479	$9^*87^{*(6-(5^*4^\wedge(3+2)-1))}$
-3500370	$9^*(87-(6^*5+43)^\wedge(2+1))$	-4003670	$(9+8^\wedge 7)^*((6+5)^\wedge(-4+3)-2)+1$
-3501936	$-9^*(87+(6^*5+43)^\wedge(2+1))$	-4003672	$(9+8^\wedge 7)^*((6+5)^\wedge(-4+3)-2)-1$
-3502278	$9^*(8+(-7-6^\wedge 5)^*((4+3)^\wedge 2+1))$	-4005045	$9^*87^{*(6-5^*4^\wedge(3+2)-1)}$
-3502422	$-9^*(8+(7+6^\wedge 5)^*((4+3)^\wedge 2+1))$	-4008177	$9^*-87^{*(6-5^*(-4^\wedge(3+2)-1))}$
-3504774	$98^*7^{*(6-5^*(4^\wedge(3+2)-1))}$	-4009743	$9^*-87^{*(6+5^*(4^\wedge(3+2)-1))}$
-3507140	$(-9/8-7)^*((654+3)^\wedge 2-1)$	-4012875	$9^*-87^{*(6-5^*(-4^\wedge(3+2)-1))}$
-3507504	$(-9/(8+7)-6)^*((5+4)^\wedge(3^*2)-1)$	-4013911	$((98/7)^\wedge 6-(5^\wedge 4^3)^\wedge 2)^{*} -1$
-3507518	$98^*7^{*(6-(5^*4^\wedge(3+2)-1))}$	-4014441	$9^*-87^{*(6-(-5^*4^\wedge(3+2)-1))}$
-3507933	$(-9+8/76)^*((5^\wedge 4+3)^\wedge 2-1)$	-4017573	$9^*-87^{*(6-5^*(-4^\wedge(3+2)-1))}$
-3508890	$98^*7^{*(6-5^*4^\wedge(3+2)-1)}$	-4035744	$(98^*7+6)^*(5^\wedge(4-3)^\wedge(2+1))$
-3511634	$98^*-7^{*(6-5^*(-4^\wedge(3+2)-1))}$	-4047066	$((9/(8-7))^\wedge 6+(5^\wedge 4^3)^\wedge 2)^{*} -1$
-3513006	$98^*-7^{*(6+5^*(4^\wedge(3+2)-1))}$	-4088484	$(9-8+(7^*6+5)^*43)^\wedge 2^*-1$
-3513176	$(9-8)^*-76^{*((5^43)^\wedge 2+1)}$	-4100593	$((9^*(8-7)^\wedge 6^*5)^\wedge 4-32)^{*} -1$
-3517122	$98^*-7^{*(6-(-5^*4^\wedge(3+2)-1))}$	-4100657	$((9^*(8-7)^\wedge 6^*5)^\wedge 4+32)^{*} -1$
-3519866	$98^*-7^{*(6-5^*(-4^\wedge(3+2)-1))}$	-4111254	$((-9+8)^*7^\wedge 6-5^\wedge(4+3))^*21$
-3538872	$9^*(8+(-7+6-5)^*4^\wedge(3^\wedge 2-1))$	-4116483	$-9/8^*7^{*((6+(-5-4)^\wedge 3)^\wedge 2-1)}$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-4116492	$9/8 * (-7 * (6 + (-5 - 4)^3)^2 - 1)$	-4741713	$-9 * ((8 * 7)^\wedge((-6 + 5) + 4) + 3) * (2 + 1)$
-4118629	$((9 * (8 - 7))^\wedge 6 - 5) / -4 * (32 - 1)$	-4754158	$(9 - 8^\wedge 7 - 6^\wedge(-5 + 4 * 3)) * 2 / 1$
-4133781	$98 + 7^\wedge 6 - (54 * 3)^\wedge(2 + 1)$	-4754167	$9 - (8^\wedge 7 + 6^\wedge(-5 + 4 * 3)) * 2 / 1$
-4133977	$(-98 + 7^\wedge 6) - (54 * 3)^\wedge(2 + 1)$	-4754185	$-9 - (8^\wedge 7 + 6^\wedge(-5 + 4 * 3)) * 2 / 1$
-4134375	$9 * ((-8 + 7) + 6)^\wedge 5 * (-4 - 3) * 21$	-4754194	$(-9 - 8^\wedge 7 - 6^\wedge(-5 + 4 * 3)) * 2 * 1$
-4190088	$98 * 7 * -6 * (-5 + 4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1)$	-4782564	$9 * 87 * -6 * (-5 + 4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1)$
-4193518	$98 * 7 * (6 * (5 - 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1)$	-4786479	$9 * 87 * (6 * (5 - 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1)$
-4195684	$9 * ((8 - 7^\wedge 6) + 5) * (4 - 3^\wedge(-2 - 1))$	-4787136	$9 * 8 * (7 - 65 * (4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1))$
-4198320	$98 * 7 * 6 * (5 - 4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1)$	-4787253	$9 * (87 * -6 * (-5 + 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1)$
-4234678	$(-9 * 8 - 7 * (-6 * (5 + 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1))$	-4787271	$-9 * (87 * 6 * (-5 + 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1)$
-4236050	$98 * -7 * (6 * (5 + 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1)$	-4788045	$9 * -87 * (-6 * (5 - 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1)$
-4239480	$98 * 7 * 6 * (-5 - 4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1)$	-4788144	$9 * 8 * (-7 - 65 * (4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1))$
-4243456	$(-9 + (-8 - 7 * 6) * 5) / 4^\wedge(-3 * 2 - 1)$	-4791744	$9 * 8 * (7 - (65 * 4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1))$
-4247165	$(-9 / 8 - 7 * ((6 - (5 + 4)^\wedge 3)^\wedge 2 - 1))$	-4791888	$9 * 8 * (7 - 65 * 4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1)$
-4251372	$9 * 8 * ((7 / 6 + (-5 - 4)^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1)$	-4792752	$9 * -8 * (7 - 65 * -4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1)$
-4251604	$(-9 + 8) * 76 + (-54 * 3)^\wedge(2 + 1)$	-4792896	$9 * -8 * (7 - (-65 * 4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1))$
-4251684	$9 * 8 * ((-7 / 6 - (5 + 4)^\wedge(3 + 2)) - 1)$	-4796496	$9 * 8 * (7 + 65 * (-4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1))$
-4254264	$-9 * 8 * 7 * ((6 + (5 + 4)^\wedge 3)^\wedge 2 - 1)$	-4797504	$9 * -8 * (7 - 65 * (-4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1))$
-4254273	$9 / 8 * (-7 * (6 + (5 + 4)^\wedge 3)^\wedge 2 - 1)$	-4810752	$(9 / 87 * -6^\wedge - 5 * 4^\wedge - 3)^\wedge(-2 + 1)$
-4258793	$(9 - 8) * -7 * ((65 * 4 * 3)^\wedge 2 - 1)$	-4821543	$9 * (8 / 7 * -6 * (5^\wedge(4 + 3) + 2) + 1)$
-4271477	$(9 + ((8 + 7)^\wedge 6 - 5) / -4 * 3) / 2 + 1$	-4821561	$-9 * (8 / 7 * 6 * (5^\wedge(4 + 3) + 2) + 1)$
-4271479	$(9 + ((8 + 7)^\wedge 6 - 5) / -4 * 3) / 2 - 1$	-4829544	$9 * 87 * 6 * (-5 - (4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1))$
-4271486	$(-9 - ((8 + 7)^\wedge 6 - 5) / 4 * 3) / 2 + 1$	-4833459	$9 * 87 * (-6 * (5 + 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1)$
-4271488	$(-9 - ((8 + 7)^\wedge 6 - 5) / 4 * 3) / 2 - 1$	-4834233	$9 * (87 * 6 * (-5 - 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1)$
-4271495	$(-9 + ((8 + 7)^\wedge 6 - 5) / -4) * 3 / 2 + 1$	-4834251	$-9 * (87 * 6 * (5 + 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1)$
-4271497	$(-9 + ((8 + 7)^\wedge 6 - 5) / -4) * 3 / 2 - 1$	-4835025	$9 * -87 * (6 * (5 + 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1)$
-4274108	$9 * ((8 - 7^\wedge 6) + 5) * (4 + 3^\wedge(-2 - 1))$	-4838940	$9 * 87 * 6 * (-5 - 4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1)$
-4300842	$(-9 + 8) * 7 * 6 * ((5 * 4^\wedge 3)^\wedge 2 + 1)$	-4849390	$(-9 - 8^\wedge(-7 + 6)) * ((-5 - 4)^\wedge(3 * 2) - 1)$
-4302360	$(-9 - 8) / 7 * ((6 + 5)^\wedge(4 * 3 / 2) - 1)$	-4975434	$-9 / 8 * (((-76 - 5^\wedge 4) * 3)^\wedge 2 - 1)$
-4318015	$(-9 / 8 - 7 * ((6 + (5 + 4)^\wedge(3 * 2)) + 1))$	-4980356	$(-9 + 8) * -76 * (5 - 4^\wedge(3^\wedge 2 - 1))$
-4329536	$((98 / 7)^\wedge 6 + (-5 * 4)^\wedge(3 + 2)) * -1$	-4981116	$(-9 + 8) * 76 * (5 + 4^\wedge(3^\wedge 2 - 1))$
-4332343	$9 - 8 / 7 * ((6^\wedge 5 / 4 + 3)^\wedge 2 - 1)$	-5038080	$9 * (-8 + 7 / 6) * 5 * 4^\wedge(3 * 2 + 1)$
-4332361	$-9 - 8 / 7 * ((6^\wedge 5 / 4 + 3)^\wedge 2 - 1)$	-5038454	$(9 * 87 - 6^\wedge(5 + 4) + 3) / 2 + 1$
-4341760	$(-9 + 8 * 7 + 6) * -5 / 4^\wedge(-3 * 2 - 1)$	-5038456	$(9 * 87 - 6^\wedge(5 + 4) + 3) / 2 - 1$
-4353198	$((-9 + 8) * 7^\wedge 6 - 5) * (4 + 32 + 1)$	-5038457	$(9 * 87 - (6^\wedge(5 + 4) + 3)) / 2 + 1$
-4369079	$98 - 7^\wedge 6 - (54 * 3)^\wedge(2 + 1)$	-5038459	$(9 * 87 - (6^\wedge(5 + 4) + 3)) / 2 - 1$
-4369275	$(-98 - 7^\wedge 6) - (54 * 3)^\wedge(2 + 1)$	-5055456	$((-9 - 8) * 7)^\wedge(-6 + 5 + 4) * 3 + 21$
-4384347	$((9 / (8 - 7))^\wedge 6 - 5) / 4 * (-32 - 1)$	-5055498	$((-9 - 8) * 7)^\wedge(-6 + 5 + 4) * 3 - 21$
-4384972	$(-9 - 8^\wedge 7) * ((6 + 5)^\wedge(-4 + 3) + 2) + 1$	-5058671	$(((-9 + 8) * 7^\wedge 6 + 5) * 43 + 21)$
-4384974	$(-9 - 8^\wedge 7) * ((6 + 5)^\wedge(-4 + 3) + 2) - 1$	-5058713	$((-9 + 8) * 7^\wedge 6 + 5) * 43 - 21$
-4389320	$(-9 / 8 - 7) * ((6 + (5 + 4)^\wedge 3)^\wedge 2 - 1)$	-5110000	$(-9 - 8 / (7 + 6)) * ((5 + 4)^\wedge(3 * 2) - 1)$
-4439074	$(-9 - 8) * ((7 * (6 * 5 + 43))^\wedge 2 + 1)$	-5118840	$9 * 8 / 7 * ((-6^\wedge 5 / 4 - 3 - 2) + 1)$
-4439808	$-9 * 8 / 7 * ((654 + 3)^\wedge 2 - 1)$	-5125770	$9 * (((8 + 7)^\wedge 6 - 5) / (-4 * (3 + 2)) + 1)$
-4455920	$(-9 - 8 / (-7 - 6)) * ((5 + 4)^\wedge(3 * 2) - 1)$	-5125788	$-9 * (((8 + 7)^\wedge 6 - 5) / 4 / (3 + 2) + 1)$
-4477450	$((9 - 8 - 7 * 6 - 5)^\wedge 4 - 3 * 2) * -1$	-5143807	$9 + 8 - (7 * 6 * 54)^\wedge(3 - 2) + 1$
-4477451	$((9 - 8 - 7 * 6 - 5)^\wedge 4 - 3 - 2) * -1$	-5144576	$(9 / 8 * (7 + 6) + 5) * -4^\wedge(3 * 2 + 1)$
-4477461	$((9 - 8 * 7 + 6 - 5)^\wedge 4 + 3 + 2) / -1$	-5183993	$(9 - 8) * 7 + (6 * 5 * -4)^\wedge 3 * (2 + 1)$
-4477462	$((9 - 8 - 7 * 6 - 5)^\wedge 4 + 3 * 2) * -1$	-5225256	$9 * 8 * ((-7 * 6^\wedge 5 * 4 / 3 + 2) + 1)$
-4504500	$-9 / 8 * (((7 * 6 + 5^\wedge 4) * 3)^\wedge 2 - 1)$	-5225688	$9 * 8 * ((7 * 6^\wedge 5 * -4 / 3 - 2) - 1)$
-4520088	$-9 / (8 - 7 + 6) * ((5^\wedge 4 * 3)^\wedge 2 - 1)$	-5241944	$9 * 8 * (7 + 6) - 5 * 4^\wedge(3^\wedge 2 + 1)$
-4531464	$(9 * -87 + 6) * (54 / 3)^\wedge(2 + 1)$	-5242956	$(-9 + 8) * 76 - 5 * 4^\wedge(3^\wedge 2 + 1)$
-4535993	$(9 - 8) * 7 - (6 + 54)^\wedge 3 * 21$	-5243816	$9 * 8 * (-7 - 6) - 5 * 4^\wedge(3^\wedge 2 + 1)$
-4538368	$((-9 + 8 * 7) * -6 + 5) / 4^\wedge(-3 * 2 - 1)$	-5248485	$9 / 8 * (7^\wedge 6 - (5 + 4)^\wedge(3 * 2 + 1))$
-4572351	$(-9 + 8) * (7 * 6^\wedge 5 * -4 - 3) * 21$	-5267952	$(9 - 87^\wedge(-6 + 5 + 4)) * (3^\wedge 2 - 1)$
-4574267	$(-9 - ((-8 * (7 + 6) + 5)^\wedge 4 - 3)) / 21$	-5268096	$(-9 - 87^\wedge(-6 + 5 + 4)) * (3^\wedge 2 - 1)$
-4594995	$-9 / 8 * (((7 * 6 + 5) * 43)^\wedge 2 - 1)$	-5361093	$(-9 - 8 / -7 - 6) * ((-5^\wedge 4 + 3)^\wedge 2 - 1)$
-4601448	$(9 * 87 + 6) * (54 / -3)^\wedge(2 + 1)$	-5364254	$-98 / 7 * (-6 + 5^\wedge 4)^\wedge(-3 - 2) + 1$
-4613740	$(-9 - 8^\wedge 7 + 6) * (5^\wedge(-4 + 3) + 2) + 1$	-5392410	$9 * ((-8^\wedge 7 * 6 + 5^\wedge 4) - 3) / 21$
-4613742	$(-9 - 8^\wedge 7 + 6) * (5^\wedge(-4 + 3) + 2) - 1$	-5392800	$-9 * ((8^\wedge 7 - 6) + 54) / (3 + 2^\wedge - 1)$
-4634667	$9 * (8 * 7 * -6^\wedge 5 - 43^\wedge(2 + 1))$	-5451639	$9 - (8^\wedge 7 - 6^\wedge(-5 + 4 * 3)) * (2 + 1)$
-4635812	$(9 + 8^\wedge 7 * 6) / (5 / (-4 - 3) - 2) + 1$	-5451657	$-9 - (8^\wedge 7 - 6^\wedge(-5 + 4 * 3)) * (2 + 1)$
-4635814	$(9 + 8^\wedge 7 * 6) / (5 / (-4 - 3) - 2) - 1$	-5489280	$-9 / 8 * ((7 * 6 + 5)^\wedge 4 - 321)$
-4640625	$(-9 * (8 + 7)^\wedge - 6 / (5 - 4 / 3))^\wedge(-2 + 1)$	-5570496	$9 * 8 * -76 * (-5 + 4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1)$
-4685815	$9 - 8^\wedge((7 - 6) * 5) * ((4 * 3)^\wedge 2 - 1)$	-5574254	$-98 / 7 * (6 + 5^\wedge 4)^\wedge(-3 - 2) + 1$
-4685833	$-9 - 8^\wedge((7 - 6) * 5) * ((4 * 3)^\wedge 2 - 1)$	-5575896	$9 * 8 * (76 * (5 - 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1)$
-4699754	$(9 - 8) * 7 - (6 + 5)^\wedge 4 * 321$	-5575959	$9 * (8 * -76 * (-5 + 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1)$
-4711938	$-98 * (7 * 6 + 5) * (4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1)$	-5575977	$-9 * (8 * 76 * (-5 + 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) + 1)$
-4716530	$(-9 + 8^\wedge(-7 + 6)) * ((-5 - 4)^\wedge(3 * 2) - 1)$	-5576040	$9 * 8 * (76 * (5 - 4^\wedge(3 + 2)) - 1)$
-4718172	$9 * 8 * (7 / 6 * 5 - 4^\wedge(3^\wedge 2 - 1))$	-5581440	$9 * 8 * 76 * (5 - 4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1)$
-4719012	$-9 * 8 * (7 / 6 * 5 + 4^\wedge(3^\wedge 2 - 1))$	-5583939	$(9 + 8) * (7 * 6 - (5 + 4^\wedge 3)^\wedge(2 + 1))$
-4721150	$98 * (7 * 6 + 5) * (-4^\wedge(3 + 2) - 1)$	-5585367	$(-9 - 8) * (7 * 6 + (5 + 4^\wedge 3)^\wedge(2 + 1))$
-4741551	$9 * ((8 * -7)^\wedge((-6 + 5) + 4) + 3) * (2 + 1)$	-5624880	$9 * 8 * (7 / 6 - 5^\wedge(4 + 3) + 2^\wedge - 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-5624952	$9*8*(7/6-5^(4+3))-2^{\wedge}-1$	-6207488	$(9/8-76*5)/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-5625048	$9*-8*(7/6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))-2^{\wedge}-1$	-6244352	$(9/8+76*5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-5625120	$9*-8*(7/6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-6245397	$(-9+8/-7-6)*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-5630679	$9*(8*76*(-5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$	-6249968	$((9+(8-7)^{\wedge}6)^5)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-5630697	$-9*(8*76*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$	-6250032	$((9+(8-7)^{\wedge}6)^5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-5630760	$9*-8*(76*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$	-6256640	$(9/-8+7)^*-65/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-5636160	$9*8*76*(-5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$	-6300666	$(-9*8/7-6)*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-5637438	$(-9-8)/7*(6*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1))$	-6310850	$(9/8-7-6)*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2))-1$
-5669769	$(9-8)^*-7*((6*5)^{\wedge}4-32)-1$	-6318080	$(9/8+76)^*-5/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-5672247	$(9-8)^*-7*((6*5)^{\wedge}4+321)$	-6352806	$(9/8*-7^{\wedge}6+5)*((-4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-5718016	$(-9-(-8+76)^5)/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$	-6353070	$(-9-8-7^{\wedge}6*54-3*2-1)$
-5718672	$9*8*(76-(-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	-6353286	$(-9/8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*((-4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-5719320	$9*8*(7-(-65+43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	-6406144	$(-9-8)*(-7+6*5)/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-5719392	$9*8*(76-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-6425472	$9*8^{\wedge}7/-6*((5/4)^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$
-5719529	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)*6/(5^{\wedge}(-4+3)+2)+1$	-6471206	$(9*8+7)*(6-5/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$
-5719531	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)*6/(5^{\wedge}(-4+3)+2)-1$	-6472154	$(-9*8-7)*(6-5/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$
-5720328	$9*-8*(7-65+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-6479719	$9+8*(7-((-6*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
-5728680	$9*-8*(7-65-43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-6479737	$-9+8*(7-((-6*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
-5729616	$9*-8*(76-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-6479831	$9-8*(7+(-6*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-5729688	$9*-8*(7-(-65-43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	-6479849	$-9-8*(7+(-6*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-5730336	$9*-8*(76-(-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	-6480151	$9+8*(7-((-6*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
-5767062	$((-9-8*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3)*21$	-6480169	$-9+8*(7-((-6*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
-5767188	$((9+8*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3)*-21$	-6480263	$9-8*(7+(-6*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-5777373	$((-9+8)^7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3)*21$	-6480281	$-9-8*(7+(-6*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-5790999	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5-4)/(-32-1)$	-6482134	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)*((6+5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)+2+1)$
-5816320	$((-9*8+7)-6)^5*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$	-6495684	$((-9-8)^*-7-((6+5)^{\wedge}(4+3)))/(-2+1)$
-5825400	$((9-8^{\wedge}7-6)+5)*((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-6495726	$(9-8)*(7+(6+5)^{\wedge}(4+3)))/(-2-1)$
-5882700	$(-9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-6508927	$(-9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)^4)*3/21$
-5906376	$(9/(-8-76*5-4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-6538644	$(9*(-8*7-6))^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))*-21$
-5923638	$9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+321)$	-6581445	$(9/8-7)*((6+5)^{\wedge}4+3)+21$
-5925960	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)-3*21)$	-6584940	$(-9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))*(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-5926230	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-(32+1))$	-6585030	$9*87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)*(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-5926248	$9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+32-1)$	-6585120	$(9+87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))*(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-5926284	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-6591795	$(9/8*-7+6)*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-5926311	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-(3+21))$	-6614370	$(-9+8)*-7*6*(54^{\wedge}3-21)$
-5926365	$9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-(3-21))$	-6635511	$9+(-87+6)^5/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-5926437	$9*((-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-6635529	$-9+(-87+6)^5/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-5926472	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)-3*2)+1$	-6655000	$((-98+76)^5)^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}(4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-5926474	$-9*(87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)-3*2)-1$	-6693978	$9-(-8/(-7-65^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-5926479	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3)+21$	-6693981	$9/8*(((-7-6)^5)^{\wedge}4/-3+2+1)$
-5926491	$9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3+2-1)$	-6693996	$-9-(-8/(-7-65^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-5926497	$(-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))-3)+2+1$	-6733824	$(-9-(-8-76)^5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-5926499	$9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3)+2-1$	-6736833	$9+8/-76*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2))-1$
-5926501	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3)-2+1$	-6736851	$-9+8/-76*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2))-1$
-5926563	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3+2-1)$	-6758400	$9*(-8-7/6)^5*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
-5926575	$9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3)-21$	-6765195	$((98/7-65)^{\wedge}4-3*2)^*-1$
-5926580	$-9*(87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3*2)+1$	-6765196	$((98/7-65)^{\wedge}4-3-2)^*-1$
-5926582	$-9*(87^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3*2)-1$	-6765206	$((98/7-65)^{\wedge}4+3+2)^*-1$
-5926617	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-6765207	$((98/7-65)^{\wedge}4+3*2)/-1$
-5926689	$9*(-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3-21)$	-6765233	$((98/7-65)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-5926743	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3+21)$	-6890593	$((-9+8^{\wedge}7)-6)*(-5-4^{\wedge}3)/21$
-5926806	$9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-(32-1))$	-6898682	$(9-8)^*7-(65+4)^{\wedge}3*21$
-5926824	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+32+1)$	-6940996	$((9-8)^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-3*21)$
-5927094	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3*21)$	-6990508	$(-9/(8^{\wedge}7*6*5+4*3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-5939096	$(-9+8)*76*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)+21)$	-6991872	$(9*8^{\wedge}7/(-6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2))))^{\wedge}-1$
-5963767	$9-8^{\wedge}7/6*((5/4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-7028736	$(-9+(-8-76)^5)/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-5963785	$-9-8^{\wedge}7/6*((5/4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-7075224	$9*8*(7+6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)))$
-5980077	$9/8*(-7*(6+5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-7079544	$9*8*(7-6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)))$
-5980086	$9/8*-7*((6+5)+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$	-7080552	$9*8*(-7-6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)))$
-5980160	$((9*8+7)-6)^5*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$	-7098639	$(9/((-8-7^{\wedge}6)^5*543))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-6023680	$(-9+8-7^{\wedge}6)/-5*-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$	-7119115	$(9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4)^*(3/2+1)$
-6036114	$98*-7*(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$	-7119160	$(-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4)^*(3/2+1)$
-6037486	$98*-7*(6^{\wedge}5-(-4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1)$	-7131255	$9-(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*(2+1)$
-6046632	$9/(8+7)*((-6^{\wedge}(5+4))-3)-21$	-7131273	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*(2+1)$
-6064289	$98*(((-7-6)^{\wedge}5+4)/(3*2)+1)$	-7135152	$((98/7)^{\wedge}6-((5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2))^*-1$
-6064386	$98*(((-7-6)^{\wedge}5+4)/(3*2)+1)$	-7142652	$((98/7)^{\wedge}6-((5^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}2))^*-1$
-6064388	$98*(((-7-6)^{\wedge}5+4)/(3*2)-1)$	-7143415	$9+(-8*(-7-6)+5)^*-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-6064485	$98*(((-7-6)^{\wedge}5+4)/(3*2)-1)$	-7143433	$(-9+(8*(-7-6)-5)^4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-6077872	$(-9/((8*7+6*5)^{\wedge}4+32))^{\wedge}-1$	-7192576	$(9*8*-7+65)/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-6086752	$9*-87*(6^{\wedge}5+(-4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-7214608	$((98/7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3*2)^*-1$
-6090464	$9*-87*(6^{\wedge}5-(-4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-7234687	$((98/7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3*2)^*-1$
-6133760	$(9/-8+76)^*-5/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$	-7260372	$-987*6*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-7267397	$((98/7)^{6+5-4^3 \wedge 2})^{*-1}$	-7529413	$((98/7)^{6+5-4^*32})^{*-1}$
-7364240	$(-9 - (-8/7+6)) * ((5+4)^{\wedge(3^*2)} - 1)$	-7529422	$((98/7)^{6+(-54-3)^*2})^{*-1}$
-7372070	$((98/7)^{6-54^{\wedge}3-2})^{*-1}$	-7529434	$((98/7)^{6+(-54+3)^*2})^{*-1}$
-7372074	$((98/7)^{6-54^{\wedge}3+2})^{*-1}$	-7529436	$((98/7)^{6-5^*4^*(3+2)})^{*-1}$
-7373286	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)^*2})^{*-1}$	-7529450	$((98/7)^{6-54-32})^{*-1}$
-7373730	$(-9/8^*7-6) * ((5+4)^{\wedge(3^*2)} - 1)$	-7529455	$((98/7)^{6+5-43^*2})^{*-1}$
-7398391	$9 - (8^* (-7^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3))^{\wedge 2/1}$	-7529460	$((98/7)^{6+(-5+43)^*-2})^{*-1}$
-7398409	$-9 - (8^* (-7^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3))^{\wedge 2/1}$	-7529469	$((98/7)^{6-5-4^{\wedge}3+2})^{*-1}$
-7427136	$((98/7)^{6-(5^*4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$	-7529475	$((98/7)^{6+5-4^{\wedge}3-2})^{*-1}$
-7436288	$(9/8-7^*65)/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$	-7529478	$((98/7)^{6-5^*4^*3+2})^{*-1}$
-7451409	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2})^{*-1}$	-7529484	$((98/7)^{6-5^*4-32})^{*-1}$
-7451413	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2})^{*-1}$	-7529491	$((98/7)^{6-54+3^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$
-7470487	$((98/7)^{6-(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)})^{*-1}$	-7529496	$((98/7)^{6+5-43-2})^{*-1}$
-7470701	$((-9/8-7)+6) * ((5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge 2-1})$	-7529514	$((98/7)^{6-5^*4+32})^{*-1}$
-7473152	$(9/8+7^*65)/-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$	-7529558	$((98/7)^{6+54-32})^{*-1}$
-7483311	$((98/7)^{6-(5^*43)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$	-7529577	$((98/7)^{6+5+4+32})^{*-1}$
-7503292	$((98/7)^{6-(54^*3)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$	-7529581	$((98/7)^{6+54-3^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$
-7506590	$(-9/8-7-6) * ((5+4)^{\wedge(3^*2)} - 1)$	-7529603	$((98/7)^{6+5+4^{\wedge}3-2})^{*-1}$
-7509056	$((98/7)^{6-5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2)})^{*-1}$	-7529612	$((98/7)^{6+(-5+43)^*2})^{*-1}$
-7509536	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}4^*32})^{*-1}$	-7529622	$((98/7)^{6+54+32})^{*-1}$
-7509749	$-9/8^* ((7 - (-6^{\wedge}5+4)/-3)^{\wedge 2-1})$	-7529638	$((98/7)^{6+(-54+3)^*-2})^{*-1}$
-7513536	$((98/7)^{6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}3^*-2})^{*-1}$	-7529650	$((98/7)^{6+(-54-3)^*2})^{*-1}$
-7520291	$((98/7)^{6-5^*43^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$	-7529659	$((98/7)^{6-5+4^*32})^{*-1}$
-7521534	$((98/7)^{6+(-5^*4)^{\wedge}3-2})^{*-1}$	-7529661	$((98/7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4/(3+2)})^{*-1}$
-7521538	$((98/7)^{6+(-5^*4)^{\wedge}3+2})^{*-1}$	-7529669	$((98/7)^{6+5+4^*32})^{*-1}$
-7523911	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}4^*3^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$	-7529685	$((98/7)^{6+5+4^*(3^*2)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$
-7524104	$((98/7)^{6-5432})^{*-1}$	-7529696	$((98/7)^{6+54^*3-2})^{*-1}$
-7524416	$((98/7)^{6-5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)})^{*-1}$	-7529700	$((98/7)^{6+54^*3+2})^{*-1}$
-7525445	$((98/7)^{6+5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)})^{*-1}$	-7529741	$((98/7)^{6+5^*(43-2)})^{*-1}$
-7525536	$((98/7)^{6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}3/-2})^{*-1}$	-7529749	$((98/7)^{6+5^*43-2})^{*-1}$
-7525786	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}4^*3^*2})^{*-1}$	-7529753	$((98/7)^{6+5^*43+2})^{*-1}$
-7525936	$((98/7)^{6-(5^*4^*3)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$	-7529806	$((98/7)^{6+54^*(3+2)})^{*-1}$
-7526287	$((98/7)^{6-(54+3)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$	-7529846	$((98/7)^{6-5^*(4^{\wedge}3+2)})^{*-1}$
-7526411	$((-98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}(4+3-2)})^{*-1}$	-7529860	$((98/7)^{6-54-3^*2})^{*-1}$
-7526935	$((98/7)^{6-(54-3)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$	-7529963	$((98/7)^{6-5+432})^{*-1}$
-7527232	$((98/7)^{6-(5+43)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$	-7529966	$((98/7)^{6-5^*43^*2})^{*-1}$
-7527376	$((98/7)^{6-5^*432})^{*-1}$	-7529973	$((98/7)^{6+5+432})^{*-1}$
-7527659	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}4^*3-2})^{*-1}$	-7530022	$((98/7)^{6+54^*3^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$
-7527663	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}4^*3+2})^{*-1}$	-7530065	$((98/7)^{6+(5^*4+3)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$
-7527682	$((98/7)^{6-5-43^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$	-7530077	$((98/7)^{6+543-2})^{*-1}$
-7527692	$((98/7)^{6+5-43^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$	-7530081	$((98/7)^{6+543+2})^{*-1}$
-7527808	$((98/7)^{6-54^*32})^{*-1}$	-7530129	$((-98/7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4-32})^{*-1}$
-7528092	$((98/7)^{6-(5-43)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$	-7530152	$((98/7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$
-7528311	$((98/7)^{6-(5^*(4+3))^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$	-7530155	$((98/7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4-3^*2})^{*-1}$
-7528450	$((98/7)^{6-543^*2})^{*-1}$	-7530170	$((-98/7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$
-7528507	$((98/7)^{6-(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)))})^{*-1}$	-7530176	$((98/7)^{6-5^*4^*3^*2})^{*-1}$
-7528517	$((98/7)^{6+5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)})^{*-1}$	-7530193	$((-98/7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4+32})^{*-1}$
-7528879	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}4-32})^{*-1}$	-7530555	$((98/7)^{6-(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)))})^{*-1}$
-7528896	$((98/7)^{6-5^*4^*32})^{*-1}$	-7530565	$((98/7)^{6+5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)})^{*-1}$
-7528902	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$	-7530761	$((98/7)^{6+5^*(5^*(4+3))^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$
-7528905	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}4-3^*2})^{*-1}$	-7530980	$((98/7)^{6+(5-43)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$
-7528917	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}4+3^*2})^{*-1}$	-7531380	$((98/7)^{6-5+43^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$
-7528920	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$	-7531390	$((98/7)^{6+5+43^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$
-7528943	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}4+32})^{*-1}$	-7531409	$((98/7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4^*3-2})^{*-1}$
-7528991	$((98/7)^{6-543-2})^{*-1}$	-7531413	$((98/7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4^*3+2})^{*-1}$
-7528995	$((98/7)^{6-543+2})^{*-1}$	-7531840	$((98/7)^{6+(5+43)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$
-7529007	$((98/7)^{6-(5^*4+3)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$	-7532137	$((98/7)^{6+(54-3)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$
-7529050	$((98/7)^{6-54^*3^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$	-7532661	$((-98/7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3-2)})^{*-1}$
-7529099	$((98/7)^{6-5-432})^{*-1}$	-7533136	$((98/7)^{6+(5^*4^*3)^{\wedge 2}})^{*-1}$
-7529106	$((98/7)^{6-5^*43^*2})^{*-1}$	-7533286	$((98/7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4^*3^*2})^{*-1}$
-7529109	$((98/7)^{6+5-432})^{*-1}$	-7533536	$((98/7)^{6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}3/-2})^{*-1}$
-7529226	$((98/7)^{6-5^*(4^{\wedge}3-2)})^{*-1}$	-7534656	$((98/7)^{6-5^*4^{\wedge}3+2})^{*-1}$
-7529248	$((98/7)^{6+(-5-4)^*32})^{*-1}$	-7534968	$((98/7)^{6+5432})^{*-1}$
-7529266	$((98/7)^{6-54^*(3+2)})^{*-1}$	-7535161	$((98/7)^{6-5^{\wedge}4^*-3^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$
-7529319	$((98/7)^{6-5^*43-2})^{*-1}$	-7537534	$((98/7)^{6-(-5^*4)^{\wedge}3-2})^{*-1}$
-7529323	$((98/7)^{6-5^*43+2})^{*-1}$	-7537538	$((98/7)^{6-(-5^*4)^{\wedge}3+2})^{*-1}$
-7529331	$((98/7)^{6-5^*(43-2)})^{*-1}$	-7538781	$((98/7)^{6+5^*43^{\wedge}2})^{*-1}$
-7529372	$((98/7)^{6-54^*3-2})^{*-1}$	-7545536	$((98/7)^{6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}3^*2})^{*-1}$
-7529376	$((98/7)^{6-54^*3+2})^{*-1}$	-7549536	$((98/7)^{6+5^{\wedge}4^*32})^{*-1}$
-7529387	$((98/7)^{6-(5+(4^*3)^{\wedge 2}))})^{*-1}$	-7550016	$((98/7)^{6-5/-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2)})^{*-1}$
-7529398	$((98/7)^{6+(-5-4^{\wedge}3)^*2})^{*-1}$	-7552440	$-9/8^* (((-7+6^{\wedge}5+4)/3)^{\wedge 2-1})$
-7529403	$((98/7)^{6-5-4^*32})^{*-1}$	-7564104	$-9/8^* (((-7-6^{\wedge}5+4)/3)^{\wedge 2-1})$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-7575761	$((98/7)^6 + (5^4 \cdot 3)^2)^{-1}$	-8542971	$(-9 + ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4)^3 + 21$
-7579670	$-9/8 * (((-7 - (6^5 + 4)) / 3)^2 - 1)$	-8542975	$(-9 + ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4)^3 - 2 + 1$
-7585792	$((-9 + 87)^{-6} + 5) / 4^{(-3^2 - 1)}$	-8542986	$-9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / (4^3) - 21$
-7588585	$((98/7)^6 + (5+4)^{(3+2)})^{-1}$	-8543013	$(-9 + ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4)^3 - 21$
-7607659	$((98/7)^6 + 5^{\wedge(4+3)} - 2)^{-1}$	-8543154	$9 * (((8+7)^6 - 5) / (-4^3) - 21)$
-7607663	$((98/7)^6 + 5^{\wedge(4+3)} + 2)^{-1}$	-8548721	$((-9 - 8)^{\wedge 7} + 65) / ((4+3)^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-7608268	$((98/7)^6 - 54^{\wedge 3} / -2)^{-1}$	-8549046	$-9 * ((8^{\wedge 7} + 65^{\wedge 4}) - 3) / 21$
-7618551	$9 + (-87 - 6)^5 / 4^{\wedge(-3^2 - 1)}$	-8578960	$(-9 - (8/7 + 6)) * ((5+4)^{\wedge(3^2)} - 1)$
-7618569	$(-9 - (-87 - 6)^5 / 4^{\wedge(-3^2 - 1)})$	-8611385	$(9 - 8) / -7 * ((6^{\wedge 5} - 4^3)^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-7628256	$((-9 - 8 - 7) + 6)^{\wedge 5} * (4 + 3^{\wedge(-2 - 1)})$	-8622480	$(-9 + 8) / 7 * ((-6^{\wedge 5} + 4 + 3)^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-7631936	$((98/7)^6 + (5^4 \cdot 3)^2)^{-1}$	-8636196	$-9 * ((8^7 + 6 + 5)^{\wedge 4} + 3) / 21$
-7650270	$-9 * ((8 + ((-7 - 6)^5)^{\wedge 4}) - 3) / 21$	-8654880	$(-9 * 8 / 7 - 6) * ((5+4)^{\wedge(3^2)} - 1)$
-7661815	$9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge((-6 + 5) + 4) + 3)})^{\wedge 2} / 1$	-8749991	$9 - 8 * 7 * 6 / (5^{\wedge(-4 - 3)} * (2+1))$
-7661833	$9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge((-6 + 5) + 4) + 3)})^{\wedge 2} / 1$	-8750009	$-9 - 8 * 7 * 6 / (5^{\wedge(-4 - 3)} * (2+1))$
-7685786	$((98/7)^6 - 5^{\wedge(4+3)} - 2)^{-1}$	-8772813	$9/8 * ((-7 - 6)^{\wedge 5} - 43)^{\wedge 2} * 21$
-7686998	$((98/7)^6 + 54^{\wedge 3} - 2)^{-1}$	-8781192	$-9 * 8 * 7 * (((-6 - 5)^4 * 3)^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-7687002	$((98/7)^6 + 54^{\wedge 3} + 2)^{-1}$	-8840256	$((98/7)^6 + 5^4 * 3^{\wedge 2})^{-1}$
-7687717	$((9+8) / ((-7^6)^{\wedge 5} + 43))^{\wedge(-2+1)}$	-8874702	$(9 * 8 + 7)^{\wedge(-6 - (-5 - 4))} * (3 - 21)$
-7733448	$-9 * (8^7 * 6 - 5 / 4^{\wedge(-3^2 - 1)})$	-8890632	$9 * -8 * (7^{\wedge 6} - (-54/3)^{\wedge(2+1)})$
-7782324	$(9 - 8)^{-7} * 76 * ((5^4 \cdot 3)^{\wedge 2} - 1)$	-8931965	$-98 * (7/6 * (5^{\wedge(4+3)} - 2) - 1)$
-7791675	$((98/7)^6 - 5 + 4 \cdot 3^{\wedge 2})^{-1}$	-8932161	$98 * (7/6 * (-5^{\wedge(4+3)} + 2) - 1)$
-7829971	$(-9/87 / ((6^5)^{\wedge 4} - 3))^{\wedge(-2+1)}$	-8957256	$(9 * 87 - 6^{\wedge(5+4)}) * (-3^{\wedge 2} + 1)$
-7844464	$((98/7)^6 - 54^{\wedge 3} - 2)^{-1}$	-8958648	$(9 * 87 + 6^{\wedge(5+4)}) * (3^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-7882818	$((-9 + 8)^7 * 6 - 5)^{\wedge(4+3^2)}$	-8984375	$(-9 - 8 * 7 * 6)^5 * 4^{\wedge(4+3)} / (2+1)$
-7890476	$((9 - 8 + 7)^6 * 5)^{\wedge 4} - 3 - 2)^{-1}$	-9062500	$(9 / (87 * -6 * 5^{\wedge(4+3)} * 2))^{\wedge -1}$
-7890479	$((9 - 8 * 7 - 6)^{\wedge(5 - 4 + 3)} - 2)^{-1}$	-9062625	$(9 + 8 * 7)^{\wedge(-6 + 5 + 4)} * (-32 - 1)$
-7890483	$((9 - 8 * 7 - 6)^{\wedge(5 - 4 + 3)} + 2)^{-1}$	-9063228	$(9 * 8 + 7 * 6)^{\wedge(5 - 43^{\wedge(2+1)})}$
-7890486	$((9 - 8 + 7)^6 * 5)^{\wedge 4} + 3 + 2)^{-1}$	-9064368	$(-9 * 8 - 7 * 6)^{\wedge(5 + 43^{\wedge(2+1)})}$
-7916420	$((98/7)^6 + ((5^4) - 3)^{\wedge 2})^{-1}$	-9100144	$((9 + 8 + 7)^{\wedge 6} + 5 + 43) / -21$
-7923920	$((98/7)^6 + (5^{\wedge 4} + 3)^{\wedge 2})^{-1}$	-9106027	$(9/8)^{\wedge 7} * (-6 + 5)^4 * 4^{\wedge(3^{\wedge 2} + 1)}$
-7954857	$9 / (-8 + 7) - 6^{\wedge 5} * (4^{\wedge(3+2)} - 1)$	-9109504	$((-9 - (8 + 7)) * 6 + 5)^4 * 4^{\wedge(3^{\wedge 2} - 1)}$
-8044400	$(-9 - 8)^7 * (65^4)^{\wedge(3 - 2 + 1)}$	-9144574	$((9 * 8 * 7 * 6)^{\wedge(-5 + 4 + 3)} - 2) / -1$
-8045834	$((9 + 8)^{\wedge(7 - (6 - 5)) - 4} / -3 + 21)$	-9144578	$((9 * 8 * 7 * 6)^{\wedge(-5 - (-4 - 3)) + 2})^{-1}$
-8045876	$((9 + 8)^{\wedge(7 - (6 - 5)) - 4} / -3 + 21)$	-9206248	$(-9 - 8) / 7 * ((6^5 / 4 + 3)^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-8050824	$9 * -8 * (7^{\wedge 6} + (-54/3)^{\wedge(2+1)})$	-9208008	$9 * (-8 * 7^{\wedge 6} - 5 / 4^{\wedge(-3^2 - 1)})$
-8052550	$(-98 + 76)^{\wedge 5} * ((4/3)^{\wedge -2} + 1)$	-9260953	$-9 + 8 * 7 + (6 * 5 * (-4 - 3))^{\wedge(2+1)}$
-8077312	$(9 * 8 * -7 + 6 + 5) / 4^{\wedge(-3^2 - 1)}$	-9261047	$9 + 8 * -7 + (6 * 5 * (-4 - 3))^{\wedge(2+1)}$
-8132031	$-9 * ((-8 + 7 - 65)^{\wedge 4} + 3) / 21$	-9282325	$(9 - 8)^{\wedge 7} * (7 + 6)^{\wedge 5} * (4 * 3^{\wedge 2} - 2 - 1)$
-8134588	$(98/7)^6 / ((5 - 4/3)^{\wedge -2} - 1)$	-9322496	$(9 * 8 * 7 + 65) / -4^{\wedge(-3^2 - 1)}$
-8156742	$(9 * 8 * -7 + 6)^{\wedge(-5 + 4^{\wedge(3^2 + 1)})}$	-9344256	$(9 * (8 * ((7 + 6)^5 * 5 + 4))^{\wedge -3} - 2)^{\wedge -1}$
-8161722	$(9 * 8 * 7 - 6)^{\wedge(-5 - 4^{\wedge(3^2 + 1)})}$	-9355264	$((-9 - 87)^6 * 6 + 5) / 4^{\wedge(-3^2 - 1)}$
-8169488	$-9^{\wedge 8} * (7 / (6 + 5^{\wedge(4 * 3)}))^{\wedge(-2 + 1)}$	-9513450	$-9 * 87 * 6 * 5 * ((4/3)^{\wedge -2} + 1)$
-8177463	$9 * ((-8^{\wedge 7} + 6^{\wedge(-5 + 4 * 3)}) / 2 + 1)$	-9519104	$((-9 - 87)^{\wedge -6} + 5) / -4^{\wedge(-3^2 - 1)}$
-8177481	$9 * ((-8^{\wedge 7} + 6^{\wedge(-5 + 4 * 3)}) / 2 - 1)$	-9525033	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge((6 - 5) + 4)})^3 * 21$
-8241152	$(9 * 8 * -7 + 6 - 5)^4 * (3^2 + 1)$	-9529377	$9/8 * ((76 - 5)^{\wedge 4} / -3 + 2 + 1)$
-8263071	$9 + 8^{\wedge 7} - (654/3)^{\wedge(2+1)}$	-9529404	$9/8 * ((76 - 5)^{\wedge 4} / -3 - 21)$
-8263089	$(-9 + 8^{\wedge 7}) - (654/3)^{\wedge(2+1)}$	-9534105	$9 * (-8 - 7^{\wedge((6 - 5) + 4)})^3 * 21$
-8272656	$9 * 8 * 7 * (-6 * 5 - 4^{\wedge(3^2 + 1)})$	-9643608	$9 * -8 * (7 * 6^{\wedge 5} + 43^{\wedge(2+1)})$
-8273920	$(9 * 8 * 7 + 6 - 5)^{-4} * (3^2 + 1)$	-9655026	$((-9 - 8)^{\wedge(7 - 6 + 5)} - 4) / (-3 + 2^{\wedge -1})$
-8331432	$9 * (8 / -7 * ((-6 * 5)^{\wedge 4} + 3^{\wedge(-2 + 1)}))$	-9687654	$9^{\wedge 8} + (7 * 6^{\wedge(-5 - 4)} + 3)^{\wedge(2+1)}$
-8334071	$9 + 8^{\wedge 7} / -6 * ((5 - 4^{\wedge -3})^{\wedge 2} - 1)$	-9719992	$((-9 + 8) - 7)^{\wedge 7} * ((6 * 5)^{\wedge 4} * 3 / 2 - 1)$
-8334089	$-9 - 8^{\wedge 7} / 6 * ((5 - 4^{\wedge -3})^{\wedge 2} - 1)$	-9720008	$((9 - 8) + 7)^{\wedge 7} * ((6 * 5)^{\wedge 4} * -3 / 2 - 1)$
-8353290	$(9 * 8 * 7 + 6)^{\wedge(5 - 4^{\wedge(3^2 + 1)})}$	-9786713	$(9 / ((8^{\wedge 7} * 6 + 5)^{\wedge(-4 - 3)} + 2))^{\wedge -1}$
-8355721	$(9 + 8)^{\wedge 7} * (7 - 6 * 5 / 4^{\wedge(-3^2 - 1)})$	-9820628	$98 + 7^{\wedge 6} - (5 * 43)^{\wedge(2+1)}$
-8355840	$((9 + 87) + 6)^{\wedge 5} * -5 / 4^{\wedge(-3^2 - 1)}$	-9820824	$(-98 + 7^{\wedge 6}) - (5^4 * 3)^{\wedge(2+1)}$
-8355959	$(-9 - 8)^{\wedge 7} * (7 - 6 * -5 / 4^{\wedge(-3^2 - 1)})$	-9834464	$((9^{\wedge(8 - 7)} - 65)^{\wedge 4} - 32)^{-1}$
-8358390	$(9 * 8 * 7 + 6)^{\wedge(5 - 4^{\wedge(3^2 + 1)})}$	-9834528	$((9^{\wedge(8 - 7)} - 65)^{\wedge 4} + 32)^{-1}$
-8372224	$(-9 - 8 * (-7 - 6)^5) / -4^{\wedge(-3^2 - 1)}$	-9843456	$(98 / 7 - 6 * 5^{\wedge(4 + 3)})^{\wedge 2} * 21$
-8404272	$9 * 8 * (7^{\wedge 6} - 5^{\wedge(4 + 3)})^{\wedge(2 + 1)}$	-9844044	$(98 / -7 - 6 * 5^{\wedge(4 + 3)})^{\wedge 2} * 21$
-8427120	$(-9 + 8 / -7 * 6)^{\wedge 5} * ((5 + 4)^{\wedge(3^2)} - 1)$	-9882873	$((((-9 + 8) * 7)^{\wedge 6} + 5)^{\wedge 4} * 3 + 4)^{\wedge 2} * 21$
-8427564	$-9/8 * ((7 + (6 - 5^4)^{\wedge 3})^{\wedge 2} - 1)$	-9904396	$(-9 + 8) * 76^{\wedge 5} * 4^{\wedge(-3 - 2 + 1)}$
-8427853	$9 * -8 * 7^{\wedge 6} + (5^{\wedge(4 + 3)})^{\wedge(2 + 1)}$	-9917013	$(9 / (8 + ((-7 - 6)^5)^{\wedge 4} * (-3 - 2)))^{\wedge -1}$
-8437760	$((-9 * 8 * 7 - 6) - 5)^4 * (3^2 + 1)$	-9938132	$9^{\wedge((-8 - 7) / -6) - (5 * 43)^{\wedge(2 + 1)}}$
-8489160	$9 * 8 * (7 + (6 * 5 + 4)^{\wedge 3})^{\wedge(-2 - 1)}$	-9938368	$((9 - 8)^{\wedge 7} + 6) - (5 * 43)^{\wedge(2 + 1)}$
-8513375	$(9 + 8 * 7)^{\wedge(-6 + 5 + 4)} * (-32 + 1)$	-9938370	$((-9 + 8)^{\wedge 7} + 6) - (5 * 43)^{\wedge(2 + 1)}$
-8513603	$9 * 8 * -7^{\wedge 6} + (-5 * (4 + 3))^{\wedge(2 + 1)}$	-9938380	$(9 - 8)^{\wedge 7} - 6 - (5 * 43)^{\wedge(2 + 1)}$
-8515625	$(9 - 8 * 7 * 6)^5 * 5^{\wedge(4 + 3)} / (2 + 1)$	-9938382	$(-9 + 8)^{\wedge 7} - 6 - (5 * 43)^{\wedge(2 + 1)}$
-8542776	$-9 * (((8 + 7)^6 - 5) / (4 * 3) - 21)$	-9938451	$(-9 + 8) * 76 + (-5 * 43)^{\wedge(2 + 1)}$
-8542944	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^6 - 5) / (4 * 3) + 21$	-9938618	$-9^{\wedge((-8 - 7) / -6) - (5 * 43)^{\wedge(2 + 1)}}$
-8542955	$9 - ((8 + 7)^6 - 5) / 4 * 3 + 2 - 1$	-9965529	$((9 - 87)^{\wedge(-6 - (-5 - 4))} + 3)^{\wedge 2} * 21$
-8542957	$(9 - ((8 + 7)^6 - 5) / 4 * 3 - 2) + 1$	-9965655	$((9 - 87)^{\wedge(-6 - (-5 - 4))} - 3)^{\wedge 2} * 21$
-8542959	$(9 - ((8 + 7)^6 - 5) / 4) * 3 - 21$	-9966761	$(9 - ((8 + 7)^6 - 5) / 4)^{\wedge(3 + 2^{\wedge -1})}$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-9966824	$(-9 + ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4) * (3+2^{\wedge} - 1)$	-11370392	$-9 - ((-8-7)^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) + 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1$
-10055926	$98 - 7^{\wedge} 6 - (5 * 43)^{\wedge} (2+1)$	-11370393	$(9 + ((8+7)^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) - 3)^{\wedge} 2) / -1$
-10056122	$(-98 - 7^{\wedge} 6) - (5 * 43)^{\wedge} (2+1)$	-11370394	$-9 - (((8+7)^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) - 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$
-10077375	$(-9+8)^{\wedge} 7 * 6^{\wedge} (5+4) + 321$	-11390376	$9 - (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 + 5 * ((4+3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
-10110954	$((-9-8)^{\wedge} 7)^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) * (3+2+1)$	-11390856	$9 - (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 - 5 * ((4+3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
-10192651	$9 / (-8 - (7 * 65 - 4)^{\wedge} 3) ^{\wedge} (-2+1)$	-11393228	$(9-8)^{\wedge} 7 / 6 * (-5^{\wedge} (4+3^{\wedge} 2) + 1)$
-10233601	$((-9-8)^{\wedge} 7 * 6 + 5)^{\wedge} -4 + 3)^{\wedge} 2 * -1$	-11410874	$9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) + 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1$
-10237661	$(-9-8 * ((7+65)^{\wedge} 4 + 3)) / 21$	-11410876	$9 - (((8+7)^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) + 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$
-10252743	$9 / ((8^{\wedge} 7 * (-6-5)^{\wedge} 4 + 3) - 2) ^{\wedge} -1$	-11410892	$-9 - ((8+7)^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) + 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1$
-10353756	$((-9 * 8 - 7)^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) + 3) * 21$	-11410894	$-9 - (((8+7)^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) + 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$
-10353882	$((-9 * 8 - 7)^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) - 3) * 21$	-11416412	$-98 * 7 * ((65+4^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$
-10356604	$(9+8)^{\wedge} (-7 - (-6-5)) * -4 * (32-1)$	-11506082	$-98 * (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5 * ((4+3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1))$
-10360097	$9 * (8+7) - (654/3)^{\wedge} (2+1)$	-11516976	$9 * -8 * (-7 * 6 + (5 * 4)^{\wedge} (3+2-1))$
-10360153	$9 * 8 - 7 - (654/3)^{\wedge} (2+1)$	-11523024	$9 * 8 * (-7 * 6 - (5 * 4)^{\wedge} (3+2-1))$
-10360311	$9 * -8 - 7 + (654/-3)^{\wedge} (2+1)$	-11528482	$-98 * (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5 / ((4/3)^{\wedge} -2 - 1))$
-10360367	$-9 * (8+7) - (654/3)^{\wedge} (2+1)$	-11529362	$-98 * 7^{\wedge} 6 + 5 * ((4+3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
-10407915	$(9/8-7) * ((6+5)^{\wedge} (4 * 3/2) - 1)$	-11529842	$-98 * 7^{\wedge} 6 - 5 * ((4+3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
-10450937	$(9-8) * 7 - 6^{\wedge} 5 / 4^{\wedge} -3 * 21$	-11530722	$-98 * (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5 / ((4/3)^{\wedge} -2 - 1))$
-10475511	$9 - 8^{\wedge} 7 * (6 - (5 * 4^{\wedge} (-3-2) + 1))$	-11553122	$-98 * (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5 * ((4+3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1))$
-10475529	$-9 - 8^{\wedge} 7 * (6 - (5 * 4^{\wedge} (-3-2) + 1))$	-11624991	$9 - (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 - 5^{\wedge} 4 * (4+3) * (2+1)$
-10495991	$9 - 8^{\wedge} 7 * (6 + 5 * 4^{\wedge} (-3-2) - 1)$	-11632640	$(-9 + 8^{\wedge} (-7+6)) * 5 / 4^{\wedge} (3 * (-2-1))$
-10496009	$-9 - 8^{\wedge} 7 * (6 + 5 * 4^{\wedge} (-3-2) - 1)$	-11632653	$-9^{\wedge} 8 / (-8+7) + 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge} 3 * (-2-1))$
-10513404	$-9 / 8 * ((-765 * 4 + 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-11635804	$(-9 - ((-8-7) * -6 + 5)^{\wedge} 4 * 3) / 21$
-10530405	$(9 / (8-7))^{\wedge} 6 * -5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge} (-2-1))$	-11647251	$(-9+8) * 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 * 4 * (3+2) - 1)$
-10554714	$-9 / 8 * ((765 * 4 + 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-11648693	$(9-8) * -7 * ((6 * 5^{\wedge} 43)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
-10555969	$((9-8+7-65)^{\wedge} 4 - 32) * -1$	-11649024	$9 * (-8 - (76-5)) / 4^{\wedge} (-3 * 2 - 1)$
-10556033	$((9-8+7-65)^{\wedge} 4 + 32) * -1$	-11694606	$(9+8) * 7 * 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge} (3 * 2 + 1))$
-10567680	$(-9 * (-8-7) - 6) * -5 / 4^{\wedge} (-3 * 2 - 1)$	-11701746	$(-9-8) * 7 * 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge} (3 * 2 + 1))$
-10607167	$(9+8)^{\wedge} (-7 - (-6-5)) * (-4 * 32 + 1)$	-11707619	$-98 * 7 / 6 * ((5/4^{\wedge} -3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
-10662948	$(9^{\wedge} 8 / (-7+6) + 5) / (4+3^{\wedge} (-2-1))$	-11740002	$((-9^{\wedge} 8 + 7 * 6) + 5) / (4 - 3^{\wedge} (-2+1))$
-10696887	$9 * ((-8^{\wedge} 7 - 6^{\wedge} (-5+4 * 3)) / 2 + 1)$	-11750760	$9 * 8 * -7 * (((6^{\wedge} 5 - 4) * 3 - 2) + 1)$
-10696895	$9 * (-8^{\wedge} 7 - 6^{\wedge} (-5+4 * 3)) / 2 + 1$	-11751237	$9 * ((8 * 7 * (6^{\wedge} 5 - 4) * -3 + 2) + 1)$
-10696897	$9 * (-8^{\wedge} 7 - 6^{\wedge} (-5+4 * 3)) / 2 - 1$	-11751291	$-9 * ((8 * 7 * (6^{\wedge} 5 - 4) * 3 + 2) + 1)$
-10696905	$9 * ((-8^{\wedge} 7 - 6^{\wedge} (-5+4 * 3)) / 2 - 1)$	-11763333	$9 * ((-8 * 7 * (6^{\wedge} 5 + 4) * 3 + 2) + 1)$
-10727235	$(9 / (8-7))^{\wedge} 6 * -5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge} (-2-1))$	-11763387	$-9 * ((8 * 7 * (6^{\wedge} 5 + 4) * 3 + 2) + 1)$
-10729536	$((98/7)^{\wedge} 6 - (5 * 4)^{\wedge} (3+2)) * -1$	-11763864	$9 * 8 * 7 * (((-6^{\wedge} 5 - 4) * 3 - 2) + 1)$
-10749544	$((9 * 8)^{\wedge} (-7+6) + 5) + 4) / (-3/2 - 1)$	-11790164	$(-9 - (8/7)^{\wedge} -6 * 5) * 4^{\wedge} (3^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$
-10774209	$(9+8)^{\wedge} (-7 - (-6-5)) * -43 * (2+1)$	-11796113	$((-9-8) * 7)^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) / 3 * 21$
-10937493	$(9-8) * -7 * ((6 * 5^{\wedge} 4 / 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-11852892	$(-9 + 87^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4))) * (3-21)$
-11024772	$(9+8)^{\wedge} (-7 - (-6-5)) * -4 * (32+1)$	-11852991	$9 * ((-87^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) + 3) * 2 + 1)$
-11035601	$(9 * 87 * 6)^{\wedge} (-5+4+3) / -2+1$	-11853009	$9 * ((-87^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) + 3) * 2 - 1)$
-11035603	$(9 * 87 * 6)^{\wedge} (-5+4+3) / -2-1$	-11853099	$-9 * ((87^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) + 3) * 2 - 1)$
-11042163	$9^{\wedge} 8 / (-8+7) + 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge} 3 * (2+1))$	-11853107	$9 * (87^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) + 3) * -2+1$
-11045161	$((98/7)^{\wedge} 6 + (5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2) * -1$	-11853109	$9 * (-87^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) - 3) * 2 - 1$
-11068929	$(9+8 * (7 * (-6-5+4+3))^{\wedge} 2 * -1$	-11853117	$9 * ((-87^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) - 3) * 2 - 1)$
-11156241	$9 - (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 + 5^{\wedge} (4+3) * (2+1)$	-11853216	$(9 + 87^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4))) * (3-21)$
-11165202	$((9-8) - 7) * (6 * 5 * 4 + 3)^{\wedge} (2+1)$	-11874855	$(9 * 8 - 76 * 5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2 + 1$
-11184808	$(9 / (-8^{\wedge} (7+6-5) + 4)) / (3^{\wedge} 2) ^{\wedge} -1$	-11874857	$(9 * 8 - 76 * 5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2 - 1$
-11196570	$(9 * 87 - 6^{\wedge} (5+4)) * (3^{\wedge} -2+1)$	-11875076	$(-9+8) * 76 * 5^{\wedge} (5^{\wedge} (4+3) * 2+1)$
-11197433	$(9-8) * 7 + 6^{\wedge} (5+4) * (-3^{\wedge} -2-1)$	-11888704	$((98 * 7 + 6) * 5 - 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2 / -1$
-11198310	$(-9 * 87 - 6^{\wedge} (5+4)) * (3^{\wedge} -2+1)$	-11960320	$(-9 - 8^{\wedge} (-7+6)) * 5 / 4^{\wedge} (3 * (-2-1))$
-11248056	$9 * 8 * ((-7 - (-6+5^{\wedge} (4+3))) * 2 + 1)$	-11967492	$(-9+8) * 76 * ((54^{\wedge} 3 + 2) + 1)$
-11248200	$9 * -8 * ((-7 - (-6+5^{\wedge} (4+3))) * 2 + 1)$	-11970815	$9 * (-8^{\wedge} 7 + 6^{\wedge} (5+4)) / (-3 * 2) + 1$
-11248560	$9 * 8 * (7 - (-6+5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2 + 1)$	-11970817	$9 * (-8^{\wedge} 7 + 6^{\wedge} (5+4)) / (-3 * 2) - 1$
-11248704	$9 * 8 * ((-7 - (-6+5^{\wedge} (4+3))) * 2) - 1)$	-11992050	$-98 * 6^{\wedge} 5 * ((4/3)^{\wedge} -2 + 1)$
-11248992	$9 * 8 * (7 - (-6+5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2) + 1)$	-12117329	$((9-8-7+65)^{\wedge} 4 - 32) * -1$
-11249136	$9 * 8 * (7 + 6 - 5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2 - 1)$	-12117393	$((9-8-7+65)^{\wedge} 4 + 32) * -1$
-11249784	$9 * 8 * ((-7 - 6 - 5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2 + 1)$	-12124160	$(9 * 8 + 76) * -5 * 4^{\wedge} (3 * 2 + 1)$
-11250216	$9 * 8 * ((-7 + 6 - 5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2 - 1)$	-12127500	$98 * ((-7-6)^{\wedge} 5 + 43) / (2+1)$
-11250864	$9 * 8 * (-7 - 6 - 5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2 + 1)$	-12176451	$9 * ((87/6^{\wedge} -5 - 43) * -2 - 1)$
-11251008	$9 * -8 * (7 - (-6-5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2) + 1)$	-12177981	$-9 * ((87/-6^{\wedge} -5 - 43) * -2 - 1)$
-11251296	$9 * 8 * ((-7 - (-6+5^{\wedge} (4+3))) * 2) + 1)$	-12187500	$(9-87) * 6 / (5^{\wedge} (-4-3) * (2+1))$
-11251440	$9 * -8 * (7 - (-6-5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2) + 1)$	-12277587	$(9+8)^{\wedge} (-7+6+5) * (-4-3) * 21$
-11251800	$9 * 8 * ((-7 - (-6+5^{\wedge} (4+3))) * 2) + 1)$	-12333060	$-9 / 8 * ((7 * (-6-5) * 43)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
-11251944	$9 * 8 * ((-7 - (-6+5^{\wedge} (4+3))) * 2) - 1)$	-12342723	$(9 * 8 + 7) * ((6-5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2 + 1)$
-11287273	$(9+8 * (-7-6)^{\wedge} 5) * (4 + (-3-2)^{\wedge} -1)$	-12342881	$(9 * 8 + 7) * ((6-5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2 - 1)$
-11294244	$9 * (-8 * 7^{\wedge} 6 + 5) / (-4^{\wedge} (-3+2) + 1)$	-12343197	$(9 * 8 + 7) * ((6-5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2) + 1)$
-11294364	$-9 * (8 * 7^{\wedge} 6 + 5) / (-4^{\wedge} (-3+2) + 1)$	-12343355	$(9 * 8 + 7) * (6 - 5^{\wedge} (4+3) * 2 - 1)$
-11324718	$((-9-8^{\wedge} 7) * -6 + 54) / (-3^{\wedge} -2 - 1)$	-12344145	$(9 * 8 + 7) * (-6 - 5^{\wedge} (4+3) * 2 + 1)$
-11344700	$(9 - (8+7+6)^{\wedge} 5) * ((4/3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	-12344303	$(9 * 8 + 7) * ((-6 - 5^{\wedge} (4+3) * 2) - 1)$
-11370374	$9 - ((-8-7)^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) + 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1$	-12344619	$(9 * 8 + 7) * ((-6 - 5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2 + 1)$
-11370376	$9 - (((8+7)^{\wedge} (-6 - (-5-4)) - 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	-12344777	$(9 * 8 + 7) * ((-6 - 5^{\wedge} (4+3)) * 2 - 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-12383700	$(-9+8)^* - 7^*6^*(-543^2-1)$	-14238229	$(9 - ((8+7)^6-5)/4)^*(3+2)+1$
-12400934	$(-9+8)^*7^*((6+5)^(4^3/2)+1)$	-14238230	$(9+((8+7)^6-5)/-4)^*(3+2)^{\wedge}1$
-12457375	$9-8^{\wedge}7-(654/3)^(2+1)$	-14238231	$(9 - ((8+7)^6-5)/4)^*(3+2)-1$
-12457393	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)-(654/3)^(2+1)$	-14238319	$(-9+((8+7)^6-5)/-4)^*(3+2)+1$
-12475407	$(9+8^*(-7-6)^5)^*(4+(3+2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-14238320	$(-9+((8+7)^6-5)/-4)^*(3+2)^{\wedge}1$
-12521463	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6^*(-5^*4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$	-14238321	$(-9+((8+7)^6-5)/-4)^*(3+2)-1$
-12521481	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*6^*(-5^*4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$	-14294070	$9/8^*((76-5)^4-3)/-2-1$
-12541943	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6-5^*4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$	-14344810	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6+5)+4^{\wedge}(3^*2))+1$
-12541961	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6-5^*4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$	-14344812	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6+5)+4^{\wedge}(3^*2))-1$
-12550135	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6-(5-(4-3)))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-14348319	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7^*6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3))/(-2-1)$
-12550153	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6-(5-(4-3)))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-14349495	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3))/(-2-1)$
-12555800	$((9+8)/7-6)^*((5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-14353002	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6+5)-4^{\wedge}(3^*2))+1$
-12577026	$(9-8^{\wedge}7)^*6+(54/3)^(2+1)$	-14353004	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6+5)-4^{\wedge}(3^*2))-1$
-12577134	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)^*6+(54/3)^(2+1)$	-14361212	$(9-8)^{\wedge}(-7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}(4^*3)-21)$
-12581125	$((9-8^{\wedge}7)^*6+5)+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-14385593	$(-9+8)^* - 7+6^{\wedge}5^*(-43^{\wedge}2-1)$
-12581135	$(9-8^{\wedge}7)^*6-5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-14393925	$(-9/8-7)^*((6+5)^(4^3/2)-1)$
-12581243	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)^*6-5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-14401536	$9^*8^{\wedge}7/-6^*(5+(-4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-12582453	$9^*((8^{\wedge}7/6-5)^*-4+32-1)$	-14669815	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6-5^*4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
-12583114	$((9+8^{\wedge}7)^*-6-5)-(4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1$	-14669833	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6-5^*4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
-12583371	$9^*((8^{\wedge}7/6+5)^*-4-32+1)$	-14690295	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5^*4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
-12584581	$((9-8^{\wedge}7)^*6+5)-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-14690313	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5^*4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
-12584689	$((-9-8^{\wedge}7)^*6+5)-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-14711112	$(9-87)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)^*(32-1)$
-12584699	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)^*6-5-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-14711949	$(9^*(87+6))^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)^*-21$
-12588690	$(9-8^{\wedge}7)^*6-(54/3)^(2+1)$	-14753907	$9^*(8^*-7-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*-21$
-12588798	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)^*6-(54/3)^(2+1)$	-14754600	$9^*8^*7^*((6+5)^{\wedge}4-3)^*-2+1$
-12615671	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+(5-(4-3)))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-14760648	$9^*8^*7^*((6+5)^{\wedge}4+3)^*-2+1$
-12615689	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+(5-(4-3)))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-14763861	$9^*(8^*7/-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*-21$
-12623863	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6-5^*-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$	-14767389	$9^*(8^*7/-6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$
-12623881	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6-5^*-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$	-14777343	$9^*(8^*-7-6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$
-12742903	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	-15046632	$-9^*((((8-7)^6+5)^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-12745728	$9^*8^{\wedge}7/6^*((-5/4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-15058423	$9+(8/(-7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1$
-12814425	$-9^*((((8+7)^6-5)/4-3)/2-1)$	-15059703	$9-(8/(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1$
-12814433	$9^*((((8+7)^6-5)/-4+3)/2+1)$	-15059721	$-9-(8/(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1$
-12814435	$9^*((((8+7)^6-5)/-4+3)/2-1)$	-15116904	$9^*8^*((7-(6-5)/4+3)^*-2+1)$
-12814445	$(-9^*((8+7)^6-5)/4+3)/2+1$	-15146093	$(-9/(8^{\wedge}7*65-43))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-12814446	$(-9^*((8+7)^6-5)/4+3)^*2^{\wedge}-1$	-15146097	$(9/(-8^{\wedge}7*65+4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-12814447	$(-9^*((8+7)^6-5)/4+3)/2-1$	-15176076	$((-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^3*2+1)$
-12814448	$(9^*((8+7)^6-5)/-4-3)/2+1$	-15284209	$(-9^*8-7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))^*(32-1)$
-12814449	$(9^*((8+7)^6-5)/4+3)/-2^*1$	-15311814	$98^*(7+6/(-5^{\wedge}(-4-3))^*(2+1)))$
-12814470	$9^*((((8+7)^6-5)/-4-3)/2-1)$	-15313186	$-98^*(7+6/(5^{\wedge}(-4-3))^*(2+1)))$
-13017854	$(-9-((8+7)^6-5)^4)/(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-15375168	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}5^*(4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-13030686	$-9^*87^*((65+4^3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-15377283	$(9-(8+7)^6/5)/4^3(2+1)$
-13123584	$9^*(-8-(76+5))/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$	-15386139	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3))/(-2-1)$
-13189120	$(9^*(-8-7)^*6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$	-15659942	$(-9/(87^*((6^5)^{\wedge}4-3)))/2^{\wedge}-1$
-13245180	$(9+8^{\wedge}7*6)/((5^*4)^{\wedge}(-3+2)-1)$	-15713280	$9^*8^{\wedge}7/6^*5^*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$
-13311675	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7^*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3))/(-2-1)$	-15725559	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7/6^*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1)$
-13352960	$(9^*(-8-7)^*6+5)^*-4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1)$	-15725577	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6^*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1)$
-13436896	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4^3)^*-2^{\wedge}-1$	-15731703	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7/6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1)$
-13436960	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4^3)^*-2^{\wedge}-1$	-15731721	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1)$
-13593741	$9-87^*6/(5^{\wedge}(-4-3))^*(2+1))$	-15744000	$9^*8^{\wedge}7/6^*5^*(-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$
-13593759	$-9-87^*6/(5^{\wedge}(-4-3))^*(2+1))$	-15752929	$((9^*(8+(-7+6)^5))^{\wedge}4-32)/-1$
-13828491	$9+(87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)-3)^*-21$	-15752993	$((9^*(8-(7-6)^5))^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-13828509	$-9+(87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)-3)^*-21$	-15803856	$(9-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*(3+21)$
-13828617	$9-(87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3)^*21$	-15804288	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*(3+21)$
-13828635	$-9-(87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3)^*21$	-15825054	$((-98+7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3)^*21$
-13835519	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^3)^*2)+1$	-15896340	$-9/8^*((7^*(6-543))^{\wedge}2-1)$
-13835521	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^3)^*2)-1$	-15917503	$9-8/7^*((6^*(-5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
-13845809	$((98-7^*6+5)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$	-15917521	$-9-8/7^*((6^*(-5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
-13845835	$((98-7-6^*5)^{\wedge}4-3^*2)^*-1$	-15974391	$9+(-8-7)^*65/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
-13845836	$((98-7-6^*5)^{\wedge}4-3-2)^*-1$	-15974409	$-9+(-8-7)^*65/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
-13845846	$((98-7^*6+5)^{\wedge}4+3+2)^*-1$	-16016130	$(-9-8+7)^*(6^5*4-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-13845847	$((98-7-6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3^*2)^*-1$	-16097143	$9-8/7^*((6^5*4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-13845873	$((98-7^*6+5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$	-16097161	$-9+8/-7^*((6^5*4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-13883816	$(9/(8+7^*(65^{\wedge}4+3)+2))^{\wedge}-1$	-16142517	$9/8^*((76+5)^{\wedge}4/-3+2+1)$
-13883820	$(-9/(8+7^*(65^{\wedge}4-3))^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-16142544	$9/8^*((76+5)^{\wedge}4/-3-2+1)$
-13919400	$(-9+8/7)^*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4^3/2)-1)$	-16249135	$(9-8)^* - 7^*(6^*(-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-13994613	$(9^*(8-7))^{\wedge}6^*(-5+4^3)/(-2-1))$	-16270287	$(-9^*8-7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))^*(32+1)$
-14062493	$(9-8)^*7-(6^5*4)^{\wedge}(3-(2-1))$	-16335883	$9+(8/((-7^*6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-14094216	$9^*-8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21)$	-16335901	$(-9-(8/((-7^*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)))^{\wedge}-1)$
-14097240	$9^*-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$	-16354755	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^3)-21)$
-14212800	$-987/(6^5*4)^{\wedge}((-3+2)-1)$	-16354917	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^3)-2-1)$
-14218750	$(-98+7)^*6/(5^{\wedge}(-4-3))^*(2+1))$	-16354923	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^3))+21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-16354925	$-9*(8^7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2)+1$	-17730946	$(98-76^{\wedge}5)/((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-16354926	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2/1)$	-17779338	$(9-87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-16354927	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2)-1$	-17779392	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)*3-21)$
-16354941	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))+2+1$	-17779500	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3)*(2+1)$
-16354942	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))+2^{\wedge}1$	-17779554	$9*(-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))*3+2+1)$
-16354946	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))-2^{\wedge}1$	-17779562	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))*3-2)+1$
-16354947	$(-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))-2)-1$	-17779564	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))*3-2)-1$
-16354961	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2))+1$	-17779598	$9*(-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))*3-2)+1$
-16354962	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2)^{\wedge}1$	-17779600	$9*(-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))*3-2)-1$
-16354963	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2))-1$	-17779608	$9*(-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))*3-(2+1))$
-16354965	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))-21$	-17779662	$9*(-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3)*(2+1)$
-16354971	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-2-1))$	-17779770	$9*(-87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)*3-21)$
-16355133	$9*((-8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))-21)$	-17779824	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-16425654	$-987*((65+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-177850297	$(9-8)^*7-65^{\wedge}4+321$
-16426799	$9*(-8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+43)^{\wedge}2+1$	-17850304	$(-9+8)^{\wedge}7*65^{\wedge}4+321$
-16426800	$(-9+(-8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+43)^{\wedge}2)*-1$	-17850946	$(-9+8)^{\wedge}7*65^{\wedge}4-321$
-16426801	$9*(-8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-43)^{\wedge}2-1$	-17968680	$(-9-8/7)*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4*3/2)-1)$
-16426817	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-43)^{\wedge}2+1$	-17799496	$((9+8)^*(-7^{\wedge}6+5)+4)/3^{\wedge}-2*1$
-16426818	$(9+(-8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+43)^{\wedge}2)*-1$	-18003041	$98*7/6*((-54^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$
-16426819	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-43)^{\wedge}2-1$	-18003727	$98*7/-6*((54^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$
-16564086	$(9-8)^*-7*6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-18104320	$(-9-8)^*(-7-6)^*-5/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-16564135	$(9-8)^*-7*(6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-18238770	$(-9+8/7)*6*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-16614729	$-9/8*((7*(6+543))^{\wedge}2-1)$	-18240000	$((9*-8+7*-6)^*(5*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$
-16656191	$(-9-8)^*7/(6^{\wedge}(5-4*3)*2)+1$	-18262271	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))/(3*2)+1$
-16656193	$(-9-8)^*7/(6^{\wedge}(5-4*3)*2)-1$	-18262273	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))/(3*2)-1$
-16661520	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(7+6-5))/((4*3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-18310545	$(-9/8*7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3*2)-1)$
-16662528	$(-987-6*5)/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$	-18321408	$9*8^{\wedge}7*(6*5/4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-16681051	$(9*8-76^{\wedge}((5-4)+3))/2+1$	-18342918	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$
-16681053	$(9*8-76^{\wedge}((5-4)+3))/2-1$	-18342936	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$
-16736265	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5))*(-4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$	-18448524	$9*(8+((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21)$
-16776544	$(9-8^{\wedge}7/6+5)*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-18448668	$9*(-8-((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/21)$
-16777888	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7/6-5)*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-18481122	$-9*8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-16796165	$9/((-8-7)*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-18481142	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*(4/3)^{\wedge}-2)+1$
-16809991	$9*(8^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4)^{\wedge}(3-2)+1$	-18481144	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*(4/3)^{\wedge}-2)-1$
-16810009	$-9*(8^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$	-18481160	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*(4/3)^{\wedge}-2)+1$
-16823807	$(-9+8)^*7*6*((5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-18481162	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*(4/3)^{\wedge}-2)-1$
-16851590	$((-9-8)^*7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-18481182	$-9*8^{\wedge}7-6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-16872192	$9*8*(7-(-6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)))^*(2-1)$	-18485568	$-9*8^{\wedge}7+6*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-16874784	$9*8*(-7+6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*(2-1)$	-18521314	$98*-7*((6*5)^{\wedge}((4-3)+2)-1)$
-16875216	$9*8*(-7+6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*(2+1)$	-18522686	$98*7*((6*5)^{\wedge}((4-3)+2)-1)$
-16877808	$9*8*(-7-(6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)))^*(2+1)$	-18541386	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2*1$
-16930314	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6+(5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-18579393	$((-9-87)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3)*21$
-16930422	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6-(5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-18579519	$((-9-87)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3)*21$
-16987320	$9*((-8^{\wedge}7+6)-54)/(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-18608670	$(9+8-7)*(6*5*-4-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-17006583	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-18714362	$-9*8^{\wedge}7+6*(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
-17006601	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5*(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-18718118	$-9*8^{\wedge}7+6/(5^{\wedge}(-4-3))*2+1$
-17009993	$-9*((-8+7*(6*5)^{\wedge}4)/3+2)+1$	-18733260	$(9/8-7)*6*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
-17010056	$(9-8)^*7-((6*5)^{\wedge}4+3)*21$	-18741610	$((9-8)^*7*6-5)^{\wedge}4*(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-17010210	$((-9+8)^*-7+(6*5)^{\wedge}4+3)*-21$	-18782208	$9*-8^{\wedge}7*(6-5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$
-17055744	$9*8^{\wedge}7/-6*(5-(-4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-18802926	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
-17124210	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*((5+4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-18808164	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1))$
-17131311	$9*(-8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+43)^{\wedge}2+1$	-18815318	$-9*8^{\wedge}7+(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1$
-17131312	$9*(-8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+43)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$	-18815320	$-9*8^{\wedge}7+(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1$
-17131313	$9*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+43)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-18823969	$((9-8)^*7*6*-5-4)*32-1$
-17131329	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+43)^{\wedge}2+1$	-18835218	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6*-5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-17131330	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+43)^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$	-18845748	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6*((5*4+3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-17131331	$-9*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+43)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-18862368	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-(6*(5*4)^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-17158590	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)*6*5/(4-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-18867012	$-9*8^{\wedge}7+6*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
-17254944	$(-9+8)^*-7*6^{\wedge}5*(4-321)$	-18871914	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6*((5*4/3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-17293668	$((-9+8)^*7*6+5)^*(4+3)*21$	-18873440	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7+65)+(4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-17294187	$(9*8-7^{\wedge}((6-5)+4+3))^*(2+1)$	-18875296	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+65)-(4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-17294214	$(9-(7-6)^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$	-18876822	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6*((5*4/3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-17294340	$((9-8)^*-7^{\wedge}(6+5-4)+3)*21$	-18881724	$-9*8^{\wedge}7-6*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
-17294592	$(9+(8-(7-6)^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(4+3))^*-21$	-18886368	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+(6*(5*4)^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-17294619	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}((6-5)+4+3))^*(-2-1)$	-18902988	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6*((5*4+3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-17321936	$(-9/8/(7+(6+5)^{\wedge}(4+3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-18913518	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-17554287	$-9*((8+7+65)^{\wedge}4+3)/21$	-18920475	$-9/8*((-76*54+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-17593337	$(9*8^{\wedge}7-(6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3))^*-2+1$	-18933416	$-9*8^{\wedge}7-(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1$
-17593339	$(9*8^{\wedge}7-(6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3))^*-2-1$	-18933418	$-9*8^{\wedge}7-(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1$
-17614647	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)/2-1)$	-18940572	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6*((5*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1))$
-17614665	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)/2-1))$	-18945810	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
-17676288	$9*8^{\wedge}7*(65*4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$	-18974704	$((9+87-6*5)^{\wedge}4-32)/-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-18974768	$((9+87-6*5)^4+32)^*-1$	-21393771	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3))+21$
-19030618	$-9*8^7-6/(5^4(-4-3)^*(2+1))$	-21393773	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3)-2)+1$
-19034362	$-9*8^7+6-(5^4)^{(3+2-1)}$	-21393774	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3)-2^1)$
-19034374	$-9*8^7-(6+(5^4)^{(3+2-1}))$	-21393775	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3)-2)-1$
-19136147	$((9*8+7)-6)^*(5-4^3(2+1))$	-21393789	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3))+2+1$
-19136877	$((-9*8-7)+6)^*(5+4^3(2+1))$	-21393790	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3))+2^1$
-19196142	$9*(8^7-6^6)/((4+3)^{-2-1})$	-21393794	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3))-2^1$
-19199982	$9+8+7+6*((5^4)^{(3+2-1)})$	-21393795	$(-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3))-2)-1$
-19199984	$9+8-7-6*((5^4)^{(3+2-1)})$	-21393809	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3)+2)+1$
-19199988	$-9+8+7-6*((5^4)^{(3+2-1)})$	-21393810	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3)+2^1)$
-19199996	$9+8-(7-6*((5^4)^{(3+2-1)}))$	-21393811	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3)+2)-1$
-19200004	$-9-(8-(7-6*((5^4)^{(3+2-1)})))$	-21393813	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3))-21$
-19200012	$9-(8+7-6*((5^4)^{(3+2-1)}))$	-21393819	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3)+2+1)$
-19200016	$-9-(8-7-6*((5^4)^{(3+2-1)}))$	-21393981	$9*(-8^7-6^6(-5+4*3)-21)$
-19200018	$-9-(8+7+6*((5^4)^{(3+2-1)}))$	-21525016	$(9^8+7*(6+5)^*43)/-2*1$
-19263168	$-9*8^7-6^6*((-4-3)^{2+1})$	-21534912	$98*7*6^6*(4+3^4(-2-1))$
-19267554	$-9*8^7+6*(5-4^3(2-1))$	-21535027	$(9^8-7+(6^6+4)^3)/-2*1$
-19267614	$-9*8^7-6*(5+4^3(2-1))$	-21547364	$(9^8+7+6*(5^4)^3)/-2*1$
-19339026	$9*(8^7+6^6)/((4+3)^{-2-1})$	-21595976	$((9-8)/-7-6)*((5^4)^3)^{2-1}$
-19403334	$-9/8*((7-65*4^3)^{2-1})$	-21658357	$(9^8-7+(6^6)^4/3)/-2*1$
-19405800	$-9*(8^7+(6/54)^{-3-2})-1$	-21658755	$(-9/(8*7)-6)*((5^4)^3)^{2-1}$
-19405818	$9*(-8^7-6/54)^{-3-2}-1$	-21722610	$(9/8-7*6)*((5^4)^3)^{2-1}$
-19439697	$-9*(8*((-7+(6^5)^4)/3-2)+1)$	-21730302	$(9-87^6(-6-(-5-4)))^*(32+1)$
-19440303	$9*(8*((-7-(6^5)^4)/3-2)+1)$	-21730590	$9-87^6(-6-(-5-4))^*(32+1)$
-19472343	$9*((8-7*6)^5-43)/21$	-21730608	$-9-87^6(-6-(-5-4))^*(32+1)$
-19526777	$9*((8+7)^6-5^6-4+3)/21$	-21730896	$(-9-87^6(-6-(-5-4)))^*(32+1)$
-19529728	$9*8^7*(-6-5*((4^3)^{-2-1}))$	-21772791	$9+8*7*6^6*(4+3)^{2+1}$
-19534374	$-9/8*((7-65^4-4^3)^{2-1})$	-21772809	$-9+8*7*6^6*(4+3)^{2+1}$
-19591787	$((9/8)^7+6^6+5)^*-4^3(3+2+1)$	-21796777	$(9^8-7*(6-5^4(4+3)))/-2*1$
-19933396	$9*((8+7)^6-5)/(-4^3)^*21$	-21864991	$9+8/-7*((6*(5+4)^3)^{2-1})$
-19933522	$(9-((8+7)^6-5)/4)/3^*21$	-21865009	$-9+8/-7*((6/(5+4)^{-3})^{2-1})$
-19933594	$-9+((8+7)^6-5)/(-4^3)^*21$	-21869986	$98/7+(6^6)^4*3^4(2+1)$
-19933648	$(-9+((8+7)^6-5)/-4)/3^*21$	-21870014	$-98/7+(6^6)^4*3^4(2+1)$
-19933774	$(-9+((8+7)^6-5)/(-4^3))^*21$	-22071202	$((9*87*6)^6)^{-5+4+3}-2)^*-1$
-20072448	$9*8^7*(-65*4^3(-3-2)-1)$	-22071206	$((9*87*6)^6)^{-5+4+3}+2)^*-1$
-20089215	$9*(8/7*(6-5^4(4+3+2))+1)$	-22114942	$(9*8+7)/-6^6(5-4*3)+2^1$
-20102652	$(-9+8*7)/-654^4(-3+2)-1$	-22114946	$(9*8+7)/-6^6(5-4*3)-2^1$
-20132688	$(-9-8^7+6)/5*((4+3)^{2-1})$	-22133945	$(9/8-7)*((6^6/5+4-3)^{2-1})$
-20134071	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3)/2-1)$	-22155840	$-9*((((87*6+5)-4)^3)^{2-1})$
-20134089	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3)/2+1)$	-22155858	$-9*((((87*6+5)-4)^3)^{2+1})$
-20259632	$(9/8-7)*(((-6+5^4)^3)^{2-1})$	-22183927	$9-8^7*(6+5-(4/3)^{-2-1})$
-20413314	$(9-8^7(-6-(-5-4)))^*(32-1)$	-22183945	$-9-8^7*(6+5-(4/3)^{-2-1})$
-20413584	$9-87^6(-6-(-5-4))^*(32-1)$	-22207779	$-9/8*((7/(-6^6/5+4+3))^{2-1})$
-20413602	$-9-87^6(-6-(-5-4))^*(32-1)$	-22270997	$(9/8-7)*((6^6/5+4+3)^{2-1})$
-20413872	$(-9-87^6(-6-(-5-4)))^*(32-1)$	-22320529	$(9-8)^*-7*(6*(5+4)^3(3+2)+1)$
-20475319	$((9-8-7-65)^4+3)/-21$	-22320564	$(9-8)^*-7*6*((5+4)^3(3+2)+1)$
-20528733	$(9/(8*7)-6)*((5^4)^3)^{2-1}$	-22373568	$-9*(8^7+6^6*(4+3)^{2+1})$
-20571768	$(-9-8)^*(7*6)^5/4^3(2-1)$	-22588158	$(9/(-8*((76-5)^4-3+2))^{-1})$
-20578304	$(9/8*(7+6)+5)^*-4^3(3+2+1)$	-22667085	$9-((8-7*(6+5))^4-3^4(2+1))$
-20591512	$((9-8)/7-6)*((5^4)^3)^{2-1}$	-22667089	$((9+8*7*6)/5)^4(4-32)^*-1$
-20719152	$(9*876)^{-5+4+3}/(-2-1)$	-22667153	$((9+8*7*6)/5)^4+32)^*-1$
-20818314	$-9*(8^7-6-(5^4*3)^{-2+1})$	-22667157	$-9-((8-7*(6+5))^4+3^4(2+1))$
-20818422	$-9*(8^7+6+(5^4*3)^{-2+1})$	-22671360	$9*8^7*6/5*(-4^4(-3-2)-1)$
-21052757	$(9/8-7)*(((-6-5^4)^3)^{2-1})$	-22738364	$(9^8+7+(6^6)^4)^3/-2*1$
-21053340	$98*7*6*5*(-4^4(3+2)+1)$	-22857141	$9+(-8/7-6)*((5^4)^{(3+2)+1})$
-21080493	$9^4((-8+7)+6)^*(-5-4^3)^*21$	-22857159	$-9+(-8/7-6)*((5^4)^{(3+2)+1})$
-21086208	$((-9-8)^*76+5)/4^4(-3^2-1)$	-22918350	$(-9/8-7*6)*((5+4)^{(3+2)-1})$
-21093753	$9/(-8+7)-6*((5^4)^3)^{2-1}$	-23046135	$9+8^7*(6+5)^*(4^4(-3-2)-1)$
-21094500	$98*7*6*5*(4^4(3+2)+1)$	-23046153	$-9+8^7*(6+5)^*(4^4(-3-2)-1)$
-21094721	$-9^8+(7*6*5*4/3)^{(2+1)}$	-23058423	$9-8^7*(6-5*(4^4(-3-2)-1))$
-21127554	$9/(8*(7+6))*((-5^4)^3)^{2-1}$	-23058441	$(-9-8^7*(6-5*(4^4(-3-2)-1)))$
-21139776	$98*7*6*5*(4-3^4(-2-1))$	-23063158	$((9+8)/((7*6)^5-4)^3)^{-1}$
-21140217	$9*-87*((6^5)^4(4-3)+2)-1$	-23078903	$9-8^7*(6+5*(4^4(-3-2)+1))$
-21141783	$9*87*((6^5)^4(4-3)+2)-1$	-23078921	$-9-8^7*(6+5*(4^4(-3-2)+1))$
-21233178	$9*((8^7+6)-54)/(3^4-2-1)$	-23091191	$9-8^7*(6+5*(4^4(-3-2)+1))$
-21234150	$-9*(8^7-6+54)/(-3^4-2+1)$	-23091209	$-9-8^7*(6+5*(4^4(-3-2)+1))$
-21249902	$(9^8-7*(6+5^4(4+3)))/-2*1$	-23246208	$-9*8^7*(6+(-5/4)^3(3+2+1))$
-21250048	$((-9-8)^*76+5)/-4^4(-3^2-1)$	-23362029	$-9/8*((7*(654-3))^2-1)$
-21381344	$((9*8+7-6-5)^4-32)^*-1$	-23436996	$9*8*(7+(-6/5^4(4-(-3-2))))^{-1}$
-21381408	$((9*8+7-6-5)^4+32)^*-1$	-23438004	$-9*8*(7+(-6/5^4(4-(-3-2))))^{-1}$
-21393603	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3)-21)$	-23544594	$(-9-8/7)*6*((-5^4+3)^{2-1})$
-21393765	$-9*(8^7+6^6(-5+4*3)-2-1)$	-23546952	$-9/8*((-7*654+3)^{2-1})$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-23569056	$(-9+8)^* - 7*6^5 * (-432 - 1)$	-25628652	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 + 3^{(2+1)}$
-23608755	$-9/8 * ((7*654+3)^2 - 1)$	-25628679	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 + 3^{2+1}$
-23626512	$-9/(87+6) * ((5^4(4*3) - 2) + 1)$	-25628733	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 - (3 - 21)$
-23794650	$-9/8 * ((7*654+3)^2 - 1)$	-25628805	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 + 3^{2+1}$
-23817657	$(-9/((8*7+65)^4 + 32))^{\wedge -1}$	-25628823	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 - (-3^{2+1})$
-23876208	$-9*8/7 * (6 * ((-5^4+3)^2 - 1))$	-25628832	$-9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / 4 + 3^* 21$
-23876280	$9*8/7 * (-6/((-5^4+3)^{\wedge -2} - 1))$	-25628840	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 + 3^* 2) + 1$
-23913215	$-9 * (8^7 + 6^{\wedge (-5+4*3)} * 2) + 1$	-25628841	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 + 3^* 2)^{\wedge 1}$
-23913217	$-9 * (8^7 + 6^{\wedge (-5+4*3)} * 2) - 1$	-25628847	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 + 3) + 21$
-23953399	$9 - 8^7 * (6 + 5 + (4/3)^{\wedge (-2 - 1)})$	-25628859	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 + 3 + 2 - 1)$
-23953417	$-9 - 8^7 * (6 + 5 + (4/3)^{\wedge (-2 - 1)})$	-25628868	$-9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / 4 + 3^{\wedge (2+1)}$
-24009968	$((9 - 8 - 76 + 5)^4 - 32)^* - 1$	-25628877	$-9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / 4 - (3 - 21)$
-24009995	$((9 - 8 - 76 + 5)^4 - 3 - 2)^* - 1$	-25628892	$-9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / 4 + 3 / (2 - 1)$
-24010005	$((9 - 8 - 76 + 5)^4 + 3 + 2)^* - 1$	-25628948	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 - 3^* 2) + 1$
-24010032	$((9 - 8 - 76 + 5)^4 + 32)^* - 1$	-25628950	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 - 3^* 2) - 1$
-24030270	$9*8^7*6^5 * (-4^{\wedge (3+2)} + 1)$	-25628958	$-9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / 4 - 3^* 21$
-24071190	$(-9 + 8 - 7^{\wedge 6}) / -5 * (-4^{\wedge (3+2)} + 1)$	-25628967	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 - 3^{2+1}$
-24077250	$9* - 8^7 * 6^5 * (4^{\wedge (3+2)} + 1)$	-25628985	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 - (3^{2+1})$
-24107127	$9 - 8/7 * 6 * ((5^4 * 3)^2 - 1)$	-25629057	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 + 3 - 21)$
-24107145	$-9 - 8/7 * 6 * ((5^4 * 3)^2 - 1)$	-25629111	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 - (3 + 21)$
-24128928	$9*8^7 * -6^{\wedge 5} * (4 - 3^{\wedge (-2 - 1)})$	-25629138	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 - 3^{\wedge (2+1)}$
-24135720	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} - 43^2)^* - 1$	-25629174	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 - (32 - 1)$
-24136545	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} - 4^{\wedge (3+2)})^* - 1$	-25629192	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 - (32 + 1)$
-24137425	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} - (4*3)^2)^* - 1$	-25629462	$9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / -4 - 3^* 21)$
-24137441	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} - 4^* 32)^* - 1$	-25701231	$-9 * ((8+7)^6 - 5) / 4 + 3) / 21$
-24137483	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} - 43^2)^* - 1$	-25716159	$(9*8+7) / -6 * (5^{\wedge (4+3+2)} + 1)$
-24137503	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} - 4^{\wedge 3 - 2})^* - 1$	-25728635	$(9 / ((8^7 * 6 - 5^{\wedge (4*3)} - 2))^{\wedge -1})$
-24137507	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} - 4^{\wedge 3 + 2})^* - 1$	-25804807	$(9 - 8)^* - 7 * ((6^5 * 4^{\wedge 3})^2 + 1)$
-24137520	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} - (4+3)^2)^* - 1$	-25907700	$(9 / -8 - 7)^* 6 * ((5+4)^{\wedge (3*2)} - 1)$
-24137524	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} - 43 - 2)^* - 1$	-26157924	$-9 / (8+76) * ((5^{\wedge (4*3)} - 2) + 1)$
-24137528	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} - 43 + 2)^* - 1$	-26372360	$(-9+8)^* 7 * ((-6^{\wedge 5} / 4 + 3)^2 - 1)$
-24137533	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} - 4 - 32)^* - 1$	-26476157	$(9+8)^{\wedge (-7+6+5)} * (4 - 321)$
-24137556	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} - 4 - 3^2)^* - 1$	-26535656	$(-9+8)^* 7 * ((6^{\wedge 5} / 4 + 3)^2 - 1)$
-24137582	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} + 4 + 3^2)^* - 1$	-26578062	$((-9 * (8+7)^{\wedge -6})^{\wedge (-5+4)} + 3)^* 21$
-24137605	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} + 4 + 32)^* - 1$	-26578188	$((-9 * (8+7)^{\wedge -6})^{\wedge (-5+4)} - 3)^* 21$
-24137610	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} + 43 - 2)^* - 1$	-26585979	$(-9 / (8^7 - (6 - 5^{\wedge 4})^{\wedge 3}))^{\wedge (-2+1)}$
-24137614	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} + 43 + 2)^* - 1$	-26697889	$(9+8 + (-76 - 5) / 4^{\wedge -3})^2 * -1$
-24137618	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} + (4+3)^2)^* - 1$	-26729993	$(9 - 8)^* 7 + (6^5)^{\wedge 4} * (-32 - 1)$
-24137631	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} + 4^{\wedge 3 - 2})^* - 1$	-26730231	$(9 - 8)^* (-7 - (6^5)^{\wedge 4}) * (32 + 1)$
-24137635	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} + 4^{\wedge 3 + 2})^* - 1$	-26794131	$98 * 7 * ((6 - 5^{\wedge (4+3)}) / 2 + 1)$
-24137655	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} + 43^2)^* - 1$	-26795503	$98 * 7 * ((6 - 5^{\wedge (4+3)}) / 2 - 1)$
-24137697	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} + 4^* 32)^* - 1$	-26798247	$98 * 7 * ((-6 - 5^{\wedge (4+3)}) / 2 + 1)$
-24137713	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} + (4*3)^2)^* - 1$	-26799619	$98 * 7 * ((-6 - 5^{\wedge (4+3)}) / 2 - 1)$
-24139150	$(-9+8)^* 7 * (((-6+5^{\wedge 4})^3)^2 + 1)$	-26808957	$((9+8)^{\wedge (-7 - (-6 - 5)) - 4})^* - 321$
-24139418	$((9+8)^{\wedge (7-6+5)} + 43^2)^* - 1$	-26811525	$((9+8)^{\wedge (-7 - (-6 - 5)) + 4})^* - 321$
-24186474	$((9+8)^{\wedge (-7+6+5)} + 4) / (-3^{\wedge -2} - 1)$	-26872007	$((9+8)^{\wedge (-7+6+5)} - 43^2)^* - 1$
-24213780	$9/8 * (((76+5)^4 - 3) / -2 - 1)$	-26873424	$((9+8)^{\wedge (-7+6+5)} - 432)^* - 1$
-24257450	$98 * (((-7 - 6)^{\wedge 5} + 4) / 3^2 + 1)$	-26873728	$((9+8)^{\wedge (-7+6+5)} - 4^{\wedge 3 * 2})^* - 1$
-24257646	$98 * (((-7 - 6)^{\wedge 5} + 4) / 3^2 - 1)$	-26873984	$((9+8)^{\wedge (-7+6+5)} - 4^{\wedge 3 * 2})^* - 1$
-24310062	$((-98 - 7)^{\wedge (-6 - (-5 - 4)) + 3}) * 21$	-26875705	$((9+8)^{\wedge (-7+6+5)} + 43^2)^* - 1$
-24310188	$((-98 - 7)^{\wedge (-6 - (-5 - 4)) - 3}) * 21$	-26877952	$((9+8)^{\wedge (-7+6+5)} + 4^{\wedge (3*2)})^* - 1$
-24504534	$9 * (8 + (-7*6)^{\wedge 5} / ((4+3)^2 - 1))$	-26946115	$(9 - 8)^* - 7 * ((654*3)^2 + 1)$
-24504678	$-9 * (8 + (-7*6)^{\wedge 5} / ((4+3)^2 - 1))$	-27043713	$-9^{\wedge 8} - (-7*6^{\wedge 4} * ((-5+4)+3))^{\wedge (2+1)}$
-24579936	$9*8^7 * -6^{\wedge 5} * (4+3^{\wedge (-2 - 1)})$	-27126734	$(9 / (8+7 - ((-6+5^{\wedge (4*3)} + 2)))^{\wedge -1})$
-25053600	$(-9+8/7)^* 6 * ((5+4)^{\wedge (3*2)} - 1)$	-27126743	$(9 / (-8*7 - (6+5^{\wedge (4*3)})))^{\wedge (-2+1)}$
-25084150	$(-9+8)^* 7 * (((-6 - 5^{\wedge 4})^3)^2 + 1)$	-27144325	$(9+8)^{\wedge (-7+6+5)} * (-4 - 321)$
-25109993	$(9 - 8)^* 7 + (6^5)^{\wedge 4} * (-32 + 1)$	-27156528	$-9/8 * 7 * (((-6+5^{\wedge 4})^3)^2 - 1)$
-25110217	$((-9+8)^* - 7 + (6^5)^{\wedge 4}) * (-32 + 1)$	-27231313	$(9 / (-8^7 * 6 - 5^{\wedge (4*3)}))^{\wedge (-2+1)}$
-25110540	$-9/8 * 7 * 6 * ((5+4)^{\wedge (3*2)} - 1)$	-27257152	$(9 / (8 - (7 - (6 - 5^{\wedge 4})^{\wedge 3})))^{\wedge (-2+1)}$
-25165582	$((9 - 8^{\wedge 7}) + 6 + 5)^* 4 * 3 + 2^{\wedge 1}$	-27261689	$(9+8^{\wedge 7} / (-6 - 5))^* ((4*3)^2 - 1)$
-25165586	$((9 - 8^{\wedge 7}) + 6 + 5)^* 4 * 3 - 2^{\wedge 1}$	-27264263	$(-9 - 8^{\wedge 7} / (6+5))^* ((4*3)^2 - 1)$
-25166062	$((-9 - 8^{\wedge 7}) - 6 - 5)^* 4 * 3 + 2^{\wedge 1}$	-27426816	$(9+87)^{\wedge (-6+5+4)} * (-32+1)$
-25166066	$((-9 - 8^{\wedge 7}) - 6 - 5)^* 4 * 3 - 2^{\wedge 1}$	-27436644	$(9 * (-87 * 6 - 5 * 4^3))^{\wedge 2} * -1$
-25192525	$(98 * 7 - 6^{\wedge (5+4)})^* (3/2 + 1)$	-27549904	$(-9^{\wedge 8} + 7 - (6+5)) / ((4/3)^{\wedge -2} + 1)$
-25195955	$(98 * 7 + 6^{\wedge (5+4)})^* (3/2 - 1)$	-27966848	$(98/7)^{\wedge 6} * (5 / (-4 - 3) - 2 - 1)$
-25345728	$9 * -8 * (7^{\wedge 6} - 5^{\wedge (4+3)}) * (-2 - 1)$	-27989280	$9 * 8 * 76 * 5 * (-4^{\wedge (3+2)} + 1)$
-25508232	$9 * 8 * (7 - 6 * ((5+4)^{\wedge (3+2)} - 1))$	-28018640	$(-9/8 - 7)^* (((-6+5^{\wedge 4})^3)^2 - 1)$
-25509161	$(9 - 8)^* 7 - 6 / (54 * 3)^{\wedge (-2 - 1)}$	-28044000	$9 * -8 * 76 * 5 * (4^{\wedge (3+2)} + 1)$
-25510104	$9 * -8 * (7 - 6 * ((-5 - 4)^{\wedge (3+2)} - 1))$	-28119528	$9 * 8 * (76 - 5^{\wedge 4} - ((-3 - 2) + 1)))$
-25628328	$9 * (((8+7)^{\wedge 6} - 5) / -4 + 3^* 21)$	-28130472	$9 * -8 * (76 + 5^{\wedge 4} - ((-3 - 2) + 1)))$
-25628598	$9 * (((8+7)^{\wedge 6} - 5) / -4 + 32 + 1)$	-28148527	$(-9 / (8^7 + (6 + 5^{\wedge 4})^{\wedge 3}))^{\wedge (-2+1)}$
-25628616	$9 * (((8+7)^{\wedge 6} - 5) / -4 + 32 - 1)$	-28218480	$(9 * 8 - 7^{\wedge 6}) * 5 * ((4+3)^2 - 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-28219653	$-9/8*7*(((-6-5^4)*3)^2-1)$	-31842729	$9/(-8+7)-6^5*(4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
-28231680	$(9-(-8+7^6))*5*((4+3)^2-1)$	-31886951	$(9-8)*(-7-6^5)*(4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$
-28233831	$9+(8-7^6)*5*((4+3)^2-1)$	-32080069	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))*((5^4*3)^2-1)$
-28233849	$-9+(8-7^6)*5*((4+3)^2-1)$	-32089421	$(-9/(8+(7+654)^3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-28235520	$(9-8-7^6)*5*((4+3)^2-1)$	-32260527	$-9/8*((765*(4+3))^2-1)$
-28236000	$(-9+8-7^6)*5*((4+3)^2-1)$	-32341920	$(-9-8/7)*6*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
-28237671	$9+(-8-7^6)*5*((4+3)^2-1)$	-32355828	$((9-8^{\wedge}7)+6)*54/(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-28237689	$-9+(-8-7^6)*5*((4+3)^2-1)$	-32762528	$9*8*76-(5/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-28239840	$(-9-(8+7^6))*5*((4+3)^2-1)$	-32763302	$9*87*6-(5/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-28253040	$(-9*8-7^6)*5*((4+3)^2-1)$	-32763884	$98*7*6-(5/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-28349993	$(-9+8)*-7*((6*5)^4*(-3-2)+1)$	-32767757	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-(5*4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-28398209	$((9-8+7+65)^4-32)*-1$	-32768243	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-(5*4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-28398273	$((9-8+7+65)^4+32)*-1$	-32772116	$98*7*6-(5/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-28520667	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*5*(5*-4-3)*21$	-32772698	$9*87*6-(5/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-28678131	$(9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6*(-54+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-32773472	$9*8*6-(5/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-28717497	$(9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6*(-54-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-32914215	$9*(8/7*(6+(5*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
-28799055	$9*(8*(7+6)+(5*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-32914233	$-9*(8/7*(-6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
-28799073	$-9*(8*(7+6)+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-33185538	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*5(5^4-3*21)$
-28799907	$9*(8*7/6-((5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1))$	-33190857	$9*((8*-7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3)*21$
-28799925	$9*(8*7/6-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-33191361	$(9/(8*-7)^{\wedge}(6-5-4)+3)*21$
-28800075	$-9*(8*7/6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-33191487	$(-9/(8*7)^{\wedge}(6-5-4)-3)*21$
-28800093	$9*(8*-7/6-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-33191991	$9*((-8*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)-3)*21$
-28800927	$9*(8*(7+6)-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-33480741	$(9-8)*7*(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$
-28800945	$-9*(8*(7+6)-(5*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-33513480	$9*8*7*65*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-28815435	$-9/8*((7*(6+(-5-4)^{\wedge}3))^2-1)$	-33579000	$9*-8*7*65*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-28854896	$(9/(8-(7+6+5^4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-33600096	$(-9+8)^{\wedge}7*6^5*4321$
-28874961	$(9/(8-7))^{\wedge}6*(-54-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-33732729	$-9*(-8-7+((-6-5)*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$
-29020055	$((-9*8-7)+6)*5*43^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-33732855	$9*(8-7-((-6-5)*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$
-29115515	$(-9/8-7)*(((-6-5^4)*3)^2-1)$	-33732873	$-9*(8-7+((-6-5)*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$
-29179069	$(9-8*(7*6+5))^{\wedge}43^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-33732999	$9*(8-7-((-6-5)*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$
-29196288	$(-9-87)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)*(32+1)$	-33740424	$9*8*(7-6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$
-29347353	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^{\wedge}54^{\wedge}-3*21$	-33741432	$9*-8*(7+6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$
-29381850	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5)*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-33747984	$9*8*(7-(6*5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$
-29403108	$(-9+8)*76*((5^4-3)^2-1)$	-33751008	$9*8*(7-6*5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21)$
-29600550	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}5)*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-33752016	$9*-8*(7-(-6*5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$
-29622847	$9-8/-7*((6*5)^4*32+1)$	-33758568	$9*-8*(7-6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$
-29622865	$-9-8/-7*((6*5)^4*32+1)$	-33759576	$9*-8*(7-6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$
-29631688	$((9+8)/-7-6)*((5^4*3)^2-1)$	-33824713	$(-9-8)/7*((6*(-5^{\wedge}4+3))^2-1)$
-29632626	$-9*(87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))*(3+2)-1$	-34007850	$9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-29632644	$9*(-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))*(3+2)-1$	-34176978	$(-9^{\wedge}8+(((7+6)*5+4)*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-29751042	$(9/((8+7)*65^{\wedge}4-3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-34335900	$-9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-29757168	$9*8*7*(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-34344360	$9*8*(7-6*(5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
-29758176	$9*8*7*(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$	-34345368	$9*8*(7-6*(5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
-29760738	$(-9+8)*7*(6-(-54*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-34348680	$9*8*(7+6*(5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
-29763216	$-9*8*7*((6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2))-1)$	-34349688	$9*-8*(7-6*(5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
-29764224	$9*-8*7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-34471157	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6*(5*(5+4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-29779902	$-9/8*((7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3))^2-1)$	-34552071	$9*(8/7*(-6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3+2)+1)$
-29818880	$(-9+8)*7*65*4^{\wedge}(3^2-1)$	-34552089	$-9*(8/7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3-2)+1)$
-29942782	$((9*8*76)^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3)-2*-1$	-34602117	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7/6)*5*4*(-3-2)+1$
-29942786	$((9*8*76)^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3)+2*-1$	-34603899	$(9+8^{\wedge}7/6)*5*4*(-3-2)+1$
-29973108	$(-9+8)*76*((5^4+3)^2-1)$	-34712064	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7)/6^{\wedge}(-5-4)*(32-1)$
-29986544	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7)+65)^4-32)*-1$	-34722223	$(-9/((8+7*6)^{\wedge}5+4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-29986581	$((9^{\wedge}(8-7)+65)^4+32)/-1$	-34722227	$(9/((-8-7*6)^{\wedge}5-43))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-29986608	$((9/(8-7)+65)^4+32)*-1$	-34728741	$9+(((8+7)+6)*5)^4/(-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-30051684	$9*(8-7*6*(-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	-34728759	$-9+(((8+7)+6)*5)^4/(-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-30051828	$9*(8-7*6*(-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	-34877135	$98-(7/(6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-30055464	$9*(8+7*6*(-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	-34877161	$9*8-(7/(6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-30055608	$-9*(8+7*6*(-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	-34877305	$-9*8-(7/(6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-30093335	$(9/(8+(7-654)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-34877331	$-98-(7/(6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-30174039	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^{\wedge}54^{\wedge}-3*21$	-34907412	$-9*((8+7)*6+5)^{\wedge}4+3/21$
-30232941	$9*(8*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3-21$	-34996224	$(9*8*-7-6*5)*4^{\wedge}(3^2-1)$
-30233235	$-9*(8*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))/3+21$	-35016057	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)/(-5^{\wedge}4+32)^{\wedge}-1$
-30387654	$(9-(((8+7)+6)*5)^4)/(3+2-1)$	-35070082	$((987*6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)-2)*-1$
-30610775	$(-9/8-7)*((6^{\wedge}5/4-3)^2-1)$	-35269535	$(98*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-30800315	$(-9/8-7)*((6^{\wedge}5/4+3)^2-1)$	-35274337	$(98*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-30965688	$9*(8*7*6*5/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$	-35309405	$-9/8*((7^{\wedge}(-6-(-5+4)))*3)^{\wedge}-2-1$
-30965832	$-9*(8*7*6*5/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$	-35388936	$9*8*(7-6*5*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$
-31078727	$(9*876)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))/-2+1$	-35389944	$-9*8*(7-6*5*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$
-31078729	$(9*876)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))/-2-1$	-35488449	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*5(5^4-3-21)$
-31201163	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))*((5^4*3)^2-1)$	-35842743	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*5(5^4-3+21)$
-31814055	$(9-8)*(-7+6^{\wedge}5)*(-4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$	-35997551	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*(-432+1)$
-31842713	$(9-8)*7-6^{\wedge}5*(4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	-36152424	$9*8*7*(6^{\wedge}5-43^{\wedge}(2+1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-36164593	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)^{*}(-432-1)$	-40323987	$-9\wedge 8+(7*6)^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-36287993	$(9-8)^{*}7+(6*5^{-}4)^{\wedge}3*21$	-40389592	$(-9+8)^{*}76*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$
-36302839	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5/-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-40444785	$((9-8^{\wedge}7)+6)^{*}5*(4-3/21)$
-36302857	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5/-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-40497143	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5/4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-36572032	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6*(-5-(-4-3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-40497161	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5/4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-36610380	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5^{\wedge}4-3*2+1)$	-40690104	$(9-8)^{\wedge}7/-6*((5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)+1)$
-36721296	$9*8/7*(65^{\wedge}4/(-3-2)-1)$	-40768596	$9\wedge 8*((7-(6/5+4))^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$
-36728476	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(-5^{\wedge}4+3)+2/1$	-40798630	$(-9\wedge 8+(-7+6*(5*4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-36728480	$(-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(-5^{\wedge}4+3)+2)^{*}-1$	-40801426	$(9-8*((-7-6)^*5)^{\wedge}4)/(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-36787527	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5^{\wedge}4-3+2-1)$	-40959968	$((98-7-6-5)^{\wedge}4-32)^{*}-1$
-36840015	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-40960032	$((98-7-6-5)^{\wedge}4+32)^{*}-1$
-36853137	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-40987310	$(-9/8-76)^{*}((5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
-36866259	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5^{\wedge}4-(3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-40996877	$-9\wedge 8-((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)-21$
-36899064	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1)$	-41087154	$-9\wedge 8+7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)+2)+1$
-36912186	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1)$	-41087156	$-9\wedge 8+7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)+2)-1$
-36944991	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5^{\wedge}4+(3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-41087182	$-9\wedge 8-7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)+2)+1$
-36951552	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7)/6^{\wedge}(-5-4)^{*}(32+1)$	-41087184	$-9\wedge 8-7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)+2)-1$
-36964674	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5^{\wedge}4+3-2^{\wedge}1)$	-41143536	$-9*8*7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-36971235	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-41149080	$(9*8-7/6^{\wedge}(5-4*3))^*21$
-37015051	$((9*8+7-6+5)^{\wedge}4-3-2)^{*}-1$	-41152104	$(9*8-7/6^{\wedge}(5-4*3))^*21$
-37015061	$((9*8+7-6+5)^{\wedge}4+3+2)^{*}-1$	-41360976	$9/8*((7^{\wedge}6*5-5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
-37023723	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5^{\wedge}4+3-(2-1))$	-41485122	$(9-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*3*21$
-37082770	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2/1$	-41485500	$(9-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*3*21$
-37082774	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5^{\wedge}4+3)-2/1$	-41485689	$9*87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))^*3*21$
-37141821	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5^{\wedge}4+3+2-1)$	-41485878	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*3*21$
-37167918	$(-9\wedge 8-(-7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)))^*21$	-41486256	$(-9-87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4)))^*3*21$
-37168212	$-9\wedge 8+(-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*21$	-41696712	$-9*8/(765-4)^{\wedge}(-3+2-1)$
-37355520	$(9*8+7*6)^{*}-5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-41748035	$(9/8-7-6)^{*}((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-37376532	$(-9\wedge 8+7*((-6*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	-42206892	$-9\wedge 8-(-7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*(2+1)$
-37376910	$(-9\wedge 8+7*((-6*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	-42206934	$(-9\wedge 8+(-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)))^*(2+1))$
-37496115	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}-5*(4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$	-42328944	$-9*8*7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-37507050	$-9*(8+7+6)^{\wedge}5*((-4-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-42378336	$9*8*7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-37564704	$((-9+8)^*7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{*}-321$	-42456231	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(-5/(4*3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-37625728	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6*(-5-(-4-3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-42473239	$(-9\wedge 8+7*(6-5*(-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)))$
-37669632	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6*(-5+(-4-3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-42473323	$-9\wedge 8-7*(6-5/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$
-37747224	$((9-8^{\wedge}7/6)+5)^*4*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-42486834	$-9\wedge 8-(-7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*2+1$
-37747995	$((-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6+54)^*321$	-42486835	$(-9\wedge 8-(-7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*2)^{\wedge}1$
-37750248	$((-9-8^{\wedge}7/6)-5)^*4*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-42486836	$-9\wedge 8-(-7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*2-1$
-37762440	$((-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*321$	-42486862	$-9\wedge 8+(-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*2+1$
-37768218	$((-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*321$	-42486863	$(-9\wedge 8+(-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*2)^{\wedge}1$
-37850409	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(5*4^{\wedge}3+2+1)$	-42486864	$-9\wedge 8+(-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*2-1$
-37965954	$((-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*321$	-42577992	$-9*8/(765+4)^{\wedge}(-3+2-1)$
-37968507	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(-5^{\wedge}4+3-21)$	-42633371	$-9\wedge 8-7*((-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$
-37988685	$-9/8*((-7+6^{\wedge}5/4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-42633385	$-9\wedge 8-7*((-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
-38122980	$98*(7-(6*5+43)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-42666666	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7)^{*}-6*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
-38124352	$-98*(7+(6*5+43)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-42794721	$-9\wedge 8-7/6*(5*(5-4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-38161527	$9-(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*21$	-42818258	$-98/(7+654)^{\wedge}(-3+2)-1$
-38161545	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*21$	-42831471	$-9\wedge 8-7*6*5*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-38234300	$((-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+321)$	-42831891	$-9\wedge 8-7*6*5*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-38274677	$(9/(8-(76+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-42870321	$-9\wedge 8+(7*(6+54))^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
-38322801	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^{*}(-5^{\wedge}4-3-21)$	-42924760	$(-9\wedge 8+7*((-6-5)^*4*3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
-38403904	$9\wedge 8-(76*5/4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	-42930227	$(-9\wedge 8+7*((65+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1))$
-38539809	$-9/8*((-7-6^{\wedge}5/4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-42961671	$-9\wedge 8+7*6^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-39127610	$-9\wedge 8-7*(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*2-1$	-42987664	$(-9\wedge 8+7-(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1$
-39127624	$-9\wedge 8-7*(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*2+1$	-42987666	$(-9\wedge 8+7-(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1$
-39162564	$(98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2*1$	-42987678	$(-9\wedge 8-7-(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1$
-39361392	$9*8*-7*(-6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21)$	-42987680	$(-9\wedge 8-7-(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1$
-39367440	$9*8*7*(-6-(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21))$	-42991621	$-9\wedge 8+7*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-39371787	$9*(8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))+21)$	-43016271	$-9\wedge 8+7*6*5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-39372165	$-9*(8*7*(6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))+21)$	-43034564	$(-9\wedge 8+7)+6^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-39377835	$9*(8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))+21)$	-43034578	$-9\wedge 8-7+6^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-39378213	$-9*(8*7*(6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))+21)$	-43037684	$-9\wedge 8+7*((6*5^{\wedge}4+3+2)-1)$
-39382560	$9*8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21)$	-43037698	$(-9\wedge 8+7*((6*5^{\wedge}4+3+2)+1))$
-39388608	$9*8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21)$	-43040848	$(-9\wedge 8+7*(6*5*(4-32)-1))$
-39513796	$(98*(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2*1$	-43040902	$((-9\wedge 8-7)-6)+(54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-39529992	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}(6+5-4))/3*2+1$	-43041254	$-9\wedge 8+7*((65*4*3+2)-1)$
-39530136	$9*-8*(7^{\wedge}(6+5-4))/3*2+1$	-43041268	$(-9\wedge 8+7*((65*4*3+2)+1))$
-39546810	$-9/8*((7*(6+5))^{\wedge}4-321)$	-43042278	$-9\wedge 8-(7/(6^{\wedge}5*4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-39743823	$((-9+8)/7-6)/(5^{\wedge}(4*3)+2))^{\wedge}-1$	-43043546	$-9\wedge 8+7+6*((5*4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-39791570	$(9-8-76)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	-43044596	$-9\wedge 8+765*((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-40163912	$-9/8*((-7-6)^*5)^{\wedge}4+3)^*2+1$	-43045141	$-9\wedge 8+7+(6+5)^*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-40163914	$-9/8*((-7-6)^*5)^{\wedge}4+3)^*2-1$	-43046407	$(-9\wedge 8+7+6-5*4+321)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-43047948	$(-9^8-7)+6-(5*(4+3))^2-1$	-46463125	$(9+8)/-7*((6/(5+4)^{-3})^2-1)$
-43048301	$(-9^8-7+(-6-5)*((4^3)^2-1))$	-46530560	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))*5*4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
-43048813	$-9^8-7/(6+5)^4+3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-46621044	$((9-8-7)*654^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-43048846	$(-9^8-765*((4/3)^2+1))$	-46655993	$(9-8)^*7+(6*5^*-4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-43049896	$(-9^8-7)-6*((5^*4+3)^2-1)$	-46965818	$-9^8-7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^2-1$
-43051164	$-9^8+7/(-6^{\wedge}5^*4+3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-46965832	$-9^8-7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^2+1$
-43052174	$-9^8-7*((65^*4^*3-2)+1)$	-47764080	$(9/8+7)/-6^{\wedge}(5-4^*3)^*21$
-43052188	$(-9^8-7*((65^*4^*3+2)-1))$	-47829683	$-9^8+7+(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$
-43052540	$(-9^8+7)+6-(54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-47829697	$(-9^8-7+(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1))$
-43052594	$-9^8-7*(6^*-5*(4-32)-1)$	-47841280	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))*5*4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
-43055744	$-9^8-7*((6^*5^*43-2)+1)$	-48093741	$9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6*((-5+(4/3)^2)-1)$
-43055758	$(-9^8-7*((6^*5^*43+2)-1))$	-48093750	$(9*(8+7)^{\wedge}-6/(5-43))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-43058864	$(-9^8+7-6^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1))$	-48716532	$-9^8-7*((-6^*5)^4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-43058878	$-9^8-7-6^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-48716910	$-9^8-7*((-6^*5)^4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-43077171	$-9^8+7*6^*-5*((4^3)^2+1)$	-48779283	$(-9/8*7-6)*((5^4*3)^2-1)$
-43101821	$-9^8+76^*-5*((4^3)^2+1)$	-48796810	$(9-8/7^{\wedge}(-6+5))^{\wedge}4*(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-43105762	$(-9^8+7+(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1$	-48925230	$-9^8-(-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*21$
-43105764	$(-9^8+7+(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1$	-48925524	$-9^8+(-7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*21$
-43105776	$(-9^8-7+(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1$	-49064832	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*(2+1)$
-43105778	$(-9^8-7+(-6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1$	-49071033	$9/87*((6-5^4)^{\wedge}3^*2-1)$
-43131771	$-9^8+7*6^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-49538900	$(-9-(8/7)^{\wedge}-6)*5*4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
-43163215	$-9^8-7*((65+4^{\wedge}3)^2+1)$	-49658189	$(-9/8-7-6)*((5^4*3)^2-1)$
-43168682	$-9^8-7*(((-6-5)^*4^*3)^2-1)$	-49787134	$((9-87-6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)-2)^*-1$
-43261551	$-9^8-7*6^*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-49787138	$((9-87-6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)+2)^*-1$
-43261971	$-9^8-7*6^*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-49918839	$9+(-8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*21$
-43298721	$-9^8-7/6*(5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-49918857	$-9+(-8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*21$
-43388569	$((9*8*(7+6)+5)*4+3)^2/-1$	-50073552	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)-6)^*54^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
-43460057	$-9^8-7*((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$	-50319351	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5-(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$
-43460071	$-9^8-7*((6/54)^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$	-50319369	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5-(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$
-43582032	$-9*(8*7+6)*5*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21)$	-50331354	$(98-((-7+6)+5)^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*(2+1)$
-43605468	$9*(8*7+6)*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-21)$	-50331942	$(98+((-7+6)+5)^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*(-2-1)$
-43606578	$-9^8-(-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2+1$	-50343927	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5-(-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$
-43606579	$(-9^8-(-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2)^{\wedge}1$	-50343945	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5-(-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$
-43606580	$-9^8-(-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2-1$	-50528513	$(-9/(8+(765+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-43606606	$-9^8+(-7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2+1$	-50704564	$((-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(432-1)$
-43606607	$(-9^8+(-7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2)^{\wedge}1$	-50822209	$((-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*432-1$
-43606608	$-9^8+(-7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2-1$	-50898204	$(-9-8)^*7/654^{\wedge}(-3+2)-1$
-43620119	$(-9^8+7*(6-5/4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)))$	-50939852	$((-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(432+1)$
-43620203	$-9^8-7*(6-5/-4^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1))$	-51029730	$9*((8-7*((6^*5)^4-3)+2)-1)$
-43620824	$(9+8^{\wedge}7-6)*5*(5^{\wedge}(-4+3)-21)$	-51029993	$(9-8)^*7+(6^*5)^{\wedge}4^*-3^*21$
-43849730	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)*((6+5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-21)$	-51030147	$((9-8)^*-7+(6^*5)^{\wedge}4^*-3)^*21$
-43886508	$-9^8-(-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*(2+1)$	-51030270	$9*((-8-7*((6^*5)^4+3)-2)+1)$
-43886550	$(-9^8+(-7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*(2+1))$	-51294964	$(9-8)^*-7^{\wedge}6*((5+432)-1)$
-43925210	$(-9^8+76/5)*((4+3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-51380221	$((-9+8^{\wedge}-7)^*6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
-43990632	$9*8^*-7*(6^{\wedge}5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-51380227	$((-9-8^{\wedge}-7)^*6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$
-44062218	$(9-8*7)*6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3))^2-1$	-51416001	$9/8*(7-6)*((5^4*3)^2-1)$
-44062782	$(9-8*7)*6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3))^2+1$	-51499476	$-9*(87*6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)^*21$
-44130825	$(-9+8)/7*((6+5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$	-51657159	$((-9-8/7)-6)*((5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-44229887	$(9^*8+7)/-6^{\wedge}(5-4^*3))^2+1$	-51828156	$9*(8/-7*((6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3)/2)-1)$
-44229889	$(9^*8+7)/-6^{\wedge}(5-4^*3))^2-1$	-51916464	$-9^8+(((7-6)^*5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-44231032	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)*((-6-5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-21)$	-51963120	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)+6)^*-54^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
-44342871	$((-9+8/7)-6)*((5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-52200593	$((9+87-6-5)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-44459686	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7+6)*5*(5^{\wedge}(-4+3)+21)$	-52200657	$((9+87-6-5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-44832940	$(-9+(8/7)^{\wedge}-6)*5*4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$	-52234400	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5)*((4/3)^2+1)$
-45006258	$-9^8+7*(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3)+2)+1$	-52320000	$(9-8*7*6)*(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
-45006260	$-9^8+7*(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3)+2)-1$	-52623200	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}5)*((4/3)^2+1)$
-45006286	$-9^8-7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3)+2)+1$	-52727993	$(9-8)^*7+(65^*4)^{\wedge}3^*-2-1$
-45006288	$-9^8-7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3)+2)-1$	-52926615	$-9/8*((7-6^*5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
-45096565	$-9^8+((76+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$	-52930800	$-9*87/(65^*4)^{\wedge}((-3+2)-1)$
-45120000	$(-9+8*7)*6*(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	-53187849	$(9*(-8-7)^*6*(-5-4)+3)^{\wedge}2^*-1$
-45199056	$((-9^8+7)-6)^*(5/4-(3+2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-53551749	$9*(8+7+(65^{\wedge}4+3)/(-2-1))$
-45212144	$(-9^8+76+5)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$	-53552001	$-9*(8+7+(-65^{\wedge}4+3)/(-2-1))$
-45212171	$((9-8+76+5)^{\wedge}4-3-2)^*-1$	-53616492	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(5+43*21)$
-45212181	$((9-8+76+5)^{\wedge}4+3+2)^*-1$	-53747584	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4^{\wedge}3)^*-2^{\wedge}1$
-45212208	$((9-8+76+5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$	-53747626	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-43)/-2^{\wedge}-1$
-45294812	$-9^8+((7-6*(5^*4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-53747798	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+43)/-2^{\wedge}-1$
-45438120	$-9/8*76*((5+4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$	-53747840	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4^{\wedge}3)^*-2^{\wedge}1$
-45643536	$((9*(8*7+6)+5)^*4^*3)^2/-1$	-53926704	$9*(8/7*(6-5^*4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)))$
-45769455	$-9^8-(7^*6)^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^2-1)$	-54225971	$((9-8^{\wedge}7)+6)^*543/21$
-45855612	$9*8*((-6-5)^{\wedge}4*((-3-2)+1))$	-54253471	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7)*((-6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*-2-1)$
-46373600	$-98*7/(65^*4)^{\wedge}((-3+2)-1)$	-54398691	$(9+8)^*(76-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-46453434	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7-6)/(-5-4-(3^*-2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-54398725	$(-9-8)^*(-76-(5^*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-54399269	$(9+8)^*(7*6+(5*-4)^(3+2)+1)$	-60170931	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))/1$
-54399303	$(-9-8)^*(-7*6+(5*4)^(3+2)+1)$	-60204032	$((-9-(-8-7))^*-6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$
-54400697	$(9+8)^*(-7*6-(5*4)^(3+2)+1)$	-60402012	$(-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-54400731	$(-9-8)^*(7*6-(5*-4)^(3+2)+1)$	-60412242	$(9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)+5)^*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-54401275	$(9+8)^*(-76+(5*-4)^(3+2)+1)$	-60445629	$9^*((-8/(7-6*5))^{\wedge}-4*3+2)+1)$
-54401309	$(-9-8)^*(76+(5*4)^(3+2)+1)$	-60445683	$9^*((-8*(7-6*5))^{\wedge}4*3-2)-1)$
-54534256	$98*7*(6-(-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	-60465701	$(9*8+7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*3*2+1$
-54549348	$98*7*(6-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-60465703	$(9*8+7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*3*2-1$
-54542488	$98*-7*(6-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-60466087	$9^*(-8-(7-6^{\wedge}(5+4)))/-3*2-1$
-54549348	$98*7*(6-(-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$	-60466265	$9^*(-8-(7+6^{\wedge}(5+4)))/3*2+1$
-54587519	$(9/-8-7)^*6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3*2+1$	-60496356	$-9^*((8*(7+6)+5)^{\wedge}4+3)/21$
-54587521	$(9/-8-7)^*6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3*2-1$	-60520100	$(-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-54684182	$(9-8)^*-7*((65*43)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-60530350	$(-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)-5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-54700784	$((9-(8+7)^*6-5)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$	-60682689	$-9^{\wedge}8+7/(-6^{\wedge}(-5-4)^*(3+2)-1)$
-54700848	$((9-(8+7)^*6-5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$	-60728320	$((-9-(-8-7))^*-6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$
-54857142	$(-9+8)/7*6*((5*4)^(3*2)-1)$	-60805111	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1)$
-55200000	$(-9-8*7*6)^*(5*4)^(3+2)-1$	-60805129	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1)$
-554272702	$((98*76)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)-2)^*-1$	-60829687	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1)$
-55792800	$(9-8)^*7*6^{\wedge}5*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-60829705	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1)$
-56003862	$(9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6)^*(5-(4*3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-61519689	$-9/8*7*((65*43)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-56010523	$(9*(8-(7*6)^{\wedge}5+4)-3)/21$	-61533447	$(9*87^{\wedge}(-6-(-5+4))^*-3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-56010533	$(-9*(8-(-7*6)^{\wedge}5+4)+3)/21$	-61865981	$((-9+8^{\wedge}7)^*-6+5)^*-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-56388711	$(9*8^{\wedge}7-(6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)))*(-2-1)$	-61865987	$((-9-8^{\wedge}7)^*-6+5)^*-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-56388747	$(9*8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)))*(-2-1)$	-62029815	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*5-(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-56752216	$(-9-(8/7+6))^*((5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-62029833	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*5-(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-56753858	$-98/(765-4)^{\wedge}((-3+2)-1)$	-62128128	$(9-87*(6+5))^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-56857461	$(9*8^{\wedge}7-(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)))*(-2-1)$	-62157454	$((9*876)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)-2)^*-1$
-56857497	$(9*8^{\wedge}7+6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)))*(-2-1)$	-62245368	$9*87*(6-(-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
-56888888	$(-9/8)^{\wedge}(-7+6)*((5*4)^(3*2)-1)$	-62253198	$9*87*(6-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-57606135	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+(-4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-62254764	$9*-87*(6-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-57606153	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+(-4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-62262594	$9*-87*(6-(-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
-57614396	$-98*7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-62417744	$((-9^{\wedge}8+7)-6)^*(5/4+(3+2)^{\wedge}-1)$
-57681624	$-98*7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-62742209	$((9+8+7+65)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-57902298	$(9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6)^*(5+(4*3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-62742273	$((9+8+7+65)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-57904121	$(9*-8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3)^*2+1$	-62783479	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-(-2+1)))$
-57904123	$(9*-8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3)^*2-1$	-62853111	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6*5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$
-57953378	$-98/(765+4)^{\wedge}((-3+2)-1)$	-62853129	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*6*5*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$
-58319640	$9*8*(7-(((6*5)^{\wedge}4+3)-2)-1)$	-62865399	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$
-58320648	$9*8*(-7-(((6*5)^{\wedge}4+3)-2)-1)$	-62865417	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$
-58368609	$-9/8*((7/(6-5))^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-62906359	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$
-58460001	$(9*8*-7+(6+5)^{\wedge}(4+3))^*(-2-1)$	-62906377	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$
-58463025	$(9*8*-7-(6+5)^{\wedge}(4+3))^*(2+1)$	-62913783	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$
-58593753	$9/(-8+7)-6*(5^{\wedge}(4*3-2)-1)$	-62913801	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$
-58720229	$9*((-8^{\wedge}7*(6/5+4+3)+2)+1)$	-62915319	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$
-58720283	$9*((-8^{\wedge}7*(6/5+4+3)-2)-1)$	-62915337	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1))$
-59049729	$-9^{\wedge}8+(-7*6^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-62922743	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(-6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$
-59265270	$9*87^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)*(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-62922761	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(-6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$
-59630203	$-9+8*7-6*(5*43)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-62963703	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$
-59630243	$(9-8)^*7-6/(5*43)^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	-62963721	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$
-59630297	$9+8*-7-6*(5*43)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-62975991	$9-8^{\wedge}7*6*5*(-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$
-59768643	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3)+21)$	-62976009	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*6*5*(-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)-1)$
-59768811	$9*8^{\wedge}7*(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4)-3)+21$	-63045623	$9+8^{\wedge}7*(-6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-(-2+1)))$
-59768829	$9*-8^{\wedge}7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3)+2+1$	-63045641	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*(-6*5-4^{\wedge}(-3-(-2+1)))$
-59768830	$9*-8^{\wedge}7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3)+2^{\wedge}1$	-63307776	$((-9-87*(6+5))^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-59768834	$9*-8^{\wedge}7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3)-2*1$	-63799287	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*5+(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-59768835	$(-9*8^{\wedge}7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4)+3)-2)-1$	-63799305	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*5+(4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-59768853	$9*8^{\wedge}7*(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4)-3)-21$	-63905303	$(-9+8)^*-7*(6-5*43)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-59769021	$9*(8^{\wedge}7*(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4)-3)-21)$	-63999756	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2)+1$
-59800503	$(9-(((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3))^*21$	-63999757	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2+1)$
-59800629	$(9-(((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3))^*21$	-63999758	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2)+1$
-59800683	$9-(((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3))^*21$	-64000242	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2)+1$
-59800701	$9-(((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3))^*21$	-64000243	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2)*1$
-59800733	$(9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3+2))+1$	-64000244	$-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1$
-59800735	$(9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3+2))-1$	-64046656	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2))/-1$
-59800809	$9+(((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4-3))^*21$	-64181376	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*(2+1)$
-59800827	$9+(((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4-3))^*21$	-64262144	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2))^*-1$
-59800881	$(-9+(((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4+3))^*21$	-64998721	$-9^{\wedge}8-(7*6*5*4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-59801007	$(9-(((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4+3))^*-21$	-64999415	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1)$
-59861169	$(9-8*-7*6*(5*4+3))^{\wedge}2*-1$	-64999433	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1)$
-59969504	$((9+8+76-5)^{\wedge}4-32)/-1$	-65023991	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1)$
-59969568	$((9+8+76-5)^{\wedge}4+32)*-1$	-65024009	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1)$
-59978633	$(9+8^{\wedge}7-6)/-5*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-65343558	$(-98+(7*6)^{\wedge}((-5-4)+3))^*-21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-65345259	$(-9-8+(7*6)^(5-4+3))*-21$	-74805196	$((98^(7-6)-5)^(4-3-2))*-1$
-65345973	$(-9-8-(7*6)^(5-4+3))*21$	-74805199	$((9+8+76)^(5-4+3)-2)*-1$
-65347674	$(-98-(7*6)^(5-4+3))*21$	-74805203	$((9+8+76)^(5-4+3)+2)*-1$
-65383397	$(-9+8)*((-7-6)^(5^4-3))^(2-1)$	-74805206	$((98^(7-6)-5)^(4+3+2))*-1$
-66355200	$9*(-8-7)*6*5*4^(3*2+1)$	-74805233	$((98^(7-6)-5)^(4+3+2))*-1$
-66787902	$-9/8*((7-(6^5-4^3))^(2-1))$	-75110328	$(-9+(8-7)/6)*54^(-3-2+1)$
-66961557	$9+(8/7*-6*54^(-3-2))^(2-1)$	-75413793	$-9/87*((6*5)^(4*3/2)-1)$
-66961575	$-9+(8/7*-6*54^(-3-2))^(2-1)$	-75466341	$(9*8^7-6^5)*-4+3^(2+1)$
-67030830	$-9/8*((7+6^5-4^3)^(2-1))$	-75466395	$(9*8^7-6^5)*-4-3^(2+1)$
-67106176	$((9-8^7/6)+5)*4^3*(2+1)$	-75485175	$9-8^7*6*(5-4^(-3-2)+1)$
-67111552	$((-9-8^7/6)-5)*4^3*(2+1)$	-75485193	$-9-8^7*6*(5-4^(-3-2)+1)$
-67354624	$(98*7*-6+5)/4^(-3*2-1)$	-75497325	$(-9*8^7+6*5)*4+3^(2+1)$
-67518464	$(98*7*6+5)/-4^(-3*2-1)$	-75497379	$(-9*8^7+6*5)*4-3^(2+1)$
-67692429	$-9/8*((7-6^5-4^3)^(2-1))$	-75497565	$(-9*8^7-6*5)*4+3^(2+1)$
-67878725	$-9/8*((7-(6^5-4/3))^(2-1))$	-75497619	$(-9*8^7-6*5)*4-3^(2+1)$
-67925339	$-9/8*((7-(6^5+4/3))^(2-1))$	-75509751	$9-8^7*6*(5+4^(-3-2)+1)$
-67936995	$-9/8*((7+6^5-4^3)^(2-1))$	-75509769	$-9-8^7*6*(5+4^(-3-2)+1)$
-68111955	$(-9+8*((7-6^5+4^3)^(2-1)))$	-75523671	$9^((8-7)+6)*5(5-4*321)$
-68170325	$-9/8*((7+6^5+4/3)^(2-1))$	-75528549	$(9*8^7+6^5)*-4+3^(2+1)$
-68222967	$9-8^7*6*(5-(-4/3)^(2-1))$	-75528603	$(9*8^7+6^5)*-4-3^(2+1)$
-68222985	$-9-8^7*6*(5-(-4/3)^(2-1))$	-76114161	$-9^((8-7)+6)*5(5+4*321)$
-68357277	$-9/8*((7+6^5+4^3)^(2-1))$	-76527457	$(-9+8*7)-(6*54^(-3-2))^(2-1)$
-68389767	$((-9-8)^(7+65))/(4*3)*2+1$	-76527490	$98/7-(6*54^(-3-2))^(2-1)$
-68389769	$((-9-8)^(7+65))/(4*3)*2-1$	-76527518	$-98/7-(6*54^(-3-2))^(2-1)$
-68574929	$((98-7*(6-5))^(4-3+2))*-1$	-76527551	$9-8*7-(6*54^(-3-2))^(2-1)$
-68574959	$((98-7)^(6+5-4-3)-2)*-1$	-76886496	$-9*((8+7)^(6-5)/4*3-21)$
-68574963	$((98-7)^(6+5-4-3)+2)*-1$	-76886604	$9*((8+7)^(6-5)/-4+3)*(2+1)$
-68574966	$((98-7*(6-5))^(4+3+2))*-1$	-76886685	$-9*((8+7)^(6-5)/4*3^(2-1))$
-68574993	$((98-7*(6-5))^(4+3+2))*-1$	-76886766	$-9*((8+7)^(6-5)/4+3)*(2+1)$
-68868024	$((9+8)^(7/6-5))/(4*3)^(2-1)$	-76886874	$9*((8+7)^(6-5)/-4*3-21)$
-68891071	$9-8/7*((6^5-4^3)^(2-1))$	-76890112	$(9*87*-6+5)/4^(-3*2-1)$
-68891089	$-9-8/7*((6^5-4^3)^(2-1))$	-77053952	$(9*87*6+5)/-4^(-3*2-1)$
-68904192	$(98-7*6*5^(4+3))*21$	-77590386	$(-9-8^(-7+6))/54^(-3-(2-1))$
-68904738	$(9*8-7*6*5^(4+3))*21$	-77662265	$(9-8)/-7*((6^5-4^3)^(2-1))$
-68907762	$(9*-8-7*6*5^(4+3))*21$	-77923954	$-9^8-(7/(6+5^4*3))^(2-1)$
-68908308	$(-98-7*6*5^(4+3))*21$	-77944680	$(-9-(8-7)/6)*54^(-3-2+1)$
-68979831	$9-8/7*((-6^5+4+3)^(2-1))$	-78051708	$(9*8*(7*-6)-5/43)^(2-1)$
-68979849	$-9-8/7*((-6^5+4+3)^(2-1))$	-78159735	$((-9-8)^(7+65))*4-3/21$
-69025374	$-9/8*((7-(6^5+4^3))^(2-1))$	-78193773	$9*((-8^7+6)-5)*(4+3/21)$
-69228663	$9-8/7*((6^5+4+3)^(2-1))$	-78624647	$9-8^7-(6*54^(-3-2))^(2-1)$
-69228681	$-9-8/7*((6^5+4+3)^(2-1))$	-78624665	$-9-8^7-(6*54^(-3-2))^(2-1)$
-69272334	$-9/8*((7+6^5+4^3)^(2-1))$	-79066611	$9^((8-7)+6)*5(5-4*3*21)$
-69500673	$-9^8-7/(6^5-4^3)^(3-2+1)$	-79114432	$(-9-8^7(6-5+4))/(3*21)$
-69568667	$(-9+8)*7*(6-(-5*43)^(2+1))$	-79355136	$(-9^((8-7)+6)+5)*4^3*21$
-69866496	$-9*(8*76)^(5+4+3)*21$	-79368576	$9^((8-7)+6)+5)*4^3*21$
-70431261	$9/((-8-76^5/4)+3)^(2-1)$	-79378628	$98*((7-(6*5)^(4+3+2))+1)$
-70543675	$(9-(-8/7+6^(5+4)))/3*21$	-79381372	$-98*((7+(6*5)^(4+3+2))+1)$
-70543691	$(9+(-8/7-6^(5+4)))/3*21$	-79657101	$-9^((8-7)+6)*5(5+4^3*21)$
-70544053	$(-9+(8/7-6^(5+4)))/3*21$	-80616080	$(98*7-6^(5+4))*3^(2-1)$
-70544069	$(-9-(8/7+6^(5+4)))/3*21$	-80621120	$9*(8*7-6^(5+4))*3^(-3^2+1)$
-70546119	$(-9+8)*7*(6^(5+4)+321)$	-80622016	$-9*(8*7+6^(5+4))*3^(-3^2+1)$
-70992841	$9+(8+7*-6)^(5*(4/3)^(2-1))$	-80627056	$(98*7+6^(5+4))*3^(-3^2+1)$
-70992859	$-9+(8+7*-6)^(5*(4/3)^(2-1))$	-80627832	$(9*87+6^(5+4))*3^(-3^2+1)$
-71639264	$((98-7+6-5)^(4-3+2))*-1$	-81340992	$((-9+8)*7^6+5^(4+3))/(2-1)$
-71639328	$((98-7+6-5)^(4+3+2))*-1$	-81380183	$((-9+8)*76+5^(4+3))/(2-1)$
-71766189	$-9/8*((7+6+(-5*4)^(3))^(2-1))$	-81380246	$(9-8*(7-6)+5^(4+3))/(2-1)$
-71982000	$-9/8*((7-6-(5*4)^(3))^(2-1))$	-81380250	$((9+8)*7+6+5^(4+3))/(2-1)$
-72018000	$-9/8*((7-6+(5*4)^(3))^(2-1))$	-81450593	$((9+87-6+5)^(4-3+2))*-1$
-72029902	$98+(7*6*5)^(4/-3)^(2+1)$	-81450657	$((9+87-6+5)^(4+3+2))*-1$
-72030098	$-98+(7*6*5)^(4*3)^(2-1)$	-82031292	$(9-8)*7*6*(5^(-4+3+2)-1)$
-72234189	$-9/8*((7+6+(-5*4)^(3))^(2-1))$	-82285713	$-9/(8-7+6)*((5*4)^(3*2)-1)$
-72521552	$9*8-7*(654/3)^(2+1)$	-82485047	$(9/8-7)*((-6*5^4+3)^(2-1))$
-72521696	$-9*8-7*(654/3)^(2+1)$	-82749422	$(9/8-7)*((6*5^4+3)^(2-1))$
-72801099	$9*((-8^7+6)-5)*(4-3/21)$	-83348919	$9*(8-(7*6*5)^(4-3+2)+1)$
-73161711	$9^((8-7)+6)*5(5-4^3)*21$	-83348937	$9*(8-((7*6*5)^(4-3+2))+1)$
-73234324	$((-9+8-7^(6+5))-4)*3^(2-1)$	-83349063	$-9*(8-((7*6*5)^(4-3+2))+1)$
-74301955	$(9-8)*-7*((6*543)^(2+1))$	-83349081	$-9*(8+(7*6*5)^(4-3+2)+1)$
-74399871	$(-9-8)*((7/((6+5)^(4+3)))^(2-1))$	-83883920	$(9-8^7/6)*5*(4+3)^(2-1)$
-74399905	$(-9-8)*((7/((6+5)^(4+3)))^(2+1))$	-83885648	$(9+8^7/-6*5)*((4+3)^(2-1))$
-74430343	$9+8^7-(6*54^(-3-2))^(2-1)$	-83886512	$(-9+8^7/6-6*5)*((4+3)^(2-1))$
-74430361	$-9+8^7-(6*54^(-3-2))^(2-1)$	-83888240	$(-9-8^7/6)*5*((4+3)^(2-1))$
-74805169	$((98^(7-6)-5)^(4-3+2))*-1$	-84131840	$(9*8+7)*-65*4^(3*2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-84917781	$(9^*8^7/-6+5^4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-95781096	$-9^{\wedge}8+(7^*6*(-5-4)+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-84934651	$((9+87^{\wedge}(6-5))^{\wedge}4-3-2)^*-1$	-96017950	$-98^*(7/(6^{\wedge}(5-4*3)^2)-1)$
-84934661	$((9+87/(6-5))^{\wedge}4+3+2)^*-1$	-96018146	$98^*(7/(-6^{\wedge}(5-4*3)^2)-1)$
-84951531	$(9^*8^7/-6-5^4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-96059569	$((98+(7-6)^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-85164629	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+6)/(5-(4+3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-96059633	$((98+(7-6)^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-85207707	$-9^{\wedge}8((-8+7)+6)^*((5-43)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-96300000	$(-9-8-7-6)^{\wedge}5*(4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-85333332	$((-9+8)-7)/6*((5^4)^{\wedge}(3^2)-1)$	-97068456	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6)^*(5-(-4-3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-85343301	$9^{\wedge}8*((-7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+4)^{\wedge}-3-2/1)$	-97290156	$((9-(8^*7)^{\wedge}6)-5)/(-4+321)$
-85562000	$9^{\wedge}8*((76+5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-2)+1$	-97494775	$(-9+8)^*7*((6^*(-5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
-85562002	$9^{\wedge}8*((76+5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-2)-1$	-97535374	$-9876^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)+2^{\wedge}1$
-85764447	$9/8*((76-5)^{\wedge}4*-3-21)$	-97535378	$(-9876^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)-2)^{\wedge}1$
-86624882	$9^{\wedge}8*((-76-5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-2)+1$	-97785144	$(-9-(8+7)/6)^{\wedge}54^{\wedge}(-3-2+1)$
-86624884	$9^{\wedge}8*((-76-5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-2)-1$	-98100000	$(-9-8-7-6)^{\wedge}5*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-86669913	$(9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3^2)+1)$	-98280070	$(-9+8)^*7*((-6^*5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-86843583	$9^{\wedge}8*((7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-4)^{\wedge}-3-2^{\wedge}1)$	-98595070	$(-9+8)^*7*((6^*5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-86868980	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5+4+3)/-2^*1$	-99384775	$(-9+8)^*7*((6^*(5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
-87328125	$(-9*(8+7)^{\wedge}-6/(5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-99999968	$((98/7+6)^*5)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-87328127	$9^{\wedge}8+(-7^*6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$	-99999998	$(9+8-7)^{\wedge}(6-5+4+3)-2)^*-1$
-87660895	$9^{\wedge}8+(-7^*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$	-100000002	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}(6-5+4+3)+2)^*-1$
-88277026	$(9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4)^*(32-1)$	-100000005	$((98/7+6)^*5)^{\wedge}4+3+2)^*-1$
-88277296	$9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4*(32-1)$	-100000032	$((98/7+6)^*5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-88277314	$-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4*(32-1)$	-100528491	$((9+8)/(7*((6-5^{\wedge}(4*3))-2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-88277584	$(-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4)^*(32-1)$	-100590336	$(-9+8)^*-7*6^{\wedge}5*(-43^{\wedge}2+1)$
-88529249	$((9+87+6-5)^{\wedge}4-32)/-1$	-100769130	$(9^*87-6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-88529313	$(9+87+6-5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$	-100770100	$(98^*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-88783860	$((-9^{\wedge}8+7)-6)^*((5/4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-100776400	$9*(8^*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-88941255	$-9/8*(7+(6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3/(-2-1))$	-100777520	$-9*(8^*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-89111319	$(9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3^2)+1)$	-100783820	$(-98^*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-89139492	$9*(8-76^{\wedge}5*4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$	-101040219	$-9/8*((7+6)^*(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-89139636	$-9*(8-76^{\wedge}5*-4^{\wedge}(-3-2+1))$	-101695500	$9/(8+7)^{\wedge}-6*(5^{\wedge}(-4-(-3+2)))-1)$
-89341137	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7^*6*54*3)^{\wedge}2)^*-1$	-101792992	$(-9/((8^*7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3^2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-89497760	$(-9+8/7)^*((6-(-5-4))^{\wedge}(3^2)-1)$	-101808576	$-9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6-5/((4^*3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-89571328	$(9^*8*-76+5)/4^{\wedge}(-3^2-1)$	-101977623	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(54*-32+1)$
-89701164	$-9/8*7*((6+5+4)^{\wedge}(3^2)-1)$	-102036665	$((-9+8)^*-7+(6*(5-4)^{\wedge}3*(2+1)))$
-89735168	$(9^*8*76+5)/-4^{\wedge}(-3^2-1)$	-102095721	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(54*-32-1)$
-90344970	$9^{\wedge}((8-7)+6)^*((-5^4+3^{\wedge}-2)+1)$	-102514833	$9*(87-(6+5+4)^{\wedge}(3^2))+1)$
-90367245	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$	-102516417	$-9*(87+(6+5+4)^{\wedge}(3^2))+1)$
-91353237	$9^{\wedge}8-7^*6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-103016448	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*(4+(3^2)^{\wedge}-1)$
-91353321	$9^{\wedge}8-7*-6*((5^*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-103312128	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)+6)/(5/(4^*-3)^*(2-1))$
-91407852	$9^{\wedge}((8-7)+6)^*((-5^4-3^{\wedge}-2)+1)$	-103335750	$-9/(8+7)^{\wedge}-6*(5^{\wedge}(-4-(-3+2)))+1)$
-91552740	$-9/8*(7+(6-5^{\wedge}(4*3))/(-2-1))$	-103656231	$9*(8/7*(-6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3^2)+1)$
-91675764	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6)^*(5-(4+3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-103656249	$-9*(8/7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3^2)+1)$
-91974672	$-98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1))$	-103656300	$9*(8/-7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)+(-3^2)^{\wedge}-1))$
-92236669	$-98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4+3)^*21$	-103656321	$9*(-8/7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3-2)-1)$
-92236684	$-98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4*(32+1)$	-104857531	$9-(8^{\wedge}7-6/5)^*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-92236692	$-98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4*(32-1)$	-104857549	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7-6/5)^*((4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-92236708	$(-98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4/3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-106165017	$((-9-8)^*7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))^*3*21$
-92236720	$-98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4*(3+21)$	-106655616	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*(-4+32^{\wedge}-1)$
-92236784	$((9+8+76+5)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$	-106666665	$(9+8-7)/-6*((5^4)^{\wedge}(3^2)-1)$
-92236848	$((9+8+76+5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$	-106677486	$9/87^{\wedge}(6-5-4)^*(3-21)$
-92236912	$(-98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4*(3+21))$	-107187500	$98^*7*6/(-5^{\wedge}(-4-3)^*(2+1))$
-92236924	$-98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4/3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	-107495103	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*-4+321$
-92236940	$(-98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4*(32-1))$	-107495391	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*-4-(-32-1)$
-92236948	$(-98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4*(32+1))$	-107495392	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*-4+32*1$
-92236960	$(98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4*(3)^{\wedge}2)^*-1$	-107495393	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*-4-(-32+1)$
-92236963	$-98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4+3)^*21$	-107495406	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*-4-3+21$
-92498960	$-98^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1))$	-107495442	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*-4-(-3+21)$
-93177117	$(-9-8*-7/6)^*(5^4*(-3-2)+1)$	-107495455	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*-4-32+1$
-93178899	$(9+8*7^{\wedge}6)^*(5^4*(-3-2)+1)$	-107495456	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*-4-32*1$
-93908348	$(-9/(8+(76^{\wedge}5-4)/3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-107495457	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*-4-32-1$
-93933000	$(9+8/7)^*(6^*5*(-4-3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-107495475	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*-4-321$
-93972318	$(9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4)^*(32+1)$	-108243184	$((98-7+6+5)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-93972606	$9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(4/(-32-1))$	-108243248	$((98-7+6+5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-93972624	$-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(4/(-32-1))$	-108335232	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*(-4-32^{\wedge}-1)$
-93972912	$(-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4)^*(32+1)$	-108827307	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(5-43^{\wedge}2+1)$
-94058482	$98/7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)/-3^2+1)$	-109172356	$(-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)+5)^*43^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
-94058510	$-98/7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3^2+1)$	-109190846	$(-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)-5)^*43^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}1$
-94279680	$9^*8^7*(-6-5/-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-109349406	$-9*(8+7)^*((6^*5)^{\wedge}4-3)-21$
-94464000	$9^*8^7*(-6-5/4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-109350594	$9*((-8-7)^*((6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3)-21)$
-94702619	$(9^{\wedge}8-76)/(-5^{\wedge}(-4+3)-2)^{\wedge}-1$	-109417797	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(5-(-43^{\wedge}2-1))$
-95482233	$9^{\wedge}(8-(7-6))^*(-5^4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-109432895	$(-9+8/7)^*((6^*(-5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
-95682560	$((-9^*8-7)+6)^*5^4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1))$	-109535895	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*(5-43^{\wedge}2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-109714284	$-9^*8/(7^*6)^*((5^*4)^(3^*2)-1)$	-124954606	$(-9+8)^*7^*((65^4+32)+1)$
-110565063	$-9/8^*7^*((-6^*5^4+3)^(2-1))$	-126247664	$((98+7+6-5)^(4-32))/-1$
-110565072	$9/8^*(-7^*((-6^*5^4+3)^(2-1)))$	-126247687	$((98+7+6-5)^(4-3^2))^*-1$
-110667920	$(-9+8/7)^*((6^*5^4+3)^(2-1))$	-126247705	$((98+7+6-5)^(4+3^2))^*-1$
-110919438	$-9/8^*7^*((6^*5^4+3)^(2-1))$	-126247728	$((98+7+6-5)^(4+32))^*-1$
-110919447	$9/8^*(-7^*((6^*5^4+3)^(2-1)))$	-127172608	$(98/7-6^5)^*4^(3^*2+1)$
-111070574	$(9/(8^*-7^*((65^4+3)+2)))^(2-1)$	-127250595	$9^(((-8+7)+6))^*-5^*(432-1)$
-111806208	$9^*(-8^7*6+(5^*4)^(3+2-1))$	-127631360	$(98/7+6^5)^*-4^(3^*2+1)$
-112550849	$((98^(7-6)+5)^(4-32))^*-1$	-127841085	$9^(((-8+7)+6))^*-5^*(432+1)$
-112550886	$((98^(7-6)+5)^(4+3+2))/-1$	-128024001	$(9^*8^*-7)^(4+3^*2+1)$
-112550913	$((98/(7-6)+5)^(4+32))^*-1$	-128024032	$(9^*-8^*7)^(4+3+2+1)$
-112860333	$9^*(8^7*6+(5^*(4+3))^(2+1))$	-128024057	$(9^*8^*-7)^(4+3^*2+1)$
-112877568	$9^*-8^7*6-(5^*4)^(3-2+1))$	-128024071	$(9^*8^*-7)^(4+3+2+1)$
-112951296	$9^*-8^7*6-(5^*(4+3))^(2-1))$	-128024096	$(9^*-8^*7)^(4+3+2+1)$
-112997661	$(-9^8-7)/(((6-5)+4)+3)/21$	-128024127	$(9^*8^*-7)^(4+3+2+1)$
-113197056	$9^*8^7*6^*((5+43)^(2-1))$	-128144466	$-9^*((8+7)^(6-5))/4^*(3+2)-1$
-113541120	$-9^*8^7*6+(5^*(4-3))^(2-1))$	-128144475	$-9^*((8+7)^(6-5))/4^*(3+2+1)$
-113614848	$9^*-8^7*6-(5^*-4)^(3-2+1))$	-128144484	$9^*((8+7)^(6-5))/-4^*(3+2)-1$
-114075065	$(-9/8-7)^*((-6/5^4+3)^(2-1))$	-128390022	$9^8*((-7^4(-6+5)+4)^(3-2+1))$
-114440690	$(-9/8-7)^*((6/5^4+3)^(2-1))$	-128562627	$-9/(8+7)^*((6+5)^(4-3))^(2+1)$
-114686208	$9^*(-8^7*6-(5^*4)^(3+2-1))$	-128581632	$9^*(-8-7^*6^5)^*4^(3^2-1)$
-114819063	$9^*8^7*6-(5-54)/(-3^2+1))$	-128608722	$9^8*((76+5)^(4+3))^(2+1))$
-114819081	$-9+8^7*6-(5-54)/(-3^2+1))$	-128668041	$-9/(8+7)^*((6+5)^(4+3))^(2-1)$
-115330023	$(9^*((8+7)^(6-5)-4))/(3^2-1)$	-128798199	$9-8^*7^*((-6-5)^*4^*-3)^(2+1)$
-115330032	$(9^*((8+7)^(6-5)+4))/(3^2-1)$	-128798217	$-9-8^*7^*((-6-5)^*4^*-3)^(2+1)$
-115533472	$(-9-8/7)^*((6-(-5-4))^(3^*2-1))$	-128894484	$(9-(8-76))^(5+4+3)/-21$
-116859348	$(9^8-7^*6^5)/(-4^4(-3+2)+1)$	-129783654	$((9-8)^*7^*6)^(5^*(4^3)^2-1)$
-116985824	$((98+7-6+5)^(4-32))^*-1$	-130674750	$98+(-7^*6)^(5+4)^(3^*2+1)$
-116985888	$((98+7-6+5)^(4+32))^*-1$	-130674946	$(-98+(-7^*6)^(5+4))^(3^*2+1)$
-117160704	$-9^*(8/7^*((6+5)+4)^(3^*2)-1))$	-130690976	$((-9+8)^*7^*6)^(5+4)^(3+2-1)$
-117186996	$-9^*-8^*(7+(-6/5^4(4+3^*2)))^(2-1)$	-130691040	$((-9+8)^*7^*6)^(5-4)^(3^*-2-1)$
-117188004	$-9^*8^*(7-(-6/5^4(4+3^*2)))^(2-1)$	-130691100	$((-9+8)^*7^*6)^(5+4^*(3+2+1))$
-117239434	$((-9-8)^(7+654))/(3+2^2-1)$	-130691108	$((-9+8)^*7^*6)^(5+4^*(3+2-1))$
-117239638	$((-9-8)^(7-6-54))/(3+2^2-1)$	-130691488	$(9-8)^*7^*6)^(5+4)^(3+2-1)$
-118061496	$9^*8^*(7^*6-5^4(4+3))^*21$	-130707518	$98+(-7^*6)^(5-4)^(3^*2+1)$
-118121976	$9^*8^*(7^*6-5^4(4+3))^*21$	-130707714	$(-98+(-7^*6)^(5-4))^(3^*2+1)$
-118128024	$9^*-8^*(7^*6+5^4(4+3))^*21$	-131079569	$((9+8+7+6+5)^(4-32))^*-1$
-118188504	$9^*-8^*(7^*6+5^4(4+3))^*21$	-131079592	$((9+8+7+6+5)^(4-3^2))^*-1$
-118589688	$9^*8^*((-7^4(6+5-4)+3)^*2+1)$	-131079610	$((9+8+7+6+5)^(4+3^2))^*-1$
-118589832	$9^*8^*((-7^4(6+5-4)+3)^*2-1)$	-131079633	$((9+8+7+6+5)^(4+32))^*-1$
-118590552	$9^*8^*((-7^4(6+5-4)-3)^*2+1)$	-132028416	$9^*-8^7*6-(5-54)/(3+2+1)$
-118590696	$9^*-8^*((7^4(6+5-4)+3)^*2+1)$	-132212736	$9^*8^7*6^*((-6-5/4)^(3+2))-1$
-118784000	$9^*8^7*6/(5^4*4^3)^(2-1)$	-133413903	$((9-8)^*7^*6^5-54+3)^*21$
-118822151	$(9-8)^*7/(65^4+3)^(2-1)$	-133413949	$9+8+(7^*6)^(5/((4+3)^(2-1)))$
-119070063	$(9-8)^*(-7^*((6^*5)^(4-3))^*21)$	-133413965	$9-8+(7^*6)^(5/((4+3)^(2-1)))$
-119070441	$(9-8)^*-7^*((6^*5)^(4+3))^*21$	-133413967	$(-9+8)+(7^*6)^(5/((4+3)^(2-1)))$
-119574218	$-9^8+7+(-6^*54)^(3-2)^(2-1)$	-133413983	$(-9-8)+(7^*6)^(5/((4+3)^(2-1)))$
-119574232	$(-9^8-7)-(6^*54)^(3-2)^(2-1)$	-133923125	$(9-8)^*7^*((6^*(5+4)^(3)^(2-1)))$
-119812608	$(9^*8)^(7-(6-5)^4)^*-321$	-134217702	$9-8^*(((-7+6)+5)^(4^3)-2)+1$
-120349812	$((9-8)^*7^6-5)^*(-4^4(3+2)+1)$	-134369260	$((9^*8)^(4((-7+6)+5)-4))^*(-3-2)^(2+1)$
-120595350	$((-9+8)^*7^6-5)^*(4^4(3+2)+1)$	-134369300	$((9^*8)^(4((-7+6)+5)+4))^*(-3-2)^(2+1)$
-120932028	$9^*8^*((7-6)^(5+4)/3)/2+1$	-135419769	$(9^*((8-7)^(6+5)^(4-3)))^(2^*-1)$
-120932172	$9^*8^*((7-6)^(5+4)/3)/2-1$	-135430135	$9-8^7*6-(5-(4/3))^(2-1)$
-120932532	$9^*8^*((7-6)^(5+4)/3)/2+1$	-135430153	$-9-8^7*6-(5-(4/3))^(2-1)$
-120932676	$9^*8^*((7-6)^(5+4)/3)/2-1$	-135498033	$(9/8^*-7-6)^*(5^4(4+3^*2)-1)$
-120943172	$(-9+8)^*7^6*(5+4)^(3+2)-1$	-135989847	$-9^(((-8+7)+6))^*(5+43)^(2-1)$
-120986732	$(9^*8-7^6)^*(5+4)^(3+2)+1$	-136048864	$((9-87-6^5)^(4-32))^*-1$
-120986734	$(9^*8-7^6)^*(5+4)^(3+2)-1$	-136048928	$(9-87-6^5)^(4+32)/-1$
-121139193	$(9-8)^*-7^*((65^4)^(3)^(2-1))$	-136181751	$9-8^7*65^*(-4^4(-3-2)+1)$
-121178470	$(-9+8)^*7^6*(5-(-4)^(3+2))-1$	-136181769	$-9-8^7*65^*(-4^4(-3-2)+1)$
-121550593	$((98+7/(6-5))^(4-32))^*-1$	-136447991	$9-8^7*65^*(4^4(-3-2)+1)$
-121550606	$9-(((8+7)+6)^5)^(4-(-3^2-1))$	-136448009	$-9-8^7*65^*(4^4(-3-2)+1)$
-121550657	$((98+7^4(6-5))^(4+32))/-1$	-137199607	$9-8^7*65+(4/3)^(2-1)$
-122070434	$(9^((8+7)/6)+5)^(4^*(3^3))/-2^*1$	-137199625	$-9-8^7*65+(4/3)^(2-1)$
-122343750	$9^*8^7*6/(-5^4(-4-3))^*(2+1))$	-137329110	$9/8^*((-7-6-5)^(4^3))/2-1$
-122851903	$9-8/7^*((6^5*4/3)^(2-1))$	-137363456	$9^*8^7*6-6^*(5/4-3)^(2-1)$
-122851921	$-9-8/7^*((6^5*4/3)^(2-1))$	-138235064	$(-9+8)/7^*((6^5*4+3)^(2-1))$
-123633664	$98^*7^*((-6-5)/4)^(3^*2-1)$	-139316147	$9^*((8^7+6)^*-5-4)^(3/2+1)$
-123925746	$(9/8-7)^*6^*((5^4)^(3)^(2-1))$	-139316149	$9^*((8^7+6)^*-5-4)^(3/2-1)$
-124452864	$9^*8^7*6^*((-6^5*4)^(3-2)+1)$	-139460419	$(9-8^7*6)^(6^4(-5+4+3))^*21$
-124687500	$(-9+8)^*7^6*5^4(4+3)^*21$	-139460797	$(-9-8^7*6)^(6^4(-5+4+3))^*21$
-124954054	$98+7^*((-65^4+32)-1)$	-141086232	$-9^*8^*(7/6)^(5-4)^(3^*2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-141087366	$-98/7*(6^{(5+4)}-3^{(2+1)})$	-151290000	$-9/(8^{(-7-(-6-5))+4})^{(-3+2-1)}$
-141087528	$-9*8*(7/6^{(5-4*3)}-2-1)$	-151511472	$-9*((8^{(-7-(-6-5))+4+3})^{(2-1)})$
-141087960	$9*8*(7/-6^{(5-4*3)}-2-1)$	-151511490	$-9*((8^{(-7-(-6-5))+4+3})^{(2+1)})$
-141088122	$-98/7*(6^{(5+4)}+3^{(2+1)})$	-151611285	$(-9/8+7*-6)*((5^{(4*3)})^{(2-1)})$
-141088191	$-98/7*(6^{(5+4)}+32)+1$	-151807039	$((98+7+6)^{(5-4+3)}-2)^*-1$
-141088193	$-98/7*(6^{(5+4)}+32)-1$	-151807043	$((98+7+6)^{(5-4+3)+2})^*-1$
-141089256	$9*8*(-7/6^{(5-4*3)}-21)$	-151880967	$-9*((8^{(-7-(-6-5))+4*3})^{(2-1)})$
-141115392	$9*87*(-6-5)/4^{(-3*2-1)}$	-151880975	$-9*(8^{((-7+6)+5)+4*3})^{(2+1)}$
-141158129	$((9*8+7+6*5)^{(4-32)})^*-1$	-151880977	$-9*(8^{((-7+6)+5)+4*3})^{(2-1)}$
-141158193	$((9*8+7+6*5)^{(4+32)})/-1$	-151880985	$-9*((8^{(-7-(-6-5))+4*3})^{(2+1)})$
-141267919	$(-9-8/7)*((6*(-5^{(4+3)}))^{(2-1)})$	-152393045	$(-9/(8^{(7*654-3)}))^{(-2+1)}$
-141557256	$9*8*(7-6*5*4^{(3^2-1)})$	-152523567	$(9*(8-7))^{(6*(5-4)*32+1)}$
-141558264	$9*8*(-7-6*5*4^{(3^2-1)})$	-153059328	$9*-8^7*(6-5*(-4/3)^{(2-1)})$
-141851745	$-9/8*((7-6*5^{(4+3)})^{(2-1)})$	-153461457	$9/8*(7*((-6-5)^{(4+3)+2})-1)$
-142248960	$(9*8*-7)^{((-6+5)+4)*(3^{(2+1)})}$	-153527400	$-9^{((-8+7)+6)*((54-3)^{(2-1)})}$
-142500000	$9*8*76/(-5^{(4-3)}*(2+1))$	-153645498	$-9^{((-8+7)+6)*((54-3)^{(2+1)})}$
-142822251	$9/8*(-7-6)*(5^{(4+3*2)}-1)$	-154181880	$-9*((8^{(-7-(-6-5))+43})^{(2-1)})$
-142862224	$(-9-8/7)*((6*5^{(4+3)})^{(2-1)})$	-154181889	$-9*(8^{(-7-(-6-5))+43})^{(2+1)}$
-142914870	$-9/8*((-7-6*5^{(4+3)})^{(2-1)})$	-154181898	$-9*((8^{(-7-(-6-5))+43})^{(2+1)})$
-143257608	$-9*8/7*((6*(-5^{(4+3)}))^{(2-1)})$	-154218750	$987*6/(5^{(4-3)}*(-2-1))$
-143701131	$(9/8-7*6)*((5^{(4*3)})^{(2-1)})$	-154533888	$-9*8^7*(6-5*(4/3)^{(2-1)})$
-144936090	$(9/((8^{(7-6)}*(-5^{(4+3)+2}))^{(2-1)}))^{(2-1)}$	-154854160	$(-9+8)*7(-6-543)^{(2+1)}$
-145282707	$9/8*((76+5)^{(4-3-21)})$	-155514447	$-9/(8*7)*((6^{(5*4+3)})^{(2-1)})$
-145489920	$((98+7)+6)^*-5*4^{(3*(2+1))}$	-157351904	$((9-8*7-65)^{(4-32)})^*-1$
-145752064	$9*8^7*-6*(5/4+3^{(2-1)})$	-157351930	$((9-8*7-65)^{(4-3*2)})^*-1$
-146393545	$(9+8)/-7*((6^{(5-4*3)})^{(2-1)})$	-157351931	$((98-7*6*5)^{(4-3-2)})/-1$
-146409968	$((98-76)^{(5)^{(4-32)})^*-1$	-157351941	$((98-7*6*5)^{(4+3+2)})^*-1$
-146409994	$((98-76)^{(5)^{(4-3*2)})^*-1$	-157351942	$((9-8*7-65)^{(4+3*2)})^*-1$
-146409995	$((98-76)^{(5)^{(4-3-2)})^*-1$	-157351968	$((9-8*7-65)^{(4+32)})^*-1$
-146410005	$((98-76)^{(5)^{(4+3+2)})^*-1$	-157436881	$(9+8)*7+(6*5*(-4-3))^{(2+1)}$
-146410032	$((98-76)^{(5)^{(4+32)})^*-1$	-157437119	$(-9-8)*7+(6*5*(4+3))^{(2+1)}$
-146582160	$(-9-8)/7*((-6^{(5+4+3)})^{(2-1)})$	-157925376	$(9+8+7)^{(6*(5/(4*3))^{(2-1)})}$
-146732724	$-9/8*((7*6)^{(5-4^{(3*(2+1))})})$	-158723705	$(9/8*-7*6^{(5+4+3)})*2+1$
-147033657	$(9/((-8^{(7*6)}(6+5^{(4-3)+2}))^{(2-1)}))^{(2-1)}$	-158723707	$(9/8*-7*6^{(5+4+3)})*2-1$
-147110928	$(-9-8)/7*((6^{(5+4+3)})^{(2-1)})$	-160102701	$-9*(8-7*6)-543^{(2+1)}$
-147322548	$-9/8*((7*6)^{(5+4^{(3*(2+1))})})$	-160103313	$9*(8-7*6)-543^{(2+1)}$
-147588768	$-9*8*((76+5)^{(4+3)/21})$	-160655256	$9*((8-((-7-6)*5)^{(4+32+1)})$
-147656208	$(-9+8)*7*6*((5^{(4*3)})^{(2-1)})$	-160655994	$-9*((8+((-7-6)*5)^{(4+32+1)})$
-147718144	$-98*(-7+6*5)^4(3^2-1)$	-161548175	$(9/((8-76)^{(5-4+3)}))^{(-2+1)}$
-147806207	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)*(-4+3/-2)+1}$	-161548179	$(9/((8-76)^{(5-43)}))^{(-2+1)}$
-147806209	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)*(-4+3/-2)-1}$	-162135027	$9/8*(-7^6*(5*(4+3))^{(2+1)})$
-147841272	$-9*(8^{(-7-(-6-5))}-43)^{(2-1)}$	-162201600	$9*-8^7*(6^{(5*4+3)}(-3-2)+1)$
-147841281	$-9*(8^{(-7-(-6-5))}-43)^{(2+1)}$	-162527400	$(9/((8^{(7-6/5^{(4*3)}-2))}))-1$
-147841290	$-9*(8^{(-7-(-6-5))}-43)^{(2+1)}$	-162760415	$(9/(8+7-6*5^{(4*3)}))^{(-2+1)}$
-148056254	$9/8-(((7-6)+5)^4)^{(3*2)+1}$	-162760416	$9^{((-8+7)*-6*(5^{(4*3)}-2-1))}$
-148056256	$9/8-(((7-6)+5)^4)^{(3*2)-1}$	-163047359	$((9+8)*7*6)^{(5-(4-3)-2)*-1}$
-150111495	$-9*((8^{(-7-(-6-5))}-4*3)^{(2-1)})$	-163047363	$((9+8)*7*6)^{(5-(4-3)+2)*-1}$
-150111503	$-9*(8^{((-7+6)+5)-4*3})^{(2+1)}$	-164916304	$-9*8-7+((-6-5)^4)^{(3+2)-1}$
-150111504	$-9*(8^{(-7-(-6-5))}-4*3)^{(2+1)}$	-165736560	$(9-8/7)*-6*((5^{(4*3)})^{(2-1)})$
-150111505	$-9*(8^{((-7+6)+5)-4*3})^{(2-1)}$	-166330359	$9*(-8^7*(6+5*(4/3)^{(2-1)+1})$
-150111513	$-9*(8^{(-7-(-6-5))}-4*3)^{(2+1)}$	-166330377	$-9*(8^7*(6+5*(4/3)^{(2-1)+1})$
-150115680	$9*(-8-7)*6^5*((4*3)^{(2-1)})$	-166418112	$(98*76)^{(-5-(-4-3))}*(-2-1)$
-150321875	$(-9+8/7)*((6/(5+4)^{(3^2-1)}))$	-167081778	$9*(8+(-7-6)^5*((4+3)^{(2+1)}))$
-150399671	$(-9+8*7)*6-((5*4)^{(3+2)-1})$	-167081922	$-9*(8+(7+6)^5*((4+3)^{(2+1)}))$
-150399765	$(-9+8*7)*6-(5*4)^{(3+2)-1}$	-168194961	$(9*(8+7*(-65-4)^3))^{(2*-1)}$
-150400235	$(9-8*7)*6+(5*4)^{(3+2)-1}$	-168291954	$((-9-8^7)+65)/4*321$
-150400329	$(9-8*7)*6-((5*4)^{(3+2)-1})$	-168300942	$((9-8^7)-65)/4*321$
-150479280	$-9*((87*((6+5)^4+3))^{(2-1)})$	-168374732	$(-9-8)*76^5*4^{(4-3-2+1)}$
-150479298	$-9*((87*((6+5)^4+3))^{(2+1)})$	-168895984	$((9+(8+7+6)*5)^{(4-32)})/-1$
-150732800	$-9*8^{(7+6-5)+4^{(3*(2+1))}}$	-168896010	$((9-(-8-(7+6)*5)^{(4-3*2)}))^*-1$
-150896647	$-9*((8^{(-7-(-6-5))}-4/3)^{(2-1)})$	-168896014	$((9*8+7*6)^{(5-4+3)-2})^*-1$
-150896656	$-9*(8^{(-7-(-6-5))}-4/3)^{(2*1)}$	-168896018	$((9*8+7*6)^{(5-4+3)+2})^*-1$
-150896665	$-9*((8^{(-7-(-6-5))}-4/3)^{(2+1)})$	-168896021	$((9+(8+7+6)*5)^{(4+3+2)})^*-1$
-150921216	$-9*((8^{(-7+6+5)}-4-3)^{(2-1)})$	-168896048	$((9+(8+7+6)*5)^{(4+32)})^*-1$
-150921234	$-9*((8^{(-7+6+5)}-4-3)^{(2+1)})$	-169599947	$(9-8*7-6)*((5*4)^{(3+2)-1})$
-150958071	$9*((-8^{(7+6-5)+4^{(3*2)+1}}))$	-169600053	$(-9+8*7+6)*((5*-4)^{(3+2)-1})$
-150958089	$-9*(8^{(7+6-5)-4^{(3*2)+1}})$	-170903327	$((9/(8+7^6))^{(5-(4+3)-2)})^*-1$
-150994869	$9*(8-((7-6)-5)^{(4*3)}-(-2-1))$	-170903331	$((9/(8+7^6))^{(5-(4+3)+2)})^*-1$
-151031799	$9*((-8^{(7+6-5)-4^{(3*2)+1}}))$	-171386670	$(9/8+7)*-6*((5^{(4*3)})^{(2-1)})$
-151031817	$-9*(8^{(7+6-5)+4^{(3*2)+1}})$	-172490743	$9-8^7*(65/4*(3+2)+1)$
-151068672	$-9*((8^{(-7+6+5)+4-3})^{(2-1)})$	-172490761	$-9-8^7*(65/4*(3+2)+1)$
-151068690	$-9*((8^{(-7+6+5)+4-3})^{(2+1)})$	-172556042	$(9/((-87*65^{(4-3)}))^{(-2+1)})$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-172641504	$(98/-7)^{\wedge}((6-5)+4)*321$	-191024244	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3/2)/-1$
-173721569	$-9^{\wedge}8+(-7^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-191024849	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2)/-1$
-173754337	$-9^{\wedge}8+(-7^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-191024853	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2)^{\wedge}-1$
-174877300	$((-9^{\wedge}8+7)-6)^{\wedge}((5/4-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-191043927	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2))^{\wedge}-1$
-174956976	$9^{\wedge}8*((-7+(6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+21)$	-191056751	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}43)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-174958461	$-9^{\wedge}*((8^{\wedge}(-7+(6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$	-191076732	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-174958515	$9^{\wedge}*((-8^{\wedge}(-7+(6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$	-191082976	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}32)^{\wedge}-1$
-174961485	$9^{\wedge}*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$	-191086976	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2)^{\wedge}-1$
-174961539	$9^{\wedge}*((8^{\wedge}(-7-(6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$	-191093731	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}32)^{\wedge}-1$
-174963024	$9^{\wedge}8*((-7-(6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-21)$	-191094974	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2)^{\wedge}-1$
-176460687	$-9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-191094978	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+2)^{\wedge}-1$
-177446679	$-9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-191097351	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-177446763	$-9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-191097544	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5432)^{\wedge}-1$
-178913280	$(-98+7)^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-191098976	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2)^{\wedge}-1$
-179199944	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}((5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-191099226	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-179200056	$(98-7^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}((5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-191099376	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-179306469	$9^{\wedge}*((-8^{\wedge}7/6*(54+3)+2)+1)$	-191099727	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(54+3)^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-179306523	$-9^{\wedge}*((8^{\wedge}7/6*(54+3)+2)+1)$	-191099851	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2)^{\wedge}-1$
-179401698	$(9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4)^{\wedge}3*21$	-191100375	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(54-3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-179402076	$(9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4)^{\wedge}3*21$	-191100672	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5+43)^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-179402256	$(9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4)^{\wedge}3*21$	-191100816	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}432)^{\wedge}-1$
-179402265	$-9^{\wedge}*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4^{\wedge}3*21$	-191101099	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3-2)^{\wedge}-1$
-179402274	$-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4^{\wedge}3*21$	-191101103	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3+2)^{\wedge}-1$
-179402454	$(-9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4)^{\wedge}3*21$	-191101132	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6+5-43^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-179402832	$(-9+((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4)^{\wedge}3*21$	-191101248	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}32)^{\wedge}-1$
-181063904	$((98+7+6+5)^{\wedge}4-32)^{\wedge}-1$	-191101532	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5-43)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-181063968	$((98+7+6+5)^{\wedge}4+32)^{\wedge}-1$	-191101751	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-181439993	$(-9+8)^{\wedge}6*((6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}4-32+1)$	-191101890	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-543^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-182845440	$9^{\wedge}8*(7+6)^{\wedge}5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-191101947	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))^{\wedge}-1$
-183606408	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7^{\wedge}((65^{\wedge}4-3)+2)-1)$	-191101957	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))/-1$
-183606432	$9^{\wedge}8/-7^{\wedge}((65^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-191102245	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3-2)^{\wedge}-1$
-183722337	$-9/87^{\wedge}(6-5-4)^{\wedge}32-1$	-191102249	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2)^{\wedge}-1$
-184265981	$(9^{\wedge}(8-7-6))^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-191102256	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5/(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-184277871	$-9^{\wedge}*((8^{\wedge}(7+6+5))^{\wedge}4+3)/21$	-191102319	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4-32)^{\wedge}-1$
-184469076	$-9^{\wedge}(((-8+7)+6)^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}(4+3-2)-1)$	-191102336	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}32)/-1$
-184473503	$(-98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$	-191102342	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-184473504	$(98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-191102346	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4-3-2)^{\wedge}-1$
-184473505	$(-98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-191102356	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3+2)^{\wedge}-1$
-184473759	$(-98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$	-191102360	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-184473760	$(98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-191102383	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+32)^{\wedge}-1$
-184473761	$(-98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-191102431	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-543-2)^{\wedge}-1$
-184527100	$(-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6))^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$	-191102435	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5432)^{\wedge}-1$
-184527102	$(-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6))^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$	-191102490	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-184529148	$(-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6))^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$	-191102539	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5-432)^{\wedge}-1$
-184529150	$(-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6))^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$	-191102546	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-184544624	$(9-8^{\wedge}7/6)^{\wedge}((5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-191102549	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6+5-432)^{\wedge}-1$
-184554128	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7/6)^{\wedge}((5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-191102652	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-184587174	$-9^{\wedge}(((-8+7)+6)^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}(4+3-2)+1)$	-191102666	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3-2))^{\wedge}-1$
-184730049	$((-9^{\wedge}8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	-191102688	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^{\wedge}32)/-1$
-184730175	$(-9^{\wedge}8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3)^{\wedge}21$	-191102706	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3(3+2))^{\wedge}-1$
-184790269	$(9^{\wedge}(8-7-6))^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-191102731	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-186472368	$(9^{\wedge}876)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	-191102751	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(43+2))^{\wedge}-1$
-187142400	$((-9+8+7^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}5/43)^{\wedge}2-1$	-191102759	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}43-2)^{\wedge}-1$
-187587351	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$	-191102763	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3+2)^{\wedge}-1$
-187902976	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2))^{\wedge}-1$	-191102771	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(43-2))^{\wedge}-1$
-188116964	$((9^{\wedge}8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4)^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-191102796	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-188117020	$((9^{\wedge}8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4)^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-191102812	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3-2)^{\wedge}-1$
-188825361	$((9-8)^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^{\wedge}321$	-191102816	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3+2)^{\wedge}-1$
-189149851	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3+2))/-1$	-191102827	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-189887147	$(9/(8+7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3)+2))^{\wedge}-1$	-191102832	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5+4+3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-189887149	$(-9/(8-7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-191102838	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-189887153	$(-9/(((8-7)+6)^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$	-191102843	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}32)^{\wedge}-1$
-190095750	$-9/8^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}(-6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-191102851	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4-3+2))^{\wedge}-1$
-190102016	$(9-(-8-7)/-6)^{\wedge}5/-4^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-191102853	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}32)^{\wedge}-1$
-190788048	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)/-1$	-191102856	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-190808127	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-543^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$	-191102858	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6+(5-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-190840827	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$	-191102862	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(54+3)^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-190937124	$(98^{\wedge}(-7^{\wedge}(6+5)-4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2^{\wedge}-1$	-191102874	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(54-3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-190945510	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3-2)^{\wedge}-1$	-191102876	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3(3+2))^{\wedge}-1$
-190945514	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3+2)^{\wedge}-1$	-191102880	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-190946726	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)^{\wedge}2)/-1$	-191102885	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-5-43^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-191000576	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5/4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$	-191102890	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6-54-32)/-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-191102900	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5-43)^2)^* - 1$	-191105136	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot 432)^* - 1$
-191102909	$((9+8+7)^6 - 5 - 4^3 + 2)^* - 1$	-191105280	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5+43)^2)^* - 1$
-191102924	$((9+8+7)^6 - 5^4 - 32)^* - 1$	-191105577	$((9+8+7)^6 + (54-3)^2)^* - 1$
-191102926	$((9+8+7)^6 - 5 - 43 - 2)^* - 1$	-191106101	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4(4+3-2))^* - 1$
-191102927	$((9+8+7)^6 - 54 + 3 + 2)^* - 1$	-191106225	$((9+8+7)^6 + (54+3)^2)^* - 1$
-191102935	$((9+8+7)^6 - 5 - 4 - 32)^* - 1$	-191106576	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5^4 \cdot 3)^2) / -1$
-191102936	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5 - 43 - 2)^* - 1$	-191106726	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot 3^2)^* - 1$
-191102947	$((9+8+7)^6 - 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2)^* - 1$	-191108408	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5432)^* - 1$
-191102954	$((9+8+7)^6 - 54 + 32)^* - 1$	-191108601	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot 3^2)^* - 1$
-191102998	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54 - 32)^* - 1$	-191110974	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5^4)^3 - 2)^* - 1$
-191103005	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5 + 4^3 \cdot 2)^* - 1$	-191110978	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5^4)^3 + 2)^* - 1$
-191103016	$((9+8+7)^6 - 5 + 43 + 2)^* - 1$	-191112221	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot 43^2)^* - 1$
-191103017	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5 + 4 + 32)^* - 1$	-191118976	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5^4)^3 \cdot 2)^* - 1$
-191103021	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54 - 3^2)^* - 1$	-191122976	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot 4^3 \cdot 32)^* - 1$
-191103026	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5 + 43 + 2)^* - 1$	-191129220	$((9+8+7)^6 + (54 \cdot 3)^2)^* - 1$
-191103028	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot 43)^* - 1$	-191149201	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5^4 \cdot 43)^2)^* - 1$
-191103043	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5 + 4^3 - 2)^* - 1$	-191162025	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5+4)^3(3+2))^* - 1$
-191103052	$((9+8+7)^6 - (5-43)^2)^* - 1$	-191181099	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4(4+3-2)) / -1$
-191103062	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54 + 32)^* - 1$	-191181103	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4(4+3+2))^* - 1$
-191103067	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5 + 43 \cdot 2)^* - 1$	-191181708	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54^3 / 2) / -1$
-191103072	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5+43)^2) / -1$	-191205376	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5/4^3)^2)^* - 1$
-191103076	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot (3+2))^* - 1$	-191259226	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4(4+3)^2)^* - 1$
-191103078	$((9+8+7)^6 + (54-3)^2)^* - 1$	-191260438	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54^3 - 2)^* - 1$
-191103090	$((9+8+7)^6 + (54+3)^2) / -1$	-191260442	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54^3 + 2) / -1$
-191103094	$((9+8+7)^6 - (5-4^3)^2) / -1$	-191365115	$((9+8+7)^6 - 5 + 4^3 \cdot 2)^* - 1$
-191103096	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot 3^2)^* - 1$	-191365125	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5 + 4^3 \cdot 2)^* - 1$
-191103099	$((9+8+7)^6 - 5 + 4^3 \cdot 2)^* - 1$	-191397825	$((9+8+7)^6 + 543^2)^* - 1$
-191103101	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 / (3+2)) / -1$	-191417904	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54^3 \cdot 2)^* - 1$
-191103109	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5 + 4^3 \cdot 2)^* - 1$	-191791152	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6) \cdot ((5+4+3)^2 - 1)$
-191103114	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5+4^3)^2) / -1$	-191909250	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6) \cdot ((5+4+3)^2 + 1)$
-191103115	$((9+8+7)^6 - 5 + (4^3)^2)^* - 1$	-193056101	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4(4+3+2)) / -1$
-191103120	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5+4+3)^2)^* - 1$	-193877744	$((9+8+7)^6 - 6 + 5^4 - 32)^* - 1$
-191103125	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5 + (4^3)^2) / -1$	-193877767	$((-9-8)^7 + 6 - 5^4 - 3^2)^* - 1$
-191103136	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54 \cdot 3 - 2)^* - 1$	-193877785	$((9+8+7)^6 - 6 + 5^4 + 3^2)^* - 1$
-191103140	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54 \cdot 3 + 2)^* - 1$	-193877808	$((9+8+7)^6 - 6 + 5^4 + 32)^* - 1$
-191103156	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot 3^2)^* - 1$	-194051875	$(-9/8/7)^6 \cdot ((6/(5+4)^3)^2 - 1)$
-191103181	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4(43-2))^* - 1$	-194302976	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5^4)^3(3+2))^* - 1$
-191103189	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot 43 - 2)^* - 1$	-194618601	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5^4 \cdot 3)^2)^* - 1$
-191103193	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot 43 + 2)^* - 1$	-195231744	$9^6(8^7 \cdot 6 + 5)^4 \cdot (3^2 - 1)$
-191103201	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4(43+2))^* - 1$	-195575391	$-9/87^{\wedge}(6-5-4) \cdot (32+1)$
-191103221	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4(4+3)^2) / -1$	-196171875	$9^6(-87-6)^5 \cdot 5^4(4+3)^2(2+1)$
-191103246	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54 \cdot (3+2))^* - 1$	-196515072	$(9-87) / (6^{\wedge}(-5-4) \cdot (3+2-1))$
-191103264	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5+4)^3 \cdot 32) / -1$	-196607993	$(9-8)^7 - 6 / (5/4^3 - 3)^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-191103286	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4(4^3 - 2))^* - 1$	-197537625	$-9/8^7 \cdot ((7^6 - 6 - 5^4)^3)^2 - 1$
-191103300	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54 \cdot 3^2)^* - 1$	-198165744	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5 - 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1))$
-191103403	$((9+8+7)^6 - 5 + 432)^* - 1$	-198195984	$-9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5 + 4^{\wedge}(3^2 - 1))$
-191103406	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot 43^2)^* - 1$	-198639616	$(9 - 8^7 \cdot 6^5)^4 \cdot (3^2 - 1)$
-191103413	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5 + 432)^* - 1$	-199148534	$9 - (8 / (7^6)^{\wedge}(5 - 4 - 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-191103462	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54 \cdot 3^2)^* - 1$	-199148536	$9 - ((8 / (7^6)^{\wedge}(5 - 4 - 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-191103517	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54 \cdot 43 - 2)^* - 1$	-199148552	$-9 - (8 / (7^6)^{\wedge}(5 - 4 - 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-191103521	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54 \cdot 43 + 2)^* - 1$	-199148554	$-9 - ((8 / (7^6)^{\wedge}(5 - 4 - 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-191103569	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 - 32)^* - 1$	-199655424	$9^6 - 8^{\wedge}7 \cdot (6 + 5 + (-4/3)^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-191103592	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 - 3^2)^* - 1$	-199819264	$(-9 - 8^7 \cdot 6^5)^4 \cdot (3^2 - 1)$
-191103595	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 - 3^2) / -1$	-200439504	$9^8 / 7^7 \cdot (((-6-5)^4)^{\wedge}(4+3-2) - 1)$
-191103596	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 - 3 - 2)^* - 1$	-200533889	$((9^8 + 7^6 + 5)^4 - 32)^* - 1$
-191103606	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 + 3 + 2)^* - 1$	-200533915	$((9^8 + 7^6 + 5)^4 - 3^2)^* - 1$
-191103610	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 + 3^2)^* - 1$	-200533916	$((9^8 + 7^6 + 5)^4 - 3 - 2)^* - 1$
-191103616	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot 4^3 \cdot 32)^* - 1$	-200533926	$((9^8 + 7^6 + 5)^4 + 3 + 2)^* - 1$
-191103633	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 + 32) / -1$	-200533927	$((9^8 + 7^6 + 5)^4 + 3^2)^* - 1$
-191103696	$((-9-8-7)^6 + 5 / (4^3)^{\wedge} - 2)^* - 1$	-200533953	$((9^8 + 7^6 + 5)^4 + 32)^* - 1$
-191103703	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5+4)^3 - 2)^* - 1$	-202709227	$(-9+8)^7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot (-5 + (4^3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-191103707	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5+4)^3 + 2)^* - 1$	-203246208	$-9^8 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot (-5 + 4)^{\wedge}(3^2 + 1)$
-191103995	$((9+8+7)^6 - 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3+2))^* - 1$	-203657135	$(-9+8/7)^6 \cdot ((6^5)^4 \cdot 32 - 1)$
-191104005	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5 + 4^{\wedge}(3+2)) / -1$	-203885717	$(-9+8)^7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot (5 - (4^3 - 3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-191104062	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54 \cdot 3^2)^* - 1$	-204119928	$9^6(8-7^6 \cdot 6^5)^4 \cdot ((3+2)-1)$
-191104201	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5^4 \cdot (4+3)^2) / -1$	-204120072	$-9^6(8+7^6 \cdot 6^5)^4 \cdot ((3+2)-1)$
-191104420	$((9+8+7)^6 + (5-43)^2)^* - 1$	-204204978	$9^8 + (-7^6)^{\wedge}5^4 \cdot ((4/3)^{\wedge} - 2 + 1)$
-191104704	$((9+8+7)^6 + 54 \cdot 32)^* - 1$	-204205050	$((9-8)^6 - 7^6)^{\wedge}5^4 \cdot ((4/3)^{\wedge} - 2 + 1)$
-191104820	$((9+8+7)^6 - 5 + 4^3 \cdot 2)^* - 1$	-204205122	$-9^8 + (-7^6)^{\wedge}5^4 \cdot ((4/3)^{\wedge} - 2 + 1)$
-191104830	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5 + 4^3 \cdot 2)^* - 1$	-204205148	$-98 + (-7^6)^{\wedge}5^4 \cdot ((4/3)^{\wedge} - 2 + 1)$
-191104849	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot 3 - 2)^* - 1$	-205312500	$9^8 \cdot 76 / (5^{\wedge}(-4-3) \cdot (-2-1))$
-191104853	$((9+8+7)^6 + 5^4 \cdot 3 + 2)^* - 1$	-206962688	$-9^8 \cdot 8^7 \cdot (6 - 5 \cdot ((4^3)^{\wedge} - 2 - 1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-207312552	$9^*(8/-7*((-6^\wedge(5+4)+3)^*-2+1))$	-231650604	$(9^\wedge 8+(7*6)^\wedge 5)/(4^\wedge(-3+2)-1)$
-207359013	$987-(6*5^4)^\wedge((3+2)-1)$	-233279595	$9^*(-8-7)*(((6*5^4)^\wedge 3-2)-1)$
-207359217	$9^*87-(6*5^4)^\wedge(3+2-1)$	-233280405	$9^*(-8-7)*(((6*5^4)^\wedge 3+2)+1)$
-207359314	$98^*7-(6*5^4)^\wedge(3+2-1)$	-233963520	$(-9-8)^*7*6*5^4^\wedge(3^\wedge 2-1)$
-207359895	$98+7-(6*5^4)^\wedge(3+2-1)$	-236136951	$9^\wedge((-8+7)+6)*((5^*-4)^\wedge 3/2+1)$
-207359904	$9+87-(6*5^4)^\wedge(3+2-1)$	-236186496	$9^*8^*7*6^*(-5^\wedge(4+3)+21)$
-207359909	$98-7-(6*5^4)^\wedge(3+2-1)$	-236196001	$9^\wedge((-8+7)+6)/((5^*-4)^\wedge-3^*2)-1$
-207359968	$((9+8)^*7+(6-5)^\wedge 4-32)^*-1$	-236243448	$9^*8^*-7^*(-6^*(-5^\wedge(4+3)+2)-1)$
-207359986	$98/7-(6*5^4)^\wedge(3+2-1)$	-236243880	$9^*8^*(7*6^*(-5^\wedge(4+3)+2)+1)$
-207360014	$9-87-(6*5^4)^\wedge(3+2-1)$	-236244024	$9^*-8^*(7*6^*(5^\wedge(4+3)-2)+1)$
-207360032	$((9+8)^*7+(6-5)^\wedge 4+32)^*-1$	-236244456	$9^*8^*7^*(6^*(-5^\wedge(4+3)+2)-1)$
-207360078	$9-87-(6*5^4)^\wedge(3+2-1)$	-236249784	$9^*-8^*(7*6^*5^\wedge(4+3)-(2+1))$
-207360686	$-98^*7-(6*5^4)^\wedge(3+2-1)$	-236249847	$-9^*(-8^*(7*6^*-5^\wedge(4+3)+2)-1)$
-207360783	$-9^*87-(6*5^4)^\wedge(3+2-1)$	-236249865	$9^*(8^*(7*6^*-5^\wedge(4+3)+2)-1)$
-207360987	$-987-(6*5^4)^\wedge(3+2-1)$	-236249928	$9^*-8^*(7*6^*5^\wedge(4+3)-(2-1))$
-207415296	$9^*8^\wedge 7^*(-6-5)^*(-4^\wedge(-3-2)+1)$	-236249964	$9^*-8^*(7*6^*5^\wedge(4+3)-2^\wedge-1)$
-207525888	$9^*8^\wedge 7^*(-6-5^*(-4^\wedge(-3-2)+1))$	-236250036	$9^*-8^*(7*6^*5^\wedge(4+3)+2^\wedge-1)$
-207612702	$9-8^\wedge 7/6^*((5^\wedge 4-32)+1)$	-236250072	$9^*-8^*(7*6^*5^\wedge(4+3)+2-1)$
-207617792	$9/8^\wedge-7^*(-6-5)+4^\wedge(3+2-1)$	-236250153	$9^*(-8^*(7*6^*5^\wedge(4+3)+2)-1)$
-207618304	$9/8^\wedge-7^*(-6-5)-4^\wedge(3+2-1)$	-236250216	$9^*-8^*(7*6^*5^\wedge(4+3)+2+1)$
-207623394	$(-9-8^\wedge 7/6^*((5^\wedge 4-32)+1)$	-236255049	$-9^\wedge((-8+7)+6)*((5^*4)^\wedge 3/2+1)$
-207682389	$-9/8^*((7^*(-6^\wedge 5/4+3))^\wedge 2-1)$	-236255544	$9^*8^*-7^*(5^\wedge(4+3)+2)-1)$
-207704796	$9^*((8-76)^\wedge 5-4)/(3^*21)$	-236255976	$9^*-8^*(7*6^*(5^\wedge(4+3)+2)-1)$
-207710208	$9^*8^\wedge 7^*(-6-5^*(4^\wedge(-3-2)+1))$	-236256120	$9^*8^*(7^*-6^*(5^\wedge(4+3)+2)-1)$
-207820800	$9^*8^\wedge 7^*(-6-5)^*(4^\wedge(-3-2)+1)$	-236256552	$9^*8^*7^*(-6^*(5^\wedge(4+3)+2)-1)$
-2078273408	$9^*8^\wedge 7^*(-6-5^*((4^*3)^\wedge-2+1))$	-236313504	$9^*-8^*7^*6^*(5^\wedge(4+3)+21)$
-208968345	$-9/8^*((7^*(6^\wedge 5/4+3))^\wedge 2-1)$	-236421344	$((9^*(8+7)-6-5)^\wedge 4-32)^*-1$
-211376574	$(9-87^\wedge(-6-(-5-4)))^*321$	-236421370	$((9^*(8+7)-6-5)^\wedge 4-3^*2)^*-1$
-211382352	$(-9-87^\wedge(-6-(-5-4)))^*321$	-236421371	$((9^*(8+7)-6-5)^\wedge 4-3-2)/-1$
-211631379	$(9^*8-7^*6^\wedge(5+4))^*3+21$	-236421381	$((9^*(8+7)-6-5)^\wedge 4+3+2)^*-1$
-211631421	$(9^*8-7^*6^\wedge(5+4))^*3-21$	-236421408	$((9^*(8+7)-6-5)^\wedge 4+32)^*-1$
-211631811	$(9^*-8-7^*6^\wedge(5+4))^*3+21$	-236924991	$9+(8+7)^\wedge 6^*(5^\wedge(-4+3)-21)$
-211631853	$(9^*-8-7^*6^\wedge(5+4))^*3-21$	-236925009	$-9+(8+7)^\wedge 6^*(5^\wedge(-4+3)-21)$
-211943424	$-9^*-8^\wedge 7^*(6+5)/(4+3)^\wedge-2-1)$	-237961216	$(9-8^*7^*65)^*4^\wedge(3^\wedge 2-1)$
-212517351	$-9^\wedge((-8+7)+6)*((5^*4^*3)^\wedge 2-1)$	-238085505	$9/8^*(-7-(6^\wedge(5+4)-3)^*21)$
-212701440	$((9^\wedge 8-7)+6)/((5/4+3)/-21)$	-238085631	$9/8^*(7-(6^\wedge(5+4)+3)^*21)$
-213081264	$((-9^\wedge 8+7)-6)^*(5+(-4^*(3+2))^\wedge-1)$	-239140864	$(-9-8^*7^*65)^*4^\wedge(3^\wedge 2-1)$
-213950832	$((9+8)^\wedge 7^*-6^*(5^\wedge 4+3)^\wedge 2-1)$	-239600592	$(9-8)^*(7^*6)^\wedge 5^*(-4/3-2^\wedge-1)$
-214089742	$((9+8)^\wedge 7^*-6+5)/(4^*3-2^\wedge-1)$	-240638824	$9^*8^*7^*6+(-5^\wedge 4+3)^\wedge(2+1)$
-214358849	$((98-7+6^*5)^\wedge 4-32)^*-1$	-240641863	$(-9^*(8-7)-6+(-5^\wedge 4+3)^\wedge(2+1))$
-214358913	$((98-7+6^*5)^\wedge 4+32)/-1$	-240644872	$9^*8^*7^*-6+(-5^\wedge 4+3)^\wedge(2+1)$
-215568864	$9^*8^*(7/654^\wedge((-3+2)-1)$	-241173289	$-9^\wedge((-8+7)^*6)-(5^\wedge 4-3)^\wedge(2+1)$
-215580672	$9^*-8^\wedge 7^*(6+5-(-4/3)^\wedge(-2-1))$	-241481241	$9-(8+7)^\wedge 6^*(5^\wedge(-4+3)+21)$
-217013928	$(9/(-8^*((7*6+5^\wedge(4^*3)+2)))^\wedge-1$	-241481259	$-9-(8+7)^\wedge 6^*(5^\wedge(-4+3)+21)$
-217385936	$((-9^\wedge 8+7)-6)^*(5+(4^*(3+2))^\wedge-1)$	-241510410	$9^\wedge((-8+7)+6)^*(5-4^\wedge(3^*2)+1)$
-217424592	$((-9+8)^*7^\wedge 6-5)^*(43^\wedge 2-1)$	-241628508	$-9^\wedge((-8+7)+6)^*(5-4^\wedge(3^*2)+1)$
-217641400	$((9-8)^*7^\wedge 6-5)^*(-43^\wedge 2-1)$	-241844223	$(-9^\wedge((-8+7)+6)+5)^*4^\wedge(3^*2)+1$
-217975696	$((-9^\wedge((-8+7)+6)+5)/4-3)^\wedge 2^*-1$	-241844225	$(-9^\wedge((-8+7)+6)+5)^*4^\wedge(3^*2)-1$
-219726540	$9^*(-8-7)/6^*(5^\wedge(4+3^*2)-1)$	-241863024	$9^*-8^*((-7+6^\wedge(5+4))/3-21)$
-219726585	$9^*(8+7)/6^*(-5^\wedge(4+3^*2)-1)$	-241863360	$9^*8^*((-7-6^\wedge(5+4))/3+21)$
-220312918	$98^*(7-6^*(5^*4+3))^\wedge(2+1)$	-241863984	$9^*8^*((-7-6^\wedge(5+4))/3+2)+1)$
-220686345	$(-9+8)/7^*((6^*5+4)^\wedge(3^*2)-1)$	-241864173	$9^*((8^*(7-6^\wedge(5+4))/3)+2)+1)$
-222899040	$(9-8)^*7^*6^\wedge 5^*(-4^\wedge(3^*2)+1)$	-241864227	$9^*((8^*(7-6^\wedge(5+4))/3)-2)-1)$
-224040600	$9^*-8^*((7^*6)^\wedge((5-4)+3)-21)$	-241864320	$9^*8^*((7-6^\wedge(5+4))/3+2+1)$
-224042109	$((-9^*8/(7^*6)^\wedge(-5-(-4+3))+2)+1)$	-241865088	$9^*8^*((-7-6^\wedge(5+4))/3-2-1)$
-224043624	$-9^*8^*((7^*6)^\wedge((5-4)+3)+21)$	-241865181	$9^*((-8^*(7+6^\wedge(5+4))/3)+2)+1)$
-226419200	$-98/(76^*5^4)^\wedge((-3+2)-1)$	-241865235	$9^*((-8^*(7+6^\wedge(5+4))/3)-2)-1)$
-228571425	$((9+8)/7-6)^*((5^*4)^\wedge(3^*2)-1)$	-241865424	$9^*8^*((-7-6^\wedge(5+4))/3-2)-1)$
-230394456	$9^*8^*(76-((5^*4)^\wedge(3+2)-1))$	-241866048	$9^*8^*((-7-6^\wedge(5+4))/3-21)$
-230394600	$9^*8^*(76+(-5^*4)^\wedge(3+2)-1)$	-241866384	$9^*8^*((-7-6^\wedge(5+4))/3-21)$
-230396967	$-9^*(8^*(-7^*6+(-5^*4)^\wedge(3+2))-1)$	-241885183	$(9^\wedge((-8+7)+6)+5)^*-4^\wedge(3^*2)+1$
-230396985	$9^*(8^*(7^*6+(-5^*4)^\wedge(3+2))-1)$	-241885185	$(9^\wedge((-8+7)+6)+5)^*-4^\wedge(3^*2)-1$
-230399907	$9^*(8^*(7/6-(-5^*4)^\wedge(3+2))+1)$	-242100900	$9^\wedge((-8+7)+6)^*(5-4^\wedge(3^*2)+1)$
-230400075	$-9^*(8^*(7/6+(-5^*4)^\wedge(3+2))-1)$	-242218998	$9^\wedge((-8+7)+6)^*(5-4^\wedge(3^*2)+1)$
-230400093	$9^*(-8^*(7/6+(-5^*4)^\wedge(3+2))-1)$	-243135625	$((-9^*8-7)+6)^*5^\wedge(4/3)^\wedge(2+1)$
-230403015	$-9^*(8^*(7^*6-(-5^*4)^\wedge(3+2))-1)$	-244022955	$((9-8)^*7^\wedge 6-5^\wedge(4^*3))+21$
-230403033	$9^*(8^*(-7^*6-(-5^*4)^\wedge(3+2))-1)$	-244022997	$((9-8)^*7^\wedge 6-5^\wedge(4^*3))-21$
-230405400	$9^*-8^*(76-(-5^*4)^\wedge(3+2)-1)$	-244140379	$((9^\wedge((8+7)/6)-5^\wedge(4^*3))+2)+1$
-230405544	$9^*-8^*(76-((-5^*4)^\wedge(3+2))-1)$	-244140380	$9^\wedge((8+7)/6)-5^\wedge(4^*3)-2^\wedge 1)$
-230660046	$9^*((8+7)^\wedge 6-5)/-4^*3^\wedge 2+1)$	-244140381	$9^\wedge((8+7)/6)-5^\wedge(4^*3)+2-1$
-230660064	$-9^*((8+7)^\wedge 6-5)/4^*3^\wedge 2+1)$	-244140382	$9^\wedge((8+7)/6)+5^\wedge(4^*3)/(-2+1)$
-230736100	$(98^*(7-6^*(5+4)^*3))^\wedge 2^*-1$	-244140384	$9^\wedge((8+7)/6)-5^\wedge(4^*3)-2/1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-244140385	$((9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-5^{\wedge}(4*3))-2)-1$	-276710433	$(98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4)^*-3+2+1$
-244140865	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-5^{\wedge}(4*3)+2)+1$	-276710434	$(98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4)^*-3+2*1$
-244140866	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-5^{\wedge}(4*3))+2/1$	-276710435	$(98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4)^*-3+2-1$
-244140868	$(9^{\wedge}(((8+7)/6)+5^{\wedge}(4*3)))/(-2+1)$	-276710461	$(98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4)^*-3-2+1$
-244140869	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-5^{\wedge}(4*3))-2+1$	-276710462	$(98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4)^*-3-2*1$
-244140870	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-5^{\wedge}(4*3))-2/1$	-276710463	$(98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4)^*-3-2-1$
-244140871	$(-9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)-1$	-276710481	$(98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4)^*-3-21$
-244187279	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)^*-1$	-276922849	$((9^*(8^*7/6+5))^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-244187283	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)+2)^*-1$	-276922875	$((9^*(8^*7/6+5))^{\wedge}4-3^*2)/-1$
-244402767	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)^*-1$	-276922876	$((9^*(8^*7/6+5))^{\wedge}4-(3+2))^*-1$
-244402771	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)+2)^*-1$	-276922879	$((9^*(8+7)-6)^{\wedge}(5-(4-3))-2)^*-1$
-244760472	$9-(8/7*654^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-276922883	$((9^*(8+7)-6)^{\wedge}(5-(4-3))+2)^*-1$
-244760490	$-9-(8/7*654^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-276922886	$((9^*(8^*7/6+5))^{\wedge}4+3+2)/-1$
-244881183	$9-8/7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-276922890	$((9^*(8^*7/6+5))^{\wedge}4+3^*2)^*-1$
-244881201	$-9+8/-7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-276922913	$((9^*(8^*7/6+5))^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-245140623	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)^*-1$	-279726236	$(9-8)^*7-654^{\wedge}3+21$
-245140627	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4*3)+2)^*-1$	-281725048	$(9/(8-76^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-247165833	$9-(8/(7^{\wedge}(6+5)-4-3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-282475168	$9*((8-(7^{\wedge}(-6-(-5+4)))^3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-247165851	$-9-(8/(7^{\wedge}(6+5)-4-3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-282475330	$-9*((8+(7^{\wedge}(-6-(-5+4)))^3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-247670128	$9*8^*7*6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-285212651	$(-9-8)^*((-7+6)+5)^{\wedge}(4*3)+21$
-247676176	$9*8^*7*6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-285212693	$(-9-8)^*((-7+6)+5)^{\wedge}(4*3)-21$
-249599454	$(9+87)^*(6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-285212705	$(-9-8)^*((-7+6)+5)^{\wedge}(4*3)+2+1$
-249599610	$(9-87)^*(-6-(5^*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-285212707	$(-9-8)^*((-7+6)+5)^{\wedge}(4*3)+2-1$
-249600390	$(-9+87)^*(-6+(5^*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-285383817	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7-(6/(-5^*4)+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-249600546	$(9-87)^*(6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-285609968	$((9+8^*7+65)^{\wedge}4-32)/-1$
-252047367	$((9+87+6^*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)/-1$	-285610032	$((9+8^*7+65)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-252047370	$((9+87+6^*5)^{\wedge}4-3^*2)^*-1$	-290816000	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^*(5/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-252047371	$((9+87+6^*5)^{\wedge}4-3-2)^*-1$	-291199363	$(98-7)^*(6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-252047381	$((9+87+6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3+2)/-1$	-291199545	$(-98+7)^*(-6-(5^*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-252047382	$((9+87+6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3^*2)^*-1$	-291200455	$(98-7)^*(-6+(5^*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-252047385	$((9+87+6^*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)^*-1$	-291200637	$(-98+7)^*(6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-254541824	$((-9+8-7)^*6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1))$	-293945922	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7-(6/5^*4-3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-254855484	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5-4321)$	-298593750	$98^*(-7-6)^*5^{\wedge}(4+3)^*(2+1)$
-2550066112	$((-9+8-7)^*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(-3^*(-2-1))$	-299008000	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6))^*(5/4^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-255102976	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2))^*-1$	-299140047	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7-(6/(-5^*4)+3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-255445974	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5+4321)$	-299428416	$(9/(8-76^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3))^{\wedge}2)^*-1$
-256048121	$((9^*8^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)-3)^*-2+1$	-301149899	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7-(6+5+4)^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1$
-256048122	$((9^*8^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)-3)^*-2*1$	-301149901	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7-(6+5+4)^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1$
-256048123	$((9^*8^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)-3)^*-2-1$	-301326726	$(-9^{\wedge}8^*7/(6-5)^{\wedge}4+321)$
-256048133	$((9^*8^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)-3)^*2+1$	-301327016	$(-9^{\wedge}8^*7-6-5+4+3-2+1)$
-256048134	$((9^*8^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)-3)^*2*1$	-301327029	$(-9^{\wedge}8^*7-6-5-4+32+1)$
-256048135	$((9^*8^*7)^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)-3)^*2-1$	-301327065	$(-9^{\wedge}8^*7-6+5^*4-32^*1)$
-257187500	$9876/(-5^{\wedge}(-4-3)^*(2+1))$	-301327078	$(-9^{\wedge}8^*7-6-5+4-3-21)$
-260009993	$(9-8)^*7-(6^*5)^{\wedge}4*321$	-301327368	$(-9^{\wedge}8^*7*(6-5)^{\wedge}4-321)$
-260012247	$((-9+8)^*-7+(6^*5)^{\wedge}4)^*-321$	-301504193	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7-(6-5-4)^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1$
-260702208	$9*8^*7*(-6-5*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1))$	-301504195	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7-(6-5-4)^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1$
-261994188	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7)^*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4+3+2)+1)$	-302070300	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-262902847	$(-9-8/7)^*((6^*5)^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	-302070496	$98*(7^{\wedge}6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-263232347	$(9/8-76)^*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-303514047	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7+(6/(-5^*4)+3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-266827932	$-98*(7^*6)^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-305854677	$9*87*(6-5^{\wedge}4(-(-3-2)+1))$
-267187424	$(9-8)^*-76*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-305864073	$9*-87*(6+5^{\wedge}4(-(-3-2)+1))$
-267964634	$98^*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4(-(-3-2)+1))$	-306122698	$(-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6*((54-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-267972866	$98^*-7*(6+5^{\wedge}4(-(-3-2)+1))$	-306500961	$-9/87*((6^{\wedge}5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
-268738520	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4)^*(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-307199328	$(9+87)^*(6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-268738600	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4)^*(-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-307199520	$(-9-87)^*(-6-(5^*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-268799928	$9^*-8*(7/6*(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-307200480	$(9+87)^*(-6+(5^*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-268800072	$9^*8*(7/6*(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-307200672	$(-9-87)^*(6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-269725596	$98^*7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2-1))$	-307529973	$9*((((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*-3+2)+1)$
-269766756	$98^*7*-6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2-1))$	-307530027	$-9*((((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3+2)+1)$
-271142501	$(-9/8-76)^*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-307563723	$9*((((8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*-3+2)+1)$
-271180945	$(-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6*((5+43)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-307563777	$9*((((8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*-3-2)-1)$
-272097207	$9*(8^*7+(-6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3)^*(2+1))$	-307864638	$9*87*6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2-1))$
-272098377	$-9*(8^*7+(6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3)^*(2+1))$	-307911618	$9*87*-6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2-1))$
-272109375	$(9*(8+7)^{\wedge}-6/(-5^*43))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-308708172	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7-(6/(-5^*4+3))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-273088512	$9*(-8-7^*65)^*4^{\wedge}(3^*2-1)$	-310361544	$(9*-8-7+6)^*(54^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-273559071	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+65)^*4/(3^*2)+1$	-313895025	$9*(8-(7/(6+5^{\wedge}(4*3))))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-273559073	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+65)^*4/(3^*2)-1$	-313895169	$-9*(8+(7/(6+5^{\wedge}(4*3))))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-273559095	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7/-6+5)^*4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-317657412	$-9*(((-8-7)^*(6+5))^{\wedge}4+3)/21$
-273559135	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7/6-5)^*4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-318047944	$9+8-7*((6^*5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-274658292	$9/8*((-76-5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)-1)$	-318047992	$(-9-8)-7*((6^*5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-275894458	$(-9+8)^*(7+(654-3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-318049639	$((98-(7-6))^{\wedge}5-4)^*-3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-276710415	$(98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4)^*-3+21$	-321550152	$98^*-7*6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-321553582	$98^{*7} * (6 * (-5^{(4+3)+2}) + 1)$	-358640352	$9^{*8} * -76^{*(5+4^{(3^2-1)})}$
-321554954	$98^{*7} * (6 * (-5^{(4+3)+2}) - 1)$	-359437824	$-9^{((-8+7) / 6^{(-5-4)^{*321}})}$
-321558384	$98^{*7} * 6^{*(5^{(4+3)-2+1})}$	-362442762	$(9 - (8+7))^{(6+5)^{*} * (-4^{(-3-2)+1})}$
-321561814	$98^{*7} * (-6^{*5^{(4+3)+2-1}})$	-362673904	$((9^{*8} - 7^{*6^5})^{(4-3)^2})^{*-1}$
-321563186	$98^{*7} * 6^{*(5^{(4+3)+2-1})}$	-362673930	$((9^{*8} - 7^{*6^5})^{(4-3)^2})^{*-1}$
-321566616	$98^{*7} * 6^{*(-5^{(4+3)-2+1})}$	-362673931	$((9^{*8} - 7^{*6^5})^{(4-3)^2})^{*-1}$
-321570046	$98^{*7} * 6^{*(5^{(4+3)+2-1})}$	-362673941	$((9^{*8} - 7^{*6^5})^{(4+3)^2})^{*-1}$
-321571418	$98^{*7} * (-6^{*(5^{(4+3)+2-1})})$	-362673942	$((9^{*8} - 7^{*6^5})^{(4+3)^2})^{*-1}$
-321574848	$98^{*7} * 6^{*(-5^{(4+3)-2-1})}$	-362673968	$((9^{*8} - 7^{*6^5})^{(4+3)^2}) / -1$
-322417904	$((9^{*(8+7)} - 6+5)^{(4-3)^2})^{*-1}$	-362796372	$9^{*8} * (7 + (-6^{(5+4)+3}) / 2+1)$
-322417927	$((-9^{*(8+7)} + 6-5)^{(4-3)^2}) / -1$	-362796588	$9^{*8} * (7 - (6^{(5+4)+3}) / 2+1)$
-322417930	$((9^{*(8+7)} - 6+5)^{(4-3)^2}) / -1$	-362796803	$9^{*8} * (7 - 6^{(5+4)})^{*32+1}$
-322417941	$((9^{*(8+7)} - 6+5)^{(4+3)^2})^{*-1}$	-362796805	$9^{*8} * (7 - 6^{(5+4)})^{*32-1}$
-322417942	$((9^{*(8+7)} - 6+5)^{(4+3)^2}) / -1$	-362796840	$9^{*8} * ((7 - 6^{(5+4)-3}) / 2+1)$
-322417945	$((9^{*(8+7)} - 6+5)^{(4+3)^2}) / -1$	-362797272	$9^{*8} * ((-7 - 6^{(5+4)+3}) / 2-1)$
-322417968	$((9^{*(8+7)} - 6+5)^{(4+3)^2})^{*-1}$	-362797307	$9^{*8} * (-7 - 6^{(5+4)})^{*32+1}$
-322828535	$(-98^{*7})^{(6 - (-5-4)) + 321}$	-362797309	$9^{*8} * (-7 - 6^{(5+4)})^{*32-1}$
-322828793	$(-98^{*7})^{(6+5+4)+3^{*21}}$	-362797524	$9^{*8} * (7 - (-6^{(5+4)+3}) / 2+1)$
-322828829	$(-98^{*7})^{(6 - (-5-4)) + 3^{(2+1)}}$	-362797740	$9^{*8} * (7 + (6^{(5+4)+3}) / 2+1)$
-322828852	$(-98^{*7})^{(6 - (-5-4)) + 3+2-1}$	-363031000	$(9^{*8} + (-7^{*6})^5)^{*} * ((4/3)^{(2+1)})$
-322828883	$(-98^{*7})^{(6 - (-5-4)) - 3^{(2+1)}}$	-363031102	$98 + (-7^{*6})^5 * ((4/3)^{(2+1)})$
-322828919	$(-98^{*7})^{(6+5+4) - 3^{*21}}$	-363031128	$9^{*8} + (-7^{*6})^5 * ((4/3)^{(2+1)})$
-322829177	$(-98^{*7})^{(6 - (-5-4)) - 321}$	-363031200	$((9-8)^{*} - 7^{*6})^5 * ((4/3)^{(2+1)})$
-323414238	$98^{*7} * (6 - 5^{*4^{(3^2-1)}})$	-363031272	$-9^{*8} + (-7^{*6})^5 * ((4/3)^{(2+1)})$
-323426082	$-98^{*7} * (6 - 5^{*4^{(3^2-1)}})$	-363031298	$-98 + (-7^{*6})^5 * ((4/3)^{(2+1)})$
-324615200	$-98 / (7^{*65^{*4}})^{((-3+2) - 1)}$	-363031400	$(-9^{*8} - (7^{*6})^5)^{*} * ((4/3)^{(2+1)})$
-325129504	$-98^{*(7^6 + (5^{*4})^{(3+2)}) - 1}$	-363151350	$(9 - (8+7))^{(6+5)^{*} * (4^{(-3-2)+1})}$
-325129700	$98^{*(7^6 + (5^{*4})^{(3+2)}) - 1}$	-363893776	$(9^{((-8+7) + 6) - 5^{(4+3)}})^{(2/-1)}$
-325771866	$9 + (8+7)^6 / -5^{*(4^{*3})^{(2-1)}}$	-364903143	$(9+8)^{7^6} - 6/5^{*(4^{*3})^{(2+1)}}$
-325771884	$9 + (8+7)^6 / -5^{*(4^{*3})^{(2-1)}}$	-364905753	$(-9 - 8^{*7^6} / 5)^{*} * ((4/3)^{(2+1)})$
-329148288	$(-9-8)^{*} * (7^{*6})^5 * 4^{*3} * (-2-1)$	-367017156	$9^{*8} * 7^{*6} * (5^{(4+3)-2-1})$
-332074706	$(-9^{(87/6-5-4)}) / (3+2^{*-1})$	-367021071	$9^{*8} * 7^{*6} * (6^{*(5^{(4+3)+2})+1})$
-332150593	$((98+7+6^{*5})^{(4-3)^2}) / -1$	-367022637	$9^{*8} * 7^{*6} * (6^{*(5^{(4+3)+2})-1})$
-332150619	$((98+7+6^{*5})^{(4-3)^2})^{*-1}$	-367026552	$9^{*8} * 7^{*6} * (5^{(4+3)-2+1})$
-332150631	$((98+7+6^{*5})^{(4+3)^2})^{*-1}$	-367030467	$9^{*8} * 7^{*6} * (-6^{*5^{(4+3)+2-1}})$
-332150657	$((98+7+6^{*5})^{(4+3)^2})^{*-1}$	-367032033	$9^{*8} * 7^{*6} * (6^{*5^{(4+3)+2-1}})$
-333811169	$(-9-8)^{(7+6^{*5^{(4-3)^2}})^{-1}}$	-367035948	$9^{*8} * 7^{*6} * (-5^{(4+3)-2+1})$
-335999265	$(-98+7)^{*} * (6 - (5^{*4})^{(3+2)+1})$	-367039863	$9^{*8} * 7^{*6} * (6^{*(5^{(4+3)+2})-1})$
-335999475	$(-98-7)^{*} * (-6 - (5^{*4})^{(3+2)+1})$	-367041429	$9^{*8} * 7^{*6} * (-6^{*(5^{(4+3)+2})-1})$
-336000525	$(98+7)^{*} * (-6 + (5^{*4})^{(3+2)+1})$	-367045344	$9^{*8} * 7^{*6} * (-5^{(4+3)-2-1})$
-336000735	$(-98-7)^{*} * (6 + (5^{*4})^{(3+2)+1})$	-369095993	$(9-8)^{*} * 7 - (65^{*4})^{(3+2)^2}$
-338035761	$((9^{*8} + 7)^{*} * (6 - 5 - 4)^{(3+2+1)})$	-372506624	$-98^{*(7+65)^{*} * 4^{(3^2-1)}}$
-341067023	$-9^{*8} * (76 / (5+4) / 3)^{(2+1)}$	-373301035	$((9 + (8+7))^{*} * 6 - 5)^{(4-3)^2})^{*-1}$
-341067025	$-9^{*8} * (76 / (5+4) / 3)^{(2-1)}$	-373301036	$((9 + (8+7))^{*} * 6 - 5)^{(4-3)^2})^{*-1}$
-342018495	$(9+8)^{((-7+6) + 5)^{*} * (-4^{(3^2+1)})}$	-373301046	$((9 + (8+7))^{*} * 6 - 5)^{(4+3)^2})^{*-1}$
-342101984	$((98^{*7} - 6) / 5)^{(4-3)^2})^{*-1}$	-373301047	$((9 + (8+7))^{*} * 6 - 5)^{(4+3)^2})^{*-1}$
-342102007	$((98^{*7} - 6) / 5)^{(4-3)^2})^{*-1}$	-373301050	$((9 + (8+7))^{*} * 6 - 5)^{(4+3)^2})^{*-1}$
-342102025	$((98^{*7} - 6) / 5)^{(4+3)^2})^{*-1}$	-374857137	$((-9+8) / -7 - 6)^{*} * (5^{*4})^{(3^2-1)}$
-342102048	$((98^{*7} - 6) / 5)^{(4+3)^2})^{*-1}$	-374863116	$9^{*8} + ((-7-6)^{*} * 5)^{(4+3)^2})^{*-21}$
-342185537	$(9+8)^{((-7+6) + 5)^{*} * (-4^{(3^2-1)})}$	-375390208	$9^{*8} * 7^{*6} * (-6 - 5^{*4})^{(4/3)^{(2+1)}}$
-342854532	$(9^{*8} - 7^6) / 54^{((-3+2) - 1)}$	-375633389	$(9-8 - 76^{*5^4})^{*3} * (-2-1)$
-342884352	$9/8 - 7^{*(6^{(5+4)+3} - 21)}$	-382359250	$(-9+8)^{*} * 7^6 * ((54+3)^{(2+1)})$
-343274436	$(9^{*8} + 7^6) / -54^{((-3+2) - 1)}$	-384159998	$((98+7^6)^{(5-4+3)-2})^{*-1}$
-343453824	$9^{*(8+7+6^{(5+4^3)})^{*21}}$	-384160002	$((98+7^6)^{(5-4+3)+2})^{*-1}$
-344196621	$-9^{*8} * ((7 + (6 - (5+4)))^{(3-2)+1})$	-385875968	$9^{*8} * 7^{*6} * (-6 - 5^{*4})^{(4-3^2-1)}$
-344255679	$9/8^{*(7^6 * (54-3)^{(2+1)})}$	-390200888	$(9 / (8 - (76^{*5^4})^3))^{((-2+1))}$
-344550915	$-9^{*8} * ((7 - (6 - (5+4)))^{(3-2)+1})$	-390483072	$(-9^{*8} + 7^6 + 6^{(5+4^3)})^{*21}$
-347253480	$-9/8^{*(7 - (6^{*5-4})^3)^{(2-1)}}$	-393142851	$((-9+8) / 7 - 6)^{*} * ((5^{*4})^{(3^2-1)})$
-347807124	$-9/8^{*(7 + (6^{*5-4})^3)^{(2-1)}}$	-395254159	$((9^{*(8+7)+6})^{(5-4+3)-2})^{*-1}$
-349360127	$(9^{*8})^{((-7+6) + 5)^{*} * (-4 - 3^2+1)}$	-395254163	$((9^{*(8+7)+6})^{(5-4+3)+2})^{*-1}$
-349360128	$(9^{*8})^{((-7+6) + 5)^{*} * (-4 - 3^2+1)}$	-396809279	$9/8^{*7^6} * (5+4)^{*} * (-3-2)+1$
-352275355	$((9^{*8} + (7+6)^{*} * 5)^{(4-3)^2})^{*-1}$	-396809281	$9/8^{*7^6} * (5+4)^{*} * (-3-2)-1$
-352275366	$((9^{*8} + (7+6)^{*} * 5)^{(4+3)^2})^{*-1}$	-398131200	$((-9+8-7)^{*} * 6)^5 * ((4/3)^{(2+1)})$
-352275370	$((9^{*8} + (7+6)^{*} * 5)^{(4+3)^2})^{*-1}$	-399169881	$(9/8 - 7^6)^{*} * (5^{(4+3)^2}) - 1$
-353046591	$9 - 8/7^{*(6+5^4)^{(3^2-1)}}$	-400400292	$((-9-8)^{(7+6)} + (5^{*4})^3)^{(2+1)}$
-353046609	$9 - 8/7^{*(6+5^4)^{(3^2-1)}}$	-400400304	$(-9-8)^{(7+6)} + (5^{*4})^3)^{(2+1)}$
-353939706	$9/8 / ((7/6+5)^{*} * (-4/3))^{((-2+1))}$	-402240384	$(9^{*8} - 7^6 - 6^{(5+4^3)})^{*21}$
-354599490	$(9/8 - 7)^{*} * ((-6^{(5+4+3)})^{(2-1)})$	-405555704	$(-9-8)^{(7+6)} + (6/54)^{((-3^2-1))}$
-355770567	$9^{*(8^7 + (6+5-4)^{*} * -3^2+1)}$	-406087139	$((-9-8)^{(7+6)} + (54^{*3})^{(2+1)})$
-355770585	$9^{*(8^7 + (6+5-4)^{*} * 3^2+1)}$	-406087151	$(-9-8)^{(7+6)} + (54^{*3})^{(2+1)}$
-355878642	$(9/8 - 7)^{*} * ((6^{(5+4+3)})^{(2-1)})$	-406265625	$(-9^{*(8+7)} - 6)^{((-5+4))} * 321$
-358585632	$9^{*8} * 76^{*(5-4^{(3^2-1)})}$	-406559520	$9^{*(8-7^6)^5} + 4^{(3^2+1)}$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-406847488	$9^*8^{\wedge}7^*(-6-5^*(4-(-3^{\wedge}-2+1)))$	-429981664	$((9^*8+7+65)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-408656672	$9^*(8-7^*6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3^*(2+1))$	-429981728	$((9^*8+7+65)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-408771360	$9^*((8+7^*-6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$	-430021800	$9/8^*(-7^{\wedge}6^*(5+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-409066272	$9^*((8+7^*-6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$	-430259193	$(-9+8)^*7^*((6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-409180960	$9^*(8-7^*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(-3^*(-2-1))$	-435243599	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3)^2)^*-1$
-409220007	$(9^*8^*7-(6+5)^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$	-435243603	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3)^2)^*-1$
-409230584	$(9-8)^*7-(6+5)^{\wedge}(4+3)^*21$	-439453041	$9^*(8^*7/6-5^{\wedge}(4+3^*2+1))$
-409241175	$(9^*8^*7+(6+5)^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$	-439453209	$-9^*(8^*7/6+5^{\wedge}(4+3^*2+1))$
-409418520	$(-9+8)^*7^{\wedge}6^*((5-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-442050593	$((98+7^*6+5)^{\wedge}4-32)/-1$
-410156208	$(9-8)^*7^*6^*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3^*2)+1)$	-442050616	$((98+7^*6+5)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-410233697	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7+(6^*54)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$	-442050619	$((98+7^*6+5)^{\wedge}4-3^*2)^*-1$
-410271073	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7+(65^*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$	-442050630	$((98+7^*6+5)^{\wedge}4+3+2)/-1$
-410331317	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7+6^*((5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-442050631	$((98+7^*6+5)^{\wedge}4+3^*2)^*-1$
-410334323	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7+6^*5^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-442050634	$((98+7^*6+5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-410336880	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+65)+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-442050657	$((98+7^*6+5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-410337010	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7-65+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-446496768	$-9^*(-8+765)^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-410340336	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+65)-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-447328259	$(-9+8)^*7^*((6+(-5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-410340466	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7-65-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-448000035	$(9-8)^*7^*(-6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2-1))$
-410343023	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7+6^*-5^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-448672259	$(-9+8)^*7^*((6-(-5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-410346029	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7-6^*((5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-448790528	$9^*8^{\wedge}7/-6)^{\wedge}(-5+4)^*321$
-410406273	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7-(65^*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$	-449269632	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*21$
-410443649	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7-(6^*54)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$	-451215288	$9^*(8-765^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-411278112	$9^*((8-7^*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(-3^*(-2-1)))$	-451215432	$-9^*(8-765^*-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-412090368	$9^*8^{\wedge}7^*((-6/5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-21)$	-452874240	$9^*8^{\wedge}7^*-6^*(5-(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$
-413208144	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7-6^*5)/(4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-453095424	$9^*8^{\wedge}7^*-6^*(5-(-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1))$
-414590195	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+6)-(54^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-454371824	$((9^*(8+7)+(6+5))^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-414590207	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7-6-(54^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-454371850	$((9^*(8+7)+(6+5))^{\wedge}4-3^*2)^*-1$
-415065456	$-9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}((6-5)+4)+3)^2-1$	-454371851	$((9^*(8+7)+6+5)^{\wedge}4-3-2)/-1$
-415065645	$9^*((-8^*7^{\wedge}(6-5+4+3)+2)+1)$	-454371862	$((9^*(8+7)+(6+5))^{\wedge}4+3^*2)^*-1$
-415065699	$9^*((-8^*7^{\wedge}(6-5+4+3)-2)-1)$	-454371865	$((9^*(8+7)+6+5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)^*-1$
-415065888	$-9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}((6-5)+4)+3)-(-2-1))$	-454371888	$((9^*(8+7)+6+5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-415121642	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7-(6/54)^{\wedge}(-3^*2-1)$	-455933952	$9^*(-8-765)^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-415409583	$9+((8-76)^{\wedge}5-4)/(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-455999488	$98^*(-76+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-415409601	$-9+((8-76)^{\wedge}5-4)/(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-459211680	$((9-8-7)^{\wedge}6+54^{\wedge}(3+2))^*-1$
-416324601	$(-9+8)^*7^*((6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-459427168	$((9-8+7)^{\wedge}6+54^{\wedge}(3+2))/-1$
-417463634	$98^*(7-65^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-460165024	$((9+8-7)^{\wedge}6+54^{\wedge}(3+2))^*-1$
-417464320	$98^*(-7-6)^*5^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-460728189	$9/8^*(-7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-417465006	$-98^*(7-65^*-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-461184059	$(-98^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+4)^*(3+2)+1$
-418161569	$((9-87-65)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$	-461184061	$(-98^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+4)^*(3+2)-1$
-418161592	$((9-87-65)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)/-1$	-461184099	$(-98^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-4)^*(3+2)+1$
-418161596	$((9-87-65)^{\wedge}4-3-2)^*-1$	-461184101	$(-98^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-4)^*(3+2)-1$
-418161606	$((9-87-65)^{\wedge}4+3+2)^*-1$	-463495284	$(9^*87^*6)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)^*21$
-418161607	$((9-87-65)^{\wedge}4+3^*2)^*-1$	-464413824	$(9^*8+7)/-6^{\wedge}(5-4^*3)^*21$
-418161610	$((9^*8+76-5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)^*-1$	-466694560	$((98/7)^{\wedge}6+54^{\wedge}(3+2))^*-1$
-418161633	$((9-87-65)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$	-470919393	$-9/8^*7^*((-6^{\wedge}5+43)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-418595016	$(-9+8)^*7^*((6^{\wedge}5-43)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-471151971	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3-21)$
-418887329	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7-65)/(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-472391997	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)/(5^*-4)^{\wedge}3-2+1$
-420277042	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+6)-(5^*43)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-472391999	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)/(5^*-4)^{\wedge}3-2-1$
-420277054	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7-6-(5^*43)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-472392001	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)/(5^*4)^{\wedge}3-2+1$
-421142535	$(-9/8-7^*6)^*5^{\wedge}(4+3^*2)-1$	-472392003	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)/(5^*4)^{\wedge}3-2-1$
-421957865	$(-9+8)^*7^*((6^{\wedge}5-4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-472451049	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*((-5^*4)^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
-422501520	$(-9+8)^*7^*((-6^{\wedge}5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-472569147	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*((-5^*4)^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
-423154368	$(-9+8)^*7^*((-6^{\wedge}5+4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-473632029	$9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)^*((-5^*4)^{\wedge}3-21)$
-423263190	$-98/7^*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)^3-2-1)$	-474360633	$9^*(8-7^*((6-5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1))$
-423263218	$-98/7^*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)^3-2+1)$	-474360903	$-9^*(8+7^*((6-5^*4)^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1))$
-423263246	$98/7^*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)^3-2-1)$	-474551993	$(9-8)^*7-(65^*4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-423263274	$98/7^*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)^3-2-1)$	-474609303	$9^*(8+(7^*6^*(-5-4)+3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-423372096	$(-9+8)^*7^*((6^{\wedge}5+4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-474609447	$-9^*(8-(7^*6^*(-5-4)+3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-424025616	$(-9+8)^*7^*((6^{\wedge}5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-475004928	$9^*8^{\wedge}7^*(-6-5^*(4-(3^*2)^{\wedge}-1))$
-424570601	$(-9+8)^*7^*((6^{\wedge}5+4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-475314210	$-9/8^*7^*((-6^{\wedge}5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-427483584	$9^*-8^*76^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2-1)$	-475314219	$9/8^*(-7^*(-6^{\wedge}5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-427488984	$9^*8^*(76^*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2)+1)$	-475410936	$9^*(8-76^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
-427489128	$9^*8^*(76^*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2)-1)$	-475411080	$-9^*(8+76^{\wedge}5/((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
-427494528	$9^*-8^*76^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2+1)$	-476048664	$-9/8^*7^*((-6^{\wedge}5+4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-427505472	$9^*8^*76^*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2+1)$	-476048673	$9/8^*(-7^*((6^{\wedge}5-4)+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-427510872	$9^*-8^*(76^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2)-1)$	-476170920	$9^*8^*((7^*6^*(-5+4+3)+1)$
-427511016	$9^*8^*(-76^*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2)-1)$	-476171352	$9^*8^*((-7^*6^*54^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$
-427516416	$9^*8^*76^*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2-1)$	-476293608	$-9/8^*7^*((6^{\wedge}5+4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-427807992	$(9-8^{\wedge}7/6)^*((5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	-476293617	$9/8^*(-7^*((6^{\wedge}5+4)-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-427830024	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7/6)^*((5^*(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	-477028818	$-9/8^*7^*((6^{\wedge}5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-427957320	$(-9+8)^*7^*((6^{\wedge}5+43)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-477028827	$9/8^*(-7^*(6^{\wedge}5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-429839592	$(-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)+5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*(2+1)$	-478416168	$-9^*8^*((((7^*6+5)^*4)^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-478416600	$9^8 * (((-7^6 - 5)^4)^{\wedge} 3 - 2) - 1$	-538206732	$(9 * ((8+7)^{\wedge} 6 - 5) / -4+3)^{*} 21$
-479785214	$((9^8 + 76)^{\wedge} (5 - 4 + 3) - 2)^{*} - 1$	-538206858	$(-9 * ((8+7)^{\wedge} 6 - 5) / 4 - 3)^{*} 21$
-479785218	$((9^8 + 76)^{\wedge} (5 - 4 + 3) + 2)^{*} - 1$	-538207362	$9^8 * ((8+7)^{\wedge} 6 - 5) / -4 - 3)^{*} 21$
-481451985	$-9/8^7 * ((6^{\wedge} 5 + 43)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-539428563	$((9+8) / -7 - 6)^{*} ((5^4)^{\wedge} (3^* 2) - 1)$
-481869824	$((-9+8)^7 * 6^5)^4 * 4^{\wedge} (3+2+1)$	-545612760	$9^{\wedge} ((-8+7)+6)^5 * (-43^{\wedge} 2+1)$
-482461546	$-98 / (7+6)^{*} ((5^4)^{\wedge} (3^* 2) + 1)$	-545908005	$9^{\wedge} ((-8+7)+6)^5 * -5^* 43^{\wedge} 2^{\wedge} 1$
-483728832	$9^8 * (7 - (6^{\wedge} (5+4) / 3^* 2 - 1))$	-545967054	$-9^{\wedge} ((-8+7)+6)^5 * (5^* 43^{\wedge} 2+1)$
-483728976	$9^8 * (7+6^{\wedge} (5+4) / -3^* 2 - 1)$	-546203250	$9^{\wedge} ((-8+7)+6)^5 * -5^* (43^{\wedge} 2+1)$
-483729840	$9^8 * (7 - 6^{\wedge} (5+4) / -3^* 2 - 1)$	-547246080	$9^8 * 8^7 * (-6^* (5 - 4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2)) + 1)$
-483729984	$9^8 * (7 - 6^{\wedge} (5+4) / -3^* 2 - 1))$	-547467264	$9^8 * 8^7 * (-6^* (5+4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2)) + 1)$
-486866177	$(-9 - 8)^{\wedge} 7 - (6^* 5^4)^{\wedge} (-3 - 2)^{\wedge} - 1$	-547981249	$((9^8 + 76 + 5)^{\wedge} 4 - 32)^{*} - 1$
-490403550	$(-9/8 - 7)^{*} ((-6^{\wedge} 5 + 4 + 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-547981275	$((9^8 + 76 + 5)^{\wedge} 4 - 3^* 2) / -1$
-490733763	$-9^8 * ((8^7 * 6 + 5)^{*} (4 + 3^{\wedge} (-2 + 1)))$	-547981287	$((9^8 + 76 + 5)^{\wedge} 4 + 3^* 2) / -1$
-492127590	$(-9/8 - 7)^{*} ((6^{\wedge} 5 + 4 + 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-547981313	$((9^8 + 76 + 5)^{\wedge} 4 + 32)^{*} - 1$
-492884395	$((9+8)^7 * 6^5)^4 - 3^* 2)^{*} - 1$	-549316410	$9/8 * ((7/6 + 5^{\wedge} (4^3))^*) - 2 - 1$
-492884406	$((9+8)^7 * 6^5)^4 + 3 + 2)^{*} - 1$	-549453824	$9^8 * 8^7 * -6^* (5 - 4^* 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$
-492884410	$((9+8)^7 * 6^5)^4 + 3^{\wedge} 2)^{*} - 1$	-550998016	$((9^8 - 7) + 6) / 5^* 4^{\wedge} 3^* (-2 + 1)$
-503312880	$(9 - (8^{\wedge} 7 - 6))^5 * ((4+3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-558268416	$9^8 * 8^7 * (6^* 5 - (4/3)^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$
-503315031	$9 - (8^{\wedge} 7 - 6)^5 * ((4+3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-559600812	$-9^8 * (7+6 - (5+4)^{\wedge} (-3 - 2 + 1))$
-503315049	$-9 - (8^{\wedge} 7 - 6)^5 * ((4+3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-559605186	$-9^8 * (7+6 - ((5+4)^3)^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$
-503315760	$(9 - 8^{\wedge} 7 - 6)^5 * ((4+3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-559609560	$-9^8 * (7+6 + ((5+4)^3)^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$
-503317200	$(9 - 8^{\wedge} 7 - 6)^5 * -5^* ((4+3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-559613934	$-9^8 * (7+6 + (5+4)^{\wedge} (-3 - 2 + 1))$
-503317911	$9 - (8^{\wedge} 7 + 6)^5 * ((4+3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-560003885	$(9/8 - 7^{\wedge} 6)^{*} ((5+4^3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
-503320080	$(-9 - (8^{\wedge} 7 + 6))^5 * ((4+3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-560009240	$(-9+8)^7 * 7^{\wedge} 6^* ((5+4^3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
-506249968	$((9^8 - 7^* 6)^5)^4 - 32)^{*} - 1$	-560014595	$(-9/8 - 7^{\wedge} 6)^{*} ((5+4^3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
-506249994	$((9^8 - 7^* 6)^5)^4 - 3^* 2)^{*} - 1$	-562448624	$((98/7^* (6+5))^{\wedge} 4 - 32)^{*} - 1$
-506250005	$((9+8+7+6)^5)^4 + 3 + 2)^{*} - 1$	-562448688	$((98 / (7 / (-6 - 5)))^{\wedge} 4 + 32)^{*} - 1$
-506250032	$((9^8 - 7^* 6)^5)^4 + 32)^{*} - 1$	-563809515	$(-9+8 / (7^* 6))^5 * ((5^4)^{\wedge} (3^* 2) - 1)$
-506306538	$9^8 + (7^* (6^5 - 4 + 3))^{\wedge} (2+1)$	-564349632	$((9^8)^{\wedge} ((-7+6)+5) - 4^{\wedge} 3)^{*} - 21$
-507354624	$9^8 * (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5)^{\wedge} ((-6+5)+4)^{*} 321$	-564350829	$((9^8)^{\wedge} (-7 - (-6 - 5)) - 4) - 3)^{*} - 21$
-508339724	$((-9+8)^7 * 6^5)^4 * 4321$	-564350948	$((9^8)^{\wedge} (-7 - (-6 - 5)) - 4/3)^{*} - 21$
-508690432	$(98/7 - 6^{\wedge} 5)^4 * 4^{\wedge} (3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-564351004	$((9^8)^{\wedge} (-7 - (-6 - 5)) + 4/3)^{*} - 21$
-509607817	$(9+8)^7 * 6^5 * 4^{\wedge} (3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-564352320	$((9^8)^{\wedge} ((-7+6)+5) + 4^{\wedge} 3)^{*} - 21$
-509607929	$(9-8)^7 * 6^5 * 4^{\wedge} (3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-565051392	$9/8^{\wedge} - 7^* (-6^* 5 + 4^{\wedge} (-3 - (-2 + 1)))$
-509607943	$(-9+8)^7 * 6^5 * 4^{\wedge} (3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-565289073	$9/8 * ((7 - (6+5^{\wedge} 4)^{\wedge} 3)^2) - 1$
-509608055	$(-9-8)^7 * 6^5 * 4^{\wedge} (3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-565678080	$9/8^{\wedge} - 7^* 6^5 * 4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2) - 1$
-510066688	$((-9+8)^7 * 6^5)^4 - 4^{\wedge} (3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-565788672	$9^8 * 8^7 * -6^* (5 - 4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2 + 1))$
-510525440	$(98/7 + 6^{\wedge} 5)^5 * -4^{\wedge} (3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-566120457	$9^8 * (8^7 * -6^* (5 - 4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2)) - 1)$
-510603264	$(9^8)^{\wedge} ((-7+6)+5)^4 * (4^* (-3 - 2) + 1)$	-566157312	$9/8^{\wedge} - 7^* (-6^* 5 + 4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2 + 1))$
-513022500	$((98^7 * (6+5)+4)^3)^{\wedge} 2 / -1$	-566304768	$9^8 * 8^7 * (6^5 + 4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2 + 1))$
-513736704	$9^8 * (-876+5)^4 * 4^{\wedge} (3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-566328360	$(9^8 + (-7^* 6)^{\wedge} 5)^5 * (4+3^{\wedge} (-2+1))$
-516428298	$9/8 * (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5^4)^{\wedge} (3+2) - 1$	-566328984	$(9^8 - 8 - (7^* 6)^{\wedge} 5)^5 * (4+3^{\wedge} (-2+1))$
-516693006	$-9/8 * (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5^4)^{\wedge} (3+2) - 1$	-566341623	$-9^8 * (8^7 * 6^5 * (5+4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2)) - 1)$
-517924414	$98 + (7^* - 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$	-566341641	$9^8 * (8^7 * -6^* (5+4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2)) - 1)$
-517924440	$9^8 + (7^* - 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$	-566406250	$9 / (87^* - 6)^5 * 5^{\wedge} (-4 - 3^* 2)^{\wedge} - 1$
-517924495	$9+8 + (7^* - 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$	-566673408	$9^8 * 8^7 * -6^* (5+4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2 + 1))$
-517924511	$9 - 8 + (7^* - 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$	-566784000	$9^8 * 8^7 * 6^5 * 4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2) + 1$
-517924512	$((-9+8)^7 * 6^5)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$	-567410688	$-9^8 * 8^7 * (6^5 + 4^{\wedge} (-3 - (-2 + 1)))$
-517924513	$((-9+8 + (-7^* 6)^{\wedge} 5)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1)))$	-569263149	$(-9+8/76)^5 * ((5^4)^{\wedge} (3^* 2) - 1)$
-517924529	$((-9 - 8 + (-7^* 6)^{\wedge} 5)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1)))$	-570949631	$9^8 * 8^7 * (-6^* 5 - 4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2)) + 1$
-517924584	$9^8 * -8 + (7^* - 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$	-570949633	$9^8 * 8^7 * (-6^* 5 - 4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2)) - 1$
-517924610	$-98 + (7^* - 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$	-574193664	$9^8 * 8^7 * (6^5 + (4/3)^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$
-519634944	$9^8 * (-876 - 5)^4 * 4^{\wedge} (3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-576239991	$9 - 8^* (7^* 6^5)^4 * 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1)$
-520224768	$98^8 * (-76 - 5)^4 * 4^{\wedge} (3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-576240009	$-9 - 8^* (7^* 6^5)^4 * 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1)$
-526436351	$-9^8 * (8^* (7+6))^{\wedge} ((5-4)+3) / 2 + 1$	-577787903	$(9^8)^{\wedge} ((-7+6)+5)^5 * -43/2 + 1$
-526436353	$-9^8 * (8^* (7+6))^{\wedge} ((5-4)+3) / 2 - 1$	-577787904	$(9^8)^{\wedge} ((-7+6)+5)^5 * -43/2^{\wedge} 1$
-526848000	$(9^8 * ((-8 - 76)^5 * 4)^{\wedge} - 3)^{\wedge} (-2 + 1)$	-577787905	$(9^8)^{\wedge} ((-7+6)+5)^5 * -43/2 - 1$
-527605246	$98 + (7^* - 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$	-582665076	$9/8 * (7^* - 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 - 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$
-527605272	$9^8 + (7^* - 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$	-582736833	$(-9 - 8/76)^5 * ((5^4)^{\wedge} (3^* 2) - 1)$
-527605327	$9+8 + (7^* - 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$	-584994816	$9^8 * 8^7 * 6^5 * (5 - 4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2)) + 1$
-527605343	$9 - 8 + (7^* - 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$	-585216000	$9^8 * 8^7 * 6^5 * (5 + 4^{\wedge} (-3 - 2)) + 1$
-527605344	$((-9+8)^7 * 6^5)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$	-585640000	$((-98 + 76)^5)^{\wedge} 5 * ((-3 - 2) + 1)$
-527605345	$((-9+8 + (-7^* 6)^{\wedge} 5)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1)))$	-585874591	$((-9 - 8^* 7^{\wedge} (6+5)) - 4)^3 * 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1)$
-527605361	$((-9 - 8 + (-7^* 6)^{\wedge} 5)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1)))$	-588190467	$(-9+8 / (-7^* 6))^5 * ((5^4)^{\wedge} (3^* 2) - 1)$
-527605416	$9^8 * -8 + (7^* - 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$	-591224832	$(9^8)^{\wedge} ((-7+6)+5)^5 * (-43+21)$
-527605442	$-98 + (7^* - 6)^{\wedge} 5 * (4 + 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$	-591847686	$9^8 - (-7+6^{\wedge} (5+4))^5 * 3^* 21$
-533387430	$(9^8 - 87)^{\wedge} ((-6+5)+4)^3 * (3^{\wedge} -2 + 1)$	-591848568	$9^8 + (-7 - 6^{\wedge} (5+4))^5 * 3^* 21$
-533647476	$9/8 * ((7 + (6 - 5^4)^{\wedge} 3)^2) - 1$	-592240864	$((98 - 7 + 65)^{\wedge} 4 - 32)^{*} - 1$
-533655855	$9^8 * 8^7 * 6^5 * (6+5-4) / -3^{\wedge} -2 + 1$	-592240890	$((98 - 7 + 65)^{\wedge} 4 - 3^* 2)^{*} - 1$
-533655873	$-9^8 * (8^7 * 6^5 * (6+5-4) / 3^{\wedge} -2 + 1)$	-592240891	$((98 - 7 + 65)^{\wedge} 4 - 3 - 2)^{*} - 1$
-536615393	$(-9+8 / (7+6))^5 * ((5^4)^{\wedge} (3^* 2) + 1)$	-592240901	$((98 - 7 + 65)^{\wedge} 4 + 3 + 2)^{*} - 1$
-538206228	$-9^8 * (((8+7)^{\wedge} 6 - 5) / 4 - 3)^{*} 21$	-592240902	$((98 - 7 + 65)^{\wedge} 4 + 3^* 2)^{*} - 1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-592240928	$((98-7+65)^4+32)/-1$	-650268000	$((9+8+7)^6+54^4(3+2))^*-1$
-592399980	$-9^8+(7*(6^5*-4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-656099979	$(9*((-8-7)*6)^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)+21$
-593556012	$9/8*(7*-6)^{\wedge}5*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-656099997	$(9*((-8-7)*6)^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)+2+1$
-595230660	$9^8+(-7*(6^5*4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-656100003	$((9*((-8-7)*6)^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-2)-1$
-595591168	$9^8*7^*(6-5*(4-(-3^{\wedge}2-2-1)))$	-656100021	$(9*((-8-7)*6)^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-21$
-597333315	$9-8^7/6*((5^4)^{\wedge}(3^2)-1)$	-656356789	$-9/((-87*-6))^{\wedge}(-5/(4-3))-21$
-597333333	$-9-8^7/6*((5^4)^{\wedge}(3^2)-1)$	-656908235	$(9/(-8-7*(65-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-600182784	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))*(-4/3-21)$	-659108868	$(9^*8-7^{\wedge}(6+5)+4)/3+21$
-600585876	$-9*(8-7/6)*(5^{\wedge}(4+3^2)-1)$	-659108958	$(9^*-8-7^{\wedge}(6+5)+4)/3-21$
-600585999	$9*(8-7/6)*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3^2)-1)$	-665832554	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+6)/(5/43+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-601406355	$(9^*8-7^{\wedge}6)*-5*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-669840888	$(9/(8-(7*65^4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-602142915	$(9^*8+7^{\wedge}6)*5*(-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-671898236	$((9+87+65)^{\wedge}4-3-2)/-1$
-602582125	$(9^*8-7^{\wedge}6)*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-671898246	$((9+87+65)^{\wedge}4+3+2)^*-1$
-602654100	$(9^8*-7*(6-5)^{\wedge}4-3)^*2/1$	-674179200	$-9^8/(765^4)^{\wedge}(-3+2)-1$
-603320125	$(9^*8+7^{\wedge}6)*-5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-675282461	$(9-8^{\wedge}7*6)*(54-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-607125495	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4)+32)+1)$	-675283427	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7*6)*(54-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-607125513	$9*(8^{\wedge}7*(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4)-32)-1)$	-677941128	$-9^8-(-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*3^*21$
-607993281	$((-9^*8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*3)^*21$	-677942010	$-9^8+(-7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*3^*21$
-607993407	$(-9^*8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3)^*21$	-679366656	$9^*8^{\wedge}7*-6*(5-4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
-611223165	$-9/8*((7+(-6^{\wedge}5+4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-679587840	$9^*8^{\wedge}7*-6*(5+4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$
-611226729	$(9*(-8/7^{\wedge}(6-5-4)-3))^{\wedge}2/-1$	-681324102	$-9^8+(-7*(6^5*4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-611296392	$(9-(-8/7)^{\wedge}6)*(54-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-683671063	$(9-8^{\wedge}7*6)*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-611296866	$9-(-8+7)^{\wedge}6*(54-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-683672041	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7*6)*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-611296884	$-9-(-8+7)^{\wedge}6*(54-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-687234375	$(-9*(8+7)^{\wedge}-6/543)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-611297358	$(9+(-8+7)^{\wedge}6)*(-54+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-688746753	$9*(87+(-6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1)$
-611408335	$(-9-8/7)*((6^{\wedge}5-4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-688747032	$9*(8^*7+(-6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1)$
-611590329	$9/8*((7-((6^{\wedge}5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-688747401	$9*(8+7-(-6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1)$
-611590347	$-9/8*((7+((6^{\wedge}5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-688747504	$((9*(-8-7)*6/5)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-611957619	$-9/8*((7-(-6^{\wedge}5+4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-688747568	$((9*(-8-7)*6/5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-612196080	$(-9-8/7)*((6^{\wedge}5-4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-688747671	$-9*(8+7+(-6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1)$
-612219967	$9+8*(7-(-6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1)$	-688748040	$9*(8*-7-(-6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1)$
-612219985	$-9+8*(7-(-6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1)$	-688748319	$-9*(87+(-6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1)$
-612220079	$9-8*(7+(-6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1)$	-691731700	$(9*-8+7/6)*(5^{\wedge}(4+3^2)-1)$
-612220097	$-9-8*(7+(-6*54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1)$	-691980165	$-9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-612482499	$-9/8*((7-(-6^{\wedge}5+4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-699560064	$(-9-8)^*7/6^{\wedge}(5-4^*3)^*21$
-612850041	$9/8*((7-(-6^{\wedge}5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-700605696	$(-9+8)^*76^{\wedge}((5-4)+3)^*21$
-612850059	$-9/8*((7+(-6^{\wedge}5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-702465363	$9+(8*(7*-6)^{\wedge}-5/43)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-613217709	$-9/8*((7+(-6^{\wedge}5+4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-702465381	$-9+(8*(7*-6)^{\wedge}5/43)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-614404464	$(-9-8/7)*((-6^{\wedge}5-4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-705911729	$((98+(7+6)^*5)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-614671866	$9-(-8+7)^{\wedge}6*(54-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-705911752	$((98-(-7-6)^*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)^*-1$
-614671884	$-9-(-8+7)^{\wedge}6*(54-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-705911755	$((98+(7+6)^*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-614752578	$(-9*(8+7)+6)^*5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}21$	-705911766	$((98+(7+6)^*5)^{\wedge}4+3+2)^*-1$
-615384625	$(-9-8/(7+6))*((5^4)^{\wedge}(3^2)+1)$	-705911770	$((98+(7+6)^*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-615515616	$9-(-8+7)^{\wedge}6*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-705911793	$((98+(7+6)^*5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-615515634	$-9-(-8+7)^{\wedge}6*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-711524352	$987*(-6-5)^*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-618098688	$(9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)*(4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-711529956	$(-9+8)*((7+(-6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3))^*(-2-1)$
-618890136	$(9-(-8+7)^{\wedge}6)*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-711529970	$(9-8)^*7+(-6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3^*(2+1)$
-618890616	$9-(-8+7)^{\wedge}6*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-714256697	$(9-8)^*7-(-6*54)^{\wedge}3^*21$
-618890634	$-9-(-8+7)^{\wedge}6*(54+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-714518156	$(9*-8-7/6)*(5^{\wedge}(4+3^2)-1)$
-618891114	$(9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6)*(-54-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-718072968	$(-9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)+5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*(-2-1)$
-620019720	$-9^*8/7*((6^{\wedge}5-4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-718092564	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+65)/(4^*3)^*21$
-620607744	$(9^*8*(7^{\wedge}((-6+5)+4)+3))^{\wedge}2/-1$	-720896000	$(-98+76)/(5/4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-621298111	$9+8/-7*((6^{\wedge}5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-725589072	$9^*8*(7-(-6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3^*21))$
-621298129	$-9+8/-7*((6^{\wedge}5-4)^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-725590080	$9*-8*(7+6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3^*21)$
-626953125	$((9-8)^{\wedge}7-6)^{\wedge}(5+4)^*321$	-725593104	$9^*8*(7-(-6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3^*21)))$
-628798464	$(9^*8*76)^{\wedge}((-5+4)+3)^*-21$	-725593518	$-9*(-8*(7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-630142749	$9/8*(-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-725593698	$9*((8*(7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))-3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-634863096	$(9^*8*-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*-3^*21$	-725594004	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)-4)^*-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-634926600	$(9^*8*-7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))^*3^*21$	-725594220	$((9^*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)+4)^*-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-641154075	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+65)*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-725594526	$9*((-8*(7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))+3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-641154175	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+65)*((4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-725594706	$9*(-8*(7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-644972040	$9^*8*(7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(-3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-725595120	$9*-8*(7+6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3^*21)$
-644972096	$9^*8*(7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(-3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-725598144	$9^*8*(7-(-6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3^*21))$
-644972992	$9^*8*(7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(-3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-725599152	$9*-8*(7+6^{\wedge}(5+4)+3^*21)$
-644973048	$9^*8*(7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(-3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-731278125	$(9*(8-(7+6)))^{\wedge}5*(4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-645657705	$((98*-7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3)^*2+1$	-732244728	$(9^{\wedge}(-8-(-7-6)))-5^{\wedge}(4^*3)^*(2+1)$
-645657706	$((98*7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3)^*-2^*1$	-732421749	$((-9+8)^*7*6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*(-2-1)$
-645657707	$((98*-7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3)^*2-1$	-732421850	$(9-8)^*7+(-6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*(-2-1)$
-645657717	$((-98*7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3)^*2+1$	-732421865	$(-9-(-8+7)+(-6-5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*(2+1))$
-645657718	$((98*7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))+3)^*2/1$	-732422103	$((-9+8)^*-76+5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*(-2-1)$
-645657719	$((-98*7)^{\wedge}(-6-(-5-4))-3)^*2-1$	-732599022	$(-9^{\wedge}(-8-(-7-6))-5^{\wedge}(4^*3))^*(2+1)$
-646232256	$(-9+8)^*76*54^{\wedge}((3+2)-1)$	-734309035	$((-9-(-8^*7)^{\wedge}6)-5)/(43-(-2-1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-734484660	$((-9^8+7)-6)*((5/4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-891795456	$(9/8-7*6^{\wedge}5)/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-741200593	$((9*(8+7)+6*5)^{\wedge}4-32)^{*}-1$	-891832320	$(9/-8-7*6^{\wedge}5)/4^{\wedge}(-3*2-1)$
-741200657	$((9*(8+7)+6*5)^{\wedge}4+32)/-1$	-896484375	$(9+8)*(7*6*(-5-4)+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-742187424	$(-9+8)^{*}-76*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3*2)+1)$	-899280144	$((-9-8)/(7*6)^{\wedge}(5-4-3))^{\wedge}2*-1$
-742187576	$(-9+8)^{*}76*(5^{\wedge}(4+3*2)+1)$	-899678208	$9*8^{\wedge}7*(6-5+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-744946875	$(9*(8-(7+6)))^{\wedge}5*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-900544265	$(9*((-8-7)-6)^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))/2+1$
-746770782	$(-9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)-5^{\wedge}(4*3))^*(2+1)$	-900544266	$(9*((-8-7)-6)^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))/2*1$
-751266778	$(9/((-8*76^{\wedge}5-4)/3+2))^{\wedge}-1$	-900544267	$(9*((-8-7)-6)^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))/2-1$
-752467975	$(9-8)^{*}-7*((6^{\wedge}5*4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-900544275	$(9-((-8-7)-6)^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))/2*-1$
-752953599	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6*5*4*(-3-2)+1$	-903449700	$9^{\wedge}8*((76+5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-21)$
-752953601	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6*5*4*(-3-2)-1$	-903980238	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7*6+(5-4)^{\wedge}3))^*-21$
-756627878	$(-9/(8-(7-6*5)^{\wedge}(4+3)*2))^{\wedge}-1$	-903981139	$(-9^{\wedge}8*7*(6-5)^{\wedge}4*3+2^{\wedge}1)$
-767400803	$-9^{\wedge}8*(76/54*3)^{\wedge}2+1$	-903981143	$(-9^{\wedge}8*7*(6-5)^{\wedge}4*3-2^{\wedge}1)$
-767400805	$-9^{\wedge}8*(76/54*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-903982044	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*6+(5-4)^{\wedge}3)*-21$
-772987056	$(-9*(87+6)^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)+21$	-904512582	$9^{\wedge}8*((-76-5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-21)$
-772987074	$(-9*(87+6)^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)+2+1$	-906987600	$9*(8*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-772987080	$((-9*(87+6)^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-2)-1$	-906997680	$-9*(8*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-772987098	$(-9*(87+6)^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(-4+3)-21$	-910752264	$9*((-87-6)^{\wedge}5+4)^*(2+1)$
-773955495	$-9/8*((7*(6*5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	-912789135	$(9-(8+76^{\wedge}5))/(4/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-775009921	$(((-9-8)^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4)/3)^{\wedge}2*-1$	-914097246	$9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4*321$
-776436120	$-9/8*((7*(6*5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	-914097264	$-9-((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4*321$
-777337856	$((-9-(8-7))^*6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}(3*(2+1))$	-916636144	$((9+(8+7)*(6+5))^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-777862144	$((-9-(8-7))^*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}(-3*(-2-1))$	-916636170	$((9+(8+7)*(6+5))^{\wedge}4-3*2)^*-1$
-784147176	$9*8*(((-7*6)^{\wedge}5/(4*3)+2)+1)$	-916636181	$((9+(8+7)*(6+5))^{\wedge}4+3+2)^*-1$
-784147608	$9*8*((7*6)^{\wedge}5/(-4*3)-2)-1$	-916636208	$((9+(8+7)*(6+5))^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-789780375	$(-9*(8+7))^{\wedge}(-6+5)+4*321$	-918330041	$(9-8)*7-(6*5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-793151881	$(-9-8)*(-7-(6*5*-4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-921001104	$(9*((-8-7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3))^{\wedge}2/-1$
-793152119	$(-9-8)*7+(6*5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-922581576	$9^{\wedge}(((-8+7)+6)*(-5^{\wedge}(4*3/2)+1))$
-794495745	$-9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4*(32-1)$	-922699674	$-9^{\wedge}(((-8+7)+6)*5^{\wedge}(4*3/2)+1)$
-794812500	$(-9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6/5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-924281604	$(9*((8+7)^{\wedge}(-6-(5-4)+3))^{\wedge}2*-1$
-799621875	$(9*(8-(7+6)))^{\wedge}5*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$	-937890593	$((98+7*(6+5))^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-805663980	$-9*(8+7/6)*5^{\wedge}(4+3*2)-1$	-937890619	$((98+7*(6+5))^{\wedge}4-3*2)^*-1$
-805664145	$9*(8+7/6)*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3*2)-1)$	-937890634	$((98+7*(6+5))^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)/-1$
-806215120	$9*8*(7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-937890657	$((98+7*(6+5))^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$
-806215176	$9*8*(7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-941685268	$(((-9+8+76)^*5)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$
-806216184	$9*8*(7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-944724951	$-9^{\wedge}(((-8+7)+6)*(5^*4)^{\wedge}3*2-1)$
-806216240	$9*8*(7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-944783999	$9^{\wedge}(((-8+7)+6)/(5*-4)^{\wedge}-3*2+1)$
-813802084	$-9^{\wedge}8*(-8+7)*6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-944784001	$9^{\wedge}(((-8+7)+6)/(5*-4)^{\wedge}-3*2-1)$
-815730689	$((98+76-5)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$	-944843049	$9^{\wedge}(((-8+7)+6)*(5^*4)^{\wedge}3*2-1)$
-815730715	$((98+76-5)^{\wedge}4-3*2)/-1$	-952430013	$(9/(8+(7*65)^{\wedge}4/(-3-2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-815730716	$((98+76-5)^{\wedge}4-3-2)/-1$	-954148916	$((98-(7-6)^{\wedge}5-4)^*-3^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-815730726	$((98+76-5)^{\wedge}4+3+2)^*-1$	-954148918	$((98-(7-6)^{\wedge}5-4)^*-3^{\wedge}-2-1$
-815730727	$((98+76-5)^{\wedge}4+3*2)^*-1$	-955511964	$(9+8+7)^{\wedge}6*(-5+4^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-815730753	$((98+76-5)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$	-955517796	$(9+8+7)^{\wedge}6*(-5-4^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-818458328	$(9*8+7)*(654/-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-960097368	$((9*-87)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3)/2^{\wedge}-1$
-820117473	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*2+1$	-960097369	$((-9*87)^{\wedge}(-6-(5-4)+3)*2-1$
-820117474	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*-2^{\wedge}1$	-960097379	$((-9*87)^{\wedge}(-6-(5-4))-3)*2+1$
-820117475	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*2-1$	-960097380	$((9*87)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3)/-2^{\wedge}-1$
-820578100	$((-9^{\wedge}8+7)-6)*((5/4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-960097381	$((-9*87)^{\wedge}(-6-(5-4))-3)*2-1$
-821237217	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*2+1$	-967163571	$-9^{\wedge}(((-8+7)+6)*(5-4)^{\wedge}3*2+1))$
-821237218	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*-2^{\wedge}1$	-967376896	$(-9^{\wedge}(((-8+7)+6)+5)*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$
-821237219	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^*2-1$	-967458690	$-9*(8-((7-(6^{\wedge}5*4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1))$
-826871976	$9*8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3)*21)$	-967458711	$98+7-(6^{\wedge}5*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$
-826878024	$9*8*-7*(6+5^{\wedge}(4+3)*21)$	-967458725	$98-(7+(6^{\wedge}5*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1))$
-835209968	$((98+7+65)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$	-967458738	$-9+87-(6^{\wedge}5*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$
-835210032	$((98+7+65)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$	-967458907	$-98+7-(6^{\wedge}5*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1)$
-845175111	$(-9+8)*(-76^{\wedge}5+43)/(-2-1)$	-967458921	$-98-(7+(6^{\wedge}5*4)^{\wedge}((3-2)+1))$
-845753535	$-9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4*(32+1)$	-967458942	$9*(8-(7+(6^{\wedge}5*4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-856406061	$(9-87*6*5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$	-967540736	$(9^{\wedge}(((-8+7)+6)+5)*-4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$
-856406439	$(-9-87*6*5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*21$	-967754061	$9^{\wedge}(((-8+7)+6)*(-5-4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)))$
-859963264	$((9*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6)+5-4)/-32^{\wedge}-1$	-968486547	$(98*-7)^{\wedge}(-6-(5-4))^*3+21$
-859963384	$((-9+8)-7)*((6^{\wedge}5*4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-968486565	$(98*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)*-3(-2-1)$
-859963400	$((-9+8)-7)*((6^{\wedge}5*4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-968486566	$(98*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)*-3+2/1$
-859963520	$((9*8)^{\wedge}(-7+6)+5+4)/-32^{\wedge}-1$	-968486567	$(98*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)*-3(-2+1)$
-862801399	$9+(8*7*((6-5*4)-3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-968486569	$(98*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)*-3-2+1$
-862801417	$-9+(8*7*((6-5*4)-3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-968486570	$(98*-7)^{\wedge}(-6-(5-4))^*3-2*1$
-871796880	$(-9+8)/7*((6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	-968486571	$(98*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)*-3-2-1$
-873813333	$(-9/(8^{\wedge}7*6*5^{\wedge}4-3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-968486589	$(98*-7)^{\wedge}(-6-(5-4))^*3-21$
-876752100	$(98*6*5/(4-3))^{\wedge}2*-1$	-976562468	$((9-8)+7)*((6-5^{\wedge}(4*3))/2+1)$
-878811889	$(9/((-8-7)^{\wedge}(6+5))^*4+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-976562488	$((9-8)+7)*((6-5^{\wedge}(4*3))/2-1)$
-885937507	$(9-8)^*-7*((6*5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-976562516	$((9-8)+7)*((-6-5^{\wedge}(4*3))/2+1)$
-886857129	$(-9+8/7-6)*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	-976562532	$((9-8)+7)*((-6-5^{\wedge}(4*3))/2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-981506209	$((9+876)/5)^{4-32} * -1$	-1161141723	$9^{(-8+7)} * (6^{(5+4)} - 3^{21})$
-981506235	$((9+876)/5)^{4-3*2} * -1$	-1161999323	$-9^{(87/6-5)} + 4^{(3*(2+1))}$
-981506236	$((9+876)/5)^{4-(3+2)} * -1$	-1162171467	$9^{(-8+7)} * ((6*5)^4 - 3^{21})$
-981506246	$((9+876)/5)^{4+3+2} / -1$	-1162258011	$9^{(-8+7)} * (6^{5*4} - 3^{21})$
-981506247	$((9+876)/5)^{4+3*2} * -1$	-1162259955	$(-9^{8+76-5*4}) * 3^{(2+1)}$
-981506273	$((9+876)/5)^{4+32} * -1$	-1162261322	$-9^{(87/6-5)} + (4*3)^{2+1}$
-988663313	$(9*8-7^{(6+5)+43})/2+1$	-1162261324	$-9^{(87/6-5)} + (4*3)^{2-1}$
-988663315	$(9*8-7^{(6+5)+43})/2-1$	-1162262979	$(-9^{8-76+5*4}) * 3^{(2+1)}$
-992174399	$(-9*(8-(7-6)))^{5+4^{(3*(2+1))}}$	-1162264923	$9^{(-8+7)} * (-6^{5*4} - 3^{21})$
-992698687	$(-9*(8-(7-6)))^{5-4^{(-3*(-2-1))}}$	-1162351467	$-9^{(-8+7)} * ((6*5)^4 + 3^{21})$
-994332672	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)} * (-4-32-1)$	-1162523611	$-9^{(87/6-5)} - 4^{(3*(2+1))}$
-997499811	$(9-8*76*5^{(4+3)}) * 21$	-1163381211	$-9^{(-8+7)} * (6^{(5+4)} + 3^{21})$
-997500189	$(-9-8*76*5^{(4+3)}) * 21$	-1164926784	$(98*76)^{(-5-(-4-3))} * -21$
-10111179654	$(9-(8*7)^6) / ((-5+4^3)/2+1)$	-1166632336	$(9+(-8-7*(6+5))^4/3)^{2* -1}$
-1012921518	$-9*(8^7-6)^*(54-3^{(-2+1)})$	-1167862276	$(9-(-8-7*(6+5))^4/3)^{2* -1}$
-1012927314	$9*(8^7-6)^*(54-3^{(-2+1)})$	-1171012279	$((9+(-87+6)*5)^4 + 3) / -21$
-1025504394	$-9*(8^7-6)^*(54+3^{(-2+1)})$	-1173861720	$9*(8+(-7*6)^5 + 4^{(3*(2+1))})$
-1025510262	$9*(8^7-6)^*(54+3^{(-2+1)})$	-1173861864	$-9*(8-(-7*6)^5 + 4^{(-3*(-2-1)))})$
-1026625672	$((98+76+5)^{4-3^2}) * -1$	-1176073560	$9*(8-(7*6)^5 + 4^{(3*2+1)})$
-1026625676	$((98+76+5)^{4-3-2}) / -1$	-1176368472	$9*(8-(7*6)^5 - 4^{(3*2+1)})$
-1026625686	$((98+76+5)^{4+3+2}) * -1$	-1176368616	$-9*(8+(7*6)^5 + 4^{(3*2+1)})$
-1026625690	$((98+76+5)^{4+3^2}) * -1$	-1178580312	$9*(8+(-7*6)^5 - 4^{(-3*(-2-1)))})$
-1033142841	$(-9-8/7-6)^*(5^4)^{(3*2)-1}$	-1178580456	$-9*(8-(-7*6)^5 + 4^{(3*(2+1))})$
-1036616265	$(9-8) / -7 * (((-6-5)^4)^{(3*2)-1})$	-1182449664	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)} * (-43-2+1)$
-1043432695	$9+8*((-7*6)^5 + 4^{(3*(2+1))})$	-1185939456	$9*8^7 * (6^{(-5+4)} - 3^{21})$
-1043432713	$-9+8*((-7*6)^5 + 4^{(3*(2+1))})$	-1186396041	$9*(8-7^{(6+5)}) / ((4+3)^{2+1})$
-1047626999	$9+8*((-7*6)^5 - 4^{(-3*(-2-1))})$	-1199078607	$-98^{(-7+6+5)} * (4+3^2) + 1$
-1047627017	$-9+8*((-7*6)^5 - 4^{(-3*(-2-1))})$	-1199078609	$-98^{(-7+6+5)} * (4+3^2) - 1$
-1049759997	$((9-8-7)*6^5)^{4-3} * (-2+1)$	-1200725622	$9*(8+(7*6)^5) / ((4+3)^{-2-1})$
-1049760005	$((9-8-7)*6^5)^{4+3+2} / -1$	-1200725766	$9*(8+(7*6)^5) / ((4+3)^{-2-1})$
-1063125000	$(9*8/7*(6*-5))^{(-4-3)^2} \wedge -1$	-1209264471	$9^{((-8+7)+6)} * (-5*4^{(3*2)+1})$
-1067311719	$9-8*(-7*6)^5 / ((4+3)^{-2-1})$	-1209382569	$-9^{((-8+7)+6)} * (5*4^{(3*2)+1})$
-1067311737	$-9-8*(-7*6)^5 / ((4+3)^{-2-1})$	-1212682752	$9*-8/(76*54)^{(-3-2)-1}$
-1068338670	$-987^{((-6+5)+4)} * (3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-1214999999	$9^{(-8+7)} * (6*5)^{4^{(4+3)}/2+1}$
-1071382528	$(-9+8^{(-7-(-6-5))}) * -4^{(3*(2+1))}$	-1215000001	$9^{(-8+7)} * (6*5)^{4^{(4+3)}/2-1}$
-1071384921	$9*(8+7*((6*5)^4/3+2+1))$	-1216342940	$(9-8^7)/6 * ((5-4^3)^{2-1})$
-1071385191	$-9*(8+7*((6*5)^4/3+2+1))$	-1216348151	$9+8^7/-6 * ((5-4^3)^{2-1})$
-1073442825	$(-9+8^{(7-6)+5}) * (-4^{(3*2)+1})$	-1216348169	$-9-8^7/6 * ((5-4^3)^{2-1})$
-1073516535	$(9+8^{(7-6)+5}) * (-4^{(3*2)+1})$	-1216353380	$(-9-8^7)/6 * ((5-4^3)^{2-1})$
-1073967095	$(9-8^{(7-6)+5}) * (4^{(3*2)+1})$	-1217341152	$-9/8 * ((765*4^3)^{2-1})$
-1074040841	$(-9-8^{(7-6)+5}) * (4^{(3*2)+1})$	-1218871296	$9*-8^7 * (65+(-4/3)^{(-2-1)})$
-1076101120	$(-9-8^{(-7-(-6-5))}) * 4^{(3*(2+1))}$	-1220703020	$((9-8)^7 - 6) * 5^{(4^3)-21}$
-1082673216	$(9*(8+76*(5+43)))^{2-1} / -1$	-1220703230	$((-9+8)^7 + 6) * (-5^{(4^3)-21})$
-1086222744	$-9/8 * (((-7+6^5)^4 - 3)^{2-1})$	-1220749781	$((9-8-7)^6 + 5^{(4+3^2)}) * -1$
-1086642270	$-9/8 * (((-7+6^5)^4 + 3)^{2-1})$	-1221703125	$((9+8-7)^6 + 5^{(4+3^2)}) / -1$
-1088390824	$(98*7-6^{(5+4)+3})/2+1$	-1222115319	$(-9*(8^7 * (65-4^{(-3+2))}) - 1)$
-1088390826	$(98*7-6^{(5+4)+3})/2-1$	-1222115337	$9*(-8^7 * (65-4^{(-3+2))}) - 1$
-1090141470	$-9/8 * (((-7-6^5)^4 + 3)^{2-1})$	-1225261056	$9*-8^7 * (65+(-4*3)^{(-2+1)})$
-1090561752	$-9/8 * (((-7-6^5)^4 - 3)^{2-1})$	-1225635840	$9*8^7 * -65 * (-4^{(-3-2)+1})$
-1095299901	$9*8^{(-7-6-((5+4/-3)^{2-1}))}$	-1225654272	$9/8 \wedge -7 * (-65+4^{(-3+2-1)})$
-1105880503	$9-8/7 * ((6^5*4+3)^{2-1})$	-1226760192	$9*-8^7 * (65-4^{((-3-2)+1)})$
-1105880521	$-9-8/7 * ((6^5*4+3)^{2-1})$	-1226815479	$-9*(8^7 * (65-4^{(-3-2))}) - 1$
-1110222400	$((98*(7^{((-6+5)+4)-3})^2) * -1$	-1226852343	$-9*(8^7 * (65+4^{(-3-2))}) - 1$
-1112246298	$9/8 * (((-7^{(6+5)} - (4+3))/2-1)$	-1226852361	$9*(-8^7 * (65+4^{(-3-2))}) - 1$
-1112246316	$9/8 * (((-7^{(6+5)} - 43)/2+1)$	-1226907648	$9*-8^7 * (65+4^{((-3-2)+1)})$
-1124589368	$(9^{(-8+7)} - 65^4) * 3^{21}$	-1228013568	$-9*8^7 * (65+4^{(-3+2-1)})$
-1124742859	$((9+((8+7)*6)^5) * -4-3)/21$	-1228032000	$9*8^7 * -65 * (4^{(-3-2)+1})$
-1126170624	$9*-8^7 * (6+5+3^{(-2+1)})$	-1228232661	$((-98/-7)^6 + 5^{(4+3^2)}) * -1$
-1139829650	$(((-9-8)^7 - 6)+5) * ((4/3)^{2+1})$	-1228406784	$9*-8^7 * (65-(-4*3)^{(-2+1)})$
-1142258475	$(9/(((8*7)^6 - 5^4)/-3+2))^{2-1}$	-1230176211	$((9+8)^7 - 6^{(-5+4^3)}) * (-2-1)$
-1142258498	$(-9+(8*7)^6 - (5-4)) / -3^{(2+1)}$	-1231855827	$((9+8)^7 + 6^{(-5+4^3)}) * (-2-1)$
-1145371743	$9*(8-7*(6*5+43))^{2+1}$	-1234796544	$9*-8^7 * (65-(-4/3)^{(-2-1)})$
-1146228704	$((9+8)^7 + 65)^{4-32} * -1$	-1236197376	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)} * (-43-2-1)$
-1146228768	$((9+8)^7 + 65)^{4+32} * -1$	-1249198408	$-9*8-((7*6+5)^4)^{(3+2-1)}$
-1155575787	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)} * -43+21$	-1255580316	$9*8/7 * ((6-5^4)^4)^{(3+2+1)}$
-1155575805	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)} * -43-(-2-1)$	-1261125578	$9*(8^7+6) - (5*4)^{(3*2+1)}$
-1155575806	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)} * -43+2*1$	-1261125686	$-9*(-8^7+6) - (5*4)^{(3*2+1)}$
-1155575807	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)} * -43-(-2+1)$	-1271529272	$9*8^7 \wedge 6 + (-5*4)^{(3*2+1)}$
-1155575809	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)} * -43-2+1$	-1275989839	$((9*(8+7+6))^{(5-(4-3))} - 2) * -1$
-1155575810	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)} * -43-2*1$	-1275989843	$(9*(8+7+6))^{(5-(4-3))} * -1$
-1155575811	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)} * -43-2-1$	-1279999526	$(9*8+7)*6 + (-5*4)^{(3*2+1)}$
-1155575829	$(9*8)^{((-7+6)+5)} * -43-21$	-1279999757	$9^{(8+7)/6} - (5*4)^{(3*2+1)}$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1279999859	$(9*(8+7)+6+(-5^4)^{(3^2+1)})$	-1416468490	$((9*(8+(7+6))+5)^4-3^2)^*-1$
-1279999871	$9*(8+7)-6-(5^4)^{(3^2+1)}$	-1416468491	$((9*(8+7+6)+5)^4-3-2)/-1$
-1279999927	$9*8+7-6-(5^4)^{(3^2+1)}$	-1416468499	$((9*(8+7+6)+5)^4+3)/(-2+1)$
-1279999980	$98/7+6-(5^4)^{(3^2+1)}$	-1416468501	$((9*(8+7+6)+5)^4+3+2)^*-1$
-1280000013	$(-9+87)/-6-(5^4)^{(3^2+1)}$	-1416468502	$((-9*(8+7+6)-5)^4-3^*-2)^*-1$
-1280000020	$(-98/7-6)-(5^4)^{(3^2+1)}$	-1416468505	$((9*(8+7+6)+5)^4+3^2)/-1$
-1280000073	$-9*8-(7-6+(5^4)^{(3^2+1)})$	-1416468528	$((9*(8+7+6)+5)^4+32)^*-1$
-1280000129	$-9*(8+7)+6+(5^4)^{(3^2+1)}$	-1431228544	$(9+8-7^6)^*(5^4+3)^{(2+1)}$
-1280000141	$-9*(8+7)-6-(5^4)^{(3^2+1)}$	-1431423216	$(9-8-7^6)^*(5^4+3)^{(2+1)}$
-1280000243	$-9^8((8+7)/6)-(5^4)^{(3^2+1)}$	-1431447550	$(-9+8-7^6)^*(5^4+3)^{(2+1)}$
-1280000474	$(-9*8-7)^6+(-5^4)^{(3^2+1)}$	-1431642222	$(-9-8-7^6)^*(5^4+3)^{(2+1)}$
-1280240640	$(9*8*-7)^(((-6+5)+4)^{(3^2+1)})$	-1436715334	$-9^8-(7/(6^5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-1285040811	$(-9-((8^7)^6-5)-4)/(3+21)$	-1437717008	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)-6)^*((5^{\wedge}(4^3)-2)+1)$
-1288470728	$9*8/7^6+(-5^4)^{(3^2+1)}$	-1437751296	$(9-8-7)^{\wedge}(6+5)^*(4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-1288685376	$(9*8)^{\wedge}7*-6^{\wedge}-5^*(4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$	-1440926979	$9*(8^7/6-543^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-1289865581	$(9*8)^{\wedge}7*-6^{\wedge}-5+43^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1440927147	$-9*(8^7/6+543^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-1290024595	$(9*8)^{\wedge}7*-6^{\wedge}-5-43^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1443851081	$(9-8)^*7+6/(-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-1291204800	$(9*8)^{\wedge}7*-6^{\wedge}-5*4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$	-1446308567	$9^8+7/(6-(5^4)^3)^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-1298874314	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7+6)-(5^4)^{(3^2+1)}$	-1453218008	$(((-9-8)^*7-6)^{\wedge}5-43)/21$
-1298874422	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6)-(5^4)^{(3^2+1)}$	-1453218009	$((9+8)^*7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3)/-21$
-1300967687	$(-9-8)^*(7+(6^54^{\wedge}(-3-2))^{\wedge}-1)$	-1458805509	$((9-8)^{\wedge}7-6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3/21$
-1301785704	$-9*8/7^6*((6^54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1464625152	$(9-8-7)^{\wedge}(6+5)^*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-1305306576	$(9*876)^{\wedge}(-5-(-4-3))^*-21$	-1464843519	$98+7+6^*(5^{\wedge}(4^3)+21)$
-1305326952	$9/8^*((7+6)^*-5)^{\wedge}(4+3-2)+1)$	-1464843533	$98-7+6^*(5^{\wedge}(4^3)+21)$
-1312713536	$(-9/(-87*-6))^{\wedge}(-5/(4-3))^*-2/-1$	-1464843637	$(9+8)^*7-6*(5^{\wedge}(4^3)+2-1)$
-1320258505	$(9+8)/-7^*((6^5-4)^3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1464843802	$-9-8^*7+6^*(5^{\wedge}(4^3)+2)+1$
-1325562413	$9-(8/((7+6)^{\wedge}(5+4)+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-1464843851	$(-9-8)^*7-6^*(5^{\wedge}(4^3)-2)-1)$
-1325562431	$-9-(8/((7+6)^{\wedge}(5+4)+3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-1464843863	$(-9-8)^*7+6^*(5^{\wedge}(4^3)+2-1)$
-1330571529	$(9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-43))^{\wedge}2*-1$	-1464843967	$(-98+7)-6*(5^{\wedge}(4^3)+21)$
-1332584841	$(-9*8^{\wedge}(7^*654)^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-1464843981	$(-98-7)-6*(5^{\wedge}(4^3)+21)$
-1347401913	$((9-8^*7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4+3)/2+1$	-1468618039	$((-9+(8^*7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)-3)/-21$
-1347401914	$((9-8^*7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4+3)^2^{\wedge}-1$	-1468618062	$9-((8^*7)^{\wedge}6-5^*(4-3))/21$
-1347401917	$((9-8^*7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3)/-2^*1$	-1475789054	$((98/7)^{\wedge}(6-5+4+3)-2)^*-1$
-1347401918	$((9-8^*7)^{\wedge}6-5)/-4-3)/2-1$	-1475789058	$((98/7)^{\wedge}(6-5+4+3)+2)^*-1$
-1350621892	$9^8-(7/(6^5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	-1481419359	$(9*8-7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3))^*21$
-1351003536	$(9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-4^3))^{\wedge}2*-1$	-1481420185	$-98*((-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^3/2-1)$
-1351836559	$9/((-8*(7+6))^{\wedge}5-4-3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-1481420241	$(9*8+7*(-6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3))^*21$
-1351836563	$9/((-8*(7+6))^{\wedge}5-43)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-1481420381	$98*((-7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))^3/2-1)$
-1355316471	$9*((8^*7)^{\wedge}6*-5/4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-1481420871	$(-9+8)^*7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3)^*21$
-1355316489	$-9*((8^*7)^{\wedge}6*5/4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-1481422243	$-98*((-7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))^3/2-1)$
-1356080625	$(9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-4)-3)^{\wedge}2/-1$	-1481422383	$(9*-8-7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3))^*21$
-1356522561	$(-9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))-4)-3)^{\wedge}2/-1$	-1481422439	$98*((-7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))^3/2-1)$
-1361388609	$(9*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4)-3)^{\wedge}2*-1$	-1481423265	$(-9*8+7*(-6^{\wedge}(5+4)-3))^*21$
-1361831409	$(-9*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4)-3)^{\wedge}2*-1$	-1489355216	$9*8+(7/(6-(5^4)^3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-1363603329	$(9*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4+3))^{\wedge}2*-1$	-1489355271	$9+8+(7/(6-(5^4)^3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-1366928784	$(9*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4^3))^{\wedge}2/-1$	-1489355287	$9-(8-(7/(6-(5^4)^3))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-1367630991	$9+((8-7^*6*(5+4))^3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1489355289	$-9+8+(7/(6-(5^4)^3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-1367631009	$-9+((8-7^*6*(5+4))^3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1489355305	$-9-(8-(7/(6-(5^4)^3))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-1373291064	$9/8*((-7^*6-5^{\wedge}(4+3^2))-1)$	-1489355360	$-9*8+(7/(6-(5^4)^3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-1380939378	$(-9+(8^*7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(-4-3-21)$	-1491970480	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)+6)^*((5^{\wedge}(4^3)+2)-1)$
-1384660625	$(-9-8)^*(76^5/4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	-1499897301	$(-9+8)^*7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-1386817600	$(98^*76^5/(4-3))^{\wedge}2*-1$	-1501127159	$(-9+8)^*7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-1387061010	$-9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)^*((5+4^3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1501852266	$(-9^{\wedge}(-8+7-6))/(5^{\wedge}4+3)^2^{\wedge}-1$
-1387487992	$((9+8-7^*6^5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)^*-1$	-1504438013	$9+((8^*7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(-43/2+1)$
-1387488010	$((9+8-7^*6^5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)^*-1$	-1504438031	$-9-((8^*7)^{\wedge}6-5)/(43/2-1)$
-1387637001	$(9*(8^{\wedge}(-7-(-6-5))+43))^{\wedge}2/-1$	-1504575094	$((-9-8)^{\wedge}7+6+5)^*(4/3^2+1)$
-1393412995	$(-9/8+7)^*((6-5^{\wedge}4)^3-21)$	-1504575138	$(((-9-8)^{\wedge}7-6)+5)^*(4/3^2+1)$
-1393668515	$98-(7/(6^5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	-1508952048	$-9*8/(7^*654)^{\wedge}((-3+2)-1)$
-1393668541	$9*8-(7/(6^5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	-1516769481	$(9-(8^*7)^{\wedge}6)/(5^4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-1393668596	$9+8-(7/(6^5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	-1516799526	$(9*8+7)^*-6*((5^4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-1393668612	$9-(8+(7/(6^5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-1516800474	$(9*8+7)^*6*((5^4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-1393668614	$-9+8-(7/(6^5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	-1524629504	$(9*-8^{\wedge}-7/6543)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-1393668630	$-9-(8+(7/(6^5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-1526726647	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(((-6+5)+4)^{\wedge}(3^2)-1)$
-1393668685	$-9*8-(7/(6^5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	-1530920951	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(((-6+5)+4)^{\wedge}(3^2)+1)$
-1393668711	$-98-(7/(6^5+43))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	-1530920969	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(((-6+5)+4)^{\wedge}(3^2)+1)$
-1395089271	$9-8/-7^*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3^2)-1)$	-1532402009	$-9^8+7/(6-(5^4)^3)^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-1395089289	$-9-8/-7^*(6-5^{\wedge}(4+3^2)-1)$	-1533011533	$(9-8^{\wedge}7)^*(6+5^*(4^3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1398752712	$987/6*-54^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-1533018103	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5^*(4^3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1400846643	$(9-(-8-7)^*-6^*5)^{\wedge}4*-3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	-1533018121	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6+5^*(4^3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1401046875	$9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*((5+4/3)^*-2-1)$	-1533024691	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)^*(6+5^*(4^3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1411806101	$((9+8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3^2))/-1$	-1536953584	$((9*(87-65))^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$
-1416468464	$((9*(8+7+6)+5)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$	-1536953610	$((9*(87-65))^{\wedge}4-3^2)^*-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1536953622	$((9*(87-65))^{4-3*-2})*-1$	-1765490769	$-9-8/7*((6*5+4)^{(3*2)-1})$
-1536953648	$((9*(87-65))^{4+32})*-1$	-1766100619	$((9-8-7*6)*5)^{4-3*2})*-1$
-1542062080	$(-9+8-7^{\wedge}6)/5*4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1766100630	$((9-8-7*6)*5)^{4+3+2})*-1$
-1544143062	$((9-8)*7^{\wedge}6*-5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21$	-1766100631	$((9-8-7*6)*5)^{4+3*2})*-1$
-1549622907	$-9^{\wedge}(((-8+7)+6)*(54*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1766100634	$((9-8-7*6)*5)^{4+3^{\wedge}2})/-1$
-1549741005	$-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)*(54*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1796535887	$((-9+8*7)^{\wedge}6-5+4)/(-3*2)+1$
-1552416768	$9*8^{\wedge}7*(65/4*(-3-2)-1)$	-1798045687	$9+(8*76*((5-4)-3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-1552836303	$9+((-8-7*6*(5+4))^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1798045705	$-9+(8*76*((5-4)-3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-1552836321	$-9+((-8-7*6*(5+4))^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1800814096	$(-9+8)*(-7*6*5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
-1553936400	$(9*876*5/(4-3))^{\wedge}2*-1$	-1800874944	$9*87*((-6-5)*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-1585557504	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)^*(4-3*21)$	-1807960095	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*6+((5+4)*3))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-1597339125	$(-9*8-7-6)^{\wedge}5/((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1807964469	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*6-((5+4)*3))^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-1599999968	$((9*(8+7)+65)^{\wedge}4-32)^*-1$	-1812361351	$((9+8^{\wedge}7)-6)/-5*4321$
-1599999994	$((9*(8+7)+65)^{\wedge}4-3*2)^*-1$	-1815328341	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7*6)^{\wedge}5*(4-3))/((2+1)$
-1599999995	$((-9*(-8-7)+65)^{\wedge}4-(3+2))^*-1$	-1818230784	$(9-876)/((-5+4)+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-1599999997	$((9*(8+7)+65)^{\wedge}4-3)/(-2+1)$	-1819653984	$(-9*(8-7)*6)^{\wedge}5*(4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-1600000005	$((9*(8+7)+65)^{\wedge}4+3+2)^*-1$	-1840444704	$-98/(7+6)*((5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)+1)$
-1600000006	$((9*(8+7)+65)^{\wedge}4+3*2)/-1$	-1844026155	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7*6)^{\wedge}5*(5+4))/(-2-1)$
-1600000032	$((9*(8+7)+65)^{\wedge}4+32)^*-1$	-1847365632	$9*(8^{\wedge}7-(6*5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$
-1612796967	$9*(8*7*(6-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$	-1853666208	$(-9*(8-7)*6)^{\wedge}5*(4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-1612800000	$9/(8/-7-6)*(5*4)^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$	-1855979520	$(9+876)/((5-4)-3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-1612803015	$-9*(8*7*(6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))-1)$	-1862270967	$9+8^{\wedge}7*6*(-5-((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
-1612803033	$9*(8*-7*(6+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))-1)$	-1862270985	$-9+8^{\wedge}7*6*(-5-((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
-1614620385	$-9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5)/4*3*21$	-1865813431	$(-9+8)/7*(6^{\wedge}(5+4^{\wedge}(3/2))+1)$
-1622736240	$(9-(8+76^{\wedge}5))/((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1867766355	$9/8*7*((6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-21)$
-1628858088	$(9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6)*((5+4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1885114368	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+(6*5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$
-1633640391	$9-8*(7*6)^{\wedge}5*((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1894683342	$(-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)-5^{\wedge}(4*3))^*(2+1)$
-1636214272	$(-9+8)*-7*(6-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1901763252	$9^{\wedge}8-((-7*6*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-1641353652	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7+65*-4)*((-3-2)+1)$	-1901763306	$9^{\wedge}8-((-7*6*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-1641355732	$((9+8)^{\wedge}7-65*-4)*((-3-2)+1)$	-1904673897	$(9*(8*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))+3)^*21$
-1641600513	$(-9+8*7*6)*((5*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-1904674023	$(9*(8*7-6^{\wedge}(5+4))-3)^*21$
-1644165110	$-98*(((-7+6)+5)^{\wedge}(4*3)-21)$	-1904695065	$(-9*(8*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))+3)^*21$
-1644167119	$-98*(((-7+6)+5)^{\wedge}(4*3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1904695191	$(-9*(8*7+6^{\wedge}(5+4))-3)^*21$
-1644169226	$-98*(((-7-6)-5)^{\wedge}(4*3)+21)$	-1908029752	$(9-8-7*6*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2-1$
-1652994048	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)+6)/5*4^{\wedge}3*(-2-1)$	-1908029756	$((9-8-7*6*5)^{\wedge}4-3-2)^*-1$
-1660236606	$(9-8)*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+2-1$	-1908029766	$((9-8-7*6*5)^{\wedge}4+3+2)^*-1$
-1666598966	$9-(8/(7*6^{\wedge}(5+4-3)))^{\wedge}2+1$	-1908029770	$((9-8-7*6*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)^*-1$
-1666598984	$-9-(8/(7*6^{\wedge}(5+4-3)))^{\wedge}2+1$	-1916799401	$(9-8*76)*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-1666598986	$-9-((8/(7*6^{\wedge}(5+4-3)))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1916800599	$(-9+8*76)*((5*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-1668294255	$9+(-8+7/6)*((5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)+1)$	-1916928000	$-9*8^{\wedge}7*65*((4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1668294273	$-9+(-8+7/6)*((5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)+1)$	-1926972971	$(-9+8)*7^{\wedge}6*(-5+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$
-1675524699	$9/8*(7/(6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	-1927060525	$(9/8+7)*((6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-21)$
-1684492894	$(9-8)*7*(6+(-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-1927479296	$((-9+8)*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
-1684492936	$((-9+8)^{\wedge}7-6)*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-1936971792	$(-98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)+4^{\wedge}3)^*21$
-1685812491	$9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(-5-((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1))$	-1936974480	$(-98^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)-4^{\wedge}3)^*21$
-1685812509	$-9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(-5-((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1))$	-1953124856	$((9+8)+7)*((6+5^{\wedge}(4*3))/(-2-1))$
-1693052712	$9*-8*((7*6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3-2)-1)$	-1953124931	$((9-8)+7)*((6-5^{\wedge}(4*3))+21)$
-1693052915	$9-8*(7*6^{\wedge}(5+4)*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1953124973	$((9-8)+7)*((6-5^{\wedge}(4*3))-21)$
-1693052923	$9-8*(7*6^{\wedge}(5+4)*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1953125027	$((-9+8)-7)*((6+5^{\wedge}(4*3))+21)$
-1693052933	$-9-8*(7*6^{\wedge}(5+4)*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1953125031	$((-9+8)-7)*((6-5^{\wedge}(4*3)+2))+1$
-1693052941	$-9-8*(7*6^{\wedge}(5+4)*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1953125069	$((-9+8)-7)*((6+5^{\wedge}(4*3))-21)$
-1693053144	$9*8*((-7*6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3-2)-1)$	-1953125144	$((-9-8)-7)*((6+5^{\wedge}(4*3))/(2+1))$
-1699199469	$(-9-87*6)*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-1960984089	$((-9^{\wedge}((-8+7)+6)+5)/4*3)^{\wedge}2*-1$
-1699200531	$(9+87*6)*((5*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-1974399383	$(-9-8*76)*((5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-1706489856	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)*((-4^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1974400617	$(9+8*76)*((5*-4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-1708984372	$((-9+8)^{\wedge}7-6)*5^{\wedge}(4*3)+2+1$	-1975509000	$(-9*(87*6*5)^{\wedge}(-4-(-3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-1708984374	$((-9+8)^{\wedge}7-6)*5^{\wedge}(4*3)+2-1$	-1982119432	$((9-8+7*6*5)^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2)^*-1$
-1713387748	$(-9-((8*7)^{\wedge}6-5)-4)/(-3+21)$	-1982119436	$((9-8+7*6*5)^{\wedge}4-3-2)^*-1$
-1731601875	$((-9-(8+76))^*5)^{\wedge}4*-3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	-1982119446	$((9-8+7*6*5)^{\wedge}4+3+2)^*-1$
-1733363712	$(9*8)^{\wedge}((-7+6)+5)*((-4^{\wedge}3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1982119450	$((9-8+7*6*5)^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2)^*-1$
-1733712022	$(9-8)*7*(6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-1987681045	$9+((-87-6)^{\wedge}5+4)/(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-1735205101	$(98*7^{\wedge}(-6-5))/(-43*2))^{\wedge}-1$	-1988268100	$(98*7*65/(4-3))^{\wedge}2*-1$
-1737285984	$-9/8*((7-(6*5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1996150987	$((9+8*-7)^{\wedge}6*5+4)/-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-1752577159	$((9+8-7*65)^{\wedge}4+3)/-21$	-2031328125	$9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*-5*(4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-1757623704	$(9*8-7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*((-3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-2046515625	$9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(-5*4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-1757623832	$((9*8+7^{\wedge}6+5)-4)*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2047025232	$(-9+8/(7+6))*((5^{\wedge}(4*3)-2)+1)$
-1759502977	$(9-8^{\wedge}7)*6*-5*(4-32)-1$	-2054109375	$9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(-5*4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-1759510519	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*-5*(4-32)-1)$	-2056065312	$((-9-(8*7)^{\wedge}6)/5-43)/(2+1)$
-1759510537	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(6*-5*(4-32)-1)$	-2061704836	$((9*8+7)-6)*((-5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2*-1$
-1759518079	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)*6*5*(4-32)+1$	-2063261007	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6+(-5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-1765490751	$9-8/7*((6*5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	-2065869024	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7+6^{\wedge}5)*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
		-2065869696	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7+6^{\wedge}5)*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2066205888	$(-9^8+765)^*((4+3)^2-1)$		
-2066220768	$(-9^8+7*65)^*((4+3)^2-1)$		
-2066224368	$(-9^8+76*5)^*((4+3)^2-1)$		
-2066232528	$(-9^8+7*6*5)^*((4+3)^2-1)$		
-2066239488	$(-9^8+(7+6)*5)^*((4+3)^2-1)$		
-2066242104	$9*8*(7+6/(-5-4)^{-3*2-1})$		
-2066242328	$(-9^8-7/-6*5)^*((4+3)^2-1)$		
-2066242888	$(-9^8+7/-6*5)^*((4+3)^2-1)$		
-2066243112	$-9*8*(7+6/(5+4)^{-3*2-1})$		
-2066245728	$(-9^8-(7+6)*5)^*((4+3)^2-1)$		
-2066252688	$(-9^8+7*-6*5)^*((4+3)^2-1)$		
-2066260848	$(-9^8-76*5)^*((4+3)^2-1)$		
-2066264448	$(-9^8-7*65)^*((4+3)^2-1)$		
-2066279328	$(-9^8-765)^*((4+3)^2-1)$		
-2066615520	$(-9^8+7-6^5)^*((4+3)^2-1)$		
-2066616192	$(-9^8-7-6^5)^*((4+3)^2-1)$		
-2068048827	$-9/8*((7*(6-(5-4)))^{3*2}-1)$		
-2069296875	$9*(8+7)^{6*5*4+3^2-1}$		
-2082471936	$(987+6)/((5-4)-3)^{-21}$		
-2084484375	$9*((8+7)^{6*5*4+3^2-1})$		
-2097273616	$(-9+8)*(7*6*5+4)^{3+2-1}$		
-2101672336	$((9*8+7)-6)^*(5^4+3)^{2-1}$		
-2126250000	$(-9*8/7*(6*5)^{-4-3})^{2+1}$		
-2126542743	$9*((8+7)^{6*5*4+3^2-1})$		
-2135696401	$(9-8^{-(7+6)})^*(5^4+3)^{2+1}$		
-2136750619	$((9-8+7*6)^5)^{4-3*2*-1}$		
-2136750630	$((9-8+7*6)^5)^{4+3+2*-1}$		
-2136750631	$((9-8+7*6)^5)^{4+3*2*-1}$		
-2136750634	$((9-8+7*6)^5)^{4+3^2}/-1$		
-2146688993	$(9-8)*7-(6*5*43)^{2+1}$		
-2146893824	$(9+(-8*(7-6))^5)^*4^{3^2-1}$		